

Monitoring zum englischsprachigen Forschungsstand „Sexuelle Gewalt in pädagogischen Kontexten“

BIBLIOGRAPHIE, NUMMER 1

INGA MARIE LIST, LINA JENNER, ANJA HENNINGSEN

Hintergrund

Dieses Monitoring dient in erster Linie den Forscher_innen innerhalb der BMBF-Förderlinie „Sexuelle Gewalt gegen Kinder und Jugendliche in pädagogischen Kontexten“, einen strukturierten sowie konzentrierten Zugang zu relevanten englischsprachigen Publikationen zu erhalten. Darüber hinaus profitieren weitere Forscher_innen und Studierende von thematischen Anschlussstellen der Literatursammlung.

Mit dieser ersten Bibliographie ist der Publikationszeitraum von 2010 bis 2017 abgedeckt. In den kommenden beiden Jahren sind aktualisierende Sammlungen sowie Schwerpunktartikel zu beachtenswerten Forschungsergebnissen geplant.

Schwerpunktmäßig erfasst das Monitoring den Ausschnitt „sexuelle Gewalt gegen Kinder und Jugendliche in pädagogischen Kontexten“ und integriert flankierende grundsätzliche Zusammenhänge von Gewalt und Sexualität. Relevante Unterthemen wurden anhand inhaltlicher Clusterungen des Forschungsnetzwerks herausgearbeitet, d.h. die Recherche konzentriert sich auf die *soziale Rahmung von sexueller Gewalt*, die *organisationalen Strukturen und Kulturen*, die *Qualifizierung von Fachkräften*, *Präventionsprogramme für Adressat_innen* sowie *Disclosure*.¹ Da aber auch sexuelle Gewalt in familialen und Peerbeziehungen eine Auswirkung auf die pädagogische Arbeit haben und im Laufe der Literaturrecherche sich als wichtige Forschungs- und Publikationsthemen herausstellten, werden sie in diesem Monitoring ebenfalls berücksichtigt.

Auswahl der Titel

Der Ausschnitt des Monitorings weist eine immense Themenbreite auf: Wegen der Inter- und Multidisziplinarität ist eine vollständige Darstellung aller relevanten Veröffentlichungen nicht möglich. Die Disziplinen und teilweise unabhängigen Netzwerke, die sich mit Gewalt und Sexualität in pädagogischen Kontexten befassen, verhindern eine vollständige systematische Literaturreview (Tranfield *et al.* 2003: 215). Für einen möglichst repräsentativen Überblick wurde deswegen eine zielgerichtete, geschichtete Zufallsauswahl getroffen, die sich auf die aktuellen Diskurse und Publikationen seit 2010 – dem Beginn der öffentlichen, politischen und pädagogischen Auf- und Bearbeitung von Missbrauchsfällen in pädagogischen Institutionen – konzentriert. Zur Qualitätssicherung und wegen der zu erwartenden Reichweite sowie des damit zusammenhängenden Einflusses wurde beschlossen, sich auf peer-reviewte Zeitschriftenartikel und, um einer einseitigen Repräsentation des Forschungsfeldes durch Artikel vorzubeugen (Hicks 2005), Monographien und Sammelbände namhafter Verlage zu konzentrieren.

Systematische Literaturreviews werden für gewöhnlich anhand von Schlagwortsuche in ausgewählten Datenbanken durchgeführt (Boell & Cecez-Kecmanovic 2010: 134f.; Okoli & Schabram 2010). Wegen der Vielfalt an relevanten Schlagwörtern einerseits und der geringen Präzision dieses Vorgehens (Boell & Cecez-Kecmanovic 2010: 132) – man denke beispielsweise an die fehlerhaft ausgewählten Artikel zu „sex*“, die sich ausschließlich auf Geschlechterunterschiede beziehen – kommt diese Methode nicht in Frage. Alternativ wird mit einer Konzentration auf *core journals* gearbeitet, ausgehend von Bradfords Gesetz, dass Themen sich nicht gleichmäßig auf alle Zeitschriften verteilen, sondern in einzelnen verstärkt anzufinden sind (Bradford 1947; Brookes 1977). Dieses Vorgehen erlaubt eine natürliche Begrenzung durch die Vorauswahl der Zeitschriften (Alavi & Carlson 1992; Okoli & Schabram 2010). Da wir aber nicht nur an Forschungserkenntnissen interessiert sind, sondern auch daran, wie die Auseinandersetzung mit sexueller Gewalt, Gewalt und Sexualität in pädagogischen Kontexten in

¹ Beiträge, die die „Entwicklung akademischer Curricula“ unterstützen könnten, wurden ebenfalls der Qualifizierung von Fachkräften zugeordnet.

den verschiedenen Disziplinen stattfindet, wie sich also das Forschungsfeld darstellt und entwickelt, ist eine ausschließliche Fokussierung auf etwaige Hauptzeitschriften ebenfalls nicht optimal. Um einen repräsentativen Einblick in das englischsprachige Forschungsfeld „sexuelle Gewalt in pädagogischen Kontexten“ zu bieten und seine Verteilung, nehmen wir deshalb neben thematischen Zeitschriften auch disziplinübergreifend Standardwerke in den Blick.

Die Auswahl der Zeitschriftenartikel erfolgte geschichtet mit einer zielgerichteten Zufallsauswahl von 25 Zeitschriften, die anschließend nach relevanten Artikeln durchsucht wurden. Bei der Auswahl der Zeitschriften, die über *Google Scholar Metrics*, *Scimano Journal and County Rank* und *SAGE Publishing* sowie Empfehlungen von einschlägigen Fachbereichen identifiziert wurden, spielten vier Kriterien eine Rolle. *Erstens* war es ein Anliegen, sowohl relevante Disziplinen zu berücksichtigen (also Zeitschriften der Erziehungswissenschaften, Psychologie und Gesundheitswissenschaften sowie Sozialwissenschaften) als auch einschlägige Fachzeitschriften der Bereiche Sexualität, sexuelle Gewalt, Kindesmisshandlung und Zeitschriften zu empirischer Forschung einzubeziehen. *Zweitens* wurden Zeitschriften bevorzugt, die eine hohe Trefferquote bei der Suche nach Schlagwörtern ergaben.² *Als drittes Kriterium* galt der h5-Index, also die Zitierhäufigkeit,³ und *viertens* wurde schließlich der Ort der Herausgeberschaft berücksichtigt. Veröffentlichungen aus dem globalen Norden wurden dabei bevorzugt, weil von besseren Vergleichsmöglichkeiten zum deutschen Kontext ausgegangen wird. Um die Überrepräsentation der USA nach dieser Auswahl auszugleichen, wurden Zeitschriften bevorzugt, die in Europa, Kanada oder Australien/Neuseeland herausgegeben wurden. Insgesamt ergab sich eine Summe von 131 Zeitschriften, sodass eine engere Auswahl in Form einer geschichteten Zufallsstichprobe getroffen wurde, die die Repräsentation der Disziplinen und Erscheinungsorte widerspiegelt.

Zeitschrift	Erscheinungsort	h5-Index	ISSN
Archives of Sexual Behavior*	Kanada	44	0004-0002
British Journal of Social Work	Großbritannien	33	0045-3102
Child Abuse & Neglect*	Kanada	39	0145-2134
Child Abuse Review	Großbritannien	17	09529136
Childhood	Norwegen	24	0907-5682
Children and Youth Services Review*	USA	44	01907409
Culture, Health & Sexuality*	Australien	27	1464-5351
Feminism & Psychology	Neuseeland	20	0959-3535
Gender & Society	USA	31	0891-2432
Gender and Education	Großbritannien	22	0954-0253
Journal of Adolescence*	USA	46	0140-1971
Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry	Großbritannien	71	1469-7610

² Die Liste der Schlagwörter kann bei Interesse eingesehen werden.

³ Der Impact-Faktor ist zwar ein umstrittenes Kriterium in den Sozialwissenschaften, bietet aber eine Annäherung an die Identifikation einflussreicher Zeitschriften (Furr 2014; Sellers *et al.* 2014).

Journal of Child Sexual Abuse*	USA	17	1053-8712
Journal of Curriculum Studies	Österreich	20	1366-5839
Journal of Sexual Aggression*	Australien	15	1355-2600
Journal of Sex Research*	Großbritannien	36	1559-8519
Journal of Youth and Adolescence*	USA	48	0047-2891
Men and Masculinities	USA	20	1097184X
Pedagogy, Culture & Society	Großbritannien	15	1468-1366
Qualitative Research	International	33	1468-7941
Research in Developmental Disabilities	Großbritannien	48	0891-4222
Sex Education*	Großbritannien	17	1472-0825
Sexuality and Disability	USA	16	0146-1044
Sexuality Research and Social Policy*	USA	18	1868-9884
Teaching and Teacher Education	Australien	51	0742051X

Tabelle 1: Auswahl der berücksichtigten Zeitschriften.

Um die für den Themenkomplex „sexuelle Gewalt, Gewalt und Sexualität in pädagogischen Kontexten“ relevanten Artikel aus den ausgewählten Zeitschriften zu identifizieren, wurden sämtliche Aufsatztitel in allen Ausgaben ab 2010 durchgesehen. Anschließend erfolgte auch hier eine Schlagwortsuche, um sicherzugehen, dass keine Artikel übersehen wurden. Bei Zeitschriften mit einer relevanten Artikelanzahl von über zehn pro Jahr wurde aus diesen eine Zufallsstichprobe ausgewählt.⁴ Insgesamt ergab sich damit eine Zahl von 706 Artikeln.

Die Auswahl der Bücher – Monographien und Sammelbände - erfolgte über die Universitätsverlage der 50 weltweit besten Universitäten (Times Higher Education Ranking 2016/2017), sowie *SAGE Publications* und *Routledge* als weitere große akademischen Verlage, die in stichprobenartigen Schlagwortsuchen bei der digitalen Bibliothek *WorldCat* am häufigsten auftauchten. Bei den Universitätsverlagen wurde wie bei der Artikelauswahl vorgegangen und die gesamten Publikationen seit 2010 durchgesehen. Bei *SAGE Publications* und *Routledge* wurde mit Schlagwörtern gesucht. Aus dieser Buchsammlung von 141 Büchern wurden anhand der o.g. Kriterien 25 Monographien und 18 Sammelbände ausgewählt.

⁴ In der Liste sind diese Zeitschriften mit einem * gekennzeichnet.

Abbildung 1: Vorgehen bei der Recherche nach Zeitschriftenartikeln und Büchern.

Kategorisierung und Einordnung der Titel

Die anschließende Strukturierung der Veröffentlichungen orientierte sich an den oben erwähnten Clustern des Forschungsnetzwerks – die *soziale Rahmung*, die *organisationalen Strukturen und Kulturen*, die *Qualifizierung von Fachkräften*, *Präventionsprogramme für Adressat_innen* sowie *Disclosure* und *Entwicklung akademischer Curricula* – wurde jedoch im Laufe der Recherche induktiv angepasst, erweitert und mit Unterkategorien versehen. Die Titel wurden anhand ihrer Abstracts oder Einleitungen diesen Kategorien zugeordnet; Mehrfachkategorien waren möglich.

1. Soziale Rahmung
 - 1.1. Policies und politische Ebene
 - 1.2. Weiterführende Diskurse rund um Sexualität, Gewalt, sexuelle Gewalt und pädagogische Arbeit
 - 1.3. Gebrauch von Medien (auch soziale/neue) und Technologie
 - 1.4. Soziale Gruppen und Diskriminierung
 - 1.4.1. Geschlechterrollen und Sexismus
 - 1.4.2. Sexuelle Orientierung und geschlechtliche Identität; Homo- und Transfeindlichkeit
 - 1.4.3. Schichtenzugehörigkeit und Klassismus
 - 1.4.4. Ethnizität und Rassismus
 - 1.4.5. Religionszugehörigkeit und -feindlichkeit
 - 1.4.6. Behinderungen und Ableismus
2. Institutioneller Kontext
 - 2.1. Institutionelle Dynamiken (inkl. Richtlinien auf Einrichtungsebene)

- 2.2. Einrichtungstypen
 - 2.2.1. Kindertagesstätte
 - 2.2.2. Grundschule
 - 2.2.3. Weiterführende Schule
 - 2.2.4. Hochschule
 - 2.2.5. Förderschule
 - 2.2.6. Kinder- und Jugendhilfe
 - 2.2.7. Sonstiges (Jugendzentrum, Kirche, Justizvollzugsanstalt, Jugendamt)
3. Pädagogischer Fokus
 - 3.1. Sexualpädagogik
 - 3.2. Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention
4. Fachkräfte (Qualifizierung, Professionalisierung, ihre Einstellungen zu Sexualität und sexueller Gewalt und Umgang damit)
 - 4.1. Innerhalb von Einrichtungen
 - 4.2. Externe
 - 4.3. Peer Education
5. Adressat_innen
 - 5.1. Kinder
 - 5.2. Jugendliche
 - 5.3. Eltern und Familien
6. Formen und Auswirkungen der Gewalt
 - 6.1. Täter*in
 - 6.1.1. Peer
 - 6.1.2. Erwachsene
 - 6.2. Art
 - 6.2.1. Sexuelle Belästigung
 - 6.2.2. Sexueller Kindesmissbrauch
 - 6.2.3. Vergewaltigung
 - 6.2.4. Übergriff
 - 6.2.5. Diskriminierung
 - 6.3. Folgen
 - 6.3.1. Negativ (u.a. Reviktimisierung, Täter_innenschaft, PTBS)
 - 6.3.3. Coping, Resilienz, Posttraumatisches Wachstum
 - 6.3.4. Disclosure
7. Rolle von Sexualität
 - 7.1. Beziehungsgestaltung und sexuelle Erfahrungen
 - 7.2. Sexuelle Selbstbestimmung
8. Forschung
 - 8.1. Forschungsethik
 - 8.2. Theorie
 - 8.3. Methodologie
 - 8.4. Wegweisende Ergebnisse
 - 8.5. Forschungslücken

Darüber hinaus wurde den Publikationen Schlagwörter zugeordnet, die sich z.T. aus den von den Verlagen bereits vorgesehenen Schlagwörtern ergaben und im Laufe der Recherche ergänzt und synthetisiert wurden. Auch hier wurden mehrere Schlagwörter vergeben.

Literatur

Alavi, Maryam; Carlson, Patricia (1992): A review of MIS research and disciplinary development. In: *Journal of Management Information Systems* 8 (4), S. 45–62.

Boell, Sebastian K.; Cecez-Kecmanovic, Dubravka (2014): A hermeneutic approach for conducting literature reviews and literature searches. In: *Communications of the Association for Information Systems* 34 (12), S. 257–286.

Bradford, Samuel C. (1947): Complete Documentation. In: *Nature* 159 (4029), S. 105–106.

Brookes, Bertram C. (1977): Theory of the Bradford Law. In: *Journal of Documentation* 33 (3), S. 180–209.

Furr, Allen L. (1995): The Relative Influence of Social Work Journals. In: *Journal of Social Work Education* 31 (1), S. 38–45.

Hicks, Diana (2005): The Four Literatures of Social Science. In: Henk F. Moed, Wolfgang Gl?nzl und Ulrich Schmoch (Hg.): *Handbook of Quantitative Science and Technology Research*. Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers, S. 473–496.

Okoli, Chitu; Schabram, Kira (2010): A guide to conducting a systematic literature review of information systems research. *Sprouts* (Working Papers on Information, 10/26). Online verfügbar unter <http://sprouts.aisnet.org/10-26>.

Sellers, Sherrill L.; Mathiesen, Sally G.; Perry, Robin; Smith, Thomas (2004): Evaluation of Social Work Journal Quality. Citation versus Reputation Approaches. In: *Journal of Social Work Education* 40 (1), S. 143–160.

Tranfield, David; Denyer, David; Smart, Palminder (2003): Towards a Methodology for Developing Evidence-Informed Management Knowledge by Means of Systematic Review. In: *British Journal of Management* 14 (3), S. 207–222.

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I Bibliographie nach Kategorien

1. Sozialer Kontext

1.1. Policies

Casella, Ronnie (2014): The Historical and political roots of school violence in South Africa. Developing a cross-national theory. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 38–56.

Castillo, Victoria A. (2016): Introduction to “In Conversation on Female Genital Cutting”: A Pedagogical Perspective. In: Gul Ozyegin (Hg.): Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures. London, New York: Routledge, S. 146–149.

Cleary, Kerry; Erooga, Marcus (2012): Policy and Legislation - Changing Responses to an Emerging Problem. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 44–62.

Grudzinskas, Albert; Cody, Richard; Brada, Sara J.; Saleh, Fabian M. (2014): New Technology Meets Old Law. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 3–23.

Hoodfar, Homa; Ghoreishian, Ana (2012): Morality policing and the public sphere: women reclaiming their bodies and their rights. In: Anissa Hélie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance. London: Zed Books, S. 234–268.

O’Neill, Brian; Staksrud, Elisabeth (2012): Policy implications and recommendations. Now what? In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 339–354.

Schmitt, irina (2012): Sexuality, Secularism, and the Nation - Reading Swedish School Policies. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 270–280.

Winter, Elizabeth A.; Elze, Diane E.; Saltzburg, Susan; Rosenwald, Mitchell (2015): Social services for LGBT young people in the United States. Are we there yet? In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 113–130.

Blackman, Jerome S.; Dring, Kathleen (2016): Sexual aggression against children. Pedophiles' and abusers' development, dynamics, treatability, and the law. 1 Edition. New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.

Drobac, Jennifer Ann (2016): Sexual exploitation of teenagers. Adolescent development, discrimination, and consent law. Chicago, London: The University of Chicago Press.

Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014): Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.

Shariff, Shaheen (2015): Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids. New York: Cambridge University Press.

Henry, Nicola; Powell, Anastasia (Hg.) (2014): Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

Bauermeister, José A. (2014): How statewide LGB policies go from “under our skin” to “into our hearts”: fatherhood aspirations and psychological well-being among emerging adult sexual minority men. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1295–1305. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0059-6.

Cocker, Christine; Hafford-Letchfield, Trish (2010): Out and Proud? Social Work's Relationship with Lesbian and Gay Equality. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (6), S. 1996–2008.

Comartin, Erin B.; Kernsmith, Poco D.; Miles, Bart W. (2010): Family experiences of young adult sex offender registration. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 204–225. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003627207.

- Fu, Huiyan (2011): The bumpy road to socialise nature. Sex education in Japan. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 903–915. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.587894.
- Gillespie, Alisdair (2010): Legal definitions of child pornography. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 19–31. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903262097.
- Goldman, Juliette (2010): The new sexuality education curriculum for Queensland primary schools. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (1), S. 47–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681810903491370.
- Kwhali, Josephine; Martin, Linda; Brady, Geraldine; Brown, Sarah J. (2017): Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation. Knowledge, Confidence and Training within a Contemporary UK Social Work Practice and Policy Context. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2208–2226. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw154.
- Lainpelto, Katrin; Isaksson, Johan; Lindblad, Frank (2016): Does Information About Neuropsychiatric Diagnoses Influence Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations? In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 276–292. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1145164.
- Lasher, Michael P.; Stinson, Jill D. (2017): Adults with Pedophilic Interests in the United States: Current Practices and Suggestions for Future Policy and Research. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 659–670. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0822-3.
- Mul, Nick J.; McKenzie, Cameron; Khan, Maryam (2017): Recognition and Legitimation of Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity (SOGI) at the UN. A Critical Systemic Analysis. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2245–2262. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw139.
- Peacock, Dean; Barker, Gary (2014): Working with Men and Boys to Prevent Gender-based Violence. Principles, Lessons Learned, and Ways Forward. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (5), S. 578–599. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14558240.
- Porta, Carolyn M.; Gower, Amy L.; Mehus, Christopher J.; Yu, Xiaohui; Saewyc, Elizabeth M.; Eisenberg, Marla E. (2017): "Kicked out". LGBTQ youths' bathroom experiences and preferences. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 107–112. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.005.
- Samms, Kimika M.; Cholewa, Blaire E. (2014): Exploring the context of child sexual abuse in Jamaica. Addressing the deficits. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 115–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870948.
- Schalet, Amy T.; Santelli, John S.; Russell, Stephen T.; Halpern, Carolyn T.; Miller, Sarah A.; Pickering, Sarah S. et al. (2014): Invited commentary. Broadening the evidence for adolescent sexual and reproductive health and education in the United States. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (10), S. 1595–1610. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0178-8.
- Smith, Connie; Allardyce, Stuart; Hackett, Simon; Bradbury-Jones, Caroline; Lazenbatt, Anne; Taylor, Julie (2014): Practice and policy in the UK with children and young people who display harmful sexual behaviours. An analysis and critical review. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 267–280. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927010.
- Sommer, Marni (2010): Where the education system and women's bodies collide. The social and health impact of girls' experiences of menstruation and schooling in Tanzania. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (4), S. 521–529. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.03.008.
- Šribar, Renata (2013): Growing-up challenged and challenging. Gender and sexuality norms in referential research on 'internet risks' and in children. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (1), S. 129–145. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.748681.
- Wells, Elizabeth A.; Asakura, Kenta; Hoppe, Marilyn J.; Balsam, Kimberly F.; Morrison, Diane M.; Beadnell, Blair (2012): Social Services for Sexual Minority Youth: Preferences for What, Where, and How Services are Delivered. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 36 (2), S. 312–320. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.11.011.
- Willis, Gwenda M.; Johnston, Lucy (2012): Planning helps. The impact of release planning on subsequent re-entry experiences of child sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 194–208. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.506576.
- Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014): Discourse Analysis of Curriculum on Sexuality Education. FLASH for Special Education. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 485–498. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9387-z.
- Winskell, Kate; Beres, Laura K.; Hill, Elizabeth; Mbakwem, Benjamin Chigozie; Obyerodhyambo, Oby (2011): Making sense of abstinence. Social representations in young Africans' HIV-related narratives from six countries. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 945–959. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.591431.

1.2. Diskurse

- Allen, Louisa (2014): *Pleasure's Perils? Critically Reflecting on Pleasure's Inclusion in Sexuality Education*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 153–169.
- Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise; Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): *Introduction. Putting Pleasure Under Pressure*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 1–12.
- Anderson, Eric (2013): *Masculinity and homophobia in high school and college sports. A personal journey from coach to researcher*. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 120–131.
- Bailey, Lucy; Graves, Karen (2012): *Introduction. Society Can Only Be as Free and Open as Its Schools*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 43–45.
- Barbovschi, Monica; Marinescu, Valentina; Velicu, Anca; Laszlo, Eva (2012): *Meeting new contacts online*. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 177–190.
- Bauwens, Joke; Paus-Hasebrink, Ingrid; Ponte, Cristina; Dürager, Andrea (2012): *Understanding digital inequality. The interplay between parental socialisation and children's development*. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 257–272.
- Blumenfeld, Warren J. (2012): *"We're Here and We're Fabulous"*. *Contemporary U.S.-American LGBT Youth Activism*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 73–83.
- Boas, Erica M. (2012): *Walking the Line. Teaching, Being, and Thinking Sexuality in Elementary School*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 131–144.
- Britzman, Deborah P. (2012): *Queer Pedagogy and Its Strange Techniques*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 292–308.
- Bryan Meek, Jane (2012): *"Being Queer Is the Luckiest Thing"*. *Investigating a New Generation's Use of Queer within Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, and Queer Groups (LGBTQ) Student*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 187–198.
- Carmody, Moira (2014): *Young people, ethical sex and violence prevention*. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 167–184.
- Castillo, Victoria A. (2016): *Introduction to "In Conversation on Female Genital Cutting": A Pedagogical Perspective*. In: Gul Ozyegin (Hg.): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge, S. 146–149.
- Davies, Cristyn; McInnes, David (2014): *Speaking violence. Homophobia and the production of injurious speech in schooling cultures*. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 131–148.
- Desjardins, Michel (2012): *The Sexualized Body of the Child. Parents and the Politics of "Voluntary" Sterilization of People Labeled Intellectually Disabled*. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 69–88.
- DeVita, James M.; Daniel Anders, Allison (2014): *Multiple Targeted Identities. Intersectionality and the Lived Experiences of Black Gay Males*. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 464–478.
- Fields, Jessica (2012): *Differences and Divisions. Social Inequality in Sex Education Debates and Policies*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), 24–32.

- Helie, Anissa (2012): Introduction. Policing gender, sexuality and 'Muslimness'. In: Anissa Hélie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books, S. 1–14.
- Henry, Nicola; Powell, Anastasia (2014): The Dark Side of the Virtual World: Towards a Digital Sexual Ethics. In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): *Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 84–105.
- Ingham, Roger (2014): A Well-Kept Secret: Sex Education, Masturbation, and Public Health. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 57–95.
- Iverson, Susan V. (2016): A Policy Discourse Analysis of Sexual Assault Policies in Higher Education. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): *The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response*. New York: Routledge, S. 15–33.
- Jennifer, Dawn (2013): Girls and indirect aggression. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 45–59.
- Lamb, Sharon (2014): The Hard Work of Pleasure. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 136–153.
- Lehtonen, Jukka (2012): Yogyakarta Principles. For the Rights of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender People. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 284.
- Lugg, Catherine A. (2012): The Religious Right and Public Education. The Paranoid Politics of Homophobia. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 61–72.
- Luschen, Kristen V. (2014): Survival, Protection, and Forgiveness. Examining Gendered Violence and Care in the Hunger Games Trilogy. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 133–146.
- Malmström, Maria Frederika (2016): The Continuous Making of Pure Womanhood among Muslim Women in Cairo. Cooking, Depilating, and Circumcising. In: Gul Ozyegin (Hg.): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge, S. 127–145.
- Masinire, Alfred (2014): Becoming a Responsible Boy. Contesting Masculinity in Rural Zimbabwe. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 110–123.
- Matrim, Jair (2014): A Philosophy of Sexual Reciprocity for Secular Public Schools of Toronto. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 313–327.
- McCall, Stephanie D. (2014): Girls Minus Boys. Heteronormative Discourses of Protection in Single-Gender Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 370–386.
- McClelland, Sara I.; Fine, Michelle (2014): Over-Sexed and under Surveillance. Adolescent Sexualities, Cultural Anxieties, and Thick Desire. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 12–35.
- Mollow, Anna (2012): Is Sex Disability? Queer Theory and the Disability Drive. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 285–312.
- Moss, Donald (2015): Sexual aberrations: do we still need the concept? If so, when and why? If not, why not? In: Alessandra Lemma und Paul E. Lynch (Hg.): *Sexualities. Contemporary psychoanalytic perspectives*. London, New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group, S. 177–188.
- Niccolini, Alyssa D. (2014): Spicing Up the Curriculum. The Uses and Pleasures of Erotica Noir in the Urban Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 159–174.

- North, Connie E. (2012): Introduction: Bending the Terrain. Queer and Justice Issues Infiltrate the Education Map. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 5–8.
- Ouer, Freedom (2014): It's Not How Regular Boys Are Supposed to Act. The Nonnormative Sexual Practices of Black Boys in All-Male Public Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 357–369.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): "What's wrong with Porn?". Engaging with Contemporary Painting to Explore the Commodification of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 78–95.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): "Butterflies Starting a Tornado". The Queer 'Not Yet' of New Zealand School-Based Queer Straight Alliance as a Utopic Site of Learning. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 272–283.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen; Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise (2014): After-Word(s). Engaging with the Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education: Affordances and Provocations. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 186–195.
- Rasmussen, Mary Louise (2014): Pleasure/Desire, Sexularism, and Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 153–169.
- Robinson, Kerry H. (2014): Sexual harassment in schools. Issues of identity and power - Negotiating the complexities, contexts and contradictions of this everyday practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 71–94.
- Robles-Fernández, Ramón (2014): A GSA's Impact on Students' Beliefs and Attitudes Toward Civic and Political Participation, Civic Engagement, and Social Justice. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 284–297.
- Roth, Jillian R.; Robinson, Lea; O'Bryant, Camille; Griffin, Pat (2014): 3 to 1. Four Women Navigating the Intersections of Racism, Sexism, Homophobia, and Heterosexism in Intercollegiate Sport. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 453–463.
- Schmidt, Sandra J. (2012): Let Me in! The Impact of the Discourse of Impossibility on Research and Curricular (Re)form. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 199–214.
- Siebers, Tobin (2012): A Sexual Culture for Disabled People. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 37–54.
- Ullman, Jacqueline; McGraw, Kelli (2014): Troubling Silences and Taboo Texts. Constructing Safer and More Positive School Climates for Same-Sex-Attracted High School Students in Australia. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 298–312.
- Vincent, Louise; Macleod, Catriona (2014): Introducing a Critical Pedagogy of Sexual and Reproductive Citizenship: Extending the 'Framework of Thick Desire'. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 115–136.
- Walker Woolley, Susan (2014): (Im)perceptible Silences. Hearing LGBTQ Silences and Voices in School. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 328–341.
- Whitlock, Reta Ugena (2014): LGBT Families and Southern Schools. Thinking About People, Place, and Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 75–89.
- Best, Joel; Bogle, Kathleen A. (2014): Kids gone wild. From rainbow parties to sexting, understanding the hype over teen sex. New York [u.a.]: New York Univ. Press.

- Carmody, Moira (2015): *Sex, ethics, and young people*. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan (Palgrave Macmillan's critical studies in gender, sexuality, and culture).
- Cheit, Ross E. (2014): *The witch-hunt narrative. Politics, psychology, and the sexual abuse of children*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Drobac, Jennifer Ann (2016): *Sexual exploitation of teenagers. Adolescent development, discrimination, and consent law*. Chicago, London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Elliott, Sinikka (2012): *Not my kid. What parents believe about the sex lives of their teenagers*. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press.
- Hasinoff, Amy Adele (2015): *Sexting panic. Rethinking criminalization, privacy, and consent*. Urbana: University of Illinois Press (Feminist media studies).
- Keenan, Marie (2013): *Child sexual abuse and the Catholic Church. Gender, power, and organizational culture*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Larremore, April (2016): *Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom*.
- Oliver, Kelly (2016): *Hunting Girls. Sexual Violence from The Hunger Games to Campus Rape*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Powell, Anastasia (2010): *Sex, Power and Consent. Youth Culture and the Unwritten Rules*. Port Melbourne, Vic.: Cambridge University Press.
- Shariff, Shaheen (2015): *Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise; Quinlivan, Kathleen (Hg.) (2014): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education).
- Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013): *Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications*. Hove: Psychology.
- Lemma, Alessandra; Lynch, Paul E. (Hg.) (2015): *Sexualities. Contemporary psychoanalytic perspectives*. London, New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Allen, Louisa (2013): *Boys as Sexy Bodies*. In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 347–365. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13497205.
- Anderson, E.; McCormack, M. (2015): *Cuddling and Spooning. Heteromascularity and Homosocial Tactility among Student-athletes*. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (2), S. 214–230. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14523433.
- Anderson, Jane (2016): *Socialization Processes and Clergy Offenders*. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (8), S. 846–865. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1241333.
- Attwood, Feona; Smith, Clarissa (2011): *Investigating young people's sexual cultures. An introduction*. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* (Vol. 11 No. 3), S. 235–242.
- Babatsikos, Georgia (2010): *Parents' knowledge, attitudes and practices about preventing child sexual abuse. A literature review*. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (2), S. 107–129. DOI: 10.1002/car.1102.
- Bale, Clare (2011): *Raunch or romance? Framing and interpreting the relationship between sexualized culture and young people's sexual health*. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 303–313. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590088.
- Bantjes, J.; Nieuwoudt, J. (2014): *Masculinity and Mayhem. The Performance of Gender in a South African Boys' School*. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (4), S. 376–395. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539964.
- Beerhuizen, Marinus G. C. J.; Brugman, Daniel (2012): *Sexually abusive youths' moral reasoning on sex*. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 125–135. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.519126.
- Bengtsson, T. T. (2016): *Performing Hypermasculinity. Experiences with Confined Young Offenders*. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (4), S. 410–428. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15595083.
- Beres, Melanie Ann (2014): *Rethinking the concept of consent for anti-sexual violence activism and education*. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 24 (3), S. 373–389. DOI: 10.1177/0959353514539652.

- Berglas, Nancy F.; Angulo-Olaiz, Francisca; Jerman, Petra; Desai, Mona; Constantine, Norman A. (2014): Engaging Youth Perspectives on Sexual Rights and Gender Equality in Intimate Relationships as a Foundation for Rights-Based Sexuality Education. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (4), S. 288–298. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0148-7.
- Blaise, Mindy (2013): Charting new territories. Re-assembling childhood sexuality in the early years classroom. In: *Gender and Education* 25 (7), S. 801–817. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2013.797070.
- Bragg, Sara; Buckingham, David; Russell, Rachel; Willett, Rebekah (2011): Too much, too soon? Children, 'sexualization' and consumer culture. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 279–292. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590085.
- Cameron-Lewis, Vanessa (2016): Escaping oppositional thinking in the teaching of pleasure and danger in sexuality education. In: *Gender and Education* 28 (4), S. 491–509. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2016.1171297.
- Cameron-Lewis, Vanessa; Allen, Louisa (2013): Teaching pleasure and danger in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (2), S. 121–132. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.697440.
- Campregher, Julia; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2016): Attitudes Toward Juvenile Sex Offender Legislation: The Influence of Case-Specific Information. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 466–482. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153558.
- Chapleau, Kristine M.; Oswald, Debra L. (2010): Power, Sex, and Rape Myth Acceptance. Testing Two Models of Rape Proclivity. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 47 (1), S. 66–78.
- Clements, Hannah; Dawson, David L.; das Nair, Roshan (2014): Female-perpetrated sexual abuse. A review of victim and professional perspectives. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 197–215. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.798690.
- Cowburn, Malcolm; Gill, Aisha K.; Harrison, Karen (2015): Speaking about sexual abuse in British South Asian communities. Offenders, victims and the challenges of shame and reintegration. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 4–15. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.929188.
- Coyne, Sarah M.; Padilla-Walker, Laura M. (2015): Sex, violence, & rock n' roll. Longitudinal effects of music on aggression, sex, and prosocial behavior during adolescence. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 41, S. 96–104. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.03.002.
- Cree, Vivienne (2017): 'Khaki Fever' during the First World War. A Historical Case Study of Social Work's Approach towards Young Women, Sex and Moral Danger. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (7), S. 1839–1854. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcv103.
- Cromer, Lisa DeMarni; Goldsmith, Rachel E. (2010): Child sexual abuse myths. Attitudes, beliefs, and individual differences. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (6), S. 618–647. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.522493.
- DePalma, Renée; Atkinson, Elizabeth (2010): The nature of institutional heteronormativity in primary schools and practice-based responses. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (8), S. 1669–1676. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.06.018.
- Epstein, Debbie; Kehily, Mary Jane; Renold, E. (2012): Culture, policy and the un/marked child. Fragments of the sexualisation debates. In: *Gender and Education* 24 (3), S. 249–254. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2012.670390.
- Everson, Mark D.; Faller, Kathleen Coulborn (2012): Base rates, multiple indicators, and comprehensive forensic evaluations. Why sexualized behavior still counts in assessments of child sexual abuse allegations. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (1), S. 45–71. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.642470.
- Fair, Brian (2011): Constructing Masculinity through Penetration Discourse. The Intersection of Misogyny and Homophobia in High School Wrestling. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 491–504. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10375936.
- Ferguson, Christopher J.; Muñoz, Mónica E.; Garza, Adolfo; Galindo, Mariza (2014): Concurrent and prospective analyses of peer, television and social media influences on body dissatisfaction, eating disorder symptoms and life satisfaction in adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (1), S. 1–14. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9898-9.
- Flannery, Dustin D.; Stephens, Clare L.; Thompson, Amy D. (2016): The Impact of High-Profile Sexual Abuse Cases in the Media on a Pediatric Emergency Department. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 627–635. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1187697.

- Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Plummer, Carol (2010): Cultural issues in disclosures of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (5), S. 491–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.512520.
- Fromuth, Mary Ellen; Kelly, David B.; Brallier, Courtney; Williams, Matthew; Benson, Kate (2016): Effects of duration on perceptions of teacher sexual misconduct. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (2), S. 159–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1122692.
- Gakhal, Baldeesh Kaur; Brown, Sarah J. (2011): A comparison of the general public's, forensic professionals' and students' attitudes towards female sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 105–116. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.540678.
- Garland-Levett, Sarah (2016): Exploring discursive barriers to sexual health and social justice in the New Zealand sexuality education curriculum. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 17 (2), S. 121–134. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1233396.
- Gilbert, Jen (2015): Walking through the school: the erotics of research. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 111–115. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1094947.
- Gilbert, Jen (2010): Ambivalence only? Sex education in the age of abstinence. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 233–237. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491631.
- Gill, Michael (2010): Rethinking sexual abuse, questions of consent, and intellectual disability. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (3), S. 201–213. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0019-9.
- Goldman, Juliette (2012): A critical analysis of UNESCO's International Technical Guidance on school-based education for puberty and sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 199–218. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.609051.
- Govender, Kaymarlin (2011): The cool, the bad, the ugly, and the powerful. Identity struggles in schoolboy peer culture. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 887–901. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.586436.
- Gray, Jacqueline M. (2014): What constitutes a "reasonable belief" in consent to sex? A thematic analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 337–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.900122.
- Greslé-Favier, Claire (2010): The legacy of abstinence-only discourses and the place of pleasure in US discourses on teenage sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515098.
- Greslé-Favier, Claire (2013): Adult discrimination against children. The case of abstinence-only education in twenty-first-century USA. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (6), S. 715–725. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.813387.
- Greteman, Adam J. (2013): Fashioning a bareback pedagogy. Towards a theory of risky (sex) education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S20–S31. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.760154.
- Grondin, Anne-Marie (2011): Thinking outside specious boxes. Constructionist and post-structuralist readings of 'child sexual abuse'. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 243–254. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590065.
- Hafford-Letchfield, Trish; Cocker, Christine; Ryan, Peter; Melonowska, Justyna (2017): Rights through Alliances. Findings from a European Project Tackling Homophobic and Transphobic Bullying in Schools through the Engagement of Families and Young People. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2338–2356. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw104.
- Haggis, Jane; Mulholland, Monique (2013): Rethinking difference and sex education. From cultural inclusivity to normative diversity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (1), S. 57–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.824873.
- Hallett, Sophie (2017): 'An Uncomfortable Comfortableness'. 'Care', Child Protection and Child Sexual Exploitation. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (7), S. 2137–2152. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcv136.
- Harper, Craig A.; Bartels, Ross M. (2017): The influence of implicit theories and offender characteristics on judgements of sexual offenders. A moderated mediation analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 139–150. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1250963.

- Harrison, Lyn; Ollis, Debbie (2014): Stepping out of our comfort zones. Pre-service teachers' responses to a critical analysis of gender/power relations in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 318–331. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1023284.
- Hicks, Stephen; Jeyasingham, Dharman (2017): Social Work, Queer Theory and After. A Genealogy of Sexuality Theory in Neo-Liberal Times. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2357–2373. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw103.
- Hirst, Julia (2013): 'It's got to be about enjoying yourself'. Young people, sexual pleasure, and sex and relationships education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 423–436. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.747433.
- Hooghe, Marc (2011): The impact of gendered friendship patterns on the prevalence of homophobia among Belgian late adolescents. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (3), S. 543–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9635-y.
- Hooghe, Marc; Meeusen, Cecil (2012): Homophobia and the transition to adulthood: a three year panel study among Belgian late adolescents and young adults, 2008–2011. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (9), S. 1197–1207. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9786-3.
- Huang, Yu-Te; Souleymanov, Rusty (2016): Rethinking Epistemological Debates and Transnationalism of Sexuality between the West and Taiwan. Implications for Social Workers. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (1), S. 98–114. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu067.
- Huitema, Anneloes; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine (2016): Attitudes of Dutch citizens towards male victims of sexual coercion by a female perpetrator. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 308–322. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1159343.
- Hyde, Abbey; Carney, Marie; Drennan, Jonathan; Butler, Michelle; Lohan, Maria; Howlett, Etaoine (2010): The silent treatment. Parents' narratives of sexuality education with young people. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 359–371. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903514455.
- James, Adilia E. E. (2010): Too Early to Talk About Sex? Issues in Creating Culturally Relevant Sexuality Education for Preadolescent Black Girls in the United States. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (2), S. 128–141. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0012-3.
- Johnson, Brooke (2010): A Few Good Boys. Masculinity at a Military-Style Charter School. In: *Men and Masculinities* 12 (5), S. 575–596. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X09342228.
- Jones, Tiffany Mary (2011): Saving rhetorical children. Sexuality education discourses from conservative to post-modern. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 369–387. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595229.
- Kaestle, Christine E.; Allen, Katherine R. (2011): The role of masturbation in healthy sexual development: perceptions of young adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 983–994. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9722-0.
- Kehily, Mary Jane (2012): Contextualising the sexualisation of girls debate. Innocence, experience and young female sexuality. In: *Gender and Education* 24 (3), S. 255–268. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2012.670391.
- Kelly, Angela; Worth, Heather; Akuani, Frances; Kepa, Barbara; Kupul, Martha; Walizopa, Lucy et al. (2010): Gendered talk about sex, sexual relationships and HIV among young people in Papua New Guinea. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 221–232. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903181107.
- Kemshall, Hazel; Kelly, Gill; Wilkinson, Bernadette (2012): Child Sex Offender Public Disclosure Scheme. The views of applicants using the English pilot disclosure scheme. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 164–178. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.552987.
- Kemshall, Hazel; Moulden, Heather M. (2017): Communicating about child sexual abuse with the public. Learning the lessons from public awareness campaigns. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 124–138. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1222004.
- King, Laura L.; Hanrahan, Kathleen J. (2015): University student beliefs about sexual violence in prison. Rape myth acceptance, punitiveness, and empathy. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 179–193. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.820851.
- Kjaran, Jón; Kristinsdóttir, Guðrún (2014): Queering the environment and caring for the self. Icelandic LGBT students' experience of the upper secondary school. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 23 (1), S. 1–20. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2014.910250.

- Koo, Kelly H.; Stephens, Kari A.; Lindgren, Kristen P.; George, William H. (2012): Misogyny, acculturation, and ethnic identity: relation to rape-supportive attitudes in Asian American college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1005–1014. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9729-1.
- Kuyper, Lisette; Wit, John de; Adam, Philippe; Woertman, Liesbeth (2012): Doing more good than harm? The effects of participation in sex research on young people in the Netherlands. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (2), S. 497–506. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9780-y.
- Lainpelto, Katrin; Isaksson, Johan; Lindblad, Frank (2016): Does Information About Neuropsychiatric Diagnoses Influence Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations? In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 276–292. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1145164.
- Lamb, Sharon; Farmer, Kaelin M.; Kosterina, Elena; Lambe Sariñana, Susan; Plocha, Aleksandra; Randazzo, Renee (2016): What's sexy? Adolescent girls discuss confidence, danger, and media influence. In: *Gender and Education* 28 (4), S. 527–545. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1107528.
- Lamb, Sharon; Lustig, Kara; Graling, Kelly (2013): The use and misuse of pleasure in sex education curricula. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (3), S. 305–318. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.738604.
- Lampert, Jo (2012): Sh-h-h-h. Representations of perpetrators of sexual child abuse in picturebooks. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 177–185. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.609048.
- Langa, Malose (2016): The Value of Using a Psychodynamic Theory in Researching Black Masculinities of Adolescent Boys in Alexandra Township, South Africa. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (3), S. 260–288. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15586434.
- Lasher, Michael P.; Stinson, Jill D. (2017): Adults with Pedophilic Interests in the United States: Current Practices and Suggestions for Future Policy and Research. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 659–670. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0822-3.
- Lavie-Ajayi, Maya (2017): "It Will Continue to Embarrass Me on Some Level, and I Think that's OK". Conceptualising Embarrassment in Discussions about Sex between Social Workers and Service Users. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2282–2299. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw116.
- Lesko, Nancy (2010): Feeling abstinent? Feeling comprehensive? Touching the affects of sexuality curricula. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 281–297. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491633.
- Luder, Marie-Thérèse; Pittet, Isabelle; Berchtold, André; Akre, Christina; Michaud, Pierre-André; Surís, Joan-Carles (2011): Associations between online pornography and sexual behavior among adolescents: myth or reality? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1027–1035. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9714-0.
- Malins, Pamela (2016): How inclusive is "inclusive education" in the Ontario elementary classroom? Teachers talk about addressing diverse gender and sexual identities. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 54, S. 128–138. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.11.004.
- Mallet, Pascal; Herbe, Dominique (2011): Does knowledge about sexuality prevent adolescents from developing rape-supportive beliefs? In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 48 (4), S. 372–380. DOI: 10.1080/00224491003794048.
- Malón, Agustín (2011): The "Participating Victim" in the Study of Erotic Experiences Between Children and Adults: An Historical Analysis. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (1), S. 169–188.
- Malón, Agustín (2010): Onanism and child sexual abuse: a comparative study of two hypotheses. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 637–652. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9465-3.
- Malón, Agustín (2015): Adult–Child Sex and the Limits of Liberal Sexual Morality. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (4), S. 1071–1083.
- Manninen, Sari; Huuki, Tuija; Sunnari, Vappu (2011): Earn Yo' Respect! Respect in the Status Struggle of Finnish School Boys. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (3), S. 335–357. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10369476.
- Mannix, Karyn; Dawson, David L.; Beckley, Kerry (2013): The implicit theories of male child sexual offenders residing in a high secure psychiatric hospital. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 264–274. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.732616.
- Marcell, Arik V.; Eftim, Sorina E.; Sonenstein, Freya L.; Pleck, Joseph H. (2011): Associations of Family and Peer Experiences with Masculinity Attitude Trajectories at the Individual and Group Level in Adolescent and Young Adult Males. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (5), S. 565–587. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X11409363.

- Martino, Wayne J.; Cumming-Potvin, Wendy (2015): Teaching about "Princess Boys" or Not. The Case of One Male Elementary School Teacher and the Polemics of Gender Expression and Embodiment. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (1), S. 79–99. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14551278.
- Maxwell, Louise; Scott, Graham (2014): A review of the role of radical feminist theories in the understanding of rape myth acceptance. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 40–54. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.773384.
- McManus, Michelle Ann; Almond, Louise (2014): Trends of indecent images of children and child sexual offences between 2005/2006 and 2012/2013 within the United Kingdom. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 142–155. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.893031.
- Miller, Susan L.; Hefner, M. Kristen; Leon, Chrysanthi S. (2014): Diffusing responsibility. A case study of child sexual abuse in popular discourse. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 37, S. 55–63. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2013.12.005.
- Muhanguzi, Florence Kyoheirwe (2011): Gender and sexual vulnerability of young women in Africa. Experiences of young girls in secondary schools in Uganda. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 713–725. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.571290.
- Munoz-Laboy, Miguel; Murray, Laura R.; Wittlin, Natalie; Wilson, Patrick A.; Terto, Veriano; Parker, Richard (2011): Divine targets. Youth at the centre of Catholic and Pentecostal responses to HIV and AIDS in Brazil. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 657–668. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.565519.
- Norman, Moss E. (2011): Embodying the Double-Bind of Masculinity. Young Men and Discourses of Normalcy, Health, Heterosexuality, and Individualism. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 430–449. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X11409360.
- Nothdurfter, Urban; Nagy, Andrea (2017): Few and Far from Radical? LGBT-Related Contributions in European Social Work Journal Publishing. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2227–2244. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw140.
- O'Leary, P.; Tsui, M.-S.; Ruch, G. (2013): The Boundaries of the Social Work Relationship Revisited. Towards a Connected, Inclusive and Dynamic Conceptualisation. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 43 (1), S. 135–153. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcr181.
- Pascoe, C. J. (2011): Resource and Risk. Youth Sexuality and New Media Use. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 5–17. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0042-5.
- Pasura, Dominic; Jones, Adele D.; Hafner, James A. H.; Maharaj, Priya E.; Nathaniel-DeCaires, Karene; Johnson, Emmanuel Janagan (2013): Competing meanings of childhood and the social construction of child sexual abuse in the Caribbean. In: *Childhood* 20 (2), S. 200–214. DOI: 10.1177/0907568212462255.
- Pavlakis, D. (2014): Reputation and the Sexual Abuse of Boys. Changing Norms in Late-Nineteenth-Century Britain. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (3), S. 325–346. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539512.
- Peacock, Dean; Barker, Gary (2014): Working with Men and Boys to Prevent Gender-based Violence. Principles, Lessons Learned, and Ways Forward. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (5), S. 578–599. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14558240.
- Piccigallo, Jaqueline R.; Lilley, Terry G.; Miller, Susan L. (2012): "It's Cool to Care about Sexual Violence". Men's Experiences with Sexual Assault Prevention. In: *Men and Masculinities* 15 (5), S. 507–525. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X12458590.
- Russell, Brenda L.; Oswald, Debra L. (2016): When Sexism Cuts Both Ways. Predictors of Tolerance of Sexual Harassment of Men. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (5), S. 524–544. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15602745.
- Rysst, Mari (2010): 'I Am Only Ten Years Old'. Femininities, clothing-fashion codes and the intergenerational gap of interpretation of young girls' clothes. In: *Childhood* 17 (1), S. 76–93. DOI: 10.1177/0907568209351552.
- Sakellariou, Dikaio (2012): Sexuality and Disability. A Discussion on Care of the Self. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 187–197. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9219-3.
- Sauntson, Helen (2013): Sexual diversity and illocutionary silencing in the English National Curriculum. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 395–408. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.745809.
- Schalet, Amy T.; Santelli, John S.; Russell, Stephen T.; Halpern, Carolyn T.; Miller, Sarah A.; Pickering, Sarah S. et al. (2014): Invited commentary. Broadening the evidence for adolescent sexual and reproductive health and

- education in the United States. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (10), S. 1595–1610. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0178-8.
- Schaub, Jason; Willis, Paul; Dunk-West, Priscilla (2016): Accounting for Self, Sex and Sexuality in UK Social Workers' Knowledge Base. Findings from an Exploratory Study. In: *The British Journal of Social Work*, bcw015. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw015.
- Seto, Michael C. (2012): Is pedophilia a sexual orientation? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (1), S. 231–236. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9882-6.
- Sloane, Heather M. (2014): Tales of a Reluctant Sex Radical. Barriers to Teaching the Importance of Pleasure for Wellbeing. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 453–467. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9381-5.
- Smith, Mark; Woodiwiss, Jo (2017): Sexuality, Innocence and Agency in Narratives of Childhood Sexual Abuse. Implications for Social Work. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2173–2189. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw160.
- Spišák, Sanna; Paasonen, Susanna (2017): Bad education? Childhood recollections of pornography, sexual exploration, learning and agency in Finland. In: *Childhood* 24 (1), S. 99–112. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216646436.
- Šriбар, Renata (2013): Growing-up challenged and challenging. Gender and sexuality norms in referential research on 'internet risks' and in children. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (1), S. 129–145. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.748681.
- Strömwall, Leif A.; Alfredsson, Helen; Landström, Sara (2013): Rape victim and perpetrator blame and the Just World hypothesis. The influence of victim gender and age. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 207–217. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.683455.
- Tabatabaie, Alireza (2014): Childhood and adolescent sexuality, Islam, and problematics of sex education. A call for re-examination. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 276–288. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1005836.
- Tsaliki, Liza (2015): Popular culture and moral panics about 'children at risk'. Revisiting the sexualisation-of-young-girls debate. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 500–514. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1022893.
- Turner, George W.; Crane, Betsy (2017): Sexually Silenced No More, Adults with Learning Disabilities Speak Up. A Call to Action for Social Work to Frame Sexual Voice as a Social Justice Issue. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2300–2317. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw133.
- Vandenbosch, Laura; Eggermont, Steven (2013): Sexualization of Adolescent Boys. In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 283–306. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13477866.
- Vries, Hein de; Eggers, Sander Matthijs; Jinabhai, Champak; Meyer-Weitz, Anna; Sathiparsad, Reshma; Taylor, Myra (2014): Adolescents' beliefs about forced sex in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (6), S. 1087–1095. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0280-8.
- Weatherred, Jane Long (2017): Framing Child Sexual Abuse. A Longitudinal Content Analysis of Newspaper and Television Coverage, 2002–2012. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 3–22. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1257528.
- Wetherill, Reagan R.; Neal, Dan J.; Fromme, Kim (2010): Parents, peers, and sexual values influence sexual behavior during the transition to college. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 682–694. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9476-8.
- Whittier, Nancy (2016): Where Are the Children? Theorizing the Missing Piece in Gendered Sexual Violence. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (1), S. 95–108. DOI: 10.1177/0891243215612412.
- Williams, Matthew L.; Hudson, Kirsty (2013): Public perceptions of internet, familial and localised sexual grooming. Predicting perceived prevalence and safety. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 218–235. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.705341.
- Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014): Why All the Talk About Sex? An Autoethnography Identifying the Troubling Discourse of Sexuality and Intellectual Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 107–116. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9331-7.
- Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014): Discourse Analysis of Curriculum on Sexuality Education. FLASH for Special Education. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 485–498. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9387-z.

Winskell, Kate; Beres, Laura K.; Hill, Elizabeth; Mbakwem, Benjamin Chigozie; Obyerodhyambo, Oby (2011): Making sense of abstinence. Social representations in young Africans' HIV-related narratives from six countries. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 945–959. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.591431.

Zafar, Sadia; Ross, Erin C. (2013): Perceptions of childhood sexual abuse survivors. Development and initial validation of a new scale to measure stereotypes of adult survivors of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (3), S. 358–378. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.743955.

1.3. Medien und Technologie

Barbovski, Monica; Marinescu, Valentina; Velicu, Anca; Laszlo, Eva (2012): Meeting new contacts online. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 177–190.

Bauwens, Joke; Paus-Hasebrink, Ingrid; Ponte, Cristina; Dürager, Andrea (2012): Understanding digital inequality. The interplay between parental socialisation and children's development. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 257–272.

Boonmann, Cyril; Grudzinskas, Albert; Aebi, Marcel (2014): Juveniles, the Internet, and Sexual Offending. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 161–179.

Chapman, Amy; Buchanan, Rachel (2014): FYI... Virtual space has a context. Towards an alternative frame for understanding cyberbullying. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 56–71.

Clark, Andrew B. (2014): Parenting Through the Digital Revolution. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 247–261.

Clavert, Clay (2014): Youth-Produced Sexual Images, "Sexting", and the Cellphone. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 89–116.

Crowley, M. Sue (2014): Defining Themselves. LGBTQ Youth Online. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 90–109.

Garmendia, Maialen; Garitaonandia, Carmelo; Martinez, Gemma; Casado, Miguel Ángel (2012): The effectiveness of parental mediation. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 231–244.

Görzig, Anke (2012): Methodological framework. The EU Kids Online project. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 15–32.

Görzig, Anke; Mascheroni, Giovanna; Murru, Maria Francesca (2012): Varieties of access and use. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 59–72.

Grudzinskas, Albert; Cody, Richard; Brada, Sara J.; Saleh, Fabian M. (2014): New Technology Meets Old Law. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 3–23.

Harris, Andrew J. (2014): Understanding the World of Digital Youth. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 24–61.

Harris, Andrew J.; Davidson, Judith (2014): Teens, Sex, and Technology: Implications for Educational Systems and Practice. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 262–292.

- Hasebrink, Uwe (2012): Young European's online environments: a typology of user practices. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 127–140.
- Helsper, Ellen (2012): Which children are fully online? In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 45–58.
- Henry, Nicola; Powell, Anastasia (2014): The Dark Side of the Virtual World: Towards a Digital Sexual Ethics. In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 84–105.
- Hua, Liwei L.; Yapo, Scott; Yule, Amy; Gorrindo, Tristan (2014): Problematic Internet Behaviours: Diagnostic and Treatment. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 293–314.
- Judge, Abigail; Graw Leary, Mary (2014): From the Streets to Cyberspace. The Effects of Technology in the Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children and Adolescents in the United States. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 180–214.
- Kalmus, Veronika; Feilitzen, Cecilia von; Siibak, Andra (2012): Effectiveness of teacher's and peers mediation in supporting opportunities and reducing risks online. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 245–256.
- Kirwil, Lucyna; Laouris, Yiannis (2012): Experimenting with the self online: a risky opportunity. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 113–126.
- Kupiainen, Reijo; Suoninen, Annikka; Nikunen, Kaarina (2012): Between public and private: privacy in social networking sites. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 99–112.
- Lampert, Claudia; Donoso, Véronica (2012): Bullying. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 141–150.
- Laurinavicius, Alfredas; Zukauskienė, Rita; Ustinaviciute, Laura (2012): Explaining vulnerability to risk and harm. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 297–308.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Görzig, Anke (2012): Sexting: the exchange of sexual messages online among European youth. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 151–164.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Haddon, Leslie (2012): Theoretical framework for children's internet use. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 1–14.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Hasebrink, Uwe; Görzig, Anke (2012): Towards a general model of determinants of risk and safety. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 323–338.
- Luschen, Kristen V. (2014): Survival, Protection, and Forgiveness. Examining Gendered Violence and Care in the Hunger Games Trilogy. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 133–146.
- Murphy, Lisa; Ranger, Rebekah; Fedorff, J. Paul (2014): Legal and Clinical Issues in Interpreting Child Pornography on the Internet. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 215–246.

- Niccolini, Alyssa D. (2014): Spicing Up the Curriculum. The Uses and Pleasures of Erotica Noir in the Urban Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 159–174.
- O’Neill, Brian; Staksrud, Elisabeth (2012): Policy implications and recommendations. Now what? In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 339–354.
- Ogan, Christine; Karakus, Türkan; Kursun, Engin; Cagiltay, Kürsat; Kasikci, Duygu (2012): Cognitive interviewing and response to EU Kids Online survey questions. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 33–44.
- Pasquier, Dominique; Simoes, José Alberto; Kredens, Elodie (2012): Agents of mediation and sources of safety awareness: a comparative overview. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 219–230.
- Pruulmann-Vengerfeldt, Pille; Runnel, Pille (2012): Online opportunities. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 73–86.
- Quayle, Ethel (2012): Organisational issues and new technologies. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 99–121.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): "What’s wrong with Porn?". Engaging with Contemporary Painting to Explore the Commodification of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 78–95.
- Racine, Christopher W.; Bates Billick, Stephen (2014): Conclusion. Understanding Adolescent Sexual Development and the Law in the Digital Era. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 346–354.
- Rivers, Ian (2013): Cyberbullying and cyberaggression. Sexualised and gendered experiences explored. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 19–44.
- Rovoliy, Antonis; Tsaliki, Liza (2012): Pornography. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 165–176.
- Ságvári, Bence; Galács, Anna (2012): Relating online practices, negative experiences and coping strategies. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 309–322.
- Saleh, Fabian M.; Feldman, Barry N.; Grudzinskas, Albert; Ravven, Simha E.; Cody, Richard (2014): Cybersexual Harassment and Suicide. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 139–160.
- Scott, Charles L. (2014): Chat Rooms and Social Networking Sites. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 117–138.
- Seroussi, Ariel; Bonnici, Daniel; Leogn, Gregory B.; Weinstock, Robert (2014): Ethical and Legal Considerations for Psychiatry Regarding Adolescents and Technology Use. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 315–345.
- Smahel, David; Blinka, Lukás (2012): Expressive internet use among European children. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 191–204.

- Smahel, David; Subrahmanyam, Kaveri (2014): Adolescent Sexuality on the Internet: A Developmental Perspective. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 62–88.
- Sonck, Nathalie; Kuiper, Els; Haan, Jos de (2012): Digital skills in the context of media literacy. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 87–98.
- Stald, Gitte; Ólafson, Kjartan (2012): Mobile access: different users, different risks, different consequences? In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 285–296.
- Vandoninck, Sofie; d’Haenens, Leen; Segers, Katia (2012): Coping and resilience: children’s response to online risks. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 205–218.
- Best, Joel; Bogle, Kathleen A. (2014): Kids gone wild. From rainbow parties to sexting, understanding the hype over teen sex. New York [u.a.]: New York Univ. Press.
- Elliott, Sinikka (2012): Not my kid. What parents believe about the sex lives of their teenagers. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press.
- Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014): Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Hasinoff, Amy Adele (2015): Sexting panic. Rethinking criminalization, privacy, and consent. Urbana: University of Illinois Press (Feminist media studies).
- Oliver, Kelly (2016): Hunting Girls. Sexual Violence from The Hunger Games to Campus Rape. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Shariff, Shaheen (2015): Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Haddon, Leslie; Görzig, Anke (Hg.) (2012): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press.
- Saleh, Fabian M.; Grudzinskas, Albert; Judge, Abigail (Hg.) (2014): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Albury, Kath (2013): Young people, media and sexual learning. Rethinking representation. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S32–S44. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.767194.
- Arrington-Sanders, Renata; Harper, Gary W.; Morgan, Anthony; Ogunbajo, Adedotun; Trent, Maria; Fortenberry, J. Dennis (2015): The role of sexually explicit material in the sexual development of same-sex-attracted Black adolescent males. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 597–608. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0416-x.
- Atkinson, Chris; Newton, David (2010): Online behaviours of adolescents. Victims, perpetrators and Web 2.0. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 107–120. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903337683.
- Bale, Clare (2011): Raunch or romance? Framing and interpreting the relationship between sexualized culture and young people's sexual health. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 303–313. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590088.
- Balfe, Myles; Gallagher, Bernard; Masson, Helen; Balfe, Shane; Brugha, Ruairi; Hackett, Simon (2015): Internet Child Sex Offenders' Concerns about Online Security and their Use of Identity Protection Technologies. A Review. In: *Child Abuse Review* 24 (6), S. 427–439. DOI: 10.1002/car.2308.
- Baumgartner, Susanne E.; Valkenburg, Patti M.; Peter, Jochen (2010): Assessing causality in the relationship between adolescents' risky sexual online behavior and their perceptions of this behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1226–1239. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9512-y.
- Bergen, Emilia; Ahto, Anna; Schulz, Anja; Imhoff, Roland; Antfolk, Jan; Schuhmann, Petya et al. (2015): Adult-Adult and Adult-Child/Adolescent Online Sexual Interactions. An Exploratory Self-Report Study on the Role of Situational Factors. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 52 (9), S. 1006–1016.

- Black, Pamela J.; Wollis, Melissa; Woodworth, Michael; Hancock, Jeffrey T. (2015): A linguistic analysis of grooming strategies of online child sex offenders: Implications for our understanding of predatory sexual behavior in an increasingly computer-mediated world. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 44, S. 140–149.
- Bragg, Sara; Buckingham, David; Russell, Rachel; Willett, Rebekah (2011): Too much, too soon? Children, 'sexualization' and consumer culture. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 279–292. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590085.
- Brakefield, Tiffany A.; Mednick, Sara C.; Wilson, Helen W.; Neve, Jan-Emmanuel de; Christakis, Nicholas A.; Fowler, James H. (2014): Same-sex sexual attraction does not spread in adolescent social networks. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 335–344. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0142-9.
- Buschman, Jos; Wilcox, Dan; Krapohl, Donald; Oelrich, Marty; Hackett, Simon (2010): Cybersex offender risk assessment. An explorative study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 197–209. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003690518.
- Choi, Hye Jeong; Ouytsel, Joris van; Temple, Jeff R. (2016): Association between sexting and sexual coercion among female adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 53, S. 164–168. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.10.005.
- Coyne, Sarah M.; Padilla-Walker, Laura M. (2015): Sex, violence, & rock n' roll. Longitudinal effects of music on aggression, sex, and prosocial behavior during adolescence. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 41, S. 96–104. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.03.002.
- Cree, Vivienne (2017): 'Khaki Fever' during the First World War. A Historical Case Study of Social Work's Approach towards Young Women, Sex and Moral Danger. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (7), S. 1839–1854. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcv103.
- D'Abreu, Lylla Cysne Frota; Krahe, Barbara (2016): Vulnerability to Sexual Victimization in Female and Male College Students in Brazil: Cross-Sectional and Prospective Evidence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1101–1115. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0451-7.
- Daneback, Kristian; Månsson, Sven-Axel; Ross, Michael W.; Markham, Christine M. (2012): The Internet as a source of information about sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 583–598. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627739.
- DeHart, Dana; Dwyer, Gregg; Seto, Michael C.; Moran, Robert; Letourneau, Elizabeth; Schwarz-Watts, Donna (2017): Internet sexual solicitation of children. A proposed typology of offenders based on their chats, e-mails, and social network posts. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 77–89. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1241309.
- Elliott, Ian A.; Findlater, Donald; Hughes, Teresa (2010): Practice report. A review of e-Safety remote computer monitoring for UK sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003686870.
- Fagerlund, Monica; Ellonen, Noora (2016): Children's Experiences of Completing a Computer-Based Violence Survey. Finnish Child Victim Survey Revisited. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 556–576. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.118769.
- Ferguson, Christopher J.; Muñoz, Mónica E.; Garza, Adolfo; Galindo, Mariza (2014): Concurrent and prospective analyses of peer, television and social media influences on body dissatisfaction, eating disorder symptoms and life satisfaction in adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (1), S. 1–14. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9898-9.
- Flannery, Dustin D.; Stephens, Clare L.; Thompson, Amy D. (2016): The Impact of High-Profile Sexual Abuse Cases in the Media on a Pediatric Emergency Department. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 627–635. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1187697.
- Gilliam, Melissa; Brindis, Claire D. (2011): Virtual Sex Ed. Youth, Race, Sex, and New Media. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 1–4. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0036-3.
- Gilliam, Melissa; Jagoda, Patrick; Jaworski, Erin; Hebert, Luciana E.; Lyman, Phoebe; Wilson, M. Claire (2015): "Because if we don't talk about it, how are we going to prevent it?". Lucidity, a narrative-based digital game about sexual violence. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (4), S. 391–404. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1123147.
- Glasgow, David (2010): The potential of digital evidence to contribute to risk assessment of internet offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 87–106. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903428839.

- González-Ortega, Eva; Vicario-Molina, Isabel; Martínez, José Luis; Orgaz, Begoña (2015): The Internet as a Source of Sexual Information in a Sample of Spanish Adolescents. Associations with Sexual Behavior. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 12 (4), S. 290–300. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-015-0196-7.
- Green, Eli R.; Hamarman, Amelia M.; McKee, Ryan W. (2014): Online sexuality education pedagogy. Translating five in-person teaching methods to online learning environments. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (1), S. 19–30. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.942033.
- Henry, Olivia; Mandeville-Norden, Rebecca; Hayes, Elizabeth; Egan, Vincent (2010): Do internet-based sexual offenders reduce to normal, inadequate and deviant groups? In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 33–46. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903454132.
- Kaestle, Christine E.; Allen, Katherine R. (2011): The role of masturbation in healthy sexual development: perceptions of young adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 983–994. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9722-0.
- Katz, Carmit (2013): Internet-related child sexual abuse. What children tell us in their testimonies. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (9), S. 1536–1542. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.06.006.
- Kennett, Deborah J.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Schultz, Kristen E. (2011): Sexual resourcefulness and the impact of family, sex education, media and peers. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615624.
- Kettleborough, Danielle G.; Merdian, Hannah L. (2017): Gateway to offending behaviour. Permission-giving thoughts of online users of child sexual exploitation material. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 19–32. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1231852.
- Kuhle, Laura F.; Schlinzig, Eliza; Kaiser, Gerd; Amelung, Till; Konrad, Anna; Röhle, Robert; Beier, Klaus M. (2017): The association of sexual preference and dynamic risk factors with undetected child pornography offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 3–18. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1201157.
- Lamb, Sharon; Farmer, Kaelin M.; Kosterina, Elena; Lambe Sariñana, Susan; Plocha, Aleksandra; Randazzo, Renee (2016): What's sexy? Adolescent girls discuss confidence, danger, and media influence. In: *Gender and Education* 28 (4), S. 527–545. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1107528.
- Leonard, Marcella Mary (2010): "I did what I was directed to do but he didn't touch me". The impact of being a victim of internet offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 249–256. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003690526.
- Levine, Deb (2011): Using Technology, New Media, and Mobile for Sexual and Reproductive Health. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 18–26. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0040-7.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Smith, Peter K. (2014): Annual Research Review: Harms experienced by child users of online and mobile technologies. The nature, prevalence and management of sexual and aggressive risks in the digital age. In: *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry* 55 (6), S. 635–654.
- Luder, Marie-Thérèse; Pittet, Isabelle; Berchtold, André; Akre, Christina; Michaud, Pierre-André; Surís, Joan-Carles (2011): Associations between online pornography and sexual behavior among adolescents: myth or reality? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1027–1035. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9714-0.
- Malón, Agustín (2010): Onanism and child sexual abuse: a comparative study of two hypotheses. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 637–652. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9465-3.
- Man-Ging, Carlos Ignacio; Bohm, Bettina; Fuchs, Katharina Anna; Witte, Susanne; Frick, Eckhard (2015): Improving Empathy in the Prevention of Sexual Abuse Against Children and Youngsters. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (7), S. 796–815. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1077366.
- Martin, Jennifer (2016): Child Sexual Abuse Images Online. Implications for Social Work Training and Practice. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (2), S. 372–388. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu116.
- McKee, Alan (2016): Learning from commercial entertainment producers in order to create entertainment sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 17 (1), S. 26–40. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1228528.
- McKee, Alan (2012): The importance of entertainment for sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 499–509. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627727.
- McManus, Michelle Ann; Long, Matthew L.; Alison, Laurence; Almond, Louise (2014): Factors associated with contact child sexual abuse in a sample of indecent image offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 368–384. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927009.

- Merdian, Hannah Lena; Curtis, Cate; Thakker, Jo; Wilson, Nick; Boer, Douglas Pieter (2013): The three dimensions of online child pornography offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 121–132. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.611898.
- Miller, Susan L.; Hefner, M. Kristen; Leon, Chrysanthi S. (2014): Diffusing responsibility. A case study of child sexual abuse in popular discourse. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 37, S. 55–63. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2013.12.005.
- Misurell, Justin R.; Springer, Craig; Tryon, Warren W. (2011): Game-based cognitive-behavioral therapy (GB-CBT) group program for children who have experienced sexual abuse. A preliminary investigation. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 14–36. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.540000.
- Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Ybarra, Michele L.; Korchmaros, Josephine D. (2014): Sexual harassment among adolescents of different sexual orientations and gender identities. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (2), S. 280–295.
- Mustanski, Brian; Greene, George J.; Ryan, Daniel; Whitton, Sarah W. (2015): Feasibility, Acceptability, and Initial Efficacy of an Online Sexual Health Promotion Program for LGBT Youth. The Queer Sex Ed Intervention. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 52 (2), S. 220–230.
- Nielsena, Silja; Paasonen, Susanna; Spišák, Sanna (2015): 'Pervy role-play and such'. Girls' experiences of sexual messaging online. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 472–485.
- O'Halloran, Elaine; Quayle, Ethel (2010): A content analysis of a "boy love" support forum. Revisiting Durkin and Bryant. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 71–85. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903395319.
- Ojanen, Timo Tapani; Boonmongkon, Pimpawun; Samakkeekarom, Ronnapoom; Samoh, Nattharat; Cholratana, Mudjalin; Guadamuz, Thomas Ebanan (2015): Connections between online harassment and offline violence among youth in Central Thailand. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 44, S. 159–169.
- Oosten, Johanna M. F. van; Vandenbosch, Laura (2017): Sexy online self-presentation on social network sites and the willingness to engage in sexting: A comparison of gender and age. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 54, S. 42–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.11.006.
- Pascoe, C. J. (2011): Resource and Risk. Youth Sexuality and New Media Use. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 5–17. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0042-5.
- Pavlakis, D. (2014): Reputation and the Sexual Abuse of Boys. Changing Norms in Late-Nineteenth-Century Britain. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (3), S. 325–346. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539512.
- Peacock, Dean; Barker, Gary (2014): Working with Men and Boys to Prevent Gender-based Violence. Principles, Lessons Learned, and Ways Forward. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (5), S. 578–599. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14558240.
- Peter, Jochen; Valkenburg, Patti M. (2011): The use of sexually explicit internet material and its antecedents: a longitudinal comparison of adolescents and adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1015–1025. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9644-x.
- Pingel, Emily Sweetnam; Thomas, Laura; Harmell, Chelsea; Bauermeister, Jose (2013): Creating comprehensive, youth centered, culturally appropriate sex education: What do young gay, bisexual and questioning men want? In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 10 (4). DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0134-5.
- Rice, Eric; Winetrobe, Hailey; Holloway, Ian W.; Montoya, Jorge; Plant, Aaron; Kordic, Timothy (2015): Cell phone internet access, online sexual solicitation, partner seeking, and sexual risk behavior among adolescents. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 755–763. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0366-3.
- Rogers, Paul; Wczasek, Ryan; Davies, Michelle (2011): Attributions of blame in a hypothetical internet solicitation case. Roles of victim naivety, parental neglect and respondent gender. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 196–214. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003664869.
- Rysst, Mari (2010): 'I Am Only Ten Years Old'. Femininities, clothing-fashion codes and the intergenerational gap of interpretation of young girls' clothes. In: *Childhood* 17 (1), S. 76–93. DOI: 10.1177/0907568209351552.
- Seto, Michael C.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2015): Viewing child pornography: prevalence and correlates in a representative community sample of young Swedish men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 67–79. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0244-4.

- Sevcikova, Anna (2016): Girls' and boys' experience with teen sexting in early and late adolescence. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 51, S. 156–162. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.06.007.
- Sheehan, Valerie; Sullivan, Joe (2010): A qualitative analysis of child sex offenders involved in the manufacture of indecent images of children. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 143–167. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003698644.
- Smith, Marshall (2013): Youth Viewing Sexually Explicit Material Online. Addressing the Elephant on the Screen. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 10 (1), S. 62–75. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-012-0103-4.
- Šribar, Renata (2013): Growing-up challenged and challenging. Gender and sexuality norms in referential research on 'internet risks' and in children. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (1), S. 129–145. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.748681.
- Stevens, Peter; Hutchin, Katie; French, Lesley; Craissati, Jackie (2013): Developmental and offence-related characteristics of different types of adolescent sex offender. A community sample. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 138–157. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.645889.
- Stulhofer, Aleksandar; Busko, Vesna; Landripet, Ivan (2010): Pornography, sexual socialization, and satisfaction among young men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (1), S. 168–178. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9387-0.
- Svedin, Carl-Göran; Akerman, Ingrid; Priebe, Gisela (2011): Frequent users of pornography. A population based epidemiological study of Swedish male adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 779–788. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.04.010.
- Temple, Jeff R.; Choi, Hye Jeong; Brem, Meagan; Wolford-Clevenger, Caitlin; Stuart, Gregory L.; Peskin, Melissa Fleschler; Elmquist, JoAnna (2016): The Temporal Association Between Traditional and Cyber Dating Abuse Among Adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 340–349. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0380-3.
- Tsagaris, George S.; Bach, Jesse E.; Cimino, Chrisa (2017): The characteristics of federal offenders sentenced for sexual exploitation of children within a large urban metropolitan region. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 181–194. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1307463.
- Tsaliki, Liza (2015): Popular culture and moral panics about 'children at risk'. Revisiting the sexualisation-of-young-girls debate. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 500–514. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1022893.
- van Oosten, Johanna M. F. (2016): Sexually Explicit Internet Material and Adolescents' Sexual Uncertainty: The Role of Disposition-Content Congruency. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (4), S. 1011–1022. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0594-1.
- van Oosten, Johanna M. F.; Peter, Jochen; Boot, Inge (2015): Exploring associations between exposure to sexy online self-presentations and adolescents' sexual attitudes and behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 1078–1091. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0194-8.
- Vandenbosch, Laura; Eggermont, Steven (2015): The role of mass media in adolescents' sexual behaviors: exploring the explanatory value of the three-step self-objectification process. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 729–742. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0292-4.
- Vandenbosch, Laura; Eggermont, Steven (2013): Sexualization of Adolescent Boys. In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 283–306. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13477866.
- Velezmore, Rodrigo; Negy, Charles; Livia, Jose (2012): Online sexual activity: cross-national comparison between United States and Peruvian college students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1015–1025. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9862-x.
- Weatherred, Jane Long (2017): Framing Child Sexual Abuse. A Longitudinal Content Analysis of Newspaper and Television Coverage, 2002–2012. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 3–22. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1257528.
- Weiler, Julia von; Haardt-Becker, Annette; Schulte, Simone (2010): Care and treatment of child victims of child pornographic exploitation (CPE) in Germany. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 211–222. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003759990.
- Williams, Matthew L.; Hudson, Kirsty (2013): Public perceptions of internet, familial and localised sexual grooming. Predicting perceived prevalence and safety. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 218–235. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.705341.

Winters, Georgia M.; Kaylor, Leah E.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2017): Sexual offenders contacting children online. An examination of transcripts of sexual grooming. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 62–76. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1271146.

Wright, Michelle F. (2015): Cyber aggression within adolescents' romantic relationships: linkages to parental and partner attachment. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 37–47. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0147-2.

Ybarra, Michele L.; Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Palmer, Neal A.; Reisner, Sari L. (2015): Online social support as a buffer against online and offline peer and sexual victimization among U.S. LGBT and non-LGBT youth. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 39, S. 123–136.

Young, T. Lorraine; Riggs, Matt; Robinson, Jill L. (2011): Childhood sexual abuse severity reconsidered. A factor structure of CSA characteristics. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 373–395. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.590124.

Zweig, Janine M.; Dank, Meredith; Yahner, Jennifer; Lachman, Pamela (2013): The rate of cyber dating abuse among teens and how it relates to other forms of teen dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1063–1077. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9922-8.

1.4. Identitäten

1.4.1. Gender

Anderson, Eric (2013): Masculinity and homophobia in high school and college sports. A personal journey from coach to researcher. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 120–131.

Atkinson, Becky (2012): Apple Jumper, Teacher Babe, and Bland Uniformer Teachers: Fashioning Feminine Teacher Bodies. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 93–104.

Burke, Kevin (2014): Impossible Women. Saints, Sinner, and the Gendered Mythology in a Catholic School. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 25–37.

Carmody, Moira (2014): Young people, ethical sex and violence prevention. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 167–184.

Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2016): Heterosexist Discourses. How Feminist Theory Shaped Campus Sexual Violence Policy. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): *The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response*. New York: Routledge, S. 33–52.

Castillo, Victoria A. (2016): Introduction to "In Conversation on Female Genital Cutting": A Pedagogical Perspective. In: Gul Ozyegin (Hg.): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge, S. 146–149.

Chapman, Amy; Buchanan, Rachel (2014): FYI... Virtual space has a context. Towards an alternative frame for understanding cyberbullying. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 56–71.

Dankmeijer, Peter (2012): LGBT, to Be or Not to Be? Education about Sexual Preferences and Gender Identities Worldwide. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 254–269.

DeVita, James M.; Daniel Anders, Allison (2014): Multiple Targeted Identities. Intersectionality and the Lived Experiences of Black Gay Males. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 464–478.

Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): Bullying and sexual violence. Definition, prevalence, outcomes and moderators. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 31–44.

Helie, Anissa (2012): Introduction. Policing gender, sexuality and 'Muslimness'. In: Anissa Hélie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books, S. 1–14.

- Hoodfar, Homa; Ghoreishian, Ana (2012): Morality policing and the public sphere: women reclaiming their bodies and their rights. In: Anissa Hélie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books, S. 234–268.
- Jennifer, Dawn (2013): Girls and indirect aggression. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 45–59.
- Karim, Shuchi (2012): Living sexualities: non-hetero female sexuality in urban middle-class Bangladesh. In: Anissa Hélie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books, S. 269–293.
- Lewis, Mel Michelle (2012): Pedagogy and the Sista' Professor. Teaching Black Queer Feminist Studies through the Self. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 33–40.
- Linville, Darla (2012): Introduction. Schooling Students in Gender and Sexuality Expectations. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 125–128.
- Luschen, Kristen V. (2014): Survival, Protection, and Forgiveness. Examining Gendered Violence and Care in the Hunger Games Trilogy. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 133–146.
- Malmström, Maria Frederika (2016): The Continuous Making of Pure Womanhood among Muslim Women in Cairo. Cooking, Depilating, and Circumcising. In: Gul Ozyegin (Hg.): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge, S. 127–145.
- Martino, Wayne (2014): Masculinities, Gender Non-Conformity, and the Significance of Queer and Transgender Perspectives in Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 9–24.
- Masinire, Alfred (2014): Becoming a Responsible Boy. Contesting Masculinity in Rural Zimbabwe. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 110–123.
- McCall, Stephanie D. (2014): Girls Minus Boys. Heteronormative Discourses of Protection in Single-Gender Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 370–386.
- McCready, Lance T. (2014): The African Dance Program. "Where is the Love?". In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), 342-356.
- Migdalek, Jack (2014): Challenging Gendered Practices Through Drama. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 414–425.
- Mills, Martin (2014): Schools, violence, masculinities and privilege. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 94–110.
- Mollow, Anna (2012): Is Sex Disability? Queer Theory and the Disability Drive. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 285–312.
- Niccolini, Alyssa D. (2014): Spicing Up the Curriculum. The Uses and Pleasures of Erotica Noir in the Urban Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 159–174.
- Ollis, Debbie (2013): Planning and delivering interventions to promote gender and sexuality. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 145–161.
- Ouer, Freedom (2014): It's Not How Regular Boys Are Supposed to Act. The Nonnormative Sexual Practices of Black Boys in All-Male Public Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 357–369.

- Pendleton Jiménez, Karleen (2014): *Off the Script. A Study of Techniques for Uncovering Gender-Bending Truths in the Classroom*. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 257–271.
- Prier, Darius D. (2014): *Schooling the Gendered Politics of Masculine Scripts in Black Popular Culture*. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 38–51.
- Rasmussen, Mary Louise (2014): *Pleasure/Desire, Sexularism, and Sexuality Education*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 153–169.
- Rivers, Ian (2013): *Cyberbullying and cyberaggression. Sexualised and gendered experiences explored*. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 19–44.
- Rivers, Ian; Duncan, Neil (2013): *Discourses of sexuality and gender considered*. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 162–168.
- Robinson, Kerry H. (2014): *Sexual harassment in schools. Issues of identity and power - Negotiating the complexities, contexts and contradictions of this everyday practice*. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 71–94.
- Robinson, Kerry H.; Davies, Cristyn; Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): *Conclusions: Rethinking School Violence. Implications for Theory, Policy and Practice*. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 184–195.
- Rofes, Eric E. (2012): *Bound and Gagged. Sexual Silences, Gender Conformity, and the Gay Male Teacher*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 105–121.
- Roth, Jillian R.; Robinson, Lea; O'Bryant, Camille; Griffin, Pat (2014): *3 to 1. Four Women Navigating the Intersections of Racism, Sexism, Homophobia, and Heterosexism in Intercollegiate Sport*. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 453–463.
- Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): *"The kid most likely". Naming, brutality and silence within and beyond school settings*. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 21–38.
- Blackman, Jerome S.; Dring, Kathleen (2016): *Sexual aggression against children. Pedophiles' and abusers' development, dynamics, treatability, and the law*. 1. Edition. New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Drobac, Jennifer Ann (2016): *Sexual exploitation of teenagers. Adolescent development, discrimination, and consent law*. Chicago, London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Elliott, Sinikka (2012): *Not my kid. What parents believe about the sex lives of their teenagers*. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press.
- Garcia, Lorena (2012): *Respect yourself, protect yourself. Latina girls and sexual identity*. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press (Intersections / [New York University Press]).
- Hasinoff, Amy Adele (2015): *Sexting panic. Rethinking criminalization, privacy, and consent*. Urbana: University of Illinois Press (Feminist media studies).
- Keenan, Marie (2013): *Child sexual abuse and the Catholic Church. Gender, power, and organizational culture*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Larremore, April (2016): *Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom*.
- Oliver, Kelly (2016): *Hunting Girls. Sexual Violence from The Hunger Games to Campus Rape*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Ozyegin, Gul (2015): *New desires, new selves. Sex, love, and piety among Turkish youth*. New York: New York University Press.
- Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2012): *Pervasive vulnerabilities. Sexual harassment in school*. New York: Peter Lang (Adolescent cultures, school & society, v. 54).

- Shariff, Shaheen (2015): Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise; Quinlivan, Kathleen (Hg.) (2014): The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education).
- Carpenter, Laura M.; DeLamater, John D. (Hg.) (2012): Sex for life. From virginity to Viagra, how sexuality changes throughout our lives. New York: New York University Press (Intersections).
- Carrigan Wooten, Sara; Mitchell, Roland W. (Hg.) (2016): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge.
- Fish, Julie; Karban, Kate (Hg.) (2015): Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work. Bristol: Policy Press.
- Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013): Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications. Hove: Psychology.
- Meiners, Erica R.; Quinn, Therese (Hg.) (2012): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367).
- Meyer, Elizabeth J.; Carlson, Dennis (Hg.) (2014): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5).
- Ozyegin, Gul (Hg.) (2016): Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures. London, New York: Routledge.
- Rivers, Ian (Hg.) (2013): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education).
- Saltmarsh, Sue (Hg.) (2014): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Alix, Stephanie; Cossette, Louise; Hebert, Martine; Cyr, Mireille; Frappier, Jean-Yves (2017): Posttraumatic Stress Disorder and Suicidal Ideation Among Sexually Abused Adolescent Girls. The Mediating Role of Shame. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (2), S. 158–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1280577.
- Allard, Troy; Rayment-McHugh, Sue; Adams, Dimity; Smallbone, Stephen; McKillop, Nadine (2015): Responding to youth sexual offending. A field-based practice model that “closes the gap” on sexual recidivism among Indigenous and non-Indigenous males. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (1), S. 82–94. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.1003107.
- Allbaugh, Lucy Jane; O'Dougherty Wright, Margaret; Atkins Seltmann, Larissa (2014): An exploratory study of domains of parenting concern among mothers who are childhood sexual abuse survivors. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (8), S. 885–899. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.960636.
- Allen, Louisa (2013): Boys as Sexy Bodies. In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 347–365. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13497205.
- Anderson, E.; McCormack, M. (2015): Cuddling and Spooning. Heteromascularity and Homosocial Tactility among Student-athletes. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (2), S. 214–230. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14523433.
- Babchishin, Kelly M.; Nunes, Kevin L.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Malcom, J. Renee (2015): Implicit sexual interest in children. Does separating gender influence discrimination when using the Implicit Association Test? In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 194–208. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836575.
- Bantjes, J.; Nieuwoudt, J. (2014): Masculinity and Mayhem. The Performance of Gender in a South African Boys' School. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (4), S. 376–395. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539964.
- Bauermeister, José A.; Johns, Michelle Marie; Sandfort, Theo G. M.; Eisenberg, Anna; Grossman, Arnold H.; D'Augelli, Anthony R. (2010): Relationship trajectories and psychological well-being among sexual minority youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1148–1163. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9557-y.
- Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Fava, Nicole M. (2014): What puts “At-Risk Girls” at risk? Sexual vulnerability and social inequality in the lives of girls in the child welfare system. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 116–125. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0142-5.
- Bengtsson, T. T. (2016): Performing Hypermasculinity. Experiences with Confined Young Offenders. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (4), S. 410–428. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15595083.
- Berglas, Nancy F.; Angulo-Olaiz, Francisca; Jerman, Petra; Desai, Mona; Constantine, Norman A. (2014): Engaging Youth Perspectives on Sexual Rights and Gender Equality in Intimate Relationships as a Foundation for Rights-

- Based Sexuality Education. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (4), S. 288–298. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0148-7.
- Bhana, D. (2016): 'Sex isn't better than love. Exploring South African Indian teenage male and female desires beyond danger. In: *Childhood* 23 (3), S. 362–377. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216642828.
- Bird, Elizabeth R.; Seehuus, Martin; Clifton, Jessica; Rellini, Alessandra H. (2014): Dissociation during sex and sexual arousal in women with and without a history of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (5), S. 953–964. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0191-0.
- Biswas, Bipasha; Vaughn, Michael G. (2011): Really troubled girls. Gender differences in risky sexual behavior and its correlates in a sample of juvenile offenders. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 33 (11), S. 2386–2391. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2011.08.010.
- Bos, Henny; Sandfort, Theo (2015): Gender Nonconformity, Sexual Orientation, and Dutch Adolescents' Relationship with Peers. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (5), S. 1269–1279. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0461-5.
- Brooks-Russell, Ashley; Foshee, Vangie A.; Ennett, Susan T. (2013): Predictors of latent trajectory classes of physical dating violence victimization. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 566–580. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9876-2.
- Bui, Thanh Cong; Diamond, Pamela M.; Markham, Christine; Ross, Michael W.; Nguyen-Le, Thanh-An; Tran, Ly Hai Thi (2010): Gender relations and sexual communication among female students in the Mekong River Delta of Vietnam. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (6), S. 591–601. DOI: 10.1080/13691050902968769.
- Busche, Mart (2013): A girl is no girl is a girl_: Girls-work after queer theory. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (1), S. 43–56.
- Buschman, Jos; Wilcox, Dan; Krapohl, Donald; Oelrich, Marty; Hackett, Simon (2010): Cybersex offender risk assessment. An explorative study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 197–209. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003690518.
- Carter, Rona; Williams, Sandra (2016): Self-perceptions of pubertal timing and patterns of peer group activities and dating behavior among heterosexual adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 47, S. 71–80. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.12.006.
- Casey, Erin A.; Beadnell, Blair (2010): The structure of male adolescent peer networks and risk for intimate partner violence perpetration: findings from a national sample. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 620–633. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9423-y.
- Castro, Ángel (2016): Sexual Behavior and Sexual Risks Among Spanish University Students. A Descriptive Study of Gender and Sexual Orientation. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 13 (1), S. 84–94. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-015-0210-0.
- Celik, Gonca Gul; Yolga Tahiroglu, Aysegul; Avci, Ayse; Cekin, Necmi; Evliyaoglu, Nurdan; Yoruldu, Belgin (2012): Sexual abuse in a classroom of ten male students. A group victimization. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (5), S. 543–552. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.694403.
- Choi, Hye Jeong; Ouytsel, Joris van; Temple, Jeff R. (2016): Association between sexting and sexual coercion among female adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 53, S. 164–168. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.10.005.
- Clements, Hannah; Dawson, David L.; das Nair, Roshan (2014): Female-perpetrated sexual abuse. A review of victim and professional perspectives. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 197–215. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.798690.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2013): Homophobic name-calling among secondary school students and its implications for mental health. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 363–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9823-2.
- Collins, Christi M.; O'Neill-Arana, Margarita R.; Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Ossege, Jennifer M. (2014): Catholicism and childhood sexual abuse. Women's coping and psychotherapy. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (5), S. 519–537. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.918071.
- Cree, Vivienne (2017): 'Khaki Fever' during the First World War. A Historical Case Study of Social Work's Approach towards Young Women, Sex and Moral Danger. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (7), S. 1839–1854. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcv103.

- Crichton, Joanna; Ibisomi, Latifat; Gyimah, Stephen Obeng (2012): Mother-daughter communication about sexual maturation, abstinence and unintended pregnancy. Experiences from an informal settlement in Nairobi, Kenya. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 21–30. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.06.008.
- Daddis, Christopher; Randolph, Danielle (2010): Dating and disclosure: Adolescent management of information regarding romantic involvement. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (2), S. 309–320. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.05.002.
- Dahlbäck, Elisabeth; Maimbolwa, Margaret; Yamba, C. Bawa; Kasonka, Lackson; Bergström, Staffan; Ransjö-Arvidson, Anna-Berit (2010): Pregnancy loss. Spontaneous and induced abortions among young women in Lusaka, Zambia. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 247–262. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903353383.
- Dank, Meredith; Lachman, Pamela; Zweig, Janine M.; Yahner, Jennifer (2014): Dating violence experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (5), S. 846–857. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9975-8.
- Das, Aniruddha; Otis, Nicholas (2016): Sexual Contact in Childhood, Revictimization, and Lifetime Sexual and Psychological Outcomes. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1117–1131.
- Dickenson, Janna A.; Huebner, David M. (2016): The Relationship Between Sexual Activity and Depressive Symptoms in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth: Effects of Gender and Family Support. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (3), S. 671–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0571-8.
- Epstein, Debbie; Kehily, Mary Jane; Renold, E. (2012): Culture, policy and the un/marked child. Fragments of the sexualisation debates. In: *Gender and Education* 24 (3), S. 249–254. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2012.670390.
- Fair, Brian (2011): Constructing Masculinity through Penetration Discourse. The Intersection of Misogyny and Homophobia in High School Wrestling. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 491–504. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10375936.
- Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2012): Young women's adolescent experiences of oral sex. Relation of age of initiation to sexual motivation, sexual coercion, and psychological functioning. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (5), S. 1191–1201. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.03.010.
- Ferguson, Christopher J.; Muñoz, Mónica E.; Garza, Adolfo; Galindo, Mariza (2014): Concurrent and prospective analyses of peer, television and social media influences on body dissatisfaction, eating disorder symptoms and life satisfaction in adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (1), S. 1–14. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9898-9.
- Fielder, Robyn L.; Walsh, Jennifer L.; Carey, Kate B.; Carey, Michael P. (2013): Predictors of sexual hookups: a theory-based, prospective study of first-year college women. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1425–1441. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0106-0.
- Finkelhor, David; Ji, Kai; Mikton, Christopher; Dunne, Michael (2013): Explaining lower rates of sexual abuse in China. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (10), S. 852–860.
- Fish, Jessica N.; Pasley, Kay (2015): Sexual (Minority) Trajectories, Mental Health, and Alcohol Use: A Longitudinal Study of Youth as They Transition to Adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (8), S. 1508–1527. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0280-6.
- Flanagan, Paul (2012): Ethical review and reflexivity in research of children's sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 535–544. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627731.
- Flannery, Dustin D.; Stephens, Clare L.; Thompson, Amy D. (2016): The Impact of High-Profile Sexual Abuse Cases in the Media on a Pediatric Emergency Department. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 627–635. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1187697.
- Fredlund, Cecilia; Svensson, Frida; Svedin, Carl Goran; Priebe, Gisela; Wadsby, Marie (2013): Adolescents' lifetime experience of selling sex. Development over five years. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (3), S. 312–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.743950.
- Frías, Sonia M.; Erviti, Joaquina (2014): Gendered experiences of sexual abuse of teenagers and children in Mexico. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (4), S. 776–787.
- Fromuth, Mary Ellen; Kelly, David B.; Brallier, Courtney; Williams, Matthew; Benson, Kate (2016): Effects of duration on perceptions of teacher sexual misconduct. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (2), S. 159–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1122692.

- Gakhal, Baldeesh Kaur; Brown, Sarah J. (2011): A comparison of the general public's, forensic professionals' and students' attitudes towards female sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 105–116. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.540678.
- Genna, Natacha M. de; Larkby, Cynthia; Cornelius, Marie D. (2011): Pubertal timing and early sexual intercourse in the offspring of teenage mothers. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (10), S. 1315–1328. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9609-3.
- Gerouki, Margarita (2010): The boy who was drawing princesses. Primary teachers' accounts of children's non-conforming behaviours. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 335–348. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515092.
- Gilbert, Jen (2015): Walking through the school: the erotics of research. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 111–115. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1094947.
- Goodkind, Sara; Schelbe, Lisa; Joseph, Andrea A.; Beers, Daphne E.; Pinsky, Stephanie L. (2013): Providing new opportunities or reinforcing old stereotypes? Perceptions and experiences of single-sex public education. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (8), S. 1174–1181. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.04.004.
- Govender, Kaymarlin (2011): The cool, the bad, the ugly, and the powerful. Identity struggles in schoolboy peer culture. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 887–901. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.586436.
- Grose, Rose Grace; Grabe, Shelly; Kohfeldt, Danielle (2014): Sexual Education, Gender Ideology, and Youth Sexual Empowerment. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), 742.753.
- Haggis, Jane; Mulholland, Monique (2013): Rethinking difference and sex education. From cultural inclusivity to normative diversity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (1), S. 57–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.824873.
- Hampshire, Kate; Porter, Gina; Mashiri, Mac; Maponya, Goodhope; Dube, Siphon (2011): Proposing love on the way to school. Mobility, sexuality and youth transitions in South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (2), S. 217–231. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.522255.
- Harris, Taylor; Rice, Eric; Rhoades, Harmony; Winetrobe, Hailey; Wenzel, Suzanne (2017): Gender Differences in the Path From Sexual Victimization to HIV Risk Behavior Among Homeless Youth. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 334–351. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1287146.
- Harrison, Lyn; Ollis, Debbie (2014): Stepping out of our comfort zones. Pre-service teachers' responses to a critical analysis of gender/power relations in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 318–331. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1023284.
- Haste, Polly (2013): Sex education and masculinity. The 'problem' of boys. In: *Gender and Education* 25 (4), S. 515–527. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2013.789830.
- Hatchard, Christine J.; Goodwin, Jamie L.; Siddall, Eryn; Muniz, Lauren (2017): Perceptions of Abusive Parenting Behaviors. A Preliminary Exploration Into the Underrecognition of Mother–Daughter Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (4), S. 428–441. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1300971.
- Hidalgo, Marco A.; Kuhns, Lisa M.; Kwon, Soyang; Mustanski, Brian; Garofalo, Robert (2015): The impact of childhood gender expression on childhood sexual abuse and psychopathology among young men who have sex with men. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 103–112.
- Hipwell, Alison E.; Stepp, Stephanie D.; Keenan, Kate; Chung, Tammy; Loeber, Rolf (2011): Brief report: Parsing the heterogeneity of adolescent girls' sexual behavior. Relationships to individual and interpersonal factors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (3), S. 589–592. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.03.002.
- Hirst, Julia (2013): 'It's got to be about enjoying yourself'. Young people, sexual pleasure, and sex and relationships education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 423–436. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.747433.
- Hooghe, Marc; Meeusen, Cecil (2012): Homophobia and the transition to adulthood: a three year panel study among Belgian late adolescents and young adults, 2008–2011. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (9), S. 1197–1207. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9786-3.
- Hovey, Angela; Stalker, Carol A.; Schachter, Candice L.; Teram, Eli; Lasiuk, Gerri (2011): Practical ways psychotherapy can support physical healthcare experiences for male survivors of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 37–57. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.539963.

- Huitema, Anneloes; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine (2016): Attitudes of Dutch citizens towards male victims of sexual coercion by a female perpetrator. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 308–322. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1159343.
- Huyge, Ellen; Maele, Dimitri van; Houtte, Mieke van (2014): Does students' machismo fit in school? Clarifying the implications of traditional gender role ideology for school belonging. In: *Gender and Education* 27 (1), S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2014.972921.
- Ingevaldson, Sara; Goulding, Anneli; Tidefors, Inga (2016): Experiences of intimate relationships in young men who sexually offended during adolescence. Interviews 10 years later. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 410–422. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1177125.
- Jackson, Sue; Weatherall, Ann (2010): The (Im)possibilities of Feminist School Based Sexuality Education. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 20 (2), S. 166–185.
- Jaffe, Anna E.; Cranston, Christopher C.; Shadlow, Joanna O. (2012): Parenting in females exposed to intimate partner violence and childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 684–700. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.726698.
- Johnson, Brooke (2010): A Few Good Boys. Masculinity at a Military-Style Charter School. In: *Men and Masculinities* 12 (5), S. 575–596. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X09342228.
- Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D.; Sanders, Stephanie A.; Dennis, Barbara; Reece, Michael (2014): Gender Differences in Heterosexual College Students' Conceptualizations and Indicators of Sexual Consent. Implications for Contemporary Sexual Assault Prevention Education. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (8), S. 904–916.
- Kehily, Mary Jane (2012): Contextualising the sexualisation of girls debate. Innocence, experience and young female sexuality. In: *Gender and Education* 24 (3), S. 255–268. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2012.670391.
- Kelly, Angela; Worth, Heather; Akuani, Frances; Kepa, Barbara; Kupul, Martha; Walizopa, Lucy et al. (2010): Gendered talk about sex, sexual relationships and HIV among young people in Papua New Guinea. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 221–232. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903181107.
- Kennett, Deborah J.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Schultz, Kristen E. (2011): Sexual resourcefulness and the impact of family, sex education, media and peers. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615624.
- Kingston, Drew A.; Graham, Franklyn J.; Knight, Raymond A. (2017): Relations Between Self-Reported Adverse Events in Childhood and Hypersexuality in Adult Male Sexual Offenders. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 707–720. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0873-5.
- Knoll, James (2010): Teacher sexual misconduct. Grooming patterns and female offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (4), S. 371–386. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.495047.
- Koo, Kelly H.; Stephens, Kari A.; Lindgren, Kristen P.; George, William H. (2012): Misogyny, acculturation, and ethnic identity: relation to rape-supportive attitudes in Asian American college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1005–1014. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9729-1.
- Koster, Shirley (2011): The self-managed heart. Teaching gender and doing emotional labour in a higher education institution. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 19 (1), S. 61–77. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2011.548988.
- Lacelle, Céline; Hébert, Martine; Lavoie, Francine; Vitaro, Frank; Tremblay, Richard E. (2012): Sexual health in women reporting a history of child sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (3), S. 247–259.
- Lamb, Sharon; Farmer, Kaelin M.; Kosterina, Elena; Lambe Sariñana, Susan; Plocha, Aleksandra; Randazzo, Renee (2016): What's sexy? Adolescent girls discuss confidence, danger, and media influence. In: *Gender and Education* 28 (4), S. 527–545. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1107528.
- Lambine, Mackenzie E. (2012): Unsafe in the Ivory Tower. The sexual victimization of college women. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (3), S. 375–376. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.711657.
- Langa, Malose (2016): The Value of Using a Psychodynamic Theory in Researching Black Masculinities of Adolescent Boys in Alexandra Township, South Africa. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (3), S. 260–288. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15586434.

- Lehrer, Jocelyn A.; Lehrer, Evelyn L.; Koss, Mary P. (2013): Unwanted sexual experiences in young men: evidence from a survey of university students in Chile. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (2), S. 213–223. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0004-x.
- Limmer, Mark (2010): Young men, masculinities and sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 349–358. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515093.
- Livingston, Jennifer A.; Testa, Maria; Windle, Michael; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2015): Sexual risk at first coitus. Does alcohol make a difference? In: *Journal of Adolescence* 43, S. 148–158. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.05.018.
- Löfgren-Mårtenson, Lotta (2012): "I Want to Do it Right!" A Pilot Study of Swedish Sex Education and Young People with Intellectual Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 209–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9239-z.
- Loftus, Jeni; Kelly, Brian C.; Mustillo, Sarah A. (2011): Depressive symptoms among adolescent girls in relationships with older partners: causes and lasting effects? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 800–813. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9589-3.
- Lopez, Silvia; Faro, Concepcio; Lopetegui, Lourdes; Pujol-Ribera, Enriqueta; Monteagudo, Monica; Avecilla-Palau, Angels et al. (2017): Child and Adolescent Sexual Abuse in Women Seeking Help for Sexual and Reproductive Mental Health Problems. Prevalence, Characteristics, and Disclosure. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 246–269. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1288186.
- Lopez, Vera; Kopak, Albert; Robillard, Alyssa; Gillmore, Mary Rogers; Holliday, Rhonda C.; Braithwaite, Ronald L. (2011): Pathways to sexual risk taking among female adolescent detainees. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (8), S. 945–957. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9623-5.
- Mahony, David (2010): Assessing sexual abuse/attack histories with bariatric surgery patients. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (4), S. 469–484. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.496713.
- Manninen, Sari; Huuki, Tuija; Sunnari, Vappu (2011): Earn Yo' Respect! Respect in the Status Struggle of Finnish School Boys. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (3), S. 335–357. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10369476.
- Marcell, Arik V.; Eftim, Sorina E.; Sonenstein, Freya L.; Pleck, Joseph H. (2011): Associations of Family and Peer Experiences with Masculinity Attitude Trajectories at the Individual and Group Level in Adolescent and Young Adult Males. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (5), S. 565–587. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X11409363.
- Martin, Karin A.; Verduzco Baker, Lynn; Torres, Jennifer; Luke, Katherine (2011): Privates, pee-pees, and coochies. Gender and genital labeling for/with young children. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (3), S. 420–430. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510384832.
- Martino, Wayne J.; Cumming-Potvin, Wendy (2015): Teaching about "Princess Boys" or Not. The Case of One Male Elementary School Teacher and the Polemics of Gender Expression and Embodiment. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (1), S. 79–99. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14551278.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa (2015): Prevalence of dating violence among sexual minority youth: variation across gender, sexual minority identity and gender of sexual partners. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 211–224. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0089-0.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa; Fromme, Kim (2016): Trajectories of dating violence. Differences by sexual minority status and gender. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 28–37. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.02.008.
- Maxwell, Louise; Scott, Graham (2014): A review of the role of radical feminist theories in the understanding of rape myth acceptance. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 40–54. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.773384.
- McCartan, Fiona Mairead; Law, Heather; Murphy, Maeve; Bailey, Susan (2011): Child and adolescent females who present with sexually abusive behaviours. A 10-year UK prevalence study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 4–14. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.488302.
- McLeod, David Axlyn (2015): Female offenders in child sexual abuse cases. A national picture. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (1), S. 97–114. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.978925.
- Milan, Stephanie; Wortel, Sanne (2015): Family obligation values as a protective and vulnerability factor among low-income adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (6), S. 1183–1193. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0206-8.

- Milhausen, Robin R.; Buchholz, Andrea C.; Opperman, Emily A.; Benson, Lindsay E. (2015): Relationships Between Body Image, Body Composition, Sexual Functioning, and Sexual Satisfaction Among Heterosexual Young Adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (6), S. 1621–1633. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0328-9.
- Miller, S. A. (2016): "How You Bully a Girl". Sexual Drama and the Negotiation of Gendered Sexuality in High School. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (5), S. 721–744. DOI: 10.1177/0891243216664723.
- Mora, Claudia; Monteiro, Simone (2010): Vulnerability to STIs/HIV. Sociability and the life trajectories of young women who have sex with women in Rio de Janeiro. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 115–124. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903180471.
- Muehlenhard, Charlene L.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D. (2016): The Complexities of Sexual Consent Among College Students. A Conceptual and Empirical Review. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (4-5), S. 1–31.
- Muhanguzi, Florence Kyoheirwe (2011): Gender and sexual vulnerability of young women in Africa. Experiences of young girls in secondary schools in Uganda. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 713–725. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.571290.
- Muise, Amy; Preyde, Michéle; Maitland, Scott B.; Milhausen, Robin R. (2010): Sexual identity and sexual well-being in female heterosexual university students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (4), S. 915–925. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9492-8.
- Myers, Kristen; Raymond, Laura (2010): Elementary School Girls and Heteronormativity. The Girl Project. In: *Gender & Society* 24 (2), S. 167–188. DOI: 10.1177/0891243209358579.
- Needham, Belinda L. (2012): Sexual attraction and trajectories of mental health and substance use during the transition from adolescence to adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 179–190. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9729-4.
- Newby, Katie; Wallace, Louise M.; Dunn, Orla; Brown, Katherine E. (2012): A survey of English teenagers' sexual experience and preferences for school-based sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 231–251. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615582.
- Niehaus, Ashley F.; Jackson, Joan; Davies, Stephanie (2010): Sexual self-schemas of female child sexual abuse survivors. Relationships with risky sexual behavior and sexual assault in adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (6), S. 1359–1374. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9600-9.
- Nielsen, Silja; Paasonen, Susanna; Spišák, Sanna (2015): 'Pervy role-play and such'. Girls' experiences of sexual messaging online. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 472–485.
- Norman, Moss E. (2011): Embodying the Double-Bind of Masculinity. Young Men and Discourses of Normalcy, Health, Heterosexuality, and Individualism. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 430–449. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X11409360.
- Novak, Jamie; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Partner Violence During Adolescence and Young Adulthood: Individual and Relationship Level Risk Factors. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (9), S. 1849–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0484-4.
- Nunes, Kevin L.; McPhail, Ian V.; Babchishin, Kelly M. (2012): Social anxiety and sexual offending against children. A cumulative meta-analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (3), S. 284–293. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.549243.
- O'Leary, Patrick J.; Gould, Nick (2010): Exploring Coping Factors amongst Men Who Were Sexually Abused in Childhood. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (8), S. 2669–2686.
- Oliver, Brian E.; Holmes, Laura (2015): Female Juvenile Sexual Offenders. Understanding Who They Are and Possible Steps That May Prevent Some Girls From Offending. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 698–715. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1058875.
- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Billen, Rhett M.; Conrad, Kathryn A.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Sex, commitment, and casual sex relationships among college men: a mixed-methods analysis. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 561–571. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0047-z.
- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Hooking up and penetrative hookups: correlates that differentiate college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 573–583. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-9907-9.

- Paechter, Carrie (2013): Girls and their bodies. Approaching a more emancipatory physical education. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (2), S. 261–277. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.712055.
- Parent, Sylvie; Bannon, Joëlle (2012): Sexual abuse in sport. What about boys? In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (2), S. 354–359. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2011.11.004.
- Parkhill, Michele R.; Pickett, Scott M. (2016): Difficulties in Emotion Regulation as a Mediator of the Relationship Between Child Sexual Abuse Victimization and Sexual Aggression Perpetration in Male College Students. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 674–685. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1205161.
- Pascoe, C. J. (2011): Resource and Risk. Youth Sexuality and New Media Use. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 5–17. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0042-5.
- Pavlakakis, D. (2014): Reputation and the Sexual Abuse of Boys. Changing Norms in Late-Nineteenth-Century Britain. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (3), S. 325–346. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539512.
- Peacock, Dean; Barker, Gary (2014): Working with Men and Boys to Prevent Gender-based Violence. Principles, Lessons Learned, and Ways Forward. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (5), S. 578–599. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14558240.
- Piccigallo, Jaqueline R.; Lilley, Terry G.; Miller, Susan L. (2012): "It's Cool to Care about Sexual Violence". Men's Experiences with Sexual Assault Prevention. In: *Men and Masculinities* 15 (5), S. 507–525. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X12458590.
- Pomerantz, S.; Raby, R.; Stefanik, A. (2013): Girls Run the World? Caught between Sexism and Postfeminism in School. In: *Gender & Society* 27 (2), S. 185–207. DOI: 10.1177/0891243212473199.
- Pradhan, Manas Ranjan; Ram, Usha (2010): Perceived gender role that shape youth sexual behaviour. Evidence from rural Orissa, India. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (4), S. 543–551. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.014.
- Preston, Marilyn J. (2015): 'They're just not mature right now': teachers' complicated perceptions of gender and anti-queer bullying. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 22–34. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1019665.
- Raine, Tina R.; Gard, Jennifer C.; Boyer, Cherrie B.; Haider, Sadia; Brown, Beth A.; Ramirez Hernandez, F. Antonio; Harper, Cynthia C. (2010): Contraceptive decision-making in sexual relationships. Young men's experiences, attitudes and values. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 373–386. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903524769.
- Rellini, Alessandra H.; Elinson, Samantha; Janssen, Erick; Meston, Cindy M. (2012): The effect of pre-existing affect on the sexual responses of women with and without a history of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (2), S. 329–339. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9772-y.
- Rellini, Alessandra H.; Meston, Cindy M. (2011): Sexual self-schemas, sexual dysfunction, and the sexual responses of women with a history of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (2), S. 351–362. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9694-0.
- Reyes, H. Luz McNaughton; Foshee, Vangie A.; Niolon, Phyllis Holditch; Reidy, Dennis E.; Hall, Jeffrey E. (2016): Gender Role Attitudes and Male Adolescent Dating Violence Perpetration: Normative Beliefs as Moderators. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 350–360. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0278-0.
- Rumble, Lauren; Mungate, Taizivei; Chigiji, Handrick; Salama, Peter; Nolan, Anthony; Sammon, Elayn; Muwoni, Leon (2015): Childhood sexual violence in Zimbabwe: evidence for the epidemic against girls. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 60–66. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.04.015.
- Russell, Brenda L.; Oswald, Debra L. (2016): When Sexism Cuts Both Ways. Predictors of Tolerance of Sexual Harassment of Men. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (5), S. 524–544. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15602745.
- Rysst, Mari (2010): 'I Am Only Ten Years Old'. Femininities, clothing-fashion codes and the intergenerational gap of interpretation of young girls' clothes. In: *Childhood* 17 (1), S. 76–93. DOI: 10.1177/0907568209351552.
- Schacht, Rebecca L.; George, William H.; Davis, Kelly Cue; Heiman, Julia R.; Norris, Jeanette; Stoner, Susan A.; Kajumulo, Kelly F. (2010): Sexual abuse history, alcohol intoxication, and women's sexual risk behavior. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (4), S. 898–906. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9544-0.
- Schnurr, Melissa P.; Lohman, Brenda J. (2013): The impact of collective efficacy on risks for adolescents' perpetration of dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 518–535. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9909-5.

- Senn, Charlene Y. (2011): An imperfect feminist journey. Reflections on the process to develop an effective sexual assault resistance programme for university women. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (1), S. 121–137. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510386094.
- Seto, Michael C. (2012): Is pedophilia a sexual orientation? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (1), S. 231–236. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9882-6.
- Seto, Michael C.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2015): Viewing child pornography: prevalence and correlates in a representative community sample of young Swedish men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 67–79. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0244-4.
- Shulman, Shmuel; Zlotnik, Aynat; Shachar-Shapira, Lital; Connolly, Jennifer; Bohr, Yvonne (2012): Adolescent daughters' romantic competence: the role of divorce, quality of parenting, and maternal romantic history. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 593–606. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9748-9.
- Slotboom, Anne-Marie; Hendriks, Jan; Verbruggen, Janna (2011): Contrasting adolescent female and male sexual aggression. A self-report study on prevalence and predictors of sexual aggression. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 15–33. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.544413.
- Smiler, Andrew P.; Frankel, Loren B. W.; Savin-Williams, Ritch C. (2011): From kissing to coitus? Sex-of-partner differences in the sexual milestone achievement of young men. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 727–735. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.08.009.
- Smith, Mark; Woodiwiss, Jo (2017): Sexuality, Innocence and Agency in Narratives of Childhood Sexual Abuse. Implications for Social Work. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2173–2189. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw160.
- Sommer, Marni (2010): Where the education system and women's bodies collide. The social and health impact of girls' experiences of menstruation and schooling in Tanzania. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (4), S. 521–529. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.03.008.
- Sommer, Marni; Likindikoki, Samuel; Kaaya, Sylvia (2015): "Bend a fish when the fish is not yet dry": adolescent boys' perceptions of sexual risk in Tanzania. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 583–595. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0406-z.
- Sorhaindo, Annik; Bonell, Chris; Fletcher, Adam; Jessiman, Patricia; Keogh, Peter; Mitchell, Kirstin (2016): Being targeted. Young women's experience of being identified for a teenage pregnancy prevention programme. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 181–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.03.013.
- Soylu, Nusret; Ayaz, Muhammed; Yüksel, Tuğb (2014): Early-married and sexually abused girls differ in their psychiatric outcomes. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (9), S. 1552–1559.
- Šribar, Renata (2013): Growing-up challenged and challenging. Gender and sexuality norms in referential research on 'internet risks' and in children. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (1), S. 129–145. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.748681.
- Stevens-Watkins, Danelle; Brown-Wright, Lynda; Tyler, Kenneth (2011): Brief report. The number of sexual partners and race-related stress in African American adolescents: preliminary findings. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 191–194. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.02.003.
- Stewart, Catherine Carolyn (2012): Beyond the call. Mothers of children with developmental disabilities responding to sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 701–727. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.722182.
- Stroebel, Sandra S.; O'Keefe, Stephen L.; Griffee, Karen; Kuo, Shih-Ya; Beard, Keith W.; Kommor, Martin J. (2013): Sister-sister incest. Data from an anonymous computerized survey. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (6), S. 695–719. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.811140.
- Strömwall, Leif A.; Alfredsson, Helen; Landström, Sara (2013): Rape victim and perpetrator blame and the Just World hypothesis. The influence of victim gender and age. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 207–217. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.683455.
- Stulhofer, Aleksandar; Busko, Vesna; Landripet, Ivan (2010): Pornography, sexual socialization, and satisfaction among young men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (1), S. 168–178. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9387-0.
- Thompson, Ashley E.; Byers, E. Sandra (2017): Heterosexual Young Adults' Interest, Attitudes, and Experiences Related to Mixed-Gender, Multi-Person Sex. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 813–822. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0699-1.

- Thrane, Lisa E.; Chen, Xiaojin (2012): Impact of running away on girls' pregnancy. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (2), S. 443–449. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.07.011.
- Towns, Alison J.; Scott, Hazel (2013): 'I couldn't even dress the way I wanted.' Young women talk of 'ownership' by boyfriends. An opportunity for the prevention of domestic violence? In: *Feminism & Psychology* 23 (4), S. 536–555. DOI: 10.1177/0959353513481955.
- Tsaliki, Liza (2015): Popular culture and moral panics about 'children at risk'. Revisiting the sexualisation-of-young-girls debate. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 500–514. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1022893.
- Updegraff, Kimberly A.; McHale, Susan M.; Zeiders, Katharine H.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J.; Perez-Brena, Norma J.; Wheeler, Lorey A.; Rodríguez De Jesús, Sue A. (2014): Mexican-American adolescents' gender role attitude development: the role of adolescents' gender and nativity and parents' gender role attitudes. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (12), S. 2041–2053. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0128-5.
- Vaillancourt-Morel, Marie-Pier; Godbout, Natacha; Labadie, Chloé; Runtz, Marsha; Lussier, Yvan; Sabourin, Stéphane (2015): Avoidant and compulsive sexual behaviors in male and female survivors of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 40, S. 48–59.
- van Oosten, Johanna M. F.; Peter, Jochen; Boot, Inge (2015): Exploring associations between exposure to sexy online self-presentations and adolescents' sexual attitudes and behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 1078–1091. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0194-8.
- Vandenbosch, Laura; Eggermont, Steven (2013): Sexualization of Adolescent Boys. In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 283–306. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13477866.
- Vannier, Sarah A.; O'Sullivan, Lucia F. (2012): Who gives and who gets: why, when, and with whom young people engage in oral sex. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 572–582. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9745-z.
- Vares, Tiina; Jackson, Sue (2015): Preteen girls, magazines, and the negotiation of young sexual femininity. In: *Gender and Education* 27 (6), S. 700–713. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1078453.
- Verhoef, Melissa; van den Eijnden, Regina J. J. M.; Koning, Ina M.; Vollebergh, Wilma A. M. (2014): Age at menarche and adolescent alcohol use. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1333–1345. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0075-6.
- Vries, Hein de; Eggers, Sander Matthijs; Jinabhai, Champak; Meyer-Weitz, Anna; Sathiparsad, Reshma; Taylor, Myra (2014): Adolescents' beliefs about forced sex in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (6), S. 1087–1095. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0280-8.
- Vrouenraets, Lieke Josephina Jeanne Johanna; Fredriks, A. Miranda; Hannema, Sabine E.; Cohen-Kettenis, Peggy T.; Vries, Martine C. de (2016): Perceptions of Sex, Gender, and Puberty Suppression: A Qualitative Analysis of Transgender Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (7), S. 1697–1703. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0764-9.
- Whittier, Nancy (2016): Where Are the Children? Theorizing the Missing Piece in Gendered Sexual Violence. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (1), S. 95–108. DOI: 10.1177/0891243215612412.
- Willis, Gwenda M.; Johnston, Lucy (2012): Planning helps. The impact of release planning on subsequent re-entry experiences of child sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 194–208. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.506576.
- Wong, Carolyn F.; Kipke, Michele D.; Weiss, George; McDavitt, Bryce (2010): The impact of recent stressful experiences on HIV-risk related behaviors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (3), S. 463–475. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.06.004.
- Zimmer-Gembeck, Melanie J.; Ducat, Wendy H.; Boislard-Pepin, Marie-Aude (2011): A prospective study of young females' sexual subjectivity: associations with age, sexual behavior, and dating. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 927–938. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9751-3.
- Zinzow, Heidi; Seth, Puja; Jackson, Joan; Niehaus, Ashley; Fitzgerald, Monica (2010): Abuse and parental characteristics, attributions of blame, and psychological adjustment in adult survivors of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (1), S. 79–98. DOI: 10.1080/10538710903485989.

1.4.2. LGBT

- Airton, Lee (2014): Hatred Haunting Hallways. Teacher Education and the Badness of Homophobia(s). In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 387–399.
- Anderson, Eric (2013): Masculinity and homophobia in high school and college sports. A personal journey from coach to researcher. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 120–131.
- Bailey, Lucy; Graves, Karen (2012): Introduction. Society Can Only Be as Free and Open as Its Schools. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 43–45.
- Betancourt, Gerardo (2015): A theoretical model for intervening in complex sexual behaviours. Sexual desires, pleasures and passion - La Pasi3n - of Spanish-speaking gay men in Canada. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 159–172.
- Blumenfeld, Warren J. (2012): "We're Here and We're Fabolous". Contemporary U.S.-American LGBT Youth Activism. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 73–83.
- Britzman, Deborah P. (2012): Queer Pedagogy and Its Strange Techniques. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 292–308.
- Bryan, Jennifer (2014): Tomboys, Sissies, and "That's So Gay". Exploring Gender and Sexuality Diversity in Early Childhood and Elementary Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 240–256.
- Bryan Meek, Jane (2012): "Being Queer Is the Luckiest Thing". Investigating a New Generation's Use of Queer within Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, and Queer Groups (LGBTQ) Student. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 187–198.
- Carlson, Dennis (2014): The Bully Curriculum. Gender, Sexualities, and the New Authoritarian Populism in Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 175–187.
- Carmody, Moira (2014): Young people, ethical sex and violence prevention. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 167–184.
- Carr, Nicola; Pinkerton, John (2015): Coming into view? The experiences of LGBT young people in the care system in Northern Ireland. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 99–112.
- Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2016): Heterosexist Discourses. How Feminist Theory Shaped Campus Sexual Violence Policy. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge, S. 33–52.
- Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2014): Critical Interventions. Addressing the Reality of LGBTQ Sexual Violence in Higher Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 426–438.
- Crowley, M. Sue (2014): Defining Themselves. LGBTQ Youth Online. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 90–109.
- Dankmeijer, Peter (2012): LGBT, to Be or Not to Be? Education about Sexual Preferences and Gender Identities Worldwide. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 254–269.
- Davies, Cristyn; McInnes, David (2014): Speaking violence. Homophobia and the production of injurious speech in schooling cultures. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 131–148.

- DeVita, James M.; Daniel Anders, Allison (2014): Multiple Targeted Identities. Intersectionality and the Lived Experiences of Black Gay Males. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 464–478.
- Elliott, Kathleen O. (2012): The Right Way to be Gay. How School Structures Sexual Inequality. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 158–166.
- Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): Bullying and sexual violence. Definition, prevalence, outcomes and moderators. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 31–44.
- Finkelstein, Sam; Mosqueda, Lucky; Birrueta, Adrian; Kitty, Eric (2012): Queer youth of color organizing for safe & affirming education. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 349–350.
- Ford, Jillian (2012): Introduction: Realidades realities, Palabras words, y and Estudios studies. LGBTQIQ Youth in Schools. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 169–171.
- Freitag, Mel B. (2014): Safety in Unity. One School's Story of Identity and Community. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 230–239.
- Gould, Deborah B. (2012): Education in the Streets. ACT UP, Emotion, and New Modes of Being. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 346–364.
- Ingrey, Jennifer C. (2014): The Heterotopic Washroom in School Space. Binary Gender Confirmed, or No Place of One's Own? In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 63–74.
- Jennings, Todd (2014): Is the Mere Mention Enough? Representation Across Five Different Venues of Educator Preparation. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 400–413.
- Karim, Shuchi (2012): Living sexualities: non-hetero female sexuality in urban middle-class Bangladesh. In: Anissa Hélie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance. London: Zed Books, S. 269–293.
- Kosciw, Joseph G.; Greytak, Emily A.; Bartkiewicz, Mark J. (2014): Failing Progress. Changes in School Climate for LGBT Youth Over Time. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 188–201.
- Lehtonen, Jukka (2012): Yogyakarta Principles. For the Rights of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender People. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 284.
- Leonardi, Bethy; Saenz, Lauren P. (2014): Conceptualizing Safety From the Inside Out. Heteronormative Spaces and Their Effects on Students' Sense of Self. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 202–216.
- Lewis, Mel Michelle (2012): Pedagogy and the Sista' Professor. Teaching Black Queer Feminist Studies through the Self. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 33–40.
- Linville, Darla (2012): Introduction. Schooling Students in Gender and Sexuality Expectations. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 125–128.
- Linville, Darla (2012): Virtual, Welcoming, Queer, School Community. An Interview with Dave Glick. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 167–168.

- Lugg, Catherine A. (2012): The Religious Right and Public Education. The Paranoid Politics of Homophobia. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 61–72.
- Martino, Wayne (2014): Masculinities, Gender Non-Conformity, and the Significance of Queer and Transgender Perspectives in Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 9–24.
- Matrim, Jair (2014): A Philosophy of Sexual Reciprocity for Secular Public Schools of Toronto. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 313–327.
- McCormack, Mark (2013): Mapping the boundaries of homophobic language in bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 91–104.
- McCoy, Sheltreese D. (2014): Some of Us Are Brave. A Review of the Research on the Experience of Black LGBT Professors in Colleges and Universities in the United States. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 439–452.
- Meyer, Elizabeth J. (2012): From Here to Queer. Mapping Sexualities in Education. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 9–17.
- Miller, sj; Gilligan, James R. (2014): Heteronormative Harassment. Queer Bullying and Gender-Non-Conforming Students. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 217–229.
- Niccolini, Alyssa D. (2014): Spicing Up the Curriculum. The Uses and Pleasures of Erotica Noir in the Urban Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 159–174.
- North, Connie E. (2012): Introduction: Bending the Terrain. Queer and Justice Issues Infiltrate the Education Map. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 5–8.
- Nunez, Isabel (2012): Introduction. Teaching as Whole Self. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 85–88.
- Ouer, Freedom (2014): It's Not How Regular Boys Are Supposed to Act. The Nonnormative Sexual Practices of Black Boys in All-Male Public Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 357–369.
- Pajor Ford, Carolyn (2012): White Trash. Manifesting the Bisexual. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 89–92.
- Pascoe, C. J. (2012): Becoming Mr. Cougar. Institutionalizing Heterosexuality and Homophobia at River High. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 145–157.
- Poole, Jay; Gause, C. P. (2012): Under Construction. Sexualities in Rural Spaces. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 242–253.
- Potter, V. Paul; Mereish, Ethan H.; DiGiovanni, Craig D.; Scheer, Jillian R. (2013): Homophobic bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 75–90.
- Pullen Sansfacon, Annie; Manning, Kimberley Ens (2015): Maximising research outcomes for trans children and their families in Canada inquiry. Using social action and other participatory methods of. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 223–236.

- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): "Butterflies Starting a Tornado". The Queer 'Not Yet' of New Zealand School-Based Queer Straight Alliance as a Utopic Site of Learning. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 272–283.
- Rajander, Silja; Sopath, Phal (2012): Drama Performances Address Stigma, Discrimination of MSM and HIV/AIDS Prevention. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 281–283.
- Rasmussen, Mary Louise (2014): Taking Homophobia's Measure. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 52–62.
- Rivers, Ian; Duncan, Neil (2013): Discourses of sexuality and gender considered. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 162–168.
- Robinson, Kerry H. (2014): Sexual harassment in schools. Issues of identity and power - Negotiating the complexities, contexts and contradictions of this everyday practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 71–94.
- Robles-Fernández, Ramón (2014): A GSA's Impact on Students' Beliefs and Attitudes Toward Civic and Political Participation, Civic Engagement, and Social Justice. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 284–297.
- Rofes, Eric E. (2012): Bound and Gagged. Sexual Silences, Gender Conformity, and the Gay Male Teacher. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 105–121.
- Roth, Jillian R.; Robinson, Lea; O'Bryant, Camille; Griffin, Pat (2014): 3 to 1. Four Women Navigating the Intersections of Racism, Sexism, Homophobia, and Heterosexism in Intercollegiate Sport. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 453–463.
- Saltzburg, Susan (2015): Pedagogy for unpacking heterosexist and cisgender bias in social work education in the United States. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 205–222.
- Schmidt, Sandra J. (2012): Let Me in! The Impact of the Discourse of Impossibility on Research and Curricular (Re)form. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 199–214.
- Schneider, Margaret; Travers, Robb; St. John, Alex; Munro, Lauren; Klein, Kate (2013): The role of Gay-Straight Alliances in addressing bullying in schools. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 132–144.
- Singh, Anneliese A.; Jackson, Ken (2012): Queer and Transgender Youth. Education and Liberation in Our Schools. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 175–186.
- Ullman, Jacqueline; McGraw, Kelli (2014): Troubling Silences and Taboo Texts. Constructing Safer and More Positive School Climates for Same-Sex-Attracted High School Students in Australia. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 298–312.
- Walker Woolley, Susan (2014): (Im)perceptible Silences. Hearing LGBTQ Silences and Voices in School. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 328–341.
- Whitlock, Reta Ugena (2014): LGBT Families and Southern Schools. Thinking About People, Place, and Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 75–89.
- Winter, Elizabeth A.; Elze, Diane E.; Saltzburg, Susan; Rosenwald, Mitchell (2015): Social services for LGBT young people in the United States. Are we there yet? In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 113–130.

- Gilbert, Jen (2014): *Sexuality in School: The Limits of Education*: University of Minnesota Press.
- Larremore, April (2016): *Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom*.
- Murray, Olivia J. (2014): *Queer Inclusion in Teacher Education. Bridging Theory, Research, and Practice*. London: Taylor & Francis Ltd.
- Ozyegin, Gul (2015): *New desires, new selves. Sex, love, and piety among Turkish youth*. New York: New York University Press.
- Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise; Quinlivan, Kathleen (Hg.) (2014): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education).
- Fish, Julie; Karban, Kate (Hg.) (2015): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press.
- Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013): *Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications*. Hove: Psychology.
- Meiners, Erica R.; Quinn, Therese (Hg.) (2012): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367).
- Meyer, Elizabeth J.; Carlson, Dennis (Hg.) (2014): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5).
- Rivers, Ian (Hg.) (2013): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education).
- Saltmarsh, Sue (Hg.) (2014): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Alessi, Edward J.; Kahn, Sarilee; Chatterji, Sangeeta (2016): 'The darkest times of my life'. Recollections of child abuse among forced migrants persecuted because of their sexual orientation and gender identity. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 51, S. 93–105.
- Allen, Louisa (2011): 'Undoing' the self. Should heterosexual teachers 'come out' in the university classroom? In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 19 (1), S. 79–95. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2011.548990.
- Arrington-Sanders, Renata; Harper, Gary W.; Morgan, Anthony; Ogunbajo, Adedotun; Trent, Maria; Fortenberry, J. Dennis (2015): The role of sexually explicit material in the sexual development of same-sex-attracted Black adolescent males. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 597–608. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0416-x.
- Bauermeister, José A. (2014): How statewide LGB policies go from "under our skin" to "into our hearts": fatherhood aspirations and psychological well-being among emerging adult sexual minority men. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1295–1305. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0059-6.
- Bauermeister, José A.; Johns, Michelle Marie; Sandfort, Theo G. M.; Eisenberg, Anna; Grossman, Arnold H.; D'Augelli, Anthony R. (2010): Relationship trajectories and psychological well-being among sexual minority youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1148–1163. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9557-y.
- Bos, Henny; van Beusekom, Gabriël; Sandfort, Theo (2014): Sexual attraction and psychological adjustment in Dutch adolescents: coping style as a mediator. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1579–1588. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0308-0.
- Brakefield, Tiffany A.; Mednick, Sara C.; Wilson, Helen W.; Neve, Jan-Emmanuel de; Christakis, Nicholas A.; Fowler, James H. (2014): Same-sex sexual attraction does not spread in adolescent social networks. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 335–344. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0142-9.
- Castro, Ángel (2016): Sexual Behavior and Sexual Risks Among Spanish University Students. A Descriptive Study of Gender and Sexual Orientation. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 13 (1), S. 84–94. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-015-0210-0.
- Clark, Caroline T. (2010): Preparing LGBTQ-allies and combating homophobia in a U.S. teacher education program. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (3), S. 704–713. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.10.006.
- Cocker, Christine; Hafford-Letchfield, Trish (2010): Out and Proud? Social Work's Relationship with Lesbian and Gay Equality. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (6), S. 1996–2008.

- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2013): Homophobic name-calling among secondary school students and its implications for mental health. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 363–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9823-2.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2012): Intergroup contact, attitudes toward homosexuality, and the role of acceptance of gender non-conformity in young adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 899–907. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.12.010.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G.M. (2015): Understanding teachers' responses to enactments of sexual and gender stigma at school. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 48, S. 34–43. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.02.002.
- Cox, Nele; Vanden Berghe, Wim; Dewaele, Alexis; Vincke, John (2010): Acculturation strategies and mental health in gay, lesbian, and bisexual youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1199–1210. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9435-7.
- Craig, Shelley L.; Dentato, Michael P.; Messinger, Lori; McInroy, Lauren B. (2016): Educational Determinants of Readiness to Practise with LGBTQ Clients. Social Work Students Speak Out. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (1), S. 115–134. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu107.
- Dank, Meredith; Lachman, Pamela; Zweig, Janine M.; Yahner, Jennifer (2014): Dating violence experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (5), S. 846–857. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9975-8.
- DePalma, Renée (2013): Choosing to lose our gender expertise. Queering sex/gender in school settings. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (1), S. 1–15. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634145.
- DePalma, Renée; Atkinson, Elizabeth (2010): The nature of institutional heteronormativity in primary schools and practice-based responses. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (8), S. 1669–1676. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.06.018.
- Dermody, Sarah S.; Marshal, Michael P.; Cheong, Jeewon; Burton, Chad; Hughes, Tonda; Aranda, Frances; Friedman, Mark S. (2014): Longitudinal disparities of hazardous drinking between sexual minority and heterosexual individuals from adolescence to young adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (1), S. 30–39. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9905-9.
- Dessel, Adrienne B.; Kulick, Alex; Wernick, Laura J.; Sullivan, Daniel (2017): The importance of teacher support. Differential impacts by gender and sexuality. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 136–144. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.002.
- Dickenson, Janna A.; Huebner, David M. (2016): The Relationship Between Sexual Activity and Depressive Symptoms in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth: Effects of Gender and Family Support. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (3), S. 671–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0571-8.
- Doty, Nathan Daniel; Willoughby, Brian L. B.; Lindahl, Kristin M.; Malik, Neena M. (2010): Sexuality related social support among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1134–1147. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9566-x.
- Endo, Hidehiro; Reece-Miller, Paul Chamness; Santavicca, Nicholas (2010): Surviving in the trenches. A narrative inquiry into queer teachers' experiences and identity. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (4), S. 1023–1030. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.10.045.
- Evrpidou, Dimitris; Çavuşoğlu, Çise (2015): English Language Teachers' Attitudes Towards the Incorporation of Gay- and Lesbian-Related Topics in the Classroom. The Case of Greek Cypriot EFL Teachers. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 12 (1), S. 70–80. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0176-3.
- Farr, Rachel H.; Crain, Emily E.; Oakley, M. K.; Cashen, Krystal K.; Garber, Karin J. (2016): Microaggressions, Feelings of Difference, and Resilience Among Adopted Children with Sexual Minority Parents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (1), S. 85–104. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0353-6.
- Ferfolja, Tania (2013): Sexual diversity, discrimination and 'homosexuality policy' in New South Wales' government schools. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (2), S. 159–171. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.697858.
- Ferfolja, Tania (2010): Lesbian teachers, harassment and the workplace. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (3), S. 408–414. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.05.007.

- Fish, Jessica N.; Pasley, Kay (2015): Sexual (Minority) Trajectories, Mental Health, and Alcohol Use: A Longitudinal Study of Youth as They Transition to Adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (8), S. 1508–1527. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0280-6.
- Formby, Eleanor (2011): Sex and relationships education, sexual health, and lesbian, gay and bisexual sexual cultures. Views from young people. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 255–266. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590078.
- Garland-Levett, Sarah (2016): Exploring discursive barriers to sexual health and social justice in the New Zealand sexuality education curriculum. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 17 (2), S. 121–134. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1233396.
- Gartrell, Nanette K.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Goldberg, Naomi G. (2011): Adolescents of the U.S. National Longitudinal Lesbian Family Study: sexual orientation, sexual behavior, and sexual risk exposure. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (6), S. 1199–1209. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9692-2.
- Gattis, Maurice N.; Woodford, Michael R.; Han, Yoonsun (2014): Discrimination and depressive symptoms among sexual minority youth: is gay-affirming religious affiliation a protective factor? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1589–1599. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0342-y.
- Gerouki, Margarita (2010): The boy who was drawing princesses. Primary teachers' accounts of children's non-conforming behaviours. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 335–348. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515092.
- Gilbert, Jen (2015): Walking through the school: the erotics of research. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 111–115. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1094947.
- Goldbach, Jeremy T.; Gibbs, Jeremy J. (2017): A developmentally informed adaptation of minority stress for sexual minority adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 36–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.007.
- Gowen, L. Kris; Wings-Yanez, Nichole (2014): Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, and Questioning Youths' Perspectives of Inclusive School-Based Sexuality Education. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), S. 788–800.
- Gray, Emily M. (2013): Coming out as a lesbian, gay or bisexual teacher. Negotiating private and professional worlds. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (6), S. 702–714. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.807789.
- Greteman, Adam J. (2013): Fashioning a bareback pedagogy. Towards a theory of risky (sex) education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S20–S31. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.760154.
- Hafford-Letchfield, Trish; Cocker, Christine; Ryan, Peter; Melonowska, Justyna (2017): Rights through Alliances. Findings from a European Project Tackling Homophobic and Transphobic Bullying in Schools through the Engagement of Families and Young People. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2338–2356. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw104.
- Haggis, Jane; Mulholland, Monique (2013): Rethinking difference and sex education. From cultural inclusivity to normative diversity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (1), S. 57–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.824873.
- Hardie, Ann (2011): Lesbian teachers and students. Issues and dilemmas of being 'out' in primary school. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–10. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615595.
- Hicks, Stephen; Jeyasingham, Dharman (2017): Social Work, Queer Theory and After. A Genealogy of Sexuality Theory in Neo-Liberal Times. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2357–2373. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw103.
- Hidalgo, Marco A.; Kuhns, Lisa M.; Kwon, Soyang; Mustanski, Brian; Garofalo, Robert (2015): The impact of childhood gender expression on childhood sexual abuse and psychopathology among young men who have sex with men. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 103–112.
- Hooghe, Marc (2011): The impact of gendered friendship patterns on the prevalence of homophobia among Belgian late adolescents. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (3), S. 543–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9635-y.
- Hooghe, Marc; Meeusen, Cecil (2012): Homophobia and the transition to adulthood: a three year panel study among Belgian late adolescents and young adults, 2008–2011. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (9), S. 1197–1207. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9786-3.

- Johnston, Lisa G.; Mon, Myo Myo; Steinhaus, Mara; Sass, Justine (2017): Correlates of Forced Sex Among Young Men Who Have Sex With Men in Yangon and Monywa, Myanmar. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 1001–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0761-z.
- Jones, Tiffany Mary; Hillier, Lynne (2012): Sexuality education school policy for Australian GLBTIQ students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (4), S. 437–454. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.677211.
- Katz-Wise, Sabra L.; Rosario, Margaret; Calzo, Jerel P.; Scherer, Emily A.; Sarda, Vishnudas; Austin, S. Bryn (2017): Endorsement and Timing of Sexual Orientation Developmental Milestones Among Sexual Minority Young Adults in the Growing Up Today Study. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (2), S. 172–185. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1170757.
- Kjaran, Jón; Kristinsdóttir, Guðrún (2014): Queering the environment and caring for the self. Icelandic LGBT students' experience of the upper secondary school. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 23 (1), S. 1–20. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2014.910250.
- La Roi, Chaïm; Kretschmer, Tina; Dijkstra, Jan Kornelis; Veenstra, René; Oldehinkel, Albertine J. (2016): Disparities in Depressive Symptoms Between Heterosexual and Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth in a Dutch Cohort: The TRAILS Study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (3), S. 440–456. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0403-0.
- Larsson, Håkan; Quennerstedt, Mikael; Öhman, Marie (2014): Heterotopias in physical education. Towards a queer pedagogy? In: *Gender and Education* 26 (2), S. 135–150. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2014.888403.
- Lea, Toby; Wit, John de; Reynolds, Robert (2014): Minority stress in lesbian, gay, and bisexual young adults in Australia: associations with psychological distress, suicidality, and substance use. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1571–1578. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0266-6.
- Löfgren-Mårtenson, Lotta (2012): "I Want to Do it Right!" A Pilot Study of Swedish Sex Education and Young People with Intellectual Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 209–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9239-z.
- Lourie, Michael A.; Needham, Belinda L. (2017): Sexual Orientation Discordance and Young Adult Mental Health. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 943–954. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0553-8.
- Malins, Pamela (2016): How inclusive is "inclusive education" in the Ontario elementary classroom? Teachers talk about addressing diverse gender and sexual identities. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 54, S. 128–138. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.11.004.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa (2015): Prevalence of dating violence among sexual minority youth: variation across gender, sexual minority identity and gender of sexual partners. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 211–224. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0089-0.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa; Crosnoe, Robert (2012): Sexual minority status, peer harassment, and adolescent depression. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 1001–1011. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.02.006.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa; Fromme, Kim (2016): Trajectories of dating violence. Differences by sexual minority status and gender. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 28–37. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.02.008.
- McCann, Edward; Lee, Regina; Brown, Michael (2016): The experiences and support needs of people with intellectual disabilities who identify as LGBT: A review of the literature. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 57, S. 39–53. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2016.06.013.
- Miller, S. A. (2016): "How You Bully a Girl". Sexual Drama and the Negotiation of Gendered Sexuality in High School. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (5), S. 721–744. DOI: 10.1177/0891243216664723.
- Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Ybarra, Michele L.; Korchmaros, Josephine D. (2014): Sexual harassment among adolescents of different sexual orientations and gender identities. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (2), S. 280–295.
- Mora, Claudia; Monteiro, Simone (2010): Vulnerability to STIs/HIV. Sociability and the life trajectories of young women who have sex with women in Rio de Janeiro. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 115–124. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903180471.
- Mul, Nick J.; McKenzie, Cameron; Khan, Maryam (2017): Recognition and Legitimation of Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity (SOGI) at the UN. A Critical Systemic Analysis. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2245–2262. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw139.

- Murphy, Meghan (2015): How organisational culture influences teachers' support of openly gay, lesbian and bisexual students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 263–275.
- Mustanski, Brian; Greene, George J.; Ryan, Daniel; Whitton, Sarah W. (2015): Feasibility, Acceptability, and Initial Efficacy of an Online Sexual Health Promotion Program for LGBT Youth. The Queer Sex Ed Intervention. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 52 (2), S. 220–230.
- Mustanski, Brian; Liu, Richard T. (2013): A longitudinal study of predictors of suicide attempts among lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (3), S. 437–448. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0013-9.
- Neary, Aoife; Gray, Breda; O'Sullivan, Mary (2016): A queer politics of emotion. Reimagining sexualities and schooling. In: *Gender and Education* 28 (2), S. 250–265. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1114074.
- Needham, Belinda L. (2012): Sexual attraction and trajectories of mental health and substance use during the transition from adolescence to adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 179–190. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9729-4.
- Nixon, David (2010): Discrimination, performance and recuperation. How teachers and pupils challenge and recover discourses of sexualities in schools. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (2), S. 145–151. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.05.003.
- Noonan, A.; Taylor Gomez, Miriam (2011): Who's Missing? Awareness of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender People with Intellectual Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (2), S. 175–180. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9175-3.
- Nothdurfter, Urban; Nagy, Andrea (2017): Few and Far from Radical? LGBT-Related Contributions in European Social Work Journal Publishing. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2227–2244. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw140.
- Oidtman, Jessica; Sherman, Susan G.; Morgan, Anthony; German, Danielle; Arrington-Sanders, Renata (2017): Satisfaction and Condomless Anal Sex at Sexual Debut and Sexual Risk Among Young Black Same-Sex Attracted Men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 947–959. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0831-2.
- Ollis, Debbie (2010): 'I haven't changed bigots but ...'. Reflections on the impact of teacher professional learning in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 217–230. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666523.
- Ott, Miles Q.; Corliss, Heather L.; Wypij, David; Rosario, Margaret; Austin, S. Bryn (2011): Stability and change in self-reported sexual orientation identity in young people: application of mobility metrics. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (3), S. 519–532. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9691-3.
- Pearson, Jennifer; Wilkinson, Lindsey (2013): Family relationships and adolescent well-being: are families equally protective for same-sex attracted youth? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 376–393. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9865-5.
- Pingel, Emily Sweetnam; Thomas, Laura; Harmell, Chelsea; Bauermeister, Jose (2013): Creating comprehensive, youth centered, culturally appropriate sex education: What do young gay, bisexual and questioning men want? In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 10 (4). DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0134-5.
- Porta, Carolyn M.; Gower, Amy L.; Mehus, Christopher J.; Yu, Xiaohui; Saewyc, Elizabeth M.; Eisenberg, Marla E. (2017): "Kicked out". LGBTQ youths' bathroom experiences and preferences. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 107–112. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.005.
- Preston, Marilyn J. (2015): 'They're just not mature right now': teachers' complicated perceptions of gender and anti-queer bullying. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 22–34. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1019665.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2013): The methodological im/possibilities of researching sexuality education in schools. Working queer conundrums. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S56–S69. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.796288.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2012): Popular culture as emotional provocation. The material enactment of queer pedagogies in a high school classroom. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 511–522. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627728.
- Rieger, Gerulf; Savin-Williams, Ritch C. (2012): Gender nonconformity, sexual orientation, and psychological well-being. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (3), S. 611–621. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9738-0.

- Riggs, Angela D.; Rosenthal, Amy R.; Smith-Bonahue, Tina (2011): The impact of a combined cognitive–affective intervention on pre-service teachers’ attitudes, knowledge, and anticipated professional behaviors regarding homosexuality and gay and lesbian issues. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 27 (1), S. 201–209. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.08.002.
- Rosario, Margaret; Schrimshaw, Eric W.; Hunter, Joyce (2012): Homelessness among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth: implications for subsequent internalizing and externalizing symptoms. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 544–560. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9681-3.
- Rudoe, Naomi (2010): Lesbian teachers’ identity, power and the public/private boundary. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (1), S. 23–36. DOI: 10.1080/14681810903491347.
- Sanjakdar, Fida (2013): Educating for sexual difference? Muslim teachers’ conversations about homosexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (1), S. 16–29. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634154.
- Sauntson, Helen (2013): Sexual diversity and illocutionary silencing in the English National Curriculum. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 395–408. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.745809.
- Savin-Williams, Ritch C.; Joyner, Kara (2014): The dubious assessment of gay, lesbian, and bisexual adolescents of add health. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (3), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0219-5.
- Schmidt, Sandra J. (2015): A queer arrangement of school. Using spatiality to understand inequity. In: *Journal of Curriculum Studies* 47 (2), S. 253–273.
- Schmidt, Sandra J.; Chang, Shih-pei; Carolan-Silva, Aliah; Lockhart, John; Anagnostopoulos, Dorothea (2012): Recognition, responsibility, and risk. Pre-service teachers’ framing and reframing of lesbian, gay, and bisexual social justice issues. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 28 (8), S. 1175–1184. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2012.07.002.
- Seelman, Kristie L.; Forge, Nicholas; Walls, N. Eugene; Bridges, Nadine (2015): School engagement among LGBTQ high school students. The roles of safe adults and gay–straight alliance characteristics. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 57, S. 19–29. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.07.021.
- Shannon, Barrie (2016): Comprehensive for who? Neoliberal directives in Australian ‘comprehensive’ sexuality education and the erasure of GLBTIQ identity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (6), S. 573–585. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1141090.
- Shelton, Stephanie Anne; Barnes, Meghan E. (2016): “Racism just isn’t an issue anymore”. Preservice teachers’ resistances to the intersections of sexuality and race. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 55, S. 165–174. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2016.01.008.
- Smiler, Andrew P.; Frankel, Loren B. W.; Savin-Williams, Ritch C. (2011): From kissing to coitus? Sex-of-partner differences in the sexual milestone achievement of young men. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 727–735. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.08.009.
- Snapp, Shannon D.; McGuire, Jenifer K.; Sinclair, Katarina O.; Gabrion, Karlee; Russell, Stephen T. (2015): LGBTQ-inclusive curricula. Why supportive curricula matter. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (6), S. 580–596. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1042573.
- Sterzing, Paul R.; Ratliff, G. Allen; Gartner, Rachel E.; McGeough, Briana L.; Johnson, Kelly C. (2017): Social Ecological Correlates of Polyvictimization among a National Sample of Transgender, Genderqueer, and Cisgender Sexual Minority Adolescents. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 67, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.02.017.
- Svendsen, Stine Helena Bang (2012): Elusive sex acts. Pleasure and politics in Norwegian sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (4), S. 397–410. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.677209.
- Swann, Gregory; Minshew, Reese; Newcomb, Michael E.; Mustanski, Brian (2016): Validation of the Sexual Orientation Microaggression Inventory in Two Diverse Samples of LGBTQ Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (6), S. 1289–1298. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0718-2.
- Toomey, Russell B.; McGuire, Jenifer K.; Russell, Stephen T. (2012): Heteronormativity, school climates, and perceived safety for gender nonconforming peers. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 187–196. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.03.001.
- Vrouenraets, Lieke Josephina Jeanne Johanna; Fredriks, A. Miranda; Hannema, Sabine E.; Cohen-Kettenis, Peggy T.; Vries, Martine C. de (2016): Perceptions of Sex, Gender, and Puberty Suppression: A Qualitative Analysis of Transgender Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (7), S. 1697–1703. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0764-9.

- Wells, Elizabeth A.; Asakura, Kenta; Hoppe, Marilyn J.; Balsam, Kimberly F.; Morrison, Diane M.; Beadnell, Blair (2012): Social Services for Sexual Minority Youth: Preferences for What, Where, and How Services are Delivered. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 36 (2), S. 312–320. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.11.011.
- Wernick, Laura J.; Kulick, Alex; Inglehart, Marita H. (2013): Factors predicting student intervention when witnessing anti-LGBTQ harassment. The influence of peers, teachers, and climate. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (2), S. 296–301. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.11.003.
- Wilkinson, Verity J.; Theodore, Kate; Raczka, Roman (2015): 'As Normal as Possible'. Sexual Identity Development in People with Intellectual Disabilities Transitioning to Adulthood. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 33 (1), S. 93–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9356-6.
- Willis, Paul; Ward, Nicki; Fish, Julie (2011): Searching for LGBT Carers. Mapping a Research Agenda in Social Work and Social Care. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 41 (7), S. 1304–1320.
- Wilson, Bianca; Kastanis, Angeliki A. (2015): Sexual and gender minority disproportionality and disparities in child welfare. A population-based study. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 58, S. 11–17. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.08.016.
- Wilson, Helen W.; Spatz Widom, Cathy (2010): Does Physical Abuse, Sexual Abuse, or Neglect in Childhood Increase the Likelihood of Same-sex Sexual Relationships and Cohabitation? A Prospective 30-year Follow-up. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (1), S. 63–74.
- Wong, Carolyn F.; Kipke, Michele D.; Weiss, George; McDavitt, Bryce (2010): The impact of recent stressful experiences on HIV-risk related behaviors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (3), S. 463–475. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.06.004.
- Xu, Yin; Zheng, Yong (2015): Prevalence of Childhood Sexual Abuse among Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual People. A Meta-Analysis. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 315–331. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006746.
- Ybarra, Michele L.; Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Palmer, Neal A.; Reisner, Sari L. (2015): Online social support as a buffer against online and offline peer and sexual victimization among U.S. LGBT and non-LGBT youth. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 39, S. 123–136.

1.4.3. Schicht

- Bauwens, Joke; Paus-Hasebrink, Ingrid; Ponte, Cristina; Dürager, Andrea (2012): Understanding digital inequality. The interplay between parental socialisation and children's development. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 257–272.
- Chapman, Amy; Buchanan, Rachel (2014): FYI... Virtual space has a context. Towards an alternative frame for understanding cyberbullying. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 56–71.
- Niccolini, Alyssa D. (2014): Spicing Up the Curriculum. The Uses and Pleasures of Erotica Noir in the Urban Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 159–174.
- Pajor Ford, Carolyn (2012): White Trash. Manifesting the Bisexual. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 89–92.
- Robinson, Kerry H. (2014): Sexual harassment in schools. Issues of identity and power - Negotiating the complexities, contexts and contradictions of this everyday practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 71–94.
- Elliott, Sinikka (2012): *Not my kid. What parents believe about the sex lives of their teenagers*. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press.
- Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014): *Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Nelson, Sarah (2016): *Tackling child sexual abuse. Radical approaches to prevention, protection and support*. Bristol: Policy Press.

- Fish, Julie; Karban, Kate (Hg.) (2015): Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work. Bristol: Policy Press.
- Meiners, Erica R.; Quinn, Therese (Hg.) (2012): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367).
- Meyer, Elizabeth J.; Carlson, Dennis (Hg.) (2014): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5).
- Saltmarsh, Sue (Hg.) (2014): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Abbott, Keeley; Ellis, Sonja J.; Abbott, Rachel (2016): "We've got a lack of family values". An examination of how teachers formulate and justify their approach to teaching sex and relationships education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (6), S. 678–691. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1169398.
- Baratvand, Mahmood; Soodani, Mansour; Zarei, Eghbal; Asadollahi, Abdollah (2013): Sexual Abuse and Drug Abuse Among Homeless Children in Ahvaz, Iran. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (6), S. 408–418. DOI: 10.1002/car.2263.
- Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Fava, Nicole M. (2014): What puts "At-Risk Girls" at risk? Sexual vulnerability and social inequality in the lives of girls in the child welfare system. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 116–125. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0142-5.
- Beerthuisen, Marinus G. C. J.; Brugman, Daniel (2012): Sexually abusive youths' moral reasoning on sex. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 125–135. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.519126.
- Berglas, Nancy F.; Angulo-Olaiz, Francisca; Jerman, Petra; Desai, Mona; Constantine, Norman A. (2014): Engaging Youth Perspectives on Sexual Rights and Gender Equality in Intimate Relationships as a Foundation for Rights-Based Sexuality Education. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (4), S. 288–298. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0148-7.
- Biswas, Bipasha; Vaughn, Michael G. (2011): Really troubled girls. Gender differences in risky sexual behavior and its correlates in a sample of juvenile offenders. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 33 (11), S. 2386–2391. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2011.08.010.
- Boustani, Maya M.; Frazier, Stacy L.; Lesperance, Nephthalie (2017): Sexual health programming for vulnerable youth. Improving knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 375–383. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2017.01.013.
- Bragg, Sara; Buckingham, David; Russell, Rachel; Willett, Rebekah (2011): Too much, too soon? Children, 'sexualization' and consumer culture. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 279–292. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590085.
- Brown, Graham; Sorenson, Anne; Hildebrand, Janina (2012): How they got it and how they wanted it. Marginalised young people's perspective on their experiences of sexual health education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 599–612. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634141.
- Chang, Ling-Yin; Foshee, Vangie A.; Reyes, Heathe Luz McNaughton; Ennett, Susan T.; Halpern, Carolyn T. (2015): Direct and indirect effects of neighborhood characteristics on the perpetration of dating violence across adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 727–744. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0190-z.
- Crandall, AliceAnn; Magnusson, Brianna M.; Novilla, M. Lelinneth B.; Novilla, Lynneth Kirsten B.; Dyer, W. Justin (2017): Family Financial Stress and Adolescent Sexual Risk-Taking: The Role of Self-Regulation. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 45–62. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0543-x.
- Fitzpatrick, Kevin M.; Dulin, Akilah; Piko, Bettina (2010): Bullying and depressive symptomatology among low-income, African-American youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 634–645. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9426-8.
- Froyum, Carissa M. (2010): Making 'good girls'. Sexual agency in the sexuality education of low-income black girls. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 59–72. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903272583.
- Goodrum, Nada M.; Armistead, Lisa P.; Tully, Erin C.; Cook, Sarah L.; Skinner, Donald (2017): Parenting and youth sexual risk in context. The role of community factors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 57, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.013.

- Haggis, Jane; Mulholland, Monique (2013): Rethinking difference and sex education. From cultural inclusivity to normative diversity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (1), S. 57–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.824873.
- Harris, Taylor; Rice, Eric; Rhoades, Harmony; Winetrobe, Hailey; Wenzel, Suzanne (2017): Gender Differences in the Path From Sexual Victimization to HIV Risk Behavior Among Homeless Youth. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 334–351. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1287146.
- Heerde, Jessica A.; Scholes-Balog, Kirsty E.; Hemphill, Sheryl A. (2015): Associations between youth homelessness, sexual offenses, sexual victimization, and sexual risk behaviors: a systematic literature review. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 181–212. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0375-2.
- Kaltiala-Heino, Riittakerttu; Fröjd, Sari; Marttunen, Mauri (2016): Sexual harassment victimization in adolescence. Associations with family background. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 56, S. 11–19.
- Langa, Malose (2016): The Value of Using a Psychodynamic Theory in Researching Black Masculinities of Adolescent Boys in Alexandra Township, South Africa. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (3), S. 260–288. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15586434.
- Looze, Margaretha de; Harakeh, Zeena; van Dorselaer, Saskia A. F. M.; Raaijmakers, Quinten A. W.; Vollebergh, Wilma A. M.; ter Bogt, Tom F. M. (2012): Explaining educational differences in adolescent substance use and early sexual debut. The role of parents and peers. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 1035–1044. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.02.009.
- Lyons, Heidi; Manning, Wendy; Giordano, Peggy; Longmore, Monica (2013): Predictors of heterosexual casual sex among young adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 585–593. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0051-3.
- McMichael, Celia; Gifford, Sandra (2010): Narratives of sexual health risk and protection amongst young people from refugee backgrounds in Melbourne, Australia. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 263–277. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903359265.
- McMillan, Karen; Worth, Heather (2011): The impact of socio-cultural context on young people's condom use. Evidence from two Pacific Island countries. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (3), S. 313–326. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.529945.
- Meek, Rosie (2011): The possible selves of young fathers in prison. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (5), S. 941–949. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.12.005.
- Milan, Stephanie; Wortel, Sanne (2015): Family obligation values as a protective and vulnerability factor among low-income adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (6), S. 1183–1193. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0206-8.
- Munoz-Laboy, Miguel; Murray, Laura R.; Wittlin, Natalie; Wilson, Patrick A.; Terto, Veriano; Parker, Richard (2011): Divine targets. Youth at the centre of Catholic and Pentecostal responses to HIV and AIDS in Brazil. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 657–668. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.565519.
- Pascoe, C. J. (2011): Resource and Risk. Youth Sexuality and New Media Use. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 5–17. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0042-5.
- Pradhan, Manas Ranjan; Ram, Usha (2010): Perceived gender role that shape youth sexual behaviour. Evidence from rural Orissa, India. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (4), S. 543–551. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.014.
- Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2011): Race, class, and emerging sexuality. Teacher perceptions and sexual harassment in schools. In: *Gender and Education* 23 (7), S. 799–810. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2010.536143.
- Raine, Tina R.; Gard, Jennifer C.; Boyer, Cherrie B.; Haider, Sadia; Brown, Beth A.; Ramirez Hernandez, F. Antonio; Harper, Cynthia C. (2010): Contraceptive decision-making in sexual relationships. Young men's experiences, attitudes and values. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 373–386. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903524769.
- Sanberk, Ismail; Emen, Meltem; Kabakci, Duygu (2017): An Investigation of Socially Advantaged and Disadvantaged Turkish Mothers' Views About Training on Preventing Children From Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 288–307. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1292338.
- Schnurr, Melissa P.; Lohman, Brenda J. (2013): The impact of collective efficacy on risks for adolescents' perpetration of dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 518–535. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9909-5.

Sorhaindo, Annik; Bonell, Chris; Fletcher, Adam; Jessiman, Patricia; Keogh, Peter; Mitchell, Kirstin (2016): Being targeted. Young women's experience of being identified for a teenage pregnancy prevention programme. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 181–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.03.013.

Thrane, Lisa E.; Chen, Xiaojin (2012): Impact of running away on girls' pregnancy. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (2), S. 443–449. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.07.011.

van Ryzin, Mark J.; Johnson, Amber B.; Leve, Leslie D.; Kim, Hyoun K. (2011): The number of sexual partners and health-risking sexual behavior: prediction from high school entry to high school exit. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 939–949. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9649-5.

Whittier, Nancy (2016): Where Are the Children? Theorizing the Missing Piece in Gendered Sexual Violence. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (1), S. 95–108. DOI: 10.1177/0891243215612412.

Wilson, Bianca; Kastanis, Angeliki A. (2015): Sexual and gender minority disproportionality and disparities in child welfare. A population-based study. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 58, S. 11–17. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2015.08.016.

1.4.4. Ethnizität

Betancourt, Gerardo (2015): A theoretical model for intervening in complex sexual behaviours. Sexual desires, pleasures and passion - La Pasi3n - of Spanish-speaking gay men in Canada. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 159–172.

Bongardt, Daphne van de (2012): Teaching sexuality and relationships education in multicultural classrooms in the Netherlands. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 417–418.

Castillo, Victoria A. (2016): Introduction to “In Conversation on Female Genital Cutting”: A Pedagogical Perspective. In: Gul Ozyegin (Hg.): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge, S. 146–149.

Chapman, Amy; Buchanan, Rachel (2014): FYI... Virtual space has a context. Towards an alternative frame for understanding cyberbullying. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 56–71.

DeVita, James M.; Daniel Anders, Allison (2014): Multiple Targeted Identities. Intersectionality and the Lived Experiences of Black Gay Males. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 464–478.

Espiritu, Yen Le (2012): U.S. Colonialism, Migration, and Sexualities. The Filipino American Case. In: Laura M. Carpenter und John D. DeLamater (Hg.): *Sex for life. From virginity to Viagra, how sexuality changes throughout our lives*. New York: New York University Press (Intersections), S. 163–179.

Finkelstein, Sam; Mosqueda, Lucky; Birrueta, Adrian; Kitty, Eric (2012): Queer youth of color organizing for safe & affirming education. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 349–350.

Helie, Anissa (2012): Introduction. Policing gender, sexuality and 'Muslimness'. In: Anissa H3lie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books, S. 1–14.

Karim, Shuchi (2012): Living sexualities: non-hetero female sexuality in urban middle-class Bangladesh. In: Anissa H3lie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books, S. 269–293.

Lewis, Mel Michelle (2012): Pedagogy and the Sista' Professor. Teaching Black Queer Feminist Studies through the Self. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 33–40.

Malmstr3m, Maria Frederika (2016): The Continuous Making of Pure Womanhood among Muslim Women in Cairo. Cooking, Depilating, and Circumcising. In: Gul Ozyegin (Hg.): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge, S. 127–145.

McCoy, Sheltreese D. (2014): Some of Us Are Brave. A Review of the Research on the Experience of Black LGBT Professors in Colleges and Universities in the United States. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.):

- Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 439–452.
- McCready, Lance T. (2014): The African Dance Program. "Where is the Love?". In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), 342–356.
- Niccolini, Alyssa D. (2014): Spicing Up the Curriculum. The Uses and Pleasures of Erotica Noir in the Urban Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 159–174.
- Ouer, Freedom (2014): It's Not How Regular Boys Are Supposed to Act. The Nonnormative Sexual Practices of Black Boys in All-Male Public Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 357–369.
- Prier, Darius D. (2014): Schooling the Gendered Politics of Masculine Scripts in Black Popular Culture. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 38–51.
- Robinson, Kerry H. (2014): Sexual harassment in schools. Issues of identity and power - Negotiating the complexities, contexts and contradictions of this everyday practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 71–94.
- Roth, Jillian R.; Robinson, Lea; O'Bryant, Camille; Griffin, Pat (2014): 3 to 1. Four Women Navigating the Intersections of Racism, Sexism, Homophobia, and Heterosexism in Intercollegiate Sport. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 453–463.
- Thigpen, Jeffrey W. (2012): Childhood Sexuality. Exploring Culture as Context. In: Laura M. Carpenter und John D. DeLamater (Hg.): Sex for life. From virginity to Viagra, how sexuality changes throughout our lives. New York: New York University Press (Intersections), S. 45–69.
- Whitlock, Reta Ugena (2014): LGBT Families and Southern Schools. Thinking About People, Place, and Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 75–89.
- Drobac, Jennifer Ann (2016): Sexual exploitation of teenagers. Adolescent development, discrimination, and consent law. Chicago, London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Elliott, Sinikka (2012): Not my kid. What parents believe about the sex lives of their teenagers. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press.
- Garcia, Lorena (2012): Respect yourself, protect yourself. Latina girls and sexual identity. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press (Intersections / [New York University Press]).
- Ozyegin, Gul (2015): New desires, new selves. Sex, love, and piety among Turkish youth. New York: New York University Press.
- Sanjakdar, Fida (2012): Living west, facing east. The deconstruction of Muslim youth's sexual identities. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints, 364).
- Carpenter, Laura M.; DeLamater, John D. (Hg.) (2012): Sex for life. From virginity to Viagra, how sexuality changes throughout our lives. New York: New York University Press (Intersections).
- Fish, Julie; Karban, Kate (Hg.) (2015): Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work. Bristol: Policy Press.
- Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013): Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications. Hove: Psychology.
- Hélie, Anissa; Hoodfar, Homa (Hg.) (2012): Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance. London: Zed Books.
- Meiners, Erica R.; Quinn, Therese (Hg.) (2012): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367).
- Meyer, Elizabeth J.; Carlson, Dennis (Hg.) (2014): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5).

- Ozyegin, Gul (Hg.) (2016): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Saltmarsh, Sue (Hg.) (2014): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Alessi, Edward J.; Kahn, Sarilee; Chatterji, Sangeeta (2016): 'The darkest times of my life'. Recollections of child abuse among forced migrants persecuted because of their sexual orientation and gender identity. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 51, S. 93–105.
- Allard, Troy; Rayment-McHugh, Sue; Adams, Dimity; Smallbone, Stephen; McKillop, Nadine (2015): Responding to youth sexual offending. A field-based practice model that "closes the gap" on sexual recidivism among Indigenous and non-Indigenous males. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (1), S. 82–94. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.1003107.
- Anderson, Gwendolyn D. (2016): The Continuum of Disclosure. Exploring Factors Predicting Tentative Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations During Forensic Interviews and the Implications for Practice, Policy, and Future Research. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 382–402. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153559.
- Arrington-Sanders, Renata; Harper, Gary W.; Morgan, Anthony; Ogunbajo, Adedotun; Trent, Maria; Fortenberry, J. Dennis (2015): The role of sexually explicit material in the sexual development of same-sex-attracted Black adolescent males. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 597–608. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0416-x.
- Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Fava, Nicole M. (2014): What puts "At-Risk Girls" at risk? Sexual vulnerability and social inequality in the lives of girls in the child welfare system. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 116–125. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0142-5.
- Berglas, Nancy F.; Angulo-Olaiz, Francisca; Jerman, Petra; Desai, Mona; Constantine, Norman A. (2014): Engaging Youth Perspectives on Sexual Rights and Gender Equality in Intimate Relationships as a Foundation for Rights-Based Sexuality Education. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (4), S. 288–298. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0148-7.
- Bhana, D. (2016): 'Sex isn't better than love. Exploring South African Indian teenage male and female desires beyond danger. In: *Childhood* 23 (3), S. 362–377. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216642828.
- Bhana, Deevia; Pattman, Rob (2011): Girls want money, boys want virgins. The materiality of love amongst South African township youth in the context of HIV and AIDS. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 961–972. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.576770.
- Carlson, Daniel L.; McNulty, Thomas L.; Bellair, Paul E.; Watts, Stephen (2014): Neighborhoods and racial/ethnic disparities in adolescent sexual risk behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (9), S. 1536–1549. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0052-0.
- Diarsvitri, Wienta; Utomo, Iwu Dwisetyani; Neeman, Teresa; Oktavian, Antonius (2011): Beyond sexual desire and curiosity. Sexuality among senior high school students in Papua and West Papua Provinces (Indonesia) and implications for HIV prevention. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (9), S. 1047–1060. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.599862.
- Espinosa-Hernandez, Graciela; Vasilenko, Sara A.; McPherson, Jenna L.; Gutierrez, Estefania; Rodriguez, Andrea (2017): Brief report. The role of three dimensions of sexual well-being in adolescents' life satisfaction. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 61–65. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.009.
- Finkelhor, David; Ji, Kai; Mikton, Christopher; Dunne, Michael (2013): Explaining lower rates of sexual abuse in China. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (10), S. 852–860.
- Fitzpatrick, Kevin M.; Dulin, Akilah; Piko, Bettina (2010): Bullying and depressive symptomatology among low-income, African-American youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 634–645. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9426-8.
- Froyum, Carissa M. (2010): Making 'good girls'. Sexual agency in the sexuality education of low-income black girls. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 59–72. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903272583.
- Garland-Levett, Sarah (2016): Exploring discursive barriers to sexual health and social justice in the New Zealand sexuality education curriculum. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 17 (2), S. 121–134. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1233396.
- Gilliam, Melissa; Brindis, Claire D. (2011): Virtual Sex Ed. Youth, Race, Sex, and New Media. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 1–4. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0036-3.

- Goodkind, Sara; Schelbe, Lisa; Joseph, Andrea A.; Beers, Daphne E.; Pinsky, Stephanie L. (2013): Providing new opportunities or reinforcing old stereotypes? Perceptions and experiences of single-sex public education. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (8), S. 1174–1181. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2013.04.004.
- Goodrum, Nada M.; Armistead, Lisa P.; Tully, Erin C.; Cook, Sarah L.; Skinner, Donald (2017): Parenting and youth sexual risk in context. The role of community factors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 57, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.013.
- Graham, Laurie M.; Lanier, Paul; Johnson-Motoyama, Michelle (2016): National profile of Latino/Latina children reported to the child welfare system for sexual abuse. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 66, S. 18–27. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2016.04.008.
- Haboush, Karen L.; Alyan, Hala (2013): "Who can you tell?" Features of Arab culture that influence conceptualization and treatment of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 499–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800935.
- Haggis, Jane; Mulholland, Monique (2013): Rethinking difference and sex education. From cultural inclusivity to normative diversity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (1), S. 57–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.824873.
- Huang, Yu-Te; Souleymanov, Rusty (2016): Rethinking Epistemological Debates and Transnationalism of Sexuality between the West and Taiwan. Implications for Social Workers. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (1), S. 98–114. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu067.
- James, Adilia E. E. (2010): Too Early to Talk About Sex? Issues in Creating Culturally Relevant Sexuality Education for Preadolescent Black Girls in the United States. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (2), S. 128–141. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0012-3.
- Johnson, Brooke (2010): A Few Good Boys. Masculinity at a Military-Style Charter School. In: *Men and Masculinities* 12 (5), S. 575–596. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X09342228.
- Kenny, Maureen C. (2010): Child sexual abuse education with ethnically diverse families. A preliminary analysis. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 32 (7), S. 981–989. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2010.03.025.
- Killoren, Sarah E.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; Christopher, F. Scott (2011): Family and cultural correlates of Mexican-origin youths' sexual intentions. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (6), S. 707–718. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9587-5.
- Killoren, Sarah E.; Zeiders, Katharine H.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J. (2016): The Sociocultural Context of Mexican-Origin Pregnant Adolescents' Attitudes Toward Teen Pregnancy and Links to Future Outcomes. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 887–899. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0387-9.
- Koo, Kelly H.; Stephens, Kari A.; Lindgren, Kristen P.; George, William H. (2012): Misogyny, acculturation, and ethnic identity: relation to rape-supportive attitudes in Asian American college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1005–1014. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9729-1.
- Langa, Malose (2016): The Value of Using a Psychodynamic Theory in Researching Black Masculinities of Adolescent Boys in Alexandra Township, South Africa. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (3), S. 260–288. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15586434.
- Liotta, Lindsay; Springer, Craig; Misurell, Justin R.; Block-Lerner, Jennifer; Brandwein, David (2015): Group treatment for child sexual abuse. Treatment referral and therapeutic outcomes. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 217–237. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006747.
- McMichael, Celia; Gifford, Sandra (2010): Narratives of sexual health risk and protection amongst young people from refugee backgrounds in Melbourne, Australia. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 263–277. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903359265.
- McMillan, Karen; Worth, Heather (2011): The impact of socio-cultural context on young people's condom use. Evidence from two Pacific Island countries. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (3), S. 313–326. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.529945.
- Miller, S. A. (2016): "How You Bully a Girl". Sexual Drama and the Negotiation of Gendered Sexuality in High School. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (5), S. 721–744. DOI: 10.1177/0891243216664723.
- Moosmann, Danyel A. V.; Roosa, Mark W. (2015): Exploring Mexican American adolescent romantic relationship profiles and adjustment. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 43, S. 181–192. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.06.004.

- Muhanguzi, Florence Kyoheirwe (2011): Gender and sexual vulnerability of young women in Africa. Experiences of young girls in secondary schools in Uganda. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 713–725. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.571290.
- Munoz-Laboy, Miguel; Murray, Laura R.; Wittlin, Natalie; Wilson, Patrick A.; Terto, Veriano; Parker, Richard (2011): Divine targets. Youth at the centre of Catholic and Pentecostal responses to HIV and AIDS in Brazil. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 657–668. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.565519.
- Murry, Velma McBride; Berkel, Cady; Chen, Yi-Fu; Brody, Gene H.; Gibbons, Frederick X.; Gerrard, Meg (2011): Intervention induced changes on parenting practices, youth self-pride and sexual norms to reduce HIV-related behaviors among rural African American youths. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (9), S. 1147–1163. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9642-x.
- Mustanski, Brian; Liu, Richard T. (2013): A longitudinal study of predictors of suicide attempts among lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (3), S. 437–448. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0013-9.
- Newby, Katie; Wallace, Louise M.; Dunn, Orla; Brown, Katherine E. (2012): A survey of English teenagers' sexual experience and preferences for school-based sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 231–251. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615582.
- O'Hara, Ross E.; Cooper, M. Lynne (2015): Bidirectional associations between alcohol use and sexual risk-taking behavior from adolescence into young adulthood. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (4), S. 857–871. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0510-8.
- Oidtman, Jessica; Sherman, Susan G.; Morgan, Anthony; German, Danielle; Arrington-Sanders, Renata (2017): Satisfaction and Condomless Anal Sex at Sexual Debut and Sexual Risk Among Young Black Same-Sex Attracted Men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 947–959. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0831-2.
- Orpinas, Pamela; Hsieh, Hsien-Lin; Song, Xiao; Holland, Kristin; Nahapetyan, Lusine (2013): Trajectories of physical dating violence from middle to high school: association with relationship quality and acceptability of aggression. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 551–565. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9881-5.
- Pascoe, C. J. (2011): Resource and Risk. Youth Sexuality and New Media Use. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 5–17. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0042-5.
- Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2011): Race, class, and emerging sexuality. Teacher perceptions and sexual harassment in schools. In: *Gender and Education* 23 (7), S. 799–810. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2010.536143.
- Raine, Tina R.; Gard, Jennifer C.; Boyer, Cherrie B.; Haider, Sadia; Brown, Beth A.; Ramirez Hernandez, F. Antonio; Harper, Cynthia C. (2010): Contraceptive decision-making in sexual relationships. Young men's experiences, attitudes and values. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 373–386. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903524769.
- Sabina, Chiara; Cuevas, Carlos A.; Cotignola-Pickens, Heather M. (2016): Longitudinal dating violence victimization among Latino teens: Rates, risk factors, and cultural influences. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 47, S. 5–15. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.11.003.
- Schnurr, Melissa P.; Lohman, Brenda J. (2013): The impact of collective efficacy on risks for adolescents' perpetration of dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 518–535. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9909-5.
- Shelton, Stephanie Anne; Barnes, Meghan E. (2016): "Racism just isn't an issue anymore". Preservice teachers' resistances to the intersections of sexuality and race. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 55, S. 165–174. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2016.01.008.
- Shepard Paynea, Jennifer; Galvan, Frank H.; Williams, John K.; Prusinskie, Missy; Zhang, Muyu; Wyatt, Gail E.; Myers, Hector F. (2014): Impact of childhood sexual abuse on the emotions and behaviours of adult men from three ethnic groups in the USA. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 16 (3), S. 231–245.
- Sorhaindo, Annik; Bonell, Chris; Fletcher, Adam; Jessiman, Patricia; Keogh, Peter; Mitchell, Kirstin (2016): Being targeted. Young women's experience of being identified for a teenage pregnancy prevention programme. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 181–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.03.013.
- Stevens-Watkins, Danelle; Brown-Wright, Lynda; Tyler, Kenneth (2011): Brief report. The number of sexual partners and race-related stress in African American adolescents: preliminary findings. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 191–194. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.02.003.

Swann, Gregory; Minshew, Reese; Newcomb, Michael E.; Mustanski, Brian (2016): Validation of the Sexual Orientation Microaggression Inventory in Two Diverse Samples of LGBTQ Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (6), S. 1289–1298. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0718-2.

Updegraff, Kimberly A.; McHale, Susan M.; Zeiders, Katharine H.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J.; Perez-Brena, Norma J.; Wheeler, Lorey A.; Rodríguez De Jesús, Sue A. (2014): Mexican-American adolescents' gender role attitude development: the role of adolescents' gender and nativity and parents' gender role attitudes. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (12), S. 2041–2053. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0128-5.

Velezmoro, Rodrigo; Negy, Charles; Livia, Jose (2012): Online sexual activity: cross-national comparison between United States and Peruvian college students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1015–1025. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9862-x.

Venable, Victoria M.; Guada, Joseph (2014): Culturally competent practice with African American juvenile sex offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (3), S. 229–246. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.888122.

Wheeler, Lorey A.; Killoren, Sarah E.; Whiteman, Shawn D.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; McHale, Susan M.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J. (2016): Romantic Relationship Experiences from Late Adolescence to Young Adulthood: The Role of Older Siblings in Mexican-Origin Families. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 900–915. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0392-z.

Whittier, Nancy (2016): Where Are the Children? Theorizing the Missing Piece in Gendered Sexual Violence. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (1), S. 95–108. DOI: 10.1177/0891243215612412.

Williams, Lela Rankin; Hickie, Kristine E. (2011): "He cheated on me, I cheated on him back". Mexican American and White adolescents' perceptions of cheating in romantic relationships. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (5), S. 1005–1016. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.11.007.

1.4.5. Religion

Burke, Kevin (2014): Impossible Women. Saints, Sinner, and the Gendered Mythology in a Catholic School. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 25–37.

Castillo, Victoria A. (2016): Introduction to "In Conversation on Female Genital Cutting": A Pedagogical Perspective. In: Gul Ozyegin (Hg.): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge, S. 146–149.

Helie, Anissa (2012): Introduction. Policing gender, sexuality and 'Muslimness'. In: Anissa Hélie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books, S. 1–14.

Karim, Shuchi (2012): Living sexualities: non-hetero female sexuality in urban middle-class Bangladesh. In: Anissa Hélie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books, S. 269–293.

Lugg, Catherine A. (2012): The Religious Right and Public Education. The Paranoid Politics of Homophobia. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 61–72.

Malmström, Maria Frederika (2016): The Continuous Making of Pure Womanhood among Muslim Women in Cairo. Cooking, Depilating, and Circumcising. In: Gul Ozyegin (Hg.): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge, S. 127–145.

Mir-Hosseini, Ziba (2012): Sexuality and inequality: the marriage contract and Muslim legal tradition. In: Anissa Hélie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books, S. 124–150.

Sanjakdar, Fida (2014): Sacred Pleasure. Exploring Dimensions of Sexual Pleasure and Desire from an Islamic Perspective. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 95–114.

Keenan, Marie (2013): *Child sexual abuse and the Catholic Church. Gender, power, and organizational culture*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.

Ozyegin, Gul (2015): *New desires, new selves. Sex, love, and piety among Turkish youth*. New York: New York University Press.

- Sanjakdar, Fida (2012): *Living west, facing east. The deconstruction of Muslim youth's sexual identities*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints, 364).
- Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise; Quinlivan, Kathleen (Hg.) (2014): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education).
- Fish, Julie; Karban, Kate (Hg.) (2015): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press.
- Hélie, Anissa; Hoodfar, Homa (Hg.) (2012): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books.
- Meiners, Erica R.; Quinn, Therese (Hg.) (2012): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367).
- Meyer, Elizabeth J.; Carlson, Dennis (Hg.) (2014): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5).
- Ozyegin, Gul (Hg.) (2016): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge.
- Burchardt, Marian (2011): Challenging Pentecostal moralism. Erotic geographies, religion and sexual practices among township youth in Cape Town. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 669–683. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.566356.
- Collins, Christi M.; O'Neill-Arana, Margarita R.; Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Ossege, Jennifer M. (2014): Catholicism and childhood sexual abuse. Women's coping and psychotherapy. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (5), S. 519–537. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.918071.
- D'Alton, Paul; Guilfoyle, Michael; Randall, Patrick (2013): Roman Catholic Clergy who have sexually abused children: Their perceptions of their developmental experience. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 698–702.
- Eriksson, Elisabet; Lindmark, Gunilla; Axemo, Pia; Haddad, Beverley; Ahlberg, Beth Maina (2010): Ambivalence, silence and gender differences in church leaders' HIV-prevention messages to young people in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 103–114. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903141192.
- Haboush, Karen L.; Alyan, Hala (2013): "Who can you tell?" Features of Arab culture that influence conceptualization and treatment of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 499–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800935.
- Haggis, Jane; Mulholland, Monique (2013): Rethinking difference and sex education. From cultural inclusivity to normative diversity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (1), S. 57–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.824873.
- Rassenhofer, Miriam; Zimmer, Andreas; Spröber, Nina; Fegert, Jörg M. (2015): Child sexual abuse in the Roman Catholic Church in Germany: Comparison of victim-impact data collected through church-sponsored and government-sponsored programs. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 40, S. 60–67.
- Sanjakdar, Fida (2013): Educating for sexual difference? Muslim teachers' conversations about homosexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (1), S. 16–29. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634154.
- Tabatabaie, Alireza (2014): Childhood and adolescent sexuality, Islam, and problematics of sex education. A call for re-examination. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 276–288. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1005836.
- Tomaszewska, Paulina; Krahé, Barbara (2016): Attitudes towards sexual coercion by Polish high school students. Links with risky sexual scripts, pornography use, and religiosity. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 291–307. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1195892.

1.4.6. Behinderungen

- Desjardins, Michel (2012): The Sexualized Body of the Child. Parents and the Politics of "Voluntary" Sterilization of People Labeled Intellectually Disabled. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 69–88.
- Duncan, Neil (2013): Disability, sexuality and bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 105–119.

- Mollow, Anna (2012): Is Sex Disability? Queer Theory and the Disability Drive. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 285–312.
- Serlin, David (2012): Touching Histories: Personality, Disability, and Sex in the 1930s. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 145–165.
- Shuttleworth, Russell (2012): Bridging Theory and Experience: A Critical-Interpretative Ethnography of Sexuality and Disability. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 54–69.
- Siebers, Tobin (2012): A Sexual Culture for Disabled People. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 37–54.
- McRuer, Robert; Mollow, Anna (Hg.) (2012): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press.
- Asscher, Jessica J.; Put, Claudia E. van der; Stams, Geert Jan (2012): Differences between juvenile offenders with and without intellectual disability in offense type and risk factors. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 33 (6), S. 1905–1913. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2012.05.022.
- Atkinson, Julie P.; Ward, Karen M. (2012): The Development of an Assessment of Interpersonal Violence for Individuals with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (3), S. 301–309. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-012-9275-3.
- Aylaz, Rukuye; Yilmaz, Ulviye; Polat, Sevinç (2012): Effect of Difficulties Experienced by Parents of Autistic Children on Their Sexual Life. A Qualitative Study. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (4), S. 395–406. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9251-3.
- Bowman, Rachel A.; Scotti, Joseph R.; Morris, Tracy L. (2010): Sexual abuse prevention. A training program for developmental disabilities service providers. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 119–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003614718.
- Brunnberg, Elinor; Lindén Boström, Margareta; Berglund, Mats (2012): Sexual force at sexual debut. Swedish adolescents with disabilities at higher risk than adolescents without disabilities. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (4), S. 285–295.
- Caldas, Stephen J.; Betsy, Mary Lou (2014): The sexual maltreatment of students with disabilities in American school settings. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (4), S. 345–366. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.906530.
- Chappell, Paul; Rule, Peter; Dlamini, Mfana; Nkala, Nompilo (2014): Troubling power dynamics. Youth with disabilities as co-researchers in sexuality research in South Africa. In: *Childhood* 21 (3), S. 385–399. DOI: 10.1177/0907568214525427.
- Corona, Laura L.; Fox, Stephanie A.; Christodulu, Kristin V.; Worlock, Jane Ann (2016): Providing Education on Sexuality and Relationships to Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder and Their Parents. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 199–214. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-015-9424-6.
- Doughty, Adam H.; Kane, Lindsey M. (2010): Teaching abuse-protection skills to people with intellectual disabilities. A review of the literature. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 31 (2), S. 331–337. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2009.12.007.
- Embregts, P.; Bogaard, K. van den; Hendriks, L.; Heestermans, M.; Schuitemaker, M.; Wouwe, H. van (2010): Sexual risk assessment for people with intellectual disabilities. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 31 (3), S. 760–767. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2010.01.018.
- Fader Wilkenfeld, B.; Ballan, Michelle S. (2011): Educators' Attitudes and Beliefs Towards the Sexuality of Individuals with Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (4), S. 351–361. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9211-y.
- Franklin, Anita; Smeaton, Emilie (2017): Recognising and responding to young people with learning disabilities who experience, or are at risk of, child sexual exploitation in the UK. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 474–481. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.11.009.
- Frawley, Patsie; Wilson, Nathan J. (2016): Young People with Intellectual Disability Talking About Sexuality Education and Information. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (4), S. 469–484. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9460-x.
- Gill, Michael (2010): Rethinking sexual abuse, questions of consent, and intellectual disability. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (3), S. 201–213. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0019-9.

- Griffin, Helen Louise; Vettor, Shannon (2012): Predicting sexual re-offending in a UK sample of adolescents with intellectual disabilities. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 64–80. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.617013.
- Haggis, Jane; Mulholland, Monique (2013): Rethinking difference and sex education. From cultural inclusivity to normative diversity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (1), S. 57–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.824873.
- Hilberink, Sander R.; Kruijver, Egbert; Wiegerink, Diana J. H. G.; Vliet Vlieland, Thea P. M. (2013): A Pilot Implementation of an Intervention to Promote Sexual Health in Adolescents and Young Adults in Rehabilitation. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 31 (4), S. 373–392. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9288-6.
- Kijak, Remigiusz J. (2011): A Desire for Love: Considerations on Sexuality and Sexual Education of People With Intellectual Disability in Poland. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (1), S. 65–74. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9184-2.
- Lainpelto, Katrin; Isaksson, Johan; Lindblad, Frank (2016): Does Information About Neuropsychiatric Diagnoses Influence Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations? In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 276–292. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1145164.
- Lee, Sally; Fenge, Lee-Ann (2017): Sexual Well-Being and Physical Disability. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2263–2281. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw107.
- Löfgren-Mårtenson, Lotta (2012): “I Want to Do it Right!” A Pilot Study of Swedish Sex Education and Young People with Intellectual Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 209–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9239-z.
- Lund, Emily M.; Hammond, Marilyn (2014): Single-Session Intervention for Abuse Awareness Among People with Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 99–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9335-3.
- Martinello, Emily (2014): Reviewing strategies for risk reduction of sexual abuse of children with intellectual disabilities. A focus on early intervention. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (2), S. 167–174. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9345-9.
- Martinello, Emily (2015): Reviewing Risks Factors of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities as Perpetrators of Sexually Abusive Behaviors. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 33 (2), S. 269–278. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9365-5.
- McCann, Edward; Lee, Regina; Brown, Michael (2016): The experiences and support needs of people with intellectual disabilities who identify as LGBT: A review of the literature. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 57, S. 39–53. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2016.06.013.
- McDaniels, Brad; Fleming, Allison (2016): Sexuality Education and Intellectual Disability. Time to Address the Challenge. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 215–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9427-y.
- Noonan, A.; Taylor Gomez, Miriam (2011): Who’s Missing? Awareness of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender People with Intellectual Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (2), S. 175–180. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9175-3.
- Parchomiuk, Monika (2012): Specialists and Sexuality of Individuals with Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (4), S. 407–419. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9249-x.
- Pasterski, Vickie; Mastroyannopoulou, Kiki; Wright, Deborah; Zucker, Kenneth J.; Hughes, Ieuan A. (2014): Predictors of posttraumatic stress in parents of children diagnosed with a disorder of sex development. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 369–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0196-8.
- Pebdani, Roxanna N. (2016): Attitudes of Group Home Employees Towards the Sexuality of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (3), S. 329–339. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9447-7.
- Rushbrooke, Elizabeth; Murray, Craig D.; Townsend, Samantha (2014): What difficulties are experienced by caregivers in relation to the sexuality of people with intellectual disabilities? A qualitative meta-synthesis. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 35 (4), S. 871–886. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2014.01.012.
- Sakellariou, Dikaos (2012): Sexuality and Disability. A Discussion on Care of the Self. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 187–197. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9219-3.
- Schaafsma, Dilana; Kok, Gerjo; Stoffelen, Joke M. T.; Curfs, Leopold M. G. (2017): People with Intellectual Disabilities Talk About Sexuality. Implications for the Development of Sex Education. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (1), S. 21–38. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9466-4.

- Seidel, Anja; Wienholz, Sabine; Michel, Marion; Lupp, Melanie; Riedel-Heller, Steffi Gerlinde (2014): Sexual Knowledge Among Adolescents with Physical Handicaps. A Systematic Review. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (3), S. 429–441. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9326-4.
- Sevlever, Melina; Roth, Matthew E.; Gillis, Jennifer M. (2013): Sexual Abuse and Offending in Autism Spectrum Disorders. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 31 (2), S. 189–200. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9286-8.
- Shandra, Carrie L.; Chowdhury, Afra R. (2012): The first sexual experience among adolescent girls with and without disabilities. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (4), S. 515–532. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9668-0.
- Soylu, Nusret; Alpaslan, Ahmet Hamdi; Ayaz, Muhammed; Esenyel, Selcen; Oruc, Mucahit (2013): Psychiatric disorders and characteristics of abuse in sexually abused children and adolescents with and without intellectual disabilities. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 34 (12), S. 4334–4342. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2013.09.010.
- van der Stege, Heleen A.; Hilberink, Sander R.; Visser, Adriaan P.; Staa, AnneLoes van (2014): Motivational factors in discussing sexual health with young people with chronic conditions or disabilities. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (6), S. 635–651. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.918877.
- Stewart, Catherine Carolyn (2012): Beyond the call. Mothers of children with developmental disabilities responding to sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 701–727. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.722182.
- Swango-Wilson, Amy (2011): Meaningful Sex Education Programs for Individuals with Intellectual/Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (2), S. 113–118. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9168-2.
- Taylor Gomez, Miriam (2012): The S Words. Sexuality, Sensuality, Sexual Expression and People with Intellectual Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 237–245. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9250-4.
- Turner, George W.; Crane, Betsy (2017): Sexually Silenced No More, Adults with Learning Disabilities Speak Up. A Call to Action for Social Work to Frame Sexual Voice as a Social Justice Issue. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2300–2317. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw133.
- Vugt, Eveline van; Asscher, Jessica J.; Stams, Geert Jan; Hendriks, Jan; Bijleveld, Catrien; Laan, Peter van der (2011): Moral judgment of young sex offenders with and without intellectual disabilities. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 32 (6), S. 2841–2846. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2011.05.022.
- White, Jacquelyn; Buehler, Cheryl; Weymouth, Bridget B. (2014): Childhood attention deficit hyperactive disorder (ADHD) symptoms and adolescent female sexual victimisation. Mediating and moderating effects of risky behaviours. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 23–39. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.782429.
- Wienholz, Sabine; Seidel, Anja; Michel, Marion; Haeussler-Sczepan, Monika; Riedel-Heller, Steffi Gerlinde (2016): Sexual Experiences of Adolescents With and Without Disabilities. Results from a Cross-Sectional Study. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 171–182. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9433-0.
- Wilkinson, Verity J.; Theodore, Kate; Raczk, Roman (2015): 'As Normal as Possible'. Sexual Identity Development in People with Intellectual Disabilities Transitioning to Adulthood. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 33 (1), S. 93–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9356-6.
- Williamson, Laura Helen; Grubb, Amy Rose (2015): An analysis of the relationship between being deaf and sexual offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 224–243. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.842001.
- Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014): Why All the Talk About Sex? An Autoethnography Identifying the Troubling Discourse of Sexuality and Intellectual Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 107–116. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9331-7.
- Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014): Discourse Analysis of Curriculum on Sexuality Education. FLASH for Special Education. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 485–498. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9387-z.
- Wissink, Inge B.; Vugt, Eveline van; Moonen, Xavier; Stams, Geert Jan; Hendriks, Jan (2015): Sexual abuse involving children with an intellectual disability (ID): a narrative review. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 36, S. 20–35. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2014.09.007.

2. Institutioneller Kontext

2.1. Dynamiken

Airton, Lee (2014): Hatred Haunting Hallways. Teacher Education and the Badness of Homophobia(s). In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 387–399.

Bailey, Lucy; Graves, Karen (2012): Introduction. Society Can Only Be as Free and Open as Its Schools. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 43–45.

Britzman, Deborah P. (2012): Queer Pedagogy and Its Strange Techniques. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 292–308.

Bryan, Jennifer (2014): Tomboys, Sissies, and "That's So Gay". Exploring Gender and Sexuality Diversity in Early Childhood and Elementary Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 240–256.

Carlson, Dennis (2014): The Bully Curriculum. Gender, Sexualities, and the New Authoritarian Populism in Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 175–187.

Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2016): Heterosexist Discourses. How Feminist Theory Shaped Campus Sexual Violence Policy. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge, S. 33–52.

Clery, Kerry; Erooga, Marcus (2012): Policy and Legislation - Changing Responses to an Emerging Problem. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 44–62.

Cowie, Helen (2013): The immediate and long-term effects of bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 10–18.

Davies, Cristyn; McInnes, David (2014): Speaking violence. Homophobia and the production of injurious speech in schooling cultures. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 131–148.

Duncan, Neil (2013): Disability, sexuality and bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 105–119.

Elliott, Kathleen O. (2012): The Right Way to be Gay. How School Structures Sexual Inequality. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 158–166.

Erooga, Marcus (2012): Understanding and Responding to People Who Sexually Abuse Children Whilst Employed In Trust. An Overview of the Relevant Literature - Part One: Offenders. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 7–26.

Erooga, Marcus; Allnock, Debra; Telford, David (2012): Sexual abuse of children by people in organisations. What offenders can teach us about protection. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 63–84.

Freitag, Mel B. (2014): Safety in Unity. One School's Story of Identity and Community. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 230–239.

Green, Jo (2012): Avoiding and managing allegations against staff. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 170–187.

Ingrey, Jennifer C. (2014): The Heterotopic Washroom in School Space. Binary Gender Confirmed, or No Place of One's Own? In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 63–74.

- Iverson, Susan V. (2016): A Policy Discourse Analysis of Sexual Assault Policies in Higher Education. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): *The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response*. New York: Routledge, S. 15–33.
- Jennifer, Dawn (2013): Girls and indirect aggression. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 45–59.
- Jennings, Todd (2014): Is the Mere Mention Enough? Representation Across Five Different Venues of Educator Preparation. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 400–413.
- Kaufman, Keith L.; Tews, Hayley; Schuett, Jessica M.; Kaufman, Benjamin R. (2012): Prevention is better than cure. The value of situational prevention in organisations. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them*. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 140–169.
- Kosciw, Joseph G.; Greytak, Emily A.; Bartkiewitz, Mark J. (2014): Failing Progress. Changes in School Climate for LGBT Youth Over Time. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 188–201.
- Leonardi, Bethy; Saenz, Lauren P. (2014): Conceptualizing Safety From the Inside Out. Heteronormative Spaces and Their Effects on Students' Sense of Self. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 202–216.
- Linville, Darla (2012): Virtual, Welcoming, Queer, School Community. An Interview with Dave Glick. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 167–168.
- Matrim, Jair (2014): A Philosophy of Sexual Reciprocity for Secular Public Schools of Toronto. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 313–327.
- McCall, Stephanie D. (2014): Girls Minus Boys. Heteronormative Discourses of Protection in Single-Gender Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 370–386.
- McCormack, Mark (2013): Mapping the boundaries of homophobic language in bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 91–104.
- Migdalek, Jack (2014): Challenging Gendered Practices Through Drama. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 414–425.
- Miller, sj; Gilligan, James R. (2014): Heteronormative Harassment. Queer Bullying and Gender-Non-Conforming Students. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 217–229.
- Ollis, Debbie (2013): Planning and delivering interventions to promote gender and sexuality. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 145–161.
- Ouer, Freeden (2014): It's Not How Regular Boys Are Supposed to Act. The Nonnormative Sexual Practices of Black Boys in All-Male Public Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 357–369.
- Pascoe, C. J. (2012): Becoming Mr. Cougar. Institutionalizing Heterosexuality and Homophobia at River High. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 145–157.
- Pendleton Jiménez, Karleen (2014): Off the Script. A Study of Techniques for Uncovering Gender-Bending Truths in the Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 257–271.

- Poteat, V. Paul; Mereish, Ethan H.; DiGiovanni, Craig D.; Scheer, Jillian R. (2013): Homophobic bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 75–90.
- Rivers, Ian (2013): Cyberbullying and cyberaggression. Sexualised and gendered experiences explored. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 19–44.
- Rivers, Ian; Duncan, Neil (2013): Discourses of sexuality and gender considered. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 162–168.
- Robinson, Kerry H. (2014): Sexual harassment in schools. Issues of identity and power - Negotiating the complexities, contexts and contradictions of this everyday practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 71–94.
- Robinson, Kerry H.; Davies, Cristyn; Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): Conclusions: Rethinking School Violence. Implications for Theory, Policy and Practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 184–195.
- Robles-Fernández, Ramón (2014): A GSA's Impact on Students' Beliefs and Attitudes Toward Civic and Political Participation, Civic Engagement, and Social Justice. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 284–297.
- Rofes, Eric E. (2012): Bound and Gagged. Sexual Silences, Gender Conformity, and the Gay Male Teacher. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 105–121.
- Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): "The kid most likely". Naming, brutality and silence within and beyond school settings. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 21–38.
- Schmidt, Sandra J. (2012): Let Me in! The Impact of the Discourse of Impossibility on Research and Curricular (Re)form. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 199–214.
- Schmitt, irina (2012): Sexuality, Secularism, and the Nation - Reading Swedish School Policies. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 270–280.
- Schneider, Margaret; Travers, Robb; St. John, Alex; Munro, Lauren; Klein, Kate (2013): The role of Gay-Straight Alliances in addressing bullying in schools. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 132–144.
- Singh, Anneliese A.; Jackson, Ken (2012): Queer and Transgender Youth. Education and Liberation in Our Schools. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 175–186.
- Ullman, Jacqueline; McGraw, Kelli (2014): Troubling Silences and Taboo Texts. Constructing Safer and More Positive School Climates for Same-Sex-Attracted High School Students in Australia. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 298–312.
- Walker Woolley, Susan (2014): (Im)perceptible Silences. Hearing LGBTQ Silences and Voices in School. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 328–341.
- Williams, Sian (2013): Sexual bullying in one local authority. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 60–74.
- Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014): Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Keenan, Marie (2013): Child sexual abuse and the Catholic Church. Gender, power, and organizational culture. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Larremore, April (2016): Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom.

- Murray, Olivia J. (2014): *Queer Inclusion in Teacher Education. Bridging Theory, Research, and Practice*. London: Taylor & Francis Ltd.
- Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2012): *Pervasive vulnerabilities. Sexual harassment in school*. New York: Peter Lang (Adolescent cultures, school & society, v. 54).
- Shariff, Shaheen (2015): *Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Erooga, Marcus (Hg.) (2012): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them*. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children).
- Rivers, Ian (Hg.) (2013): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education).
- Allen, Louisa (2013): *Boys as Sexy Bodies*. In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 347–365. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13497205.
- Anderson, E.; McCormack, M. (2015): *Cuddling and Spooning. Heteromascularity and Homosocial Tactility among Student-athletes*. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (2), S. 214–230. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14523433.
- Ballonoff Suleiman, Ahna; Brindis, Claire D. (2014): *Adolescent School-Based Sex Education. Using Developmental Neuroscience to Guide New Directions for Policy and Practice*. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 137–152. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0147-8.
- Bantjes, J.; Nieuwoudt, J. (2014): *Masculinity and Mayhem. The Performance of Gender in a South African Boys' School*. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (4), S. 376–395. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539964.
- Bengtsson, T. T. (2016): *Performing Hypermasculinity. Experiences with Confined Young Offenders*. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (4), S. 410–428. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15595083.
- Blaise, Mindy (2013): *Charting new territories. Re-assembling childhood sexuality in the early years classroom*. In: *Gender and Education* 25 (7), S. 801–817. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2013.797070.
- Caldas, Stephen J.; Bensy, Mary Lou (2014): *The sexual maltreatment of students with disabilities in American school settings*. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (4), S. 345–366. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.906530.
- Carrion, Melissa L.; Jensen, Robin E. (2014): *Curricular decision-making among public sex educators*. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (6), S. 623–634. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919444.
- Celik, Gonca Gul; Yolga Tahiroglu, Aysegul; Avci, Ayse; Cekin, Necmi; Evliyaoglu, Nurdan; Yoruldu, Belgin (2012): *Sexual abuse in a classroom of ten male students. A group victimization*. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (5), S. 543–552. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.694403.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2013): *Homophobic name-calling among secondary school students and its implications for mental health*. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 363–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9823-2.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G.M. (2015): *Understanding teachers' responses to enactments of sexual and gender stigma at school*. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 48, S. 34–43. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.02.002.
- DePalma, Renée (2013): *Choosing to lose our gender expertise. Queering sex/gender in school settings*. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (1), S. 1–15. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634145.
- DePalma, Renée; Atkinson, Elizabeth (2010): *The nature of institutional heteronormativity in primary schools and practice-based responses*. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (8), S. 1669–1676. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.06.018.
- Dessel, Adrienne B.; Kulick, Alex; Wernick, Laura J.; Sullivan, Daniel (2017): *The importance of teacher support. Differential impacts by gender and sexuality*. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 136–144. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.002.
- Doel, Mark; Allmark, Peter; Conway, Paul; Cowburn, Malcolm; Flynn, Margaret; Nelson, Pete; Tod, Angela (2010): *Professional Boundaries. Crossing a Line or Entering the Shadows?* In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (6), S. 1866–1889.

- Fair, Brian (2011): Constructing Masculinity through Penetration Discourse. The Intersection of Misogyny and Homophobia in High School Wrestling. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 491–504. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10375936.
- Ferfolja, Tania (2013): Sexual diversity, discrimination and 'homosexuality policy' in New South Wales' government schools. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (2), S. 159–171. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.697858.
- Fitzpatrick, Mark; Carr, Alan; Dooley, Barbara; Flanagan-Howard, Roisín; Flanagan, Edel; Tierney, Kevin et al. (2010): Profiles of adult survivors of severe sexual, physical and emotional institutional abuse in Ireland. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (6), S. 387–404. DOI: 10.1002/car.1083.
- Formby, Eleanor; Hirst, Julia; Owen, Jenny; Hayter, Mark; Stapleton, Helen (2010): 'Selling it as a holistic health provision and not just about condoms ...' Sexual health services in school settings. Current models and their relationship with sex and relationships education policy and provision. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 423–435. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515099.
- Garland-Levett, Sarah (2016): Exploring discursive barriers to sexual health and social justice in the New Zealand sexuality education curriculum. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 17 (2), S. 121–134. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1233396.
- Gerouki, Margarita (2010): The boy who was drawing princesses. Primary teachers' accounts of children's non-conforming behaviours. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 335–348. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515092.
- Gill, Michael (2010): Rethinking sexual abuse, questions of consent, and intellectual disability. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (3), S. 201–213. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0019-9.
- Goodkind, Sara; Schelbe, Lisa; Joseph, Andrea A.; Beers, Daphne E.; Pinsky, Stephanie L. (2013): Providing new opportunities or reinforcing old stereotypes? Perceptions and experiences of single-sex public education. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (8), S. 1174–1181. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.04.004.
- Govender, Kaymarlin (2011): The cool, the bad, the ugly, and the powerful. Identity struggles in schoolboy peer culture. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 887–901. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.586436.
- Green, Lorraine (2016): The Trouble with Touch? New Insights and Observations on Touch for Social Work and Social Care. In: *The British Journal of Social Work*, bcw071. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw071.
- Hafford-Letchfield, Trish; Cocker, Christine; Ryan, Peter; Melonowska, Justyna (2017): Rights through Alliances. Findings from a European Project Tackling Homophobic and Transphobic Bullying in Schools through the Engagement of Families and Young People. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2338–2356. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw104.
- Hampshire, Kate; Porter, Gina; Mashiri, Mac; Maponya, Goodhope; Dube, Siphon (2011): Proposing love on the way to school. Mobility, sexuality and youth transitions in South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (2), S. 217–231. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.522255.
- Hicks, Stephen; Jeyasingham, Dharman (2017): Social Work, Queer Theory and After. A Genealogy of Sexuality Theory in Neo-Liberal Times. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2357–2373. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw103.
- Huyge, Ellen; Maele, Dimitri van; Houtte, Mieke van (2014): Does students' machismo fit in school? Clarifying the implications of traditional gender role ideology for school belonging. In: *Gender and Education* 27 (1), S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2014.972921.
- Jackson, Vicki; Browne, Kevin; Joseph, Stephen (2016): The prevalence of childhood victimization experienced outside of the family. Findings from an English prevalence study. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 51, S. 343–357. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.08.006.
- Johnson, Brooke (2010): A Few Good Boys. Masculinity at a Military-Style Charter School. In: *Men and Masculinities* 12 (5), S. 575–596. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X09342228.
- Jones, Tiffany Mary; Hillier, Lynne (2012): Sexuality education school policy for Australian GLBTIQ students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (4), S. 437–454. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.677211.
- Lambine, Mackenzie E. (2012): Unsafe in the Ivory Tower. The sexual victimization of college women. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (3), S. 375–376. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.711657.

- Lueger-Schuster, Brigitte; Kantor, Viktoria; Weindl, Dina; Knefel, Matthias; Moy, Yvonne; Butollo, Asisa et al. (2014): Institutional abuse of children in the Austrian Catholic Church. Types of abuse and impact on adult survivors' current mental health. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (1), S. 52–64.
- Makura, Alfred Henry; Zireva, Davison (2013): School heads and mentors in cahoots? Challenges to teaching practice in Zimbabwean teacher education programmes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 3–16. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.573583.
- Malins, Pamela (2016): How inclusive is "inclusive education" in the Ontario elementary classroom? Teachers talk about addressing diverse gender and sexual identities. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 54, S. 128–138. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.11.004.
- Manninen, Sari; Huuki, Tuija; Sunnari, Vappu (2011): Earn Yo' Respect! Respect in the Status Struggle of Finnish School Boys. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (3), S. 335–357. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10369476.
- Martino, Wayne J.; Cumming-Potvin, Wendy (2015): Teaching about "Princess Boys" or Not. The Case of One Male Elementary School Teacher and the Polemics of Gender Expression and Embodiment. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (1), S. 79–99. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14551278.
- McLoone-Richards, Claire (2012): Say Nothing! How Pathology within Catholicism Created and Sustained the Institutional Abuse of Children in 20 th Century Ireland. In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (6), S. 394–404. DOI: 10.1002/car.2209.
- Melville-Wiseman, Janet (2017): The Sexual Abuse of Vulnerable People by Registered Social Workers in England. An Analysis of the Health and Care Professions Council Fitness to Practise Cases. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2190–2207. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw150.
- Miller, S. A. (2016): "How You Bully a Girl". Sexual Drama and the Negotiation of Gendered Sexuality in High School. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (5), S. 721–744. DOI: 10.1177/0891243216664723.
- Moore, Tim P.; McArthur, Morag; Noble-Carr, Debbie (2017): More a marathon than a hurdle. Towards children's informed consent in a study on safety. In: *Qualitative Research* 7 (2), 146879411770070. DOI: 10.1177/1468794117700708.
- Mulumeoderhwa, Maroyi; Harris, Geoff (2015): Forced sex, rape and sexual exploitation. Attitudes and experiences of high school students in South Kivu, Democratic Republic of Congo. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 17 (3), S. 284–295.
- Murphy, Meghan (2015): How organisational culture influences teachers' support of openly gay, lesbian and bisexual students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 263–275.
- Nelson, Pete; Cowburn, Malcolm (2010): Social Work Admissions. Applicants with Criminal Convictions -The Challenge of Ethical Risk Assessment. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (4), S. 1081–1099.
- O'Leary, P.; Tsui, M.-S.; Ruch, G. (2013): The Boundaries of the Social Work Relationship Revisited. Towards a Connected, Inclusive and Dynamic Conceptualisation. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 43 (1), S. 135–153. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcr181.
- Parent, Sylvie; Bannon, Joëlle (2012): Sexual abuse in sport. What about boys? In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (2), S. 354–359. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2011.11.004.
- Piccigallo, Jaqueline R.; Lilley, Terry G.; Miller, Susan L. (2012): "It's Cool to Care about Sexual Violence". Men's Experiences with Sexual Assault Prevention. In: *Men and Masculinities* 15 (5), S. 507–525. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X12458590.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2012): Popular culture as emotional provocation. The material enactment of queer pedagogies in a high school classroom. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 511–522. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627728.
- Russell, Brenda L.; Oswald, Debra L. (2016): When Sexism Cuts Both Ways. Predictors of Tolerance of Sexual Harassment of Men. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (5), S. 524–544. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15602745.
- Sauntson, Helen (2013): Sexual diversity and illocutionary silencing in the English National Curriculum. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 395–408. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.745809.
- Schalet, Amy T.; Santelli, John S.; Russell, Stephen T.; Halpern, Carolyn T.; Miller, Sarah A.; Pickering, Sarah S. et al. (2014): Invited commentary. Broadening the evidence for adolescent sexual and reproductive health and

- education in the United States. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (10), S. 1595–1610. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0178-8.
- Schaub, Jason; Willis, Paul; Dunk-West, Priscilla (2016): Accounting for Self, Sex and Sexuality in UK Social Workers' Knowledge Base. Findings from an Exploratory Study. In: *The British Journal of Social Work*, bcw015. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw015.
- Schmidt, Sandra J. (2015): A queer arrangement of school. Using spatiality to understand inequity. In: *Journal of Curriculum Studies* 47 (2), S. 253–273.
- Seelman, Kristie L.; Forge, Nicholas; Walls, N. Eugene; Bridges, Nadine (2015): School engagement among LGBTQ high school students. The roles of safe adults and gay–straight alliance characteristics. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 57, S. 19–29. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.07.021.
- Senn, Charlene Y. (2011): An imperfect feminist journey. Reflections on the process to develop an effective sexual assault resistance programme for university women. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (1), S. 121–137. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510386094.
- Snapp, Shannon D.; McGuire, Jenifer K.; Sinclair, Katarina O.; Gabrion, Karlee; Russell, Stephen T. (2015): LGBTQ-inclusive curricula. Why supportive curricula matter. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (6), S. 580–596. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1042573.
- Spraitz, Jason D.; Bowen, Kendra N.; Arthurs, Shavonne (2017): Neutralisation and sexual abuse. A study of monks from one Benedictine Abbey. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 195–206. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1204471.
- Svendsen, Stine Helena Bang (2012): Elusive sex acts. Pleasure and politics in Norwegian sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (4), S. 397–410. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.677209.
- Toomey, Russell B.; McGuire, Jenifer K.; Russell, Stephen T. (2012): Heteronormativity, school climates, and perceived safety for gender nonconforming peers. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 187–196. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.03.001.
- Turner, Daniel; Hoyer, Juergen; Schmidt, Alexander F.; Klein, Verena; Briken, Peer (2016): Risk Factors for Sexual Offending in Men Working With Children: A Community-Based Survey. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (7), S. 1851–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0746-y.
- Walsh, Kerryann; Mathews, Ben; Rassafiani, Mehdi; Farrell, Ann; Butler, Des (2012): Understanding teachers' reporting of child sexual abuse. Measurement methods matter. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (9), S. 1937–1946. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.06.004.
- Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014): Discourse Analysis of Curriculum on Sexuality Education. FLASH for Special Education. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 485–498. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9387-z.
- Wonnacott, Jane (2013): Keeping children safe in nurseries. A focus on culture and context. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 32–45. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.747631.
- Wurtele, Sandy K. (2012): Preventing the sexual exploitation of minors in youth-serving organizations. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (12), S. 2442–2453. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.09.009.
- Yoder, Jamie R.; Hansen, Jesse; Ruch, Donna; Hodge, Ashleigh (2016): Effects of School-Based Risk and Protective Factors on Treatment Success Among Youth Adjudicated of a Sexual Crime. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 310–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1137668.

2.2. Einrichtungstypen

2.2.1. Kindertagesstätte

- Boas, Erica M. (2012): Walking the Line. Teaching, Being, and Thinking Sexuality in Elementary School. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 131–144.
- Bryan, Jennifer (2014): Tomboys, Sissies, and "That's So Gay". Exploring Gender and Sexuality Diversity in Early Childhood and Elementary Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 240–256.

Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014): Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.

Larremore, April (2016): Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom.

Åmot, Ingvild; Ytterhus, Borgunn (2014): 'Talking bodies'. Power and counter-power between children and adults in day care. In: *Childhood* 21 (2), S. 260–273. DOI: 10.1177/0907568213490971.

Blaise, Mindy (2013): Charting new territories. Re-assembling childhood sexuality in the early years classroom. In: *Gender and Education* 25 (7), S. 801–817. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2013.797070.

Martin, Karin A. (2014): Making sense of children's sexual behavior in child care. An analysis of adult responses in special investigation reports. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (10), S. 1636–1646.

Wonnacott, Jane (2013): Keeping children safe in nurseries. A focus on culture and context. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 32–45. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.747631.

2.2.2. Grundschule

Boas, Erica M. (2012): Walking the Line. Teaching, Being, and Thinking Sexuality in Elementary School. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 131–144.

Gilbert, Jen (2014): *Sexuality in School: The Limits of Education*: University of Minnesota Press.

Larremore, April (2016): Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom.

DePalma, Renée (2013): Choosing to lose our gender expertise. Queering sex/gender in school settings. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (1), S. 1–15. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634145.

DePalma, Renée; Atkinson, Elizabeth (2010): The nature of institutional heteronormativity in primary schools and practice-based responses. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (8), S. 1669–1676. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.06.018.

Fu, Huiyan (2011): The bumpy road to socialise nature. Sex education in Japan. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 903–915. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.587894.

Gerouki, Margarita (2010): The boy who was drawing princesses. Primary teachers' accounts of children's non-conforming behaviours. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 335–348. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515092.

James, Adilia E. E. (2010): Too Early to Talk About Sex? Issues in Creating Culturally Relevant Sexuality Education for Preadolescent Black Girls in the United States. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (2), S. 128–141. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0012-3.

Jin, Yichen; Chen, Jingqi; Yu, Buyi (2016): Knowledge and Skills of Sexual Abuse Prevention. A Study on School-Aged Children in Beijing, China. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 686–696. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1199079.

Johnson, Rebecca L.; Sendall, Marguerite C.; McCuaig, Louise A. (2014): Primary schools and the delivery of relationships and sexuality education. The experience of Queensland teachers. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 359–374. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.909351.

Makura, Alfred Henry; Zireva, Davison (2013): School heads and mentors in cahoots? Challenges to teaching practice in Zimbabwean teacher education programmes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 3–16. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.573583.

Martino, Wayne J.; Cumming-Potvin, Wendy (2015): Teaching about "Princess Boys" or Not. The Case of One Male Elementary School Teacher and the Polemics of Gender Expression and Embodiment. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (1), S. 79–99. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14551278.

Mason, Sacha (2010): Braving it out! An illuminative evaluation of the provision of sex and relationship education in two primary schools in England. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 157–169. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666366.

Myers, Kristen; Raymond, Laura (2010): Elementary School Girls and Heteronormativity. The Girl Project. In: *Gender & Society* 24 (2), S. 167–188. DOI: 10.1177/0891243209358579.

Schonfeld, David J.; Adams, Ryan E.; Fredstrom, Bridget K.; Tomlin, Ricarda; Voyce, Charlene; Vaughn, Lisa M. (2012): Social-Emotional Learning in Grades 3 to 6 and the Early Onset of Sexual Behavior. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 9 (2), S. 178–186. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0077-7.

2.2.3. Weiterführende Schule

Airton, Lee (2014): Hatred Haunting Hallways. Teacher Education and the Badness of Homophobia(s). In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 387–399.

Anderson, Eric (2013): Masculinity and homophobia in high school and college sports. A personal journey from coach to researcher. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 120–131.

Atkinson, Becky (2012): Apple Jumper, Teacher Babe, and Bland Uniformer Teachers: Fashioning Feminine Teacher Bodies. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 93–104.

Bailey, Lucy; Graves, Karen (2012): Introduction. Society Can Only Be as Free and Open as Its Schools. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 43–45.

Boas, Erica M. (2012): Walking the Line. Teaching, Being, and Thinking Sexuality in Elementary School. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 131–144.

Bongardt, Daphne van de (2012): Teaching sexuality and relationships education in multicultural classrooms in the Netherlands. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 417–418.

Bryan, Jennifer (2014): Tomboys, Sissies, and "That's So Gay". Exploring Gender and Sexuality Diversity in Early Childhood and Elementary Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 240–256.

Bryan Meek, Jane (2012): "Being Queer Is the Luckiest Thing". Investigating a New Generation's Use of Queer within Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, and Queer Groups (LGBTQ) Student. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 187–198.

Burke, Kevin (2014): Impossible Women. Saints, Sinner, and the Gendered Mythology in a Catholic School. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 25–37.

Carlson, Dennis (2014): The Bully Curriculum. Gender, Sexualities, and the New Authoritarian Populism in Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 175–187.

Carmody, Moira (2014): Young people, ethical sex and violence prevention. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 167–184.

Casella, Ronnie (2014): The Historical and political roots of school violence in South Africa. Developing a cross-national theory. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 38–56.

Davies, Cristyn; McInnes, David (2014): Speaking violence. Homophobia and the production of injurious speech in schooling cultures. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 131–148.

Duncan, Neil (2013): Disability, sexuality and bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 105–119.

Elliott, Kathleen O. (2012): The Right Way to be Gay. How School Structures Sexual Inequality. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 158–166.

- Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): Bullying and sexual violence. Definition, prevalence, outcomes and moderators. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 31–44.
- Ford, Jillian (2012): Introduction: Realidades realities, Palabras words, y and Estudios studies. LGBTQIQ Youth in Schools. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 169–171.
- Freitag, Mel B. (2014): Safety in Unity. One School's Story of Identity and Community. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 230–239.
- Hirst, Julia (2014): 'Get some Rhythm Round the Clitoris': Addressing Sexual Pleasure in Sexuality Education in Schools and other Youth Settings. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 35–57.
- Ingrey, Jennifer C. (2014): The Heterotopic Washroom in School Space. Binary Gender Confirmed, or No Place of One's Own? In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 63–74.
- Jennifer, Dawn (2013): Girls and indirect aggression. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 45–59.
- Jennings, Todd (2014): Is the Mere Mention Enough? Representation Across Five Different Venues of Educator Preparation. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 400–413.
- Kosciw, Joseph G.; Greytak, Emily A.; Bartkiewitz, Mark J. (2014): Failing Progress. Changes in School Climate for LGBT Youth Over Time. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 188–201.
- Leonardi, Bethy; Saenz, Lauren P. (2014): Conceptualizing Safety From the Inside Out. Heteronormative Spaces and Their Effects on Students' Sense of Self. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 202–216.
- Linville, Darla (2012): Introduction. Schooling Students in Gender and Sexuality Expectations. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 125–128.
- Linville, Darla (2012): Virtual, Welcoming, Queer, School Community. An Interview with Dave Glick. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 167–168.
- Matrim, Jair (2014): A Philosophy of Sexual Reciprocity for Secular Public Schools of Toronto. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 313–327.
- Maxwell, Claire (2014): The Prevention of Sexual Violence in Schools: Developing Some Theoretical Starting Points. In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): *Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 105–127.
- McCall, Stephanie D. (2014): Girls Minus Boys. Heteronormative Discourses of Protection in Single-Gender Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 370–386.
- McCready, Lance T. (2014): The African Dance Program. "Where is the Love?". In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), 342–356.
- Migdalek, Jack (2014): Challenging Gendered Practices Through Drama. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 414–425.

- Miller, sj; Gilligan, James R. (2014): Heteronormative Harassment. Queer Bullying and Gender-Non-Conforming Students. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 217–229.
- Mills, Martin (2014): Schools, violence, masculinities and privilege. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 94–110.
- Niccolini, Alyssa D. (2014): Spicing Up the Curriculum. The Uses and Pleasures of Erotica Noir in the Urban Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 159–174.
- Nunez, Isabel (2012): Introduction. Teaching as Whole Self. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 85–88.
- Ollis, Debbie (2013): Planning and delivering interventions to promote gender and sexuality. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 145–161.
- Ouer, Freeden (2014): It's Not How Regular Boys Are Supposed to Act. The Nonnormative Sexual Practices of Black Boys in All-Male Public Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 357–369.
- Pascoe, C. J. (2012): Becoming Mr. Cougar. Institutionalizing Heterosexuality and Homophobia at River High. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 145–157.
- Pendleton Jiménez, Karleen (2014): Off the Script. A Study of Techniques for Uncovering Gender-Bending Truths in the Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 257–271.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): "Butterflies Starting a Tornado". The Queer 'Not Yet' of New Zealand School-Based Queer Straight Alliance as a Utopic Site of Learning. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 272–283.
- Rivers, Ian; Duncan, Neil (2013): Discourses of sexuality and gender considered. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 162–168.
- Robinson, Kerry H. (2014): Sexual harassment in schools. Issues of identity and power - Negotiating the complexities, contexts and contradictions of this everyday practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 71–94.
- Robinson, Kerry H.; Davies, Cristyn; Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): Conclusions: Rethinking School Violence. Implications for Theory, Policy and Practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 184–195.
- Robles-Fernández, Ramón (2014): A GSA's Impact on Students' Beliefs and Attitudes Toward Civic and Political Participation, Civic Engagement, and Social Justice. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 284–297.
- Rofes, Eric E. (2012): Bound and Gagged. Sexual Silences, Gender Conformity, and the Gay Male Teacher. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 105–121.
- Roth, Jillian R.; Robinson, Lea; O'Bryant, Camille; Griffin, Pat (2014): 3 to 1. Four Women Navigating the Intersections of Racism, Sexism, Homophobia, and Heterosexism in Intercollegiate Sport. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 453–463.
- Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): "The kid most likely". Naming, brutality and silence within and beyond school settings. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 21–38.
- Schmidt, Sandra J. (2012): Let Me in! The Impact of the Discourse of Impossibility on Research and Curricular (Re)form. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 199–214.

- Schmitt, irina (2012): Sexuality, Secularism, and the Nation - Reading Swedish School Policies. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 270–280.
- Schneider, Margaret; Travers, Robb; St. John, Alex; Munro, Lauren; Klein, Kate (2013): The role of Gay-Straight Alliances in addressing bullying in schools. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 132–144.
- Singh, Anneliese A.; Jackson, Ken (2012): Queer and Transgender Youth. Education and Liberation in Our Schools. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 175–186.
- Ullman, Jacqueline; McGraw, Kelli (2014): Troubling Silences and Taboo Texts. Constructing Safer and More Positive School Climates for Same-Sex-Attracted High School Students in Australia. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 298–312.
- Walker Woolley, Susan (2014): (Im)perceptible Silences. Hearing LGBTQ Silences and Voices in School. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 328–341.
- Whitlock, Reta Ugena (2014): LGBT Families and Southern Schools. Thinking About People, Place, and Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 75–89.
- Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014): Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Gilbert, Jen (2014): *Sexuality in School: The Limits of Education*: University of Minnesota Press.
- Larremore, April (2016): Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom.
- Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2012): Pervasive vulnerabilities. Sexual harassment in school. New York: Peter Lang (*Adolescent cultures, school & society*, v. 54).
- Shariff, Shaheen (2015): *Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Meiners, Erica R.; Quinn, Therese (Hg.) (2012): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367).
- Meyer, Elizabeth J.; Carlson, Dennis (Hg.) (2014): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5).
- Saltmarsh, Sue (Hg.) (2014): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Abbott, Keeley; Ellis, Sonja J.; Abbott, Rachel (2016): "We've got a lack of family values". An examination of how teachers formulate and justify their approach to teaching sex and relationships education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (6), S. 678–691. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1169398.
- Allen, Louisa (2013): Boys as Sexy Bodies. In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 347–365. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13497205.
- Allen, Louisa (2011): 'Picture this'. Using photo-methods in research on sexualities and schooling. In: *Qualitative Research* 11 (5), S. 487–504. DOI: 10.1177/1468794111413224.
- Anderson, E.; McCormack, M. (2015): Cuddling and Spooning. Heteromascularity and Homosocial Tactility among Student-athletes. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (2), S. 214–230. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14523433.
- Ballonoff Suleiman, Ahna; Brindis, Claire D. (2014): Adolescent School-Based Sex Education. Using Developmental Neuroscience to Guide New Directions for Policy and Practice. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 137–152. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0147-8.
- Bantjes, J.; Nieuwoudt, J. (2014): Masculinity and Mayhem. The Performance of Gender in a South African Boys' School. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (4), S. 376–395. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539964.
- Caldas, Stephen J.; Betsy, Mary Lou (2014): The sexual maltreatment of students with disabilities in American school settings. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (4), S. 345–366. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.906530.

- Celik, Gonca Gul; Yolga Tahiroglu, Aysegul; Avci, Ayse; Cekin, Necmi; Evliyaoglu, Nurdan; Yoruldu, Belgin (2012): Sexual abuse in a classroom of ten male students. A group victimization. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (5), S. 543–552. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.694403.
- Cohen, Jacqueline N.; Byers, E. Sandra; Sears, Heather A. (2011): Factors affecting Canadian teachers' willingness to teach sexual health education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615606.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2013): Homophobic name-calling among secondary school students and its implications for mental health. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 363–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9823-2.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G.M. (2015): Understanding teachers' responses to enactments of sexual and gender stigma at school. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 48, S. 34–43. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.02.002.
- DePalma, Renée (2013): Choosing to lose our gender expertise. Queering sex/gender in school settings. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (1), S. 1–15. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634145.
- DePalma, Renée; Atkinson, Elizabeth (2010): The nature of institutional heteronormativity in primary schools and practice-based responses. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (8), S. 1669–1676. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.06.018.
- Dessel, Adrienne B.; Kulick, Alex; Wernick, Laura J.; Sullivan, Daniel (2017): The importance of teacher support. Differential impacts by gender and sexuality. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 136–144. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.002.
- Diarsvitri, Wienta; Utomo, Iwu Dwisetyani; Neeman, Teresa; Oktavian, Antonius (2011): Beyond sexual desire and curiosity. Sexuality among senior high school students in Papua and West Papua Provinces (Indonesia) and implications for HIV prevention. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (9), S. 1047–1060. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.599862.
- Evrpidou, Dimitris; Çavuşoğlu, Çise (2015): English Language Teachers' Attitudes Towards the Incorporation of Gay- and Lesbian-Related Topics in the Classroom. The Case of Greek Cypriot EFL Teachers. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 12 (1), S. 70–80. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0176-3.
- Fader Wilkenfeld, B.; Ballan, Michelle S. (2011): Educators' Attitudes and Beliefs Towards the Sexuality of Individuals with Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (4), S. 351–361. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9211-y.
- Fair, Brian (2011): Constructing Masculinity through Penetration Discourse. The Intersection of Misogyny and Homophobia in High School Wrestling. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 491–504. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10375936.
- Ferfolja, Tania (2013): Sexual diversity, discrimination and 'homosexuality policy' in New South Wales' government schools. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (2), S. 159–171. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.697858.
- Ferfolja, Tania (2010): Lesbian teachers, harassment and the workplace. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (3), S. 408–414. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.05.007.
- Formby, Eleanor; Hirst, Julia; Owen, Jenny; Hayter, Mark; Stapleton, Helen (2010): 'Selling it as a holistic health provision and not just about condoms ...' Sexual health services in school settings. Current models and their relationship with sex and relationships education policy and provision. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 423–435. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515099.
- Fromuth, Mary Ellen; Kelly, David B.; Brallier, Courtney; Williams, Matthew; Benson, Kate (2016): Effects of duration on perceptions of teacher sexual misconduct. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (2), S. 159–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1122692.
- Fu, Huiyan (2011): The bumpy road to socialise nature. Sex education in Japan. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 903–915. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.587894.
- Garland-Levett, Sarah (2016): Exploring discursive barriers to sexual health and social justice in the New Zealand sexuality education curriculum. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 17 (2), S. 121–134. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1233396.

- Gerouki, Margarita (2010): The boy who was drawing princesses. Primary teachers' accounts of children's non-conforming behaviours. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 335–348. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515092.
- Gilbert, Jen (2015): Walking through the school: the erotics of research. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 111–115. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1094947.
- Goldman, Juliette (2010): The new sexuality education curriculum for Queensland primary schools. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (1), S. 47–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681810903491370.
- Goldman, Juliette (2011): External providers' sexuality education teaching and pedagogies for primary school students in Grade 1 to Grade 7. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (02), S. 155–174. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.558423.
- Goldman, Juliette (2012): A critical analysis of UNESCO's International Technical Guidance on school-based education for puberty and sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 199–218. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.609051.
- Goldman, Juliette D. G.; Grimbeek, Peter (2015): Preservice teachers' sources of information on mandatory reporting of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 238–258. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1009607.
- Goodkind, Sara; Schelbe, Lisa; Joseph, Andrea A.; Beers, Daphne E.; Pinsky, Stephanie L. (2013): Providing new opportunities or reinforcing old stereotypes? Perceptions and experiences of single-sex public education. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (8), S. 1174–1181. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.04.004.
- Govender, Kaymarlin (2011): The cool, the bad, the ugly, and the powerful. Identity struggles in schoolboy peer culture. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 887–901. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.586436.
- Gowen, L. Kris; Wings-Yanez, Nichole (2014): Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, and Questioning Youths' Perspectives of Inclusive School-Based Sexuality Education. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), S. 788–800.
- Gray, Emily M. (2013): Coming out as a lesbian, gay or bisexual teacher. Negotiating private and professional worlds. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (6), S. 702–714. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.807789.
- Grose, Rose Grace; Grabe, Shelly; Kohfeldt, Danielle (2014): Sexual Education, Gender Ideology, and Youth Sexual Empowerment. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), 742.753.
- Gwirayi, Pesanayi (2013): The prevalence of child sexual abuse among secondary school pupils in Gweru, Zimbabwe. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 253–263. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.723755.
- Hampshire, Kate; Porter, Gina; Mashiri, Mac; Maponya, Goodhope; Dube, Siphon (2011): Proposing love on the way to school. Mobility, sexuality and youth transitions in South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (2), S. 217–231. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.522255.
- Hardie, Ann (2011): Lesbian teachers and students. Issues and dilemmas of being 'out' in primary school. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–10. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615595.
- Huyge, Ellen; Maele, Dimitri van; Houtte, Mieke van (2014): Does students' machismo fit in school? Clarifying the implications of traditional gender role ideology for school belonging. In: *Gender and Education* 27 (1), S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2014.972921.
- Jackson, Sue; Weatherall, Ann (2010): The (Im)possibilities of Feminist School Based Sexuality Education. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 20 (2), S. 166–185.
- James, Adilia E. E. (2010): Too Early to Talk About Sex? Issues in Creating Culturally Relevant Sexuality Education for Preadolescent Black Girls in the United States. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (2), S. 128–141. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0012-3.
- Johnson, Brooke (2010): A Few Good Boys. Masculinity at a Military-Style Charter School. In: *Men and Masculinities* 12 (5), S. 575–596. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X09342228.
- Johnson, Rebecca L.; Sendall, Marguerite C.; McCuaig, Louise A. (2014): Primary schools and the delivery of relationships and sexuality education. The experience of Queensland teachers. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 359–374. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.909351.
- Jones, Tiffany Mary; Hillier, Lynne (2012): Sexuality education school policy for Australian GLBTIQ students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (4), S. 437–454. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.677211.

- Kjaran, Jón; Kristinsdóttir, Guðrún (2014): Queering the environment and caring for the self. Icelandic LGBT students' experience of the upper secondary school. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 23 (1), S. 1–20. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2014.910250.
- Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2010): Sexually coercive behavior in male youth: population survey of general and specific risk factors. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1161–1169. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9572-9.
- Kontula, Osmo (2010): The evolution of sex education and students' sexual knowledge in Finland in the 2000s. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 373–386. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515095.
- Larsson, Håkan; Quennerstedt, Mikael; Öhman, Marie (2014): Heterotopias in physical education. Towards a queer pedagogy? In: *Gender and Education* 26 (2), S. 135–150. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2014.888403.
- Lesko, Nancy (2010): Feeling abstinent? Feeling comprehensive? Touching the affects of sexuality curricula. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 281–297. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491633.
- MacDonald, Jo-Ann; Gagnon, Anita J.; Mitchell, Claudia; Di Meglio, Giuseppina; Rennick, Janet E.; Cox, Joseph (2011): Asking to listen. Towards a youth perspective on sexual health education and needs. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 443–457. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595268.
- Makura, Alfred Henry; Zireva, Davison (2013): School heads and mentors in cahoots? Challenges to teaching practice in Zimbabwean teacher education programmes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 3–16. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.573583.
- Malins, Pamela (2016): How inclusive is “inclusive education” in the Ontario elementary classroom? Teachers talk about addressing diverse gender and sexual identities. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 54, S. 128–138. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.11.004.
- Manninen, Sari; Huuki, Tuija; Sunnari, Vappu (2011): Earn Yo' Respect! Respect in the Status Struggle of Finnish School Boys. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (3), S. 335–357. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10369476.
- Marquez-Flores, Maria Mercedes; Marquez-Hernandez, Veronica V.; Granados-Gamez, Genoveva (2016): Teachers' knowledge and beliefs about child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 538–555. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1189474.
- Mason, Sacha (2010): Braving it out! An illuminative evaluation of the provision of sex and relationship education in two primary schools in England. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 157–169. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666366.
- Miller, S. A. (2016): "How You Bully a Girl". Sexual Drama and the Negotiation of Gendered Sexuality in High School. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (5), S. 721–744. DOI: 10.1177/0891243216664723.
- Morris, Matthew C.; Kouros, Chrystyna D.; Janecek, Kim; Freeman, Rachel; Mielock, Alyssa; Garber, Judy (2017): Community-level moderators of a school-based childhood sexual assault prevention program. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 295–306. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.10.005.
- Mulumeoderhwa, Maroyi; Harris, Geoff (2015): Forced sex, rape and sexual exploitation. Attitudes and experiences of high school students in South Kivu, Democratic Republic of Congo. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 17 (3), S. 284–295.
- Murphy, Meghan (2015): How organisational culture influences teachers' support of openly gay, lesbian and bisexual students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 263–275.
- Myers, Kristen; Raymond, Laura (2010): Elementary School Girls and Heteronormativity. The Girl Project. In: *Gender & Society* 24 (2), S. 167–188. DOI: 10.1177/0891243209358579.
- Neary, Aoife; Gray, Breda; O'Sullivan, Mary (2016): A queer politics of emotion. Reimagining sexualities and schooling. In: *Gender and Education* 28 (2), S. 250–265. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1114074.
- Newby, Katie; Wallace, Louise M.; Dunn, Orla; Brown, Katherine E. (2012): A survey of English teenagers' sexual experience and preferences for school-based sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 231–251. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615582.
- Nishina, Adrienne (2012): Microcontextual characteristics of peer victimization experiences and adolescents' daily well-being. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 191–201. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9669-z.

- Nixon, David (2010): Discrimination, performance and recuperation. How teachers and pupils challenge and recover discourses of sexualities in schools. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (2), S. 145–151. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.05.003.
- Ollis, Debbie (2010): 'I haven't changed bigots but ...'. Reflections on the impact of teacher professional learning in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 217–230. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666523.
- Paechter, Carrie (2013): Girls and their bodies. Approaching a more emancipatory physical education. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (2), S. 261–277. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.712055.
- Parent, Sylvie; Bannon, Joëlle (2012): Sexual abuse in sport. What about boys? In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (2), S. 354–359. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2011.11.004.
- Pingel, Emily Sweetnam; Thomas, Laura; Harmell, Chelsea; Bauermeister, Jose (2013): Creating comprehensive, youth centered, culturally appropriate sex education: What do young gay, bisexual and questioning men want? In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 10 (4). DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0134-5.
- Pomerantz, S.; Raby, R.; Stefanik, A. (2013): Girls Run the World? Caught between Sexism and Postfeminism in School. In: *Gender & Society* 27 (2), S. 185–207. DOI: 10.1177/0891243212473199.
- Preston, Marilyn J. (2015): 'They're just not mature right now': teachers' complicated perceptions of gender and anti-queer bullying. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 22–34. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1019665.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2013): The methodological im/possibilities of researching sexuality education in schools. Working queer conundrums. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S56–S69. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.796288.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2012): Popular culture as emotional provocation. The material enactment of queer pedagogies in a high school classroom. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 511–522. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627728.
- Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2011): Race, class, and emerging sexuality. Teacher perceptions and sexual harassment in schools. In: *Gender and Education* 23 (7), S. 799–810. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2010.536143.
- Rice, Eric; Winetrobe, Hailey; Holloway, Ian W.; Montoya, Jorge; Plant, Aaron; Kordic, Timothy (2015): Cell phone internet access, online sexual solicitation, partner seeking, and sexual risk behavior among adolescents. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 755–763. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0366-3.
- Rieger, Gerulf; Savin-Williams, Ritch C. (2012): Gender nonconformity, sexual orientation, and psychological well-being. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (3), S. 611–621. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9738-0.
- Rocha, Ana Cristina; Leal, Cláudia; Duarte, Cidália (2015): School-based sexuality education in Portugal. Strengths and weaknesses. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (2), S. 172–183. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1087839.
- Rudoe, Naomi (2010): Lesbian teachers' identity, power and the public/private boundary. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (1), S. 23–36. DOI: 10.1080/14681810903491347.
- Sanjakdar, Fida (2013): Educating for sexual difference? Muslim teachers' conversations about homosexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (1), S. 16–29. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634154.
- Sauntson, Helen (2013): Sexual diversity and illocutionary silencing in the English National Curriculum. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 395–408. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.745809.
- Savin-Williams, Ritch C.; Joyner, Kara (2014): The dubious assessment of gay, lesbian, and bisexual adolescents of add health. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (3), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0219-5.
- Schmidt, Sandra J. (2015): A queer arrangement of school. Using spatiality to understand inequity. In: *Journal of Curriculum Studies* 47 (2), S. 253–273.
- Schonfeld, David J.; Adams, Ryan E.; Fredstrom, Bridget K.; Tomlin, Ricarda; Voyce, Charlene; Vaughn, Lisa M. (2012): Social-Emotional Learning in Grades 3 to 6 and the Early Onset of Sexual Behavior. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 9 (2), S. 178–186. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0077-7.

Seelman, Kristie L.; Forge, Nicholas; Walls, N. Eugene; Bridges, Nadine (2015): School engagement among LGBTQ high school students. The roles of safe adults and gay-straight alliance characteristics. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 57, S. 19–29. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.07.021.

Snapp, Shannon D.; McGuire, Jenifer K.; Sinclair, Katarina O.; Gabrion, Karlee; Russell, Stephen T. (2015): LGBTQ-inclusive curricula. Why supportive curricula matter. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (6), S. 580–596. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1042573.

Sorhaindo, Annik; Bonell, Chris; Fletcher, Adam; Jessiman, Patricia; Keogh, Peter; Mitchell, Kirstin (2016): Being targeted. Young women's experience of being identified for a teenage pregnancy prevention programme. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 181–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.03.013.

Toomey, Russell B.; McGuire, Jenifer K.; Russell, Stephen T. (2012): Heteronormativity, school climates, and perceived safety for gender nonconforming peers. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 187–196. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.03.001.

Walsh, Kerryann; Mathews, Ben; Rassafiani, Mehdi; Farrell, Ann; Butler, Des (2012): Understanding teachers' reporting of child sexual abuse. Measurement methods matter. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (9), S. 1937–1946. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.06.004.

Wernick, Laura J.; Kulick, Alex; Inglehart, Marita H. (2013): Factors predicting student intervention when witnessing anti-LGBTQ harassment. The influence of peers, teachers, and climate. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (2), S. 296–301. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.11.003.

Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014): Discourse Analysis of Curriculum on Sexuality Education. FLASH for Special Education. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 485–498. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9387-z.

Wurtele, Sandy K. (2012): Preventing the sexual exploitation of minors in youth-serving organizations. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (12), S. 2442–2453. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.09.009.

Yoder, Jamie R.; Hansen, Jesse; Ruch, Donna; Hodge, Ashleigh (2016): Effects of School-Based Risk and Protective Factors on Treatment Success Among Youth Adjudicated of a Sexual Crime. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 310–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1137668.

2.2.3.1. Sportunterricht

Anderson, Eric (2013): Masculinity and homophobia in high school and college sports. A personal journey from coach to researcher. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 120–131.

Roth, Jillian R.; Robinson, Lea; O'Bryant, Camille; Griffin, Pat (2014): 3 to 1. Four Women Navigating the Intersections of Racism, Sexism, Homophobia, and Heterosexism in Intercollegiate Sport. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 453–463.

Anderson, E.; McCormack, M. (2015): Cuddling and Spooning. Heteromascularity and Homosocial Tactility among Student-athletes. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (2), S. 214–230. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14523433.

Fair, Brian (2011): Constructing Masculinity through Penetration Discourse. The Intersection of Misogyny and Homophobia in High School Wrestling. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 491–504. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10375936.

Larsson, Håkan; Quennerstedt, Mikael; Öhman, Marie (2014): Heterotopias in physical education. Towards a queer pedagogy? In: *Gender and Education* 26 (2), S. 135–150. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2014.888403.

Paechter, Carrie (2013): Girls and their bodies. Approaching a more emancipatory physical education. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (2), S. 261–277. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.712055.

Parent, Sylvie; Bannon, Joëlle (2012): Sexual abuse in sport. What about boys? In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (2), S. 354–359. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2011.11.004.

2.2.3.2. AGs

Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): "Butterflies Starting a Tornado". The Queer 'Not Yet' of New Zealand School-Based Queer Straight Alliance as a Utopic Site of Learning. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 272–283.

Seelman, Kristie L.; Forge, Nicholas; Walls, N. Eugene; Bridges, Nadine (2015): School engagement among LGBTQ high school students. The roles of safe adults and gay–straight alliance characteristics. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 57, S. 19–29. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2015.07.021.

2.2.4. Sonderpädagogik

Gill, Michael (2010): Rethinking sexual abuse, questions of consent, and intellectual disability. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (3), S. 201–213. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0019-9.

Löfgren-Mårtenson, Lotta (2012): "I Want to Do it Right!" A Pilot Study of Swedish Sex Education and Young People with Intellectual Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 209–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9239-z.

2.2.5. Hochschule

Anderson, Eric (2013): Masculinity and homophobia in high school and college sports. A personal journey from coach to researcher. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 120–131.

Bryan Meek, Jane (2012): "Being Queer Is the Luckiest Thing". Investigating a New Generation's Use of Queer within Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, and Queer Groups (LGBTQ) Student. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 187–198.

Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2016): Heterosexist Discourses. How Feminist Theory Shaped Campus Sexual Violence Policy. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge, S. 33–52.

Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2014): Critical Interventions. Addressing the Reality of LGBTQ Sexual Violence in Higher Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 426–438.

Crosset, Todd W. (2016): Athletes, Sexual Assault, and Universities' Failure to Address Rape-Prone Subcultures on Campus. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge, S. 74–93.

DeVita, James M.; Daniel Anders, Allison (2014): Multiple Targeted Identities. Intersectionality and the Lived Experiences of Black Gay Males. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 464–478.

Henriksen, Caitlin B.; Mattick, Kelsey L.; Fisher, Bonnie S. (2016): Mandatory Bystander Intervention Training: Is the SaVE Act Requirement the "Right" Program to Reduce Violence Among College Students? In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge, S. 169–185.

Iverson, Susan V. (2016): A Policy Discourse Analysis of Sexual Assault Policies in Higher Education. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge, S. 15–33.

Marine, Susan (2016): Combating Sexual Violence in the Ivy League: Reflections on Politics, Pain, and Progress. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge, S. 55–74.

McCoy, Sheltreese D. (2014): Some of Us Are Brave. A Review of the Research on the Experience of Black LGBT Professors in Colleges and Universities in the United States. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 439–452.

- Nunez, Isabel (2012): Introduction. Teaching as Whole Self. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 85–88.
- Saltzburg, Susan (2015): Pedagogy for unpacking heterosexist and cisgender bias in social work education in the United States. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 205–222.
- Thomas-Card, Traci; Eichele, Katie (2012): Comprehensive College- or University-Based Sexual Violence Prevention and Direct Services Program. A Framework. In: Laura M. Carpenter und John D. DeLamater (Hg.): *Sex for life. From virginity to Viagra, how sexuality changes throughout our lives*. New York: New York University Press (Intersections), S. 149–169.
- Murray, Olivia J. (2014): *Queer Inclusion in Teacher Education. Bridging Theory, Research, and Practice*. London: Taylor & Francis Ltd.
- Oliver, Kelly (2016): *Hunting Girls. Sexual Violence from The Hunger Games to Campus Rape*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Carrigan Wooten, Sara; Mitchell, Roland W. (Hg.) (2016): *The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response*. New York: Routledge.
- Allen, Louisa (2011): 'Undoing' the self. Should heterosexual teachers 'come out' in the university classroom? In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 19 (1), S. 79–95. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2011.548990.
- Ávila, Marisa; Cabral, Joana; Matos, Paula Mena (2012): Identity in university students. The role of parental and romantic attachment. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 133–142. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.05.002.
- Boratav, Hale Bolak; Çavdar, Alev (2012): Sexual stereotypes and practices of university students in Turkey. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (1), S. 271–281. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9811-8.
- Bui, Thanh Cong; Diamond, Pamela M.; Markham, Christine; Ross, Michael W.; Nguyen-Le, Thanh-An; Tran, Ly Hai Thi (2010): Gender relations and sexual communication among female students in the Mekong River Delta of Vietnam. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (6), S. 591–601. DOI: 10.1080/13691050902968769.
- Castro, Ángel (2016): Sexual Behavior and Sexual Risks Among Spanish University Students. A Descriptive Study of Gender and Sexual Orientation. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 13 (1), S. 84–94. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-015-0210-0.
- Chapleau, Kristine M.; Oswald, Debra L. (2010): Power, Sex, and Rape Myth Acceptance. Testing Two Models of Rape Proclivity. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 47 (1), S. 66–78.
- Clark, Caroline T. (2010): Preparing LGBTQ-allies and combating homophobia in a U.S. teacher education program. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (3), S. 704–713. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.10.006.
- D'Abreu, Lylla Cysne Frota; Krahe, Barbara (2016): Vulnerability to Sexual Victimization in Female and Male College Students in Brazil: Cross-Sectional and Prospective Evidence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1101–1115. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0451-7.
- Fielder, Robyn L.; Carey, Michael P. (2010): Predictors and consequences of sexual "hookups" among college students: a short-term prospective study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1105–1119. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9448-4.
- Fielder, Robyn L.; Walsh, Jennifer L.; Carey, Kate B.; Carey, Michael P. (2013): Predictors of sexual hookups: a theory-based, prospective study of first-year college women. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1425–1441. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0106-0.
- Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D.; Sanders, Stephanie A.; Dennis, Barbara; Reece, Michael (2014): Gender Differences in Heterosexual College Students' Conceptualizations and Indicators of Sexual Consent. Implications for Contemporary Sexual Assault Prevention Education. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (8), S. 904–916.
- Katz, Jennifer; Schneider, Monica E. (2013): Casual hook up sex during the first year of college: Prospective associations with attitudes about sex and love relationships. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1451–1462. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0078-0.

- King, Laura L.; Hanrahan, Kathleen J. (2015): University student beliefs about sexual violence in prison. Rape myth acceptance, punitiveness, and empathy. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 179–193. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.820851.
- Koster, Shirley (2011): The self-managed heart. Teaching gender and doing emotional labour in a higher education institution. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 19 (1), S. 61–77. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2011.548988.
- Lambine, Mackenzie E. (2012): Unsafe in the Ivory Tower. The sexual victimization of college women. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (3), S. 375–376. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.711657.
- Lefkowitz, Eva S.; Vasilenko, Sara A.; Leavitt, Chelom E. (2016): Oral vs. Vaginal Sex Experiences and Consequences Among First-Year College Students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (2), S. 329–337. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0654-6.
- Lehrer, Jocelyn A.; Lehrer, Evelyn L.; Koss, Mary P. (2013): Unwanted sexual experiences in young men: evidence from a survey of university students in Chile. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (2), S. 213–223. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0004-x.
- Muehlenhard, Charlene L.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D. (2016): The Complexities of Sexual Consent Among College Students. A Conceptual and Empirical Review. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (4-5), S. 1–31.
- Muise, Amy; Preyde, Michéle; Maitland, Scott B.; Milhausen, Robin R. (2010): Sexual identity and sexual well-being in female heterosexual university students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (4), S. 915–925. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9492-8.
- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Billen, Rhett M.; Conrad, Kathryn A.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Sex, commitment, and casual sex relationships among college men: a mixed-methods analysis. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 561–571. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0047-z.
- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Hooking up and penetrative hookups: correlates that differentiate college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 573–583. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-9907-9.
- Oswald, Sara B.; Wagner, Laurie M.; Eastman-Mueller, Heather P.; Nevers, Joleen M. (2014): Pedagogy and content in sexuality education courses in US colleges and universities. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (2), S. 172–187. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.991958.
- Parkhill, Michele R.; Pickett, Scott M. (2016): Difficulties in Emotion Regulation as a Mediator of the Relationship Between Child Sexual Abuse Victimization and Sexual Aggression Perpetration in Male College Students. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 674–685. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1205161.
- Patrick, Megan E.; Lee, Christine M. (2010): Sexual motivations and engagement in sexual behavior during the transition to college. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 674–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9435-9.
- Patrick, Megan E.; Maggs, Jennifer L. (2010): Profiles of motivations for alcohol use and sexual behavior among first-year university students. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (5), S. 755–765. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.003.
- Piccigallo, Jaqueline R.; Lilley, Terry G.; Miller, Susan L. (2012): "It's Cool to Care about Sexual Violence". Men's Experiences with Sexual Assault Prevention. In: *Men and Masculinities* 15 (5), S. 507–525. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X12458590.
- Rinehart, Jenny K.; Nason, Erica E.; Yeater, Elizabeth A.; Miller, Geoffrey F. (2017): Do Some Students Need Special Protection From Research on Sex and Trauma? New Evidence for Young Adult Resilience in "Sensitive Topics" Research. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (3), S. 273–283. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1156047.
- Russell, Brenda L.; Oswald, Debra L. (2016): When Sexism Cuts Both Ways. Predictors of Tolerance of Sexual Harassment of Men. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (5), S. 524–544. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15602745.
- Rutledge, Scott Edward; Siebert, Darcy Clay; Chonody, Jill; Killian, Michael (2011): Information about human sexuality. Sources, satisfaction, and perceived knowledge among college students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 471–487. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.601133.
- Senn, Charlene Y. (2011): An imperfect feminist journey. Reflections on the process to develop an effective sexual assault resistance programme for university women. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (1), S. 121–137. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510386094.

Wolff, Jennifer M.; Rospenda, Kathleen M.; Colaneri, Anthony S. (2017): Sexual Harassment, Psychological Distress, and Problematic Drinking Behavior Among College Students: An Examination of Reciprocal Causal Relations. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (3), S. 362–373. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1143439.

2.2.6. Jugendamt

Carr, Nicola; Pinkerton, John (2015): Coming into view? The experiences of LGBT young people in the care system in Northern Ireland. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 99–112.

Baril, Karine; Tourigny, Marc; Paille, Pierre; Pauze, Robert (2016): Characteristics of Sexually Abused Children and Their Nonoffending Mothers Followed by Child Welfare Services. The Role of a Maternal History of Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 504–523. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1176096.

Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Fava, Nicole M. (2014): What puts “At-Risk Girls” at risk? Sexual vulnerability and social inequality in the lives of girls in the child welfare system. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 116–125. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0142-5.

Biswas, Bipasha; Vaughn, Michael G. (2011): Really troubled girls. Gender differences in risky sexual behavior and its correlates in a sample of juvenile offenders. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 33 (11), S. 2386–2391. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2011.08.010.

Cocker, Christine; Hafford-Letchfield, Trish (2010): Out and Proud? Social Work's Relationship with Lesbian and Gay Equality. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (6), S. 1996–2008.

Green, Lorraine (2016): The Trouble with Touch? New Insights and Observations on Touch for Social Work and Social Care. In: *The British Journal of Social Work*, bcw071. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw071.

Grossi, Laura M.; Lee, Austin F.; Schuler, Ann; Ryan, Julie L.; Prentky, Robert A. (2016): Sexualized behaviors in cohorts of children in the child welfare system. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 52, S. 49–61. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.12.014.

Hackett, Simon; Carpenter, John; Patsios, Demi; Szilassy, Eszter (2013): Interprofessional and interagency training for working with young people with harmful sexual behaviours. An evaluation of outcomes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 329–344. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.753122.

Hallett, Sophie (2017): ‘An Uncomfortable Comfortableness’. ‘Care’, Child Protection and Child Sexual Exploitation. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (7), S. 2137–2152. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcv136.

Masson, H.; Hackett, Simon; Phillips, J.; Balfe, M. (2014): Looking Back on the Long-Term Fostering and Adoption of Children with Harmful Sexual Behaviours. Carers' Reflections on Their Experiences. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 44 (8), S. 2200–2217. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bct073.

Melville-Wiseman, Janet (2017): The Sexual Abuse of Vulnerable People by Registered Social Workers in England. An Analysis of the Health and Care Professions Council Fitness to Practise Cases. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2190–2207. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw150.

O'Brien, Jennifer E.; White, Kevin; Wu, Qi; Killian-Farrell, Candace (2016): Mental Health and Behavioral Outcomes of Sexual and Nonsexual Child Maltreatment Among Child Welfare-Involved Youth. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 483–503. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1167801.

Rosario, Margaret; Schrimshaw, Eric W.; Hunter, Joyce (2012): Homelessness among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth: implications for subsequent internalizing and externalizing symptoms. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 544–560. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9681-3.

Schaub, Jason; Willis, Paul; Dunk-West, Priscilla (2016): Accounting for Self, Sex and Sexuality in UK Social Workers' Knowledge Base. Findings from an Exploratory Study. In: *The British Journal of Social Work*, bcw015. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw015.

Venable, Victoria M.; Guada, Joseph (2014): Culturally competent practice with African American juvenile sex offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (3), S. 229–246. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.888122.

Wells, Elizabeth A.; Asakura, Kenta; Hoppe, Marilyn J.; Balsam, Kimberly F.; Morrison, Diane M.; Beadnell, Blair (2012): Social Services for Sexual Minority Youth: Preferences for What, Where, and How Services are Delivered. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 36 (2), S. 312–320. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2012.11.011.

Wilson, Bianca; Kastanis, Angeliki A. (2015): Sexual and gender minority disproportionality and disparities in child welfare. A population-based study. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 58, S. 11–17. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2015.08.016.

Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014): Discourse Analysis of Curriculum on Sexuality Education. FLASH for Special Education. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 485–498. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9387-z.

2.2.7. Kinder- und Jugendhilfe

Carr, Nicola; Pinkerton, John (2015): Coming into view? The experiences of LGBT young people in the care system in Northern Ireland. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 99–112.

Hirst, Julia (2014): 'Get some Rhythm Round the Clitoris': Addressing Sexual Pleasure in Sexuality Education in Schools and other Youth Settings. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 35–57.

Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014): Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.

Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Fava, Nicole M. (2014): What puts "At-Risk Girls" at risk? Sexual vulnerability and social inequality in the lives of girls in the child welfare system. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 116–125. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0142-5.

Boustani, Maya M.; Frazier, Stacy L.; Lesperance, Nephtalie (2017): Sexual health programming for vulnerable youth. Improving knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 375–383. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2017.01.013.

Lindroth, Malin (2014): Sex education and young people in group homes. Balancing risks, rights and resilience in sexual health promotion. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 400–413. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919910.

Pebdani, Roxanna N. (2016): Attitudes of Group Home Employees Towards the Sexuality of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (3), S. 329–339. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9447-7.

Wissink, Inge B.; Vugt, Eveline van; Moonen, Xavier; Stams, Geert Jan; Hendriks, Jan (2015): Sexual abuse involving children with an intellectual disability (ID): a narrative review. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 36, S. 20–35. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2014.09.007.

Wurtele, Sandy K. (2012): Preventing the sexual exploitation of minors in youth-serving organizations. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (12), S. 2442–2453. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2012.09.009.

2.2.8. Offene Kinder- und Jugendarbeit

Betancourt, Gerardo (2015): A theoretical model for intervening in complex sexual behaviours. Sexual desires, pleasures and passion - La Pasi3n - of Spanish-speaking gay men in Canada. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 159–172.

Hirst, Julia (2014): 'Get some Rhythm Round the Clitoris': Addressing Sexual Pleasure in Sexuality Education in Schools and other Youth Settings. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 35–57.

Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014): Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.

Keenan, Marie (2013): Child sexual abuse and the Catholic Church. Gender, power, and organizational culture. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.

Busche, Mart (2013): A girl is no girl is a girl_: Girls-work after queer theory. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (1), S. 43–56.

Carrion, Melissa L.; Jensen, Robin E. (2014): Curricular decision-making among public sex educators. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (6), S. 623–634. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919444.

Munoz-Laboy, Miguel; Murray, Laura R.; Wittlin, Natalie; Wilson, Patrick A.; Terto, Veriano; Parker, Richard (2011): Divine targets. Youth at the centre of Catholic and Pentecostal responses to HIV and AIDS in Brazil. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 657–668. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.565519.

Wurtele, Sandy K. (2012): Preventing the sexual exploitation of minors in youth-serving organizations. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (12), S. 2442–2453. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2012.09.009.

2.2.9. Kirche

Anderson, Jane (2016): Socialization Processes and Clergy Offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (8), S. 846–865. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1241333.

D’Alton, Paul; Guilfoyle, Michael; Randall, Patrick (2013): Roman Catholic Clergy who have sexually abused children: Their perceptions of their developmental experience. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 698–702.

Eriksson, Elisabet; Lindmark, Gunilla; Axemo, Pia; Haddad, Beverley; Ahlberg, Beth Maina (2010): Ambivalence, silence and gender differences in church leaders' HIV-prevention messages to young people in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 103–114. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903141192.

Langeland, Willemiem; Hoogendoorn, Adriaan W.; Mager, Daniel; Smit, Jan H.; Draijer, Nel (2015): Childhood sexual abuse by representatives of the Roman Catholic Church. A prevalence estimate among the Dutch population. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 67–77.

Lueger-Schuster, Brigitte; Kantor, Viktoria; Weindl, Dina; Knefel, Matthias; Moy, Yvonne; Butollo, Asisa et al. (2014): Institutional abuse of children in the Austrian Catholic Church. Types of abuse and impact on adult survivors' current mental health. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (1), S. 52–64.

Munoz-Laboy, Miguel; Murray, Laura R.; Wittlin, Natalie; Wilson, Patrick A.; Terto, Veriano; Parker, Richard (2011): Divine targets. Youth at the centre of Catholic and Pentecostal responses to HIV and AIDS in Brazil. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 657–668. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.565519.

Spraitz, Jason D.; Bowen, Kendra N.; Arthurs, Shavonne (2017): Neutralisation and sexual abuse. A study of monks from one Benedictine Abbey. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 195–206. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1204471.

2.2.10. Justizvollzugsanstalt

Beerthuisen, Marinus G. C. J.; Brugman, Daniel (2012): Sexually abusive youths' moral reasoning on sex. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 125–135. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.519126.

Bengtsson, T. T. (2016): Performing Hypermasculinity. Experiences with Confined Young Offenders. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (4), S. 410–428. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15595083.

Biswas, Bipasha; Vaughn, Michael G. (2011): Really troubled girls. Gender differences in risky sexual behavior and its correlates in a sample of juvenile offenders. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 33 (11), S. 2386–2391. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2011.08.010.

Mannix, Karyn; Dawson, David L.; Beckley, Kerry (2013): The implicit theories of male child sexual offenders residing in a high secure psychiatric hospital. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 264–274. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.732616.

Meek, Rosie (2011): The possible selves of young fathers in prison. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (5), S. 941–949. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.12.005.

Willis, Gwenda M.; Johnston, Lucy (2012): Planning helps. The impact of release planning on subsequent re-entry experiences of child sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 194–208. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.506576.

3. Fokus

3.1. Sexualpädagogik

- Allen, Louisa (2014): *Pleasure's Perils? Critically Reflecting on Pleasure's Inclusion in Sexuality Education*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 153–169.
- Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise; Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): *Introduction. Putting Pleasure Under Pressure*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 1–12.
- Betancourt, Gerardo (2015): *A theoretical model for intervening in complex sexual behaviours. Sexual desires, pleasures and passion - La Pasi3n - of Spanish-speaking gay men in Canada*. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 159–172.
- Bongardt, Daphne van de (2012): *Teaching sexuality and relationships education in multicultural classrooms in the Netherlands*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 417–418.
- Casemore, Brian (2012): *"A Different Idea" in the Sex Education Curriculum. Thinking Through the Emotional Experience of Sexuality*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 321–335.
- Dankmeijer, Peter (2012): *LGBT, to Be or Not to Be? Education about Sexual Preferences and Gender Identities Worldwide*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 254–269.
- Fields, Jessica (2012): *Differences and Divisions. Social Inequality in Sex Education Debates and Policies*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), 24-32.
- Hirst, Julia (2014): *'Get some Rhythm Round the Clitoris': Addressing Sexual Pleasure in Sexuality Education in Schools and other Youth Settings*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 35–57.
- Ingham, Roger (2014): *A Well-Kept Secret: Sex Education, Masturbation, and Public Health*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 57–95.
- Lamb, Sharon (2014): *The Hard Work of Pleasure*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 136–153.
- Lemma, Alessandra; Lynch, Paul E. (2015): *Introduction: let's talk about sex or...maybe not...*. In: Alessandra Lemma und Paul E. Lynch (Hg.): *Sexualities. Contemporary psychoanalytic perspectives*. London, New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group, S. 1–16.
- Linville, Darla (2012): *Introduction. Schooling Students in Gender and Sexuality Expectations*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 125–128.
- Lugg, Catherine A. (2012): *The Religious Right and Public Education. The Paranoid Politics of Homophobia*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 61–72.
- Meyer, Elizabeth J. (2012): *From Here to Queer. Mapping Sexualities in Education*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 9–17.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): *"What's wrong with Porn?" Engaging with Contemporary Painting to Explore the Commodification of Pleasure in Sexuality Education*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 78–95.

- Quinlivan, Kathleen; Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise (2014): After-Word(s). Engaging with the Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education: Affordances and Provocations. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education*. Pleasure Bound. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 186–195.
- Rasmussen, Mary Louise (2014): Pleasure/Desire, Sexularism, and Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education*. Pleasure Bound. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 153–169.
- Sanjakdar, Fida (2014): Sacred Pleasure. Exploring Dimensions of Sexual Pleasure and Desire from an Islamic Perspective. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education*. Pleasure Bound. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 95–114.
- Vincent, Louise; Macleod, Catriona (2014): Introducing a Critical Pedagogy of Sexual and Reproductive Citizenship: Extending the ‘Framework of Thick Desire’. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education*. Pleasure Bound. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 115–136.
- Best, Joel; Bogle, Kathleen A. (2014): *Kids gone wild. From rainbow parties to sexting, understanding the hype over teen sex*. New York [u.a.]: New York Univ. Press.
- Carlson, Dennis; Roseboro, Donyell L. (2011): *The Sexuality Curriculum and Youth Culture* (Counterpoints, 392).
- Gilbert, Jen (2014): *Sexuality in School: The Limits of Education*: University of Minnesota Press.
- Larremore, April (2016): *Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom*.
- Sanjakdar, Fida (2012): *Living west, facing east. The deconstruction of Muslim youth's sexual identities*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints, 364).
- Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise; Quinlivan, Kathleen (Hg.) (2014): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education*. Pleasure Bound. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education).
- Meiners, Erica R.; Quinn, Therese (Hg.) (2012): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367).
- Ponzetti, James J. (Hg.) (2016): *Evidence-based approaches to sexuality education. A global perspective* (Textbooks in family studies series).
- Abbott, Keeley; Ellis, Sonja J.; Abbott, Rachel (2016): "We've got a lack of family values". An examination of how teachers formulate and justify their approach to teaching sex and relationships education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (6), S. 678–691. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1169398.
- Albury, Kath (2013): Young people, media and sexual learning. Rethinking representation. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S32-S44. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.767194.
- Ali, Mir M.; Dwyer, Debra S. (2011): Estimating peer effects in sexual behavior among adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 183–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.12.008.
- Attwood, Feona; Smith, Clarissa (2011): Investigating young people's sexual cultures. An introduction. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* (Vol. 11 No. 3), S. 235–242.
- Ávila, Marisa; Cabral, Joana; Matos, Paula Mena (2012): Identity in university students. The role of parental and romantic attachment. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 133–142. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.05.002.
- Ballonoff Suleiman, Ahna; Brindis, Claire D. (2014): Adolescent School-Based Sex Education. Using Developmental Neuroscience to Guide New Directions for Policy and Practice. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 137–152. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0147-8.
- Berglas, Nancy F.; Angulo-Olaiz, Francisca; Jerman, Petra; Desai, Mona; Constantine, Norman A. (2014): Engaging Youth Perspectives on Sexual Rights and Gender Equality in Intimate Relationships as a Foundation for Rights-Based Sexuality Education. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (4), S. 288–298. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0148-7.
- Bhana, D. (2016): 'Sex isnt better than love. Exploring South African Indian teenage male and female desires beyond danger. In: *Childhood* 23 (3), S. 362–377. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216642828.

- Bhana, Deevia; Pattman, Rob (2011): Girls want money, boys want virgins. The materiality of love amongst South African township youth in the context of HIV and AIDS. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 961–972. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.576770.
- Boisvert, Stéphanie; Poulin, François (2016): Romantic Relationship Patterns from Adolescence to Emerging Adulthood: Associations with Family and Peer Experiences in Early Adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 945–958. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0435-0.
- Boratav, Hale Bolak; Çavdar, Alev (2012): Sexual stereotypes and practices of university students in Turkey. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (1), S. 271–281. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9811-8.
- Bos, Henny; Sandfort, Theo (2015): Gender Nonconformity, Sexual Orientation, and Dutch Adolescents' Relationship with Peers. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (5), S. 1269–1279. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0461-5.
- Boustani, Maya M.; Frazier, Stacy L.; Lesperance, Nephtalie (2017): Sexual health programming for vulnerable youth. Improving knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 375–383. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2017.01.013.
- Bower, Andrew R.; Nishina, Adrienne; Witkow, Melissa R.; Bellmore, Amy (2015): Nice Guys and Gals Finish Last? Not in Early Adolescence When Empathic, Accepted, and Popular Peers are Desirable. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (12), S. 2275–2288. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0346-5.
- Brown, Graham; Sorenson, Anne; Hildebrand, Janina (2012): How they got it and how they wanted it. Marginalised young people's perspective on their experiences of sexual health education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 599–612. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634141.
- Cameron-Lewis, Vanessa (2016): Escaping oppositional thinking in the teaching of pleasure and danger in sexuality education. In: *Gender and Education* 28 (4), S. 491–509. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2016.1171297.
- Cameron-Lewis, Vanessa; Allen, Louisa (2013): Teaching pleasure and danger in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (2), S. 121–132. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.697440.
- Campero, Lourdes; Walker, Dilys; Atienzo, Erika E.; Gutierrez, Juan Pablo (2011): A quasi-experimental evaluation of parents as sexual health educators resulting in delayed sexual initiation and increased access to condoms. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 215–223. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.05.010.
- Carrion, Melissa L.; Jensen, Robin E. (2014): Curricular decision-making among public sex educators. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (6), S. 623–634. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919444.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2012): Intergroup contact, attitudes toward homosexuality, and the role of acceptance of gender non-conformity in young adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 899–907. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.12.010.
- Corona, Laura L.; Fox, Stephanie A.; Christodulu, Kristin V.; Worlock, Jane Ann (2016): Providing Education on Sexuality and Relationships to Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder and Their Parents. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 199–214. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-015-9424-6.
- Crichton, Joanna; Ibisomi, Latifat; Gyimah, Stephen Obeng (2012): Mother-daughter communication about sexual maturation, abstinence and unintended pregnancy. Experiences from an informal settlement in Nairobi, Kenya. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 21–30. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.06.008.
- Daneback, Kristian; Månsson, Sven-Axel; Ross, Michael W.; Markham, Christine M. (2012): The Internet as a source of information about sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 583–598. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627739.
- Dickenson, Janna A.; Huebner, David M. (2016): The Relationship Between Sexual Activity and Depressive Symptoms in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth: Effects of Gender and Family Support. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (3), S. 671–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0571-8.
- Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2013): Trauma-informed sexuality education. Recognising the rights and resilience of youth. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 383–394. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.745808.
- Fielder, Robyn L.; Carey, Michael P. (2010): Predictors and consequences of sexual "hookups" among college students: a short-term prospective study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1105–1119. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9448-4.

- Formby, Eleanor (2011): Sex and relationships education, sexual health, and lesbian, gay and bisexual sexual cultures. Views from young people. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 255–266. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590078.
- Formby, Eleanor; Hirst, Julia; Owen, Jenny; Hayter, Mark; Stapleton, Helen (2010): 'Selling it as a holistic health provision and not just about condoms ...' Sexual health services in school settings. Current models and their relationship with sex and relationships education policy and provision. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 423–435. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515099.
- Frawley, Patsie; Wilson, Nathan J. (2016): Young People with Intellectual Disability Talking About Sexuality Education and Information. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (4), S. 469–484. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9460-x.
- Froyum, Carissa M. (2010): Making 'good girls'. Sexual agency in the sexuality education of low-income black girls. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 59–72. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903272583.
- Fu, Huiyan (2011): The bumpy road to socialise nature. Sex education in Japan. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 903–915. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.587894.
- Garland-Levett, Sarah (2016): Exploring discursive barriers to sexual health and social justice in the New Zealand sexuality education curriculum. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 17 (2), S. 121–134. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1233396.
- Gattis, Maurice N.; Woodford, Michael R.; Han, Yoonsun (2014): Discrimination and depressive symptoms among sexual minority youth: is gay-affirming religious affiliation a protective factor? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1589–1599. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0342-y.
- Genna, Natacha M. de; Larkby, Cynthia; Cornelius, Marie D. (2011): Pubertal timing and early sexual intercourse in the offspring of teenage mothers. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (10), S. 1315–1328. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9609-3.
- Gilbert, Jen (2010): Ambivalence only? Sex education in the age of abstinence. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 233–237. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491631.
- Gilliam, Melissa; Brindis, Claire D. (2011): Virtual Sex Ed. Youth, Race, Sex, and New Media. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 1–4. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0036-3.
- Gillmore, Mary Rogers; Chen, Angela Chia-Chen; Haas, Steven A.; Kopak, Albert M.; Robillard, Alyssa G. (2011): Do family and parenting factors in adolescence influence condom use in early adulthood in a multiethnic sample of young adults? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (11), S. 1503–1518. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9631-0.
- Goldman, Juliette (2010): The new sexuality education curriculum for Queensland primary schools. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (1), S. 47–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681810903491370.
- Goldman, Juliette (2011): External providers' sexuality education teaching and pedagogies for primary school students in Grade 1 to Grade 7. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (02), S. 155–174. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.558423.
- Goldman, Juliette (2012): A critical analysis of UNESCO's International Technical Guidance on school-based education for puberty and sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 199–218. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.609051.
- Goodkind, Sara; Schelbe, Lisa; Joseph, Andrea A.; Beers, Daphne E.; Pinsky, Stephanie L. (2013): Providing new opportunities or reinforcing old stereotypes? Perceptions and experiences of single-sex public education. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (8), S. 1174–1181. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.04.004.
- Gowen, L. Kris; Winges-Yanez, Nichole (2014): Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, and Questioning Youths' Perspectives of Inclusive School-Based Sexuality Education. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), S. 788–800.
- Green, Eli R.; Hamarman, Amelia M.; McKee, Ryan W. (2014): Online sexuality education pedagogy. Translating five in-person teaching methods to online learning environments. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (1), S. 19–30. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.942033.
- Greslé-Favier, Claire (2010): The legacy of abstinence-only discourses and the place of pleasure in US discourses on teenage sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515098.

- Greslé-Favier, Claire (2013): Adult discrimination against children. The case of abstinence-only education in twenty-first-century USA. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (6), S. 715–725. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.813387.
- Greteman, Adam J. (2013): Fashioning a bareback pedagogy. Towards a theory of risky (sex) education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S20-S31. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.760154.
- Grose, Rose Grace; Grabe, Shelly; Kohfeldt, Danielle (2014): Sexual Education, Gender Ideology, and Youth Sexual Empowerment. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), 742-753.
- Haggis, Jane; Mulholland, Monique (2013): Rethinking difference and sex education. From cultural inclusivity to normative diversity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (1), S. 57–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.824873.
- Harrison, Lyn; Ollis, Debbie (2014): Stepping out of our comfort zones. Pre-service teachers' responses to a critical analysis of gender/power relations in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 318–331. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1023284.
- Haste, Polly (2013): Sex education and masculinity. The 'problem' of boys. In: *Gender and Education* 25 (4), S. 515–527. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2013.789830.
- Hilberink, Sander R.; Kruijver, Egbert; Wiegerink, Diana J. H. G.; Vliet Vlieland, Thea P. M. (2013): A Pilot Implementation of an Intervention to Promote Sexual Health in Adolescents and Young Adults in Rehabilitation. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 31 (4), S. 373–392. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9288-6.
- Hirst, Julia (2013): 'It's got to be about enjoying yourself'. Young people, sexual pleasure, and sex and relationships education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 423–436. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.747433.
- Hyde, Abbey; Carney, Marie; Drennan, Jonathan; Butler, Michelle; Lohan, Maria; Howlett, Etaoine (2010): The silent treatment. Parents' narratives of sexuality education with young people. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 359–371. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903514455.
- Jackson, Sue; Weatherall, Ann (2010): The (Im)possibilities of Feminist School Based Sexuality Education. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 20 (2), S. 166–185.
- James, Adilia E. E. (2010): Too Early to Talk About Sex? Issues in Creating Culturally Relevant Sexuality Education for Preadolescent Black Girls in the United States. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (2), S. 128–141. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0012-3.
- Jerman, Petra; Constantine, Norman A. (2010): Demographic and psychological predictors of parent-adolescent communication about sex: a representative statewide analysis. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1164–1174. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9546-1.
- Johnson, Rebecca L.; Sendall, Marguerite C.; McCuaig, Louise A. (2014): Primary schools and the delivery of relationships and sexuality education. The experience of Queensland teachers. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 359–374. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.909351.
- Jones, Tiffany Mary (2011): Saving rhetorical children. Sexuality education discourses from conservative to post-modern. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 369–387. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595229.
- Jones, Tiffany Mary; Hillier, Lynne (2012): Sexuality education school policy for Australian GLBTIQ students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (4), S. 437–454. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.677211.
- Kennett, Deborah J.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Schultz, Kristen E. (2011): Sexual resourcefulness and the impact of family, sex education, media and peers. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615624.
- Kijak, Remigiusz J. (2011): A Desire for Love: Considerations on Sexuality and Sexual Education of People With Intellectual Disability in Poland. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (1), S. 65–74. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9184-2.
- Killoren, Sarah E.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; Christopher, F. Scott (2011): Family and cultural correlates of Mexican-origin youths' sexual intentions. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (6), S. 707–718. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9587-5.
- Kontula, Osmo (2010): The evolution of sex education and students' sexual knowledge in Finland in the 2000s. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 373–386. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515095.

- Lamb, Sharon; Lustig, Kara; Graling, Kelly (2013): The use and misuse of pleasure in sex education curricula. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (3), S. 305–318. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.738604.
- Lefkowitz, Eva S.; Vasilenko, Sara A.; Leavitt, Chelom E. (2016): Oral vs. Vaginal Sex Experiences and Consequences Among First-Year College Students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (2), S. 329–337. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0654-6.
- Lesko, Nancy (2010): Feeling abstinent? Feeling comprehensive? Touching the affects of sexuality curricula. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 281–297. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491633.
- Levine, Deb (2011): Using Technology, New Media, and Mobile for Sexual and Reproductive Health. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 18–26. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0040-7.
- Limmer, Mark (2010): Young men, masculinities and sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 349–358. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515093.
- Lindroth, Malin (2014): Sex education and young people in group homes. Balancing risks, rights and resilience in sexual health promotion. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 400–413. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919910.
- Löfgren-Mårtenson, Lotta (2012): "I Want to Do it Right!" A Pilot Study of Swedish Sex Education and Young People with Intellectual Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 209–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9239-z.
- Luder, Marie-Thérèse; Pittet, Isabelle; Berchtold, André; Akre, Christina; Michaud, Pierre-André; Surís, Joan-Carles (2011): Associations between online pornography and sexual behavior among adolescents: myth or reality? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1027–1035. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9714-0.
- MacDonald, Jo-Ann; Gagnon, Anita J.; Mitchell, Claudia; Di Meglio, Giuseppina; Rennick, Janet E.; Cox, Joseph (2011): Asking to listen. Towards a youth perspective on sexual health education and needs. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 443–457. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595268.
- Martino, Wayne J.; Cumming-Potvin, Wendy (2015): Teaching about "Princess Boys" or Not. The Case of One Male Elementary School Teacher and the Polemics of Gender Expression and Embodiment. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (1), S. 79–99. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14551278.
- Mason, Sacha (2010): Braving it out! An illuminative evaluation of the provision of sex and relationship education in two primary schools in England. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 157–169. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666366.
- McDaniels, Brad; Fleming, Allison (2016): Sexuality Education and Intellectual Disability. Time to Address the Challenge. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 215–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9427-y.
- McKee, Alan (2016): Learning from commercial entertainment producers in order to create entertainment sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 17 (1), S. 26–40. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1228528.
- McKee, Alan (2012): The importance of entertainment for sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 499–509. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627727.
- McMichael, Celia; Gifford, Sandra (2010): Narratives of sexual health risk and protection amongst young people from refugee backgrounds in Melbourne, Australia. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 263–277. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903359265.
- Muhanguzi, Florence Kyoheirwe (2011): Gender and sexual vulnerability of young women in Africa. Experiences of young girls in secondary schools in Uganda. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 713–725. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.571290.
- Muise, Amy; Preyde, Michéle; Maitland, Scott B.; Milhausen, Robin R. (2010): Sexual identity and sexual well-being in female heterosexual university students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (4), S. 915–925. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9492-8.
- Munoz-Laboy, Miguel; Murray, Laura R.; Wittlin, Natalie; Wilson, Patrick A.; Terto, Veriano; Parker, Richard (2011): Divine targets. Youth at the centre of Catholic and Pentecostal responses to HIV and AIDS in Brazil. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 657–668. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.565519.

- Mustanski, Brian; Greene, George J.; Ryan, Daniel; Whitton, Sarah W. (2015): Feasibility, Acceptability, and Initial Efficacy of an Online Sexual Health Promotion Program for LGBT Youth. The Queer Sex Ed Intervention. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 52 (2), S. 220–230.
- Newby, Katie; Wallace, Louise M.; Dunn, Orla; Brown, Katherine E. (2012): A survey of English teenagers' sexual experience and preferences for school-based sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 231–251. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615582.
- Noonan, A.; Taylor Gomez, Miriam (2011): Who's Missing? Awareness of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender People with Intellectual Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (2), S. 175–180. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9175-3.
- O'Hara, Ross E.; Cooper, M. Lynne (2015): Bidirectional associations between alcohol use and sexual risk-taking behavior from adolescence into young adulthood. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (4), S. 857–871. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0510-8.
- O'Higgins, Siobhán; Gabhainn, Saoirse Nic (2010): Youth participation in setting the agenda. Learning outcomes for sex education in Ireland. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 387–403. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515096.
- Oidtman, Jessica; Sherman, Susan G.; Morgan, Anthony; German, Danielle; Arrington-Sanders, Renata (2017): Satisfaction and Condomless Anal Sex at Sexual Debut and Sexual Risk Among Young Black Same-Sex Attracted Men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 947–959. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0831-2.
- Ollis, Debbie (2010): 'I haven't changed bigots but ...'. Reflections on the impact of teacher professional learning in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 217–230. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666523.
- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Billen, Rhett M.; Conrad, Kathryn A.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Sex, commitment, and casual sex relationships among college men: a mixed-methods analysis. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 561–571. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0047-z.
- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Hooking up and penetrative hookups: correlates that differentiate college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 573–583. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-9907-9.
- Oswalt, Sara B.; Wagner, Laurie M.; Eastman-Mueller, Heather P.; Nevers, Joleen M. (2014): Pedagogy and content in sexuality education courses in US colleges and universities. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (2), S. 172–187. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.991958.
- Ott, Miles Q.; Corliss, Heather L.; Wypij, David; Rosario, Margaret; Austin, S. Bryn (2011): Stability and change in self-reported sexual orientation identity in young people: application of mobility metrics. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (3), S. 519–532. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9691-3.
- Patrick, Megan E.; Maggs, Jennifer L. (2010): Profiles of motivations for alcohol use and sexual behavior among first-year university students. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (5), S. 755–765. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.003.
- Peter, Jochen; Valkenburg, Patti M. (2011): The use of sexually explicit internet material and its antecedents: a longitudinal comparison of adolescents and adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1015–1025. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9644-x.
- Pingel, Emily Sweetnam; Thomas, Laura; Harmell, Chelsea; Bauermeister, Jose (2013): Creating comprehensive, youth centered, culturally appropriate sex education: What do young gay, bisexual and questioning men want? In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 10 (4). DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0134-5.
- Pradhan, Manas Ranjan; Ram, Usha (2010): Perceived gender role that shape youth sexual behaviour. Evidence from rural Orissa, India. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (4), S. 543–551. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.014.
- Preston, Marilyn J. (2015): 'They're just not mature right now': teachers' complicated perceptions of gender and anti-queer bullying. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 22–34. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1019665.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2013): The methodological im/possibilities of researching sexuality education in schools. Working queer conundrums. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S56–S69. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.796288.
- Raine, Tina R.; Gard, Jennifer C.; Boyer, Cherrie B.; Haider, Sadia; Brown, Beth A.; Ramirez Hernandez, F. Antonio; Harper, Cynthia C. (2010): Contraceptive decision-making in sexual relationships. Young men's experiences, attitudes and values. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 373–386. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903524769.

- Rice, Eric; Winetrobe, Hailey; Holloway, Ian W.; Montoya, Jorge; Plant, Aaron; Kordic, Timothy (2015): Cell phone internet access, online sexual solicitation, partner seeking, and sexual risk behavior among adolescents. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 755–763. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0366-3.
- Rocha, Ana Cristina; Leal, Cláudia; Duarte, Cidália (2015): School-based sexuality education in Portugal. Strengths and weaknesses. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (2), S. 172–183. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1087839.
- Sandlos, Karyn (2010): On the aesthetic difficulties of research on sex education. Toward a methodology of affect. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 299–308. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491634.
- Schaafsma, Dilana; Kok, Gerjo; Stoffelen, Joke M. T.; Curfs, Leopold M. G. (2017): People with Intellectual Disabilities Talk About Sexuality. Implications for the Development of Sex Education. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (1), S. 21–38. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9466-4.
- Schalet, Amy T.; Santelli, John S.; Russell, Stephen T.; Halpern, Carolyn T.; Miller, Sarah A.; Pickering, Sarah S. et al. (2014): Invited commentary. Broadening the evidence for adolescent sexual and reproductive health and education in the United States. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (10), S. 1595–1610. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0178-8.
- Schmidt, Sandra J.; Chang, Shih-pei; Carolan-Silva, Aliah; Lockhart, John; Anagnostopoulos, Dorothea (2012): Recognition, responsibility, and risk. Pre-service teachers' framing and reframing of lesbian, gay, and bisexual social justice issues. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 28 (8), S. 1175–1184. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2012.07.002.
- Seidel, Anja; Wienholz, Sabine; Michel, Marion; Luppa, Melanie; Riedel-Heller, Steffi Gerlinde (2014): Sexual Knowledge Among Adolescents with Physical Handicaps. A Systematic Review. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (3), S. 429–441. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9326-4.
- Shannon, Barrie (2016): Comprehensive for who? Neoliberal directives in Australian 'comprehensive' sexuality education and the erasure of GLBTIQ identity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (6), S. 573–585. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1141090.
- Sloane, Heather M. (2014): Tales of a Reluctant Sex Radical. Barriers to Teaching the Importance of Pleasure for Wellbeing. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 453–467. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9381-5.
- Sommer, Marni; Likindikoki, Samuel; Kaaya, Sylvia (2015): "Bend a fish when the fish is not yet dry": adolescent boys' perceptions of sexual risk in Tanzania. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 583–595. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0406-z.
- Sorhaindo, Annik; Bonell, Chris; Fletcher, Adam; Jessiman, Patricia; Keogh, Peter; Mitchell, Kirstin (2016): Being targeted. Young women's experience of being identified for a teenage pregnancy prevention programme. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 181–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.03.013.
- van der Stege, Heleen A.; Hilberink, Sander R.; Visser, Adriaan P.; Staa, AnneLoes van (2014): Motivational factors in discussing sexual health with young people with chronic conditions or disabilities. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (6), S. 635–651. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.918877.
- Steinhart, Katharina; Kaenel, Andreas von; Cerruti, Stella; Chequer, Pedro; Gomes, Rebeca; Herlt, Claudia; Horstick, Olaf (2013): International networking for sexuality education. A politically sensitive subject. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (6), S. 630–643. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.784194.
- Stevens-Watkins, Danelle; Brown-Wright, Lynda; Tyler, Kenneth (2011): Brief report. The number of sexual partners and race-related stress in African American adolescents: preliminary findings. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 191–194. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.02.003.
- Stulhofer, Aleksandar; Busko, Vesna; Landripet, Ivan (2010): Pornography, sexual socialization, and satisfaction among young men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (1), S. 168–178. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9387-0.
- Svendsen, Stine Helena Bang (2012): Elusive sex acts. Pleasure and politics in Norwegian sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (4), S. 397–410. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.677209.
- Swango-Wilson, Amy (2011): Meaningful Sex Education Programs for Individuals with Intellectual/Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (2), S. 113–118. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9168-2.
- Tabatabaie, Alireza (2014): Childhood and adolescent sexuality, Islam, and problematics of sex education. A call for re-examination. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 276–288. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1005836.

- Thompson, Ashley E.; Byers, E. Sandra (2017): Heterosexual Young Adults' Interest, Attitudes, and Experiences Related to Mixed-Gender, Multi-Person Sex. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 813–822. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0699-1.
- van Oosten, Johanna M. F. (2016): Sexually Explicit Internet Material and Adolescents' Sexual Uncertainty: The Role of Disposition-Content Congruency. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (4), S. 1011–1022. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0594-1.
- van Ryzin, Mark J.; Johnson, Amber B.; Leve, Leslie D.; Kim, Hyoun K. (2011): The number of sexual partners and health-risking sexual behavior: prediction from high school entry to high school exit. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 939–949. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9649-5.
- Vandenbosch, Laura; Eggermont, Steven (2015): The role of mass media in adolescents' sexual behaviors: exploring the explanatory value of the three-step self-objectification process. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 729–742. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0292-4.
- Wienholz, Sabine; Seidel, Anja; Michel, Marion; Haeussler-Sczegan, Monika; Riedel-Heller, Steffi Gerlinde (2016): Sexual Experiences of Adolescents With and Without Disabilities. Results from a Cross-Sectional Study. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 171–182. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9433-0.
- Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014): Discourse Analysis of Curriculum on Sexuality Education. FLASH for Special Education. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 485–498. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9387-z.
- Winskell, Kate; Beres, Laura K.; Hill, Elizabeth; Mbakwem, Benjamin Chigozie; Obyerodhyambo, Oby (2011): Making sense of abstinence. Social representations in young Africans' HIV-related narratives from six countries. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 945–959. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.591431.
- Yu, Juping (2010): Sex education beyond school. Implications for practice and research. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 187–199. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666515.

3.2. Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

- Betancourt, Gerardo (2015): A theoretical model for intervening in complex sexual behaviours. Sexual desires, pleasures and passion - La Pasi3n - of Spanish-speaking gay men in Canada. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 159–172.
- Cares, Alison C.; Moynihan, Mary M.; Banyard, Victoria L. (2014): Taking Stock of Bystander Programmes: Changing Attitudes and Behaviours Towards Sexual Violence. In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): *Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 170–189.
- Carmody, Moira (2014): Sexual Violence Prevention Educator Training: Opportunities and Challenges. In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): *Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 150–170.
- Carmody, Moira (2014): Young people, ethical sex and violence prevention. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 167–184.
- Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2016): Heterosexist Discourses. How Feminist Theory Shaped Campus Sexual Violence Policy. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): *The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response*. New York: Routledge, S. 33–52.
- Cleary, Kerry (2012): Safer recruitment. Guidance for organisations. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them*. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 122–139.
- Cleary, Kerry; Erooga, Marcus (2012): Policy and Legislation - Changing Responses to an Emerging Problem. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them*. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 44–62.
- Crosset, Todd W. (2016): Athletes, Sexual Assault, and Universities' Failure to Address Rape-Prone Subcultures on Campus. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): *The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response*. New York: Routledge, S. 74–93.

- Erooga, Marcus (2012): Understanding and Responding to People Who Sexually Abuse Children Whilst Employed In Trust. An Overview of the Relevant Literature - Part One: Offenders. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 7–26.
- Erooga, Marcus; Allnock, Debra; Telford, David (2012): Sexual abuse of children by people in organisations. What offenders can teach us about protection. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 63–84.
- Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): Bullying and sexual violence. Definition, prevalence, outcomes and moderators. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 31–44.
- Fletcher, Gillian (2014): Just How Do We Create Change? Sites of Contradiction and the 'Black Box' of Change in Primary Prevention. In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 127–150.
- Garmendia, Maialen; Garitaonandia, Carmelo; Martinez, Gemma; Casado, Miguel Ángel (2012): The effectiveness of parental mediation. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 231–244.
- Görzig, Anke (2012): Methodological framework. The EU Kids Online project. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 15–32.
- Green, Jo (2012): Avoiding and managing allegations against staff. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 170–187.
- Henriksen, Caitlin B.; Mattick, Kelsey L.; Fisher, Bonnie S. (2016): Mandatory Bystander Intervention Training: Is the SaVE Act Requirement the "Right" Program to Reduce Violence Among Collge Students? In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge, S. 169–185.
- Iverson, Susan V. (2016): A Policy Discourse Analysis of Sexual Assault Policies in Higher Education. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge, S. 15–33.
- Kalmus, Veronika; Feilitzen, Cecilia von; Siibak, Andra (2012): Effectiveness of teacher's and peers mediation in supporting opportunities and reducing risks online. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 245–256.
- Kaufman, Keith L.; Tews, Hayley; Schuett, Jessica M.; Kaufman, Benjamin R. (2012): Prevention is better than cure. The value of situational prevention in organisations. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 140–169.
- Kirwil, Lucyna; Laouris, Yiannis (2012): Experimenting with the self online: a risky opportunity. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 113–126.
- Kupiainen, Reijo; Suoninen, Annikka; Nikunen, Kaarina (2012): Between public and private: privacy in social networking sites. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 99–112.
- Lampert, Claudia; Donoso, Véronica (2012): Bullying. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 141–150.

- Laurinavicius, Alfredas; Zukauskienė, Rita; Ustinaviciūtė, Laura (2012): Explaining vulnerability to risk and harm. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 297–308.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Hasebrink, Uwe; Görzig, Anke (2012): Towards a general model of determinants of risk and safety. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 323–338.
- Masinire, Alfred (2014): *Becoming a Responsible Boy. Contesting Masculinity in Rural Zimbabwe*. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 110–123.
- Maxwell, Claire (2014): *The Prevention of Sexual Violence in Schools: Developing Some Theoretical Starting Points*. In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): *Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 105–127.
- Mills, Martin (2014): *Schools, violence, masculinities and privilege*. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 94–110.
- O’Neill, Brian; Staksrud, Elisabeth (2012): Policy implications and recommendations. Now what? In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 339–354.
- Ollis, Debbie (2013): *Planning and delivering interventions to promote gender and sexuality*. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 145–161.
- Pasquier, Dominique; Simoes, José Alberto; Kredens, Elodie (2012): Agents of mediation and sources of safety awareness: a comparative overview. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 219–230.
- Powell, Anastasia; Henry, Nicola (2014): *Framing Sexual Violence Prevention: What does it Mean to Challenge a Rape Culture?* In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): *Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 1–22.
- Pruulmann-Vengerfeldt, Pille; Runnel, Pille (2012): *Online opportunities*. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 73–86.
- Quadara, Antonia (2014): *The Everydayness of Rape: How Understanding Sexual Assault Perpetration Can Inform Prevention Efforts*. In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): *Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 41–64.
- Quayle, Ethel (2012): *Organisational issues and new technologies*. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them*. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 99–121.
- Rajander, Silja; Sopath, Phal (2012): *Drama Performances Address Stigma, Discrimination of MSM and HIV/AIDS Prevention*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 281–283.
- Rivers, Ian; Duncan, Neil (2013): *Discourses of sexuality and gender considered*. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 162–168.
- Robinson, Kerry H. (2014): *Sexual harassment in schools. Issues of identity and power - Negotiating the complexities, contexts and contradictions of this everyday practice*. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 71–94.
- Robinson, Kerry H.; Davies, Cristyn; Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): *Conclusions: Rethinking School Violence. Implications for Theory, Policy and Practice*. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 184–195.

- Rovoliy, Antonis; Tsaliki, Liza (2012): Pornography. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 165–176.
- Ságvári, Bence; Galács, Anna (2012): Relating online practices, negative experiences and coping strategies. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 309–322.
- Schneider, Margaret; Travers, Robb; St. John, Alex; Munro, Lauren; Klein, Kate (2013): The role of Gay-Straight Alliances in addressing bullying in schools. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 132–144.
- Sullivan, Joe; Quayle, Ethel (2012): Manipulation styles of abusers who work with children. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 85–98.
- Thomas-Card, Traci; Eichele, Katie (2012): Comprehensive College- or University-Based Sexual Violence Prevention and Direct Services Program. A Framework. In: Laura M. Carpenter und John D. DeLamater (Hg.): Sex for life. From virginity to Viagra, how sexuality changes throughout our lives. New York: New York University Press (Intersections), S. 149–169.
- Carlson, Dennis; Roseboro, Donyell L. (2011): The Sexuality Curriculum and Youth Culture (Counterpoints, 392).
- Carmody, Moira (2015): Sex, ethics, and young people. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan (Palgrave Macmillan's critical studies in gender, sexuality, and culture).
- Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014): Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Miller-Perrin, Cindy L.; Perrin, Robin D. (2013): Child maltreatment. An introduction. 3. ed. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Nelson, Sarah (2016): Tackling child sexual abuse. Radical approaches to prevention, protection and support. Bristol: Policy Press.
- Postmus, Judy L. (2013): Sexual Violence and Abuse. An Encyclopedia of Prevention, Impacts, and Recovery. Santa Barbara, Calif: Abc-Clío.
- Shariff, Shaheen (2015): Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Carrigan Wooten, Sara; Mitchell, Roland W. (Hg.) (2016): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge.
- Erooga, Marcus (Hg.) (2012): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children).
- Henry, Nicola; Powell, Anastasia (Hg.) (2014): Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Abajobir, Amanuel Alemu; Kisely, Steve; Williams, Gail Marilyn; Clavarino, Alexandra Marie; Najman, Jakob Moses (2017): Substantiated Childhood Maltreatment and Intimate Partner Violence Victimization in Young Adulthood: A Birth Cohort Study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 165–179. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0558-3.
- Allard, Troy; Rayment-McHugh, Sue; Adams, Dimity; Smallbone, Stephen; McKillop, Nadine (2015): Responding to youth sexual offending. A field-based practice model that “closes the gap” on sexual recidivism among Indigenous and non-Indigenous males. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (1), S. 82–94. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.1003107.
- Alleyne, Binta; Coleman-Cowger, Victoria H.; Crown, Laurel; Gibbons, Maya A.; Vines, Linda Nicole (2011): The effects of dating violence, substance use and risky sexual behavior among a diverse sample of Illinois youth. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 11–18. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.03.006.
- Atkinson, Julie P.; Ward, Karen M. (2012): The Development of an Assessment of Interpersonal Violence for Individuals with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (3), S. 301–309. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-012-9275-3.

- Babatsikos, Georgia (2010): Parents' knowledge, attitudes and practices about preventing child sexual abuse. A literature review. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (2), S. 107–129. DOI: 10.1002/car.1102.
- Baril, Karine; Tourigny, Marc; Paille, Pierre; Pauze, Robert (2016): Characteristics of Sexually Abused Children and Their Nonoffending Mothers Followed by Child Welfare Services. The Role of a Maternal History of Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 504–523. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1176096.
- Barron, Ian G.; Topping, Keith J. (2011): Sexual abuse prevention programme fidelity. Video analysis of interactions. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 134–151. DOI: 10.1002/car.1134.
- Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Fava, Nicole M. (2014): What puts “At-Risk Girls” at risk? Sexual vulnerability and social inequality in the lives of girls in the child welfare system. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 116–125. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0142-5.
- Beier, Klaus M.; Oezdemir, Umut C.; Schlinzig, Eliza; Groll, Anna; Hupp, Elena; Hellenschmidt, Tobias (2016): “Just dreaming of them”. The Berlin Project for Primary Prevention of Child Sexual Abuse by Juveniles (PPJ). In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 52, S. 1–10.
- Beres, Melanie Ann (2014): Rethinking the concept of consent for anti-sexual violence activism and education. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 24 (3), S. 373–389. DOI: 10.1177/0959353514539652.
- Biswas, Bipasha; Vaughn, Michael G. (2011): Really troubled girls. Gender differences in risky sexual behavior and its correlates in a sample of juvenile offenders. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 33 (11), S. 2386–2391. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2011.08.010.
- Boustani, Maya M.; Frazier, Stacy L.; Lesperance, Nephtalie (2017): Sexual health programming for vulnerable youth. Improving knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 375–383. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2017.01.013.
- Bowker, Julie C.; Etkin, Rebecca G. (2014): Does humor explain why relationally aggressive adolescents are popular? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1322–1332. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0031-5.
- Bowman, Rachel A.; Scotti, Joseph R.; Morris, Tracy L. (2010): Sexual abuse prevention. A training program for developmental disabilities service providers. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 119–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003614718.
- Braje, Sopagna Eap; Eddy, J. Mark; Hall, Gordon C. N. (2016): A Comparison of Two Models of Risky Sexual Behavior During Late Adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (1), S. 73–83. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0523-3.
- Brooks-Russell, Ashley; Foshee, Vangie A.; Ennett, Susan T. (2013): Predictors of latent trajectory classes of physical dating violence victimization. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 566–580. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9876-2.
- Buschman, Jos; Wilcox, Dan; Krapohl, Donald; Oelrich, Marty; Hackett, Simon (2010): Cybersex offender risk assessment. An explorative study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 197–209. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003690518.
- Caiozzo, Christina N.; Houston, Jessica; Grych, John (2016): Predicting aggression in late adolescent romantic relationships. A short-term longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 53, S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.10.012.
- Caldas, Stephen J.; Betsy, Mary Lou (2014): The sexual maltreatment of students with disabilities in American school settings. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (4), S. 345–366. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.906530.
- Cameron-Lewis, Vanessa; Allen, Louisa (2013): Teaching pleasure and danger in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (2), S. 121–132. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.697440.
- Campero, Lourdes; Walker, Dilys; Atienzo, Erika E.; Gutierrez, Juan Pablo (2011): A quasi-experimental evaluation of parents as sexual health educators resulting in delayed sexual initiation and increased access to condoms. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 215–223. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.05.010.
- Casey, Erin A.; Beadnell, Blair (2010): The structure of male adolescent peer networks and risk for intimate partner violence perpetration: findings from a national sample. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 620–633. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9423-y.

- Castro, Ángel (2016): Sexual Behavior and Sexual Risks Among Spanish University Students. A Descriptive Study of Gender and Sexual Orientation. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 13 (1), S. 84–94. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-015-0210-0.
- Cavazos-Rehg, Patricia A.; Spitznagel, Edward L.; Bucholz, Kathleen K.; Nurnberger, John; Edenberg, Howard J.; Kramer, John R. et al. (2010): Predictors of sexual debut at age 16 or younger. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 664–673. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9397-y.
- Chang, Ling-Yin; Foshee, Vangie A.; Reyes, Heathe Luz McNaughton; Ennett, Susan T.; Halpern, Carolyn T. (2015): Direct and indirect effects of neighborhood characteristics on the perpetration of dating violence across adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 727–744. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0190-z.
- Collibee, Charlene; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Chronic and Acute Relational Risk Factors for Dating Aggression in Adolescence and Young Adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (4), S. 763–776. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0427-0.
- Collin-Vézina, Delphine; Sablonnière-Griffin, Mireille de la; Palmer, Andrea M.; Milne, Lise (2015): A preliminary mapping of individual, relational, and social factors that impede disclosure of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 43, S. 123–134.
- Comartin, Erin B.; Kernsmith, Poco D.; Miles, Bart W. (2010): Family experiences of young adult sex offender registration. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 204–225. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003627207.
- Coren, Esther; Thomae, Manuela; Hutchfield, Jemeela; Iredale, Wendy (2013): Report on the Implementation and Results of an Outcomes-focused Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Interventions in the UK. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (1), S. 44–59. DOI: 10.1002/car.2200.
- Crandall, AliceAnn; Magnusson, Brianna M.; Novilla, M. Lelinneth B.; Novilla, Lynneth Kirsten B.; Dyer, W. Justin (2017): Family Financial Stress and Adolescent Sexual Risk-Taking: The Role of Self-Regulation. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 45–62. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0543-x.
- Craun, Sarah W.; Bourke, Michael L. (2014): The use of humor to cope with secondary traumatic stress. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (7), S. 840–852. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.949395.
- D'Abreu, Lylla Cysne Frota; Krahe, Barbara (2016): Vulnerability to Sexual Victimization in Female and Male College Students in Brazil: Cross-Sectional and Prospective Evidence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1101–1115. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0451-7.
- Daigneault, Isabelle; Hebert, Martine; McDuff, Pierre; Frappier, Jean-Yves (2012): Evaluation of a sexual abuse prevention workshop in a multicultural, impoverished urban area. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (5), S. 521–542. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.703291.
- Das, Aniruddha; Otis, Nicholas (2016): Sexual Contact in Childhood, Revictimization, and Lifetime Sexual and Psychological Outcomes. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1117–1131. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0620-3.
- DeHart, Dana; Dwyer, Gregg; Seto, Michael C.; Moran, Robert; Letourneau, Elizabeth; Schwarz-Watts, Donna (2017): Internet sexual solicitation of children. A proposed typology of offenders based on their chats, e-mails, and social network posts. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 77–89. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1241309.
- Doty, Nathan Daniel; Willoughby, Brian L. B.; Lindahl, Kristin M.; Malik, Neena M. (2010): Sexuality related social support among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1134–1147. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9566-x.
- Doughty, Adam H.; Kane, Lindsey M. (2010): Teaching abuse-protection skills to people with intellectual, disabilities. A review of the literature. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 31 (2), S. 331–337. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2009.12.007.
- Edwards, Rachel; Whittaker, Mette Kristensen; Beckett, Richard; Bishopp, Daz; Bates, Andrew (2012): Adolescents who have sexually harmed. An evaluation of a specialist treatment programme. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 91–111. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.635317.
- Elliott, Ian A.; Findlater, Donald; Hughes, Teresa (2010): Practice report. A review of e-Safety remote computer monitoring for UK sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003686870.

- Ellis, Wendy E.; Chung-Hall, Janet; Dumas, Tara M. (2013): The role of peer group aggression in predicting adolescent dating violence and relationship quality. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 487–499. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9797-0.
- Embregts, P.; Bogaard, K. van den; Hendriks, L.; Heestermans, M.; Schuitemaker, M.; Wouwe, H. van (2010): Sexual risk assessment for people with intellectual disabilities. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 31 (3), S. 760–767. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2010.01.018.
- Everson, Mark D.; Faller, Kathleen Coulborn (2012): Base rates, multiple indicators, and comprehensive forensic evaluations. Why sexualized behavior still counts in assessments of child sexual abuse allegations. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (1), S. 45–71. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.642470.
- Fader Wilkenfeld, B.; Ballan, Michelle S. (2011): Educators' Attitudes and Beliefs Towards the Sexuality of Individuals with Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (4), S. 351–361. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9211-y.
- Felson, Richard B.; Cundiff, Patrick R. (2014): Sexual assault as a crime against young people. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 273–284. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0127-8.
- Fernet, Mylene; Hébert, Martine; Paradis, Alison (2016): Conflict resolution patterns and violence perpetration in adolescent couples. A gender-sensitive mixed-methods approach. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 51–59. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.02.004.
- Fitzpatrick, Kevin M.; Dulin, Akilah; Piko, Bettina (2010): Bullying and depressive symptomatology among low-income, African-American youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 634–645. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9426-8.
- Flannery, Dustin D.; Stephens, Clare L.; Thompson, Amy D. (2016): The Impact of High-Profile Sexual Abuse Cases in the Media on a Pediatric Emergency Department. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 627–635. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1187697.
- Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Plummer, Carol (2010): Cultural issues in disclosures of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (5), S. 491–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.512520.
- Foshee, Vangie A.; Benefield, Thad; Dixon, Kimberly S.; Chang, Ling-Yin; Senkomago, Virginia; Ennett, Susan T. et al. (2015): The effects of moms and teens for safe dates: a dating abuse prevention program for adolescents exposed to domestic violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 995–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0272-6.
- Franklin, Anita; Smeaton, Emilie (2017): Recognising and responding to young people with learning disabilities who experience, or are at risk of, child sexual exploitation in the UK. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 474–481. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.11.009.
- Frías, Sonia M.; Erviti, Joaquina (2014): Gendered experiences of sexual abuse of teenagers and children in Mexico. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (4), S. 776–787.
- Gakhal, Baldeesh Kaur; Brown, Sarah J. (2011): A comparison of the general public's, forensic professionals' and students' attitudes towards female sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 105–116. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.540678.
- Geary, Jan; Lambie, Ian; Seymour, Fred (2011): Consumer perspectives of New Zealand community treatment programmes for sexually abusive youth. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 181–195. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003778693.
- Gilliam, Melissa; Jagoda, Patrick; Jaworski, Erin; Hebert, Luciana E.; Lyman, Phoebe; Wilson, M. Claire (2015): "Because if we don't talk about it, how are we going to prevent it?". Lucidity, a narrative-based digital game about sexual violence. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (4), S. 391–404. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1123147.
- Glasgow, David (2010): The potential of digital evidence to contribute to risk assessment of internet offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 87–106. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903428839.
- Goldman, Juliette D. G.; Grimbeek, Peter (2015): Preservice teachers' sources of information on mandatory reporting of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 238–258. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1009607.

- Goodrum, Nada M.; Armistead, Lisa P.; Tully, Erin C.; Cook, Sarah L.; Skinner, Donald (2017): Parenting and youth sexual risk in context. The role of community factors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 57, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.013.
- Gowen, L. Kris; Wings-Yanez, Nichole (2014): Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, and Questioning Youths' Perspectives of Inclusive School-Based Sexuality Education. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), S. 788–800.
- Graham, Laurie M.; Lanier, Paul; Johnson-Motoyama, Michelle (2016): National profile of Latino/Latina children reported to the child welfare system for sexual abuse. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 66, S. 18–27. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2016.04.008.
- Gray, Jacqueline M. (2014): What constitutes a “reasonable belief” in consent to sex? A thematic analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 337–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.900122.
- Griffin, Helen Louise; Vettor, Shannon (2012): Predicting sexual re-offending in a UK sample of adolescents with intellectual disabilities. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 64–80. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.617013.
- Grossi, Laura M.; Lee, Austin F.; Schuler, Ann; Ryan, Julie L.; Prentky, Robert A. (2016): Sexualized behaviors in cohorts of children in the child welfare system. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 52, S. 49–61. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.12.014.
- Gwirayi, Pesanayi (2013): The prevalence of child sexual abuse among secondary school pupils in Gweru, Zimbabwe. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 253–263. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.723755.
- Haboush, Karen L.; Alyan, Hala (2013): "Who can you tell?" Features of Arab culture that influence conceptualization and treatment of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 499–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800935.
- Hackett, Simon; Carpenter, John; Patsios, Demi; Szilassy, Eszter (2013): Interprofessional and interagency training for working with young people with harmful sexual behaviours. An evaluation of outcomes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 329–344. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.753122.
- Hall, Charlotte L.; Hogue, Todd E.; Guo, Kun (2014): Gaze patterns to child figures reflect deviant sexual preference in child sex offenders—a first glance. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 303–317. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.931475.
- Harden, K. Paige; Mendle, Jane (2011): Adolescent sexual activity and the development of delinquent behavior: the role of relationship context. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 825–838. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9601-y.
- Hatchard, Christine J.; Goodwin, Jamie L.; Siddall, Eryn; Muniz, Lauren (2017): Perceptions of Abusive Parenting Behaviors. A Preliminary Exploration Into the Underrecognition of Mother-Daughter Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (4), S. 428–441. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1300971.
- Hay, Carter; Meldrum, Ryan (2010): Bullying victimization and adolescent self-harm: testing hypotheses from general strain theory. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (5), S. 446–459. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9502-0.
- Henry, Olivia; Mandeville-Norden, Rebecca; Hayes, Elizabeth; Egan, Vincent (2010): Do internet-based sexual offenders reduce to normal, inadequate and deviant groups? In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 33–46. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903454132.
- Hilberink, Sander R.; Kruijver, Egbert; Wiegerink, Diana J. H. G.; Vliet Vlieland, Thea P. M. (2013): A Pilot Implementation of an Intervention to Promote Sexual Health in Adolescents and Young Adults in Rehabilitation. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 31 (4), S. 373–392. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9288-6.
- Horn, Joan van; Eisenberg, Mara; Nicholls McNaughton, Carol; Mulder, Jules; Webster, Stephen; Paskell, Caroline et al. (2015): Stop It Now! A Pilot Study Into the Limits and Benefits of a Free Helpline Preventing Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 853–872. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088914.
- Houser, John J.; Mayeux, Lara; Cross, Cassandra (2015): Peer status and aggression as predictors of dating popularity in adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 683–695. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0174-z.
- Hovey, Angela; Stalker, Carol A.; Schachter, Candice L.; Teram, Eli; Lasiuk, Gerri (2011): Practical ways psychotherapy can support physical healthcare experiences for male survivors of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 37–57. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.539963.

- Jackson, Vicki; Browne, Kevin; Joseph, Stephen (2016): The prevalence of childhood victimization experienced outside of the family. Findings from an English prevalence study. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 51, S. 343–357. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.08.006.
- Jaffe, Anna E.; Cranston, Christopher C.; Shadlow, Joanna O. (2012): Parenting in females exposed to intimate partner violence and childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 684–700. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.726698.
- Jennings, Wesley G.; Richards, Tara N.; Tomsich, Elizabeth; Gover, Angela R. (2015): Investigating the Role of Child Sexual Abuse in Intimate Partner Violence Victimization and Perpetration in Young Adulthood From a Propensity Score Matching Approach. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 659–681. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1057665.
- Jin, Yichen; Chen, Jingqi; Yu, Buyi (2016): Knowledge and Skills of Sexual Abuse Prevention. A Study on School-Aged Children in Beijing, China. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 686–696. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1199079.
- Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D.; Sanders, Stephanie A.; Dennis, Barbara; Reece, Michael (2014): Gender Differences in Heterosexual College Students' Conceptualizations and Indicators of Sexual Consent. Implications for Contemporary Sexual Assault Prevention Education. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (8), S. 904–916.
- Katz, Carmit (2013): Internet-related child sexual abuse. What children tell us in their testimonies. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (9), S. 1536–1542. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2013.06.006.
- Kenny, Maureen C. (2010): Child sexual abuse education with ethnically diverse families. A preliminary analysis. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 32 (7), S. 981–989. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2010.03.025.
- Kenny, Maureen C.; Wurtele, Sandy K.; Alonso, Laura (2012): Evaluation of a personal safety program with Latino preschoolers. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (4), S. 368–385. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.675426.
- Kettleborough, Danielle G.; Merdian, Hannah L. (2017): Gateway to offending behaviour. Permission-giving thoughts of online users of child sexual exploitation material. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 19–32. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1231852.
- Kisanga, Felix; Nystrom, Lennarth; Hogan, Nora; Emmelin, Maria (2011): Child sexual abuse. Community concerns in urban Tanzania. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (2), S. 196–217. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.555356.
- Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2010): Sexually coercive behavior in male youth: population survey of general and specific risk factors. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1161–1169. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9572-9.
- Knoll, James (2010): Teacher sexual misconduct. Grooming patterns and female offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (4), S. 371–386. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.495047.
- Koo, Kelly H.; Stephens, Kari A.; Lindgren, Kristen P.; George, William H. (2012): Misogyny, acculturation, and ethnic identity: relation to rape-supportive attitudes in Asian American college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1005–1014. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9729-1.
- Kuhle, Laura F.; Schlinzig, Eliza; Kaiser, Gerd; Amelung, Till; Konrad, Anna; Röhle, Robert; Beier, Klaus M. (2017): The association of sexual preference and dynamic risk factors with undetected child pornography offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 3–18. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1201157.
- Kwhali, Josephine; Martin, Linda; Brady, Geraldine; Brown, Sarah J. (2017): Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation. Knowledge, Confidence and Training within a Contemporary UK Social Work Practice and Policy Context. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2208–2226. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw154.
- Lambie, Ian; Price, Mnthali (2015): Transitioning youth with sexually harmful behaviour back into the community. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 244–265. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.873829.
- Lambine, Mackenzie E. (2012): Unsafe in the Ivory Tower. The sexual victimization of college women. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (3), S. 375–376. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.711657.
- Lampert, Jo (2012): Sh-h-h-h. Representations of perpetrators of sexual child abuse in picturebooks. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 177–185. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.609048.

- Lehrer, Jocelyn A.; Lehrer, Evelyn L.; Koss, Mary P. (2013): Unwanted sexual experiences in young men: evidence from a survey of university students in Chile. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (2), S. 213–223. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0004-x.
- Lin, Danhua; Li, Xiaoming; Fan, Xinghua; Fang, Xiaoyi (2011): Child sexual abuse and its relationship with health risk behaviors among rural children and adolescents in Hunan, China. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (9), S. 680–687. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2011.05.006.
- Livingston, Jennifer A.; Testa, Maria; Windle, Michael; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2015): Sexual risk at first coitus. Does alcohol make a difference? In: *Journal of Adolescence* 43, S. 148–158. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.05.018.
- Lopez, Silvia; Faro, Concepcio; Lopetegui, Lourdes; Pujol-Ribera, Enriqueta; Monteagudo, Monica; Avecilla-Palau, Angels et al. (2017): Child and Adolescent Sexual Abuse in Women Seeking Help for Sexual and Reproductive Mental Health Problems. Prevalence, Characteristics, and Disclosure. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 246–269. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1288186.
- Lopez, Vera; Kopak, Albert; Robillard, Alyssa; Gillmore, Mary Rogers; Holliday, Rhonda C.; Braithwaite, Ronald L. (2011): Pathways to sexual risk taking among female adolescent detainees. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (8), S. 945–957. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9623-5.
- Low, Sabina; Polanin, Joshua R.; Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): The role of social networks in physical and relational aggression among young adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1078–1089. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9933-5.
- Luder, Marie-Thérèse; Pittet, Isabelle; Berchtold, André; Akre, Christina; Michaud, Pierre-André; Surís, Joan-Carles (2011): Associations between online pornography and sexual behavior among adolescents: myth or reality? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1027–1035. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9714-0.
- Lund, Emily M.; Hammond, Marilyn (2014): Single-Session Intervention for Abuse Awareness Among People with Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 99–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9335-3.
- MacDonald, Jo-Ann; Gagnon, Anita J.; Mitchell, Claudia; Di Meglio, Giuseppina; Rennick, Janet E.; Cox, Joseph (2011): Asking to listen. Towards a youth perspective on sexual health education and needs. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 443–457. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595268.
- Makin-Byrd, Kerry; Bierman, Karen L. (2013): Individual and family predictors of the perpetration of dating violence and victimization in late adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 536–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9810-7.
- Makura, Alfred Henry; Zireva, Davison (2013): School heads and mentors in cahoots? Challenges to teaching practice in Zimbabwean teacher education programmes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 3–16. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.573583.
- Mallet, Pascal; Herbe, Dominique (2011): Does knowledge about sexuality prevent adolescents from developing rape-supportive beliefs? In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 48 (4), S. 372–380. DOI: 10.1080/00224491003794048.
- Man-Ging, Carlos Ignacio; Bohm, Bettina; Fuchs, Katharina Anna; Witte, Susanne; Frick, Eckhard (2015): Improving Empathy in the Prevention of Sexual Abuse Against Children and Youngsters. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (7), S. 796–815. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1077366.
- Mannix, Karyn; Dawson, David L.; Beckley, Kerry (2013): The implicit theories of male child sexual offenders residing in a high secure psychiatric hospital. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 264–274. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.732616.
- Manson, William (2015): “Keeping Children Safe”. The Child Sex Offender Disclosure Scheme in Scotland. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 43–55. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.950352.
- Marquez-Flores, Maria Mercedes; Marquez-Hernandez, Veronica V.; Granados-Gamez, Genoveva (2016): Teachers' knowledge and beliefs about child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 538–555. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1189474.
- Marriott, Clare; Hamilton-Giachritsis, Catherine; Harrop, Chris (2014): Factors Promoting Resilience Following Childhood Sexual Abuse. A Structured, Narrative Review of the Literature. In: *Child Abuse Review* 23 (1), S. 17–34. DOI: 10.1002/car.2258.
- Marshall, W. L.; Marshall, L. E.; Kingston, Drew A. (2011): Are the cognitive distortions of child molesters in need of treatment? In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 118–129. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.580572.

- Martinello, Emily (2015): Reviewing Risks Factors of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities as Perpetrators of Sexually Abusive Behaviors. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 33 (2), S. 269–278. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9365-5.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa (2015): Prevalence of dating violence among sexual minority youth: variation across gender, sexual minority identity and gender of sexual partners. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 211–224. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0089-0.
- McCartan, Fiona Mairead; Law, Heather; Murphy, Maeve; Bailey, Susan (2011): Child and adolescent females who present with sexually abusive behaviours. A 10-year UK prevalence study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 4–14. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.488302.
- McManus, Michelle Ann; Almond, Louise (2014): Trends of indecent images of children and child sexual offences between 2005/2006 and 2012/2013 within the United Kingdom. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 142–155. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.893031.
- McManus, Michelle Ann; Long, Matthew L.; Alison, Laurence; Almond, Louise (2014): Factors associated with contact child sexual abuse in a sample of indecent image offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 368–384. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927009.
- Mejia, Pamela; Cheyne, Andrew; Dorfman, Lori (2012): News coverage of child sexual abuse and prevention, 2007–2009. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (4), S. 470–487. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.692465.
- Merdian, Hannah Lena; Curtis, Cate; Thakker, Jo; Wilson, Nick; Boer, Douglas Pieter (2013): The three dimensions of online child pornography offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 121–132. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.611898.
- Miller, Shari; Williams, Jason; Cutbush, Stacey; Gibbs, Deborah; Clinton-Sherrod, Monique; Jones, Sarah (2013): Dating violence, bullying, and sexual harassment: longitudinal profiles and transitions over time. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 607–618. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9914-8.
- Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Ybarra, Michele L.; Korchmaros, Josephine D. (2014): Sexual harassment among adolescents of different sexual orientations and gender identities. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (2), S. 280–295.
- Morris, Matthew C.; Kouros, Chrystyna D.; Janecek, Kim; Freeman, Rachel; Mielock, Alyssa; Garber, Judy (2017): Community-level moderators of a school-based childhood sexual assault prevention program. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 295–306. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.10.005.
- Murphy, Meghan (2015): How organisational culture influences teachers' support of openly gay, lesbian and bisexual students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 263–275.
- Nishina, Adrienne (2012): Microcontextual characteristics of peer victimization experiences and adolescents' daily well-being. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 191–201. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9669-z.
- Novak, Jamie; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Partner Violence During Adolescence and Young Adulthood: Individual and Relationship Level Risk Factors. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (9), S. 1849–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0484-4.
- Olafson, Erna (2012): A call for field-relevant research about child forensic interviewing for child protection. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (1), S. 109–129. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.642469.
- Oliver, Brian E.; Holmes, Laura (2015): Female Juvenile Sexual Offenders. Understanding Who They Are and Possible Steps That May Prevent Some Girls From Offending. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 698–715. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1058875.
- Ollis, Debbie (2010): 'I haven't changed bigots but ...'. Reflections on the impact of teacher professional learning in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 217–230. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666523.
- Parent, Sylvie; Demers, Guylaine (2011): Sexual abuse in sport. A model to prevent and protect athletes. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 120–133. DOI: 10.1002/car.1135.
- Peacock, Dean; Barker, Gary (2014): Working with Men and Boys to Prevent Gender-based Violence. Principles, Lessons Learned, and Ways Forward. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (5), S. 578–599. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14558240.

- Pearce, Jenny J. (2014): 'What's Going On' to Safeguard Children and Young People from Child Sexual Exploitation. A Review of Local Safeguarding Children Boards' Work to Protect Children from Sexual Exploitation. In: *Child Abuse Review* 23 (3), S. 159–170. DOI: 10.1002/car.2269.
- Perdahli Fis, Nese; Arman, Ayse; Kalaca, Sibel; Berkem, Meral (2010): Psychiatric evaluation of sexual abuse cases. A clinical representative sample from Turkey. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 32 (10), S. 1285–1290. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2010.04.020.
- Piccigallo, Jaqueline R.; Lilley, Terry G.; Miller, Susan L. (2012): "It's Cool to Care about Sexual Violence". Men's Experiences with Sexual Assault Prevention. In: *Men and Masculinities* 15 (5), S. 507–525. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X12458590.
- Reyes, H. Luz McNaughton; Foshee, Vangie A.; Niolon, Phyllis Holditch; Reidy, Dennis E.; Hall, Jeffrey E. (2016): Gender Role Attitudes and Male Adolescent Dating Violence Perpetration: Normative Beliefs as Moderators. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 350–360. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0278-0.
- Russell, Brenda L.; Oswald, Debra L. (2016): When Sexism Cuts Both Ways. Predictors of Tolerance of Sexual Harassment of Men. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (5), S. 524–544. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15602745.
- Samms, Kimika M.; Cholewa, Blaire E. (2014): Exploring the context of child sexual abuse in Jamaica. Addressing the deficits. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 115–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870948.
- Sanberk, Ismail; Emen, Meltem; Kabakci, Duygu (2017): An Investigation of Socially Advantaged and Disadvantaged Turkish Mothers' Views About Training on Preventing Children From Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 288–307. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1292338.
- Schober, Daniel J.; Fawcett, Stephen B.; Bernier, Jetta (2012): The Enough Abuse Campaign. Building the movement to prevent child sexual abuse in Massachusetts. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (4), S. 456–469. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.675423.
- Schönbucher, Verena; Maier, Thomas; Mohler-Kuo, Meichun; Schnyder, Ulrich; Landolt, Markus A. (2014): Adolescent perspectives on social support received in the aftermath of sexual abuse: a qualitative study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (3), S. 571–586. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0230-x.
- Schonfeld, David J.; Adams, Ryan E.; Fredstrom, Bridget K.; Tomlin, Ricarda; Voyce, Charlene; Vaughn, Lisa M. (2012): Social-Emotional Learning in Grades 3 to 6 and the Early Onset of Sexual Behavior. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 9 (2), S. 178–186. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0077-7.
- Senn, Charlene Y. (2011): An imperfect feminist journey. Reflections on the process to develop an effective sexual assault resistance programme for university women. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (1), S. 121–137. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510386094.
- Seto, Michael C.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2015): Viewing child pornography: prevalence and correlates in a representative community sample of young Swedish men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 67–79. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0244-4.
- Smothers, Melissa Kraemer; Smothers, D. Brian (2011): A sexual assault primary prevention model with diverse urban youth. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (6), S. 708–727. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.622355.
- Steinhart, Katharina; Kaenel, Andreas von; Cerruti, Stella; Chequer, Pedro; Gomes, Rebeca; Herlt, Claudia; Horstick, Olaf (2013): International networking for sexuality education. A politically sensitive subject. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (6), S. 630–643. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.784194.
- Stewart, Catherine Carolyn (2012): Beyond the call. Mothers of children with developmental disabilities responding to sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 701–727. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.722182.
- Tishelman, Amy C.; Geffner, Robert (2010): Forensic, cultural, and systems issues in child sexual abuse cases--part 2. Research and practitioner issues. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (6), S. 609–617. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.523514.
- Toomey, Russell B.; McGuire, Jenifer K.; Russell, Stephen T. (2012): Heteronormativity, school climates, and perceived safety for gender nonconforming peers. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 187–196. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.03.001.
- Towns, Alison J.; Scott, Hazel (2013): 'I couldn't even dress the way I wanted.' Young women talk of 'ownership' by boyfriends. An opportunity for the prevention of domestic violence? In: *Feminism & Psychology* 23 (4), S. 536–555. DOI: 10.1177/0959353513481955.

- Turner, Daniel; Hoyer, Juergen; Schmidt, Alexander F.; Klein, Verena; Briken, Peer (2016): Risk Factors for Sexual Offending in Men Working With Children: A Community-Based Survey. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (7), S. 1851–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0746-y.
- van Ouysel, Joris; Ponnet, Koen; Walrave, Michel (2017): The associations of adolescents' dating violence victimization, well-being and engagement in risk behaviors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 66–71. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.005.
- Vandenbosch, Laura; Eggermont, Steven (2013): Sexualization of Adolescent Boys. In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 283–306. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13477866.
- Williams, Matthew L.; Hudson, Kirsty (2013): Public perceptions of internet, familial and localised sexual grooming. Predicting perceived prevalence and safety. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 218–235. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.705341.
- Winters, Georgia M.; Kaylor, Leah E.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2017): Sexual offenders contacting children online. An examination of transcripts of sexual grooming. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 62–76. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1271146.
- Wissink, Inge B.; Vugt, Eveline van; Moonen, Xavier; Stams, Geert Jan; Hendriks, Jan (2015): Sexual abuse involving children with an intellectual disability (ID): a narrative review. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 36, S. 20–35. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2014.09.007.
- Wurtele, Sandy K.; Kenny, Maureen C. (2010): Partnering with parents to prevent childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (2), S. 130–152. DOI: 10.1002/car.1112.
- Yoder, Jamie R.; Hansen, Jesse; Ruch, Donna; Hodge, Ashleigh (2016): Effects of School-Based Risk and Protective Factors on Treatment Success Among Youth Adjudicated of a Sexual Crime. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 310–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1137668.
- Zhang, Wenjing; Chen, Jingqi; Feng, Yanan; Li, Jingyi; Zhao, Xiaoxia; Luo, Xiaoling (2013): Young children's knowledge and skills related to sexual abuse prevention. A pilot study in Beijing, China. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 623–630.

4. Fachkräfte

4.1. Intern

- Airton, Lee (2014): Hatred Haunting Hallways. Teacher Education and the Badness of Homophobia(s). In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 387–399.
- Anderson, Eric (2013): Masculinity and homophobia in high school and college sports. A personal journey from coach to researcher. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 120–131.
- Atkinson, Becky (2012): Apple Jumper, Teacher Babe, and Bland Uniformer Teachers: Fashioning Feminine Teacher Bodies. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 93–104.
- Boas, Erica M. (2012): Walking the Line. Teaching, Being, and Thinking Sexuality in Elementary School. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 131–144.
- Britzman, Deborah P. (2012): Queer Pedagogy and Its Strange Techniques. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 292–308.
- Erooga, Marcus (2012): Understanding and Responding to People Who Sexually Abuse Children Whilst Employed In Trust. An Overview of the Relevant Literature - Part One: Offenders. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them*. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 7–26.
- Erooga, Marcus; Allnock, Debra; Telford, David (2012): Sexual abuse of children by people in organisations. What offenders can teach us about protection. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to*

prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 63–84.

Green, Jo (2012): Avoiding and managing allegations against staff. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 170–187.

Jennings, Todd (2014): Is the Mere Mention Enough? Representation Across Five Different Venues of Educator Preparation. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 400–413.

Kalmus, Veronika; Feilitzen, Cecilia von; Siibak, Andra (2012): Effectiveness of teacher's and peers mediation in supporting opportunities and reducing risks online. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 245–256.

Lewis, Mel Michelle (2012): Pedagogy and the Sista' Professor. Teaching Black Queer Feminist Studies through the Self. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 33–40.

McCoy, Sheltreese D. (2014): Some of Us Are Brave. A Review of the Research on the Experience of Black LGBT Professors in Colleges and Universities in the United States. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 439–452.

Migdalek, Jack (2014): Challenging Gendered Practices Through Drama. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 414–425.

Nunez, Isabel (2012): Introduction. Teaching as Whole Self. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 85–88.

Ollis, Debbie (2013): Planning and delivering interventions to promote gender and sexuality. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 145–161.

Pascoe, C. J. (2012): Becoming Mr. Cougar. Institutionalizing Heterosexuality and Homophobia at River High. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 145–157.

Pendleton Jiménez, Karleen (2014): Off the Script. A Study of Techniques for Uncovering Gender-Bending Truths in the Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 257–271.

Rivers, Ian; Duncan, Neil (2013): Discourses of sexuality and gender considered. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 162–168.

Rofes, Eric E. (2012): Bound and Gagged. Sexual Silences, Gender Conformity, and the Gay Male Teacher. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 105–121.

Roth, Jillian R.; Robinson, Lea; O'Bryant, Camille; Griffin, Pat (2014): 3 to 1. Four Women Navigating the Intersections of Racism, Sexism, Homophobia, and Heterosexism in Intercollegiate Sport. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 453–463.

Saltzburg, Susan (2015): Pedagogy for unpacking heterosexist and cisgender bias in social work education in the United States. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 205–222.

Sullivan, Joe; Quayle, Ethel (2012): Manipulation styles of abusers who work with children. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 85–98.

- Larremore, April (2016): Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom.
- Murray, Olivia J. (2014): *Queer Inclusion in Teacher Education. Bridging Theory, Research, and Practice*. London: Taylor & Francis Ltd.
- Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2012): Pervasive vulnerabilities. Sexual harassment in school. New York: Peter Lang (Adolescent cultures, school & society, v. 54).
- Erooga, Marcus (Hg.) (2012): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them*. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children).
- Abbott, Keeley; Ellis, Sonja J.; Abbott, Rachel (2016): "We've got a lack of family values". An examination of how teachers formulate and justify their approach to teaching sex and relationships education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (6), S. 678–691. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1169398.
- Allen, Louisa (2011): 'Undoing' the self. Should heterosexual teachers 'come out' in the university classroom? In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 19 (1), S. 79–95. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2011.548990.
- Almond, Tracy Jane (2014): Working with children and young people with harmful sexual behaviours. Exploring impact on practitioners and sources of support. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 333–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836576.
- Åmot, Ingvild; Ytterhus, Borgunn (2014): 'Talking bodies'. Power and counter-power between children and adults in day care. In: *Childhood* 21 (2), S. 260–273. DOI: 10.1177/0907568213490971.
- Bowman, Rachel A.; Scotti, Joseph R.; Morris, Tracy L. (2010): Sexual abuse prevention. A training program for developmental disabilities service providers. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 119–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003614718.
- Britzman, Deborah P. (2010): Teachers and Eros. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 325–330. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491627.
- Caldas, Stephen J.; Betsy, Mary Lou (2014): The sexual maltreatment of students with disabilities in American school settings. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (4), S. 345–366. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.906530.
- Clark, Caroline T. (2010): Preparing LGBTQ-allies and combating homophobia in a U.S. teacher education program. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (3), S. 704–713. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.10.006.
- Cocker, Christine; Hafford-Letchfield, Trish (2010): Out and Proud? Social Work's Relationship with Lesbian and Gay Equality. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (6), S. 1996–2008.
- Cohen, Jacqueline N.; Byers, E. Sandra; Sears, Heather A. (2011): Factors affecting Canadian teachers' willingness to teach sexual health education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615606.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G.M. (2015): Understanding teachers' responses to enactments of sexual and gender stigma at school. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 48, S. 34–43. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.02.002.
- Craig, Shelley L.; Dentato, Michael P.; Messinger, Lori; McInroy, Lauren B. (2016): Educational Determinants of Readiness to Practise with LGBTQ Clients. Social Work Students Speak Out. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (1), S. 115–134. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu107.
- D'Alton, Paul; Guilfoyle, Michael; Randall, Patrick (2013): Roman Catholic Clergy who have sexually abused children: Their perceptions of their developmental experience. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 698–702.
- Dessel, Adrienne B.; Kulick, Alex; Wernick, Laura J.; Sullivan, Daniel (2017): The importance of teacher support. Differential impacts by gender and sexuality. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 136–144. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.002.
- Doel, Mark; Allmark, Peter; Conway, Paul; Cowburn, Malcolm; Flynn, Margaret; Nelson, Pete; Tod, Angela (2010): Professional Boundaries. Crossing a Line or Entering the Shadows? In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (6), S. 1866–1889.
- Endo, Hidehiro; Reece-Miller, Paul Chamness; Santavicca, Nicholas (2010): Surviving in the trenches. A narrative inquiry into queer teachers' experiences and identity. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (4), S. 1023–1030. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.10.045.

- Eriksson, Elisabet; Lindmark, Gunilla; Axemo, Pia; Haddad, Beverley; Ahlberg, Beth Maina (2010): Ambivalence, silence and gender differences in church leaders' HIV-prevention messages to young people in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 103–114. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903141192.
- Fader Wilkenfeld, B.; Ballan, Michelle S. (2011): Educators' Attitudes and Beliefs Towards the Sexuality of Individuals with Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (4), S. 351–361. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9211-y.
- Ferfolja, Tania (2010): Lesbian teachers, harassment and the workplace. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (3), S. 408–414. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.05.007.
- Franklin, Anita; Smeaton, Emilie (2017): Recognising and responding to young people with learning disabilities who experience, or are at risk of, child sexual exploitation in the UK. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 474–481. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.11.009.
- Fromuth, Mary Ellen; Kelly, David B.; Brallier, Courtney; Williams, Matthew; Benson, Kate (2016): Effects of duration on perceptions of teacher sexual misconduct. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (2), S. 159–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1122692.
- Gerouki, Margarita (2010): The boy who was drawing princesses. Primary teachers' accounts of children's non-conforming behaviours. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 335–348. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515092.
- Gill, Michael (2010): Rethinking sexual abuse, questions of consent, and intellectual disability. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (3), S. 201–213. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0019-9.
- Goldman, Juliette (2012): A critical analysis of UNESCO's International Technical Guidance on school-based education for puberty and sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 199–218. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.609051.
- Goldman, Juliette D. G.; Grimbeek, Peter (2015): Preservice teachers' sources of information on mandatory reporting of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 238–258. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1009607.
- Gray, Emily M. (2013): Coming out as a lesbian, gay or bisexual teacher. Negotiating private and professional worlds. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (6), S. 702–714. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.807789.
- Green, Lorraine (2016): The Trouble with Touch? New Insights and Observations on Touch for Social Work and Social Care. In: *The British Journal of Social Work*, bcw071. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw071.
- Hackett, Simon; Carpenter, John; Patsios, Demi; Szilassy, Eszter (2013): Interprofessional and interagency training for working with young people with harmful sexual behaviours. An evaluation of outcomes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 329–344. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.753122.
- Hardie, Ann (2011): Lesbian teachers and students. Issues and dilemmas of being 'out' in primary school. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–10. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615595.
- Harrison, Lyn; Ollis, Debbie (2014): Stepping out of our comfort zones. Pre-service teachers' responses to a critical analysis of gender/power relations in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 318–331. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1023284.
- Hilberink, Sander R.; Kruijver, Egbert; Wiegerink, Diana J. H. G.; Vliet Vlieland, Thea P. M. (2013): A Pilot Implementation of an Intervention to Promote Sexual Health in Adolescents and Young Adults in Rehabilitation. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 31 (4), S. 373–392. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9288-6.
- Jackson, Sue; Weatherall, Ann (2010): The (Im)possibilities of Feminist School Based Sexuality Education. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 20 (2), S. 166–185.
- Johnson, Rebecca L.; Sendall, Marguerite C.; McCuaig, Louise A. (2014): Primary schools and the delivery of relationships and sexuality education. The experience of Queensland teachers. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 359–374. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.909351.
- Knoll, James (2010): Teacher sexual misconduct. Grooming patterns and female offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (4), S. 371–386. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.495047.
- Koster, Shirley (2011): The self-managed heart. Teaching gender and doing emotional labour in a higher education institution. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 19 (1), S. 61–77. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2011.548988.

- Kwhali, Josephine; Martin, Linda; Brady, Geraldine; Brown, Sarah J. (2017): Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation. Knowledge, Confidence and Training within a Contemporary UK Social Work Practice and Policy Context. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2208–2226. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw154.
- Lavie-Ajayi, Maya (2017): "It Will Continue to Embarrass Me on Some Level, and I Think that's OK". Conceptualising Embarrassment in Discussions about Sex between Social Workers and Service Users. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2282–2299. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw116.
- Makura, Alfred Henry; Zireva, Davison (2013): School heads and mentors in cahoots? Challenges to teaching practice in Zimbabwean teacher education programmes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 3–16. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.573583.
- Malins, Pamela (2016): How inclusive is "inclusive education" in the Ontario elementary classroom? Teachers talk about addressing diverse gender and sexual identities. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 54, S. 128–138. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.11.004.
- Man-Ging, Carlos Ignacio; Bohm, Bettina; Fuchs, Katharina Anna; Witte, Susanne; Frick, Eckhard (2015): Improving Empathy in the Prevention of Sexual Abuse Against Children and Youngsters. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (7), S. 796–815. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1077366.
- Marquez-Flores, Maria Mercedes; Marquez-Hernandez, Veronica V.; Granados-Gamez, Genoveva (2016): Teachers' knowledge and beliefs about child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 538–555. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1189474.
- Martin, Jennifer (2016): Child Sexual Abuse Images Online. Implications for Social Work Training and Practice. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (2), S. 372–388. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu116.
- Martino, Wayne J.; Cumming-Potvin, Wendy (2015): Teaching about "Princess Boys" or Not. The Case of One Male Elementary School Teacher and the Polemics of Gender Expression and Embodiment. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (1), S. 79–99. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14551278.
- Melville-Wiseman, Janet (2017): The Sexual Abuse of Vulnerable People by Registered Social Workers in England. An Analysis of the Health and Care Professions Council Fitness to Practise Cases. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2190–2207. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw150.
- Munoz-Laboy, Miguel; Murray, Laura R.; Wittlin, Natalie; Wilson, Patrick A.; Terto, Veriano; Parker, Richard (2011): Divine targets. Youth at the centre of Catholic and Pentecostal responses to HIV and AIDS in Brazil. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 657–668. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.565519.
- Murphy, Meghan (2015): How organisational culture influences teachers' support of openly gay, lesbian and bisexual students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 263–275.
- Nelson, Pete; Cowburn, Malcolm (2010): Social Work Admissions. Applicants with Criminal Convictions -The Challenge of Ethical Risk Assessment. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (4), S. 1081–1099.
- Nixon, David (2010): Discrimination, performance and recuperation. How teachers and pupils challenge and recover discourses of sexualities in schools. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (2), S. 145–151. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.05.003.
- O'Leary, P.; Tsui, M.-S.; Ruch, G. (2013): The Boundaries of the Social Work Relationship Revisited. Towards a Connected, Inclusive and Dynamic Conceptualisation. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 43 (1), S. 135–153. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcr181.
- Ollis, Debbie (2010): 'I haven't changed bigots but ...'. Reflections on the impact of teacher professional learning in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 217–230. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666523.
- Paakkari, Leena; Välimaa, Raili (2013): Ethical issues in the teaching and learning of health topics in schools. The conceptions of teacher trainees. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 34, S. 66–76. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2013.04.004.
- Parchomiuk, Monika (2012): Specialists and Sexuality of Individuals with Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (4), S. 407–419. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9249-x.
- Pebdani, Roxanna N. (2016): Attitudes of Group Home Employees Towards the Sexuality of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (3), S. 329–339. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9447-7.

- Preston, Marilyn J. (2015): 'They're just not mature right now': teachers' complicated perceptions of gender and anti-queer bullying. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 22–34. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1019665.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2012): Popular culture as emotional provocation. The material enactment of queer pedagogies in a high school classroom. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 511–522. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627728.
- Riggs, Angela D.; Rosenthal, Amy R.; Smith-Bonahue, Tina (2011): The impact of a combined cognitive–affective intervention on pre-service teachers' attitudes, knowledge, and anticipated professional behaviors regarding homosexuality and gay and lesbian issues. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 27 (1), S. 201–209. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.08.002.
- Rudoe, Naomi (2010): Lesbian teachers' identity, power and the public/private boundary. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (1), S. 23–36. DOI: 10.1080/14681810903491347.
- Rushbrooke, Elizabeth; Murray, Craig D.; Townsend, Samantha (2014): What difficulties are experienced by caregivers in relation to the sexuality of people with intellectual disabilities? A qualitative meta-synthesis. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 35 (4), S. 871–886. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2014.01.012.
- Sanjakdar, Fida (2013): Educating for sexual difference? Muslim teachers' conversations about homosexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (1), S. 16–29. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634154.
- Schaub, Jason; Willis, Paul; Dunk-West, Priscilla (2016): Accounting for Self, Sex and Sexuality in UK Social Workers' Knowledge Base. Findings from an Exploratory Study. In: *The British Journal of Social Work*, bcw015. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw015.
- Schmidt, Sandra J.; Chang, Shih-pei; Carolan-Silva, Aliah; Lockhart, John; Anagnostopoulos, Dorothea (2012): Recognition, responsibility, and risk. Pre-service teachers' framing and reframing of lesbian, gay, and bisexual social justice issues. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 28 (8), S. 1175–1184. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2012.07.002.
- Shelton, Stephanie Anne; Barnes, Meghan E. (2016): "Racism just isn't an issue anymore". Preservice teachers' resistances to the intersections of sexuality and race. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 55, S. 165–174. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2016.01.008.
- Sivis-Cetinkaya, Rahsan (2015): Turkish School Counselors' Experiences of Reporting Child Sexual Abuse: A Brief Report. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 908–921. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1084072.
- Spraitz, Jason D.; Bowen, Kendra N.; Arthurs, Shavonne (2017): Neutralisation and sexual abuse. A study of monks from one Benedictine Abbey. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 195–206. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1204471.
- Toledo, Annik van; Seymour, Fred (2016): Caregiver Needs Following Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 403–414. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1156206.
- Turner, Daniel; Hoyer, Juergen; Schmidt, Alexander F.; Klein, Verena; Briken, Peer (2016): Risk Factors for Sexual Offending in Men Working With Children: A Community-Based Survey. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (7), S. 1851–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0746-y.
- Walsh, Kerryann; Mathews, Ben; Rassafiani, Mehdi; Farrell, Ann; Butler, Des (2012): Understanding teachers' reporting of child sexual abuse. Measurement methods matter. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (9), S. 1937–1946. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2012.06.004.
- Willis, Paul; Ward, Nicki; Fish, Julie (2011): Searching for LGBT Carers. Mapping a Research Agenda in Social Work and Social Care. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 41 (7), S. 1304–1320.

4.2. Extern

- Migdalek, Jack (2014): Challenging Gendered Practices Through Drama. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 414–425.
- Albury, Kath (2013): Young people, media and sexual learning. Rethinking representation. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S32–S44. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.767194.

- Barron, Ian G.; Topping, Keith J. (2011): Sexual abuse prevention programme fidelity. Video analysis of interactions. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 134–151. DOI: 10.1002/car.1134.
- Carrion, Melissa L.; Jensen, Robin E. (2014): Curricular decision-making among public sex educators. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (6), S. 623–634. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919444.
- Clements, Hannah; Dawson, David L.; das Nair, Roshan (2014): Female-perpetrated sexual abuse. A review of victim and professional perspectives. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 197–215. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.798690.
- Craig, Shelley L.; Dentato, Michael P.; Messinger, Lori; McInroy, Lauren B. (2016): Educational Determinants of Readiness to Practise with LGBTQ Clients. Social Work Students Speak Out. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (1), S. 115–134. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu107.
- Gakhal, Baldeesh Kaur; Brown, Sarah J. (2011): A comparison of the general public's, forensic professionals' and students' attitudes towards female sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 105–116. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.540678.
- Goldman, Juliette (2011): External providers' sexuality education teaching and pedagogies for primary school students in Grade 1 to Grade 7. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (02), S. 155–174. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.558423.
- Goldman, Juliette (2012): A critical analysis of UNESCO's International Technical Guidance on school-based education for puberty and sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 199–218. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.609051.
- Kwhali, Josephine; Martin, Linda; Brady, Geraldine; Brown, Sarah J. (2017): Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation. Knowledge, Confidence and Training within a Contemporary UK Social Work Practice and Policy Context. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2208–2226. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw154.
- Lavie-Ajayi, Maya (2017): "It Will Continue to Embarrass Me on Some Level, and I Think that's OK". Conceptualising Embarrassment in Discussions about Sex between Social Workers and Service Users. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2282–2299. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw116.
- Makura, Alfred Henry; Zireva, Davison (2013): School heads and mentors in cahoots? Challenges to teaching practice in Zimbabwean teacher education programmes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 3–16. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.573583.
- Man-Ging, Carlos Ignacio; Bohm, Bettina; Fuchs, Katharina Anna; Witte, Susanne; Frick, Eckhard (2015): Improving Empathy in the Prevention of Sexual Abuse Against Children and Youngsters. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (7), S. 796–815. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1077366.
- Martin, Jennifer (2016): Child Sexual Abuse Images Online. Implications for Social Work Training and Practice. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (2), S. 372–388. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu116.
- Masson, H.; Hackett, Simon; Phillips, J.; Balfe, M. (2014): Looking Back on the Long-Term Fostering and Adoption of Children with Harmful Sexual Behaviours. Carers' Reflections on Their Experiences. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 44 (8), S. 2200–2217. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bct073.
- Melville-Wiseman, Janet (2017): The Sexual Abuse of Vulnerable People by Registered Social Workers in England. An Analysis of the Health and Care Professions Council Fitness to Practise Cases. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2190–2207. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw150.
- Schaub, Jason; Willis, Paul; Dunk-West, Priscilla (2016): Accounting for Self, Sex and Sexuality in UK Social Workers' Knowledge Base. Findings from an Exploratory Study. In: *The British Journal of Social Work*, bcw015. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw015.
- Wilkinson, Verity J.; Theodore, Kate; Raczka, Roman (2015): 'As Normal as Possible'. Sexual Identity Development in People with Intellectual Disabilities Transitioning to Adulthood. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 33 (1), S. 93–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9356-6.

4.3. Peers

- Kalmus, Veronika; Feilitzen, Cecilia von; Siibak, Andra (2012): Effectiveness of teacher's and peers mediation in supporting opportunities and reducing risks online. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.):

Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 245–256.

Berglas, Nancy F.; Angulo-Olaiz, Francisca; Jerman, Petra; Desai, Mona; Constantine, Norman A. (2014): Engaging Youth Perspectives on Sexual Rights and Gender Equality in Intimate Relationships as a Foundation for Rights-Based Sexuality Education. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (4), S. 288–298. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0148-7.

Brown, Graham; Sorenson, Anne; Hildebrand, Janina (2012): How they got it and how they wanted it. Marginalised young people's perspective on their experiences of sexual health education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 599–612. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634141.

5. Adressat_innen

5.1. Kinder

Barbovschi, Monica; Marinescu, Valentina; Velicu, Anca; Laszlo, Eva (2012): Meeting new contacts online. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 177–190.

Bauwens, Joke; Paus-Hasebrink, Ingrid; Ponte, Cristina; Dürager, Andrea (2012): Understanding digital inequality. The interplay between parental socialisation and children's development. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 257–272.

Boas, Erica M. (2012): Walking the Line. Teaching, Being, and Thinking Sexuality in Elementary School. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 131–144.

Bryan, Jennifer (2014): Tomboys, Sissies, and "That's So Gay". Exploring Gender and Sexuality Diversity in Early Childhood and Elementary Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 240–256.

Erooga, Marcus (2012): Understanding and Responding to People Who Sexually Abuse Children Whilst Employed In Trust. An Overview of the Relevant Literature - Part One: Offenders. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 7–26.

Erooga, Marcus; Allnock, Debra; Telford, David (2012): Sexual abuse of children by people in organisations. What offenders can teach us about protection. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 63–84.

Görzig, Anke (2012): Methodological framework. The EU Kids Online project. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 15–32.

Görzig, Anke; Mascheroni, Giovanna; Murru, Maria Francesca (2012): Varieties of access and use. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 59–72.

Hasebrink, Uwe (2012): Young European's online environments: a typology of user practices. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 127–140.

Helsper, Ellen (2012): Which children are fully online? In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 45–58.

Judge, Abigail; Graw Leary, Mary (2014): From the Streets to Cyberspace. The Effects of Technology in the Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children and Adolescents in the United States. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinkas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 180–214.

- Kalmus, Veronika; Feilitzen, Cecilia von; Siibak, Andra (2012): Effectiveness of teacher's and peers mediation in supporting opportunities and reducing risks online. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 245–256.
- Kirwil, Lucyna; Laouris, Yiannis (2012): Experimenting with the self online: a risky opportunity. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 113–126.
- Kupiainen, Reijo; Suoninen, Annikka; Nikunen, Kaarina (2012): Between public and private: privacy in social networking sites. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 99–112.
- Lampert, Claudia; Donoso, Verónica (2012): Bullying. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 141–150.
- Laurinavicius, Alfredas; Zukauskienė, Rita; Ustinaviciute, Laura (2012): Explaining vulnerability to risk and harm. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 297–308.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Görzig, Anke (2012): Sexting: the exchange of sexual messages online among European youth. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 151–164.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Haddon, Leslie (2012): Theoretical framework for children's internet use. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 1–14.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Hasebrink, Uwe; Görzig, Anke (2012): Towards a general model of determinants of risk and safety. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 323–338.
- O'Neill, Brian; Staksrud, Elisabeth (2012): Policy implications and recommendations. Now what? In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 339–354.
- Ogan, Christine; Karakus, Türkan; Kursun, Engin; Cagiltay, Kürsat; Kasikci, Duygu (2012): Cognitive interviewing and response to EU Kids Online survey questions. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 33–44.
- Pasquier, Dominique; Simoes, José Alberto; Kredens, Elodie (2012): Agents of mediation and sources of safety awareness: a comparative overview. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 219–230.
- Pruulmann-Vengerfeldt, Pille; Runnel, Pille (2012): Online opportunities. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 73–86.
- Pullen Sansfacon, Annie; Manning, Kimberley Ens (2015): Maximising research outcomes for trans children and their families in Canada inquiry. Using social action and other participatory methods of. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 223–236.
- Rovoliy, Antonis; Tsaliki, Liza (2012): Pornography. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 165–176.
- Ságvári, Bence; Galács, Anna (2012): Relating online practices, negative experiences and coping strategies. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 309–322.

- Smahel, David; Blinka, Lukás (2012): Expressive internet use among European children. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 191–204.
- Sullivan, Joe; Quayle, Ethel (2012): Manipulation styles of abusers who work with children. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them*. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 85–98.
- Thigpen, Jeffrey W. (2012): Childhood Sexuality. Exploring Culture as Context. In: Laura M. Carpenter und John D. DeLamater (Hg.): *Sex for life. From virginity to Viagra, how sexuality changes throughout our lives*. New York: New York University Press (Intersections), S. 45–69.
- Vandoninck, Sofie; d’Haenens, Leen; Segers, Katia (2012): Coping and resilience: children’s response to online risks. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 205–218.
- Whitlock, Reta Ugena (2014): LGBT Families and Southern Schools. Thinking About People, Place, and Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 75–89.
- Williams, Sian (2013): Sexual bullying in one local authority. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 60–74.
- Larremore, April (2016): Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom.
- Miller-Perrin, Cindy L.; Perrin, Robin D. (2013): *Child maltreatment. An introduction*. 3. ed. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Erooga, Marcus (Hg.) (2012): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them*. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children).
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Haddon, Leslie; Görzig, Anke (Hg.) (2012): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press.
- Alessi, Edward J.; Kahn, Sarilee; Chatterji, Sangeeta (2016): ‘The darkest times of my life’. Recollections of child abuse among forced migrants persecuted because of their sexual orientation and gender identity. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 51, S. 93–105.
- Allardyce, Stuart; Yates, Peter Michael (2013): Assessing Risk of Victim Crossover with Children and Young People who display Harmful Sexual Behaviours. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (4), S. 255–267. DOI: 10.1002/car.2277.
- Allbaugh, Lucy Jane; O’Dougherty Wright, Margaret; Atkins Seltmann, Larissa (2014): An exploratory study of domains of parenting concern among mothers who are childhood sexual abuse survivors. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (8), S. 885–899. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.960636.
- Allnock, Debra; Radford, Lorraine; Bunting, Lisa; Price, Avril; Morgan-Klein, Natalie; Ellis, Jane; Stafford, Anne (2012): In Demand. Therapeutic Services for Children and Young People Who Have Experienced Sexual Abuse. In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (5), S. 318–334. DOI: 10.1002/car.1205.
- Almond, Tracy Jane (2014): Working with children and young people with harmful sexual behaviours. Exploring impact on practitioners and sources of support. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 333–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836576.
- Åmot, Ingvild; Ytterhus, Borgunn (2014): ‘Talking bodies’. Power and counter-power between children and adults in day care. In: *Childhood* 21 (2), S. 260–273. DOI: 10.1177/0907568213490971.
- Aylaz, Rukuye; Yilmaz, Ulviye; Polat, Sevinç (2012): Effect of Difficulties Experienced by Parents of Autistic Children on Their Sexual Life. A Qualitative Study. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (4), S. 395–406. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9251-3.
- Bajaj, Monika (2012): Vesicular Genital Lesions in a Toddler – Is it Sexual Abuse? In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (5), S. 370–373. DOI: 10.1002/car.1188.
- Baratvand, Mahmood; Soodani, Mansour; Zarei, Eghbal; Asadollahi, Abdolrahim (2013): Sexual Abuse and Drug Abuse Among Homeless Children in Ahvaz, Iran. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (6), S. 408–418. DOI: 10.1002/car.2263.

- Baril, Karine; Tourigny, Marc; Paille, Pierre; Pauze, Robert (2016): Characteristics of Sexually Abused Children and Their Nonoffending Mothers Followed by Child Welfare Services. The Role of a Maternal History of Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 504–523. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1176096.
- Benia, Luis Roberto; Hauck-Filho, Nelson; Dillenburg, Mariana; Stein, Lilian Milnitsky (2015): The NICHD Investigative Interview Protocol. A Meta-Analytic Review. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 259–279. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006749.
- Benuto, Lorraine T.; O'Donohue, William (2015): Treatment of the Sexually Abused Child. Review and Synthesis of Recent Meta-Analyses. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 56, S. 52–60. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.06.009.
- Blaise, Mindy (2013): Charting new territories. Re-assembling childhood sexuality in the early years classroom. In: *Gender and Education* 25 (7), S. 801–817. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2013.797070.
- Bragg, Sara; Buckingham, David; Russell, Rachel; Willett, Rebekah (2011): Too much, too soon? Children, 'sexualization' and consumer culture. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 279–292. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590085.
- Caldas, Stephen J.; Betsy, Mary Lou (2014): The sexual maltreatment of students with disabilities in American school settings. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (4), S. 345–366. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.906530.
- Capella, Claudia; Lama, Ximena; Rodriguez, Loreto; Aguila, Daniela; Beiza, Gretchen; Dussert, Denise; Gutierrez, Carolina (2016): Winning a Race. Narratives of Healing and Psychotherapy in Children and Adolescents Who Have Been Sexually Abused. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 73–92. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088915.
- Celik, Gonca Gul; Yolga Tahiroglu, Aysegul; Avci, Ayse; Cekin, Necmi; Evliyaoglu, Nurdan; Yoruldu, Belgin (2012): Sexual abuse in a classroom of ten male students. A group victimization. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (5), S. 543–552. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.694403.
- Connon, Graham; Crooks, Allian; Carr, Alan; Dooley, Barbara; Guerin, Suzanne; Deasy, Derek et al. (2011): Child sex abuse and the Irish criminal justice system. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 102–119. DOI: 10.1002/car.1156.
- Coren, Esther; Thomae, Manuela; Hutchfield, Jemeela; Iredale, Wendy (2013): Report on the Implementation and Results of an Outcomes-focused Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Interventions in the UK. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (1), S. 44–59. DOI: 10.1002/car.2200.
- Cromer, Lisa DeMarni; Goldsmith, Rachel E. (2010): Child sexual abuse myths. Attitudes, beliefs, and individual differences. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (6), S. 618–647. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.522493.
- Cyr, Mireille; McDuff, Pierre; Hebert, Martine (2013): Support and profiles of nonoffending mothers of sexually abused children. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (2), S. 209–230. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.737444.
- Das, Aniruddha; Otis, Nicholas (2016): Sexual Contact in Childhood, Revictimization, and Lifetime Sexual and Psychological Outcomes. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1117–1131.
- DeHart, Dana; Dwyer, Gregg; Seto, Michael C.; Moran, Robert; Letourneau, Elizabeth; Schwarz-Watts, Donna (2017): Internet sexual solicitation of children. A proposed typology of offenders based on their chats, e-mails, and social network posts. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 77–89. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1241309.
- Elklit, Ask; Christiansen, Dorte M.; Palic, Sabina; Karsberg, Sidsel; Eriksen, Sara Bek (2014): Impact of traumatic events on posttraumatic stress disorder among Danish survivors of sexual abuse in childhood. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (8), S. 918–934. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.964440.
- Elliott, Ian A.; Findlater, Donald; Hughes, Teresa (2010): Practice report. A review of e-Safety remote computer monitoring for UK sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003686870.
- Epstein, Debbie; Kehily, Mary Jane; Renold, E. (2012): Culture, policy and the un/marked child. Fragments of the sexualisation debates. In: *Gender and Education* 24 (3), S. 249–254. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2012.670390.
- Everson, Mark D.; Faller, Kathleen Coulborn (2012): Base rates, multiple indicators, and comprehensive forensic evaluations. Why sexualized behavior still counts in assessments of child sexual abuse allegations. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (1), S. 45–71. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.642470.
- Fagerlund, Monica; Ellonen, Noora (2016): Children's Experiences of Completing a Computer-Based Violence Survey. Finnish Child Victim Survey Revisited. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 556–576. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1186769.

- Farr, Rachel H.; Crain, Emily E.; Oakley, M. K.; Cashen, Krystal K.; Garber, Karin J. (2016): Microaggressions, Feelings of Difference, and Resilience Among Adopted Children with Sexual Minority Parents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (1), S. 85–104. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0353-6.
- Flanagan, Paul (2012): Ethical review and reflexivity in research of children's sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 535–544. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627731.
- Flannery, Dustin D.; Stephens, Clare L.; Thompson, Amy D. (2016): The Impact of High-Profile Sexual Abuse Cases in the Media on a Pediatric Emergency Department. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 627–635. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1187697.
- Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Plummer, Carol (2010): Cultural issues in disclosures of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (5), S. 491–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.512520.
- Franklin, Anita; Smeaton, Emilie (2017): Recognising and responding to young people with learning disabilities who experience, or are at risk of, child sexual exploitation in the UK. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 474–481. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.11.009.
- Fresno, Andres; Spencer, Rosario; Ramos, Nadia; Pierrehumbert, Blaise (2014): The effect of sexual abuse on children's attachment representations in Chile. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 128–145. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870949.
- Gerouki, Margarita (2010): The boy who was drawing princesses. Primary teachers' accounts of children's non-conforming behaviours. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 335–348. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515092.
- Gibson, Kerry; Morgan, Mandy; Woolley, Cheryl; Powis, Tracey (2011): Growing up at centrepiece. Retrospective accounts of childhood spent at an intentional community. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 413–434. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.591364.
- Gillespie, Alisdair (2010): Legal definitions of child pornography. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 19–31. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903262097.
- Gokten, Emel Sari; Saday Duman, Nagihan (2016): Factors influencing the development of psychiatric disorders in the victims of sexual abuse. A study on Turkish children. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 69, S. 49–55. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.07.022.
- Goldman, Juliette (2011): External providers' sexuality education teaching and pedagogies for primary school students in Grade 1 to Grade 7. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (02), S. 155–174. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.558423.
- Goldman, Juliette D. G.; Grimbeek, Peter (2015): Preservice teachers' sources of information on mandatory reporting of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 238–258. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1009607.
- Graaf, Hanneke de; Rademakers, Jany (2011): The Psychological Measurement of Childhood Sexual Development in Western Societies. Methodologica IChallenges. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 48 (2-3), S. 118–129.
- Graham, Laurie M.; Lanier, Paul; Johnson-Motoyama, Michelle (2016): National profile of Latino/Latina children reported to the child welfare system for sexual abuse. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 66, S. 18–27. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.04.008.
- Greslé-Favier, Claire (2013): Adult discrimination against children. The case of abstinence-only education in twenty-first-century USA. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (6), S. 715–725. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.813387.
- Grondin, Anne-Marie (2011): Thinking outside specious boxes. Constructionist and post-structuralist readings of 'child sexual abuse'. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 243–254. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590065.
- Grossi, Laura M.; Lee, Austin F.; Schuler, Ann; Ryan, Julie L.; Prentky, Robert A. (2016): Sexualized behaviors in cohorts of children in the child welfare system. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 52, S. 49–61. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.12.014.
- Haboush, Karen L.; Alyan, Hala (2013): "Who can you tell?" Features of Arab culture that influence conceptualization and treatment of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 499–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800935.

- Hall, Charlotte L.; Hogue, Todd E.; Guo, Kun (2014): Gaze patterns to child figures reflect deviant sexual preference in child sex offenders—a first glance. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 303–317. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.931475.
- Hawkes, Colin (2011): Description of a UK study of onset of sexually harmful behaviour before the age of ten years in boys referred to a specialist assessment and treatment service. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 82–101. DOI: 10.1002/car.1133.
- Hutchfield, Jemeela; Coren, Esther (2011): The Child's Voice in Service Evaluation. Ethical and Methodological Issues. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 173–186. DOI: 10.1002/car.1142.
- Jaffe, Anna E.; Cranston, Christopher C.; Shadlow, Joanna O. (2012): Parenting in females exposed to intimate partner violence and childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 684–700. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.726698.
- James, Adilia E. E. (2010): Too Early to Talk About Sex? Issues in Creating Culturally Relevant Sexuality Education for Preadolescent Black Girls in the United States. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (2), S. 128–141. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0012-3.
- Jin, Yichen; Chen, Jingqi; Yu, Buyi (2016): Knowledge and Skills of Sexual Abuse Prevention. A Study on School-Aged Children in Beijing, China. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 686–696. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1199079.
- Johnson, Rebecca L.; Sendall, Marguerite C.; McCuaig, Louise A. (2014): Primary schools and the delivery of relationships and sexuality education. The experience of Queensland teachers. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 359–374. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.909351.
- Jones, Tiffany Mary (2011): Saving rhetorical children. Sexuality education discourses from conservative to post-modern. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 369–387. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595229.
- Katz, Carmit (2013): Internet-related child sexual abuse. What children tell us in their testimonies. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (9), S. 1536–1542. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.06.006.
- Katz, Carmit; Hamama, Liat (2013): “Draw me everything that happened to you”. Exploring children's drawings of sexual abuse. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (5), S. 877–882. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.02.007.
- Kettleborough, Danielle G.; Merdian, Hannah L. (2017): Gateway to offending behaviour. Permission-giving thoughts of online users of child sexual exploitation material. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 19–32. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1231852.
- Kim, Tae Kyung; Choi, Soul; Shin, Yee Jin (2011): Psychosocial factors influencing competency of children's statements on sexual trauma. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (3), S. 173–179.
- Kisanga, Felix; Nystrom, Lennarth; Hogan, Nora; Emmelin, Maria (2011): Child sexual abuse. Community concerns in urban Tanzania. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (2), S. 196–217. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.555356.
- Kloppen, Kathrine; Haugland, Siren; Svedin, Carl-Göran; Maehle, Magne; Breivik, Kyrre (2016): Prevalence of Child Sexual Abuse in the Nordic Countries. A Literature Review. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 37–55. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1108944.
- Kostolitz, Alessandra C.; Hyman, Scott M.; Gold, Steven N. (2014): How ineffective family environments can compound maldevelopment of critical thinking skills in childhood abuse survivors. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (6), S. 690–707. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.931318.
- Kosuri, Mahathi D.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2017): Child sex tourism. American perceptions of foreign victims. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 207–221. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1231350.
- Krause-Parello, Cheryl A.; Gulick, Elsie E. (2015): Forensic Interviews for Child Sexual Abuse Allegations. An Investigation into the Effects of Animal-Assisted Intervention on Stress Biomarkers. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 873–886. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088916.
- Krayer, Anne; Seddon, Diane; Robinson, Catherine A.; Gwilym, Hefin (2015): The influence of child sexual abuse on the self from adult narrative perspectives. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (2), S. 135–151. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1001473.
- Kucuk, Sibel (2016): Analyses of Child Sex Abuse Cases in Turkey: A Provincial Case. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 262–275. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153557.

- Lainpelto, Katrin; Isaksson, Johan; Lindblad, Frank (2016): Does Information About Neuropsychiatric Diagnoses Influence Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations? In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 276–292. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1145164.
- Lampert, Jo (2012): Sh-h-h-h. Representations of perpetrators of sexual child abuse in picturebooks. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 177–185. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.609048.
- Langeland, Willemiem; Hoogendoorn, Adriaan W.; Mager, Daniel; Smit, Jan H.; Draijer, Nel (2015): Childhood sexual abuse by representatives of the Roman Catholic Church. A prevalence estimate among the Dutch population. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 67–77.
- Langevin, Rachel; Hébert, Martine; Cossette, Louise (2015): Emotion regulation as a mediator of the relation between sexual abuse and behavior problems in preschoolers. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 16–26.
- Leventhal, John M.; Murphy, Janet L.; Asnes, Andrea G. (2010): Evaluations of child sexual abuse. Recognition of overt and latent family concerns. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34 (5), S. 289–295.
- Lin, Danhua; Li, Xiaoming; Fan, Xinghua; Fang, Xiaoyi (2011): Child sexual abuse and its relationship with health risk behaviors among rural children and adolescents in Hunan, China. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (9), S. 680–687. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2011.05.006.
- Liotta, Lindsay; Springer, Craig; Misurell, Justin R.; Block-Lerner, Jennifer; Brandwein, David (2015): Group treatment for child sexual abuse. Treatment referral and therapeutic outcomes. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 217–237. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006747.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Smith, Peter K. (2014): Annual Research Review: Harms experienced by child users of online and mobile technologies. The nature, prevalence and management of sexual and aggressive risks in the digital age. In: *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry* 55 (6), S. 635–654.
- Malins, Pamela (2016): How inclusive is “inclusive education” in the Ontario elementary classroom? Teachers talk about addressing diverse gender and sexual identities. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 54, S. 128–138. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.11.004.
- Malón, Agustín (2011): The “Participating Victim” in the Study of Erotic Experiences Between Children and Adults: An Historical Analysis. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (1), S. 169–188.
- Malón, Agustín (2015): Adult–Child Sex and the Limits of Liberal Sexual Morality. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (4), S. 1071–1083.
- Man-Ging, Carlos Ignacio; Bohm, Bettina; Fuchs, Katharina Anna; Witte, Susanne; Frick, Eckhard (2015): Improving Empathy in the Prevention of Sexual Abuse Against Children and Youngsters. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (7), S. 796–815. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1077366.
- Manson, William (2015): “Keeping Children Safe”. The Child Sex Offender Disclosure Scheme in Scotland. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 43–55. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.950352.
- Marriott, Clare; Hamilton-Giachrisis, Catherine; Harrop, Chris (2014): Factors Promoting Resilience Following Childhood Sexual Abuse. A Structured, Narrative Review of the Literature. In: *Child Abuse Review* 23 (1), S. 17–34. DOI: 10.1002/car.2258.
- Martin, Karin A. (2014): Making sense of children's sexual behavior in child care. An analysis of adult responses in special investigation reports. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (10), S. 1636–1646.
- Martin, Karin A.; Verduzco Baker, Lynn; Torres, Jennifer; Luke, Katherine (2011): Privates, pee-pees, and coochies. Gender and genital labeling for/with young children. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (3), S. 420–430. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510384832.
- Martino, Wayne J.; Cumming-Potvin, Wendy (2015): Teaching about “Princess Boys” or Not. The Case of One Male Elementary School Teacher and the Polemics of Gender Expression and Embodiment. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (1), S. 79–99. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14551278.
- Masson, Helen; Balfe, Myles; Hackett, Simon; Phillips, Josie (2012): Making use of historical case material. The problems of looking back and the implications for service development in relation to research and evaluation activities. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 112–122. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.630539.

- McElvaney, Rosaleen (2015): Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse. Delays, Non-disclosure and Partial Disclosure. What the Research Tells Us and Implications for Practice. In: *Child Abuse Review* 24 (3), S. 159–169. DOI: 10.1002/car.2280.
- McLoone-Richards, Claire (2012): Say Nothing! How Pathology within Catholicism Created and Sustained the Institutional Abuse of Children in 20 th Century Ireland. In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (6), S. 394–404. DOI: 10.1002/car.2209.
- McManus, Michelle Ann; Almond, Louise (2014): Trends of indecent images of children and child sexual offences between 2005/2006 and 2012/2013 within the United Kingdom. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 142–155. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.893031.
- McManus, Michelle Ann; Long, Matthew L.; Alison, Laurence; Almond, Louise (2014): Factors associated with contact child sexual abuse in a sample of indecent image offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 368–384. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927009.
- Merdian, Hannah Lena; Curtis, Cate; Thakker, Jo; Wilson, Nick; Boer, Douglas Pieter (2013): The three dimensions of online child pornography offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 121–132. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.611898.
- Milam, Lisa J.; Nugent, William R. (2017): Children's Knowledge of Genital Anatomy and Its Relationship With Children's Use of the Word "Inside" During Questioning About Possible Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 23–39. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1269863.
- Miller, Susan L.; Hefner, M. Kristen; Leon, Chrysanthi S. (2014): Diffusing responsibility. A case study of child sexual abuse in popular discourse. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 37, S. 55–63. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2013.12.005.
- Misurell, Justin R.; Springer, Craig; Tryon, Warren W. (2011): Game-based cognitive-behavioral therapy (GB-CBT) group program for children who have experienced sexual abuse. A preliminary investigation. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 14–36. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.540000.
- Moore, Tim P.; McArthur, Morag; Noble-Carr, Debbie (2017): More a marathon than a hurdle. Towards children's informed consent in a study on safety. In: *Qualitative Research* 7 (2), 146879411770070. DOI: 10.1177/1468794117700708.
- Myers, Kristen; Raymond, Laura (2010): Elementary School Girls and Heteronormativity. The Girl Project. In: *Gender & Society* 24 (2), S. 167–188. DOI: 10.1177/0891243209358579.
- Niehaus, Ashley F.; Jackson, Joan; Davies, Stephanie (2010): Sexual self-schemas of female child sexual abuse survivors. Relationships with risky sexual behavior and sexual assault in adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (6), S. 1359–1374. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9600-9.
- O'Brien, Jennifer E.; White, Kevin; Wu, Qi; Killian-Farrell, Candace (2016): Mental Health and Behavioral Outcomes of Sexual and Nonsexual Child Maltreatment Among Child Welfare-Involved Youth. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 483–503. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1167801.
- O'Leary, Patrick J.; Gould, Nick (2010): Exploring Coping Factors amongst Men Who Were Sexually Abused in Childhood. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (8), S. 2669–2686.
- Parent, Sylvie; Bannon, Joëlle (2012): Sexual abuse in sport. What about boys? In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (2), S. 354–359. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2011.11.004.
- Pasura, Dominic; Jones, Adele D.; Hafner, James A. H.; Maharaj, Priya E.; Nathaniel-DeCaires, Karene; Johnson, Emmanuel Janagan (2013): Competing meanings of childhood and the social construction of child sexual abuse in the Caribbean. In: *Childhood* 20 (2), S. 200–214. DOI: 10.1177/0907568212462255.
- Pearce, Jenny J. (2014): 'What's Going On' to Safeguard Children and Young People from Child Sexual Exploitation. A Review of Local Safeguarding Children Boards' Work to Protect Children from Sexual Exploitation. In: *Child Abuse Review* 23 (3), S. 159–170. DOI: 10.1002/car.2269.
- Rakow, Aaron; Smith, Daniel; Begle, Angela M.; Ayer, Lynsay (2011): The association of maternal depressive symptoms with child externalizing problems. The role of maternal support following child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 467–480. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.588189.

- Rumble, Lauren; Mungate, Taizivei; Chigiji, Handrick; Salama, Peter; Nolan, Anthony; Sammon, Elayn; Muwoni, Leon (2015): Childhood sexual violence in Zimbabwe: evidence for the epidemic against girls. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 60–66. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.04.015.
- Rysst, Mari (2010): 'I Am Only Ten Years Old'. Femininities, clothing-fashion codes and the intergenerational gap of interpretation of young girls' clothes. In: *Childhood* 17 (1), S. 76–93. DOI: 10.1177/0907568209351552.
- Samms, Kimika M.; Cholewa, Blaire E. (2014): Exploring the context of child sexual abuse in Jamaica. Addressing the deficits. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 115–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870948.
- Schaeffer, Paula; Leventhal, John M.; Gottsegen Asnes, Andrea (2011): Children's disclosures of sexual abuse. Learning from direct inquiry. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (5), S. 343–352.
- Schonfeld, David J.; Adams, Ryan E.; Fredstrom, Bridget K.; Tomlin, Ricarda; Voyce, Charlene; Vaughn, Lisa M. (2012): Social-Emotional Learning in Grades 3 to 6 and the Early Onset of Sexual Behavior. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 9 (2), S. 178–186. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0077-7.
- Smith, Connie; Allardyce, Stuart; Hackett, Simon; Bradbury-Jones, Caroline; Lazenbatt, Anne; Taylor, Julie (2014): Practice and policy in the UK with children and young people who display harmful sexual behaviours. An analysis and critical review. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 267–280. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927010.
- Smith, Mark; Woodiwiss, Jo (2017): Sexuality, Innocence and Agency in Narratives of Childhood Sexual Abuse. Implications for Social Work. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2173–2189. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw160.
- Soylu, Nusret; Alpaslan, Ahmet Hamdi; Ayaz, Muhammed; Esenyel, Selen; Oruc, Mucahit (2013): Psychiatric disorders and characteristics of abuse in sexually abused children and adolescents with and without intellectual disabilities. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 34 (12), S. 4334–4342. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2013.09.010.
- Soylu, Nusret; Ayaz, Muhammed; Yüksel, Tuğb (2014): Early-married and sexually abused girls differ in their psychiatric outcomes. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (9), S. 1552–1559.
- Spišák, Sanna; Paasonen, Susanna (2017): Bad education? Childhood recollections of pornography, sexual exploration, learning and agency in Finland. In: *Childhood* 24 (1), S. 99–112. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216646436.
- Šribar, Renata (2013): Growing-up challenged and challenging. Gender and sexuality norms in referential research on 'internet risks' and in children. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (1), S. 129–145. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.748681.
- Tabatabaie, Alireza (2014): Childhood and adolescent sexuality, Islam, and problematics of sex education. A call for re-examination. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 276–288. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1005836.
- Toledo, Annik van; Seymour, Fred (2016): Caregiver Needs Following Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 403–414. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1156206.
- Tsaliki, Liza (2015): Popular culture and moral panics about 'children at risk'. Revisiting the sexualisation-of-young-girls debate. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 500–514. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1022893.
- Weiler, Julia von; Haardt-Becker, Annette; Schulte, Simone (2010): Care and treatment of child victims of child pornographic exploitation (CPE) in Germany. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 211–222. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003759990.
- White, Jacquelyn; Buehler, Cheryl; Weymouth, Bridget B. (2014): Childhood attention deficit hyperactive disorder (ADHD) symptoms and adolescent female sexual victimisation. Mediating and moderating effects of risky behaviours. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 23–39. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.782429.
- Williams, Andy (2015): Child sexual victimisation. Ethnographic stories of stranger and acquaintance grooming. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 28–42. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.948085.
- Wissink, Inge B.; Vugt, Eveline van; Moonen, Xavier; Stams, Geert Jan; Hendriks, Jan (2015): Sexual abuse involving children with an intellectual disability (ID): a narrative review. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 36, S. 20–35. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2014.09.007.
- Wonnacott, Jane (2013): Keeping children safe in nurseries. A focus on culture and context. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 32–45. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.747631.

Zhang, Wenjing; Chen, Jingqi; Feng, Yanan; Li, Jingyi; Zhao, Xiaoxia; Luo, Xiaoling (2013): Young children's knowledge and skills related to sexual abuse prevention. A pilot study in Beijing, China. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 623–630.

5.2. Jugendliche und junge Erwachsene

Betancourt, Gerardo (2015): A theoretical model for intervening in complex sexual behaviours. Sexual desires, pleasures and passion - La Pasi3n - of Spanish-speaking gay men in Canada. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 159–172.

Blumenfeld, Warren J. (2012): "We're Here and We're Fabulous". Contemporary U.S.-American LGBT Youth Activism. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 73–83.

Boonmann, Cyril; Grudzinskas, Albert; Aebi, Marcel (2014): Juveniles, the Internet, and Sexual Offending. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 161–179.

Bryan Meek, Jane (2012): "Being Queer Is the Luckiest Thing". Investigating a New Generation's Use of Queer within Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, and Queer Groups (LGBTQ) Student. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 187–198.

Burke, Kevin (2014): Impossible Women. Saints, Sinner, and the Gendered Mythology in a Catholic School. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 25–37.

Carmody, Moira (2014): Young people, ethical sex and violence prevention. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 167–184.

Carr, Nicola; Pinkerton, John (2015): Coming into view? The experiences of LGBT young people in the care system in Northern Ireland. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 99–112.

Chapman, Amy; Buchanan, Rachel (2014): FYI... Virtual space has a context. Towards an alternative frame for understanding cyberbullying. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 56–71.

Clavert, Clay (2014): Youth-Produced Sexual Images, "Sexting", and the Cellphone. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 89–116.

Crowley, M. Sue (2014): Defining Themselves. LGBQS Youth Online. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 90–109.

DeVita, James M.; Daniel Anders, Allison (2014): Multiple Targeted Identities. Intersectionality and the Lived Experiences of Black Gay Males. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 464–478.

Espiritu, Yen Le (2012): U.S. Colonialism, Migration, and Sexualities. The Filipino American Case. In: Laura M. Carpenter und John D. DeLamater (Hg.): *Sex for life. From virginity to Viagra, how sexuality changes throughout our lives*. New York: New York University Press (Intersections), S. 163–179.

Finkelstein, Sam; Mosqueda, Lucky; Birrueta, Adrian; Kitty, Eric (2012): Queer youth of color organizing for safe & affirming education. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 349–350.

Harris, Andrew J. (2014): Understanding the World of Digital Youth. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 24–61.

Harris, Andrew J.; Davidson, Judith (2014): Teens, Sex, and Technology: Implications for Educational Systems and Practice. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital*

age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 262–292.

Hasebrink, Uwe (2012): Young European's online environments: a typology of user practices. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 127–140.

Hirst, Julia (2014): 'Get some Rhythm Round the Clitoris': Addressing Sexual Pleasure in Sexuality Education in Schools and other Youth Settings. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 35–57.

Jennifer, Dawn (2013): Girls and indirect aggression. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 45–59.

Judge, Abigail; Graw Leary, Mary (2014): From the Streets to Cyberspace. The Effects of Technology in the Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children and Adolescents in the United States. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 180–214.

Livingstone, Sonia M.; Görzig, Anke (2012): Sexting: the exchange of sexual messages online among European youth. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 151–164.

Luschen, Kristen V. (2014): Survival, Protection, and Forgiveness. Examining Gendered Violence and Care in the Hunger Games Trilogy. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 133–146.

Masinire, Alfred (2014): Becoming a Responsible Boy. Contesting Masculinity in Rural Zimbabwe. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 110–123.

McClelland, Sara I.; Fine, Michelle (2014): Over-Sexed and under Surveillance. Adolescent Sexualities, Cultural Anxieties, and Thick Desire. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 12–35.

McCready, Lance T. (2014): The African Dance Program. "Where is the Love?". In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), 342–356.

Ollis, Debbie (2013): Planning and delivering interventions to promote gender and sexuality. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 145–161.

Ouer, Freedom (2014): It's Not How Regular Boys Are Supposed to Act. The Nonnormative Sexual Practices of Black Boys in All-Male Public Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 357–369.

Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): "Butterflies Starting a Tornado". The Queer 'Not Yet' of New Zealand School-Based Queer Straight Alliance as a Utopic Site of Learning. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 272–283.

Racine, Christopher W.; Bates Billick, Stephen (2014): Conclusion. Understanding Adolescent Sexual Development and the Law in the Digital Era. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 346–354.

Rivers, Ian; Duncan, Neil (2013): Discourses of sexuality and gender considered. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 162–168.

Robinson, Kerry H. (2014): Sexual harassment in schools. Issues of identity and power - Negotiating the complexities, contexts and contradictions of this everyday practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 71–94.

- Robles-Fernández, Ramón (2014): A GSA's Impact on Students' Beliefs and Attitudes Toward Civic and Political Participation, Civic Engagement, and Social Justice. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 284–297.
- Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): "The kid most likely". Naming, brutality and silence within and beyond school settings. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 21–38.
- Seroussi, Ariel; Bonnici, Daniel; Leogn, Gregory B.; Weinstock, Robert (2014): Ethical and Legal Considerations for Psychiatry Regarding Adolescents and Technology Use. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 315–345.
- Singh, Anneliese A.; Jackson, Ken (2012): Queer and Transgender Youth. Education and Liberation in Our Schools. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 175–186.
- Smahel, David; Subrahmanyam, Kaveri (2014): Adolescent Sexuality on the Internet: A Developmental Perspective. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 62–88.
- Ullman, Jacqueline; McGraw, Kelli (2014): Troubling Silences and Taboo Texts. Constructing Safer and More Positive School Climates for Same-Sex-Attracted High School Students in Australia. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 298–312.
- Whitlock, Reta Ugena (2014): LGBT Families and Southern Schools. Thinking About People, Place, and Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): Gender and sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 75–89.
- Williams, Sian (2013): Sexual bullying in one local authority. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 60–74.
- Winter, Elizabeth A.; Elze, Diane E.; Saltzburg, Susan; Rosenwald, Mitchell (2015): Social services for LGBT young people in the United States. Are we there yet? In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 113–130.
- Best, Joel; Bogle, Kathleen A. (2014): Kids gone wild. From rainbow parties to sexting, understanding the hype over teen sex. New York [u.a.]: New York Univ. Press.
- Carlson, Dennis; Roseboro, Donyell L. (2011): The Sexuality Curriculum and Youth Culture (Counterpoints, 392).
- Carmody, Moira (2015): Sex, ethics, and young people. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan (Palgrave Macmillan's critical studies in gender, sexuality, and culture).
- Drobac, Jennifer Ann (2016): Sexual exploitation of teenagers. Adolescent development, discrimination, and consent law. Chicago, London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Elliott, Sinikka (2012): Not my kid. What parents believe about the sex lives of their teenagers. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press.
- Garcia, Lorena (2012): Respect yourself, protect yourself. Latina girls and sexual identity. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press (Intersections / [New York University Press]).
- Hasinoff, Amy Adele (2015): Sexting panic. Rethinking criminalization, privacy, and consent. Urbana: University of Illinois Press (Feminist media studies).
- Ozyegin, Gul (2015): New desires, new selves. Sex, love, and piety among Turkish youth. New York: New York University Press.
- Powell, Anastasia (2010): Sex, Power and Consent. Youth Culture and the Unwritten Rules. Port Melbourne, Vic.: Cambridge University Press.
- Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2012): Pervasive vulnerabilities. Sexual harassment in school. New York: Peter Lang (Adolescent cultures, school & society, v. 54).
- Sanjakdar, Fida (2012): Living west, facing east. The deconstruction of Muslim youth's sexual identities. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints, 364).

- Shariff, Shaheen (2015): Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013): Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications. Hove: Psychology.
- Meiners, Erica R.; Quinn, Therese (Hg.) (2012): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367).
- Saleh, Fabian M.; Grudzinskas, Albert; Judge, Abigail (Hg.) (2014): Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Abajobir, Amanuel Alemu; Kisely, Steve; Williams, Gail Marilyn; Clavarino, Alexandra Marie; Najman, Jakob Moses (2017): Substantiated Childhood Maltreatment and Intimate Partner Violence Victimization in Young Adulthood: A Birth Cohort Study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 165–179. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0558-3.
- Albury, Kath (2013): Young people, media and sexual learning. Rethinking representation. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S32–S44. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.767194.
- Alessi, Edward J.; Kahn, Sarilee; Chatterji, Sangeeta (2016): 'The darkest times of my life'. Recollections of child abuse among forced migrants persecuted because of their sexual orientation and gender identity. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 51, S. 93–105.
- Ali, Mir M.; Dwyer, Debra S. (2011): Estimating peer effects in sexual behavior among adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 183–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.12.008.
- Alix, Stephanie; Cossette, Louise; Hebert, Martine; Cyr, Mireille; Frappier, Jean-Yves (2017): Posttraumatic Stress Disorder and Suicidal Ideation Among Sexually Abused Adolescent Girls. The Mediating Role of Shame. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (2), S. 158–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1280577.
- Allard, Troy; Rayment-McHugh, Sue; Adams, Dimity; Smallbone, Stephen; McKillop, Nadine (2015): Responding to youth sexual offending. A field-based practice model that "closes the gap" on sexual recidivism among Indigenous and non-Indigenous males. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (1), S. 82–94. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.1003107.
- Allardyce, Stuart; Yates, Peter Michael (2013): Assessing Risk of Victim Crossover with Children and Young People who display Harmful Sexual Behaviours. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (4), S. 255–267. DOI: 10.1002/car.2277.
- Allen, Louisa (2013): Boys as Sexy Bodies. In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 347–365. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13497205.
- Allen, Louisa (2011): 'Picture this'. Using photo-methods in research on sexualities and schooling. In: *Qualitative Research* 11 (5), S. 487–504. DOI: 10.1177/1468794111413224.
- Alleyne, Binta; Coleman-Cowger, Victoria H.; Crown, Laurel; Gibbons, Maya A.; Vines, Linda Nicole (2011): The effects of dating violence, substance use and risky sexual behavior among a diverse sample of Illinois youth. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 11–18. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.03.006.
- Allnock, Debra; Radford, Lorraine; Bunting, Lisa; Price, Avril; Morgan-Klein, Natalie; Ellis, Jane; Stafford, Anne (2012): In Demand. Therapeutic Services for Children and Young People Who Have Experienced Sexual Abuse. In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (5), S. 318–334. DOI: 10.1002/car.1205.
- Almond, Tracy Jane (2014): Working with children and young people with harmful sexual behaviours. Exploring impact on practitioners and sources of support. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 333–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836576.
- Anderson, E.; McCormack, M. (2015): Cuddling and Spooning. Heteromascularity and Homosocial Tactility among Student-athletes. In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (2), S. 214–230. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14523433.
- Arrington-Sanders, Renata; Harper, Gary W.; Morgan, Anthony; Ogunbajo, Adedotun; Trent, Maria; Fortenberry, J. Dennis (2015): The role of sexually explicit material in the sexual development of same-sex-attracted Black adolescent males. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 597–608. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0416-x.
- Asscher, Jessica J.; Put, Claudia E. van der; Stams, Geert Jan (2012): Differences between juvenile offenders with and without intellectual disability in offense type and risk factors. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 33 (6), S. 1905–1913. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2012.05.022.
- Atkinson, Chris; Newton, David (2010): Online behaviours of adolescents. Victims, perpetrators and Web 2.0. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 107–120. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903337683.

- Attwood, Feona; Smith, Clarissa (2011): Investigating young people's sexual cultures. An introduction. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* (Vol. 11 No. 3), S. 235–242.
- Ávila, Marisa; Cabral, Joana; Matos, Paula Mena (2012): Identity in university students. The role of parental and romantic attachment. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 133–142. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.05.002.
- Bale, Clare (2011): Raunch or romance? Framing and interpreting the relationship between sexualized culture and young people's sexual health. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 303–313. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590088.
- Ballonoff Suleiman, Ahna; Brindis, Claire D. (2014): Adolescent School-Based Sex Education. Using Developmental Neuroscience to Guide New Directions for Policy and Practice. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 137–152. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0147-8.
- Bantjes, J.; Nieuwoudt, J. (2014): Masculinity and Mayhem. The Performance of Gender in a South African Boys' School. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (4), S. 376–395. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539964.
- Barron, Ian G.; Topping, Keith J. (2011): Sexual abuse prevention programme fidelity. Video analysis of interactions. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 134–151. DOI: 10.1002/car.1134.
- Bauermeister, José A.; Johns, Michelle Marie; Sandfort, Theo G. M.; Eisenberg, Anna; Grossman, Arnold H.; D'Augelli, Anthony R. (2010): Relationship trajectories and psychological well-being among sexual minority youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1148–1163. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9557-y.
- Baumgartner, Susanne E.; Valkenburg, Patti M.; Peter, Jochen (2010): Assessing causality in the relationship between adolescents' risky sexual online behavior and their perceptions of this behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1226–1239. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9512-y.
- Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Fava, Nicole M. (2014): What puts “At-Risk Girls” at risk? Sexual vulnerability and social inequality in the lives of girls in the child welfare system. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 116–125. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0142-5.
- Beckmeyer, Jonathon J. (2015): Comparing the associations between three types of adolescents' romantic involvement and their engagement in substance use. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 42, S. 140–147. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.04.008.
- Beerhuizen, Marinus G. C. J.; Brugman, Daniel (2012): Sexually abusive youths' moral reasoning on sex. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 125–135. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.519126.
- Beier, Klaus M.; Oezdemir, Umut C.; Schlinzig, Eliza; Groll, Anna; Hupp, Elena; Hellenschmidt, Tobias (2016): “Just dreaming of them”. The Berlin Project for Primary Prevention of Child Sexual Abuse by Juveniles (PPJ). In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 52, S. 1–10.
- Bengtsson, T. T. (2016): Performing Hypermasculinity. Experiences with Confined Young Offenders. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (4), S. 410–428. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15595083.
- Benia, Luis Roberto; Hauck-Filho, Nelson; Dillenburg, Mariana; Stein, Lilian Milnitsky (2015): The NICHD Investigative Interview Protocol. A Meta-Analytic Review. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 259–279. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006749.
- Beres, Melanie Ann (2014): Rethinking the concept of consent for anti-sexual violence activism and education. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 24 (3), S. 373–389. DOI: 10.1177/0959353514539652.
- Berglas, Nancy F.; Angulo-Olaiz, Francisca; Jerman, Petra; Desai, Mona; Constantine, Norman A. (2014): Engaging Youth Perspectives on Sexual Rights and Gender Equality in Intimate Relationships as a Foundation for Rights-Based Sexuality Education. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (4), S. 288–298. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0148-7.
- Bhana, D. (2016): 'Sex isn't better than love. Exploring South African Indian teenage male and female desires beyond danger. In: *Childhood* 23 (3), S. 362–377. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216642828.
- Bhana, Deevia; Pattman, Rob (2011): Girls want money, boys want virgins. The materiality of love amongst South African township youth in the context of HIV and AIDS. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 961–972. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.576770.

- Biswas, Bipasha; Vaughn, Michael G. (2011): Really troubled girls. Gender differences in risky sexual behavior and its correlates in a sample of juvenile offenders. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 33 (11), S. 2386–2391. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2011.08.010.
- Black, Pamela J.; Wollis, Melissa; Woodworth, Michael; Hancock, Jeffrey T. (2015): A linguistic analysis of grooming strategies of online child sex offenders: Implications for our understanding of predatory sexual behavior in an increasingly computer-mediated world. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 44, S. 140–149.
- Boislard P., Marie-Aude; Poulin, Francois (2011): Individual, familial, friends-related and contextual predictors of early sexual intercourse. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 289–300. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.05.002.
- Boisvert, Stéphanie; Poulin, François (2016): Romantic Relationship Patterns from Adolescence to Emerging Adulthood: Associations with Family and Peer Experiences in Early Adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 945–958. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0435-0.
- Bos, Henny; Sandfort, Theo (2015): Gender Nonconformity, Sexual Orientation, and Dutch Adolescents' Relationship with Peers. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (5), S. 1269–1279. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0461-5.
- Bos, Henny; van Beusekom, Gabriël; Sandfort, Theo (2014): Sexual attraction and psychological adjustment in Dutch adolescents: coping style as a mediator. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1579–1588. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0308-0.
- Boustani, Maya M.; Frazier, Stacy L.; Lesperance, Nephtalie (2017): Sexual health programming for vulnerable youth. Improving knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 375–383. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2017.01.013.
- Bower, Andrew R.; Nishina, Adrienne; Witkow, Melissa R.; Bellmore, Amy (2015): Nice Guys and Gals Finish Last? Not in Early Adolescence When Empathic, Accepted, and Popular Peers are Desirable. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (12), S. 2275–2288. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0346-5.
- Bowker, Julie C.; Etkin, Rebecca G. (2014): Does humor explain why relationally aggressive adolescents are popular? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1322–1332. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0031-5.
- Braje, Sopagna Eap; Eddy, J. Mark; Hall, Gordon C. N. (2016): A Comparison of Two Models of Risky Sexual Behavior During Late Adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (1), S. 73–83. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0523-3.
- Brakefield, Tiffany A.; Mednick, Sara C.; Wilson, Helen W.; Neve, Jan-Emmanuel de; Christakis, Nicholas A.; Fowler, James H. (2014): Same-sex sexual attraction does not spread in adolescent social networks. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 335–344. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0142-9.
- Brooks-Russell, Ashley; Foshee, Vangie A.; Ennett, Susan T. (2013): Predictors of latent trajectory classes of physical dating violence victimization. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 566–580. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9876-2.
- Brown, Graham; Sorenson, Anne; Hildebrand, Janina (2012): How they got it and how they wanted it. Marginalised young people's perspective on their experiences of sexual health education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 599–612. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634141.
- Brunnberg, Elinor; Lindén Boström, Margareta; Berglund, Mats (2012): Sexual force at sexual debut. Swedish adolescents with disabilities at higher risk than adolescents without disabilities. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (4), S. 285–295.
- Bui, Thanh Cong; Diamond, Pamela M.; Markham, Christine; Ross, Michael W.; Nguyen-Le, Thanh-An; Tran, Ly Hai Thi (2010): Gender relations and sexual communication among female students in the Mekong River Delta of Vietnam. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (6), S. 591–601. DOI: 10.1080/13691050902968769.
- Burchardt, Marian (2011): Challenging Pentecostal moralism. Erotic geographies, religion and sexual practices among township youth in Cape Town. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 669–683. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.566356.
- Caiozzo, Christina N.; Houston, Jessica; Grych, John (2016): Predicting aggression in late adolescent romantic relationships. A short-term longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 53, S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.10.012.

- Calafat, Amador; Hughes, Karen; Blay, Nicole; Bellis, Mark A.; Mendes, Fernando; Juan, Montse et al. (2013): Sexual harassment among young tourists visiting Mediterranean resorts. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 603–613. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-9979-6.
- Caldas, Stephen J.; Betsy, Mary Lou (2014): The sexual maltreatment of students with disabilities in American school settings. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (4), S. 345–366. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.906530.
- Campero, Lourdes; Walker, Dilys; Atienzo, Erika E.; Gutierrez, Juan Pablo (2011): A quasi-experimental evaluation of parents as sexual health educators resulting in delayed sexual initiation and increased access to condoms. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 215–223. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.05.010.
- Carlson, Daniel L.; McNulty, Thomas L.; Bellair, Paul E.; Watts, Stephen (2014): Neighborhoods and racial/ethnic disparities in adolescent sexual risk behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (9), S. 1536–1549. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0052-0.
- Carlson, Wendy; Rose, Amanda J. (2012): Brief report. Activities in heterosexual romantic relationships: grade differences and associations with relationship satisfaction. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 219–224. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.09.001.
- Carter, Rona; Williams, Sandra (2016): Self-perceptions of pubertal timing and patterns of peer group activities and dating behavior among heterosexual adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 47, S. 71–80. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.12.006.
- Casey, Erin A.; Beadnell, Blair (2010): The structure of male adolescent peer networks and risk for intimate partner violence perpetration: findings from a national sample. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 620–633. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9423-y.
- Cavazos-Rehg, Patricia A.; Spitznagel, Edward L.; Bucholz, Kathleen K.; Nurnberger, John; Edenberg, Howard J.; Kramer, John R. et al. (2010): Predictors of sexual debut at age 16 or younger. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 664–673. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9397-y.
- Chang, Ling-Yin; Foshee, Vangie A.; Reyes, Heathe Luz McNaughton; Ennett, Susan T.; Halpern, Carolyn T. (2015): Direct and indirect effects of neighborhood characteristics on the perpetration of dating violence across adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 727–744. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0190-z.
- Choi, Hye Jeong; Ouytsel, Joris van; Temple, Jeff R. (2016): Association between sexting and sexual coercion among female adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 53, S. 164–168. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.10.005.
- Collibee, Charlene; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Chronic and Acute Relational Risk Factors for Dating Aggression in Adolescence and Young Adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (4), S. 763–776. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0427-0.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2013): Homophobic name-calling among secondary school students and its implications for mental health. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 363–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9823-2.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2012): Intergroup contact, attitudes toward homosexuality, and the role of acceptance of gender non-conformity in young adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 899–907. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.12.010.
- Comartin, Erin B.; Kernsmith, Poco D.; Miles, Bart W. (2010): Family experiences of young adult sex offender registration. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 204–225. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003627207.
- Corona, Laura L.; Fox, Stephanie A.; Christodulu, Kristin V.; Worlock, Jane Ann (2016): Providing Education on Sexuality and Relationships to Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder and Their Parents. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 199–214. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-015-9424-6.
- Cox, Nele; Vanden Berghe, Wim; Dewaele, Alexis; Vincke, John (2010): Acculturation strategies and mental health in gay, lesbian, and bisexual youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1199–1210. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9435-7.
- Coyne, Sarah M.; Padilla-Walker, Laura M. (2015): Sex, violence, & rock n' roll. Longitudinal effects of music on aggression, sex, and prosocial behavior during adolescence. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 41, S. 96–104. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.03.002.

- Crandall, AliceAnn; Magnusson, Brianna M.; Novilla, M. Lelinneth B.; Novilla, Lynneth Kirsten B.; Dyer, W. Justin (2017): Family Financial Stress and Adolescent Sexual Risk-Taking: The Role of Self-Regulation. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 45–62. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0543-x.
- Crichton, Joanna; Ibisomi, Latifat; Gyimah, Stephen Obeng (2012): Mother-daughter communication about sexual maturation, abstinence and unintended pregnancy. Experiences from an informal settlement in Nairobi, Kenya. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 21–30. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.06.008.
- D'Abreu, Lylla Cysne Frota; Krahé, Barbara (2016): Vulnerability to Sexual Victimization in Female and Male College Students in Brazil: Cross-Sectional and Prospective Evidence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1101–1115. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0451-7.
- Daddis, Christopher; Randolph, Danielle (2010): Dating and disclosure: Adolescent management of information regarding romantic involvement. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (2), S. 309–320. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.05.002.
- Dahlbäck, Elisabeth; Maimbolwa, Margaret; Yamba, C. Bawa; Kasonka, Lackson; Bergström, Staffan; Ransjö-Arvidson, Anna-Berit (2010): Pregnancy loss. Spontaneous and induced abortions among young women in Lusaka, Zambia. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 247–262. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903353383.
- Daneback, Kristian; Månsson, Sven-Axel; Ross, Michael W.; Markham, Christine M. (2012): The Internet as a source of information about sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 583–598. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627739.
- Dank, Meredith; Lachman, Pamela; Zweig, Janine M.; Yahner, Jennifer (2014): Dating violence experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (5), S. 846–857. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9975-8.
- DePalma, Renée; Atkinson, Elizabeth (2010): The nature of institutional heteronormativity in primary schools and practice-based responses. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (8), S. 1669–1676. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.06.018.
- Dermody, Sarah S.; Marshal, Michael P.; Cheong, Jeewon; Burton, Chad; Hughes, Tonda; Aranda, Frances; Friedman, Mark S. (2014): Longitudinal disparities of hazardous drinking between sexual minority and heterosexual individuals from adolescence to young adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (1), S. 30–39. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9905-9.
- Dessel, Adrienne B.; Kulick, Alex; Wernick, Laura J.; Sullivan, Daniel (2017): The importance of teacher support. Differential impacts by gender and sexuality. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 136–144. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.002.
- Diarsvitri, Wienta; Utomo, Iwu Dwisetyani; Neeman, Teresa; Oktavian, Antonius (2011): Beyond sexual desire and curiosity. Sexuality among senior high school students in Papua and West Papua Provinces (Indonesia) and implications for HIV prevention. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (9), S. 1047–1060. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.599862.
- Dickenson, Janna A.; Huebner, David M. (2016): The Relationship Between Sexual Activity and Depressive Symptoms in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth: Effects of Gender and Family Support. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (3), S. 671–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0571-8.
- Doty, Nathan Daniel; Willoughby, Brian L. B.; Lindahl, Kristin M.; Malik, Neena M. (2010): Sexuality related social support among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1134–1147. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9566-x.
- Edwards, Rachel; Whittaker, Mette Kristensen; Beckett, Richard; Bishopp, Daz; Bates, Andrew (2012): Adolescents who have sexually harmed. An evaluation of a specialist treatment programme. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 91–111. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.635317.
- Eklund, Jenny M.; Kerr, Margaret; Stattin, Hakan (2010): Romantic relationships and delinquent behaviour in adolescence: the moderating role of delinquency propensity. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (3), S. 377–386. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.09.002.
- Ellis, Wendy E.; Chung-Hall, Janet; Dumas, Tara M. (2013): The role of peer group aggression in predicting adolescent dating violence and relationship quality. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 487–499. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9797-0.

- Eriksson, Elisabet; Lindmark, Gunilla; Axemo, Pia; Haddad, Beverley; Ahlberg, Beth Maina (2010): Ambivalence, silence and gender differences in church leaders' HIV-prevention messages to young people in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 103–114. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903141192.
- Espinosa-Hernandez, Graciela; Vasilenko, Sara A.; McPherson, Jenna L.; Gutierrez, Estefania; Rodriguez, Andrea (2017): Brief report. The role of three dimensions of sexual well-being in adolescents' life satisfaction. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 61–65. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.009.
- Fair, Brian (2011): Constructing Masculinity through Penetration Discourse. The Intersection of Misogyny and Homophobia in High School Wrestling. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 491–504. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10375936.
- Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2013): Trauma-informed sexuality education. Recognising the rights and resilience of youth. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 383–394. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.745808.
- Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2012): Young women's adolescent experiences of oral sex. Relation of age of initiation to sexual motivation, sexual coercion, and psychological functioning. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (5), S. 1191–1201. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.03.010.
- Felson, Richard B.; Cundiff, Patrick R. (2014): Sexual assault as a crime against young people. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 273–284. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0127-8.
- Ferguson, Christopher J.; Muñoz, Mónica E.; Garza, Adolfo; Galindo, Mariza (2014): Concurrent and prospective analyses of peer, television and social media influences on body dissatisfaction, eating disorder symptoms and life satisfaction in adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (1), S. 1–14. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9898-9.
- Fernet, Mylene; Hébert, Martine; Paradis, Alison (2016): Conflict resolution patterns and violence perpetration in adolescent couples. A gender-sensitive mixed-methods approach. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 51–59. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.02.004.
- Fielder, Robyn L.; Carey, Michael P. (2010): Predictors and consequences of sexual "hookups" among college students: a short-term prospective study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1105–1119. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9448-4.
- Fielder, Robyn L.; Walsh, Jennifer L.; Carey, Kate B.; Carey, Michael P. (2013): Predictors of sexual hookups: a theory-based, prospective study of first-year college women. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1425–1441. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0106-0.
- Firmin, Carlene; Warrington, Camille; Pearce, Jenny (2017): Sexual Exploitation and Its Impact on Developing Sexualities and Sexual Relationships. The Need for Contextual Social Work Interventions. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2318–2337. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw134.
- Fish, Jessica N.; Pasley, Kay (2015): Sexual (Minority) Trajectories, Mental Health, and Alcohol Use: A Longitudinal Study of Youth as They Transition to Adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (8), S. 1508–1527. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0280-6.
- Fitzpatrick, Kevin M.; Dulin, Akilah; Piko, Bettina (2010): Bullying and depressive symptomatology among low-income, African-American youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 634–645. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9426-8.
- Flannery, Dustin D.; Stephens, Clare L.; Thompson, Amy D. (2016): The Impact of High-Profile Sexual Abuse Cases in the Media on a Pediatric Emergency Department. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 627–635. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1187697.
- Formby, Eleanor (2011): Sex and relationships education, sexual health, and lesbian, gay and bisexual sexual cultures. Views from young people. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 255–266. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590078.
- Foshee, Vangie A.; Benefield, Thad; Dixon, Kimberly S.; Chang, Ling-Yin; Senkomago, Virginia; Ennett, Susan T. et al. (2015): The effects of moms and teens for safe dates: a dating abuse prevention program for adolescents exposed to domestic violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 995–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0272-6.

- Franklin, Anita; Smeaton, Emilie (2017): Recognising and responding to young people with learning disabilities who experience, or are at risk of, child sexual exploitation in the UK. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 474–481. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.11.009.
- Frawley, Patsie; Wilson, Nathan J. (2016): Young People with Intellectual Disability Talking About Sexuality Education and Information. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (4), S. 469–484. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9460-x.
- Fredlund, Cecilia; Svensson, Frida; Svedin, Carl Goran; Priebe, Gisela; Wadsby, Marie (2013): Adolescents' lifetime experience of selling sex. Development over five years. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (3), S. 312–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.743950.
- Frías, Sonia M.; Erviti, Joaquina (2014): Gendered experiences of sexual abuse of teenagers and children in Mexico. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (4), S. 776–787.
- Froyum, Carissa M. (2010): Making 'good girls'. Sexual agency in the sexuality education of low-income black girls. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 59–72. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903272583.
- Fu, Huiyan (2011): The bumpy road to socialise nature. Sex education in Japan. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 903–915. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.587894.
- Galinsky, Adena M.; Sonenstein, Freya Lund (2013): Relationship commitment, perceived equity, and sexual enjoyment among young adults in the United States. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (1), S. 93–104. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0003-y.
- Gartrell, Nanette K.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Goldberg, Naomi G. (2011): Adolescents of the U.S. National Longitudinal Lesbian Family Study: sexual orientation, sexual behavior, and sexual risk exposure. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (6), S. 1199–1209. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9692-2.
- Gattis, Maurice N.; Woodford, Michael R.; Han, Yoonsun (2014): Discrimination and depressive symptoms among sexual minority youth: is gay-affirming religious affiliation a protective factor? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1589–1599. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0342-y.
- Geary, Jan; Lambie, Ian; Seymour, Fred (2011): Consumer perspectives of New Zealand community treatment programmes for sexually abusive youth. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 181–195. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003778693.
- Genna, Natacha M. de; Larkby, Cynthia; Cornelius, Marie D. (2011): Pubertal timing and early sexual intercourse in the offspring of teenage mothers. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (10), S. 1315–1328. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9609-3.
- Gilliam, Melissa; Brindis, Claire D. (2011): Virtual Sex Ed. Youth, Race, Sex, and New Media. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 1–4. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0036-3.
- Gilliam, Melissa; Jagoda, Patrick; Jaworski, Erin; Hebert, Luciana E.; Lyman, Phoebe; Wilson, M. Claire (2015): "Because if we don't talk about it, how are we going to prevent it?". Lucidity, a narrative-based digital game about sexual violence. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (4), S. 391–404. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1123147.
- Gillmore, Mary Rogers; Chen, Angela Chia-Chen; Haas, Steven A.; Kopak, Albert M.; Robillard, Alyssa G. (2011): Do family and parenting factors in adolescence influence condom use in early adulthood in a multiethnic sample of young adults? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (11), S. 1503–1518. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9631-0.
- Goldbach, Jeremy T.; Gibbs, Jeremy J. (2017): A developmentally informed adaptation of minority stress for sexual minority adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 36–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.007.
- Goldman, Juliette D. G.; Grimbeek, Peter (2015): Preservice teachers' sources of information on mandatory reporting of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 238–258. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1009607.
- González-Ortega, Eva; Vicario-Molina, Isabel; Martínez, José Luis; Orgaz, Begoña (2015): The Internet as a Source of Sexual Information in a Sample of Spanish Adolescents. Associations with Sexual Behavior. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 12 (4), S. 290–300. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-015-0196-7.
- Goodrum, Nada M.; Armistead, Lisa P.; Tully, Erin C.; Cook, Sarah L.; Skinner, Donald (2017): Parenting and youth sexual risk in context. The role of community factors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 57, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.013.

- Govender, Kaymarlin (2011): The cool, the bad, the ugly, and the powerful. Identity struggles in schoolboy peer culture. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 887–901. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.586436.
- Gowen, L. Kris; Wings-Yanez, Nichole (2014): Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, and Questioning Youths' Perspectives of Inclusive School-Based Sexuality Education. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), S. 788–800.
- Graaf, Hanneke de; van de Schoot, Rens; Woertman, Liesbeth; Hawk, Skyler T.; Meeus, Wim (2012): Family cohesion and romantic and sexual initiation: a three wave longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 583–592. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9708-9.
- Graaf, Hanneke de; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine; Woertman, Liesbeth; Keijsers, Loes; Meijer, Suzanne; Meeus, Wim (2010): Parental support and knowledge and adolescents' sexual health: testing two mediational models in a national Dutch sample. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (2), S. 189–198. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-008-9387-3.
- Greslé-Favier, Claire (2010): The legacy of abstinence-only discourses and the place of pleasure in US discourses on teenage sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515098.
- Griffin, Helen Louise; Vettor, Shannon (2012): Predicting sexual re-offending in a UK sample of adolescents with intellectual disabilities. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 64–80. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.617013.
- Grose, Rose Grace; Grabe, Shelly; Kohfeldt, Danielle (2014): Sexual Education, Gender Ideology, and Youth Sexual Empowerment. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), 742.753.
- Gwirayi, Pesanayi (2013): The prevalence of child sexual abuse among secondary school pupils in Gweru, Zimbabwe. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 253–263. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.723755.
- Hackett, Simon; Carpenter, John; Patsios, Demi; Szilassy, Eszter (2013): Interprofessional and interagency training for working with young people with harmful sexual behaviours. An evaluation of outcomes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 329–344. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.753122.
- Hafford-Letchfield, Trish; Cocker, Christine; Ryan, Peter; Melonowska, Justyna (2017): Rights through Alliances. Findings from a European Project Tackling Homophobic and Transphobic Bullying in Schools through the Engagement of Families and Young People. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2338–2356. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw104.
- Hampshire, Kate; Porter, Gina; Mashiri, Mac; Maponya, Goodhope; Dube, Siphon (2011): Proposing love on the way to school. Mobility, sexuality and youth transitions in South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (2), S. 217–231. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.522255.
- Harden, K. Paige; Mendle, Jane (2011): Adolescent sexual activity and the development of delinquent behavior: the role of relationship context. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 825–838. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9601-y.
- Harris, Taylor; Rice, Eric; Rhoades, Harmony; Winetrobe, Hailey; Wenzel, Suzanne (2017): Gender Differences in the Path From Sexual Victimization to HIV Risk Behavior Among Homeless Youth. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 334–351. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1287146.
- Haste, Polly (2013): Sex education and masculinity. The 'problem' of boys. In: *Gender and Education* 25 (4), S. 515–527. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2013.789830.
- Hay, Carter; Meldrum, Ryan (2010): Bullying victimization and adolescent self-harm: testing hypotheses from general strain theory. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (5), S. 446–459. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9502-0.
- Haydon, Abigail A.; Halpern, Carolyn Tucker (2010): Older romantic partners and depressive symptoms during adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1240–1251. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9539-0.
- Heerde, Jessica A.; Scholes-Balog, Kirsty E.; Hemphill, Sheryl A. (2015): Associations between youth homelessness, sexual offenses, sexual victimization, and sexual risk behaviors: a systematic literature review. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 181–212. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0375-2.
- Hensel, Devon J.; Fortenberry, J. Dennis; O'Sullivan, Lucia F.; Orr, Donald P. (2011): The developmental association of sexual self-concept with sexual behavior among adolescent women. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 675–684. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.09.005.

- Heywood, Wendy; Patrick, Kent; Pitts, Marian; Mitchell, Anne (2016): "Dude, I'm Seventeen ... It's Okay Not to Have Sex by This Age": Feelings, Reasons, Pressures, and Intentions Reported by Adolescents Who Have Not Had Sexual Intercourse. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (9), S. 1207–1214. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2015.1092105.
- Hilberink, Sander R.; Kruijver, Egbert; Wiegerink, Diana J. H. G.; Vliet Vlieland, Thea P. M. (2013): A Pilot Implementation of an Intervention to Promote Sexual Health in Adolescents and Young Adults in Rehabilitation. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 31 (4), S. 373–392. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9288-6.
- Hipwell, Alison E.; Stepp, Stephanie D.; Keenan, Kate; Chung, Tammy; Loeber, Rolf (2011): Brief report: Parsing the heterogeneity of adolescent girls' sexual behavior. Relationships to individual and interpersonal factors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (3), S. 589–592. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.03.002.
- Hirst, Julia (2013): 'It's got to be about enjoying yourself'. Young people, sexual pleasure, and sex and relationships education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 423–436. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.747433.
- Hlavka, H. R. (2014): Normalizing Sexual Violence. Young Women Account for Harassment and Abuse. In: *Gender & Society* 28 (3), S. 337–358. DOI: 10.1177/0891243214526468.
- Höing, Mechtild; Jonker, Marianne; Berlo, Willy van (2010): Juvenile sex offenders in a Dutch mandatory educational programme. Subtypes and characteristics. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (3), S. 332–346. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903350991.
- Hooghe, Marc (2011): The impact of gendered friendship patterns on the prevalence of homophobia among Belgian late adolescents. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (3), S. 543–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9635-y.
- Hooghe, Marc; Meeusen, Cecil (2012): Homophobia and the transition to adulthood: a three year panel study among Belgian late adolescents and young adults, 2008-2011. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (9), S. 1197–1207. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9786-3.
- Houser, John J.; Mayeux, Lara; Cross, Cassandra (2015): Peer status and aggression as predictors of dating popularity in adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 683–695. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0174-z.
- Huyge, Ellen; Maele, Dimitri van; Houtte, Mieke van (2014): Does students' machismo fit in school? Clarifying the implications of traditional gender role ideology for school belonging. In: *Gender and Education* 27 (1), S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2014.972921.
- Hyde, Abbey; Carney, Marie; Drennan, Jonathan; Butler, Michelle; Lohan, Maria; Howlett, Etaoine (2010): The silent treatment. Parents' narratives of sexuality education with young people. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 359–371. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903514455.
- Ingevaldson, Sara; Goulding, Anneli; Tidefors, Inga (2016): Experiences of intimate relationships in young men who sexually offended during adolescence. Interviews 10 years later. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 410–422. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1177125.
- Jackson, Sue; Weatherall, Ann (2010): The (Im)possibilities of Feminist School Based Sexuality Education. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 20 (2), S. 166–185.
- Jennings, Wesley G.; Richards, Tara N.; Tomsich, Elizabeth; Gover, Angela R. (2015): Investigating the Role of Child Sexual Abuse in Intimate Partner Violence Victimization and Perpetration in Young Adulthood From a Propensity Score Matching Approach. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 659–681. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1057665.
- Jerman, Petra; Constantine, Norman A. (2010): Demographic and psychological predictors of parent-adolescent communication about sex: a representative statewide analysis. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1164–1174. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9546-1.
- Johnson, Brooke (2010): A Few Good Boys. Masculinity at a Military-Style Charter School. In: *Men and Masculinities* 12 (5), S. 575–596. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X09342228.
- Johnson, Matthew D. (2013): Parent-child relationship quality directly and indirectly influences hooking up behavior reported in young adulthood through alcohol use in adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1463–1472. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0098-9.

- Johnston, Lisa G.; Mon, Myo Myo; Steinhaus, Mara; Sass, Justine (2017): Correlates of Forced Sex Among Young Men Who Have Sex With Men in Yangon and Monywa, Myanmar. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 1001–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0761-z.
- Jones, Sara; Joyal, Christian C.; Cisler, Josh M.; Bai, Shasha (2017): Exploring Emotion Regulation in Juveniles Who Have Sexually Offended. An fMRI Study. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 40–57. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1259280.
- Joyal, Christian C.; Carpentier, Julie; Martin, Caroline (2016): Discriminant factors for adolescent sexual offending. On the usefulness of considering both victim age and sibling incest. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 54, S. 10–22.
- Kaestle, Christine E.; Allen, Katherine R. (2011): The role of masturbation in healthy sexual development: perceptions of young adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 983–994. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9722-0.
- Kaltiala-Heino, Riittakerttu; Fröjd, Sari; Marttunen, Mauri (2016): Sexual harassment victimization in adolescence. Associations with family background. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 56, S. 11–19.
- Katz, Jennifer; Schneider, Monica E. (2013): Casual hook up sex during the first year of college: Prospective associations with attitudes about sex and love relationships. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1451–1462. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0078-0.
- Katz-Wise, Sabra L.; Rosario, Margaret; Calzo, Jerel P.; Scherer, Emily A.; Sarda, Vishnudas; Austin, S. Bryn (2017): Endorsement and Timing of Sexual Orientation Developmental Milestones Among Sexual Minority Young Adults in the Growing Up Today Study. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (2), S. 172–185. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1170757.
- Kehily, Mary Jane (2012): Contextualising the sexualisation of girls debate. Innocence, experience and young female sexuality. In: *Gender and Education* 24 (3), S. 255–268. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2012.670391.
- Kelly, Angela; Worth, Heather; Akuani, Frances; Kepa, Barbara; Kupul, Martha; Walizopa, Lucy et al. (2010): Gendered talk about sex, sexual relationships and HIV among young people in Papua New Guinea. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 221–232. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903181107.
- Kennett, Deborah J.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Schultz, Kristen E. (2011): Sexual resourcefulness and the impact of family, sex education, media and peers. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615624.
- Kijak, Remigiusz J. (2011): A Desire for Love: Considerations on Sexuality and Sexual Education of People With Intellectual Disability in Poland. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (1), S. 65–74. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9184-2.
- Killoren, Sarah E.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; Christopher, F. Scott (2011): Family and cultural correlates of Mexican-origin youths' sexual intentions. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (6), S. 707–718. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9587-5.
- Killoren, Sarah E.; Zeiders, Katharine H.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J. (2016): The Sociocultural Context of Mexican-Origin Pregnant Adolescents' Attitudes Toward Teen Pregnancy and Links to Future Outcomes. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 887–899. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0387-9.
- Kjaran, Jón; Kristinsdóttir, Guðrún (2014): Queering the environment and caring for the self. Icelandic LGBT students' experience of the upper secondary school. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 23 (1), S. 1–20. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2014.910250.
- Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2010): Sexually coercive behavior in male youth: population survey of general and specific risk factors. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1161–1169. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9572-9.
- Kloppen, Kathrine; Haugland, Siren; Svedin, Carl-Göran; Maehle, Magne; Breivik, Kyrre (2016): Prevalence of Child Sexual Abuse in the Nordic Countries. A Literature Review. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 37–55. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1108944.
- Kontula, Osmo (2010): The evolution of sex education and students' sexual knowledge in Finland in the 2000s. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 373–386. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515095.
- Koo, Kelly H.; Stephens, Kari A.; Lindgren, Kristen P.; George, William H. (2012): Misogyny, acculturation, and ethnic identity: relation to rape-supportive attitudes in Asian American college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1005–1014. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9729-1.

- Krahé, Barbara; Berger, Anja (2017): Gendered pathways from child sexual abuse to sexual aggression victimization and perpetration in adolescence and young adulthood. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 261–272. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.10.004.
- Kuyper, Lisette; Wit, John de; Adam, Philippe; Woertman, Liesbeth (2012): Doing more good than harm? The effects of participation in sex research on young people in the Netherlands. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (2), S. 497–506. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9780-y.
- La Roi, Chaïm; Kretschmer, Tina; Dijkstra, Jan Kornelis; Veenstra, René; Oldehinkel, Albertine J. (2016): Disparities in Depressive Symptoms Between Heterosexual and Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth in a Dutch Cohort: The TRAILS Study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (3), S. 440–456. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0403-0.
- Lamb, Sharon; Farmer, Kaelin M.; Kosterina, Elena; Lambe Sariñana, Susan; Plocha, Aleksandra; Randazzo, Renee (2016): What's sexy? Adolescent girls discuss confidence, danger, and media influence. In: *Gender and Education* 28 (4), S. 527–545. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1107528.
- Lambie, Ian; Price, Mnthali (2015): Transitioning youth with sexually harmful behaviour back into the community. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 244–265. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.873829.
- Langa, Malose (2016): The Value of Using a Psychodynamic Theory in Researching Black Masculinities of Adolescent Boys in Alexandra Township, South Africa. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (3), S. 260–288. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15586434.
- Lansford, Jennifer E.; Dodge, Kenneth A.; Fontaine, Reid Griffith; Bates, John E.; Pettit, Gregory S. (2014): Peer rejection, affiliation with deviant peers, delinquency, and risky sexual behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (10), S. 1742–1751. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0175-y.
- Lea, Toby; Wit, John de; Reynolds, Robert (2014): Minority stress in lesbian, gay, and bisexual young adults in Australia: associations with psychological distress, suicidality, and substance use. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1571–1578. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0266-6.
- Leech, Tamara G. J.; Dias, Janice Johnson (2012): Risky sexual behavior: a race-specific social consequence of obesity. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (1), S. 41–52. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9670-6.
- Lefkowitz, Eva S.; Vasilenko, Sara A.; Leavitt, Chelom E. (2016): Oral vs. Vaginal Sex Experiences and Consequences Among First-Year College Students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (2), S. 329–337. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0654-6.
- Lehrer, Jocelyn A.; Lehrer, Evelyn L.; Koss, Mary P. (2013): Unwanted sexual experiences in young men: evidence from a survey of university students in Chile. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (2), S. 213–223. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0004-x.
- Lev-Wiesel, Rachel; Markus, Liora (2013): Perception vs. circumstances of the child sexual abuse event in relation to depression and post-traumatic stress symptomatology. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 519–533. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800932.
- Limmer, Mark (2010): Young men, masculinities and sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 349–358. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515093.
- Lin, Danhua; Li, Xiaoming; Fan, Xinghua; Fang, Xiaoyi (2011): Child sexual abuse and its relationship with health risk behaviors among rural children and adolescents in Hunan, China. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (9), S. 680–687. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2011.05.006.
- Lindahl, Mats G.; Lundin, Mattias (2016): How do 15–16 year old students use scientific knowledge to justify their reasoning about human sexuality and relationships? In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 60, S. 121–130. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2016.08.009.
- Lindroth, Malin (2014): Sex education and young people in group homes. Balancing risks, rights and resilience in sexual health promotion. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 400–413. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919910.
- Livingston, Jennifer A.; Testa, Maria; Windle, Michael; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2015): Sexual risk at first coitus. Does alcohol make a difference? In: *Journal of Adolescence* 43, S. 148–158. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.05.018.
- Löfgren-Mårtenson, Lotta (2012): "I Want to Do it Right!" A Pilot Study of Swedish Sex Education and Young People with Intellectual Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 209–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9239-z.

- Loftus, Jeni; Kelly, Brian C.; Mustillo, Sarah A. (2011): Depressive symptoms among adolescent girls in relationships with older partners: causes and lasting effects? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 800–813. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9589-3.
- Looze, Margaretha de; Harakeh, Zeena; van Dorsselaer, Saskia A. F. M.; Raaijmakers, Quinten A. W.; Vollebergh, Wilma A. M.; ter Bogt, Tom F. M. (2012): Explaining educational differences in adolescent substance use and early sexual debut. The role of parents and peers. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 1035–1044. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.02.009.
- Lopez, Vera; Kopak, Albert; Robillard, Alyssa; Gillmore, Mary Rogers; Holliday, Rhonda C.; Braithwaite, Ronald L. (2011): Pathways to sexual risk taking among female adolescent detainees. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (8), S. 945–957. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9623-5.
- Lourie, Michael A.; Needham, Belinda L. (2017): Sexual Orientation Discordance and Young Adult Mental Health. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 943–954. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0553-8.
- Low, Sabina; Polanin, Joshua R.; Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): The role of social networks in physical and relational aggression among young adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1078–1089. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9933-5.
- Luder, Marie-Thérèse; Pittet, Isabelle; Berchtold, André; Akre, Christina; Michaud, Pierre-André; Surís, Joan-Carles (2011): Associations between online pornography and sexual behavior among adolescents: myth or reality? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1027–1035. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9714-0.
- Lyons, Heidi; Manning, Wendy; Giordano, Peggy; Longmore, Monica (2013): Predictors of heterosexual casual sex among young adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 585–593. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0051-3.
- Macapagal, Kathryn; Janssen, Erick; Matson, Margaret; Finn, Peter R.; Heiman, Julia R. (2017): The Impact of Gain- and Loss-Framed Messages on Young Adults' Sexual Decision Making: An Experimental Study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (2), S. 385–394. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0679-x.
- MacDonald, Jo-Ann; Gagnon, Anita J.; Mitchell, Claudia; Di Meglio, Giuseppina; Rennick, Janet E.; Cox, Joseph (2011): Asking to listen. Towards a youth perspective on sexual health education and needs. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 443–457. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595268.
- Maikovich-Fong, Andrea Kohn; Jaffee, Sara R. (2010): Sex differences in childhood sexual abuse characteristics and victims' emotional and behavioral problems. Findings from a national sample of youth. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34 (6), S. 429–437. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2009.10.006.
- Makin-Byrd, Kerry; Bierman, Karen L. (2013): Individual and family predictors of the perpetration of dating violence and victimization in late adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 536–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9810-7.
- Mallet, Pascal; Herbe, Dominique (2011): Does knowledge about sexuality prevent adolescents from developing rape-supportive beliefs? In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 48 (4), S. 372–380. DOI: 10.1080/00224491003794048.
- Manninen, Sari; Huuki, Tuija; Sunnari, Vappu (2011): Earn Yo' Respect! Respect in the Status Struggle of Finnish School Boys. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (3), S. 335–357. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10369476.
- Marcell, Arik V.; Eftim, Sorina E.; Sonenstein, Freya L.; Pleck, Joseph H. (2011): Associations of Family and Peer Experiences with Masculinity Attitude Trajectories at the Individual and Group Level in Adolescent and Young Adult Males. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (5), S. 565–587. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X11409363.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa (2015): Prevalence of dating violence among sexual minority youth: variation across gender, sexual minority identity and gender of sexual partners. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 211–224. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0089-0.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa; Crosnoe, Robert (2012): Sexual minority status, peer harassment, and adolescent depression. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 1001–1011. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.02.006.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa; Fromme, Kim (2016): Trajectories of dating violence. Differences by sexual minority status and gender. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 28–37. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.02.008.
- Masson, Helen; Balfe, Myles; Hackett, Simon; Phillips, Josie (2012): Making use of historical case material. The problems of looking back and the implications for service development in relation to research and evaluation activities. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 112–122. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.630539.

- McCartan, Fiona Mairead; Law, Heather; Murphy, Maeve; Bailey, Susan (2011): Child and adolescent females who present with sexually abusive behaviours. A 10-year UK prevalence study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 4–14. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.488302.
- McKee, Alan (2012): The importance of entertainment for sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 499–509. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627727.
- McMichael, Celia; Gifford, Sandra (2010): Narratives of sexual health risk and protection amongst young people from refugee backgrounds in Melbourne, Australia. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 263–277. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903359265.
- McMillan, Karen; Worth, Heather (2011): The impact of socio-cultural context on young people's condom use. Evidence from two Pacific Island countries. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (3), S. 313–326. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.529945.
- Meek, Rosie (2011): The possible selves of young fathers in prison. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (5), S. 941–949. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.12.005.
- Milan, Stephanie; Wortel, Sanne (2015): Family obligation values as a protective and vulnerability factor among low-income adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (6), S. 1183–1193. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0206-8.
- Milhausen, Robin R.; Buchholz, Andrea C.; Opperman, Emily A.; Benson, Lindsay E. (2015): Relationships Between Body Image, Body Composition, Sexual Functioning, and Sexual Satisfaction Among Heterosexual Young Adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (6), S. 1621–1633. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0328-9.
- Miller, S. A. (2016): "How You Bully a Girl". Sexual Drama and the Negotiation of Gendered Sexuality in High School. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (5), S. 721–744. DOI: 10.1177/0891243216664723.
- Miller, Shari; Williams, Jason; Cutbush, Stacey; Gibbs, Deborah; Clinton-Sherrod, Monique; Jones, Sarah (2013): Dating violence, bullying, and sexual harassment: longitudinal profiles and transitions over time. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 607–618. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9914-8.
- Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Ybarra, Michele L.; Korchmaros, Josephine D. (2014): Sexual harassment among adolescents of different sexual orientations and gender identities. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (2), S. 280–295.
- Moilanen, Kristin L. (2016): Why Do Parents Grant or Deny Consent for Adolescent Participation in Sexuality Research? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 1020–1036. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0445-y.
- Moosmann, Danyel A. V.; Roosa, Mark W. (2015): Exploring Mexican American adolescent romantic relationship profiles and adjustment. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 43, S. 181–192. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.06.004.
- Mora, Claudia; Monteiro, Simone (2010): Vulnerability to STIs/HIV. Sociability and the life trajectories of young women who have sex with women in Rio de Janeiro. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 115–124. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903180471.
- Muehlenhard, Charlene L.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D. (2016): The Complexities of Sexual Consent Among College Students. A Conceptual and Empirical Review. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (4-5), S. 1–31.
- Muhanguzi, Florence Kyoheirwe (2011): Gender and sexual vulnerability of young women in Africa. Experiences of young girls in secondary schools in Uganda. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 713–725. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.571290.
- Muise, Amy; Preyde, Michèle; Maitland, Scott B.; Milhausen, Robin R. (2010): Sexual identity and sexual well-being in female heterosexual university students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (4), S. 915–925. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9492-8.
- Mulumeoderhwa, Maroyi; Harris, Geoff (2015): Forced sex, rape and sexual exploitation. Attitudes and experiences of high school students in South Kivu, Democratic Republic of Congo. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 17 (3), S. 284–295.
- Munoz-Laboy, Miguel; Murray, Laura R.; Wittlin, Natalie; Wilson, Patrick A.; Terto, Veriano; Parker, Richard (2011): Divine targets. Youth at the centre of Catholic and Pentecostal responses to HIV and AIDS in Brazil. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 657–668. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.565519.

- Murphy, Meghan (2015): How organisational culture influences teachers' support of openly gay, lesbian and bisexual students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 263–275.
- Murry, Velma McBride; Berkel, Cady; Chen, Yi-Fu; Brody, Gene H.; Gibbons, Frederick X.; Gerrard, Meg (2011): Intervention induced changes on parenting practices, youth self-pride and sexual norms to reduce HIV-related behaviors among rural African American youths. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (9), S. 1147–1163. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9642-x.
- Mustanski, Brian; Greene, George J.; Ryan, Daniel; Whitton, Sarah W. (2015): Feasibility, Acceptability, and Initial Efficacy of an Online Sexual Health Promotion Program for LGBT Youth. The Queer Sex Ed Intervention. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 52 (2), S. 220–230.
- Mustanski, Brian; Liu, Richard T. (2013): A longitudinal study of predictors of suicide attempts among lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (3), S. 437–448. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0013-9.
- Needham, Belinda L. (2012): Sexual attraction and trajectories of mental health and substance use during the transition from adolescence to adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 179–190. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9729-4.
- Newby, Katie; Wallace, Louise M.; Dunn, Orla; Brown, Katherine E. (2012): A survey of English teenagers' sexual experience and preferences for school-based sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 231–251. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615582.
- Niehaus, Ashley F.; Jackson, Joan; Davies, Stephanie (2010): Sexual self-schemas of female child sexual abuse survivors. Relationships with risky sexual behavior and sexual assault in adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (6), S. 1359–1374. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9600-9.
- Nielsena, Silja; Paasonen, Susanna; Spišák, Sanna (2015): 'Pervy role-play and such'. Girls' experiences of sexual messaging online. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 472–485.
- Nishina, Adrienne (2012): Microcontextual characteristics of peer victimization experiences and adolescents' daily well-being. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 191–201. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9669-z.
- Norman, Moss E. (2011): Embodying the Double-Bind of Masculinity. Young Men and Discourses of Normalcy, Health, Heterosexuality, and Individualism. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 430–449. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X11409360.
- Novak, Jamie; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Partner Violence During Adolescence and Young Adulthood: Individual and Relationship Level Risk Factors. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (9), S. 1849–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0484-4.
- O'Brien, Jennifer E.; White, Kevin; Wu, Qi; Killian-Farrell, Candace (2016): Mental Health and Behavioral Outcomes of Sexual and Nonsexual Child Maltreatment Among Child Welfare-Involved Youth. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 483–503. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1167801.
- O'Hara, Ross E.; Cooper, M. Lynne (2015): Bidirectional associations between alcohol use and sexual risk-taking behavior from adolescence into young adulthood. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (4), S. 857–871. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0510-8.
- O'Higgins, Siobhán; Gabhainn, Saoirse Nic (2010): Youth participation in setting the agenda. Learning outcomes for sex education in Ireland. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 387–403. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515096.
- Oidtman, Jessica; Sherman, Susan G.; Morgan, Anthony; German, Danielle; Arrington-Sanders, Renata (2017): Satisfaction and Condomless Anal Sex at Sexual Debut and Sexual Risk Among Young Black Same-Sex Attracted Men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 947–959. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0831-2.
- Ojanen, Timo Tapani; Boonmongkon, Pimpawun; Samakkeekarom, Ronnapoom; Samoh, Nattharat; Cholratana, Mudjalini; Guadamuz, Thomas Ebanan (2015): Connections between online harassment and offline violence among youth in Central Thailand. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 44, S. 159–169.
- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Billen, Rhett M.; Conrad, Kathryn A.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Sex, commitment, and casual sex relationships among college men: a mixed-methods analysis. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 561–571. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0047-z.

- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Hooking up and penetrative hookups: correlates that differentiate college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 573–583. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-9907-9.
- Oosten, Johanna M. F. van; Vandenbosch, Laura (2017): Sexy online self-presentation on social network sites and the willingness to engage in sexting: A comparison of gender and age. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 54, S. 42–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.11.006.
- Orpinas, Pamela; Hsieh, Hsien-Lin; Song, Xiao; Holland, Kristin; Nahapetyan, Lusine (2013): Trajectories of physical dating violence from middle to high school: association with relationship quality and acceptability of aggression. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 551–565. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9881-5.
- Ott, Miles Q.; Corliss, Heather L.; Wypij, David; Rosario, Margaret; Austin, S. Bryn (2011): Stability and change in self-reported sexual orientation identity in young people: application of mobility metrics. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (3), S. 519–532. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9691-3.
- Parent, Sylvie; Bannon, Joëlle (2012): Sexual abuse in sport. What about boys? In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (2), S. 354–359. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2011.11.004.
- Parkes, Alison; Wight, Daniel; Henderson, Marion; West, Patrick (2010): Does early sexual debut reduce teenagers' participation in tertiary education? Evidence from the SHARE longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (5), S. 741–754. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.006.
- Pascoe, C. J. (2011): Resource and Risk. Youth Sexuality and New Media Use. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 5–17. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0042-5.
- Patrick, Megan E.; Lee, Christine M. (2010): Sexual motivations and engagement in sexual behavior during the transition to college. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 674–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9435-9.
- Patrick, Megan E.; Maggs, Jennifer L. (2010): Profiles of motivations for alcohol use and sexual behavior among first-year university students. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (5), S. 755–765. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.003.
- Patrick, Megan E.; Morgan, Nicole; Maggs, Jennifer L.; Lefkowitz, Eva S. (2011): "I got your back": friends' understandings regarding college student spring break behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (1), S. 108–120. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9515-8.
- Pearce, Jenny J. (2014): 'What's Going On' to Safeguard Children and Young People from Child Sexual Exploitation. A Review of Local Safeguarding Children Boards' Work to Protect Children from Sexual Exploitation. In: *Child Abuse Review* 23 (3), S. 159–170. DOI: 10.1002/car.2269.
- Pearson, Jennifer; Wilkinson, Lindsey (2013): Family relationships and adolescent well-being: are families equally protective for same-sex attracted youth? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 376–393. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9865-5.
- Peter, Jochen; Valkenburg, Patti M. (2011): The use of sexually explicit internet material and its antecedents: a longitudinal comparison of adolescents and adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1015–1025. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9644-x.
- Petering, Robin (2016): Sexual risk, substance use, mental health, and trauma experiences of gang-involved homeless youth. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 48, S. 73–81. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.01.009.
- Piccigallo, Jaqueline R.; Lilley, Terry G.; Miller, Susan L. (2012): "It's Cool to Care about Sexual Violence". Men's Experiences with Sexual Assault Prevention. In: *Men and Masculinities* 15 (5), S. 507–525. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X12458590.
- Pingel, Emily Sweetnam; Thomas, Laura; Harmell, Chelsea; Bauermeister, Jose (2013): Creating comprehensive, youth centered, culturally appropriate sex education: What do young gay, bisexual and questioning men want? In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 10 (4). DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0134-5.
- Pomerantz, S.; Raby, R.; Stefanik, A. (2013): Girls Run the World? Caught between Sexism and Postfeminism in School. In: *Gender & Society* 27 (2), S. 185–207. DOI: 10.1177/0891243212473199.
- Porta, Carolyn M.; Gower, Amy L.; Mehus, Christopher J.; Yu, Xiaohui; Saewyc, Elizabeth M.; Eisenberg, Marla E. (2017): "Kicked out". LGBTQ youths' bathroom experiences and preferences. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 107–112. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.005.
- Pradhan, Manas Ranjan; Ram, Usha (2010): Perceived gender role that shape youth sexual behaviour. Evidence from rural Orissa, India. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (4), S. 543–551. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.014.

- Priebe, Gisela; Bäckström, Martin; Ainsaar, Mare (2010): Vulnerable adolescent participants' experience in surveys on sexuality and sexual abuse. Ethical aspects. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34 (6), S. 438–447.
- Pritchard, Duncan; Graham, Nicola; Penney, Heather; Owen, Gwynne; Peters, Sandra; Mace, F. Charles (2016): Multi-component behavioural intervention reduces harmful sexual behaviour in a 17-year-old male with autism spectrum disorder. A case study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 368–378. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1130269.
- Pullman, Lesleigh E.; Seto, Michael C. (2012): Assessment and treatment of adolescent sexual offenders. Implications of recent research on generalist versus specialist explanations. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (3), S. 203–209.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2012): Popular culture as emotional provocation. The material enactment of queer pedagogies in a high school classroom. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 511–522. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627728.
- Raine, Tina R.; Gard, Jennifer C.; Boyer, Cherrie B.; Haider, Sadia; Brown, Beth A.; Ramirez Hernandez, F. Antonio; Harper, Cynthia C. (2010): Contraceptive decision-making in sexual relationships. Young men's experiences, attitudes and values. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 373–386. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903524769.
- Ramseyer Winter, Virginia; Brandon-Friedman, Richard A.; Ely, Gretchen E. (2016): Sexual health behaviors and outcomes among current and former foster youth. A review of the literature. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 64, S. 1–14. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.02.023.
- Rasmussen, Lucinda A. (2013): Young people who sexually abuse. A historical perspective and future directions. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (1), S. 119–141. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.744646.
- Rasmussen, Lucinda A.; Lev-Wiesel, Rachel; Eisikovits, Zvi (2013): Current perspectives on children and youth who sexually abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (1), S. 1–8. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.744644.
- Reyes, H. Luz McNaughton; Foshee, Vangie A.; Niolon, Phyllis Holditch; Reidy, Dennis E.; Hall, Jeffrey E. (2016): Gender Role Attitudes and Male Adolescent Dating Violence Perpetration: Normative Beliefs as Moderators. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 350–360. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0278-0.
- Rice, Eric; Winetrobe, Hailey; Holloway, Ian W.; Montoya, Jorge; Plant, Aaron; Kordic, Timothy (2015): Cell phone internet access, online sexual solicitation, partner seeking, and sexual risk behavior among adolescents. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 755–763. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0366-3.
- Rieger, Gerulf; Savin-Williams, Ritch C. (2012): Gender nonconformity, sexual orientation, and psychological well-being. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (3), S. 611–621. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9738-0.
- Robertson, Roni Diamant (2013): The invisibility of adolescent sexual development in foster care. Seriously addressing sexually transmitted infections and access to services. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (3), S. 493–504. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.12.009.
- Rosario, Margaret; Schrimshaw, Eric W.; Hunter, Joyce (2012): Homelessness among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth: implications for subsequent internalizing and externalizing symptoms. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 544–560. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9681-3.
- Rossi, Erika; Poulin, François; Boislard, Marie-Aude (2017): Trajectories of Annual Number of Sexual Partners from Adolescence to Emerging Adulthood: Individual and Family Predictors. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 995–1008. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0571-6.
- Russell, Brenda L.; Oswald, Debra L. (2016): When Sexism Cuts Both Ways. Predictors of Tolerance of Sexual Harassment of Men. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (5), S. 524–544. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15602745.
- Rutledge, Scott Edward; Siebert, Darcy Clay; Chonody, Jill; Killian, Michael (2011): Information about human sexuality. Sources, satisfaction, and perceived knowledge among college students. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 471–487. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.601133.
- Sabina, Chiara; Cuevas, Carlos A.; Cotignola-Pickens, Heather M. (2016): Longitudinal dating violence victimization among Latino teens: Rates, risk factors, and cultural influences. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 47, S. 5–15. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.11.003.
- Samms, Kimika M.; Cholewa, Blaire E. (2014): Exploring the context of child sexual abuse in Jamaica. Addressing the deficits. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 115–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870948.

- Savin-Williams, Ritch C.; Joyner, Kara (2014): The dubious assessment of gay, lesbian, and bisexual adolescents of add health. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (3), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0219-5.
- Schnurr, Melissa P.; Lohman, Brenda J. (2013): The impact of collective efficacy on risks for adolescents' perpetration of dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 518–535. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9909-5.
- Schönbucher, Verena; Maier, Thomas; Mohler-Kuo, Meichun; Schnyder, Ulrich; Landolt, Markus A. (2014): Adolescent perspectives on social support received in the aftermath of sexual abuse: a qualitative study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (3), S. 571–586. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0230-x.
- Schwarz, Beate; Stutz, Melanie; Ledermann, Thomas (2012): Perceived interparental conflict and early adolescents' friendships: the role of attachment security and emotion regulation. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (9), S. 1240–1252. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9769-4.
- Seelman, Kristie L.; Forge, Nicholas; Walls, N. Eugene; Bridges, Nadine (2015): School engagement among LGBTQ high school students. The roles of safe adults and gay–straight alliance characteristics. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 57, S. 19–29. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.07.021.
- Seidel, Anja; Wienholz, Sabine; Michel, Marion; Lupp, Melanie; Riedel-Heller, Steffi Gerlinde (2014): Sexual Knowledge Among Adolescents with Physical Handicaps. A Systematic Review. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (3), S. 429–441. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9326-4.
- Seto, Michael C.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2015): Viewing child pornography: prevalence and correlates in a representative community sample of young Swedish men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 67–79. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0244-4.
- Sevcikova, Anna (2016): Girls' and boys' experience with teen sexting in early and late adolescence. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 51, S. 156–162. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.06.007.
- Shandra, Carrie L.; Chowdhury, Afra R. (2012): The first sexual experience among adolescent girls with and without disabilities. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (4), S. 515–532. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9668-0.
- Shrier, Lydia A.; Feldman, Henry A.; Black, Shimrit K.; Walls, Courtney; Kendall, Ashley D.; Lops, Christopher; Beardslee, William R. (2012): Momentary affective states surrounding sexual intercourse in depressed adolescents and young adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (5), S. 1161–1171. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9787-4.
- Shulman, Shmuel; Zlotnik, Aynat; Shachar-Shapira, Lital; Connolly, Jennifer; Bohr, Yvonne (2012): Adolescent daughters' romantic competence: the role of divorce, quality of parenting, and maternal romantic history. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 593–606. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9748-9.
- Sipsma, Heather L.; Ickovics, Jeannette R.; Lin, Haiqun; Kershaw, Trace S. (2015): The impact of future expectations on adolescent sexual risk behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 170–183. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0082-7.
- Slotboom, Anne-Marie; Hendriks, Jan; Verbruggen, Janna (2011): Contrasting adolescent female and male sexual aggression. A self-report study on prevalence and predictors of sexual aggression. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 15–33. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.544413.
- Smiler, Andrew P.; Frankel, Loren B. W.; Savin-Williams, Ritch C. (2011): From kissing to coitus? Sex-of-partner differences in the sexual milestone achievement of young men. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 727–735. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.08.009.
- Smith, Connie; Allardyce, Stuart; Hackett, Simon; Bradbury-Jones, Caroline; Lazenbatt, Anne; Taylor, Julie (2014): Practice and policy in the UK with children and young people who display harmful sexual behaviours. An analysis and critical review. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 267–280. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927010.
- Smith, Mark; Woodiwiss, Jo (2017): Sexuality, Innocence and Agency in Narratives of Childhood Sexual Abuse. Implications for Social Work. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2173–2189. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw160.
- Smith, Marshall (2013): Youth Viewing Sexually Explicit Material Online. Addressing the Elephant on the Screen. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 10 (1), S. 62–75. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-012-0103-4.
- Smith-Darden, Joanne P.; Reidy, Dennis E.; Kernsmith, Poco D. (2016): Adolescent stalking and risk of violence. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 52, S. 191–200. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.08.005.

- Sommer, Marni (2010): Where the education system and women's bodies collide. The social and health impact of girls' experiences of menstruation and schooling in Tanzania. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (4), S. 521–529. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.03.008.
- Sommer, Marni; Likindikoki, Samuel; Kaaya, Sylvia (2015): "Bend a fish when the fish is not yet dry": adolescent boys' perceptions of sexual risk in Tanzania. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 583–595. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0406-z.
- Sorhaindo, Annik; Bonell, Chris; Fletcher, Adam; Jessiman, Patricia; Keogh, Peter; Mitchell, Kirstin (2016): Being targeted. Young women's experience of being identified for a teenage pregnancy prevention programme. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 181–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.03.013.
- Soylu, Nusret; Alpaslan, Ahmet Hamdi; Ayaz, Muhammed; Esenyel, Selcen; Oruc, Mucahit (2013): Psychiatric disorders and characteristics of abuse in sexually abused children and adolescents with and without intellectual disabilities. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 34 (12), S. 4334–4342. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2013.09.010.
- Soylu, Nusret; Ayaz, Muhammed; Yüksel, Tuğb (2014): Early-married and sexually abused girls differ in their psychiatric outcomes. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (9), S. 1552–1559.
- van der Stege, Heleen A.; Hilberink, Sander R.; Visser, Adriaan P.; Staa, AnneLoes van (2014): Motivational factors in discussing sexual health with young people with chronic conditions or disabilities. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (6), S. 635–651. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.918877.
- Sterzing, Paul R.; Ratliff, G. Allen; Gartner, Rachel E.; McGeough, Briana L.; Johnson, Kelly C. (2017): Social Ecological Correlates of Polyvictimization among a National Sample of Transgender, Genderqueer, and Cisgender Sexual Minority Adolescents. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 67, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.02.017.
- Stevens, Peter; Hutchin, Katie; French, Lesley; Craissati, Jackie (2013): Developmental and offence-related characteristics of different types of adolescent sex offender. A community sample. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 138–157. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.645889.
- Stevens-Watkins, Danelle; Brown-Wright, Lynda; Tyler, Kenneth (2011): Brief report. The number of sexual partners and race-related stress in African American adolescents: preliminary findings. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 191–194. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.02.003.
- Strömwall, Leif A.; Alfredsson, Helen; Landström, Sara (2013): Rape victim and perpetrator blame and the Just World hypothesis. The influence of victim gender and age. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 207–217. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.683455.
- Stulhofer, Aleksandar; Busko, Vesna; Landripet, Ivan (2010): Pornography, sexual socialization, and satisfaction among young men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (1), S. 168–178. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9387-0.
- Svedin, Carl-Göran; Akerman, Ingrid; Priebe, Gisela (2011): Frequent users of pornography. A population based epidemiological study of Swedish male adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 779–788. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.04.010.
- Swann, Gregory; Minshew, Reese; Newcomb, Michael E.; Mustanski, Brian (2016): Validation of the Sexual Orientation Microaggression Inventory in Two Diverse Samples of LGBTQ Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (6), S. 1289–1298. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0718-2.
- Swenson, Rebecca R.; Houck, Christopher D.; Barker, David; Zeanah, Paula D.; Brown, Larry K. (2012): Prospective analysis of the transition to sexual experience and changes in sexual self-esteem among adolescents attending therapeutic schools. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 77–85. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.06.002.
- Tabatabaie, Alireza (2014): Childhood and adolescent sexuality, Islam, and problematics of sex education. A call for re-examination. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 276–288. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1005836.
- Temple, Jeff R.; Choi, Hye Jeong; Brem, Meagan; Wolford-Clevenger, Caitlin; Stuart, Gregory L.; Peskin, Melissa Fleschler; Elmquist, JoAnna (2016): The Temporal Association Between Traditional and Cyber Dating Abuse Among Adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 340–349. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0380-3.
- Thompson, Ashley E.; Byers, E. Sandra (2017): Heterosexual Young Adults' Interest, Attitudes, and Experiences Related to Mixed-Gender, Multi-Person Sex. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 813–822. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0699-1.

- Thrane, Lisa E.; Chen, Xiaojin (2012): Impact of running away on girls' pregnancy. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (2), S. 443–449. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.07.011.
- Tidefors, Inga; Arvidsson, Hans; Rudolfsson, Lisa (2012): Agreement between ratings from self-rating scales and assessments by treatment staff concerning a group of adolescent males who have sexually offended. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 136–148. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.528845.
- Tomaszewska, Paulina; Krahé, Barbara (2016): Attitudes towards sexual coercion by Polish high school students. Links with risky sexual scripts, pornography use, and religiosity. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 291–307. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1195892.
- Toomey, Russell B.; McGuire, Jenifer K.; Russell, Stephen T. (2012): Heteronormativity, school climates, and perceived safety for gender nonconforming peers. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 187–196. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.03.001.
- Towns, Alison J.; Scott, Hazel (2013): 'I couldn't even dress the way I wanted.' Young women talk of 'ownership' by boyfriends. An opportunity for the prevention of domestic violence? In: *Feminism & Psychology* 23 (4), S. 536–555. DOI: 10.1177/0959353513481955.
- Updegraff, Kimberly A.; McHale, Susan M.; Zeiders, Katharine H.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J.; Perez-Brena, Norma J.; Wheeler, Lorey A.; Rodríguez De Jesús, Sue A. (2014): Mexican-American adolescents' gender role attitude development: the role of adolescents' gender and nativity and parents' gender role attitudes. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (12), S. 2041–2053. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0128-5.
- van Oosten, Johanna M. F. (2016): Sexually Explicit Internet Material and Adolescents' Sexual Uncertainty: The Role of Disposition-Content Congruency. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (4), S. 1011–1022. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0594-1.
- van Oosten, Johanna M. F.; Peter, Jochen; Boot, Inge (2015): Exploring associations between exposure to sexy online self-presentations and adolescents' sexual attitudes and behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 1078–1091. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0194-8.
- van Ouytsel, Joris; Ponnet, Koen; Walrave, Michel (2017): The associations of adolescents' dating violence victimization, well-being and engagement in risk behaviors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 66–71. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.005.
- van Ryzin, Mark J.; Johnson, Amber B.; Leve, Leslie D.; Kim, Hyoun K. (2011): The number of sexual partners and health-risking sexual behavior: prediction from high school entry to high school exit. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 939–949. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9649-5.
- Vandenbosch, Laura; Eggermont, Steven (2015): The role of mass media in adolescents' sexual behaviors: exploring the explanatory value of the three-step self-objectification process. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 729–742. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0292-4.
- Vandenbosch, Laura; Eggermont, Steven (2013): Sexualization of Adolescent Boys. In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 283–306. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13477866.
- Vannier, Sarah A.; O'Sullivan, Lucia F. (2012): Who gives and who gets: why, when, and with whom young people engage in oral sex. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 572–582. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9745-z.
- Vares, Tiina; Jackson, Sue (2015): Preteen girls, magazines, and the negotiation of young sexual femininity. In: *Gender and Education* 27 (6), S. 700–713. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1078453.
- Vasilenko, Sara A.; Ram, Nilam; Lefkowitz, Eva S. (2011): Body image and first sexual intercourse in late adolescence. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 327–335. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.04.005.
- Velezmore, Rodrigo; Negy, Charles; Livia, Jose (2012): Online sexual activity: cross-national comparison between United States and Peruvian college students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1015–1025. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9862-x.
- Venable, Victoria M.; Guada, Joseph (2014): Culturally competent practice with African American juvenile sex offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (3), S. 229–246. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.888122.
- Verhoef, Melissa; van den Eijnden, Regina J. J. M.; Koning, Ina M.; Vollebergh, Wilma A. M. (2014): Age at menarche and adolescent alcohol use. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1333–1345. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0075-6.

- Vézina, Johanne; Hébert, Martine; Poulin, François; Lavoie, Francine; Vitaro, Frank; Tremblay, Richard E. (2011): Risky lifestyle as a mediator of the relationship between deviant peer affiliation and dating violence victimization among adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 814–824. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9602-x.
- Vries, Hein de; Eggers, Sander Matthijs; Jinabhai, Champak; Meyer-Weitz, Anna; Sathiparsad, Reshma; Taylor, Myra (2014): Adolescents' beliefs about forced sex in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (6), S. 1087–1095. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0280-8.
- Vrouenraets, Lieke Josephina Jeanne Johanna; Fredriks, A. Miranda; Hannema, Sabine E.; Cohen-Kettenis, Peggy T.; Vries, Martine C. de (2016): Perceptions of Sex, Gender, and Puberty Suppression: A Qualitative Analysis of Transgender Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (7), S. 1697–1703. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0764-9.
- Wargo Aikins, Julie; Simon, Valerie A.; Prinstein, Mitchell J. (2010): Romantic partner selection and socialization of young adolescents' substance use and behavior problems. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (6), S. 813–826. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.07.007.
- Wells, Elizabeth A.; Asakura, Kenta; Hoppe, Marilyn J.; Balsam, Kimberly F.; Morrison, Diane M.; Beadnell, Blair (2012): Social Services for Sexual Minority Youth: Preferences for What, Where, and How Services are Delivered. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 36 (2), S. 312–320. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.11.011.
- Wetherill, Reagan R.; Neal, Dan J.; Fromme, Kim (2010): Parents, peers, and sexual values influence sexual behavior during the transition to college. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 682–694. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9476-8.
- Wheeler, Lorey A.; Killoren, Sarah E.; Whiteman, Shawn D.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; McHale, Susan M.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J. (2016): Romantic Relationship Experiences from Late Adolescence to Young Adulthood: The Role of Older Siblings in Mexican-Origin Families. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 900–915. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0392-z.
- White, Jacquelyn; Buehler, Cheryl; Weymouth, Bridget B. (2014): Childhood attention deficit hyperactive disorder (ADHD) symptoms and adolescent female sexual victimisation. Mediating and moderating effects of risky behaviours. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 23–39. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.782429.
- Wienholz, Sabine; Seidel, Anja; Michel, Marion; Haeussler-Sczepan, Monika; Riedel-Heller, Steffi Gerlinde (2016): Sexual Experiences of Adolescents With and Without Disabilities. Results from a Cross-Sectional Study. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 171–182. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9433-0.
- Wilkinson, Verity J.; Theodore, Kate; Raczk, Roman (2015): 'As Normal as Possible'. Sexual Identity Development in People with Intellectual Disabilities Transitioning to Adulthood. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 33 (1), S. 93–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9356-6.
- Williams, Lela Rankin; Hickie, Kristine E. (2011): "He cheated on me, I cheated on him back". Mexican American and White adolescents' perceptions of cheating in romantic relationships. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (5), S. 1005–1016. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.11.007.
- Wilson, Bianca; Kastanis, Angeliki A. (2015): Sexual and gender minority disproportionality and disparities in child welfare. A population-based study. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 58, S. 11–17. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.08.016.
- Winskell, Kate; Beres, Laura K.; Hill, Elizabeth; Mbakwem, Benjamin Chigozie; Obyerodhyambo, Oby (2011): Making sense of abstinence. Social representations in young Africans' HIV-related narratives from six countries. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 945–959. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.591431.
- Wolff, Jennifer M.; Rospenda, Kathleen M.; Colaneri, Anthony S. (2017): Sexual Harassment, Psychological Distress, and Problematic Drinking Behavior Among College Students: An Examination of Reciprocal Causal Relations. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (3), S. 362–373. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1143439.
- Wondie, Yemataw; Zemene, Workie; Reschke, Konrad; Schroder, Harry (2011): Early marriage, rape, child prostitution, and related factors determining the psychosocial effects severity of child sexual abuse in Ethiopia. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (3), S. 305–321. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.573458.
- Wong, Carolyn F.; Kipke, Michele D.; Weiss, George; McDavitt, Bryce (2010): The impact of recent stressful experiences on HIV-risk related behaviors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (3), S. 463–475. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.06.004.

- Wright, Michelle F. (2015): Cyber aggression within adolescents' romantic relationships: linkages to parental and partner attachment. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 37–47. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0147-2.
- Ybarra, Michele L.; Espelage, Dorothy L.; Langhinrichsen-Rohling, Jennifer; Korchmaros, Josephine D.; Boyd, Danah (2016): Lifetime Prevalence Rates and Overlap of Physical, Psychological, and Sexual Dating Abuse Perpetration and Victimization in a National Sample of Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1083–1099. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0748-9.
- Ybarra, Michele L.; Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Palmer, Neal A.; Reisner, Sari L. (2015): Online social support as a buffer against online and offline peer and sexual victimization among U.S. LGBT and non-LGBT youth. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 39, S. 123–136.
- Yoder, Jamie; Ruch, Donna (2015): A qualitative investigation of treatment components for families of youth who have sexually offended. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (2), S. 192–205. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1107141.
- Yoder, Jamie R.; Hansen, Jesse; Ruch, Donna; Hodge, Ashleigh (2016): Effects of School-Based Risk and Protective Factors on Treatment Success Among Youth Adjudicated of a Sexual Crime. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 310–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1137668.
- Zimmer-Gembeck, Melanie J.; Ducat, Wendy (2010): Positive and negative romantic relationship quality: age, familiarity, attachment and well-being as correlates of couple agreement and projection. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (6), S. 879–890. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.07.008.
- Zimmer-Gembeck, Melanie J.; Ducat, Wendy H.; Boislard-Pepin, Marie-Aude (2011): A prospective study of young females' sexual subjectivity: associations with age, sexual behavior, and dating. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 927–938. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9751-3.
- Zweig, Janine M.; Dank, Meredith; Yahner, Jennifer; Lachman, Pamela (2013): The rate of cyber dating abuse among teens and how it relates to other forms of teen dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1063–1077. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9922-8.

5.3. Eltern und Familie

- Bauwens, Joke; Paus-Hasebrink, Ingrid; Ponte, Cristina; Dürager, Andrea (2012): Understanding digital inequality. The interplay between parental socialisation and children's development. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 257–272.
- Clark, Andrew B. (2014): Parenting Through the Digital Revolution. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 247–261.
- Desjardins, Michel (2012): The Sexualized Body of the Child. Parents and the Politics of "Voluntary" Sterilization of People Labeled Intellectually Disabled. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 69–88.
- Espiritu, Yen Le (2012): U.S. Colonialism, Migration, and Sexualities. The Filipino American Case. In: Laura M. Carpenter und John D. DeLamater (Hg.): *Sex for life. From virginity to Viagra, how sexuality changes throughout our lives*. New York: New York University Press (Intersections), S. 163–179.
- Garmendia, Maialen; Garitaonandia, Carmelo; Martinez, Gemma; Casado, Miguel Ángel (2012): The effectiveness of parental mediation. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 231–244.
- Whitlock, Reta Ugena (2014): LGBT Families and Southern Schools. Thinking About People, Place, and Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 75–89.
- Best, Joel; Bogle, Kathleen A. (2014): *Kids gone wild. From rainbow parties to sexting, understanding the hype over teen sex*. New York [u.a.]: New York Univ. Press.
- Elliott, Sinikka (2012): *Not my kid. What parents believe about the sex lives of their teenagers*. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press.

- Garcia, Lorena (2012): Respect yourself, protect yourself. Latina girls and sexual identity. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press (Intersections / [New York University Press]).
- Allbaugh, Lucy Jane; O'Dougherty Wright, Margaret; Atkins Seltmann, Larissa (2014): An exploratory study of domains of parenting concern among mothers who are childhood sexual abuse survivors. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (8), S. 885–899. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.960636.
- Ávila, Marisa; Cabral, Joana; Matos, Paula Mena (2012): Identity in university students. The role of parental and romantic attachment. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 133–142. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.05.002.
- Aylaz, Rukuye; Yilmaz, Ulviye; Polat, Sevinç (2012): Effect of Difficulties Experienced by Parents of Autistic Children on Their Sexual Life. A Qualitative Study. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (4), S. 395–406. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9251-3.
- Babatsikos, Georgia (2010): Parents' knowledge, attitudes and practices about preventing child sexual abuse. A literature review. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (2), S. 107–129. DOI: 10.1002/car.1102.
- Baril, Karine; Tourigny, Marc; Paille, Pierre; Pauze, Robert (2016): Characteristics of Sexually Abused Children and Their Nonoffending Mothers Followed by Child Welfare Services. The Role of a Maternal History of Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 504–523. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1176096.
- Bauermeister, José A. (2014): How statewide LGB policies go from “under our skin” to “into our hearts”: fatherhood aspirations and psychological well-being among emerging adult sexual minority men. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1295–1305. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0059-6.
- Boislard P., Marie-Aude; Poulin, Francois (2011): Individual, familial, friends-related and contextual predictors of early sexual intercourse. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 289–300. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.05.002.
- Boisvert, Stéphanie; Poulin, François (2016): Romantic Relationship Patterns from Adolescence to Emerging Adulthood: Associations with Family and Peer Experiences in Early Adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 945–958. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0435-0.
- Bragg, Sara; Buckingham, David; Russell, Rachel; Willett, Rebekah (2011): Too much, too soon? Children, ‘sexualization’ and consumer culture. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 279–292. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590085.
- Campero, Lourdes; Walker, Dilys; Atienzo, Erika E.; Gutierrez, Juan Pablo (2011): A quasi-experimental evaluation of parents as sexual health educators resulting in delayed sexual initiation and increased access to condoms. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 215–223. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.05.010.
- Cavazos-Rehg, Patricia A.; Spitznagel, Edward L.; Bucholz, Kathleen K.; Nurnberger, John; Edenberg, Howard J.; Kramer, John R. et al. (2010): Predictors of sexual debut at age 16 or younger. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 664–673. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9397-y.
- Comartin, Erin B.; Kernsmith, Poco D.; Miles, Bart W. (2010): Family experiences of young adult sex offender registration. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 204–225. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003627207.
- Corona, Laura L.; Fox, Stephanie A.; Christodulu, Kristin V.; Worlock, Jane Ann (2016): Providing Education on Sexuality and Relationships to Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder and Their Parents. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 199–214. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-015-9424-6.
- Crandall, AliceAnn; Magnusson, Brianna M.; Novilla, M. Lelinneth B.; Novilla, Lynneth Kirsten B.; Dyer, W. Justin (2017): Family Financial Stress and Adolescent Sexual Risk-Taking: The Role of Self-Regulation. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 45–62. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0543-x.
- Crichton, Joanna; Ibisomi, Latifat; Gyimah, Stephen Obeng (2012): Mother-daughter communication about sexual maturation, abstinence and unintended pregnancy. Experiences from an informal settlement in Nairobi, Kenya. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 21–30. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.06.008.
- Cyr, Mireille; McDuff, Pierre; Hebert, Martine (2013): Support and profiles of nonoffending mothers of sexually abused children. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (2), S. 209–230. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.737444.
- Dickenson, Janna A.; Huebner, David M. (2016): The Relationship Between Sexual Activity and Depressive Symptoms in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth: Effects of Gender and Family Support. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (3), S. 671–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0571-8.

- Farr, Rachel H.; Crain, Emily E.; Oakley, M. K.; Cashen, Krystal K.; Garber, Karin J. (2016): Microaggressions, Feelings of Difference, and Resilience Among Adopted Children with Sexual Minority Parents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (1), S. 85–104. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0353-6.
- Foshee, Vangie A.; Benefield, Thad; Dixon, Kimberly S.; Chang, Ling-Yin; Senkomago, Virginia; Ennett, Susan T. et al. (2015): The effects of moms and teens for safe dates: a dating abuse prevention program for adolescents exposed to domestic violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 995–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0272-6.
- Gartrell, Nanette K.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Goldberg, Naomi G. (2011): Adolescents of the U.S. National Longitudinal Lesbian Family Study: sexual orientation, sexual behavior, and sexual risk exposure. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (6), S. 1199–1209. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9692-2.
- Gibson, Kerry; Morgan, Mandy; Woolley, Cheryl; Powis, Tracey (2011): Growing up at centrepiece. Retrospective accounts of childhood spent at an intentional community. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 413–434. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.591364.
- Gillmore, Mary Rogers; Chen, Angela Chia-Chen; Haas, Steven A.; Kopak, Albert M.; Robillard, Alyssa G. (2011): Do family and parenting factors in adolescence influence condom use in early adulthood in a multiethnic sample of young adults? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (11), S. 1503–1518. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9631-0.
- Goodrum, Nada M.; Armistead, Lisa P.; Tully, Erin C.; Cook, Sarah L.; Skinner, Donald (2017): Parenting and youth sexual risk in context. The role of community factors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 57, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.013.
- Graaf, Hanneke de; van de Schoot, Rens; Woertman, Liesbeth; Hawk, Skyler T.; Meeus, Wim (2012): Family cohesion and romantic and sexual initiation: a three wave longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 583–592. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9708-9.
- Graaf, Hanneke de; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine; Woertman, Liesbeth; Keijsers, Loes; Meijer, Suzanne; Meeus, Wim (2010): Parental support and knowledge and adolescents' sexual health: testing two mediational models in a national Dutch sample. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (2), S. 189–198. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-008-9387-3.
- Hatchard, Christine J.; Goodwin, Jamie L.; Siddall, Eryn; Muniz, Lauren (2017): Perceptions of Abusive Parenting Behaviors. A Preliminary Exploration Into the Underrecognition of Mother-Daughter Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (4), S. 428–441. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1300971.
- Hyde, Abbey; Carney, Marie; Drennan, Jonathan; Butler, Michelle; Lohan, Maria; Howlett, Etaine (2010): The silent treatment. Parents' narratives of sexuality education with young people. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 359–371. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903514455.
- Jaffe, Anna E.; Cranston, Christopher C.; Shadlow, Joanna O. (2012): Parenting in females exposed to intimate partner violence and childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 684–700. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.726698.
- Jerman, Petra; Constantine, Norman A. (2010): Demographic and psychological predictors of parent-adolescent communication about sex: a representative statewide analysis. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1164–1174. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9546-1.
- Johnson, Matthew D. (2013): Parent-child relationship quality directly and indirectly influences hooking up behavior reported in young adulthood through alcohol use in adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1463–1472. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0098-9.
- Kaltiala-Heino, Riittakerttu; Fröjd, Sari; Marttunen, Mauri (2016): Sexual harassment victimization in adolescence. Associations with family background. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 56, S. 11–19.
- Kennett, Deborah J.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Schultz, Kristen E. (2011): Sexual resourcefulness and the impact of family, sex education, media and peers. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615624.
- Kenny, Maureen C. (2010): Child sexual abuse education with ethnically diverse families. A preliminary analysis. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 32 (7), S. 981–989. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2010.03.025.
- Killoren, Sarah E.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; Christopher, F. Scott (2011): Family and cultural correlates of Mexican-origin youths' sexual intentions. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (6), S. 707–718. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9587-5.

- Kisanga, Felix; Nystrom, Lennarth; Hogan, Nora; Emmelin, Maria (2011): Child sexual abuse. Community concerns in urban Tanzania. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (2), S. 196–217. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.555356.
- Kostolitz, Alessandra C.; Hyman, Scott M.; Gold, Steven N. (2014): How ineffective family environments can compound maldevelopment of critical thinking skills in childhood abuse survivors. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (6), S. 690–707. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.931318.
- Leventhal, John M.; Murphy, Janet L.; Asnes, Andrea G. (2010): Evaluations of child sexual abuse. Recognition of overt and latent family concerns. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34 (5), S. 289–295.
- Makin-Byrd, Kerry; Bierman, Karen L. (2013): Individual and family predictors of the perpetration of dating violence and victimization in late adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 536–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9810-7.
- Martin, Karin A. (2014): Making sense of children's sexual behavior in child care. An analysis of adult responses in special investigation reports. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (10), S. 1636–1646.
- Martin, Karin A.; Verduzco Baker, Lynn; Torres, Jennifer; Luke, Katherine (2011): Privates, pee-pees, and coochies. Gender and genital labeling for/with young children. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (3), S. 420–430. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510384832.
- Mason, Sacha (2010): Braving it out! An illuminative evaluation of the provision of sex and relationship education in two primary schools in England. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 157–169. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666366.
- Moilanen, Kristin L. (2016): Why Do Parents Grant or Deny Consent for Adolescent Participation in Sexuality Research? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 1020–1036. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0445-y.
- Murry, Velma McBride; Berkel, Cady; Chen, Yi-Fu; Brody, Gene H.; Gibbons, Frederick X.; Gerrard, Meg (2011): Intervention induced changes on parenting practices, youth self-pride and sexual norms to reduce HIV-related behaviors among rural African American youths. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (9), S. 1147–1163. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9642-x.
- Pasterski, Vickie; Mastroyannopoulou, Kiki; Wright, Deborah; Zucker, Kenneth J.; Hughes, Teuan A. (2014): Predictors of posttraumatic stress in parents of children diagnosed with a disorder of sex development. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 369–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0196-8.
- Pearson, Jennifer; Wilkinson, Lindsey (2013): Family relationships and adolescent well-being: are families equally protective for same-sex attracted youth? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 376–393. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9865-5.
- Rakow, Aaron; Smith, Daniel; Begle, Angela M.; Ayer, Lynsay (2011): The association of maternal depressive symptoms with child externalizing problems. The role of maternal support following child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 467–480. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.588189.
- Sanberk, Ismail; Emen, Meltem; Kabakci, Duygu (2017): An Investigation of Socially Advantaged and Disadvantaged Turkish Mothers' Views About Training on Preventing Children From Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 288–307. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1292338.
- Schwarz, Beate; Stutz, Melanie; Ledermann, Thomas (2012): Perceived interparental conflict and early adolescents' friendships: the role of attachment security and emotion regulation. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (9), S. 1240–1252. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9769-4.
- Shulman, Shmuel; Zlotnik, Aynat; Shachar-Shapira, Lital; Connolly, Jennifer; Bohr, Yvonne (2012): Adolescent daughters' romantic competence: the role of divorce, quality of parenting, and maternal romantic history. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 593–606. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9748-9.
- Stewart, Catherine Carolyn (2012): Beyond the call. Mothers of children with developmental disabilities responding to sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 701–727. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.722182.
- Updegraff, Kimberly A.; McHale, Susan M.; Zeiders, Katharine H.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J.; Perez-Brena, Norma J.; Wheeler, Lorey A.; Rodríguez De Jesús, Sue A. (2014): Mexican-American adolescents' gender role attitude development: the role of adolescents' gender and nativity and parents' gender role attitudes. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (12), S. 2041–2053. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0128-5.
- Wheeler, Lorey A.; Killoren, Sarah E.; Whiteman, Shawn D.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; McHale, Susan M.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J. (2016): Romantic Relationship Experiences from Late Adolescence to Young Adulthood: The Role

of Older Siblings in Mexican-Origin Families. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 900–915. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0392-z.

Wurtele, Sandy K.; Kenny, Maureen C. (2010): Partnering with parents to prevent childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (2), S. 130–152. DOI: 10.1002/car.1112.

Yoder, Jamie; Ruch, Donna (2015): A qualitative investigation of treatment components for families of youth who have sexually offended. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (2), S. 192–205. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1107141.

Zinzow, Heidi; Seth, Puja; Jackson, Joan; Niehaus, Ashley; Fitzgerald, Monica (2010): Abuse and parental characteristics, attributions of blame, and psychological adjustment in adult survivors of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (1), S. 79–98. DOI: 10.1080/10538710903485989.

6. Gewalt

6.1. Täter*in

6.1.1. Peer

Chapman, Amy; Buchanan, Rachel (2014): FYI... Virtual space has a context. Towards an alternative frame for understanding cyberbullying. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 56–71.

Cowie, Helen (2013): The immediate and long-term effects of bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 10–18.

Duncan, Neil (2013): Disability, sexuality and bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 105–119.

Jennifer, Dawn (2013): Girls and indirect aggression. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 45–59.

McCormack, Mark (2013): Mapping the boundaries of homophobic language in bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 91–104.

Ollis, Debbie (2013): Planning and delivering interventions to promote gender and sexuality. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 145–161.

Poteat, V. Paul; Mereish, Ethan H.; DiGiovanni, Craig D.; Scheer, Jillian R. (2013): Homophobic bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 75–90.

Rivers, Ian (2013): Cyberbullying and cyberaggression. Sexualised and gendered experiences explored. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 19–44.

Rivers, Ian; Duncan, Neil (2013): Discourses of sexuality and gender considered. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 162–168.

Robinson, Kerry H. (2014): Sexual harassment in schools. Issues of identity and power - Negotiating the complexities, contexts and contradictions of this everyday practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 71–94.

Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): "The kid most likely". Naming, brutality and silence within and beyond school settings. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 21–38.

Williams, Sian (2013): Sexual bullying in one local authority. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 60–74.

Shariff, Shaheen (2015): *Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids*. New York: Cambridge University Press.

- Rivers, Ian (Hg.) (2013): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education).
- Saltmarsh, Sue (Hg.) (2014): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Abajobir, Amanuel Alemu; Kisely, Steve; Williams, Gail Marilyn; Clavarino, Alexandra Marie; Najman, Jakob Moses (2017): Substantiated Childhood Maltreatment and Intimate Partner Violence Victimization in Young Adulthood: A Birth Cohort Study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 165–179. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0558-3.
- Allard, Troy; Rayment-McHugh, Sue; Adams, Dimity; Smallbone, Stephen; McKillop, Nadine (2015): Responding to youth sexual offending. A field-based practice model that “closes the gap” on sexual recidivism among Indigenous and non-Indigenous males. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (1), S. 82–94. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.1003107.
- Allardyce, Stuart; Yates, Peter Michael (2013): Assessing Risk of Victim Crossover with Children and Young People who display Harmful Sexual Behaviours. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (4), S. 255–267. DOI: 10.1002/car.2277.
- Alleyne, Binta; Coleman-Cowger, Victoria H.; Crown, Laurel; Gibbons, Maya A.; Vines, Linda Nicole (2011): The effects of dating violence, substance use and risky sexual behavior among a diverse sample of Illinois youth. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 11–18. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.03.006.
- Almond, Tracy Jane (2014): Working with children and young people with harmful sexual behaviours. Exploring impact on practitioners and sources of support. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 333–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836576.
- Asscher, Jessica J.; Put, Claudia E. van der; Stams, Geert Jan (2012): Differences between juvenile offenders with and without intellectual disability in offense type and risk factors. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 33 (6), S. 1905–1913. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2012.05.022.
- Beerthuisen, Marinus G. C. J.; Brugman, Daniel (2012): Sexually abusive youths' moral reasoning on sex. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 125–135. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.519126.
- Beier, Klaus M.; Oezdemir, Umut C.; Schlinzig, Eliza; Groll, Anna; Hupp, Elena; Hellenschmidt, Tobias (2016): “Just dreaming of them”. The Berlin Project for Primary Prevention of Child Sexual Abuse by Juveniles (PPJ). In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 52, S. 1–10.
- Bengtsson, T. T. (2016): Performing Hypermasculinity. Experiences with Confined Young Offenders. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (4), S. 410–428. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15595083.
- Biswas, Bipasha; Vaughn, Michael G. (2011): Really troubled girls. Gender differences in risky sexual behavior and its correlates in a sample of juvenile offenders. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 33 (11), S. 2386–2391. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2011.08.010.
- Bower, Andrew R.; Nishina, Adrienne; Witkow, Melissa R.; Bellmore, Amy (2015): Nice Guys and Gals Finish Last? Not in Early Adolescence When Empathic, Accepted, and Popular Peers are Desirable. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (12), S. 2275–2288. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0346-5.
- Bowker, Julie C.; Etkin, Rebecca G. (2014): Does humor explain why relationally aggressive adolescents are popular? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1322–1332. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0031-5.
- Brooks-Russell, Ashley; Foshee, Vangie A.; Ennett, Susan T. (2013): Predictors of latent trajectory classes of physical dating violence victimization. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 566–580. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9876-2.
- Caiozzo, Christina N.; Houston, Jessica; Grych, John (2016): Predicting aggression in late adolescent romantic relationships. A short-term longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 53, S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.10.012.
- Campregher, Julia; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2016): Attitudes Toward Juvenile Sex Offender Legislation: The Influence of Case-Specific Information. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 466–482. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153558.
- Casey, Erin A.; Beadnell, Blair (2010): The structure of male adolescent peer networks and risk for intimate partner violence perpetration: findings from a national sample. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 620–633. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9423-y.

- Chang, Ling-Yin; Foshee, Vangie A.; Reyes, Heath Luz McNaughton; Ennett, Susan T.; Halpern, Carolyn T. (2015): Direct and indirect effects of neighborhood characteristics on the perpetration of dating violence across adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 727–744. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0190-z.
- Collibee, Charlene; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Chronic and Acute Relational Risk Factors for Dating Aggression in Adolescence and Young Adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (4), S. 763–776. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0427-0.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2013): Homophobic name-calling among secondary school students and its implications for mental health. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 363–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9823-2.
- Comartin, Erin B.; Kernsmith, Poco D.; Miles, Bart W. (2010): Family experiences of young adult sex offender registration. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 204–225. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003627207.
- Dank, Meredith; Lachman, Pamela; Zweig, Janine M.; Yahner, Jennifer (2014): Dating violence experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (5), S. 846–857. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9975-8.
- Edwards, Rachel; Whittaker, Mette Kristensen; Beckett, Richard; Bishopp, Daz; Bates, Andrew (2012): Adolescents who have sexually harmed. An evaluation of a specialist treatment programme. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 91–111. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.635317.
- Ellis, Wendy E.; Chung-Hall, Janet; Dumas, Tara M. (2013): The role of peer group aggression in predicting adolescent dating violence and relationship quality. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 487–499. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9797-0.
- Fernet, Mylene; Hébert, Martine; Paradis, Alison (2016): Conflict resolution patterns and violence perpetration in adolescent couples. A gender-sensitive mixed-methods approach. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 51–59. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.02.004.
- Foshee, Vangie A.; Benefield, Thad; Dixon, Kimberly S.; Chang, Ling-Yin; Senkomago, Virginia; Ennett, Susan T. et al. (2015): The effects of moms and teens for safe dates: a dating abuse prevention program for adolescents exposed to domestic violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 995–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0272-6.
- Geary, Jan; Lambie, Ian; Seymour, Fred (2011): Consumer perspectives of New Zealand community treatment programmes for sexually abusive youth. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 181–195. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003778693.
- Griffin, Helen Louise; Vettor, Shannon (2012): Predicting sexual re-offending in a UK sample of adolescents with intellectual disabilities. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 64–80. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.617013.
- Grossi, Laura M.; Lee, Austin F.; Schuler, Ann; Ryan, Julie L.; Prentky, Robert A. (2016): Sexualized behaviors in cohorts of children in the child welfare system. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 52, S. 49–61. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.12.014.
- Hackett, Simon; Carpenter, John; Patsios, Demi; Szilassy, Eszter (2013): Interprofessional and interagency training for working with young people with harmful sexual behaviours. An evaluation of outcomes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 329–344. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.753122.
- Hackett, Simon; Phillips, Josie; Masson, Helen; Balfe, Myles (2013): Individual, Family and Abuse Characteristics of 700 British Child and Adolescent Sexual Abusers. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (4), S. 232–245. DOI: 10.1002/car.2246.
- Hafford-Letchfield, Trish; Cocker, Christine; Ryan, Peter; Melonowska, Justyna (2017): Rights through Alliances. Findings from a European Project Tackling Homophobic and Transphobic Bullying in Schools through the Engagement of Families and Young People. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2338–2356. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw104.
- Hawkes, Colin (2011): Description of a UK study of onset of sexually harmful behaviour before the age of ten years in boys referred to a specialist assessment and treatment service. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 82–101. DOI: 10.1002/car.1133.
- Höing, Mechtild; Jonker, Marianne; Berlo, Willy van (2010): Juvenile sex offenders in a Dutch mandatory educational programme. Subtypes and characteristics. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (3), S. 332–346. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903350991.

- Ingevaldson, Sara; Goulding, Anneli; Tidefors, Inga (2016): Experiences of intimate relationships in young men who sexually offended during adolescence. Interviews 10 years later. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 410–422. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1177125.
- Jennings, Wesley G.; Richards, Tara N.; Tomsich, Elizabeth; Gover, Angela R. (2015): Investigating the Role of Child Sexual Abuse in Intimate Partner Violence Victimization and Perpetration in Young Adulthood From a Propensity Score Matching Approach. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 659–681. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1057665.
- Jones, Sara; Joyal, Christian C.; Cisler, Josh M.; Bai, Shasha (2017): Exploring Emotion Regulation in Juveniles Who Have Sexually Offended. An fMRI Study. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 40–57. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1259280.
- Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2010): Sexually coercive behavior in male youth: population survey of general and specific risk factors. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1161–1169. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9572-9.
- Lambie, Ian; Price, Mnthali (2015): Transitioning youth with sexually harmful behaviour back into the community. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 244–265. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.873829.
- Low, Sabina; Polanin, Joshua R.; Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): The role of social networks in physical and relational aggression among young adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1078–1089. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9933-5.
- Makin-Byrd, Kerry; Bierman, Karen L. (2013): Individual and family predictors of the perpetration of dating violence and victimization in late adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 536–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9810-7.
- Martinello, Emily (2015): Reviewing Risks Factors of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities as Perpetrators of Sexually Abusive Behaviors. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 33 (2), S. 269–278. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9365-5.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa (2015): Prevalence of dating violence among sexual minority youth: variation across gender, sexual minority identity and gender of sexual partners. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 211–224. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0089-0.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa; Crosnoe, Robert (2012): Sexual minority status, peer harassment, and adolescent depression. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 1001–1011. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.02.006.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa; Fromme, Kim (2016): Trajectories of dating violence. Differences by sexual minority status and gender. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 28–37. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.02.008.
- Masson, H.; Hackett, Simon; Phillips, J.; Balfe, M. (2014): Looking Back on the Long-Term Fostering and Adoption of Children with Harmful Sexual Behaviours. Carers' Reflections on Their Experiences. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 44 (8), S. 2200–2217. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bct073.
- McCartan, Fiona Mairead; Law, Heather; Murphy, Maeve; Bailey, Susan (2011): Child and adolescent females who present with sexually abusive behaviours. A 10-year UK prevalence study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 4–14. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.488302.
- Miller, S. A. (2016): "How You Bully a Girl". Sexual Drama and the Negotiation of Gendered Sexuality in High School. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (5), S. 721–744. DOI: 10.1177/0891243216664723.
- Miller, Shari; Williams, Jason; Cutbush, Stacey; Gibbs, Deborah; Clinton-Sherrod, Monique; Jones, Sarah (2013): Dating violence, bullying, and sexual harassment: longitudinal profiles and transitions over time. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 607–618. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9914-8.
- Nishina, Adrienne (2012): Microcontextual characteristics of peer victimization experiences and adolescents' daily well-being. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 191–201. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9669-z.
- Novak, Jamie; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Partner Violence During Adolescence and Young Adulthood: Individual and Relationship Level Risk Factors. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (9), S. 1849–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0484-4.
- Ojanen, Timo Tapani; Boonmongkon, Pimpawun; Samakkeekarom, Ronnapoom; Samoh, Nattharat; Cholratana, Mudjalin; Guadamuz, Thomas Ebanan (2015): Connections between online harassment and offline violence among youth in Central Thailand. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 44, S. 159–169.

- Oliver, Brian E.; Holmes, Laura (2015): Female Juvenile Sexual Offenders. Understanding Who They Are and Possible Steps That May Prevent Some Girls From Offending. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 698–715. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1058875.
- Orpinas, Pamela; Hsieh, Hsien-Lin; Song, Xiao; Holland, Kristin; Nahapetyan, Lusine (2013): Trajectories of physical dating violence from middle to high school: association with relationship quality and acceptability of aggression. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 551–565. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9881-5.
- Piccigallo, Jaqueline R.; Lilley, Terry G.; Miller, Susan L. (2012): "It's Cool to Care about Sexual Violence". Men's Experiences with Sexual Assault Prevention. In: *Men and Masculinities* 15 (5), S. 507–525. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X12458590.
- Pritchard, Duncan; Graham, Nicola; Penney, Heather; Owen, Gwynne; Peters, Sandra; Mace, F. Charles (2016): Multi-component behavioural intervention reduces harmful sexual behaviour in a 17-year-old male with autism spectrum disorder. A case study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 368–378. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1130269.
- Pullman, Lesleigh E.; Seto, Michael C. (2012): Assessment and treatment of adolescent sexual offenders. Implications of recent research on generalist versus specialist explanations. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (3), S. 203–209.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2012): Popular culture as emotional provocation. The material enactment of queer pedagogies in a high school classroom. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 511–522. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627728.
- Rasmussen, Lucinda A. (2013): Young people who sexually abuse. A historical perspective and future directions. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (1), S. 119–141. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.744646.
- Rasmussen, Lucinda A.; Lev-Wiesel, Rachel; Eisikovits, Zvi (2013): Current perspectives on children and youth who sexually abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (1), S. 1–8. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.744644.
- Reyes, H. Luz McNaughton; Foshee, Vangie A.; Niolon, Phyllis Holditch; Reidy, Dennis E.; Hall, Jeffrey E. (2016): Gender Role Attitudes and Male Adolescent Dating Violence Perpetration: Normative Beliefs as Moderators. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 350–360. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0278-0.
- Sabina, Chiara; Cuevas, Carlos A.; Cotignola-Pickens, Heather M. (2016): Longitudinal dating violence victimization among Latino teens: Rates, risk factors, and cultural influences. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 47, S. 5–15. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.11.003.
- Schnurr, Melissa P.; Lohman, Brenda J. (2013): The impact of collective efficacy on risks for adolescents' perpetration of dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 518–535. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9909-5.
- Slotboom, Anne-Marie; Hendriks, Jan; Verbruggen, Janna (2011): Contrasting adolescent female and male sexual aggression. A self-report study on prevalence and predictors of sexual aggression. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 15–33. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.544413.
- Smith, Connie; Allardyce, Stuart; Hackett, Simon; Bradbury-Jones, Caroline; Lazenbatt, Anne; Taylor, Julie (2014): Practice and policy in the UK with children and young people who display harmful sexual behaviours. An analysis and critical review. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 267–280. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927010.
- Stevens, Peter; Hutchin, Katie; French, Lesley; Craissati, Jackie (2013): Developmental and offence-related characteristics of different types of adolescent sex offender. A community sample. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 138–157. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.645889.
- Stroebel, Sandra S.; O'Keefe, Stephen L.; Griffiee, Karen; Kuo, Shih-Ya; Beard, Keith W.; Kommor, Martin J. (2013): Sister-sister incest. Data from an anonymous computerized survey. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (6), S. 695–719. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.811140.
- Sullivan, Terri N.; Garthe, Rachel C.; Goncy, Elizabeth A.; Carlson, Megan M.; Behrhorst, Kathryn L. (2017): Longitudinal Relations between Beliefs Supporting Aggression, Anger Regulation, and Dating Aggression among Early Adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 982–994. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0569-0.
- Temple, Jeff R.; Choi, Hye Jeong; Brem, Meagan; Wolford-Clevenger, Caitlin; Stuart, Gregory L.; Peskin, Melissa Fleschler; Elmquist, JoAnna (2016): The Temporal Association Between Traditional and Cyber Dating Abuse Among Adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 340–349. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0380-3.

Tidefors, Inga; Arvidsson, Hans; Rudolfsson, Lisa (2012): Agreement between ratings from self-rating scales and assessments by treatment staff concerning a group of adolescent males who have sexually offended. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 136–148. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.528845.

van Ouysel, Joris; Ponnet, Koen; Walrave, Michel (2017): The associations of adolescents' dating violence victimization, well-being and engagement in risk behaviors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 66–71. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.005.

Venable, Victoria M.; Guada, Joseph (2014): Culturally competent practice with African American juvenile sex offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (3), S. 229–246. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.888122.

Vézina, Johanne; Hébert, Martine; Poulin, François; Lavoie, Francine; Vitaro, Frank; Tremblay, Richard E. (2011): Risky lifestyle as a mediator of the relationship between deviant peer affiliation and dating violence victimization among adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 814–824. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9602-x.

Vugt, Eveline van; Asscher, Jessica J.; Stams, Geert Jan; Hendriks, Jan; Bijleveld, Catrien; Laan, Peter van der (2011): Moral judgment of young sex offenders with and without intellectual disabilities. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 32 (6), S. 2841–2846. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2011.05.022.

Worling, James (2012): The assessment and treatment of deviant sexual arousal with adolescents who have offended sexually. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 36–63. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.630152.

Wright, Michelle F. (2015): Cyber aggression within adolescents' romantic relationships: linkages to parental and partner attachment. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 37–47. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0147-2.

Yates, Peter; Allardyce, Stuart; MacQueen, Sarah (2012): Children who display harmful sexual behaviour. Assessing the risks of boys abusing at home, in the community or across both settings. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 23–35. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.634527.

Ybarra, Michele L.; Espelage, Dorothy L.; Langhinrichsen-Rohling, Jennifer; Korchmaros, Josephine D.; Boyd, Danah (2016): Lifetime Prevalence Rates and Overlap of Physical, Psychological, and Sexual Dating Abuse Perpetration and Victimization in a National Sample of Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1083–1099. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0748-9.

Yoder, Jamie; Ruch, Donna (2015): A qualitative investigation of treatment components for families of youth who have sexually offended. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (2), S. 192–205. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1107141.

Yoder, Jamie R.; Hansen, Jesse; Ruch, Donna; Hodge, Ashleigh (2016): Effects of School-Based Risk and Protective Factors on Treatment Success Among Youth Adjudicated of a Sexual Crime. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 310–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1137668.

Zweig, Janine M.; Dank, Meredith; Yahner, Jennifer; Lachman, Pamela (2013): The rate of cyber dating abuse among teens and how it relates to other forms of teen dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1063–1077. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9922-8.

6.1.2. Erwachsene

Erooga, Marcus (2012): Understanding and Responding to People Who Sexually Abuse Children Whilst Employed In Trust. An Overview of the Relevant Literature - Part One: Offenders. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them.* Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 7–26.

Erooga, Marcus; Allnock, Debra; Telford, David (2012): Sexual abuse of children by people in organisations. What offenders can teach us about protection. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them.* Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 63–84.

Kaufman, Keith L.; Tews, Hayley; Schuett, Jessica M.; Kaufman, Benjamin R. (2012): Prevention is better than cure. The value of situational prevention in organisations. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): *Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them.* Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 140–169.

Blackman, Jerome S.; Dring, Kathleen (2016): *Sexual aggression against children. Pedophiles' and abusers' development, dynamics, treatability, and the law.* 1 Edition. New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.

- Drobac, Jennifer Ann (2016): Sexual exploitation of teenagers. Adolescent development, discrimination, and consent law. Chicago, London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Keenan, Marie (2013): Child sexual abuse and the Catholic Church. Gender, power, and organizational culture. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Miller-Perrin, Cindy L.; Perrin, Robin D. (2013): Child maltreatment. An introduction. 3. ed. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Erooga, Marcus (Hg.) (2012): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children).
- Anderson, Jane (2016): Socialization Processes and Clergy Offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (8), S. 846–865. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1241333.
- Babchishin, Kelly M.; Nunes, Kevin L.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Malcom, J. Renee (2015): Implicit sexual interest in children. Does separating gender influence discrimination when using the Implicit Association Test? In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 194–208. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836575.
- Balfe, Myles; Gallagher, Bernard; Masson, Helen; Balfe, Shane; Brugha, Ruairi; Hackett, Simon (2015): Internet Child Sex Offenders' Concerns about Online Security and their Use of Identity Protection Technologies. A Review. In: *Child Abuse Review* 24 (6), S. 427–439. DOI: 10.1002/car.2308.
- Bergen, Emilia; Ahto, Anna; Schulz, Anja; Imhoff, Roland; Antfolk, Jan; Schuhmann, Petya et al. (2015): Adult-Adult and Adult-Child/Adolescent Online Sexual Interactions. An Exploratory Self-Report Study on the Role of Situational Factors. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 52 (9), S. 1006–1016.
- Bowman, Rachel A.; Scotti, Joseph R.; Morris, Tracy L. (2010): Sexual abuse prevention. A training program for developmental disabilities service providers. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 119–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003614718.
- Buschman, Jos; Wilcox, Dan; Krapohl, Donald; Oelrich, Marty; Hackett, Simon (2010): Cybersex offender risk assessment. An explorative study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 197–209. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003690518.
- Celik, Gonca Gul; Yolga Tahiroglu, Aysegul; Avci, Ayse; Cekin, Necmi; Evliyaoglu, Nurdan; Yoruldu, Belgin (2012): Sexual abuse in a classroom of ten male students. A group victimization. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (5), S. 543–552. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.694403.
- Clements, Hannah; Dawson, David L.; das Nair, Roshan (2014): Female-perpetrated sexual abuse. A review of victim and professional perspectives. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 197–215. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.798690.
- Coburn, Patricia I.; Chong, Kristin; Connolly, Deborah A. (2017): The Effect of Case Severity on Sentence Length in Cases of Child Sexual Assault in Canada. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 319–333. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1283651.
- Collins, Christi M.; O'Neill-Arana, Margarita R.; Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Ossege, Jennifer M. (2014): Catholicism and childhood sexual abuse. Women's coping and psychotherapy. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (5), S. 519–537. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.918071.
- Cowburn, Malcolm; Gill, Aisha K.; Harrison, Karen (2015): Speaking about sexual abuse in British South Asian communities. Offenders, victims and the challenges of shame and reintegration. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 4–15. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.929188.
- D'Alton, Paul; Guilfoyle, Michael; Randall, Patrick (2013): Roman Catholic Clergy who have sexually abused children: Their perceptions of their developmental experience. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 698–702.
- DeHart, Dana; Dwyer, Gregg; Seto, Michael C.; Moran, Robert; Letourneau, Elizabeth; Schwarz-Watts, Donna (2017): Internet sexual solicitation of children. A proposed typology of offenders based on their chats, e-mails, and social network posts. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 77–89. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1241309.
- Doel, Mark; Allmark, Peter; Conway, Paul; Cowburn, Malcolm; Flynn, Margaret; Nelson, Pete; Tod, Angela (2010): Professional Boundaries. Crossing a Line or Entering the Shadows? In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (6), S. 1866–1889.

- Elliott, Ian A.; Findlater, Donald; Hughes, Teresa (2010): Practice report. A review of e-Safety remote computer monitoring for UK sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003686870.
- Embregts, P.; Bogaard, K. van den; Hendriks, L.; Heestermans, M.; Schuitemaker, M.; Wouwe, H. van (2010): Sexual risk assessment for people with intellectual disabilities. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 31 (3), S. 760–767. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2010.01.018.
- Fromuth, Mary Ellen; Kelly, David B.; Brallier, Courtney; Williams, Matthew; Benson, Kate (2016): Effects of duration on perceptions of teacher sexual misconduct. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (2), S. 159–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1122692.
- Gakhal, Baldeesh Kaur; Brown, Sarah J. (2011): A comparison of the general public's, forensic professionals' and students' attitudes towards female sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 105–116. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.540678.
- Gill, Michael (2010): Rethinking sexual abuse, questions of consent, and intellectual disability. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (3), S. 201–213. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0019-9.
- Glasgow, David (2010): The potential of digital evidence to contribute to risk assessment of internet offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 87–106. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903428839.
- Hall, Charlotte L.; Hogue, Todd E.; Guo, Kun (2014): Gaze patterns to child figures reflect deviant sexual preference in child sex offenders—a first glance. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 303–317. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.931475.
- Harper, Craig A.; Bartels, Ross M. (2017): The influence of implicit theories and offender characteristics on judgements of sexual offenders. A moderated mediation analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 139–150. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1250963.
- Hatchard, Christine J.; Goodwin, Jamie L.; Siddall, Eryn; Muniz, Lauren (2017): Perceptions of Abusive Parenting Behaviors. A Preliminary Exploration Into the Underrecognition of Mother-Daughter Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (4), S. 428–441. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1300971.
- Henry, Olivia; Mandeville-Norden, Rebecca; Hayes, Elizabeth; Egan, Vincent (2010): Do internet-based sexual offenders reduce to normal, inadequate and deviant groups? In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 33–46. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903454132.
- Horn, Joan van; Eisenberg, Mara; Nicholls McNaughton, Carol; Mulder, Jules; Webster, Stephen; Paskell, Caroline et al. (2015): Stop It Now! A Pilot Study Into the Limits and Benefits of a Free Helpline Preventing Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 853–872. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088914.
- Huitema, Anneloes; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine (2016): Attitudes of Dutch citizens towards male victims of sexual coercion by a female perpetrator. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 308–322. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1159343.
- Kemshall, Hazel; Kelly, Gill; Wilkinson, Bernadette (2012): Child Sex Offender Public Disclosure Scheme. The views of applicants using the English pilot disclosure scheme. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 164–178. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.552987.
- Kettleborough, Danielle G.; Merdian, Hannah L. (2017): Gateway to offending behaviour. Permission-giving thoughts of online users of child sexual exploitation material. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 19–32. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1231852.
- Kingston, Drew A.; Graham, Franklyn J.; Knight, Raymond A. (2017): Relations Between Self-Reported Adverse Events in Childhood and Hypersexuality in Adult Male Sexual Offenders. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 707–720. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0873-5.
- Knoll, James (2010): Teacher sexual misconduct. Grooming patterns and female offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (4), S. 371–386. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.495047.
- Kosuri, Mahathi D.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2017): Child sex tourism. American perceptions of foreign victims. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 207–221. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1231350.
- Kuhle, Laura F.; Schlinzig, Eliza; Kaiser, Gerd; Amelung, Till; Konrad, Anna; Röhle, Robert; Beier, Klaus M. (2017): The association of sexual preference and dynamic risk factors with undetected child pornography offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 3–18. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1201157.

- Langeland, Willemiem; Hoogendoorn, Adriaan W.; Mager, Daniel; Smit, Jan H.; Draijer, Nel (2015): Childhood sexual abuse by representatives of the Roman Catholic Church. A prevalence estimate among the Dutch population. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 67–77.
- Lasher, Michael P.; Stinson, Jill D. (2017): Adults with Pedophilic Interests in the United States: Current Practices and Suggestions for Future Policy and Research. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 659–670. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0822-3.
- Leonard, Marcella Mary (2010): "I did what I was directed to do but he didn't touch me". The impact of being a victim of internet offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 249–256. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003690526.
- Mahony, David (2010): Assessing sexual abuse/attack histories with bariatric surgery patients. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (4), S. 469–484. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.496713.
- Malón, Agustín (2011): The "Participating Victim" in the Study of Erotic Experiences Between Children and Adults: An Historical Analysis. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (1), S. 169–188.
- Man-Ging, Carlos Ignacio; Bohm, Bettina; Fuchs, Katharina Anna; Witte, Susanne; Frick, Eckhard (2015): Improving Empathy in the Prevention of Sexual Abuse Against Children and Youngsters. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (7), S. 796–815. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1077366.
- Mannix, Karyn; Dawson, David L.; Beckley, Kerry (2013): The implicit theories of male child sexual offenders residing in a high secure psychiatric hospital. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 264–274. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.732616.
- Manson, William (2015): "Keeping Children Safe". The Child Sex Offender Disclosure Scheme in Scotland. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 43–55. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.950352.
- Marshall, W. L.; Marshall, L. E.; Kingston, Drew A. (2011): Are the cognitive distortions of child molesters in need of treatment? In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 118–129. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.580572.
- Maxwell, Louise; Scott, Graham (2014): A review of the role of radical feminist theories in the understanding of rape myth acceptance. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 40–54. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.773384.
- McLeod, David Axlyn (2015): Female offenders in child sexual abuse cases. A national picture. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (1), S. 97–114. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.978925.
- McManus, Michelle Ann; Long, Matthew L.; Alison, Laurence; Almond, Louise (2014): Factors associated with contact child sexual abuse in a sample of indecent image offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 368–384. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927009.
- McPhail, Ian V.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Fernandez, Yolanda M. (2014): Correlates of emotional congruence with children in sexual offenders against children. A test of theoretical models in an incarcerated sample. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (2), S. 336–346.
- Melville-Wiseman, Janet (2017): The Sexual Abuse of Vulnerable People by Registered Social Workers in England. An Analysis of the Health and Care Professions Council Fitness to Practise Cases. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2190–2207. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw150.
- Merdian, Hannah Lena; Curtis, Cate; Thakker, Jo; Wilson, Nick; Boer, Douglas Pieter (2013): The three dimensions of online child pornography offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 121–132. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.611898.
- Mitchell, Renae C.; Galupo, M. Paz (2015): Interest in child molestation among a community sample of men sexually attracted to children. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (2), S. 224–232. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1056263.
- Morgan, Wendy; Gilchrist, Elizabeth (2010): Risk assessment with intimate partner sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (3), S. 361–372. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.502976.
- Nunes, Kevin L.; McPhail, Ian V.; Babchishin, Kelly M. (2012): Social anxiety and sexual offending against children. A cumulative meta-analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (3), S. 284–293. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.549243.
- Ó Ciardha, Caoilte; Gannon, Theresa A. (2011): The cognitive distortions of child molesters are in need of treatment. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 130–141. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.580573.
- O'Halloran, Elaine; Quayle, Ethel (2010): A content analysis of a "boy love" support forum. Revisiting Durkin and Bryant. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 71–85. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903395319.

- O'Leary, P.; Tsui, M.-S.; Ruch, G. (2013): The Boundaries of the Social Work Relationship Revisited. Towards a Connected, Inclusive and Dynamic Conceptualisation. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 43 (1), S. 135–153. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcr181.
- Paquette, Sarah; Cortoni, Franca; Proulx, Jean; Longpre, Nicholas (2014): An examination of implicit theories among francophone child molesters. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 182–196. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.798689.
- Park, Jisun; Kim, Seunghee (2016): Group size does matter. Differences among sexual assaults committed by lone, double, and groups of three or more perpetrators. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 342–354. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1144801.
- Roberts, Susan (2011): Doing Research with Imprisoned Adult Male Child Sexual Abusers. Reflecting on the Challenges. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 187–196. DOI: 10.1002/car.1175.
- Rogers, Paul; Wczasek, Ryan; Davies, Michelle (2011): Attributions of blame in a hypothetical internet solicitation case. Roles of victim naivety, parental neglect and respondent gender. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 196–214. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003664869.
- Schmidt, Alexander F.; Babchishin, Kelly M.; Lehmann, Robert J. B. (2017): A Meta-Analysis of Viewing Time Measures of Sexual Interest in Children. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (1), S. 287–300. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0806-3.
- Seto, Michael C.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2015): Viewing child pornography: prevalence and correlates in a representative community sample of young Swedish men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 67–79. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0244-4.
- Sheehan, Valerie; Sullivan, Joe (2010): A qualitative analysis of child sex offenders involved in the manufacture of indecent images of children. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 143–167. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003698644.
- Spraitz, Jason D.; Bowen, Kendra N.; Arthurs, Shavonne (2017): Neutralisation and sexual abuse. A study of monks from one Benedictine Abbey. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 195–206. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1204471.
- Stewart, Catherine Carolyn (2012): Beyond the call. Mothers of children with developmental disabilities responding to sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 701–727. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.722182.
- Tsagaris, George S.; Bach, Jesse E.; Cimino, Chrisa (2017): The characteristics of federal offenders sentenced for sexual exploitation of children within a large urban metropolitan region. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 181–194. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1307463.
- Turner, Daniel; Hoyer, Juergen; Schmidt, Alexander F.; Klein, Verena; Briken, Peer (2016): Risk Factors for Sexual Offending in Men Working With Children: A Community-Based Survey. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (7), S. 1851–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0746-y.
- van Leeuwen, Matthijs L.; van Baaren, Rick B.; Chakhssi, Farid; Loonen, Marijke G. M.; Lippman, Maarten; Dijksterhuis, Ap (2013): Assessment of implicit sexual associations in non-incarcerated pedophiles. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1501–1507. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0094-0.
- Williams, Matthew L.; Hudson, Kirsty (2013): Public perceptions of internet, familial and localised sexual grooming. Predicting perceived prevalence and safety. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 218–235. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.705341.
- Williamson, Laura Helen; Grubb, Amy Rose (2015): An analysis of the relationship between being deaf and sexual offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 224–243. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.842001.
- Willis, Gwenda M.; Johnston, Lucy (2012): Planning helps. The impact of release planning on subsequent re-entry experiences of child sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 194–208. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.506576.
- Willis, Gwenda M.; Levenson, Jill S. (2016): The relationship between childhood adversity and adult psychosocial outcomes in females who have sexually offended. Implications for treatment. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 355–367. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1131341.
- Willis, Gwenda M.; Ward, Tony (2011): Striving for a good life. The good lives model applied to released child molesters. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (3), S. 290–303. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.505349.

Winters, Georgia M.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2016): I Knew It All Along. The Sexual Grooming Behaviors of Child Molesters and the Hindsight Bias. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 20–36. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1108945.

Winters, Georgia M.; Kaylor, Leah E.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2017): Sexual offenders contacting children online. An examination of transcripts of sexual grooming. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 62–76. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1271146.

Wurtele, Sandy K. (2012): Preventing the sexual exploitation of minors in youth-serving organizations. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (12), S. 2442–2453. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.09.009.

Zinzow, Heidi; Seth, Puja; Jackson, Joan; Niehaus, Ashley; Fitzgerald, Monica (2010): Abuse and parental characteristics, attributions of blame, and psychological adjustment in adult survivors of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (1), S. 79–98. DOI: 10.1080/10538710903485989.

6.2. Art

6.2.1. Belästigung

Chapman, Amy; Buchanan, Rachel (2014): FYI... Virtual space has a context. Towards an alternative frame for understanding cyberbullying. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 56–71.

Cowie, Helen (2013): The immediate and long-term effects of bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 10–18.

Davies, Cristyn; McInnes, David (2014): Speaking violence. Homophobia and the production of injurious speech in schooling cultures. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 131–148.

Duncan, Neil (2013): Disability, sexuality and bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 105–119.

Jennifer, Dawn (2013): Girls and indirect aggression. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 45–59.

Luschen, Kristen V. (2014): Survival, Protection, and Forgiveness. Examining Gendered Violence and Care in the Hunger Games Trilogy. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 133–146.

McCormack, Mark (2013): Mapping the boundaries of homophobic language in bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 91–104.

McCready, Lance T. (2014): The African Dance Program. "Where is the Love?". In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), 342–356.

Miller, sj; Gilligan, James R. (2014): Heteronormative Harassment. Queer Bullying and Gender-Non-Conforming Students. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 217–229.

Ollis, Debbie (2013): Planning and delivering interventions to promote gender and sexuality. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 145–161.

Poteat, V. Paul; Mereish, Ethan H.; DiGiovanni, Craig D.; Scheer, Jillian R. (2013): Homophobic bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 75–90.

Rivers, Ian (2013): Cyberbullying and cyberaggression. Sexualised and gendered experiences explored. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 19–44.

- Rivers, Ian; Duncan, Neil (2013): Discourses of sexuality and gender considered. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 162–168.
- Robinson, Kerry H. (2014): Sexual harassment in schools. Issues of identity and power - Negotiating the complexities, contexts and contradictions of this everyday practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 71–94.
- Saleh, Fabian M.; Feldman, Barry N.; Grudzinskas, Albert; Ravven, Simha E.; Cody, Richard (2014): Cybersexual Harassment and Suicide. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 139–160.
- Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): "The kid most likely". Naming, brutality and silence within and beyond school settings. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 21–38.
- Williams, Sian (2013): Sexual bullying in one local authority. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 60–74.
- Drobac, Jennifer Ann (2016): *Sexual exploitation of teenagers. Adolescent development, discrimination, and consent law*. Chicago, London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Oliver, Kelly (2016): *Hunting Girls. Sexual Violence from The Hunger Games to Campus Rape*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Postmus, Judy L. (2013): *Sexual Violence and Abuse. An Encyclopedia of Prevention, Impacts, and Recovery*. Santa Barbara, Calif: Abc-Clío.
- Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2012): Pervasive vulnerabilities. Sexual harassment in school. New York: Peter Lang (*Adolescent cultures, school & society*, v. 54).
- Shariff, Shaheen (2015): *Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Rivers, Ian (Hg.) (2013): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education).
- Saltmarsh, Sue (Hg.) (2014): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Bantjes, J.; Nieuwoudt, J. (2014): Masculinity and Mayhem. The Performance of Gender in a South African Boys' School. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (4), S. 376–395. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539964.
- Calafat, Amador; Hughes, Karen; Blay, Nicole; Bellis, Mark A.; Mendes, Fernando; Juan, Montse et al. (2013): Sexual harassment among young tourists visiting Mediterranean resorts. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 603–613. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-9979-6.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2013): Homophobic name-calling among secondary school students and its implications for mental health. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 363–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9823-2.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G.M. (2015): Understanding teachers' responses to enactments of sexual and gender stigma at school. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 48, S. 34–43. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.02.002.
- Fagerlund, Monica; Ellonen, Noora (2016): Children's Experiences of Completing a Computer-Based Violence Survey. Finnish Child Victim Survey Revisited. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 556–576. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1186769.
- Ferfolja, Tania (2010): Lesbian teachers, harassment and the workplace. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (3), S. 408–414. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.05.007.
- Hafford-Letchfield, Trish; Cocker, Christine; Ryan, Peter; Melonowska, Justyna (2017): Rights through Alliances. Findings from a European Project Tackling Homophobic and Transphobic Bullying in Schools through the Engagement of Families and Young People. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2338–2356. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw104.
- Hlavka, H. R. (2014): Normalizing Sexual Violence. Young Women Account for Harassment and Abuse. In: *Gender & Society* 28 (3), S. 337–358. DOI: 10.1177/0891243214526468.

- James, Adilia E. E. (2010): Too Early to Talk About Sex? Issues in Creating Culturally Relevant Sexuality Education for Preadolescent Black Girls in the United States. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (2), S. 128–141. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0012-3.
- Kaltiala-Heino, Riittakerttu; Fröjd, Sari; Marttunen, Mauri (2016): Sexual harassment victimization in adolescence. Associations with family background. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 56, S. 11–19.
- Lund, Emily M.; Hammond, Marilyn (2014): Single-Session Intervention for Abuse Awareness Among People with Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 99–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9335-3.
- Makura, Alfred Henry; Zireva, Davison (2013): School heads and mentors in cahoots? Challenges to teaching practice in Zimbabwean teacher education programmes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 3–16. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.573583.
- Miller, S. A. (2016): "How You Bully a Girl". Sexual Drama and the Negotiation of Gendered Sexuality in High School. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (5), S. 721–744. DOI: 10.1177/0891243216664723.
- Miller, Shari; Williams, Jason; Cutbush, Stacey; Gibbs, Deborah; Clinton-Sherrod, Monique; Jones, Sarah (2013): Dating violence, bullying, and sexual harassment: longitudinal profiles and transitions over time. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 607–618. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9914-8.
- Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Ybarra, Michele L.; Korchmaros, Josephine D. (2014): Sexual harassment among adolescents of different sexual orientations and gender identities. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (2), S. 280–295.
- Morris, Matthew C.; Kouros, Chrystyna D.; Janecek, Kim; Freeman, Rachel; Mielock, Alyssa; Garber, Judy (2017): Community-level moderators of a school-based childhood sexual assault prevention program. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 295–306. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.10.005.
- Ojanen, Timo Tapani; Boonmongkon, Pimpawun; Samakkeekarom, Ronnapoom; Samoh, Nattharat; Cholratana, Mudjalin; Guadamuz, Thomas Ebanan (2015): Connections between online harassment and offline violence among youth in Central Thailand. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 44, S. 159–169.
- Preston, Marilyn J. (2015): 'They're just not mature right now': teachers' complicated perceptions of gender and anti-queer bullying. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 22–34. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1019665.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2012): Popular culture as emotional provocation. The material enactment of queer pedagogies in a high school classroom. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 511–522. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627728.
- Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2011): Race, class, and emerging sexuality. Teacher perceptions and sexual harassment in schools. In: *Gender and Education* 23 (7), S. 799–810. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2010.536143.
- Russell, Brenda L.; Oswald, Debra L. (2016): When Sexism Cuts Both Ways. Predictors of Tolerance of Sexual Harassment of Men. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (5), S. 524–544. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15602745.
- Wolff, Jennifer M.; Rospenda, Kathleen M.; Colaneri, Anthony S. (2017): Sexual Harassment, Psychological Distress, and Problematic Drinking Behavior Among College Students: An Examination of Reciprocal Causal Relations. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (3), S. 362–373. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1143439.

6.2.2. Missbrauch

- Cleary, Kerry; Erooga, Marcus (2012): Policy and Legislation - Changing Responses to an Emerging Problem. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 44–62.
- Erooga, Marcus (2012): Understanding and Responding to People Who Sexually Abuse Children Whilst Employed In Trust. An Overview of the Relevant Literature - Part One: Offenders. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 7–26.
- Erooga, Marcus; Allnock, Debra; Telford, David (2012): Sexual abuse of children by people in organisations. What offenders can teach us about protection. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 63–84.

- Green, Jo (2012): Avoiding and managing allegations against staff. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 170–187.
- Kaufman, Keith L.; Tews, Hayley; Schuett, Jessica M.; Kaufman, Benjamin R. (2012): Prevention is better than cure. The value of situational prevention in organisations. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 140–169.
- Sullivan, Joe; Quayle, Ethel (2012): Manipulation styles of abusers who work with children. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 85–98.
- Cheit, Ross E. (2014): The witch-hunt narrative. Politics, psychology, and the sexual abuse of children. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014): Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Keenan, Marie (2013): Child sexual abuse and the Catholic Church. Gender, power, and organizational culture. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Miller-Perrin, Cindy L.; Perrin, Robin D. (2013): Child maltreatment. An introduction. 3. ed. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Nelson, Sarah (2016): Tackling child sexual abuse. Radical approaches to prevention, protection and support. Bristol: Policy Press.
- Postmus, Judy L. (2013): Sexual Violence and Abuse. An Encyclopedia of Prevention, Impacts, and Recovery. Santa Barbara, Calif: Abc-Clío.
- Erooga, Marcus (Hg.) (2012): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children).
- Saltmarsh, Sue (Hg.) (2014): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Alessi, Edward J.; Kahn, Sarilee; Chatterji, Sangeeta (2016): 'The darkest times of my life'. Recollections of child abuse among forced migrants persecuted because of their sexual orientation and gender identity. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 51, S. 93–105.
- Alix, Stephanie; Cossette, Louise; Hebert, Martine; Cyr, Mireille; Frappier, Jean-Yves (2017): Posttraumatic Stress Disorder and Suicidal Ideation Among Sexually Abused Adolescent Girls. The Mediating Role of Shame. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (2), S. 158–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1280577.
- Allbaugh, Lucy Jane; O'Dougherty Wright, Margaret; Atkins Seltmann, Larissa (2014): An exploratory study of domains of parenting concern among mothers who are childhood sexual abuse survivors. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (8), S. 885–899. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.960636.
- Allnock, Debra; Radford, Lorraine; Bunting, Lisa; Price, Avril; Morgan-Klein, Natalie; Ellis, Jane; Stafford, Anne (2012): In Demand. Therapeutic Services for Children and Young People Who Have Experienced Sexual Abuse. In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (5), S. 318–334. DOI: 10.1002/car.1205.
- Anderson, Gwendolyn D. (2016): The Continuum of Disclosure. Exploring Factors Predicting Tentative Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations During Forensic Interviews and the Implications for Practice, Policy, and Future Research. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 382–402. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153559.
- Anderson, Jane (2016): Socialization Processes and Clergy Offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (8), S. 846–865. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1241333.
- Babatsikos, Georgia (2010): Parents' knowledge, attitudes and practices about preventing child sexual abuse. A literature review. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (2), S. 107–129. DOI: 10.1002/car.1102.
- Bajaj, Monika (2012): Vesicular Genital Lesions in a Toddler – Is it Sexual Abuse? In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (5), S. 370–373. DOI: 10.1002/car.1188.

- Balfe, Myles; Gallagher, Bernard; Masson, Helen; Balfe, Shane; Brugha, Ruairi; Hackett, Simon (2015): Internet Child Sex Offenders' Concerns about Online Security and their Use of Identity Protection Technologies. A Review. In: *Child Abuse Review* 24 (6), S. 427–439. DOI: 10.1002/car.2308.
- Baratvand, Mahmood; Soodani, Mansour; Zarei, Eghbal; Asadollahi, Abdolrahim (2013): Sexual Abuse and Drug Abuse Among Homeless Children in Ahvaz, Iran. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (6), S. 408–418. DOI: 10.1002/car.2263.
- Baril, Karine; Tourigny, Marc; Paille, Pierre; Pauze, Robert (2016): Characteristics of Sexually Abused Children and Their Nonoffending Mothers Followed by Child Welfare Services. The Role of a Maternal History of Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 504–523. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1176096.
- Barron, Ian G.; Topping, Keith J. (2011): Sexual abuse prevention programme fidelity. Video analysis of interactions. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 134–151. DOI: 10.1002/car.1134.
- Benia, Luis Roberto; Hauck-Filho, Nelson; Dillenburg, Mariana; Stein, Lilian Milnitsky (2015): The NICHD Investigative Interview Protocol. A Meta-Analytic Review. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 259–279. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006749.
- Benuto, Lorraine T.; O'Donohue, William (2015): Treatment of the Sexually Abused Child. Review and Synthesis of Recent Meta-Analyses. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 56, S. 52–60. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.06.009.
- Bird, Elizabeth R.; Seehuus, Martin; Clifton, Jessica; Rellini, Alessandra H. (2014): Dissociation during sex and sexual arousal in women with and without a history of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (5), S. 953–964. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0191-0.
- Bowman, Rachel A.; Scotti, Joseph R.; Morris, Tracy L. (2010): Sexual abuse prevention. A training program for developmental disabilities service providers. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 119–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003614718.
- Caldas, Stephen J.; Betsy, Mary Lou (2014): The sexual maltreatment of students with disabilities in American school settings. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (4), S. 345–366. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.906530.
- Capella, Claudia; Lama, Ximena; Rodriguez, Loreto; Aguila, Daniela; Beiza, Gretchen; Dussert, Denise; Gutierrez, Carolina (2016): Winning a Race. Narratives of Healing and Psychotherapy in Children and Adolescents Who Have Been Sexually Abused. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 73–92. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088915.
- Celik, Gonca Gul; Yolga Tahiroglu, Aysegul; Avci, Ayse; Cekin, Necmi; Evliyaoglu, Nurdan; Yoruldu, Belgin (2012): Sexual abuse in a classroom of ten male students. A group victimization. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (5), S. 543–552. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.694403.
- Clements, Hannah; Dawson, David L.; das Nair, Roshan (2014): Female-perpetrated sexual abuse. A review of victim and professional perspectives. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 197–215. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.798690.
- Collins, Christi M.; O'Neill-Arana, Margarita R.; Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Ossege, Jennifer M. (2014): Catholicism and childhood sexual abuse. Women's coping and psychotherapy. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (5), S. 519–537. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.918071.
- Collin-Vézina, Delphine; Garrido, Edward F. (2017): Current issues in child sexual abuse, gender and health outcomes: Shedding new lights to inform worldwide policy and practice. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 245–248. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.11.032.
- Collin-Vézina, Delphine; Sablonnière-Griffin, Mireille de la; Palmer, Andrea M.; Milne, Lise (2015): A preliminary mapping of individual, relational, and social factors that impede disclosure of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 43, S. 123–134.
- Connon, Graham; Crooks, Allian; Carr, Alan; Dooley, Barbara; Guerin, Suzanne; Deasy, Derek et al. (2011): Child sex abuse and the Irish criminal justice system. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 102–119. DOI: 10.1002/car.1156.
- Coren, Esther; Thomae, Manuela; Hutchfield, Jemeela; Iredale, Wendy (2013): Report on the Implementation and Results of an Outcomes-focused Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Interventions in the UK. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (1), S. 44–59. DOI: 10.1002/car.2200.
- Cowburn, Malcolm; Gill, Aisha K.; Harrison, Karen (2015): Speaking about sexual abuse in British South Asian communities. Offenders, victims and the challenges of shame and reintegration. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 4–15. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.929188.

- Cromer, Lisa DeMarni; Goldsmith, Rachel E. (2010): Child sexual abuse myths. Attitudes, beliefs, and individual differences. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (6), S. 618–647. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.522493.
- Cyr, Mireille; McDuff, Pierre; Hebert, Martine (2013): Support and profiles of nonoffending mothers of sexually abused children. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (2), S. 209–230. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.737444.
- D'Alton, Paul; Guilfoyle, Michael; Randall, Patrick (2013): Roman Catholic Clergy who have sexually abused children: Their perceptions of their developmental experience. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 698–702.
- D'Abreu, Lylla Cysne Frota; Krahé, Barbara (2016): Vulnerability to Sexual Victimization in Female and Male College Students in Brazil: Cross-Sectional and Prospective Evidence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1101–1115. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0451-7.
- Das, Aniruddha; Otis, Nicholas (2016): Sexual Contact in Childhood, Revictimization, and Lifetime Sexual and Psychological Outcomes. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1117–1131.
- DeHart, Dana; Dwyer, Gregg; Seto, Michael C.; Moran, Robert; Letourneau, Elizabeth; Schwarz-Watts, Donna (2017): Internet sexual solicitation of children. A proposed typology of offenders based on their chats, e-mails, and social network posts. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 77–89. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1241309.
- Delft, Ivanka van; Finkenauer, Catrin; Schipper, J. Clasiën de; Lamers-Winkelmann, Francien; Visser, Margreet M. (2015): The mediating role of secrecy in the development of psychopathology in sexually abused children. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 27–36.
- Dolan, Mairead; Whitworth, Helen (2013): Childhood sexual abuse, adult psychiatric morbidity, and criminal outcomes in women assessed by medium secure forensic service. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (2), S. 191–208. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.751951.
- Doughty, Adam H.; Kane, Lindsey M. (2010): Teaching abuse-protection skills to people with intellectual, disabilities. A review of the literature. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 31 (2), S. 331–337. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2009.12.007.
- Elklit, Ask; Christiansen, Dorte M.; Palic, Sabina; Karsberg, Sidsel; Eriksen, Sara Bek (2014): Impact of traumatic events on posttraumatic stress disorder among Danish survivors of sexual abuse in childhood. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (8), S. 918–934. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.964440.
- Elliott, Ian A.; Findlater, Donald; Hughes, Teresa (2010): Practice report. A review of e-Safety remote computer monitoring for UK sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003686870.
- Everson, Mark D.; Faller, Kathleen Coulborn (2012): Base rates, multiple indicators, and comprehensive forensic evaluations. Why sexualized behavior still counts in assessments of child sexual abuse allegations. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (1), S. 45–71. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.642470.
- Fagerlund, Monica; Ellonen, Noora (2016): Children's Experiences of Completing a Computer-Based Violence Survey. Finnish Child Victim Survey Revisited. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 556–576. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1186769.
- Finkelhor, David; Ji, Kai; Mikton, Christopher; Dunne, Michael (2013): Explaining lower rates of sexual abuse in China. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (10), S. 852–860.
- Firmin, Carlene; Warrington, Camille; Pearce, Jenny (2017): Sexual Exploitation and Its Impact on Developing Sexualities and Sexual Relationships. The Need for Contextual Social Work Interventions. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2318–2337. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw134.
- Fitzpatrick, Mark; Carr, Alan; Dooley, Barbara; Flanagan-Howard, Roisín; Flanagan, Edel; Tierney, Kevin et al. (2010): Profiles of adult survivors of severe sexual, physical and emotional institutional abuse in Ireland. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (6), S. 387–404. DOI: 10.1002/car.1083.
- Flannery, Dustin D.; Stephens, Clare L.; Thompson, Amy D. (2016): The Impact of High-Profile Sexual Abuse Cases in the Media on a Pediatric Emergency Department. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 627–635. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1187697.
- Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Plummer, Carol (2010): Cultural issues in disclosures of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (5), S. 491–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.512520.

- Forsman, Mats; Johansson, Ada; Santtila, Pekka; Sandnabba, Kenneth; Långström, Niklas (2015): Sexually Coercive Behavior Following Childhood Maltreatment. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 149–156.
- Franklin, Anita; Smeaton, Emilie (2017): Recognising and responding to young people with learning disabilities who experience, or are at risk of, child sexual exploitation in the UK. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 474–481. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.11.009.
- Fresno, Andres; Spencer, Rosario; Ramos, Nadia; Pierrehumbert, Blaise (2014): The effect of sexual abuse on children's attachment representations in Chile. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 128–145. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870949.
- Frías, Sonia M.; Erviti, Joaquina (2014): Gendered experiences of sexual abuse of teenagers and children in Mexico. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (4), S. 776–787.
- Fromuth, Mary Ellen; Kelly, David B.; Brallier, Courtney; Williams, Matthew; Benson, Kate (2016): Effects of duration on perceptions of teacher sexual misconduct. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (2), S. 159–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1122692.
- Gakhal, Baldeesh Kaur; Brown, Sarah J. (2011): A comparison of the general public's, forensic professionals' and students' attitudes towards female sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 105–116. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.540678.
- Geary, Jan; Lambie, Ian; Seymour, Fred (2011): Consumer perspectives of New Zealand community treatment programmes for sexually abusive youth. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 181–195. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003778693.
- Gibson, Kerry; Morgan, Mandy; Woolley, Cheryl; Powis, Tracey (2011): Growing up at centrepiece. Retrospective accounts of childhood spent at an intentional community. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 413–434. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.591364.
- Gill, Michael (2010): Rethinking sexual abuse, questions of consent, and intellectual disability. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (3), S. 201–213. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0019-9.
- Gillespie, Alisdair (2010): Legal definitions of child pornography. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 19–31. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903262097.
- Gokten, Emel Sari; Saday Duman, Nagihan (2016): Factors influencing the development of psychiatric disorders in the victims of sexual abuse. A study on Turkish children. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 69, S. 49–55. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.07.022.
- Goldman, Juliette D. G.; Grimbeek, Peter (2015): Preservice teachers' sources of information on mandatory reporting of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 238–258. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1009607.
- Graham, Laurie M.; Lanier, Paul; Johnson-Motoyama, Michelle (2016): National profile of Latino/Latina children reported to the child welfare system for sexual abuse. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 66, S. 18–27. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2016.04.008.
- Griffin, Helen Louise; Vettor, Shannon (2012): Predicting sexual re-offending in a UK sample of adolescents with intellectual disabilities. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 64–80. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.617013.
- Grondin, Anne-Marie (2011): Thinking outside specious boxes. Constructionist and post-structuralist readings of 'child sexual abuse'. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 243–254. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590065.
- Gwirayi, Pesanayi (2013): The prevalence of child sexual abuse among secondary school pupils in Gweru, Zimbabwe. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 253–263. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.723755.
- Haboush, Karen L.; Alyan, Hala (2013): "Who can you tell?" Features of Arab culture that influence conceptualization and treatment of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 499–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800935.
- Hackett, Simon; Phillips, Josie; Masson, Helen; Balfe, Myles (2013): Individual, Family and Abuse Characteristics of 700 British Child and Adolescent Sexual Abusers. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (4), S. 232–245. DOI: 10.1002/car.2246.

- Hall, Charlotte L.; Hogue, Todd E.; Guo, Kun (2014): Gaze patterns to child figures reflect deviant sexual preference in child sex offenders—a first glance. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 303–317. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.931475.
- Hallett, Sophie (2017): 'An Uncomfortable Comfortableness'. 'Care', Child Protection and Child Sexual Exploitation. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (7), S. 2137–2152. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcv136.
- Hartley, Sarah; Johnco, Carly; Hofmeyr, Marthinus; Berry, Alexis (2016): The Nature of Posttraumatic Growth in Adult Survivors of Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (2), S. 201–220. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1119773.
- Hatchard, Christine J.; Goodwin, Jamie L.; Siddall, Eryn; Muniz, Lauren (2017): Perceptions of Abusive Parenting Behaviors. A Preliminary Exploration Into the Underrecognition of Mother–Daughter Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (4), S. 428–441. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1300971.
- Hidalgo, Marco A.; Kuhns, Lisa M.; Kwon, Soyang; Mustanski, Brian; Garofalo, Robert (2015): The impact of childhood gender expression on childhood sexual abuse and psychopathology among young men who have sex with men. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 103–112.
- Hlavka, H. R. (2014): Normalizing Sexual Violence. Young Women Account for Harassment and Abuse. In: *Gender & Society* 28 (3), S. 337–358. DOI: 10.1177/0891243214526468.
- Horn, Joan van; Eisenberg, Mara; Nicholls McNaughton, Carol; Mulder, Jules; Webster, Stephen; Paskell, Caroline et al. (2015): Stop It Now! A Pilot Study Into the Limits and Benefits of a Free Helpline Preventing Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 853–872. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088914.
- Hovey, Angela; Stalker, Carol A.; Schachter, Candice L.; Teram, Eli; Lasiuk, Gerri (2011): Practical ways psychotherapy can support physical healthcare experiences for male survivors of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 37–57. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.539963.
- Hutchfield, Jemeela; Coren, Esther (2011): The Child's Voice in Service Evaluation. Ethical and Methodological Issues. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 173–186. DOI: 10.1002/car.1142.
- Jackson, Vicki; Browne, Kevin; Joseph, Stephen (2016): The prevalence of childhood victimization experienced outside of the family. Findings from an English prevalence study. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 51, S. 343–357. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.08.006.
- Jaffe, Anna E.; Cranston, Christopher C.; Shadlow, Joanna O. (2012): Parenting in females exposed to intimate partner violence and childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 684–700. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.726698.
- Jennings, Wesley G.; Richards, Tara N.; Tomsich, Elizabeth; Gover, Angela R. (2015): Investigating the Role of Child Sexual Abuse in Intimate Partner Violence Victimization and Perpetration in Young Adulthood From a Propensity Score Matching Approach. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 659–681. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1057665.
- Jin, Yichen; Chen, Jingqi; Yu, Buyi (2016): Knowledge and Skills of Sexual Abuse Prevention. A Study on School-Aged Children in Beijing, China. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 686–696. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1199079.
- Katz, Carmit (2013): Internet-related child sexual abuse. What children tell us in their testimonies. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (9), S. 1536–1542. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.06.006.
- Katz, Carmit; Hamama, Liat (2013): "Draw me everything that happened to you". Exploring children's drawings of sexual abuse. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (5), S. 877–882. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.02.007.
- Kemshall, Hazel; Moulden, Heather M. (2017): Communicating about child sexual abuse with the public. Learning the lessons from public awareness campaigns. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 124–138. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1222004.
- Kenny, Maureen C. (2010): Child sexual abuse education with ethnically diverse families. A preliminary analysis. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 32 (7), S. 981–989. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2010.03.025.
- Kim, Tae Kyung; Choi, Soul; Shin, Yee Jin (2011): Psychosocial factors influencing competency of children's statements on sexual trauma. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (3), S. 173–179.

- Kingston, Drew A.; Graham, Franklyn J.; Knight, Raymond A. (2017): Relations Between Self-Reported Adverse Events in Childhood and Hypersexuality in Adult Male Sexual Offenders. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 707–720. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0873-5.
- Kisanga, Felix; Nystrom, Lennarth; Hogan, Nora; Emmelin, Maria (2011): Child sexual abuse. Community concerns in urban Tanzania. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (2), S. 196–217. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.555356.
- Kloppen, Kathrine; Haugland, Siren; Svedin, Carl-Göran; Maehle, Magne; Breivik, Kyrre (2016): Prevalence of Child Sexual Abuse in the Nordic Countries. A Literature Review. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 37–55. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1108944.
- Knoll, James (2010): Teacher sexual misconduct. Grooming patterns and female offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (4), S. 371–386. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.495047.
- Kostolitz, Alessandra C.; Hyman, Scott M.; Gold, Steven N. (2014): How ineffective family environments can compound maldevelopment of critical thinking skills in childhood abuse survivors. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (6), S. 690–707. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.931318.
- Kosuri, Mahathi D.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2017): Child sex tourism. American perceptions of foreign victims. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 207–221. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1231350.
- Krahé, Barbara; Berger, Anja (2017): Gendered pathways from child sexual abuse to sexual aggression victimization and perpetration in adolescence and young adulthood. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 261–272. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.10.004.
- Krause-Parello, Cheryl A.; Gulick, Elsie E. (2015): Forensic Interviews for Child Sexual Abuse Allegations. An Investigation into the Effects of Animal-Assisted Intervention on Stress Biomarkers. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 873–886. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088916.
- Krayer, Anne; Seddon, Diane; Robinson, Catherine A.; Gwilym, Hefin (2015): The influence of child sexual abuse on the self from adult narrative perspectives. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (2), S. 135–151. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1001473.
- Kucuk, Sibel (2016): Analyses of Child Sex Abuse Cases in Turkey: A Provincial Case. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 262–275. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153557.
- Kwhali, Josephine; Martin, Linda; Brady, Geraldine; Brown, Sarah J. (2017): Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation. Knowledge, Confidence and Training within a Contemporary UK Social Work Practice and Policy Context. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2208–2226. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw154.
- Lacelle, Céline; Hébert, Martine; Lavoie, Francine; Vitaro, Frank; Tremblay, Richard E. (2012): Sexual health in women reporting a history of child sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (3), S. 247–259.
- Lainpelto, Katrin; Isaksson, Johan; Lindblad, Frank (2016): Does Information About Neuropsychiatric Diagnoses Influence Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations? In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 276–292. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1145164.
- Lampert, Jo (2012): Sh-h-h-h. Representations of perpetrators of sexual child abuse in picturebooks. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 177–185. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.609048.
- Langeland, Willemiem; Hoogendoorn, Adriaan W.; Mager, Daniel; Smit, Jan H.; Draijer, Nel (2015): Childhood sexual abuse by representatives of the Roman Catholic Church. A prevalence estimate among the Dutch population. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 67–77.
- Langevin, Rachel; Hébert, Martine; Cossette, Louise (2015): Emotion regulation as a mediator of the relation between sexual abuse and behavior problems in preschoolers. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 16–26.
- Lasher, Michael P.; Stinson, Jill D. (2017): Adults with Pedophilic Interests in the United States: Current Practices and Suggestions for Future Policy and Research. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 659–670. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0822-3.
- Leventhal, John M.; Murphy, Janet L.; Asnes, Andrea G. (2010): Evaluations of child sexual abuse. Recognition of overt and latent family concerns. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34 (5), S. 289–295.
- Lev-Wiesel, Rachel; Markus, Liora (2013): Perception vs. circumstances of the child sexual abuse event in relation to depression and post-traumatic stress symptomatology. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 519–533. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800932.

- Lewis, Tiffany; Klettke, Bianca; Day, Andrew (2014): Sentencing in child sexual assault cases. Factors influencing judicial decision-making. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 281–295. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.804603.
- Lin, Danhua; Li, Xiaoming; Fan, Xinghua; Fang, Xiaoyi (2011): Child sexual abuse and its relationship with health risk behaviors among rural children and adolescents in Hunan, China. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (9), S. 680–687. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2011.05.006.
- Liotta, Lindsay; Springer, Craig; Misurell, Justin R.; Block-Lerner, Jennifer; Brandwein, David (2015): Group treatment for child sexual abuse. Treatment referral and therapeutic outcomes. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 217–237. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006747.
- Loeb, Tamra B.; Gaines, Tommi; Wyatt, Gail E.; Zhang, Muyu; Liu, Honghu (2011): Associations between child sexual abuse and negative sexual experiences and revictimization among women. Does measuring severity matter? In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (11), S. 946–955.
- Lopez, Silvia; Faro, Concepcio; Lopetegui, Lourdes; Pujol-Ribera, Enriqueta; Monteagudo, Monica; Avecilla-Palau, Angels et al. (2017): Child and Adolescent Sexual Abuse in Women Seeking Help for Sexual and Reproductive Mental Health Problems. Prevalence, Characteristics, and Disclosure. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 246–269. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1288186.
- Lopez, Vera; Kopak, Albert; Robillard, Alyssa; Gillmore, Mary Rogers; Holliday, Rhonda C.; Braithwaite, Ronald L. (2011): Pathways to sexual risk taking among female adolescent detainees. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (8), S. 945–957. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9623-5.
- Lorenz, Tierney Ahrold; Meston, Cindy May (2012): Associations among childhood sexual abuse, language use, and adult sexual functioning and satisfaction. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (2), S. 190–199.
- Lueger-Schuster, Brigitte; Kantor, Viktoria; Weindl, Dina; Knefel, Matthias; Moy, Yvonne; Butollo, Asisa et al. (2014): Institutional abuse of children in the Austrian Catholic Church. Types of abuse and impact on adult survivors' current mental health. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (1), S. 52–64.
- Lund, Emily M.; Hammond, Marilyn (2014): Single-Session Intervention for Abuse Awareness Among People with Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 99–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9335-3.
- Mahony, David (2010): Assessing sexual abuse/attack histories with bariatric surgery patients. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (4), S. 469–484. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.496713.
- Maikovitch-Fong, Andrea Kohn; Jaffee, Sara R. (2010): Sex differences in childhood sexual abuse characteristics and victims' emotional and behavioral problems. Findings from a national sample of youth. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34 (6), S. 429–437. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2009.10.006.
- Malón, Agustín (2011): The “Participating Victim” in the Study of Erotic Experiences Between Children and Adults: An Historical Analysis. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (1), S. 169–188.
- Malón, Agustín (2010): Onanism and child sexual abuse: a comparative study of two hypotheses. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 637–652. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9465-3.
- Man-Ging, Carlos Ignacio; Bohm, Bettina; Fuchs, Katharina Anna; Witte, Susanne; Frick, Eckhard (2015): Improving Empathy in the Prevention of Sexual Abuse Against Children and Youngsters. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (7), S. 796–815. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1077366.
- Mannix, Karyn; Dawson, David L.; Beckley, Kerry (2013): The implicit theories of male child sexual offenders residing in a high secure psychiatric hospital. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 264–274. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.732616.
- Marquez-Flores, Maria Mercedes; Marquez-Hernandez, Veronica V.; Granados-Gamez, Genoveva (2016): Teachers' knowledge and beliefs about child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 538–555. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1189474.
- Marriott, Clare; Hamilton-Giachritsis, Catherine; Harrop, Chris (2014): Factors Promoting Resilience Following Childhood Sexual Abuse. A Structured, Narrative Review of the Literature. In: *Child Abuse Review* 23 (1), S. 17–34. DOI: 10.1002/car.2258.
- Marshall, W. L.; Marshall, L. E.; Kingston, Drew A. (2011): Are the cognitive distortions of child molesters in need of treatment? In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 118–129. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.580572.

- Martin, Jennifer (2016): Child Sexual Abuse Images Online. Implications for Social Work Training and Practice. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (2), S. 372–388. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu116.
- Martin, Karin A. (2014): Making sense of children's sexual behavior in child care. An analysis of adult responses in special investigation reports. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (10), S. 1636–1646.
- Martinello, Emily (2014): Reviewing strategies for risk reduction of sexual abuse of children with intellectual disabilities. A focus on early intervention. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (2), S. 167–174. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9345-9.
- Martinello, Emily (2015): Reviewing Risks Factors of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities as Perpetrators of Sexually Abusive Behaviors. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 33 (2), S. 269–278. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9365-5.
- McDaniels, Brad; Fleming, Allison (2016): Sexuality Education and Intellectual Disability. Time to Address the Challenge. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 215–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9427-y.
- McElvaney, Rosaleen (2015): Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse. Delays, Non-disclosure and Partial Disclosure. What the Research Tells Us and Implications for Practice. In: *Child Abuse Review* 24 (3), S. 159–169. DOI: 10.1002/car.2280.
- McLeod, David Axlyn (2015): Female offenders in child sexual abuse cases. A national picture. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (1), S. 97–114. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.978925.
- McLoone-Richards, Claire (2012): Say Nothing! How Pathology within Catholicism Created and Sustained the Institutional Abuse of Children in 20 th Century Ireland. In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (6), S. 394–404. DOI: 10.1002/car.2209.
- McManus, Michelle Ann; Almond, Louise (2014): Trends of indecent images of children and child sexual offences between 2005/2006 and 2012/2013 within the United Kingdom. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 142–155. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.893031.
- McManus, Michelle Ann; Long, Matthew L.; Alison, Laurence; Almond, Louise (2014): Factors associated with contact child sexual abuse in a sample of indecent image offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 368–384. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927009.
- McPhail, Ian V.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Fernandez, Yolanda M. (2014): Correlates of emotional congruence with children in sexual offenders against children. A test of theoretical models in an incarcerated sample. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (2), S. 336–346.
- Merdian, Hannah Lena; Curtis, Cate; Thakker, Jo; Wilson, Nick; Boer, Douglas Pieter (2013): The three dimensions of online child pornography offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 121–132. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.611898.
- Milam, Lisa J.; Nugent, William R. (2017): Children's Knowledge of Genital Anatomy and Its Relationship With Children's Use of the Word "Inside" During Questioning About Possible Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 23–39. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1269863.
- Miller, Susan L.; Hefner, M. Kristen; Leon, Chrysanthi S. (2014): Diffusing responsibility. A case study of child sexual abuse in popular discourse. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 37, S. 55–63. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.12.005.
- Misurell, Justin R.; Springer, Craig; Tryon, Warren W. (2011): Game-based cognitive-behavioral therapy (GB-CBT) group program for children who have experienced sexual abuse. A preliminary investigation. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 14–36. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.540000.
- Mitchell, Renae C.; Galupo, M. Paz (2015): Interest in child molestation among a community sample of men sexually attracted to children. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (2), S. 224–232. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1056263.
- Moore, Tim P.; McArthur, Morag; Noble-Carr, Debbie (2017): More a marathon than a hurdle. Towards children's informed consent in a study on safety. In: *Qualitative Research* 7 (2), 146879411770070. DOI: 10.1177/1468794117700708.
- Niehaus, Ashley F.; Jackson, Joan; Davies, Stephanie (2010): Sexual self-schemas of female child sexual abuse survivors. Relationships with risky sexual behavior and sexual assault in adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (6), S. 1359–1374. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9600-9.

- Nunes, Kevin L.; McPhail, Ian V.; Babchishin, Kelly M. (2012): Social anxiety and sexual offending against children. A cumulative meta-analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (3), S. 284–293. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.549243.
- Ó Ciardha, Caoilte; Gannon, Theresa A. (2011): The cognitive distortions of child molesters are in need of treatment. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 130–141. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.580573.
- O'Brien, Jennifer E.; White, Kevin; Wu, Qi; Killian-Farrell, Candace (2016): Mental Health and Behavioral Outcomes of Sexual and Nonsexual Child Maltreatment Among Child Welfare-Involved Youth. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 483–503. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1167801.
- O'Halloran, Elaine; Quayle, Ethel (2010): A content analysis of a "boy love" support forum. Revisiting Durkin and Bryant. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 71–85. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903395319.
- O'Leary, Patrick; Cooney, Carol; Easton, Scott D. (2010): The effect of severe child sexual abuse and disclosure on mental health during adulthood. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (3), S. 275–289. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003781251.
- O'Leary, Patrick J.; Gould, Nick (2010): Exploring Coping Factors amongst Men Who Were Sexually Abused in Childhood. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (8), S. 2669–2686.
- Oliver, Brian E.; Holmes, Laura (2015): Female Juvenile Sexual Offenders. Understanding Who They Are and Possible Steps That May Prevent Some Girls From Offending. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 698–715. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1058875.
- Paquette, Sarah; Cortoni, Franca; Proulx, Jean; Longpre, Nicholas (2014): An examination of implicit theories among francophone child molesters. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 182–196. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.798689.
- Parent, Sylvie; Bannon, Joëlle (2012): Sexual abuse in sport. What about boys? In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (2), S. 354–359. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2011.11.004.
- Parent, Sylvie; Demers, Guylaine (2011): Sexual abuse in sport. A model to prevent and protect athletes. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 120–133. DOI: 10.1002/car.1135.
- Parkhill, Michele R.; Pickett, Scott M. (2016): Difficulties in Emotion Regulation as a Mediator of the Relationship Between Child Sexual Abuse Victimization and Sexual Aggression Perpetration in Male College Students. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 674–685. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1205161.
- Pasura, Dominic; Jones, Adele D.; Hafner, James A. H.; Maharaj, Priya E.; Nathaniel-DeCaires, Karene; Johnson, Emmanuel Janagan (2013): Competing meanings of childhood and the social construction of child sexual abuse in the Caribbean. In: *Childhood* 20 (2), S. 200–214. DOI: 10.1177/0907568212462255.
- Pavlakakis, D. (2014): Reputation and the Sexual Abuse of Boys. Changing Norms in Late-Nineteenth-Century Britain. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (3), S. 325–346. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539512.
- Pearce, Jenny J. (2014): 'What's Going On' to Safeguard Children and Young People from Child Sexual Exploitation. A Review of Local Safeguarding Children Boards' Work to Protect Children from Sexual Exploitation. In: *Child Abuse Review* 23 (3), S. 159–170. DOI: 10.1002/car.2269.
- Pechtel, Pia; Evans, Ian M.; Podd, John V. (2011): Conceptualization of the complex outcomes of sexual abuse. A signal detection analysis. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (6), S. 677–694. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.627418.
- Perdahli Fis, Nese; Arman, Ayse; Kalaca, Sibel; Berkem, Meral (2010): Psychiatric evaluation of sexual abuse cases. A clinical representative sample from Turkey. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 32 (10), S. 1285–1290. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2010.04.020.
- Priebe, Gisela; Bäckström, Martin; Ainsaar, Mare (2010): Vulnerable adolescent participants' experience in surveys on sexuality and sexual abuse. Ethical aspects. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34 (6), S. 438–447.
- Rakow, Aaron; Smith, Daniel; Begle, Angela M.; Ayer, Lynsay (2011): The association of maternal depressive symptoms with child externalizing problems. The role of maternal support following child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 467–480. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.588189.
- Rassenhofer, Miriam; Zimmer, Andreas; Spröber, Nina; Fegert, Jörg M. (2015): Child sexual abuse in the Roman Catholic Church in Germany: Comparison of victim-impact data collected through church-sponsored and government-sponsored programs. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 40, S. 60–67.

- Reed-Gavish, Maya (2013): Cognitive abuse within the incestuous family as a factor in the development of dissociative identity disorder. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (4), S. 444–461. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.781093.
- Rellini, Alessandra H.; Elinson, Samantha; Janssen, Erick; Meston, Cindy M. (2012): The effect of pre-existing affect on the sexual responses of women with and without a history of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (2), S. 329–339. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9772-y.
- Rellini, Alessandra H.; Meston, Cindy M. (2011): Sexual self-schemas, sexual dysfunction, and the sexual responses of women with a history of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (2), S. 351–362. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9694-0.
- Rogers, Paul; Wczasek, Ryan; Davies, Michelle (2011): Attributions of blame in a hypothetical internet solicitation case. Roles of victim naivety, parental neglect and respondent gender. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 196–214. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003664869.
- Rumble, Lauren; Mungate, Taizivei; Chigiji, Handrick; Salama, Peter; Nolan, Anthony; Sammon, Elayn; Muwoni, Leon (2015): Childhood sexual violence in Zimbabwe: evidence for the epidemic against girls. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 60–66. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.04.015.
- Samms, Kimika M.; Cholewa, Blaire E. (2014): Exploring the context of child sexual abuse in Jamaica. Addressing the deficits. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 115–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870948.
- Sanberk, Ismail; Emen, Meltem; Kabakci, Duygu (2017): An Investigation of Socially Advantaged and Disadvantaged Turkish Mothers' Views About Training on Preventing Children From Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 288–307. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1292338.
- Schacht, Rebecca L.; George, William H.; Davis, Kelly Cue; Heiman, Julia R.; Norris, Jeanette; Stoner, Susan A.; Kajumulo, Kelly F. (2010): Sexual abuse history, alcohol intoxication, and women's sexual risk behavior. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (4), S. 898–906. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9544-0.
- Schaeffer, Paula; Leventhal, John M.; Gottsegen Asnes, Andrea (2011): Children's disclosures of sexual abuse. Learning from direct inquiry. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (5), S. 343–352.
- Seehuus, Martin; Clifton, Jessica; Rellini, Alessandra H. (2015): The Role of Family Environment and Multiple Forms of Childhood Abuse in the Shaping of Sexual Function and Satisfaction in Women. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (6), S. 1595–1608. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0364-5.
- Senn, Theresa E.; Carey, Michael P.; Coury-Doniger, Patricia (2012): Mediators of the relation between childhood sexual abuse and women's sexual risk behavior: a comparison of two theoretical frameworks. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (6), S. 1363–1377. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9897-z.
- Seto, Michael C.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2015): Viewing child pornography: prevalence and correlates in a representative community sample of young Swedish men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 67–79. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0244-4.
- Sevlever, Melina; Roth, Matthew E.; Gillis, Jennifer M. (2013): Sexual Abuse and Offending in Autism Spectrum Disorders. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 31 (2), S. 189–200. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9286-8.
- Sheehan, Valerie; Sullivan, Joe (2010): A qualitative analysis of child sex offenders involved in the manufacture of indecent images of children. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 143–167. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003698644.
- Shepard Paynea, Jennifer; Galvan, Frank H.; Williams, John K.; Prusinskie, Missy; Zhang, Muyu; Wyatt, Gail E.; Myers, Hector F. (2014): Impact of childhood sexual abuse on the emotions and behaviours of adult men from three ethnic groups in the USA. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 16 (3), S. 231–245.
- Sivis-Cetinkaya, Rahsan (2015): Turkish School Counselors' Experiences of Reporting Child Sexual Abuse: A Brief Report. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 908–921. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1084072.
- Smith, Mark; Woodiwiss, Jo (2017): Sexuality, Innocence and Agency in Narratives of Childhood Sexual Abuse. Implications for Social Work. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2173–2189. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw160.
- Soylu, Nusret; Alpaslan, Ahmet Hamdi; Ayaz, Muhammed; Esenyel, Selcen; Oruc, Mucahit (2013): Psychiatric disorders and characteristics of abuse in sexually abused children and adolescents with and without intellectual disabilities. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 34 (12), S. 4334–4342. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2013.09.010.

- Soylu, Nusret; Ayaz, Muhammed; Yüksel, Tuğb (2014): Early-married and sexually abused girls differ in their psychiatric outcomes. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (9), S. 1552–1559.
- Spraitz, Jason D.; Bowen, Kendra N.; Arthurs, Shavonne (2017): Neutralisation and sexual abuse. A study of monks from one Benedictine Abbey. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 195–206. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1204471.
- Stewart, Catherine Carolyn (2012): Beyond the call. Mothers of children with developmental disabilities responding to sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 701–727. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.722182.
- Stroebe, Sandra S.; O'Keefe, Stephen L.; Griffee, Karen; Kuo, Shih-Ya; Beard, Keith W.; Kommor, Martin J. (2013): Sister-sister incest. Data from an anonymous computerized survey. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (6), S. 695–719. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.811140.
- Toledo, Annik van; Seymour, Fred (2016): Caregiver Needs Following Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 403–414. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1156206.
- Tsagaris, George S.; Bach, Jesse E.; Cimino, Chrisa (2017): The characteristics of federal offenders sentenced for sexual exploitation of children within a large urban metropolitan region. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 181–194. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1307463.
- Turner, Daniel; Hoyer, Juergen; Schmidt, Alexander F.; Klein, Verena; Briken, Peer (2016): Risk Factors for Sexual Offending in Men Working With Children: A Community-Based Survey. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (7), S. 1851–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0746-y.
- Vaillancourt-Morel, Marie-Pier; Godbout, Natacha; Labadie, Chloé; Runtz, Marsha; Lussier, Yvan; Sabourin, Stéphane (2015): Avoidant and compulsive sexual behaviors in male and female survivors of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 40, S. 48–59.
- van Leeuwen, Matthijs L.; van Baaren, Rick B.; Chakhssi, Farid; Loonen, Marijke G. M.; Lippman, Maarten; Dijksterhuis, Ap (2013): Assessment of implicit sexual associations in non-incarcerated pedophiles. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1501–1507. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0094-0.
- Ventus, Daniel; Antfolk, Jan; Salo, Benny (2017): The associations between abuse characteristics in child sexual abuse. A meta-analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 167–180. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1318963.
- Wager, Nadia (2011): Researching Sexual Revictimisation. Associated Ethical and Methodological Issues, and Possible Solutions. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 158–172. DOI: 10.1002/car.1152.
- Walsh, Kerryann; Mathews, Ben; Rassafiani, Mehdi; Farrell, Ann; Butler, Des (2012): Understanding teachers' reporting of child sexual abuse. Measurement methods matter. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (9), S. 1937–1946. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.06.004.
- Weatherred, Jane Long (2017): Framing Child Sexual Abuse. A Longitudinal Content Analysis of Newspaper and Television Coverage, 2002–2012. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 3–22. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1257528.
- Weiler, Julia von; Haardt-Becker, Annette; Schulte, Simone (2010): Care and treatment of child victims of child pornographic exploitation (CPE) in Germany. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 211–222. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003759990.
- White, Jacquelyn; Buehler, Cheryl; Weymouth, Bridget B. (2014): Childhood attention deficit hyperactive disorder (ADHD) symptoms and adolescent female sexual victimisation. Mediating and moderating effects of risky behaviours. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 23–39. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.782429.
- Whittier, Nancy (2016): Where Are the Children? Theorizing the Missing Piece in Gendered Sexual Violence. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (1), S. 95–108. DOI: 10.1177/0891243215612412.
- Williams, Andy (2015): Child sexual victimisation. Ethnographic stories of stranger and acquaintance grooming. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 28–42. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.948085.
- Williams, Javonda; Nelson-Gardell, Debra; Coulborn Faller, Kathleen; Tishelman, Amy; Cordisco-Steele, Linda (2014): Is there a place for extended assessments in addressing child sexual abuse allegations? How sensitivity and specificity impact professional perspectives. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 179–197. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.871380.

- Williams, Matthew L.; Hudson, Kirsty (2013): Public perceptions of internet, familial and localised sexual grooming. Predicting perceived prevalence and safety. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 218–235. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.705341.
- Willis, Gwenda M.; Johnston, Lucy (2012): Planning helps. The impact of release planning on subsequent re-entry experiences of child sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 194–208. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.506576.
- Willis, Gwenda M.; Ward, Tony (2011): Striving for a good life. The good lives model applied to released child molesters. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (3), S. 290–303. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.505349.
- Wilson, Helen W.; Spatz Widom, Cathy (2010): Does Physical Abuse, Sexual Abuse, or Neglect in Childhood Increase the Likelihood of Same-sex Sexual Relationships and Cohabitation? A Prospective 30-year Follow-up. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (1), S. 63–74.
- Winters, Georgia M.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2016): I Knew It All Along. The Sexual Grooming Behaviors of Child Molesters and the Hindsight Bias. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 20–36. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1108945.
- Winters, Georgia M.; Kaylor, Leah E.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2017): Sexual offenders contacting children online. An examination of transcripts of sexual grooming. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 62–76. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1271146.
- Wissink, Inge B.; Vugt, Eveline van; Moonen, Xavier; Stams, Geert Jan; Hendriks, Jan (2015): Sexual abuse involving children with an intellectual disability (ID): a narrative review. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 36, S. 20–35. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2014.09.007.
- Wondie, Yemataw; Zemene, Workie; Reschke, Konrad; Schroder, Harry (2011): Early marriage, rape, child prostitution, and related factors determining the psychosocial effects severity of child sexual abuse in Ethiopia. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (3), S. 305–321. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.573458.
- Wonnacott, Jane (2013): Keeping children safe in nurseries. A focus on culture and context. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 32–45. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.747631.
- Wurtele, Sandy K. (2012): Preventing the sexual exploitation of minors in youth-serving organizations. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (12), S. 2442–2453. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.09.009.
- Wurtele, Sandy K.; Kenny, Maureen C. (2010): Partnering with parents to prevent childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (2), S. 130–152. DOI: 10.1002/car.1112.
- Xu, Yin; Zheng, Yong (2015): Prevalence of Childhood Sexual Abuse among Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual People. A Meta-Analysis. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 315–331. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006746.
- Yancey, C. Thresa; Hansen, David J.; Naufel, Karen Z. (2011): Heterogeneity of individuals with a history of child sexual abuse. An examination of children presenting to treatment. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (2), S. 111–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.554341.
- Yoder, Jamie R.; Hansen, Jesse; Ruch, Donna; Hodge, Ashleigh (2016): Effects of School-Based Risk and Protective Factors on Treatment Success Among Youth Adjudicated of a Sexual Crime. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 310–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1137668.
- Young, T. Lorraine; Riggs, Matt; Robinson, Jill L. (2011): Childhood sexual abuse severity reconsidered. A factor structure of CSA characteristics. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 373–395. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.590124.
- Zafar, Sadia; Ross, Erin C. (2013): Perceptions of childhood sexual abuse survivors. Development and initial validation of a new scale to measure stereotypes of adult survivors of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (3), S. 358–378. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.743955.
- Zhang, Wenjing; Chen, Jingqi; Feng, Yanan; Li, Jingyi; Zhao, Xiaoxia; Luo, Xiaoling (2013): Young children's knowledge and skills related to sexual abuse prevention. A pilot study in Beijing, China. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 623–630.
- Zinzow, Heidi; Seth, Puja; Jackson, Joan; Niehaus, Ashley; Fitzgerald, Monica (2010): Abuse and parental characteristics, attributions of blame, and psychological adjustment in adult survivors of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (1), S. 79–98. DOI: 10.1080/10538710903485989.

6.2.3. Vergewaltigung

Crosset, Todd W. (2016): Athletes, Sexual Assault, and Universities' Failure to Address Rape-Prone Subcultures on Campus. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): *The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response*. New York: Routledge, S. 74–93.

Quadara, Antonia (2014): The Everydayness of Rape: How Understanding Sexual Assault Perpetration Can Inform Prevention Efforts. In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): *Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 41–64.

Oliver, Kelly (2016): *Hunting Girls. Sexual Violence from The Hunger Games to Campus Rape*. New York: Columbia University Press.

Postmus, Judy L. (2013): *Sexual Violence and Abuse. An Encyclopedia of Prevention, Impacts, and Recovery*. Santa Barbara, Calif: Abc-Clio.

Henry, Nicola; Powell, Anastasia (Hg.) (2014): *Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

Beres, Melanie Ann (2014): Rethinking the concept of consent for anti-sexual violence activism and education. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 24 (3), S. 373–389. DOI: 10.1177/0959353514539652.

Brunnberg, Elinor; Lindén Boström, Margareta; Berglund, Mats (2012): Sexual force at sexual debut. Swedish adolescents with disabilities at higher risk than adolescents without disabilities. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (4), S. 285–295.

Chapleau, Kristine M.; Oswald, Debra L. (2010): Power, Sex, and Rape Myth Acceptance. Testing Two Models of Rape Proclivity. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 47 (1), S. 66–78.

Gray, Jacqueline M. (2014): What constitutes a "reasonable belief" in consent to sex? A thematic analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 337–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.900122.

Hlavka, H. R. (2014): Normalizing Sexual Violence. Young Women Account for Harassment and Abuse. In: *Gender & Society* 28 (3), S. 337–358. DOI: 10.1177/0891243214526468.

King, Laura L.; Hanrahan, Kathleen J. (2015): University student beliefs about sexual violence in prison. Rape myth acceptance, punitiveness, and empathy. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 179–193. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.820851.

Koo, Kelly H.; Stephens, Kari A.; Lindgren, Kristen P.; George, William H. (2012): Misogyny, acculturation, and ethnic identity: relation to rape-supportive attitudes in Asian American college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1005–1014. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9729-1.

Mallet, Pascal; Herbe, Dominique (2011): Does knowledge about sexuality prevent adolescents from developing rape-supportive beliefs? In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 48 (4), S. 372–380. DOI: 10.1080/00224491003794048.

Maxwell, Louise; Scott, Graham (2014): A review of the role of radical feminist theories in the understanding of rape myth acceptance. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 40–54. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.773384.

Mulumeoderhwa, Maroyi; Harris, Geoff (2015): Forced sex, rape and sexual exploitation. Attitudes and experiences of high school students in South Kivu, Democratic Republic of Congo. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 17 (3), S. 284–295.

Senn, Charlene Y. (2011): An imperfect feminist journey. Reflections on the process to develop an effective sexual assault resistance programme for university women. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (1), S. 121–137. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510386094.

Strömwall, Leif A.; Alfredsson, Helen; Landström, Sara (2013): Rape victim and perpetrator blame and the Just World hypothesis. The influence of victim gender and age. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 207–217. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.683455.

6.2.4. Übergriff

Carmody, Moira (2014): Young people, ethical sex and violence prevention. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 167–184.

- Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2016): Heterosexist Discourses. How Feminist Theory Shaped Campus Sexual Violence Policy. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): *The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response*. New York: Routledge, S. 33–52.
- Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2014): Critical Interventions. Addressing the Reality of LGBTQ Sexual Violence in Higher Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 426–438.
- Crosset, Todd W. (2016): Athletes, Sexual Assault, and Universities' Failure to Address Rape-Prone Subcultures on Campus. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): *The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response*. New York: Routledge, S. 74–93.
- Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): Bullying and sexual violence. Definition, prevalence, outcomes and moderators. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 31–44.
- Iverson, Susan V. (2016): A Policy Discourse Analysis of Sexual Assault Policies in Higher Education. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): *The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response*. New York: Routledge, S. 15–33.
- Judge, Abigail; Graw Leary, Mary (2014): From the Streets to Cyberspace. The Effects of Technology in the Commercial Sexual Exploitation of Children and Adolescents in the United States. In: Fabian M. Saleh, Albert Grudzinskas und Abigail Judge (Hg.): *Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press, S. 180–214.
- Luschen, Kristen V. (2014): Survival, Protection, and Forgiveness. Examining Gendered Violence and Care in the Hunger Games Trilogy. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 133–146.
- Robinson, Kerry H.; Davies, Cristyn; Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): Conclusions: Rethinking School Violence. Implications for Theory, Policy and Practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 184–195.
- Drobac, Jennifer Ann (2016): *Sexual exploitation of teenagers. Adolescent development, discrimination, and consent law*. Chicago, London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Oliver, Kelly (2016): *Hunting Girls. Sexual Violence from The Hunger Games to Campus Rape*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Postmus, Judy L. (2013): *Sexual Violence and Abuse. An Encyclopedia of Prevention, Impacts, and Recovery*. Santa Barbara, Calif: Abc-Clío.
- Shariff, Shaheen (2015): *Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Abajobir, Amanuel Alemu; Kisely, Steve; Williams, Gail Marilyn; Clavarino, Alexandra Marie; Najman, Jakob Moses (2017): Substantiated Childhood Maltreatment and Intimate Partner Violence Victimization in Young Adulthood: A Birth Cohort Study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 165–179. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0558-3.
- Allardyce, Stuart; Yates, Peter Michael (2013): Assessing Risk of Victim Crossover with Children and Young People who display Harmful Sexual Behaviours. In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (4), S. 255–267. DOI: 10.1002/car.2277.
- Alleyne, Binta; Coleman-Cowger, Victoria H.; Crown, Laurel; Gibbons, Maya A.; Vines, Linda Nicole (2011): The effects of dating violence, substance use and risky sexual behavior among a diverse sample of Illinois youth. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 11–18. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.03.006.
- Almond, Tracy Jane (2014): Working with children and young people with harmful sexual behaviours. Exploring impact on practitioners and sources of support. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 333–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836576.
- Atkinson, Chris; Newton, David (2010): Online behaviours of adolescents. Victims, perpetrators and Web 2.0. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 107–120. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903337683.
- Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Fava, Nicole M. (2014): What puts “At-Risk Girls” at risk? Sexual vulnerability and social inequality in the lives of girls in the child welfare system. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 116–125. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0142-5.

- Beerthuisen, Marinus G. C. J.; Brugman, Daniel (2012): Sexually abusive youths' moral reasoning on sex. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 125–135. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.519126.
- Beier, Klaus M.; Oezdemir, Umut C.; Schlinzig, Eliza; Groll, Anna; Hupp, Elena; Hellenschmidt, Tobias (2016): "Just dreaming of them". The Berlin Project for Primary Prevention of Child Sexual Abuse by Juveniles (PPJ). In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 52, S. 1–10.
- Bengtsson, T. T. (2016): Performing Hypermasculinity. Experiences with Confined Young Offenders. In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (4), S. 410–428. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15595083.
- Bower, Andrew R.; Nishina, Adrienne; Witkow, Melissa R.; Bellmore, Amy (2015): Nice Guys and Gals Finish Last? Not in Early Adolescence When Empathic, Accepted, and Popular Peers are Desirable. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (12), S. 2275–2288. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0346-5.
- Brunnberg, Elinor; Lindén Boström, Margareta; Berglund, Mats (2012): Sexual force at sexual debut. Swedish adolescents with disabilities at higher risk than adolescents without disabilities. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (4), S. 285–295.
- Caiozzo, Christina N.; Houston, Jessica; Grych, John (2016): Predicting aggression in late adolescent romantic relationships. A short-term longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 53, S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.10.012.
- Collibee, Charlene; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Chronic and Acute Relational Risk Factors for Dating Aggression in Adolescence and Young Adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (4), S. 763–776. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0427-0.
- Dank, Meredith; Lachman, Pamela; Zweig, Janine M.; Yahner, Jennifer (2014): Dating violence experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (5), S. 846–857. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9975-8.
- Das, Aniruddha; Otis, Nicholas (2016): Sexual Contact in Childhood, Revictimization, and Lifetime Sexual and Psychological Outcomes. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1117–1131. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0620-3.
- Doel, Mark; Allmark, Peter; Conway, Paul; Cowburn, Malcolm; Flynn, Margaret; Nelson, Pete; Tod, Angela (2010): Professional Boundaries. Crossing a Line or Entering the Shadows? In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (6), S. 1866–1889.
- Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2012): Young women's adolescent experiences of oral sex. Relation of age of initiation to sexual motivation, sexual coercion, and psychological functioning. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (5), S. 1191–1201. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.03.010.
- Felson, Richard B.; Cundiff, Patrick R. (2014): Sexual assault as a crime against young people. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 273–284. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0127-8.
- Firmin, Carlene; Warrington, Camille; Pearce, Jenny (2017): Sexual Exploitation and Its Impact on Developing Sexualities and Sexual Relationships. The Need for Contextual Social Work Interventions. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2318–2337. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw134.
- Fitzpatrick, Kevin M.; Dulin, Akilah; Piko, Bettina (2010): Bullying and depressive symptomatology among low-income, African-American youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 634–645. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9426-8.
- Foshee, Vangie A.; Benefield, Thad; Dixon, Kimberly S.; Chang, Ling-Yin; Senkomago, Virginia; Ennett, Susan T. et al. (2015): The effects of moms and teens for safe dates: a dating abuse prevention program for adolescents exposed to domestic violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 995–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0272-6.
- Gill, Michael (2010): Rethinking sexual abuse, questions of consent, and intellectual disability. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (3), S. 201–213. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0019-9.
- Gilliam, Melissa; Jagoda, Patrick; Jaworski, Erin; Hebert, Luciana E.; Lyman, Phoebe; Wilson, M. Claire (2015): "Because if we don't talk about it, how are we going to prevent it?". Lucidity, a narrative-based digital game about sexual violence. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (4), S. 391–404. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1123147.
- Hampshire, Kate; Porter, Gina; Mashiri, Mac; Maponya, Goodhope; Dube, Siphon (2011): Proposing love on the way to school. Mobility, sexuality and youth transitions in South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (2), S. 217–231. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.522255.

Harris, Taylor; Rice, Eric; Rhoades, Harmony; Winetrobe, Hailey; Wenzel, Suzanne (2017): Gender Differences in the Path From Sexual Victimization to HIV Risk Behavior Among Homeless Youth. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 334–351. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1287146.

Hawkes, Colin (2011): Description of a UK study of onset of sexually harmful behaviour before the age of ten years in boys referred to a specialist assessment and treatment service. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 82–101. DOI: 10.1002/car.1133.

Hay, Carter; Meldrum, Ryan (2010): Bullying victimization and adolescent self-harm: testing hypotheses from general strain theory. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (5), S. 446–459. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9502-0.

Heerde, Jessica A.; Scholes-Balog, Kirsty E.; Hemphill, Sheryl A. (2015): Associations between youth homelessness, sexual offenses, sexual victimization, and sexual risk behaviors: a systematic literature review. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 181–212. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0375-2.

Houser, John J.; Mayeux, Lara; Cross, Cassandra (2015): Peer status and aggression as predictors of dating popularity in adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 683–695. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0174-z.

Johnston, Lisa G.; Mon, Myo Myo; Steinhaus, Mara; Sass, Justine (2017): Correlates of Forced Sex Among Young Men Who Have Sex With Men in Yangon and Monywa, Myanmar. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 1001–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0761-z.

Jones, Sara; Joyal, Christian C.; Cisler, Josh M.; Bai, Shasha (2017): Exploring Emotion Regulation in Juveniles Who Have Sexually Offended. An fMRI Study. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 40–57. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1259280.

Joyal, Christian C.; Carpentier, Julie; Martin, Caroline (2016): Discriminant factors for adolescent sexual offending. On the usefulness of considering both victim age and sibling incest. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 54, S. 10–22.

Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D.; Sanders, Stephanie A.; Dennis, Barbara; Reece, Michael (2014): Gender Differences in Heterosexual College Students' Conceptualizations and Indicators of Sexual Consent. Implications for Contemporary Sexual Assault Prevention Education. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (8), S. 904–916.

Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2010): Sexually coercive behavior in male youth: population survey of general and specific risk factors. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1161–1169. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9572-9.

Lambine, Mackenzie E. (2012): Unsafe in the Ivory Tower. The sexual victimization of college women. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (3), S. 375–376. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.711657.

Lehrer, Jocelyn A.; Lehrer, Evelyn L.; Koss, Mary P. (2013): Unwanted sexual experiences in young men: evidence from a survey of university students in Chile. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (2), S. 213–223. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0004-x.

Leonard, Marcella Mary (2010): "I did what I was directed to do but he didn't touch me". The impact of being a victim of internet offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 249–256. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003690526.

Lund, Emily M.; Hammond, Marilyn (2014): Single-Session Intervention for Abuse Awareness Among People with Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 99–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9335-3.

Makin-Byrd, Kerry; Bierman, Karen L. (2013): Individual and family predictors of the perpetration of dating violence and victimization in late adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 536–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9810-7.

Martin-Storey, Alexa (2015): Prevalence of dating violence among sexual minority youth: variation across gender, sexual minority identity and gender of sexual partners. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 211–224. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0089-0.

Martin-Storey, Alexa; Fromme, Kim (2016): Trajectories of dating violence. Differences by sexual minority status and gender. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 28–37. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.02.008.

McCartan, Fiona Mairead; Law, Heather; Murphy, Maeve; Bailey, Susan (2011): Child and adolescent females who present with sexually abusive behaviours. A 10-year UK prevalence study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 4–14. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.488302.

- Miller, Shari; Williams, Jason; Cutbush, Stacey; Gibbs, Deborah; Clinton-Sherrod, Monique; Jones, Sarah (2013): Dating violence, bullying, and sexual harassment: longitudinal profiles and transitions over time. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 607–618. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9914-8.
- Morgan, Wendy; Gilchrist, Elizabeth (2010): Risk assessment with intimate partner sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (3), S. 361–372. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.502976.
- Muehlenhard, Charlene L.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D. (2016): The Complexities of Sexual Consent Among College Students. A Conceptual and Empirical Review. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (4-5), S. 1–31.
- Muhanguzi, Florence Kyoheirwe (2011): Gender and sexual vulnerability of young women in Africa. Experiences of young girls in secondary schools in Uganda. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 713–725. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.571290.
- Mulumeoderhwa, Maroyi; Harris, Geoff (2015): Forced sex, rape and sexual exploitation. Attitudes and experiences of high school students in South Kivu, Democratic Republic of Congo. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 17 (3), S. 284–295.
- Niehaus, Ashley F.; Jackson, Joan; Davies, Stephanie (2010): Sexual self-schemas of female child sexual abuse survivors. Relationships with risky sexual behavior and sexual assault in adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (6), S. 1359–1374. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9600-9.
- Nishina, Adrienne (2012): Microcontextual characteristics of peer victimization experiences and adolescents' daily well-being. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 191–201. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9669-z.
- Novak, Jamie; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Partner Violence During Adolescence and Young Adulthood: Individual and Relationship Level Risk Factors. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (9), S. 1849–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0484-4.
- Orpinas, Pamela; Hsieh, Hsien-Lin; Song, Xiao; Holland, Kristin; Nahapetyan, Lusine (2013): Trajectories of physical dating violence from middle to high school: association with relationship quality and acceptability of aggression. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 551–565. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9881-5.
- Park, Jisun; Kim, Seunghee (2016): Group size does matter. Differences among sexual assaults committed by lone, double, and groups of three or more perpetrators. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 342–354. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1144801.
- Parkhill, Michele R.; Pickett, Scott M. (2016): Difficulties in Emotion Regulation as a Mediator of the Relationship Between Child Sexual Abuse Victimization and Sexual Aggression Perpetration in Male College Students. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 674–685. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1205161.
- Peacock, Dean; Barker, Gary (2014): Working with Men and Boys to Prevent Gender-based Violence. Principles, Lessons Learned, and Ways Forward. In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (5), S. 578–599. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14558240.
- Piccigallo, Jaqueline R.; Lilley, Terry G.; Miller, Susan L. (2012): "It's Cool to Care about Sexual Violence". Men's Experiences with Sexual Assault Prevention. In: *Men and Masculinities* 15 (5), S. 507–525. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X12458590.
- Pritchard, Duncan; Graham, Nicola; Penney, Heather; Owen, Gwynne; Peters, Sandra; Mace, F. Charles (2016): Multi-component behavioural intervention reduces harmful sexual behaviour in a 17-year-old male with autism spectrum disorder. A case study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 368–378. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1130269.
- Pullman, Lesleigh E.; Seto, Michael C. (2012): Assessment and treatment of adolescent sexual offenders. Implications of recent research on generalist versus specialist explanations. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (3), S. 203–209.
- Rasmussen, Lucinda A. (2013): Young people who sexually abuse. A historical perspective and future directions. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (1), S. 119–141. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.744646.
- Rasmussen, Lucinda A.; Lev-Wiesel, Rachel; Eisikovits, Zvi (2013): Current perspectives on children and youth who sexually abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (1), S. 1–8. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.744644.

- Reyes, H. Luz McNaughton; Foshee, Vangie A.; Niolon, Phyllis Holditch; Reidy, Dennis E.; Hall, Jeffrey E. (2016): Gender Role Attitudes and Male Adolescent Dating Violence Perpetration: Normative Beliefs as Moderators. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 350–360. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0278-0.
- Rice, Eric; Winetrobe, Hailey; Holloway, Ian W.; Montoya, Jorge; Plant, Aaron; Kordic, Timothy (2015): Cell phone internet access, online sexual solicitation, partner seeking, and sexual risk behavior among adolescents. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 755–763. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0366-3.
- Sabina, Chiara; Cuevas, Carlos A.; Cotignola-Pickens, Heather M. (2016): Longitudinal dating violence victimization among Latino teens: Rates, risk factors, and cultural influences. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 47, S. 5–15. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.11.003.
- Schnurr, Melissa P.; Lohman, Brenda J. (2013): The impact of collective efficacy on risks for adolescents' perpetration of dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 518–535. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9909-5.
- Schönbucher, Verena; Maier, Thomas; Mohler-Kuo, Meichun; Schnyder, Ulrich; Landolt, Markus A. (2014): Adolescent perspectives on social support received in the aftermath of sexual abuse: a qualitative study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (3), S. 571–586. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0230-x.
- Senn, Charlene Y. (2011): An imperfect feminist journey. Reflections on the process to develop an effective sexual assault resistance programme for university women. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (1), S. 121–137. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510386094.
- Slotboom, Anne-Marie; Hendriks, Jan; Verbruggen, Janna (2011): Contrasting adolescent female and male sexual aggression. A self-report study on prevalence and predictors of sexual aggression. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 15–33. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.544413.
- Smith, Connie; Allardyce, Stuart; Hackett, Simon; Bradbury-Jones, Caroline; Lazenbatt, Anne; Taylor, Julie (2014): Practice and policy in the UK with children and young people who display harmful sexual behaviours. An analysis and critical review. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 267–280. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927010.
- Smith-Darden, Joanne P.; Reidy, Dennis E.; Kernsmith, Poco D. (2016): Adolescent stalking and risk of violence. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 52, S. 191–200. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.08.005.
- Sommer, Marni; Likindikoki, Samuel; Kaaya, Sylvia (2015): "Bend a fish when the fish is not yet dry": adolescent boys' perceptions of sexual risk in Tanzania. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 583–595. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0406-z.
- Stevens, Peter; Hutchin, Katie; French, Lesley; Craissati, Jackie (2013): Developmental and offence-related characteristics of different types of adolescent sex offender. A community sample. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 138–157. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.645889.
- Sullivan, Terri N.; Garthe, Rachel C.; Goncy, Elizabeth A.; Carlson, Megan M.; Behrhorst, Kathryn L. (2017): Longitudinal Relations between Beliefs Supporting Aggression, Anger Regulation, and Dating Aggression among Early Adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 982–994. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0569-0.
- Temple, Jeff R.; Choi, Hye Jeong; Brem, Meagan; Wolford-Clevenger, Caitlin; Stuart, Gregory L.; Peskin, Melissa Fleschler; Elmquist, JoAnna (2016): The Temporal Association Between Traditional and Cyber Dating Abuse Among Adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 340–349. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0380-3.
- Thrane, Lisa E.; Chen, Xiaojin (2012): Impact of running away on girls' pregnancy. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (2), S. 443–449. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.07.011.
- Tidefors, Inga; Arvidsson, Hans; Rudolfsson, Lisa (2012): Agreement between ratings from self-rating scales and assessments by treatment staff concerning a group of adolescent males who have sexually offended. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 136–148. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.528845.
- van Ouytsel, Joris; Ponnet, Koen; Walrave, Michel (2017): The associations of adolescents' dating violence victimization, well-being and engagement in risk behaviors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 66–71. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.005.
- Venable, Victoria M.; Guada, Joseph (2014): Culturally competent practice with African American juvenile sex offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (3), S. 229–246. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.888122.

- Vézina, Johanne; Hébert, Martine; Poulin, François; Lavoie, Francine; Vitaro, Frank; Tremblay, Richard E. (2011): Risky lifestyle as a mediator of the relationship between deviant peer affiliation and dating violence victimization among adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 814–824. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9602-x.
- Vries, Hein de; Eggers, Sander Matthijs; Jinabhai, Champak; Meyer-Weitz, Anna; Sathiparsad, Reshma; Taylor, Myra (2014): Adolescents' beliefs about forced sex in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (6), S. 1087–1095. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0280-8.
- Worling, James (2012): The assessment and treatment of deviant sexual arousal with adolescents who have offended sexually. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 36–63. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.630152.
- Wright, Michelle F. (2015): Cyber aggression within adolescents' romantic relationships: linkages to parental and partner attachment. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 37–47. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0147-2.
- Yates, Peter; Allardyce, Stuart; MacQueen, Sarah (2012): Children who display harmful sexual behaviour. Assessing the risks of boys abusing at home, in the community or across both settings. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 23–35. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.634527.
- Ybarra, Michele L.; Espelage, Dorothy L.; Langhinrichsen-Rohling, Jennifer; Korchmaros, Josephine D.; Boyd, Danah (2016): Lifetime Prevalence Rates and Overlap of Physical, Psychological, and Sexual Dating Abuse Perpetration and Victimization in a National Sample of Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1083–1099. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0748-9.
- Ybarra, Michele L.; Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Palmer, Neal A.; Reisner, Sari L. (2015): Online social support as a buffer against online and offline peer and sexual victimization among U.S. LGBT and non-LGBT youth. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 39, S. 123–136.
- Yoder, Jamie; Ruch, Donna (2015): A qualitative investigation of treatment components for families of youth who have sexually offended. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (2), S. 192–205. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1107141.
- Zweig, Janine M.; Dank, Meredith; Yahner, Jennifer; Lachman, Pamela (2013): The rate of cyber dating abuse among teens and how it relates to other forms of teen dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1063–1077. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9922-8.

6.2.5. Diskriminierung

- Airton, Lee (2014): Hatred Haunting Hallways. Teacher Education and the Badness of Homophobia(s). In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 387–399.
- Anderson, Eric (2013): Masculinity and homophobia in high school and college sports. A personal journey from coach to researcher. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 120–131.
- Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2014): Critical Interventions. Addressing the Reality of LGBTQ Sexual Violence in Higher Education. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 426–438.
- Davies, Cristyn; McInnes, David (2014): Speaking violence. Homophobia and the production of injurious speech in schooling cultures. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 131–148.
- Desjardins, Michel (2012): The Sexualized Body of the Child. Parents and the Politics of "Voluntary" Sterilization of People Labeled Intellectually Disabled. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 69–88.
- DeVita, James M.; Daniel Anders, Allison (2014): Multiple Targeted Identities. Intersectionality and the Lived Experiences of Black Gay Males. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 464–478.
- Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): Bullying and sexual violence. Definition, prevalence, outcomes and moderators. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 31–44.

- Lugg, Catherine A. (2012): The Religious Right and Public Education. The Paranoid Politics of Homophobia. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 61–72.
- McCormack, Mark (2013): Mapping the boundaries of homophobic language in bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 91–104.
- McCoy, Sheltreese D. (2014): Some of Us Are Brave. A Review of the Research on the Experience of Black LGBT Professors in Colleges and Universities in the United States. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 439–452.
- McCready, Lance T. (2014): The African Dance Program. "Where is the Love?". In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), 342–356.
- Ouer, Freeden (2014): It's Not How Regular Boys Are Supposed to Act. The Nonnormative Sexual Practices of Black Boys in All-Male Public Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 357–369.
- Pendleton Jiménez, Karleen (2014): Off the Script. A Study of Techniques for Uncovering Gender-Bending Truths in the Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 257–271.
- Rajander, Silja; Sopath, Phal (2012): Drama Performances Address Stigma, Discrimination of MSM and HIV/AIDS Prevention. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 281–283.
- Roth, Jillian R.; Robinson, Lea; O'Bryant, Camille; Griffin, Pat (2014): 3 to 1. Four Women Navigating the Intersections of Racism, Sexism, Homophobia, and Heterosexism in Intercollegiate Sport. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 453–463.
- Larremore, April (2016): Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom.
- Clark, Caroline T. (2010): Preparing LGBTQ-allies and combating homophobia in a U.S. teacher education program. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (3), S. 704–713. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.10.006.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G.M. (2015): Understanding teachers' responses to enactments of sexual and gender stigma at school. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 48, S. 34–43. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.02.002.
- DePalma, Renée; Atkinson, Elizabeth (2010): The nature of institutional heteronormativity in primary schools and practice-based responses. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (8), S. 1669–1676. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.06.018.
- Dessel, Adrienne B.; Kulick, Alex; Wernick, Laura J.; Sullivan, Daniel (2017): The importance of teacher support. Differential impacts by gender and sexuality. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 136–144. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.002.
- Fair, Brian (2011): Constructing Masculinity through Penetration Discourse. The Intersection of Misogyny and Homophobia in High School Wrestling. In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 491–504. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10375936.
- Gerouki, Margarita (2010): The boy who was drawing princesses. Primary teachers' accounts of children's non-conforming behaviours. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 335–348. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515092.
- Goldbach, Jeremy T.; Gibbs, Jeremy J. (2017): A developmentally informed adaptation of minority stress for sexual minority adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 36–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.007.
- Hafford-Letchfield, Trish; Cocker, Christine; Ryan, Peter; Melonowska, Justyna (2017): Rights through Alliances. Findings from a European Project Tackling Homophobic and Transphobic Bullying in Schools through the Engagement of Families and Young People. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2338–2356. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw104.

- Hooghe, Marc (2011): The impact of gendered friendship patterns on the prevalence of homophobia among Belgian late adolescents. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (3), S. 543–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9635-y.
- Lea, Toby; Wit, John de; Reynolds, Robert (2014): Minority stress in lesbian, gay, and bisexual young adults in Australia: associations with psychological distress, suicidality, and substance use. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1571–1578. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0266-6.
- Lund, Emily M.; Hammond, Marilyn (2014): Single-Session Intervention for Abuse Awareness Among People with Developmental Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 99–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9335-3.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa; Crosnoe, Robert (2012): Sexual minority status, peer harassment, and adolescent depression. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 1001–1011. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.02.006.
- Mul, Nick J.; McKenzie, Cameron; Khan, Maryam (2017): Recognition and Legitimation of Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity (SOGI) at the UN. A Critical Systemic Analysis. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2245–2262. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw139.
- Mustanski, Brian; Liu, Richard T. (2013): A longitudinal study of predictors of suicide attempts among lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (3), S. 437–448. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0013-9.
- Ollis, Debbie (2010): 'I haven't changed bigots but ...'. Reflections on the impact of teacher professional learning in sexuality education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 217–230. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666523.
- Pearson, Jennifer; Wilkinson, Lindsey (2013): Family relationships and adolescent well-being: are families equally protective for same-sex attracted youth? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 376–393. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9865-5.
- Porta, Carolyn M.; Gower, Amy L.; Mehus, Christopher J.; Yu, Xiaohui; Saewyc, Elizabeth M.; Eisenberg, Marla E. (2017): "Kicked out". LGBTQ youths' bathroom experiences and preferences. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 107–112. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.005.
- Preston, Marilyn J. (2015): 'They're just not mature right now': teachers' complicated perceptions of gender and anti-queer bullying. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 22–34. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1019665.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2012): Popular culture as emotional provocation. The material enactment of queer pedagogies in a high school classroom. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 511–522. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627728.
- Rosario, Margaret; Schrimshaw, Eric W.; Hunter, Joyce (2012): Homelessness among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth: implications for subsequent internalizing and externalizing symptoms. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 544–560. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9681-3.
- Sanjakdar, Fida (2013): Educating for sexual difference? Muslim teachers' conversations about homosexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (1), S. 16–29. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634154.
- Sauntson, Helen (2013): Sexual diversity and illocutionary silencing in the English National Curriculum. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 395–408. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.745809.
- Shelton, Stephanie Anne; Barnes, Meghan E. (2016): "Racism just isn't an issue anymore". Preservice teachers' resistances to the intersections of sexuality and race. In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 55, S. 165–174. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2016.01.008.
- Sterzing, Paul R.; Ratliff, G. Allen; Gartner, Rachel E.; McGeough, Briana L.; Johnson, Kelly C. (2017): Social Ecological Correlates of Polyvictimization among a National Sample of Transgender, Genderqueer, and Cisgender Sexual Minority Adolescents. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 67, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.02.017.
- Svendsen, Stine Helena Bang (2012): Elusive sex acts. Pleasure and politics in Norwegian sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (4), S. 397–410. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.677209.
- Swann, Gregory; Minshew, Reese; Newcomb, Michael E.; Mustanski, Brian (2016): Validation of the Sexual Orientation Microaggression Inventory in Two Diverse Samples of LGBTQ Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (6), S. 1289–1298. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0718-2.

Toomey, Russell B.; McGuire, Jenifer K.; Russell, Stephen T. (2012): Heteronormativity, school climates, and perceived safety for gender nonconforming peers. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 187–196. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.03.001.

Turner, George W.; Crane, Betsy (2017): Sexually Silenced No More, Adults with Learning Disabilities Speak Up. A Call to Action for Social Work to Frame Sexual Voice as a Social Justice Issue. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2300–2317. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw133.

Wernick, Laura J.; Kulick, Alex; Inglehart, Marita H. (2013): Factors predicting student intervention when witnessing anti-LGBTQ harassment. The influence of peers, teachers, and climate. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (2), S. 296–301. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.11.003.

Willis, Paul; Ward, Nicki; Fish, Julie (2011): Searching for LGBT Carers. Mapping a Research Agenda in Social Work and Social Care. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 41 (7), S. 1304–1320.

6.3. Negative Folgen

Cowie, Helen (2013): The immediate and long-term effects of bullying. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 10–18.

Postmus, Judy L. (2013): *Sexual Violence and Abuse. An Encyclopedia of Prevention, Impacts, and Recovery*. Santa Barbara, Calif: Abc-Clio.

Abajobir, Amanuel Alemu; Kisely, Steve; Williams, Gail Marilyn; Clavarino, Alexandra Marie; Najman, Jakob Moses (2017): Substantiated Childhood Maltreatment and Intimate Partner Violence Victimization in Young Adulthood: A Birth Cohort Study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 165–179. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0558-3.

Alix, Stephanie; Cossette, Louise; Hebert, Martine; Cyr, Mireille; Frappier, Jean-Yves (2017): Posttraumatic Stress Disorder and Suicidal Ideation Among Sexually Abused Adolescent Girls. The Mediating Role of Shame. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (2), S. 158–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1280577.

Benuto, Lorraine T.; O'Donohue, William (2015): Treatment of the Sexually Abused Child. Review and Synthesis of Recent Meta-Analyses. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 56, S. 52–60. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.06.009.

Bird, Elizabeth R.; Seehuus, Martin; Clifton, Jessica; Rellini, Alessandra H. (2014): Dissociation during sex and sexual arousal in women with and without a history of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (5), S. 953–964. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0191-0.

Braje, Sopagna Eap; Eddy, J. Mark; Hall, Gordon C. N. (2016): A Comparison of Two Models of Risky Sexual Behavior During Late Adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (1), S. 73–83. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0523-3.

Capella, Claudia; Lama, Ximena; Rodriguez, Loreto; Aguila, Daniela; Beiza, Gretchen; Dussert, Denise; Gutierrez, Carolina (2016): Winning a Race. Narratives of Healing and Psychotherapy in Children and Adolescents Who Have Been Sexually Abused. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 73–92. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088915.

D'Alton, Paul; Guilfoyle, Michael; Randall, Patrick (2013): Roman Catholic Clergy who have sexually abused children: Their perceptions of their developmental experience. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 698–702.

Das, Aniruddha; Otis, Nicholas (2016): Sexual Contact in Childhood, Revictimization, and Lifetime Sexual and Psychological Outcomes. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1117–1131. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0620-3.

Das, Aniruddha; Otis, Nicholas (2016): Sexual Contact in Childhood, Revictimization, and Lifetime Sexual and Psychological Outcomes. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1117–1131.

Delft, Ivanka van; Finkenauer, Catrin; Schipper, J. Clasiën de; Lamers-Winkelmann, Francien; Visser, Margreet M. (2015): The mediating role of secrecy in the development of psychopathology in sexually abused children. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 27–36.

Dolan, Mairead; Whitworth, Helen (2013): Childhood sexual abuse, adult psychiatric morbidity, and criminal outcomes in women assessed by medium secure forensic service. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (2), S. 191–208. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.751951.

Elklit, Ask; Christiansen, Dorte M.; Palic, Sabina; Karsberg, Sidsel; Eriksen, Sara Bek (2014): Impact of traumatic events on posttraumatic stress disorder among Danish survivors of sexual abuse in childhood. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (8), S. 918–934. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.964440.

- Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2013): Trauma-informed sexuality education. Recognising the rights and resilience of youth. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 383–394. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.745808.
- Firmin, Carlene; Warrington, Camille; Pearce, Jenny (2017): Sexual Exploitation and Its Impact on Developing Sexualities and Sexual Relationships. The Need for Contextual Social Work Interventions. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2318–2337. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw134.
- Fitzpatrick, Mark; Carr, Alan; Dooley, Barbara; Flanagan-Howard, Roisín; Flanagan, Edel; Tierney, Kevin et al. (2010): Profiles of adult survivors of severe sexual, physical and emotional institutional abuse in Ireland. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (6), S. 387–404. DOI: 10.1002/car.1083.
- Forsman, Mats; Johansson, Ada; Santtila, Pekka; Sandnabba, Kenneth; Långström, Niklas (2015): Sexually Coercive Behavior Following Childhood Maltreatment. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 149–156.
- Fresno, Andres; Spencer, Rosario; Ramos, Nadia; Pierrehumbert, Blaise (2014): The effect of sexual abuse on children's attachment representations in Chile. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 128–145. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870949.
- Gokten, Emel Sari; Saday Duman, Nagihan (2016): Factors influencing the development of psychiatric disorders in the victims of sexual abuse. A study on Turkish children. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 69, S. 49–55. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2016.07.022.
- Goldbach, Jeremy T.; Gibbs, Jeremy J. (2017): A developmentally informed adaptation of minority stress for sexual minority adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 36–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.007.
- Harris, Taylor; Rice, Eric; Rhoades, Harmony; Winetrobe, Hailey; Wenzel, Suzanne (2017): Gender Differences in the Path From Sexual Victimization to HIV Risk Behavior Among Homeless Youth. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 334–351. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1287146.
- Hay, Carter; Meldrum, Ryan (2010): Bullying victimization and adolescent self-harm: testing hypotheses from general strain theory. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (5), S. 446–459. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9502-0.
- Hidalgo, Marco A.; Kuhns, Lisa M.; Kwon, Soyang; Mustanski, Brian; Garofalo, Robert (2015): The impact of childhood gender expression on childhood sexual abuse and psychopathology among young men who have sex with men. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 103–112.
- Jennings, Wesley G.; Richards, Tara N.; Tomsich, Elizabeth; Gover, Angela R. (2015): Investigating the Role of Child Sexual Abuse in Intimate Partner Violence Victimization and Perpetration in Young Adulthood From a Propensity Score Matching Approach. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 659–681. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1057665.
- Kim, Tae Kyung; Choi, Soul; Shin, Yee Jin (2011): Psychosocial factors influencing competency of children's statements on sexual trauma. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (3), S. 173–179.
- Kingston, Drew A.; Graham, Franklyn J.; Knight, Raymond A. (2017): Relations Between Self-Reported Adverse Events in Childhood and Hypersexuality in Adult Male Sexual Offenders. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 707–720. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0873-5.
- Kisanga, Felix; Nystrom, Lennarth; Hogan, Nora; Emmelin, Maria (2011): Child sexual abuse. Community concerns in urban Tanzania. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (2), S. 196–217. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.555356.
- Krahé, Barbara; Berger, Anja (2017): Gendered pathways from child sexual abuse to sexual aggression victimization and perpetration in adolescence and young adulthood. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 261–272. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.10.004.
- Krause-Parello, Cheryl A.; Gulick, Elsie E. (2015): Forensic Interviews for Child Sexual Abuse Allegations. An Investigation into the Effects of Animal-Assisted Intervention on Stress Biomarkers. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 873–886. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088916.
- Krayer, Anne; Seddon, Diane; Robinson, Catherine A.; Gwilym, Hefin (2015): The influence of child sexual abuse on the self from adult narrative perspectives. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (2), S. 135–151. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1001473.
- Langevin, Rachel; Hébert, Martine; Cossette, Louise (2015): Emotion regulation as a mediator of the relation between sexual abuse and behavior problems in preschoolers. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 16–26.

- Lea, Toby; Wit, John de; Reynolds, Robert (2014): Minority stress in lesbian, gay, and bisexual young adults in Australia: associations with psychological distress, suicidality, and substance use. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1571–1578. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0266-6.
- Leonard, Marcella Mary (2010): "I did what I was directed to do but he didn't touch me". The impact of being a victim of internet offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 249–256. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003690526.
- Lev-Wiesel, Rachel; Markus, Liora (2013): Perception vs. circumstances of the child sexual abuse event in relation to depression and post-traumatic stress symptomatology. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 519–533. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800932.
- Liotta, Lindsay; Springer, Craig; Misurell, Justin R.; Block-Lerner, Jennifer; Brandwein, David (2015): Group treatment for child sexual abuse. Treatment referral and therapeutic outcomes. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 217–237. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006747.
- Loeb, Tamra B.; Gaines, Tommi; Wyatt, Gail E.; Zhang, Muyu; Liu, Honghu (2011): Associations between child sexual abuse and negative sexual experiences and revictimization among women. Does measuring severity matter? In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (11), S. 946–955.
- Lopez, Silvia; Faro, Concepcio; Lopetegui, Lourdes; Pujol-Ribera, Enriqueta; Monteagudo, Monica; Avecilla-Palau, Angels et al. (2017): Child and Adolescent Sexual Abuse in Women Seeking Help for Sexual and Reproductive Mental Health Problems. Prevalence, Characteristics, and Disclosure. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 246–269. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1288186.
- Lueger-Schuster, Brigitte; Kantor, Viktoria; Weindl, Dina; Knefel, Matthias; Moy, Yvonne; Butollo, Asisa et al. (2014): Institutional abuse of children in the Austrian Catholic Church. Types of abuse and impact on adult survivors' current mental health. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (1), S. 52–64.
- Mahony, David (2010): Assessing sexual abuse/attack histories with bariatric surgery patients. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (4), S. 469–484. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.496713.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa (2015): Prevalence of dating violence among sexual minority youth: variation across gender, sexual minority identity and gender of sexual partners. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 211–224. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0089-0.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa; Crosnoe, Robert (2012): Sexual minority status, peer harassment, and adolescent depression. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 1001–1011. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.02.006.
- Misurell, Justin R.; Springer, Craig; Tryon, Warren W. (2011): Game-based cognitive-behavioral therapy (GB-CBT) group program for children who have experienced sexual abuse. A preliminary investigation. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 14–36. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.540000.
- Muhanguzi, Florence Kyoheirwe (2011): Gender and sexual vulnerability of young women in Africa. Experiences of young girls in secondary schools in Uganda. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 713–725. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.571290.
- Mustanski, Brian; Liu, Richard T. (2013): A longitudinal study of predictors of suicide attempts among lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (3), S. 437–448. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0013-9.
- Nishina, Adrienne (2012): Microcontextual characteristics of peer victimization experiences and adolescents' daily well-being. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 191–201. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9669-z.
- O'Brien, Jennifer E.; White, Kevin; Wu, Qi; Killian-Farrell, Candace (2016): Mental Health and Behavioral Outcomes of Sexual and Nonsexual Child Maltreatment Among Child Welfare-Involved Youth. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 483–503. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1167801.
- O'Halloran, Elaine; Quayle, Ethel (2010): A content analysis of a "boy love" support forum. Revisiting Durkin and Bryant. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 71–85. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903395319.
- O'Leary, Patrick; Coohey, Carol; Easton, Scott D. (2010): The effect of severe child sexual abuse and disclosure on mental health during adulthood. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (3), S. 275–289. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003781251.
- Parkhill, Michele R.; Pickett, Scott M. (2016): Difficulties in Emotion Regulation as a Mediator of the Relationship Between Child Sexual Abuse Victimization and Sexual Aggression Perpetration in Male College Students. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 674–685. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1205161.

- Pechtel, Pia; Evans, Ian M.; Podd, John V. (2011): Conceptualization of the complex outcomes of sexual abuse. A signal detection analysis. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (6), S. 677–694. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.627418.
- Rakow, Aaron; Smith, Daniel; Begle, Angela M.; Ayer, Lynsay (2011): The association of maternal depressive symptoms with child externalizing problems. The role of maternal support following child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 467–480. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.588189.
- Reed-Gavish, Maya (2013): Cognitive abuse within the incestuous family as a factor in the development of dissociative identity disorder. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (4), S. 444–461. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.781093.
- Rellini, Alessandra H.; Meston, Cindy M. (2011): Sexual self-schemas, sexual dysfunction, and the sexual responses of women with a history of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (2), S. 351–362. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9694-0.
- Rinehart, Jenny K.; Nason, Erica E.; Yeater, Elizabeth A.; Miller, Geoffrey F. (2017): Do Some Students Need Special Protection From Research on Sex and Trauma? New Evidence for Young Adult Resilience in "Sensitive Topics" Research. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (3), S. 273–283. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1156047.
- Rosario, Margaret; Schrimshaw, Eric W.; Hunter, Joyce (2012): Homelessness among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth: implications for subsequent internalizing and externalizing symptoms. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 544–560. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9681-3.
- Ross, Colin A. (2017): Response to Miccio-Fonseca (2015) and Defeo (2015) Concerning Commentary About DSM-5 Sexual Disorders Section. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 92–95. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1263263.
- Samms, Kimika M.; Cholewa, Blaire E. (2014): Exploring the context of child sexual abuse in Jamaica. Addressing the deficits. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 115–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870948.
- Schacht, Rebecca L.; George, William H.; Davis, Kelly Cue; Heiman, Julia R.; Norris, Jeanette; Stoner, Susan A.; Kajumulo, Kelly F. (2010): Sexual abuse history, alcohol intoxication, and women's sexual risk behavior. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (4), S. 898–906. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9544-0.
- Seehuus, Martin; Clifton, Jessica; Rellini, Alessandra H. (2015): The Role of Family Environment and Multiple Forms of Childhood Abuse in the Shaping of Sexual Function and Satisfaction in Women. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (6), S. 1595–1608. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0364-5.
- Senn, Theresa E.; Carey, Michael P.; Coury-Doniger, Patricia (2012): Mediators of the relation between childhood sexual abuse and women's sexual risk behavior: a comparison of two theoretical frameworks. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (6), S. 1363–1377. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9897-z.
- Shepard Paynea, Jennifer; Galvan, Frank H.; Williams, John K.; Prusinskie, Missy; Zhang, Muyu; Wyatt, Gail E.; Myers, Hector F. (2014): Impact of childhood sexual abuse on the emotions and behaviours of adult men from three ethnic groups in the USA. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 16 (3), S. 231–245.
- Soylu, Nusret; Ayaz, Muhammed; Yüksel, Tuğb (2014): Early-married and sexually abused girls differ in their psychiatric outcomes. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (9), S. 1552–1559.
- Sterzing, Paul R.; Ratliff, G. Allen; Gartner, Rachel E.; McGeough, Briana L.; Johnson, Kelly C. (2017): Social Ecological Correlates of Polyvictimization among a National Sample of Transgender, Genderqueer, and Cisgender Sexual Minority Adolescents. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 67, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.02.017.
- Stewart, Catherine Carolyn (2012): Beyond the call. Mothers of children with developmental disabilities responding to sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 701–727. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.722182.
- Stroebel, Sandra S.; O'Keefe, Stephen L.; Griffee, Karen; Kuo, Shih-Ya; Beard, Keith W.; Kommor, Martin J. (2013): Sister-sister incest. Data from an anonymous computerized survey. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (6), S. 695–719. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.811140.
- Thrane, Lisa E.; Chen, Xiaojin (2012): Impact of running away on girls' pregnancy. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (2), S. 443–449. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.07.011.
- Vaillancourt-Morel, Marie-Pier; Godbout, Natacha; Labadie, Chloé; Runtz, Marsha; Lussier, Yvan; Sabourin, Stéphane (2015): Avoidant and compulsive sexual behaviors in male and female survivors of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 40, S. 48–59.

- Wager, Nadia (2012): Psychogenic amnesia for childhood sexual abuse and risk for sexual revictimisation in both adolescence and adulthood. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (3), S. 331–349.
- Wager, Nadia (2011): Researching Sexual Revictimisation. Associated Ethical and Methodological Issues, and Possible Solutions. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 158–172. DOI: 10.1002/car.1152.
- Weiler, Julia von; Haardt-Becker, Annette; Schulte, Simone (2010): Care and treatment of child victims of child pornographic exploitation (CPE) in Germany. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 211–222. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003759990.
- White, Jacquelyn; Buehler, Cheryl; Weymouth, Bridget B. (2014): Childhood attention deficit hyperactive disorder (ADHD) symptoms and adolescent female sexual victimisation. Mediating and moderating effects of risky behaviours. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 23–39. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.782429.
- Willis, Gwenda M.; Levenson, Jill S. (2016): The relationship between childhood adversity and adult psychosocial outcomes in females who have sexually offended. Implications for treatment. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 355–367. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1131341.
- Wondie, Yemataw; Zemene, Workie; Reschke, Konrad; Schroder, Harry (2011): Early marriage, rape, child prostitution, and related factors determining the psychosocial effects severity of child sexual abuse in Ethiopia. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (3), S. 305–321. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.573458.
- Yancey, C. Thresa; Hansen, David J.; Naufel, Karen Z. (2011): Heterogeneity of individuals with a history of child sexual abuse. An examination of children presenting to treatment. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (2), S. 111–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.554341.
- Zafar, Sadia; Ross, Erin C. (2013): Perceptions of childhood sexual abuse survivors. Development and initial validation of a new scale to measure stereotypes of adult survivors of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (3), S. 358–378. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.743955.
- Zinzow, Heidi; Seth, Puja; Jackson, Joan; Niehaus, Ashley; Fitzgerald, Monica (2010): Abuse and parental characteristics, attributions of blame, and psychological adjustment in adult survivors of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (1), S. 79–98. DOI: 10.1080/10538710903485989.

6.4. Resilienz und Coping

- Vandoninck, Sofie; d’Haenens, Leen; Segers, Katia (2012): Coping and resilience: children’s response to online risks. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 205–218.
- Postmus, Judy L. (2013): *Sexual Violence and Abuse. An Encyclopedia of Prevention, Impacts, and Recovery*. Santa Barbara, Calif: Abc-Clio.
- Allnock, Debra; Radford, Lorraine; Bunting, Lisa; Price, Avril; Morgan-Klein, Natalie; Ellis, Jane; Stafford, Anne (2012): In Demand. Therapeutic Services for Children and Young People Who Have Experienced Sexual Abuse. In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (5), S. 318–334. DOI: 10.1002/car.1205.
- Benuto, Lorraine T.; O’Donohue, William (2015): Treatment of the Sexually Abused Child. Review and Synthesis of Recent Meta-Analyses. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 56, S. 52–60. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.06.009.
- Collins, Christi M.; O’Neill-Arana, Margarita R.; Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Ossege, Jennifer M. (2014): Catholicism and childhood sexual abuse. Women’s coping and psychotherapy. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (5), S. 519–537. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.918071.
- Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2013): Trauma-informed sexuality education. Recognising the rights and resilience of youth. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 383–394. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.745808.
- Firmin, Carlene; Warrington, Camille; Pearce, Jenny (2017): Sexual Exploitation and Its Impact on Developing Sexualities and Sexual Relationships. The Need for Contextual Social Work Interventions. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2318–2337. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw134.
- Fitzpatrick, Mark; Carr, Alan; Dooley, Barbara; Flanagan-Howard, Roisín; Flanagan, Edel; Tierney, Kevin et al. (2010): Profiles of adult survivors of severe sexual, physical and emotional institutional abuse in Ireland. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (6), S. 387–404. DOI: 10.1002/car.1083.

- Goldbach, Jeremy T.; Gibbs, Jeremy J. (2017): A developmentally informed adaptation of minority stress for sexual minority adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 36–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.007.
- Hartley, Sarah; Johnco, Carly; Hofmeyr, Marthinus; Berry, Alexis (2016): The Nature of Posttraumatic Growth in Adult Survivors of Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (2), S. 201–220. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1119773.
- Lacelle, Céline; Hébert, Martine; Lavoie, Francine; Vitaro, Frank; Tremblay, Richard E. (2012): Sexual health in women reporting a history of child sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (3), S. 247–259.
- Lueger-Schuster, Brigitte; Kantor, Viktoria; Weindl, Dina; Knefel, Matthias; Moy, Yvonne; Butollo, Asisa et al. (2014): Institutional abuse of children in the Austrian Catholic Church. Types of abuse and impact on adult survivors' current mental health. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (1), S. 52–64.
- Marriott, Clare; Hamilton-Giachrisis, Catherine; Harrop, Chris (2014): Factors Promoting Resilience Following Childhood Sexual Abuse. A Structured, Narrative Review of the Literature. In: *Child Abuse Review* 23 (1), S. 17–34. DOI: 10.1002/car.2258.
- Misurell, Justin R.; Springer, Craig; Tryon, Warren W. (2011): Game-based cognitive-behavioral therapy (GB-CBT) group program for children who have experienced sexual abuse. A preliminary investigation. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 14–36. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.540000.
- O'Leary, Patrick J.; Gould, Nick (2010): Exploring Coping Factors amongst Men Who Were Sexually Abused in Childhood. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (8), S. 2669–2686.
- Pechtel, Pia; Evans, Ian M.; Podd, John V. (2011): Conceptualization of the complex outcomes of sexual abuse. A signal detection analysis. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (6), S. 677–694. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.627418.
- Pritchard, Duncan; Graham, Nicola; Penney, Heather; Owen, Gwynne; Peters, Sandra; Mace, F. Charles (2016): Multi-component behavioural intervention reduces harmful sexual behaviour in a 17-year-old male with autism spectrum disorder. A case study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 368–378. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1130269.
- Rakow, Aaron; Smith, Daniel; Begle, Angela M.; Ayer, Lynsay (2011): The association of maternal depressive symptoms with child externalizing problems. The role of maternal support following child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 467–480. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.588189.
- Reed-Gavish, Maya (2013): Cognitive abuse within the incestuous family as a factor in the development of dissociative identity disorder. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (4), S. 444–461. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.781093.
- Rinehart, Jenny K.; Nason, Erica E.; Yeater, Elizabeth A.; Miller, Geoffrey F. (2017): Do Some Students Need Special Protection From Research on Sex and Trauma? New Evidence for Young Adult Resilience in "Sensitive Topics" Research. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (3), S. 273–283. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1156047.
- Samms, Kimika M.; Cholewa, Blaire E. (2014): Exploring the context of child sexual abuse in Jamaica. Addressing the deficits. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 115–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870948.
- Schönbucher, Verena; Maier, Thomas; Mohler-Kuo, Meichun; Schnyder, Ulrich; Landolt, Markus A. (2014): Adolescent perspectives on social support received in the aftermath of sexual abuse: a qualitative study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (3), S. 571–586. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0230-x.
- Stewart, Catherine Carolyn (2012): Beyond the call. Mothers of children with developmental disabilities responding to sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 701–727. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.722182.

6.5. Disclosure

- Robinson, Kerry H.; Davies, Cristyn; Saltmarsh, Sue (2014): Conclusions: Rethinking School Violence. Implications for Theory, Policy and Practice. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 184–195.
- Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014): *Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Postmus, Judy L. (2013): *Sexual Violence and Abuse. An Encyclopedia of Prevention, Impacts, and Recovery*. Santa Barbara, Calif: Abc-Clio.

- Anderson, Gwendolyn D. (2016): The Continuum of Disclosure. Exploring Factors Predicting Tentative Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations During Forensic Interviews and the Implications for Practice, Policy, and Future Research. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 382–402. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153559.
- Campregher, Julia; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2016): Attitudes Toward Juvenile Sex Offender Legislation: The Influence of Case-Specific Information. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 466–482. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153558.
- Coburn, Patricia I.; Chong, Kristin; Connolly, Deborah A. (2017): The Effect of Case Severity on Sentence Length in Cases of Child Sexual Assault in Canada. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 319–333. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1283651.
- Collin-Vézina, Delphine; Sablonnière-Griffin, Mireille de la; Palmer, Andrea M.; Milne, Lise (2015): A preliminary mapping of individual, relational, and social factors that impede disclosure of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 43, S. 123–134.
- Connon, Graham; Crooks, Allian; Carr, Alan; Dooley, Barbara; Guerin, Suzanne; Deasy, Derek et al. (2011): Child sex abuse and the Irish criminal justice system. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 102–119. DOI: 10.1002/car.1156.
- Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Plummer, Carol (2010): Cultural issues in disclosures of child sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (5), S. 491–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.512520.
- Frías, Sonia M.; Erviti, Joaquina (2014): Gendered experiences of sexual abuse of teenagers and children in Mexico. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (4), S. 776–787.
- Kisanga, Felix; Nystrom, Lennarth; Hogan, Nora; Emmelin, Maria (2011): Child sexual abuse. Community concerns in urban Tanzania. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (2), S. 196–217. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.555356.
- Kucuk, Sibel (2016): Analyses of Child Sex Abuse Cases in Turkey: A Provincial Case. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 262–275. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153557.
- Kwhali, Josephine; Martin, Linda; Brady, Geraldine; Brown, Sarah J. (2017): Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation. Knowledge, Confidence and Training within a Contemporary UK Social Work Practice and Policy Context. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2208–2226. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw154.
- Lainpelto, Katrin; Isaksson, Johan; Lindblad, Frank (2016): Does Information About Neuropsychiatric Diagnoses Influence Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations? In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 276–292. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1145164.
- Milam, Lisa J.; Nugent, William R. (2017): Children's Knowledge of Genital Anatomy and Its Relationship With Children's Use of the Word "Inside" During Questioning About Possible Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 23–39. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1269863.
- Nelson, Pete; Cowburn, Malcolm (2010): Social Work Admissions. Applicants with Criminal Convictions -The Challenge of Ethical Risk Assessment. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (4), S. 1081–1099.
- Rassenhofer, Miriam; Zimmer, Andreas; Spröber, Nina; Fegert, Jörg M. (2015): Child sexual abuse in the Roman Catholic Church in Germany: Comparison of victim-impact data collected through church-sponsored and government-sponsored programs. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 40, S. 60–67.
- Schaeffer, Paula; Leventhal, John M.; Gottsegen Asnes, Andrea (2011): Children's disclosures of sexual abuse. Learning from direct inquiry. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (5), S. 343–352.
- Sivis-Cetinkaya, Rahsan (2015): Turkish School Counselors' Experiences of Reporting Child Sexual Abuse: A Brief Report. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 908–921. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1084072.
- Toledo, Annik van; Seymour, Fred (2016): Caregiver Needs Following Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 403–414. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1156206.
- Walsh, Kerryann; Mathews, Ben; Rassafiani, Mehdi; Farrell, Ann; Butler, Des (2012): Understanding teachers' reporting of child sexual abuse. Measurement methods matter. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (9), S. 1937–1946. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.06.004.
- Williams, Javonda; Nelson-Gardell, Debra; Coulborn Faller, Kathleen; Tishelman, Amy; Cordisco-Steele, Linda (2014): Is there a place for extended assessments in addressing child sexual abuse allegations? How sensitivity and specificity impact professional perspectives. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 179–197. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.871380.

Winters, Georgia M.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2016): I Knew It All Along. The Sexual Grooming Behaviors of Child Molesters and the Hindsight Bias. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 20–36. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1108945.

7. Sexualität

7.1. Beziehungsgestaltung

Barbovschi, Monica; Marinescu, Valentina; Velicu, Anca; Laszlo, Eva (2012): Meeting new contacts online. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 177–190.

Betancourt, Gerardo (2015): A theoretical model for intervening in complex sexual behaviours. Sexual desires, pleasures and passion - La Pasi3n - of Spanish-speaking gay men in Canada. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 159–172.

Carmody, Moira (2014): Young people, ethical sex and violence prevention. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 167–184.

Crowley, M. Sue (2014): Defining Themselves. LGBQS Youth Online. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 90–109.

Gallop, Jane (2012): Knot a Love Story. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 115–121.

Luschen, Kristen V. (2014): Survival, Protection, and Forgiveness. Examining Gendered Violence and Care in the Hunger Games Trilogy. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 133–146.

Best, Joel; Bogle, Kathleen A. (2014): Kids gone wild. From rainbow parties to sexting, understanding the hype over teen sex. New York [u.a.]: New York Univ. Press.

Carmody, Moira (2015): *Sex, ethics, and young people*. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan (Palgrave Macmillan's critical studies in gender, sexuality, and culture).

Elliott, Sinikka (2012): *Not my kid. What parents believe about the sex lives of their teenagers*. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press.

Garcia, Lorena (2012): *Respect yourself, protect yourself. Latina girls and sexual identity*. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press (Intersections / [New York University Press]).

Powell, Anastasia (2010): *Sex, Power and Consent. Youth Culture and the Unwritten Rules*. Port Melbourne, Vic.: Cambridge University Press.

Sanjakdar, Fida (2012): *Living west, facing east. The deconstruction of Muslim youth's sexual identities*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints, 364).

Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013): *Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications*. Hove: Psychology.

Lemma, Alessandra; Lynch, Paul E. (Hg.) (2015): *Sexualities. Contemporary psychoanalytic perspectives*. London, New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.

Abajobir, Amanuel Alemu; Kisely, Steve; Williams, Gail Marilyn; Clavarino, Alexandra Marie; Najman, Jakob Moses (2017): Substantiated Childhood Maltreatment and Intimate Partner Violence Victimization in Young Adulthood: A Birth Cohort Study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 165–179. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0558-3.

Albury, Kath (2013): Young people, media and sexual learning. Rethinking representation. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S32-S44. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.767194.

Ali, Mir M.; Dwyer, Debra S. (2011): Estimating peer effects in sexual behavior among adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 183–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.12.008.

- Allen, Louisa (2011): 'Picture this'. Using photo-methods in research on sexualities and schooling. In: *Qualitative Research* 11 (5), S. 487–504. DOI: 10.1177/1468794111413224.
- Alleyne, Binta; Coleman-Cowger, Victoria H.; Crown, Laurel; Gibbons, Maya A.; Vines, Linda Nicole (2011): The effects of dating violence, substance use and risky sexual behavior among a diverse sample of Illinois youth. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 11–18. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.03.006.
- Åmot, Ingvild; Ytterhus, Borgunn (2014): 'Talking bodies'. Power and counter-power between children and adults in day care. In: *Childhood* 21 (2), S. 260–273. DOI: 10.1177/0907568213490971.
- Attwood, Feona; Smith, Clarissa (2011): Investigating young people's sexual cultures. An introduction. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* (Vol. 11 No. 3), S. 235–242.
- Bale, Clare (2011): Raunch or romance? Framing and interpreting the relationship between sexualized culture and young people's sexual health. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 303–313. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590088.
- Bauermeister, José A.; Johns, Michelle Marie; Sandfort, Theo G. M.; Eisenberg, Anna; Grossman, Arnold H.; D'Augelli, Anthony R. (2010): Relationship trajectories and psychological well-being among sexual minority youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1148–1163. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9557-y.
- Beckmeyer, Jonathon J. (2015): Comparing the associations between three types of adolescents' romantic involvement and their engagement in substance use. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 42, S. 140–147. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.04.008.
- Berglas, Nancy F.; Angulo-Olaiz, Francisca; Jerman, Petra; Desai, Mona; Constantine, Norman A. (2014): Engaging Youth Perspectives on Sexual Rights and Gender Equality in Intimate Relationships as a Foundation for Rights-Based Sexuality Education. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (4), S. 288–298. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0148-7.
- Bhana, Deevia; Pattman, Rob (2011): Girls want money, boys want virgins. The materiality of love amongst South African township youth in the context of HIV and AIDS. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 961–972. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.576770.
- Boisvert, Stéphanie; Poulin, François (2016): Romantic Relationship Patterns from Adolescence to Emerging Adulthood: Associations with Family and Peer Experiences in Early Adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 945–958. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0435-0.
- Bos, Henny; Sandfort, Theo (2015): Gender Nonconformity, Sexual Orientation, and Dutch Adolescents' Relationship with Peers. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (5), S. 1269–1279. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0461-5.
- Bower, Andrew R.; Nishina, Adrienne; Witkow, Melissa R.; Bellmore, Amy (2015): Nice Guys and Gals Finish Last? Not in Early Adolescence When Empathic, Accepted, and Popular Peers are Desirable. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (12), S. 2275–2288. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0346-5.
- Bowker, Julie C.; Etkin, Rebecca G. (2014): Does humor explain why relationally aggressive adolescents are popular? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1322–1332. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0031-5.
- Bui, Thanh Cong; Diamond, Pamela M.; Markham, Christine; Ross, Michael W.; Nguyen-Le, Thanh-An; Tran, Ly Hai Thi (2010): Gender relations and sexual communication among female students in the Mekong River Delta of Vietnam. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (6), S. 591–601. DOI: 10.1080/13691050902968769.
- Caiozzo, Christina N.; Houston, Jessica; Grych, John (2016): Predicting aggression in late adolescent romantic relationships. A short-term longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 53, S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.10.012.
- Carlson, Wendy; Rose, Amanda J. (2012): Brief report. Activities in heterosexual romantic relationships: grade differences and associations with relationship satisfaction. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 219–224. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.09.001.
- Carter, Rona; Williams, Sandra (2016): Self-perceptions of pubertal timing and patterns of peer group activities and dating behavior among heterosexual adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 47, S. 71–80. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.12.006.
- Casey, Erin A.; Beadnell, Blair (2010): The structure of male adolescent peer networks and risk for intimate partner violence perpetration: findings from a national sample. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 620–633. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9423-y.

- Collibee, Charlene; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Chronic and Acute Relational Risk Factors for Dating Aggression in Adolescence and Young Adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (4), S. 763–776. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0427-0.
- Corona, Laura L.; Fox, Stephanie A.; Christodulu, Kristin V.; Worlock, Jane Ann (2016): Providing Education on Sexuality and Relationships to Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder and Their Parents. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 199–214. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-015-9424-6.
- Daddis, Christopher; Randolph, Danielle (2010): Dating and disclosure: Adolescent management of information regarding romantic involvement. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (2), S. 309–320. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.05.002.
- Dank, Meredith; Lachman, Pamela; Zweig, Janine M.; Yahner, Jennifer (2014): Dating violence experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (5), S. 846–857. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9975-8.
- Eklund, Jenny M.; Kerr, Margaret; Stattin, Hakan (2010): Romantic relationships and delinquent behaviour in adolescence: the moderating role of delinquency propensity. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (3), S. 377–386. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.09.002.
- Ellis, Wendy E.; Chung-Hall, Janet; Dumas, Tara M. (2013): The role of peer group aggression in predicting adolescent dating violence and relationship quality. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 487–499. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9797-0.
- Fielder, Robyn L.; Carey, Michael P. (2010): Predictors and consequences of sexual "hookups" among college students: a short-term prospective study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1105–1119. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9448-4.
- Fielder, Robyn L.; Walsh, Jennifer L.; Carey, Kate B.; Carey, Michael P. (2013): Predictors of sexual hookups: a theory-based, prospective study of first-year college women. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1425–1441. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0106-0.
- Firmin, Carlene; Warrington, Camille; Pearce, Jenny (2017): Sexual Exploitation and Its Impact on Developing Sexualities and Sexual Relationships. The Need for Contextual Social Work Interventions. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2318–2337. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw134.
- Galinsky, Adena M.; Sonenstein, Freya Lund (2013): Relationship commitment, perceived equity, and sexual enjoyment among young adults in the United States. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (1), S. 93–104. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0003-y.
- Graaf, Hanneke de; van de Schoot, Rens; Woertman, Liesbeth; Hawk, Skyler T.; Meeus, Wim (2012): Family cohesion and romantic and sexual initiation: a three wave longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 583–592. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9708-9.
- Hampshire, Kate; Porter, Gina; Mashiri, Mac; Maponya, Goodhope; Dube, Siphon (2011): Proposing love on the way to school. Mobility, sexuality and youth transitions in South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (2), S. 217–231. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.522255.
- Harden, K. Paige; Mendle, Jane (2011): Adolescent sexual activity and the development of delinquent behavior: the role of relationship context. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 825–838. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9601-y.
- Haydon, Abigail A.; Halpern, Carolyn Tucker (2010): Older romantic partners and depressive symptoms during adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1240–1251. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9539-0.
- Heywood, Wendy; Patrick, Kent; Pitts, Marian; Mitchell, Anne (2016): "Dude, I'm Seventeen ... It's Okay Not to Have Sex by This Age": Feelings, Reasons, Pressures, and Intentions Reported by Adolescents Who Have Not Had Sexual Intercourse. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (9), S. 1207–1214. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2015.1092105.
- Hilberink, Sander R.; Kruijver, Egbert; Wiegerink, Diana J. H. G.; Vliet Vlieland, Thea P. M. (2013): A Pilot Implementation of an Intervention to Promote Sexual Health in Adolescents and Young Adults in Rehabilitation. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 31 (4), S. 373–392. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9288-6.
- Houser, John J.; Mayeux, Lara; Cross, Cassandra (2015): Peer status and aggression as predictors of dating popularity in adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 683–695. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0174-z.

Hyde, Abbey; Carney, Marie; Drennan, Jonathan; Butler, Michelle; Lohan, Maria; Howlett, Etaoine (2010): The silent treatment. Parents' narratives of sexuality education with young people. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 359–371. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903514455.

Ingevaldson, Sara; Goulding, Anneli; Tidefors, Inga (2016): Experiences of intimate relationships in young men who sexually offended during adolescence. Interviews 10 years later. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 410–422. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1177125.

Johnson, Matthew D. (2013): Parent-child relationship quality directly and indirectly influences hooking up behavior reported in young adulthood through alcohol use in adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1463–1472. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0098-9.

Johnston, Lisa G.; Mon, Myo Myo; Steinhaus, Mara; Sass, Justine (2017): Correlates of Forced Sex Among Young Men Who Have Sex With Men in Yangon and Monywa, Myanmar. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 1001–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0761-z.

Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D.; Sanders, Stephanie A.; Dennis, Barbara; Reece, Michael (2014): Gender Differences in Heterosexual College Students' Conceptualizations and Indicators of Sexual Consent. Implications for Contemporary Sexual Assault Prevention Education. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (8), S. 904–916.

Katz, Jennifer; Schneider, Monica E. (2013): Casual hook up sex during the first year of college: Prospective associations with attitudes about sex and love relationships. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1451–1462. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0078-0.

Kelly, Angela; Worth, Heather; Akuani, Frances; Kepa, Barbara; Kupul, Martha; Walizopa, Lucy et al. (2010): Gendered talk about sex, sexual relationships and HIV among young people in Papua New Guinea. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 221–232. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903181107.

Lee, Sally; Fenge, Lee-Ann (2017): Sexual Well-Being and Physical Disability. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2263–2281. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw107.

Lindroth, Malin (2014): Sex education and young people in group homes. Balancing risks, rights and resilience in sexual health promotion. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 400–413. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919910.

Loftus, Jeni; Kelly, Brian C.; Mustillo, Sarah A. (2011): Depressive symptoms among adolescent girls in relationships with older partners: causes and lasting effects? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 800–813. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9589-3.

Mallet, Pascal; Herbe, Dominique (2011): Does knowledge about sexuality prevent adolescents from developing rape-supportive beliefs? In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 48 (4), S. 372–380. DOI: 10.1080/00224491003794048.

Martin-Storey, Alexa (2015): Prevalence of dating violence among sexual minority youth: variation across gender, sexual minority identity and gender of sexual partners. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 211–224. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0089-0.

Meek, Rosie (2011): The possible selves of young fathers in prison. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (5), S. 941–949. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.12.005.

Milhausen, Robin R.; Buchholz, Andrea C.; Opperman, Emily A.; Benson, Lindsay E. (2015): Relationships Between Body Image, Body Composition, Sexual Functioning, and Sexual Satisfaction Among Heterosexual Young Adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (6), S. 1621–1633. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0328-9.

Miller, Shari; Williams, Jason; Cutbush, Stacey; Gibbs, Deborah; Clinton-Sherrod, Monique; Jones, Sarah (2013): Dating violence, bullying, and sexual harassment: longitudinal profiles and transitions over time. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 607–618. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9914-8.

Moosmann, Danyel A. V.; Roosa, Mark W. (2015): Exploring Mexican American adolescent romantic relationship profiles and adjustment. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 43, S. 181–192. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.06.004.

Muehlenhard, Charlene L.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D. (2016): The Complexities of Sexual Consent Among College Students. A Conceptual and Empirical Review. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (4-5), S. 1–31.

Muhanguzi, Florence Kyoheirwe (2011): Gender and sexual vulnerability of young women in Africa. Experiences of young girls in secondary schools in Uganda. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 713–725. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.571290.

- Nielsena, Silja; Paasonen, Susanna; Spišák, Sanna (2015): 'Pervy role-play and such'. Girls' experiences of sexual messaging online. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 472–485.
- Novak, Jamie; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Partner Violence During Adolescence and Young Adulthood: Individual and Relationship Level Risk Factors. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (9), S. 1849–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0484-4.
- O'Hara, Ross E.; Cooper, M. Lynne (2015): Bidirectional associations between alcohol use and sexual risk-taking behavior from adolescence into young adulthood. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (4), S. 857–871. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0510-8.
- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Billen, Rhett M.; Conrad, Kathryn A.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Sex, commitment, and casual sex relationships among college men: a mixed-methods analysis. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 561–571. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0047-z.
- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Hooking up and penetrative hookups: correlates that differentiate college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 573–583. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-9907-9.
- Orpinas, Pamela; Hsieh, Hsien-Lin; Song, Xiao; Holland, Kristin; Nahapetyan, Lusine (2013): Trajectories of physical dating violence from middle to high school: association with relationship quality and acceptability of aggression. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 551–565. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9881-5.
- Pearson, Jennifer; Wilkinson, Lindsey (2013): Family relationships and adolescent well-being: are families equally protective for same-sex attracted youth? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 376–393. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9865-5.
- Reyes, H. Luz McNaughton; Foshee, Vangie A.; Niolon, Phyllis Holditch; Reidy, Dennis E.; Hall, Jeffrey E. (2016): Gender Role Attitudes and Male Adolescent Dating Violence Perpetration: Normative Beliefs as Moderators. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 350–360. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0278-0.
- Sabina, Chiara; Cuevas, Carlos A.; Cotignola-Pickens, Heather M. (2016): Longitudinal dating violence victimization among Latino teens: Rates, risk factors, and cultural influences. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 47, S. 5–15. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.11.003.
- Schnurr, Melissa P.; Lohman, Brenda J. (2013): The impact of collective efficacy on risks for adolescents' perpetration of dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 518–535. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9909-5.
- Schwarz, Beate; Stutz, Melanie; Ledermann, Thomas (2012): Perceived interparental conflict and early adolescents' friendships: the role of attachment security and emotion regulation. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (9), S. 1240–1252. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9769-4.
- Shulman, Shmuel; Zlotnik, Aynat; Shachar-Shapira, Lital; Connolly, Jennifer; Bohr, Yvonne (2012): Adolescent daughters' romantic competence: the role of divorce, quality of parenting, and maternal romantic history. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 593–606. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9748-9.
- Sommer, Marni; Likindikoki, Samuel; Kaaya, Sylvia (2015): "Bend a fish when the fish is not yet dry": adolescent boys' perceptions of sexual risk in Tanzania. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 583–595. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0406-z.
- Sullivan, Terri N.; Garthe, Rachel C.; Goncy, Elizabeth A.; Carlson, Megan M.; Behrhorst, Kathryn L. (2017): Longitudinal Relations between Beliefs Supporting Aggression, Anger Regulation, and Dating Aggression among Early Adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 982–994. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0569-0.
- Temple, Jeff R.; Choi, Hye Jeong; Brem, Meagan; Wolford-Clevenger, Caitlin; Stuart, Gregory L.; Peskin, Melissa Fleschler; Elmquist, JoAnna (2016): The Temporal Association Between Traditional and Cyber Dating Abuse Among Adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 340–349. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0380-3.
- Towns, Alison J.; Scott, Hazel (2013): 'I couldn't even dress the way I wanted.' Young women talk of 'ownership' by boyfriends. An opportunity for the prevention of domestic violence? In: *Feminism & Psychology* 23 (4), S. 536–555. DOI: 10.1177/0959353513481955.
- van Ouytsel, Joris; Ponnet, Koen; Walrave, Michel (2017): The associations of adolescents' dating violence victimization, well-being and engagement in risk behaviors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 66–71. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.005.

- Vannier, Sarah A.; O'Sullivan, Lucia F. (2012): Who gives and who gets: why, when, and with whom young people engage in oral sex. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 572–582. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9745-z.
- Vézina, Johanne; Hébert, Martine; Poulin, François; Lavoie, Francine; Vitaro, Frank; Tremblay, Richard E. (2011): Risky lifestyle as a mediator of the relationship between deviant peer affiliation and dating violence victimization among adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 814–824. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9602-x.
- Wargo Aikins, Julie; Simon, Valerie A.; Prinstein, Mitchell J. (2010): Romantic partner selection and socialization of young adolescents' substance use and behavior problems. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (6), S. 813–826. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.07.007.
- Wheeler, Lorey A.; Killoren, Sarah E.; Whiteman, Shawn D.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; McHale, Susan M.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J. (2016): Romantic Relationship Experiences from Late Adolescence to Young Adulthood: The Role of Older Siblings in Mexican-Origin Families. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 900–915. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0392-z.
- Williams, Lela Rankin; Hickie, Kristine E. (2011): "He cheated on me, I cheated on him back". Mexican American and White adolescents' perceptions of cheating in romantic relationships. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (5), S. 1005–1016. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.11.007.
- Wright, Michelle F. (2015): Cyber aggression within adolescents' romantic relationships: linkages to parental and partner attachment. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 37–47. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0147-2.
- Ybarra, Michele L.; Espelage, Dorothy L.; Langhinrichsen-Rohling, Jennifer; Korchmaros, Josephine D.; Boyd, Danah (2016): Lifetime Prevalence Rates and Overlap of Physical, Psychological, and Sexual Dating Abuse Perpetration and Victimization in a National Sample of Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1083–1099. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0748-9.
- Zimmer-Gembeck, Melanie J.; Ducat, Wendy H.; Boislard-Pepin, Marie-Aude (2011): A prospective study of young females' sexual subjectivity: associations with age, sexual behavior, and dating. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 927–938. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9751-3.
- Zweig, Janine M.; Dank, Meredith; Yahner, Jennifer; Lachman, Pamela (2013): The rate of cyber dating abuse among teens and how it relates to other forms of teen dating violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1063–1077. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9922-8.

7.2. Selbstbestimmung

- Allen, Louisa (2014): Pleasure's Perils? Critically Reflecting on Pleasure's Inclusion in Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 153–169.
- Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise; Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): Introduction. Putting Pleasure Under Pressure. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 1–12.
- Betancourt, Gerardo (2015): A theoretical model for intervening in complex sexual behaviours. Sexual desires, pleasures and passion - La Pasión - of Spanish-speaking gay men in Canada. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 159–172.
- Burke, Kevin (2014): Impossible Women. Saints, Sinner, and the Gendered Mythology in a Catholic School. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 25–37.
- Carmody, Moira (2014): Young people, ethical sex and violence prevention. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): *Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 167–184.
- Castillo, Victoria A. (2016): Introduction to "In Conversation on Female Genital Cutting": A Pedagogical Perspective. In: Gul Ozyegin (Hg.): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge, S. 146–149.
- Crowley, M. Sue (2014): Defining Themselves. LGBTQ Youth Online. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 90–109.

Desjardins, Michel (2012): *The Sexualized Body of the Child. Parents and the Politics of "Voluntary" Sterilization of People Labeled Intellectually Disabled*. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 69–88.

Finkelstein, Sam; Mosqueda, Lucky; Birrueta, Adrian; Kitty, Eric (2012): *Queer youth of color organizing for safe & affirming education*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 349–350.

Hoodfar, Homa; Ghoreishian, Ana (2012): *Morality policing and the public sphere: women reclaiming their bodies and their rights*. In: Anissa Hélie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books, S. 234–268.

Lehtonen, Jukka (2012): *Yogyakarta Principles. For the Rights of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender People*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 284.

Malmström, Maria Frederika (2016): *The Continuous Making of Pure Womanhood among Muslim Women in Cairo. Cooking, Depilating, and Circumcising*. In: Gul Ozyegin (Hg.): *Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures*. London, New York: Routledge, S. 127–145.

McCready, Lance T. (2014): *The African Dance Program. "Where is the Love?"*. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), 342-356.

Mir-Hosseini, Ziba (2012): *Sexuality and inequality: the marriage contract and Muslim legal tradition*. In: Anissa Hélie und Homa Hoodfar (Hg.): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books, S. 124–150.

Quinlivan, Kathleen; Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise (2014): *After-Word(s). Engaging with the Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education: Affordances and Provocations*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 186–195.

Rasmussen, Mary Louise (2014): *Pleasure/Desire, Sexularism, and Sexuality Education*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 153–169.

Rofes, Eric E. (2012): *Bound and Gagged. Sexual Silences, Gender Conformity, and the Gay Male Teacher*. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 105–121.

Sanjakdar, Fida (2014): *Sacred Pleasure. Exploring Dimensions of Sexual Pleasure and Desire from an Islamic Perspective*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 95–114.

Shuttleworth, Russell (2012): *Bridging Theory and Experience: A Critical-Interpretative Ethnography of Sexuality and Disability*. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 54–69.

Siebers, Tobin (2012): *A Sexual Culture for Disabled People*. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 37–54.

Vincent, Louise; Macleod, Catriona (2014): *Introducing a Critical Pedagogy of Sexual and Reproductive Citizenship: Extending the 'Framework of Thick Desire'*. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 115–136.

Best, Joel; Bogle, Kathleen A. (2014): *Kids gone wild. From rainbow parties to sexting, understanding the hype over teen sex*. New York [u.a.]: New York Univ. Press.

Carmody, Moira (2015): *Sex, ethics, and young people*. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan (Palgrave Macmillan's critical studies in gender, sexuality, and culture).

Elliott, Sinikka (2012): *Not my kid. What parents believe about the sex lives of their teenagers*. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press.

- Garcia, Lorena (2012): *Respect yourself, protect yourself. Latina girls and sexual identity*. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press (Intersections / [New York University Press]).
- Larremore, April (2016): *Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom*.
- Powell, Anastasia (2010): *Sex, Power and Consent. Youth Culture and the Unwritten Rules*. Port Melbourne, Vic.: Cambridge University Press.
- Sanjakdar, Fida (2012): *Living west, facing east. The deconstruction of Muslim youth's sexual identities*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints, 364).
- Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013): *Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications*. Hove: Psychology.
- Hélie, Anissa; Hoodfar, Homa (Hg.) (2012): *Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance*. London: Zed Books.
- Lemma, Alessandra; Lynch, Paul E. (Hg.) (2015): *Sexualities. Contemporary psychoanalytic perspectives*. London, New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Albury, Kath (2013): *Young people, media and sexual learning. Rethinking representation*. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S32-S44. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.767194.
- Allen, Louisa (2011): 'Picture this'. Using photo-methods in research on sexualities and schooling. In: *Qualitative Research* 11 (5), S. 487–504. DOI: 10.1177/1468794111413224.
- Bale, Clare (2011): *Raunch or romance? Framing and interpreting the relationship between sexualized culture and young people's sexual health*. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 303–313. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590088.
- Bauermeister, José A. (2014): *How statewide LGB policies go from "under our skin" to "into our hearts": fatherhood aspirations and psychological well-being among emerging adult sexual minority men*. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1295–1305. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0059-6.
- Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Fava, Nicole M. (2014): *What puts "At-Risk Girls" at risk? Sexual vulnerability and social inequality in the lives of girls in the child welfare system*. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 116–125. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0142-5.
- Beres, Melanie Ann (2014): *Rethinking the concept of consent for anti-sexual violence activism and education*. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 24 (3), S. 373–389. DOI: 10.1177/0959353514539652.
- Berglas, Nancy F.; Angulo-Olaiz, Francisca; Jerman, Petra; Desai, Mona; Constantine, Norman A. (2014): *Engaging Youth Perspectives on Sexual Rights and Gender Equality in Intimate Relationships as a Foundation for Rights-Based Sexuality Education*. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (4), S. 288–298. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0148-7.
- Bhana, D. (2016): *'Sex isn't better than love. Exploring South African Indian teenage male and female desires beyond danger*. In: *Childhood* 23 (3), S. 362–377. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216642828.
- Cameron-Lewis, Vanessa; Allen, Louisa (2013): *Teaching pleasure and danger in sexuality education*. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (2), S. 121–132. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.697440.
- Daddis, Christopher; Randolph, Danielle (2010): *Dating and disclosure: Adolescent management of information regarding romantic involvement*. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (2), S. 309–320. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.05.002.
- Dahlbäck, Elisabeth; Maimbolwa, Margaret; Yamba, C. Bawa; Kasonka, Lackson; Bergström, Staffan; Ransjö-Arvidson, Anna-Berit (2010): *Pregnancy loss. Spontaneous and induced abortions among young women in Lusaka, Zambia*. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 247–262. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903353383.
- Epstein, Debbie; Kehily, Mary Jane; Renold, E. (2012): *Culture, policy and the un/marked child. Fragments of the sexualisation debates*. In: *Gender and Education* 24 (3), S. 249–254. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2012.670390.
- Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2012): *Young women's adolescent experiences of oral sex. Relation of age of initiation to sexual motivation, sexual coercion, and psychological functioning*. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (5), S. 1191–1201. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.03.010.

- Firmin, Carlene; Warrington, Camille; Pearce, Jenny (2017): Sexual Exploitation and Its Impact on Developing Sexualities and Sexual Relationships. The Need for Contextual Social Work Interventions. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2318–2337. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw134.
- Frawley, Patsie; Wilson, Nathan J. (2016): Young People with Intellectual Disability Talking About Sexuality Education and Information. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (4), S. 469–484. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9460-x.
- Froyum, Carissa M. (2010): Making 'good girls'. Sexual agency in the sexuality education of low-income black girls. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 59–72. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903272583.
- Gill, Michael (2010): Rethinking sexual abuse, questions of consent, and intellectual disability. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (3), S. 201–213. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0019-9.
- Govender, Kaymarlin (2011): The cool, the bad, the ugly, and the powerful. Identity struggles in schoolboy peer culture. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 887–901. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.586436.
- Graaf, Hanneke de; van de Schoot, Rens; Woertman, Liesbeth; Hawk, Skyler T.; Meeus, Wim (2012): Family cohesion and romantic and sexual initiation: a three wave longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 583–592. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9708-9.
- Greslé-Favier, Claire (2010): The legacy of abstinence-only discourses and the place of pleasure in US discourses on teenage sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515098.
- Grose, Rose Grace; Grabe, Shelly; Kohfeldt, Danielle (2014): Sexual Education, Gender Ideology, and Youth Sexual Empowerment. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), 742.753.
- Hafford-Letchfield, Trish; Cocker, Christine; Ryan, Peter; Melonowska, Justyna (2017): Rights through Alliances. Findings from a European Project Tackling Homophobic and Transphobic Bullying in Schools through the Engagement of Families and Young People. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2338–2356. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw104.
- Hallett, Sophie (2017): 'An Uncomfortable Comfortableness'. 'Care', Child Protection and Child Sexual Exploitation. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (7), S. 2137–2152. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcv136.
- Hampshire, Kate; Porter, Gina; Mashiri, Mac; Ma ponya, Goodhope; Dube, Siphon (2011): Proposing love on the way to school. Mobility, sexuality and youth transitions in South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (2), S. 217–231. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.522255.
- Hensel, Devon J.; Fortenberry, J. Dennis; O'Sullivan, Lucia F.; Orr, Donald P. (2011): The developmental association of sexual self-concept with sexual behavior among adolescent women. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 675–684. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.09.005.
- Hicks, Stephen; Jeyasingham, Dharman (2017): Social Work, Queer Theory and After. A Genealogy of Sexuality Theory in Neo-Liberal Times. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2357–2373. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw103.
- Hirst, Julia (2013): 'It's got to be about enjoying yourself'. Young people, sexual pleasure, and sex and relationships education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 423–436. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.747433.
- Jackson, Sue; Weatherall, Ann (2010): The (Im)possibilities of Feminist School Based Sexuality Education. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 20 (2), S. 166–185.
- Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D.; Sanders, Stephanie A.; Dennis, Barbara; Reece, Michael (2014): Gender Differences in Heterosexual College Students' Conceptualizations and Indicators of Sexual Consent. Implications for Contemporary Sexual Assault Prevention Education. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (8), S. 904–916.
- Kaestle, Christine E.; Allen, Katherine R. (2011): The role of masturbation in healthy sexual development: perceptions of young adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 983–994. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9722-0.
- Kjaran, Jón; Kristinsdóttir, Guðrún (2014): Queering the environment and caring for the self. Icelandic LGBT students' experience of the upper secondary school. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 23 (1), S. 1–20. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2014.910250.
- Lamb, Sharon; Farmer, Kaelin M.; Kosterina, Elena; Lambe Sariñana, Susan; Plocha, Aleksandra; Randazzo, Renee (2016): What's sexy? Adolescent girls discuss confidence, danger, and media influence. In: *Gender and Education* 28 (4), S. 527–545. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1107528.

- Lee, Sally; Fenge, Lee-Ann (2017): Sexual Well-Being and Physical Disability. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2263–2281. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw107.
- Lindroth, Malin (2014): Sex education and young people in group homes. Balancing risks, rights and resilience in sexual health promotion. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 400–413. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919910.
- Lourie, Michael A.; Needham, Belinda L. (2017): Sexual Orientation Discordance and Young Adult Mental Health. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 943–954. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0553-8.
- Malón, Agustín (2015): Adult–Child Sex and the Limits of Liberal Sexual Morality. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (4), S. 1071–1083.
- Milhausen, Robin R.; Buchholz, Andrea C.; Opperman, Emily A.; Benson, Lindsay E. (2015): Relationships Between Body Image, Body Composition, Sexual Functioning, and Sexual Satisfaction Among Heterosexual Young Adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (6), S. 1621–1633. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0328-9.
- Miller, S. A. (2016): "How You Bully a Girl". Sexual Drama and the Negotiation of Gendered Sexuality in High School. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (5), S. 721–744. DOI: 10.1177/0891243216664723.
- Muehlenhard, Charlene L.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D. (2016): The Complexities of Sexual Consent Among College Students. A Conceptual and Empirical Review. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (4-5), S. 1–31.
- Muhanguzi, Florence Kyoheirwe (2011): Gender and sexual vulnerability of young women in Africa. Experiences of young girls in secondary schools in Uganda. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 713–725. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.571290.
- Muise, Amy; Preyde, Michéle; Maitland, Scott B.; Milhausen, Robin R. (2010): Sexual identity and sexual well-being in female heterosexual university students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (4), S. 915–925. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9492-8.
- Munoz-Laboy, Miguel; Murray, Laura R.; Wittlin, Natalie; Wilson, Patrick A.; Terto, Veriano; Parker, Richard (2011): Divine targets. Youth at the centre of Catholic and Pentecostal responses to HIV and AIDS in Brazil. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 657–668. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.565519.
- Nielsen, Silja; Paasonen, Susanna; Spišák, Sanna (2015): 'Pervy role-play and such'. Girls' experiences of sexual messaging online. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 472–485.
- Noonan, A.; Taylor Gomez, Miriam (2011): Who's Missing? Awareness of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender People with Intellectual Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (2), S. 175–180. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9175-3.
- Ott, Miles Q.; Corliss, Heather L.; Wypij, David; Rosario, Margaret; Austin, S. Bryn (2011): Stability and change in self-reported sexual orientation identity in young people: application of mobility metrics. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (3), S. 519–532. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9691-3.
- Parchomiuk, Monika (2012): Specialists and Sexuality of Individuals with Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (4), S. 407–419. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9249-x.
- Pearson, Jennifer; Wilkinson, Lindsey (2013): Family relationships and adolescent well-being: are families equally protective for same-sex attracted youth? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 376–393. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9865-5.
- Pebdani, Roxanna N. (2016): Attitudes of Group Home Employees Towards the Sexuality of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (3), S. 329–339. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9447-7.
- Rysst, Mari (2010): 'I Am Only Ten Years Old'. Femininities, clothing-fashion codes and the intergenerational gap of interpretation of young girls' clothes. In: *Childhood* 17 (1), S. 76–93. DOI: 10.1177/0907568209351552.
- Sakellariou, Dikaos (2012): Sexuality and Disability. A Discussion on Care of the Self. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 187–197. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9219-3.
- Schaafsma, Dilana; Kok, Gerjo; Stoffelen, Joke M. T.; Curfs, Leopold M. G. (2017): People with Intellectual Disabilities Talk About Sexuality. Implications for the Development of Sex Education. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (1), S. 21–38. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9466-4.
- Sloane, Heather M. (2014): Tales of a Reluctant Sex Radical. Barriers to Teaching the Importance of Pleasure for Wellbeing. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 453–467. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9381-5.

- Smith, Mark; Woodiwiss, Jo (2017): Sexuality, Innocence and Agency in Narratives of Childhood Sexual Abuse. Implications for Social Work. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2173–2189. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw160.
- Sorhaindo, Annik; Bonell, Chris; Fletcher, Adam; Jessiman, Patricia; Keogh, Peter; Mitchell, Kirstin (2016): Being targeted. Young women's experience of being identified for a teenage pregnancy prevention programme. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 181–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.03.013.
- Tabatabaie, Alireza (2014): Childhood and adolescent sexuality, Islam, and problematics of sex education. A call for re-examination. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 276–288. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1005836.
- Taylor Gomez, Miriam (2012): The S Words. Sexuality, Sensuality, Sexual Expression and People with Intellectual Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 237–245. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9250-4.
- Tomaszewska, Paulina; Krahé, Barbara (2016): Attitudes towards sexual coercion by Polish high school students. Links with risky sexual scripts, pornography use, and religiosity. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 291–307. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1195892.
- Towns, Alison J.; Scott, Hazel (2013): 'I couldn't even dress the way I wanted.' Young women talk of 'ownership' by boyfriends. An opportunity for the prevention of domestic violence? In: *Feminism & Psychology* 23 (4), S. 536–555. DOI: 10.1177/0959353513481955.
- Turner, George W.; Crane, Betsy (2017): Sexually Silenced No More, Adults with Learning Disabilities Speak Up. A Call to Action for Social Work to Frame Sexual Voice as a Social Justice Issue. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2300–2317. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw133.
- van Oosten, Johanna M. F.; Peter, Jochen; Boot, Inge (2015): Exploring associations between exposure to sexy online self-presentations and adolescents' sexual attitudes and behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 1078–1091. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0194-8.
- Vannier, Sarah A.; O'Sullivan, Lucia F. (2012): Who gives and who gets: why, when, and with whom young people engage in oral sex. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 572–582. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9745-z.
- Vries, Hein de; Eggers, Sander Matthijs; Jinabhai, Champak; Meyer-Weitz, Anna; Sathiparsad, Reshma; Taylor, Myra (2014): Adolescents' beliefs about forced sex in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (6), S. 1087–1095. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0280-8.
- Vrouenraets, Lieke Josephina Jeanne Johanna; Fredriks, A. Miranda; Hannema, Sabine E.; Cohen-Kettenis, Peggy T.; Vries, Martine C. de (2016): Perceptions of Sex, Gender, and Puberty Suppression: A Qualitative Analysis of Transgender Youth. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (7), S. 1697–1703. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0764-9.
- Wetherill, Reagan R.; Neal, Dan J.; Fromme, Kim (2010): Parents, peers, and sexual values influence sexual behavior during the transition to college. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 682–694. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9476-8.
- Wilkinson, Verity J.; Theodore, Kate; Raczka, Roman (2015): 'As Normal as Possible'. Sexual Identity Development in People with Intellectual Disabilities Transitioning to Adulthood. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 33 (1), S. 93–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9356-6.
- Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014): Why All the Talk About Sex? An Autoethnography Identifying the Troubling Discourse of Sexuality and Intellectual Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 107–116. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9331-7.
- Winskell, Kate; Beres, Laura K.; Hill, Elizabeth; Mbakwem, Benjamin Chigozie; Obyerodhyambo, Oby (2011): Making sense of abstinence. Social representations in young Africans' HIV-related narratives from six countries. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 945–959. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.591431.
- Zimmer-Gembeck, Melanie J.; Ducat, Wendy H.; Boislard-Pepin, Marie-Aude (2011): A prospective study of young females' sexual subjectivity: associations with age, sexual behavior, and dating. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 927–938. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9751-3.

7.3. Sexuelle Erfahrungen

- Allen, Louisa (2014): Pleasure's Perils? Critically Reflecting on Pleasure's Inclusion in Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 153–169.

- Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise; Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): Introduction. Putting Pleasure Under Pressure. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 1–12.
- Betancourt, Gerardo (2015): A theoretical model for intervening in complex sexual behaviours. Sexual desires, pleasures and passion - La Pasi3n - of Spanish-speaking gay men in Canada. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 159–172.
- Boas, Erica M. (2012): Walking the Line. Teaching, Being, and Thinking Sexuality in Elementary School. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 131–144.
- Burke, Kevin (2014): Impossible Women. Saints, Sinner, and the Gendered Mythology in a Catholic School. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 25–37.
- Casemore, Brian (2012): "A Different Idea" in the Sex Education Curriculum. Thinking Through the Emotional Experience of Sexuality. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): *Sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 321–335.
- Desjardins, Michel (2012): The Sexualized Body of the Child. Parents and the Politics of "Voluntary" Sterilization of People Labeled Intellectually Disabled. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 69–88.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; G3rzig, Anke (2012): Sexting: the exchange of sexual messages online among European youth. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke G3rzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 151–164.
- Ouer, Freedom (2014): It's Not How Regular Boys Are Supposed to Act. The Nonnormative Sexual Practices of Black Boys in All-Male Public Schools. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 357–369.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2014): "What's wrong with Porn?". Engaging with Contemporary Painting to Explore the Commodification of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 78–95.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen; Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise (2014): After-Word(s). Engaging with the Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education: Affordances and Provocations. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): *The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 186–195.
- Rivers, Ian (2013): Cyberbullying and cyberaggression. Sexualised and gendered experiences explored. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): *Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender*. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 19–44.
- Best, Joel; Bogle, Kathleen A. (2014): Kids gone wild. From rainbow parties to sexting, understanding the hype over teen sex. New York [u.a.]: New York Univ. Press.
- Elliott, Sinikka (2012): Not my kid. What parents believe about the sex lives of their teenagers. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press.
- Garcia, Lorena (2012): Respect yourself, protect yourself. Latina girls and sexual identity. New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press (Intersections / [New York University Press]).
- Powell, Anastasia (2010): Sex, Power and Consent. Youth Culture and the Unwritten Rules. Port Melbourne, Vic.: Cambridge University Press.
- Sanjakdar, Fida (2012): Living west, facing east. The deconstruction of Muslim youth's sexual identities. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints, 364).
- Shariff, Shaheen (2015): Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013): Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications. Hove: Psychology.

- Lemma, Alessandra; Lynch, Paul E. (Hg.) (2015): *Sexualities. Contemporary psychoanalytic perspectives*. London, New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Albury, Kath (2013): Young people, media and sexual learning. Rethinking representation. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S32–S44. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.767194.
- Ali, Mir M.; Dwyer, Debra S. (2011): Estimating peer effects in sexual behavior among adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 183–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.12.008.
- Allen, Louisa (2011): 'Picture this'. Using photo-methods in research on sexualities and schooling. In: *Qualitative Research* 11 (5), S. 487–504. DOI: 10.1177/1468794111413224.
- Almond, Tracy Jane (2014): Working with children and young people with harmful sexual behaviours. Exploring impact on practitioners and sources of support. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 333–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836576.
- Attwood, Feona; Smith, Clarissa (2011): Investigating young people's sexual cultures. An introduction. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* (Vol. 11 No. 3), S. 235–242.
- Bajaj, Monika (2012): Vesicular Genital Lesions in a Toddler – Is it Sexual Abuse? In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (5), S. 370–373. DOI: 10.1002/car.1188.
- Bale, Clare (2011): Raunch or romance? Framing and interpreting the relationship between sexualized culture and young people's sexual health. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 303–313. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590088.
- Baumgartner, Susanne E.; Valkenburg, Patti M.; Peter, Jochen (2010): Assessing causality in the relationship between adolescents' risky sexual online behavior and their perceptions of this behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1226–1239. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9512-y.
- Biswas, Bipasha; Vaughn, Michael G. (2011): Really troubled girls. Gender differences in risky sexual behavior and its correlates in a sample of juvenile offenders. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 33 (11), S. 2386–2391. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2011.08.010.
- Boislard P., Marie-Aude; Poulin, Francois (2011): Individual, familial, friends-related and contextual predictors of early sexual intercourse. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 289–300. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.05.002.
- Boisvert, Stéphanie; Poulin, François (2016): Romantic Relationship Patterns from Adolescence to Emerging Adulthood: Associations with Family and Peer Experiences in Early Adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 945–958. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0435-0.
- Boratav, Hale Bolak; Çavdar, Alev (2012): Sexual stereotypes and practices of university students in Turkey. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (1), S. 271–281. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9811-8.
- Brunnberg, Elinor; Lindén Boström, Margareta; Berglund, Mats (2012): Sexual force at sexual debut. Swedish adolescents with disabilities at higher risk than adolescents without disabilities. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (4), S. 285–295.
- Campero, Lourdes; Walker, Dilys; Atienzo, Erika E.; Gutierrez, Juan Pablo (2011): A quasi-experimental evaluation of parents as sexual health educators resulting in delayed sexual initiation and increased access to condoms. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 215–223. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.05.010.
- Carlson, Daniel L.; McNulty, Thomas L.; Bellair, Paul E.; Watts, Stephen (2014): Neighborhoods and racial/ethnic disparities in adolescent sexual risk behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (9), S. 1536–1549. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0052-0.
- Carter, Rona; Williams, Sandra (2016): Self-perceptions of pubertal timing and patterns of peer group activities and dating behavior among heterosexual adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 47, S. 71–80. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.12.006.
- Cavazos-Rehg, Patricia A.; Spitznagel, Edward L.; Bucholz, Kathleen K.; Nurnberger, John; Edenberg, Howard J.; Kramer, John R. et al. (2010): Predictors of sexual debut at age 16 or younger. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 664–673. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9397-y.
- Coyne, Sarah M.; Padilla-Walker, Laura M. (2015): Sex, violence, & rock n' roll. Longitudinal effects of music on aggression, sex, and prosocial behavior during adolescence. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 41, S. 96–104. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.03.002.

- Crichton, Joanna; Ibisomi, Latifat; Gyimah, Stephen Obeng (2012): Mother-daughter communication about sexual maturation, abstinence and unintended pregnancy. Experiences from an informal settlement in Nairobi, Kenya. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 21–30. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.06.008.
- Dahlbäck, Elisabeth; Maimbolwa, Margaret; Yamba, C. Bawa; Kasonka, Lackson; Bergström, Staffan; Ransjö-Arvidson, Anna-Berit (2010): Pregnancy loss. Spontaneous and induced abortions among young women in Lusaka, Zambia. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 247–262. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903353383.
- Das, Aniruddha; Otis, Nicholas (2016): Sexual Contact in Childhood, Revictimization, and Lifetime Sexual and Psychological Outcomes. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1117–1131. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0620-3.
- Das, Aniruddha; Otis, Nicholas (2016): Sexual Contact in Childhood, Revictimization, and Lifetime Sexual and Psychological Outcomes. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1117–1131.
- Dickenson, Janna A.; Huebner, David M. (2016): The Relationship Between Sexual Activity and Depressive Symptoms in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth: Effects of Gender and Family Support. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (3), S. 671–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0571-8.
- Epstein, Debbie; Kehily, Mary Jane; Renold, E. (2012): Culture, policy and the un/marked child. Fragments of the sexualisation debates. In: *Gender and Education* 24 (3), S. 249–254. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2012.670390.
- Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2012): Young women's adolescent experiences of oral sex. Relation of age of initiation to sexual motivation, sexual coercion, and psychological functioning. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (5), S. 1191–1201. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.03.010.
- Fielder, Robyn L.; Carey, Michael P. (2010): Predictors and consequences of sexual "hookups" among college students: a short-term prospective study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1105–1119. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9448-4.
- Fielder, Robyn L.; Walsh, Jennifer L.; Carey, Kate B.; Carey, Michael P. (2013): Predictors of sexual hookups: a theory-based, prospective study of first-year college women. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1425–1441. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0106-0.
- Firmin, Carlene; Warrington, Camille; Pearce, Jenny (2017): Sexual Exploitation and Its Impact on Developing Sexualities and Sexual Relationships. The Need for Contextual Social Work Interventions. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2318–2337. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw134.
- Flanagan, Paul (2012): Ethical review and reflexivity in research of children's sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 535–544. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627731.
- Fredlund, Cecilia; Svensson, Frida; Svedin, Carl Goran; Priebe, Gisela; Wadsby, Marie (2013): Adolescents' lifetime experience of selling sex. Development over five years. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (3), S. 312–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.743950.
- Galinsky, Adena M.; Sonenstein, Freya Lund (2013): Relationship commitment, perceived equity, and sexual enjoyment among young adults in the United States. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (1), S. 93–104. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0003-y.
- Gartrell, Nanette K.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Goldberg, Naomi G. (2011): Adolescents of the U.S. National Longitudinal Lesbian Family Study: sexual orientation, sexual behavior, and sexual risk exposure. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (6), S. 1199–1209. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9692-2.
- Genna, Natacha M. de; Larkby, Cynthia; Cornelius, Marie D. (2011): Pubertal timing and early sexual intercourse in the offspring of teenage mothers. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (10), S. 1315–1328. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9609-3.
- Goodrum, Nada M.; Armistead, Lisa P.; Tully, Erin C.; Cook, Sarah L.; Skinner, Donald (2017): Parenting and youth sexual risk in context. The role of community factors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 57, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.013.
- Graaf, Hanneke de; van de Schoot, Rens; Woertman, Liesbeth; Hawk, Skyler T.; Meeus, Wim (2012): Family cohesion and romantic and sexual initiation: a three wave longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 583–592. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9708-9.
- Greslé-Favier, Claire (2010): The legacy of abstinence-only discourses and the place of pleasure in US discourses on teenage sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515098.

- Hensel, Devon J.; Fortenberry, J. Dennis; O'Sullivan, Lucia F.; Orr, Donald P. (2011): The developmental association of sexual self-concept with sexual behavior among adolescent women. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 675–684. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.09.005.
- Heywood, Wendy; Patrick, Kent; Pitts, Marian; Mitchell, Anne (2016): "Dude, I'm Seventeen ... It's Okay Not to Have Sex by This Age": Feelings, Reasons, Pressures, and Intentions Reported by Adolescents Who Have Not Had Sexual Intercourse. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (9), S. 1207–1214. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2015.1092105.
- Hipwell, Alison E.; Stepp, Stephanie D.; Keenan, Kate; Chung, Tammy; Loeber, Rolf (2011): Brief report: Parsing the heterogeneity of adolescent girls' sexual behavior. Relationships to individual and interpersonal factors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (3), S. 589–592. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.03.002.
- Hirst, Julia (2013): 'It's got to be about enjoying yourself'. Young people, sexual pleasure, and sex and relationships education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 423–436. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.747433.
- James, Adilia E. E. (2010): Too Early to Talk About Sex? Issues in Creating Culturally Relevant Sexuality Education for Preadolescent Black Girls in the United States. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (2), S. 128–141. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0012-3.
- Johnson, Matthew D. (2013): Parent-child relationship quality directly and indirectly influences hooking up behavior reported in young adulthood through alcohol use in adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1463–1472. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0098-9.
- Johnston, Lisa G.; Mon, Myo Myo; Steinhaus, Mara; Sass, Justine (2017): Correlates of Forced Sex Among Young Men Who Have Sex With Men in Yangon and Monywa, Myanmar. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 1001–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0761-z.
- Kaestle, Christine E.; Allen, Katherine R. (2011): The role of masturbation in healthy sexual development: perceptions of young adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 983–994. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9722-0.
- Katz, Jennifer; Schneider, Monica E. (2013): Casual hook up sex during the first year of college: Prospective associations with attitudes about sex and love relationships. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1451–1462. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0078-0.
- Kehily, Mary Jane (2012): Contextualising the sexualisation of girls debate. Innocence, experience and young female sexuality. In: *Gender and Education* 24 (3), S. 255–268. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2012.670391.
- Kelly, Angela; Worth, Heather; Akuani, Frances; Kepa, Barbara; Kupul, Martha; Walizopa, Lucy et al. (2010): Gendered talk about sex, sexual relationships and HIV among young people in Papua New Guinea. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 221–232. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903181107.
- Kennett, Deborah J.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Schultz, Kristen E. (2011): Sexual resourcefulness and the impact of family, sex education, media and peers. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615624.
- Lee, Sally; Fenge, Lee-Ann (2017): Sexual Well-Being and Physical Disability. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2263–2281. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw107.
- Lefkowitz, Eva S.; Vasilenko, Sara A.; Leavitt, Chelom E. (2016): Oral vs. Vaginal Sex Experiences and Consequences Among First-Year College Students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (2), S. 329–337. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0654-6.
- Lindroth, Malin (2014): Sex education and young people in group homes. Balancing risks, rights and resilience in sexual health promotion. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 400–413. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919910.
- Livingston, Jennifer A.; Testa, Maria; Windle, Michael; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2015): Sexual risk at first coitus. Does alcohol make a difference? In: *Journal of Adolescence* 43, S. 148–158. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.05.018.
- Looze, Margaretha de; Harakeh, Zeena; van Dorsselaer, Saskia A. F. M.; Raaijmakers, Quinten A. W.; Vollebergh, Wilma A. M.; ter Bogt, Tom F. M. (2012): Explaining educational differences in adolescent substance use and early sexual debut. The role of parents and peers. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 1035–1044. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.02.009.

- Lopez, Vera; Kopak, Albert; Robillard, Alyssa; Gillmore, Mary Rogers; Holliday, Rhonda C.; Braithwaite, Ronald L. (2011): Pathways to sexual risk taking among female adolescent detainees. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (8), S. 945–957. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9623-5.
- Luder, Marie-Thérèse; Pittet, Isabelle; Berchtold, André; Akre, Christina; Michaud, Pierre-André; Surís, Joan-Carles (2011): Associations between online pornography and sexual behavior among adolescents: myth or reality? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1027–1035. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9714-0.
- Lyons, Heidi; Manning, Wendy; Giordano, Peggy; Longmore, Monica (2013): Predictors of heterosexual casual sex among young adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 585–593. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0051-3.
- Macapagal, Kathryn; Janssen, Erick; Matson, Margaret; Finn, Peter R.; Heiman, Julia R. (2017): The Impact of Gain- and Loss-Framed Messages on Young Adults' Sexual Decision Making: An Experimental Study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (2), S. 385–394. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0679-x.
- Makin-Byrd, Kerry; Bierman, Karen L. (2013): Individual and family predictors of the perpetration of dating violence and victimization in late adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 536–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9810-7.
- Malón, Agustín (2015): Adult-Child Sex and the Limits of Liberal Sexual Morality. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (4), S. 1071–1083.
- Martin, Karin A.; Verduzco Baker, Lynn; Torres, Jennifer; Luke, Katherine (2011): Privates, pee-pees, and coochies. Gender and genital labeling for/with young children. In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (3), S. 420–430. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510384832.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa (2015): Prevalence of dating violence among sexual minority youth: variation across gender, sexual minority identity and gender of sexual partners. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 211–224. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0089-0.
- McCann, Edward; Lee, Regina; Brown, Michael (2016): The experiences and support needs of people with intellectual disabilities who identify as LGBT: A review of the literature. In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 57, S. 39–53. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2016.06.013.
- McMichael, Celia; Gifford, Sandra (2010): Narratives of sexual health risk and protection amongst young people from refugee backgrounds in Melbourne, Australia. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 263–277. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903359265.
- McMillan, Karen; Worth, Heather (2011): The impact of socio-cultural context on young people's condom use. Evidence from two Pacific Island countries. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (3), S. 313–326. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.529945.
- Milan, Stephanie; Wortel, Sanne (2015): Family obligation values as a protective and vulnerability factor among low-income adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (6), S. 1183–1193. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0206-8.
- Milhausen, Robin R.; Buchholz, Andrea C.; Opperman, Emily A.; Benson, Lindsay E. (2015): Relationships Between Body Image, Body Composition, Sexual Functioning, and Sexual Satisfaction Among Heterosexual Young Adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (6), S. 1621–1633. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0328-9.
- Miller, S. A. (2016): "How You Bully a Girl". Sexual Drama and the Negotiation of Gendered Sexuality in High School. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (5), S. 721–744. DOI: 10.1177/0891243216664723.
- Miller, Shari; Williams, Jason; Cutbush, Stacey; Gibbs, Deborah; Clinton-Sherrod, Monique; Jones, Sarah (2013): Dating violence, bullying, and sexual harassment: longitudinal profiles and transitions over time. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 607–618. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9914-8.
- Mora, Claudia; Monteiro, Simone (2010): Vulnerability to STIs/HIV. Sociability and the life trajectories of young women who have sex with women in Rio de Janeiro. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 115–124. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903180471.
- Muehlenhard, Charlene L.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D. (2016): The Complexities of Sexual Consent Among College Students. A Conceptual and Empirical Review. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (4-5), S. 1–31.

- Muhanguzi, Florence Kyoheirwe (2011): Gender and sexual vulnerability of young women in Africa. Experiences of young girls in secondary schools in Uganda. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 713–725. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.571290.
- Muise, Amy; Preyde, Michéle; Maitland, Scott B.; Milhausen, Robin R. (2010): Sexual identity and sexual well-being in female heterosexual university students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (4), S. 915–925. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9492-8.
- Munoz-Laboy, Miguel; Murray, Laura R.; Wittlin, Natalie; Wilson, Patrick A.; Terto, Veriano; Parker, Richard (2011): Divine targets. Youth at the centre of Catholic and Pentecostal responses to HIV and AIDS in Brazil. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 657–668. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.565519.
- Newby, Katie; Wallace, Louise M.; Dunn, Orla; Brown, Katherine E. (2012): A survey of English teenagers' sexual experience and preferences for school-based sex education. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 231–251. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615582.
- O'Hara, Ross E.; Cooper, M. Lynne (2015): Bidirectional associations between alcohol use and sexual risk-taking behavior from adolescence into young adulthood. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (4), S. 857–871. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0510-8.
- Oidtman, Jessica; Sherman, Susan G.; Morgan, Anthony; German, Danielle; Arrington-Sanders, Renata (2017): Satisfaction and Condomless Anal Sex at Sexual Debut and Sexual Risk Among Young Black Same-Sex Attracted Men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 947–959. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0831-2.
- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Billen, Rhett M.; Conrad, Kathryn A.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Sex, commitment, and casual sex relationships among college men: a mixed-methods analysis. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 561–571. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0047-z.
- Olmstead, Spencer B.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013): Hooking up and penetrative hookups: correlates that differentiate college men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 573–583. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-9907-9.
- Parchomiuk, Monika (2012): Specialists and Sexuality of Individuals with Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (4), S. 407–419. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9249-x.
- Parkes, Alison; Wight, Daniel; Henderson, Marion; West, Patrick (2010): Does early sexual debut reduce teenagers' participation in tertiary education? Evidence from the SHARE longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (5), S. 741–754. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.006.
- Patrick, Megan E.; Lee, Christine M. (2010): Sexual motivations and engagement in sexual behavior during the transition to college. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 674–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9435-9.
- Patrick, Megan E.; Maggs, Jennifer L. (2010): Profiles of motivations for alcohol use and sexual behavior among first-year university students. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (5), S. 755–765. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.003.
- Patrick, Megan E.; Morgan, Nicole; Maggs, Jennifer L.; Lefkowitz, Eva S. (2011): "I got your back": friends' understandings regarding college student spring break behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (1), S. 108–120. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9515-8.
- Peter, Jochen; Valkenburg, Patti M. (2011): The use of sexually explicit internet material and its antecedents: a longitudinal comparison of adolescents and adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1015–1025. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9644-x.
- Pradhan, Manas Ranjan; Ram, Usha (2010): Perceived gender role that shape youth sexual behaviour. Evidence from rural Orissa, India. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (4), S. 543–551. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.014.
- Raine, Tina R.; Gard, Jennifer C.; Boyer, Cherrie B.; Haider, Sadia; Brown, Beth A.; Ramirez Hernandez, F. Antonio; Harper, Cynthia C. (2010): Contraceptive decision-making in sexual relationships. Young men's experiences, attitudes and values. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 373–386. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903524769.
- Rellini, Alessandra H.; Elinson, Samantha; Janssen, Erick; Meston, Cindy M. (2012): The effect of pre-existing affect on the sexual responses of women with and without a history of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (2), S. 329–339. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9772-y.
- Rellini, Alessandra H.; Meston, Cindy M. (2011): Sexual self-schemas, sexual dysfunction, and the sexual responses of women with a history of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (2), S. 351–362. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9694-0.

- Rice, Eric; Winetrobe, Hailey; Holloway, Ian W.; Montoya, Jorge; Plant, Aaron; Kordic, Timothy (2015): Cell phone internet access, online sexual solicitation, partner seeking, and sexual risk behavior among adolescents. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 755–763. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0366-3.
- Rossi, Erika; Poulin, François; Boislard, Marie-Aude (2017): Trajectories of Annual Number of Sexual Partners from Adolescence to Emerging Adulthood: Individual and Family Predictors. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 995–1008. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0571-6.
- Seidel, Anja; Wienholz, Sabine; Michel, Marion; Lupp, Melanie; Riedel-Heller, Steffi Gerlinde (2014): Sexual Knowledge Among Adolescents with Physical Handicaps. A Systematic Review. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (3), S. 429–441. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9326-4.
- Shandra, Carrie L.; Chowdhury, Afra R. (2012): The first sexual experience among adolescent girls with and without disabilities. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (4), S. 515–532. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9668-0.
- Shrier, Lydia A.; Feldman, Henry A.; Black, Shimrit K.; Walls, Courtney; Kendall, Ashley D.; Lops, Christopher; Beardslee, William R. (2012): Momentary affective states surrounding sexual intercourse in depressed adolescents and young adults. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (5), S. 1161–1171. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9787-4.
- Sipsma, Heather L.; Ickovics, Jeannette R.; Lin, Haiqun; Kershaw, Trace S. (2015): The impact of future expectations on adolescent sexual risk behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 170–183. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0082-7.
- Slotboom, Anne-Marie; Hendriks, Jan; Verbruggen, Janna (2011): Contrasting adolescent female and male sexual aggression. A self-report study on prevalence and predictors of sexual aggression. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 15–33. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.544413.
- Smiler, Andrew P.; Frankel, Loren B. W.; Savin-Williams, Ritch C. (2011): From kissing to coitus? Sex-of-partner differences in the sexual milestone achievement of young men. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 727–735. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.08.009.
- Sommer, Marni; Likindikoki, Samuel; Kaaya, Sylvia (2015): "Bend a fish when the fish is not yet dry": adolescent boys' perceptions of sexual risk in Tanzania. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 583–595. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0406-z.
- Sorhaindo, Annik; Bonell, Chris; Fletcher, Adam; Jessiman, Patricia; Keogh, Peter; Mitchell, Kirstin (2016): Being targeted. Young women's experience of being identified for a teenage pregnancy prevention programme. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 181–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.03.013.
- Spišák, Sanna; Paasonen, Susanna (2017): Bad education? Childhood recollections of pornography, sexual exploration, learning and agency in Finland. In: *Childhood* 24 (1), S. 99–112. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216646436.
- Šribar, Renata (2013): Growing-up challenged and challenging. Gender and sexuality norms in referential research on 'internet risks' and in children. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (1), S. 129–145. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.748681.
- Stevens-Watkins, Danelle; Brown-Wright, Lynda; Tyler, Kenneth (2011): Brief report. The number of sexual partners and race-related stress in African American adolescents: preliminary findings. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 191–194. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.02.003.
- Stulhofer, Aleksandar; Busko, Vesna; Landripet, Ivan (2010): Pornography, sexual socialization, and satisfaction among young men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (1), S. 168–178. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9387-0.
- Swenson, Rebecca R.; Houck, Christopher D.; Barker, David; Zeanah, Paula D.; Brown, Larry K. (2012): Prospective analysis of the transition to sexual experience and changes in sexual self-esteem among adolescents attending therapeutic schools. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 77–85. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.06.002.
- Thompson, Ashley E.; Byers, E. Sandra (2017): Heterosexual Young Adults' Interest, Attitudes, and Experiences Related to Mixed-Gender, Multi-Person Sex. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 813–822. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0699-1.
- Thrane, Lisa E.; Chen, Xiaojin (2012): Impact of running away on girls' pregnancy. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (2), S. 443–449. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.07.011.
- Tsaliki, Liza (2015): Popular culture and moral panics about 'children at risk'. Revisiting the sexualisation-of-young-girls debate. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 500–514. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1022893.

- Vaillancourt-Morel, Marie-Pier; Godbout, Natacha; Labadie, Chloé; Runtz, Marsha; Lussier, Yvan; Sabourin, Stéphane (2015): Avoidant and compulsive sexual behaviors in male and female survivors of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 40, S. 48–59.
- van Oosten, Johanna M. F. (2016): Sexually Explicit Internet Material and Adolescents' Sexual Uncertainty: The Role of Disposition-Content Congruency. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (4), S. 1011–1022. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0594-1.
- van Oosten, Johanna M. F.; Peter, Jochen; Boot, Inge (2015): Exploring associations between exposure to sexy online self-presentations and adolescents' sexual attitudes and behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 1078–1091. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0194-8.
- van Ryzin, Mark J.; Johnson, Amber B.; Leve, Leslie D.; Kim, Hyoun K. (2011): The number of sexual partners and health-risking sexual behavior: prediction from high school entry to high school exit. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 939–949. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9649-5.
- Vandenbosch, Laura; Eggermont, Steven (2015): The role of mass media in adolescents' sexual behaviors: exploring the explanatory value of the three-step self-objectification process. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 729–742. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0292-4.
- Vannier, Sarah A.; O'Sullivan, Lucia F. (2012): Who gives and who gets: why, when, and with whom young people engage in oral sex. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 572–582. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9745-z.
- Vasilenko, Sara A.; Ram, Nilam; Lefkowitz, Eva S. (2011): Body image and first sexual intercourse in late adolescence. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 327–335. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.04.005.
- Velezmoro, Rodrigo; Negy, Charles; Livia, Jose (2012): Online sexual activity: cross-national comparison between United States and Peruvian college students. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1015–1025. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9862-x.
- Verhoef, Melissa; van den Eijnden, Regina J. J. M.; Koning, Ina M.; Vollebergh, Wilma A. M. (2014): Age at menarche and adolescent alcohol use. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1333–1345. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0075-6.
- Wargo Aikins, Julie; Simon, Valerie A.; Prinstein, Mitchell J. (2010): Romantic partner selection and socialization of young adolescents' substance use and behavior problems. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (6), S. 813–826. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.07.007.
- Wetherill, Reagan R.; Neal, Dan J.; Fromme, Kim (2010): Parents, peers, and sexual values influence sexual behavior during the transition to college. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 682–694. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9476-8.
- Wienholz, Sabine; Seidel, Anja; Michel, Marion; Haeussler-Sczepan, Monika; Riedel-Heller, Steffi Gerlinde (2016): Sexual Experiences of Adolescents With and Without Disabilities. Results from a Cross-Sectional Study. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 171–182. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9433-0.
- Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014): Why All the Talk About Sex? An Autoethnography Identifying the Troubling Discourse of Sexuality and Intellectual Disability. In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 107–116. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9331-7.
- Winskell, Kate; Beres, Laura K.; Hill, Elizabeth; Mbakwem, Benjamin Chigozie; Obyerodhyambo, Oby (2011): Making sense of abstinence. Social representations in young Africans' HIV-related narratives from six countries. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 945–959. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.591431.
- Wong, Carolyn F.; Kipke, Michele D.; Weiss, George; McDavitt, Bryce (2010): The impact of recent stressful experiences on HIV-risk related behaviors. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (3), S. 463–475. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.06.004.
- Zimmer-Gembeck, Melanie J.; Ducat, Wendy H.; Boislard-Pepin, Marie-Aude (2011): A prospective study of young females' sexual subjectivity: associations with age, sexual behavior, and dating. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 927–938. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9751-3.

8. Forschung

8.1. Forschungsethik

Schmidt, Sandra J. (2012): Let Me in! The Impact of the Discourse of Impossibility on Research and Curricular (Re)form. In: Erica R. Meiners und Therese Quinn (Hg.): Sexualities in education. A reader. New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367), S. 199–214.

Chappell, Paul; Rule, Peter; Dlamini, Mfana; Nkala, Nompilo (2014): Troubling power dynamics. Youth with disabilities as co-researchers in sexuality research in South Africa. In: *Childhood* 21 (3), S. 385–399. DOI: 10.1177/0907568214525427.

Fagerlund, Monica; Ellonen, Noora (2016): Children's Experiences of Completing a Computer-Based Violence Survey. Finnish Child Victim Survey Revisited. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 556–576. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1186769.

Flanagan, Paul (2012): Ethical review and reflexivity in research of children's sexuality. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 535–544. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627731.

Hutchfield, Jemeela; Coren, Esther (2011): The Child's Voice in Service Evaluation. Ethical and Methodological Issues. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 173–186. DOI: 10.1002/car.1142.

James, Adilia E. E. (2010): Too Early to Talk About Sex? Issues in Creating Culturally Relevant Sexuality Education for Preadolescent Black Girls in the United States. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (2), S. 128–141. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0012-3.

Kuyper, Lisette; Wit, John de; Adam, Philippe; Woertman, Liesbeth (2012): Doing more good than harm? The effects of participation in sex research on young people in the Netherlands. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (2), S. 497–506. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9780-y.

Low, Sabina; Polanin, Joshua R.; Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): The role of social networks in physical and relational aggression among young adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1078–1089. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9933-5.

Masson, Helen; Balfe, Myles; Hackett, Simon; Phillips, Josie (2012): Making use of historical case material. The problems of looking back and the implications for service development in relation to research and evaluation activities. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 112–122. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.630539.

Moilanen, Kristin L. (2016): Why Do Parents Grant or Deny Consent for Adolescent Participation in Sexuality Research? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 1020–1036. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0445-y.

Moore, Tim P.; McArthur, Morag; Noble-Carr, Debbie (2017): More a marathon than a hurdle. Towards children's informed consent in a study on safety. In: *Qualitative Research* 7 (2), 146879411770070. DOI: 10.1177/1468794117700708.

Priebe, Gisela; Bäckström, Martin; Ainsaar, Mare (2010): Vulnerable adolescent participants' experience in surveys on sexuality and sexual abuse. Ethical aspects. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34 (6), S. 438–447.

Rinehart, Jenny K.; Nason, Erica E.; Yeater, Elizabeth A.; Miller, Geoffrey F. (2017): Do Some Students Need Special Protection From Research on Sex and Trauma? New Evidence for Young Adult Resilience in "Sensitive Topics" Research. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (3), S. 273–283. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1156047.

Roberts, Susan (2011): Doing Research with Imprisoned Adult Male Child Sexual Abusers. Reflecting on the Challenges. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 187–196. DOI: 10.1002/car.1175.

Wager, Nadia (2011): Researching Sexual Revictimisation. Associated Ethical and Methodological Issues, and Possible Solutions. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 158–172. DOI: 10.1002/car.1152.

Walsh, Kerryann; Mathews, Ben; Rassafiani, Mehdi; Farrell, Ann; Butler, Des (2012): Understanding teachers' reporting of child sexual abuse. Measurement methods matter. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (9), S. 1937–1946. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.06.004.

8.2. Theorie

Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2016): Heterosexist Discourses. How Feminist Theory Shaped Campus Sexual Violence Policy. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge, S. 33–52.

- Casella, Ronnie (2014): The Historical and political roots of school violence in South Africa. Developing a cross-national theory. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 38–56.
- Chapman, Amy; Buchanan, Rachel (2014): FYI... Virtual space has a context. Towards an alternative frame for understanding cyberbullying. In: Sue Saltmarsh (Hg.): Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 56–71.
- Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): Bullying and sexual violence. Definition, prevalence, outcomes and moderators. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 31–44.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Haddon, Leslie (2012): Theoretical framework for children's internet use. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 1–14.
- Livingstone, Sonia M.; Hasebrink, Uwe; Görzig, Anke (2012): Towards a general model of determinants of risk and safety. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 323–338.
- Maxwell, Claire (2014): The Prevention of Sexual Violence in Schools: Developing Some Theoretical Starting Points. In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 105–127.
- Mollow, Anna (2012): Is Sex Disability? Queer Theory and the Disability Drive. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): Sex and disability. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 285–312.
- Moss, Donald (2015): Sexual aberrations: do we still need the concept? If so, when and why? If not, why not? In: Alessandra Lemma und Paul E. Lynch (Hg.): Sexualities. Contemporary psychoanalytic perspectives. London, New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group, S. 177–188.
- Thomas-Card, Traci; Eichele, Katie (2012): Comprehensive College- or University-Based Sexual Violence Prevention and Direct Services Program. A Framework. In: Laura M. Carpenter und John D. DeLamater (Hg.): Sex for life. From virginity to Viagra, how sexuality changes throughout our lives. New York: New York University Press (Intersections), S. 149–169.
- Vincent, Louise; Macleod, Catriona (2014): Introducing a Critical Pedagogy of Sexual and Reproductive Citizenship: Extending the 'Framework of Thick Desire'. In: Louisa Allen, Mary Louise Rasmussen und Kathleen Quinlivan (Hg.): The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education), S. 115–136.
- Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013): Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications. Hove: Psychology.
- Henry, Nicola; Powell, Anastasia (Hg.) (2014): Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Albury, Kath (2013): Young people, media and sexual learning. Rethinking representation. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S32-S44. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.767194.
- Anderson, Jane (2016): Socialization Processes and Clergy Offenders. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (8), S. 846–865. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1241333.
- Ávila, Marisa; Cabral, Joana; Matos, Paula Mena (2012): Identity in university students. The role of parental and romantic attachment. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 133–142. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.05.002.
- Braje, Sopagna Eap; Eddy, J. Mark; Hall, Gordon C. N. (2016): A Comparison of Two Models of Risky Sexual Behavior During Late Adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (1), S. 73–83. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0523-3.
- Brooks-Russell, Ashley; Foshee, Vangie A.; Ennett, Susan T. (2013): Predictors of latent trajectory classes of physical dating violence victimization. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 566–580. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9876-2.
- Gilbert, Jen (2015): Walking through the school: the erotics of research. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 111–115. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1094947.

- Grondin, Anne-Marie (2011): Thinking outside specious boxes. Constructionist and post-structuralist readings of 'child sexual abuse'. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 243–254. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590065.
- Haboush, Karen L.; Alyan, Hala (2013): "Who can you tell?" Features of Arab culture that influence conceptualization and treatment of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 499–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800935.
- Haggis, Jane; Mulholland, Monique (2013): Rethinking difference and sex education. From cultural inclusivity to normative diversity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (1), S. 57–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.824873.
- Huang, Yu-Te; Souleymanov, Rusty (2016): Rethinking Epistemological Debates and Transnationalism of Sexuality between the West and Taiwan. Implications for Social Workers. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (1), S. 98–114. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu067.
- Jones, Tiffany Mary (2011): Saving rhetorical children. Sexuality education discourses from conservative to post-modern. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 369–387. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595229.
- Maxwell, Louise; Scott, Graham (2014): A review of the role of radical feminist theories in the understanding of rape myth acceptance. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 40–54. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.773384.
- O'Leary, P.; Tsui, M.-S.; Ruch, G. (2013): The Boundaries of the Social Work Relationship Revisited. Towards a Connected, Inclusive and Dynamic Conceptualisation. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 43 (1), S. 135–153. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcr181.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2012): Popular culture as emotional provocation. The material enactment of queer pedagogies in a high school classroom. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 511–522. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627728.
- Rasmussen, Lucinda A. (2013): Young people who sexually abuse. A historical perspective and future directions. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (1), S. 119–141. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.744646.
- Ross, Colin A. (2017): Response to Miccio-Fonseca (2015) and Defeo (2015) Concerning Commentary About DSM-5 Sexual Disorders Section. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 92–95. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1263263.
- Seto, Michael C. (2012): Is pedophilia a sexual orientation? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (1), S. 231–236. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9882-6.
- Whittier, Nancy (2016): Where Are the Children? Theorizing the Missing Piece in Gendered Sexual Violence. In: *Gender & Society* 30 (1), S. 95–108. DOI: 10.1177/0891243215612412.

8.3. Methodologie

- Görzig, Anke (2012): Methodological framework. The EU Kids Online project. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 15–32.
- Luschen, Kristen V. (2014): Survival, Protection, and Forgiveness. Examining Gendered Violence and Care in the Hunger Games Trilogy. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 133–146.
- Migdalek, Jack (2014): Challenging Gendered Practices Through Drama. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 414–425.
- Ogan, Christine; Karakus, Türkan; Kursun, Engin; Cagiltay, Kürsat; Kasikci, Duygu (2012): Cognitive interviewing and response to EU Kids Online survey questions. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): *Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective*. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 33–44.
- Pendleton Jiménez, Karleen (2014): Off the Script. A Study of Techniques for Uncovering Gender-Bending Truths in the Classroom. In: Elizabeth J. Meyer und Dennis Carlson (Hg.): *Gender and sexualities in education. A reader*. New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5), S. 257–271.

- Pullen Sansfacon, Annie; Manning, Kimberley Ens (2015): Maximising research outcomes for trans children and their families in Canada inquiry. Using social action and other participatory methods of. In: Julie Fish und Kate Karban (Hg.): *Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work*. Bristol: Policy Press, S. 223–236.
- Shuttleworth, Russell (2012): Bridging Theory and Experience: A Critical-Interpretative Ethnography of Sexuality and Disability. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): *Sex and disability*. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 54–69.
- Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013): *Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications*. Hove: Psychology.
- Ponzetti, James J. (Hg.) (2016): *Evidence-based approaches to sexuality education. A global perspective (Textbooks in family studies series)*.
- Albury, Kath (2013): Young people, media and sexual learning. Rethinking representation. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S32–S44. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.767194.
- Allen, Louisa (2011): 'Picture this'. Using photo-methods in research on sexualities and schooling. In: *Qualitative Research* 11 (5), S. 487–504. DOI: 10.1177/14687941111413224.
- Anderson, Gwendolyn D. (2016): The Continuum of Disclosure. Exploring Factors Predicting Tentative Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations During Forensic Interviews and the Implications for Practice, Policy, and Future Research. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 382–402. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153559.
- Arrington-Sanders, Renata; Harper, Gary W.; Morgan, Anthony; Ogunbajo, Adedotun; Trent, Maria; Fortenberry, J. Dennis (2015): The role of sexually explicit material in the sexual development of same-sex-attracted Black adolescent males. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 597–608. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0416-x.
- Attwood, Feona; Smith, Clarissa (2011): Investigating young people's sexual cultures. An introduction. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* (Vol. 11 No. 3), S. 235–242.
- Babatsikos, Georgia (2010): Parents' knowledge, attitudes and practices about preventing child sexual abuse. A literature review. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (2), S. 107–129. DOI: 10.1002/car.1102.
- Babchishin, Kelly M.; Nunes, Kevin L.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Malcom, J. Renee (2015): Implicit sexual interest in children. Does separating gender influence discrimination when using the Implicit Association Test? In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 194–208. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836575.
- Balfe, Myles; Gallagher, Bernard; Masson, Helen; Balfe, Shane; Brugha, Ruairi; Hackett, Simon (2015): Internet Child Sex Offenders' Concerns about Online Security and their Use of Identity Protection Technologies. A Review. In: *Child Abuse Review* 24 (6), S. 427–439. DOI: 10.1002/car.2308.
- Barron, Ian G.; Topping, Keith J. (2011): Sexual abuse prevention programme fidelity. Video analysis of interactions. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 134–151. DOI: 10.1002/car.1134.
- Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Fava, Nicole M. (2014): What puts "At-Risk Girls" at risk? Sexual vulnerability and social inequality in the lives of girls in the child welfare system. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 116–125. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0142-5.
- Benia, Luis Roberto; Hauck-Filho, Nelson; Dillenburg, Mariana; Stein, Lilian Milnitsky (2015): The NICHD Investigative Interview Protocol. A Meta-Analytic Review. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 259–279. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006749.
- Brooks-Russell, Ashley; Foshee, Vangie A.; Ennett, Susan T. (2013): Predictors of latent trajectory classes of physical dating violence victimization. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 566–580. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9876-2.
- Burchardt, Marian (2011): Challenging Pentecostal moralism. Erotic geographies, religion and sexual practices among township youth in Cape Town. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 669–683. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.566356.
- Campero, Lourdes; Walker, Dilys; Atienzo, Erika E.; Gutierrez, Juan Pablo (2011): A quasi-experimental evaluation of parents as sexual health educators resulting in delayed sexual initiation and increased access to condoms. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 215–223. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.05.010.

- Carlson, Wendy; Rose, Amanda J. (2012): Brief report. Activities in heterosexual romantic relationships: grade differences and associations with relationship satisfaction. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 219–224. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.09.001.
- Chappell, Paul; Rule, Peter; Dlamini, Mfana; Nkala, Nompilo (2014): Troubling power dynamics. Youth with disabilities as co-researchers in sexuality research in South Africa. In: *Childhood* 21 (3), S. 385–399. DOI: 10.1177/0907568214525427.
- Clements, Hannah; Dawson, David L.; das Nair, Roshan (2014): Female-perpetrated sexual abuse. A review of victim and professional perspectives. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 197–215. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.798690.
- Collin-Vézina, Delphine; Sablonnière-Griffin, Mireille de la; Palmer, Andrea M.; Milne, Lise (2015): A preliminary mapping of individual, relational, and social factors that impede disclosure of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 43, S. 123–134.
- DeHart, Dana; Dwyer, Gregg; Seto, Michael C.; Moran, Robert; Letourneau, Elizabeth; Schwarz-Watts, Donna (2017): Internet sexual solicitation of children. A proposed typology of offenders based on their chats, e-mails, and social network posts. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 77–89. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1241309.
- Everson, Mark D.; Faller, Kathleen Coulborn (2012): Base rates, multiple indicators, and comprehensive forensic evaluations. Why sexualized behavior still counts in assessments of child sexual abuse allegations. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (1), S. 45–71. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.642470.
- Fagerlund, Monica; Ellonen, Noora (2016): Children's Experiences of Completing a Computer-Based Violence Survey. Finnish Child Victim Survey Revisited. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 556–576. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1186769.
- Flannery, Dustin D.; Stephens, Clare L.; Thompson, Amy D. (2016): The Impact of High-Profile Sexual Abuse Cases in the Media on a Pediatric Emergency Department. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 627–635. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1187697.
- Fletcher, Gillian; Dowsett, Gary W.; Duncan, Duane; Slavin, Sean; Corboz, Julienne (2013): Advancing Sexuality Studies. A short course on sexuality theory and research methodologies. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (3), S. 319–335. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.742847.
- Galinsky, Adena M.; Sonenstein, Freya Lund (2013): Relationship commitment, perceived equity, and sexual enjoyment among young adults in the United States. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (1), S. 93–104. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0003-y.
- Gilbert, Jen (2015): Walking through the school: the erotics of research. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 111–115. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1094947.
- Graaf, Hanneke de; Rademakers, Jany (2011): The Psychological Measurement of Childhood Sexual Development in Western Societies. Methodologica IChallenges. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 48 (2-3), S. 118–129.
- Haggis, Jane; Mulholland, Monique (2013): Rethinking difference and sex education. From cultural inclusivity to normative diversity. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (1), S. 57–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.824873.
- Harden, K. Paige; Mendle, Jane (2011): Adolescent sexual activity and the development of delinquent behavior: the role of relationship context. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 825–838. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9601-y.
- Harper, Craig A.; Bartels, Ross M. (2017): The influence of implicit theories and offender characteristics on judgements of sexual offenders. A moderated mediation analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 139–150. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1250963.
- Hutchfield, Jemeela; Coren, Esther (2011): The Child's Voice in Service Evaluation. Ethical and Methodological Issues. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 173–186. DOI: 10.1002/car.1142.
- Ingevaldson, Sara; Goulding, Anneli; Tidefors, Inga (2016): Experiences of intimate relationships in young men who sexually offended during adolescence. Interviews 10 years later. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 410–422. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1177125.
- Katz, Carmit (2013): Internet-related child sexual abuse. What children tell us in their testimonies. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (9), S. 1536–1542. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.06.006.

- Katz, Carmit; Hamama, Liat (2013): "Draw me everything that happened to you". Exploring children's drawings of sexual abuse. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (5), S. 877–882. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2013.02.007.
- Krahé, Barbara; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine (2015): Mapping an agenda for the study of youth sexual aggression in Europe. Assessment, principles of good practice, and the multilevel analysis of risk factors. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (2), S. 161–176. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1066885.
- Krayer, Anne; Seddon, Diane; Robinson, Catherine A.; Gwilym, Hefin (2015): The influence of child sexual abuse on the self from adult narrative perspectives. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (2), S. 135–151. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1001473.
- Lamb, Sharon; Farmer, Kaelin M.; Kosterina, Elena; Lambe Sariñana, Susan; Plocha, Aleksandra; Randazzo, Renee (2016): What's sexy? Adolescent girls discuss confidence, danger, and media influence. In: *Gender and Education* 28 (4), S. 527–545. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1107528.
- Lansford, Jennifer E.; Dodge, Kenneth A.; Fontaine, Reid Griffith; Bates, John E.; Pettit, Gregory S. (2014): Peer rejection, affiliation with deviant peers, delinquency, and risky sexual behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (10), S. 1742–1751. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0175-y.
- Loeb, Tamra B.; Gaines, Tommi; Wyatt, Gail E.; Zhang, Muyu; Liu, Honghu (2011): Associations between child sexual abuse and negative sexual experiences and revictimization among women. Does measuring severity matter? In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (11), S. 946–955.
- Macapagal, Kathryn; Janssen, Erick; Matson, Margaret; Finn, Peter R.; Heiman, Julia R. (2017): The Impact of Gain- and Loss-Framed Messages on Young Adults' Sexual Decision Making: An Experimental Study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (2), S. 385–394. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0679-x.
- MacDonald, Jo-Ann; Gagnon, Anita J.; Mitchell, Claudia; Di Meglio, Giuseppina; Rennick, Janet E.; Cox, Joseph (2011): Asking to listen. Towards a youth perspective on sexual health education and needs. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 443–457. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595268.
- Makin-Byrd, Kerry; Bierman, Karen L. (2013): Individual and family predictors of the perpetration of dating violence and victimization in late adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 536–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9810-7.
- Martin, Karin A. (2014): Making sense of children's sexual behavior in child care. An analysis of adult responses in special investigation reports. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (10), S. 1636–1646.
- Masson, Helen; Balfe, Myles; Hackett, Simon; Phillips, Josie (2012): Making use of historical case material. The problems of looking back and the implications for service development in relation to research and evaluation activities. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 112–122. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.630539.
- Moilanen, Kristin L. (2016): Why Do Parents Grant or Deny Consent for Adolescent Participation in Sexuality Research? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 1020–1036. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0445-y.
- Moore, Tim P.; McArthur, Morag; Noble-Carr, Debbie (2017): More a marathon than a hurdle. Towards children's informed consent in a study on safety. In: *Qualitative Research* 7 (2), 146879411770070. DOI: 10.1177/1468794117700708.
- Muehlenhard, Charlene L.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D. (2016): The Complexities of Sexual Consent Among College Students. A Conceptual and Empirical Review. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (4-5), S. 1–31.
- Parkes, Alison; Wight, Daniel; Henderson, Marion; West, Patrick (2010): Does early sexual debut reduce teenagers' participation in tertiary education? Evidence from the SHARE longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (5), S. 741–754. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.006.
- Perdahli Fis, Nese; Arman, Ayse; Kalaca, Sibel; Berkem, Meral (2010): Psychiatric evaluation of sexual abuse cases. A clinical representative sample from Turkey. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 32 (10), S. 1285–1290. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2010.04.020.
- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2013): The methodological im/possibilities of researching sexuality education in schools. Working queer conundrums. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S56–S69. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.796288.

- Quinlivan, Kathleen (2012): Popular culture as emotional provocation. The material enactment of queer pedagogies in a high school classroom. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 511–522. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627728.
- Roberts, Susan (2011): Doing Research with Imprisoned Adult Male Child Sexual Abusers. Reflecting on the Challenges. In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 187–196. DOI: 10.1002/car.1175.
- Sandlos, Karyn (2010): On the aesthetic difficulties of research on sex education. Toward a methodology of affect. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 299–308. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491634.
- Savin-Williams, Ritch C.; Joyner, Kara (2014): The dubious assessment of gay, lesbian, and bisexual adolescents of add health. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (3), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0219-5.
- Schaeffer, Paula; Leventhal, John M.; Gottsegen Asnes, Andrea (2011): Children's disclosures of sexual abuse. Learning from direct inquiry. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (5), S. 343–352.
- Schmidt, Alexander F.; Babchishin, Kelly M.; Lehmann, Robert J. B. (2017): A Meta-Analysis of Viewing Time Measures of Sexual Interest in Children. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (1), S. 287–300. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0806-3.
- Seto, Michael C. (2012): Is pedophilia a sexual orientation? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (1), S. 231–236. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9882-6.
- Seto, Michael C.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2015): Viewing child pornography: prevalence and correlates in a representative community sample of young Swedish men. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 67–79. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0244-4.
- Smith, Marshall (2013): Youth Viewing Sexually Explicit Material Online. Addressing the Elephant on the Screen. In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 10 (1), S. 62–75. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-012-0103-4.
- Šribar, Renata (2013): Growing-up challenged and challenging. Gender and sexuality norms in referential research on 'internet risks' and in children. In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (1), S. 129–145. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.748681.
- van Leeuwen, Matthijs L.; van Baaren, Rick B.; Chakhssi, Farid; Loonen, Marijke G. M.; Lippman, Maarten; Dijksterhuis, Ap (2013): Assessment of implicit sexual associations in non-incarcerated pedophiles. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1501–1507. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0094-0.
- Williams, Andy (2015): Child sexual victimisation. Ethnographic stories of stranger and acquaintance grooming. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 28–42. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.948085.
- Zimmer-Gembeck, Melanie J.; Ducat, Wendy (2010): Positive and negative romantic relationship quality: age, familiarity, attachment and well-being as correlates of couple agreement and projection. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (6), S. 879–890. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.07.008.

8.4. Ergebnisse

- Cares, Alison C.; Moynihan, Mary M.; Banyard, Victoria L. (2014): Taking Stock of Bystander Programmes: Changing Attitudes and Behaviours Towards Sexual Violence. In: Nicola Henry und Anastasia Powell (Hg.): Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, S. 170–189.
- Carrigan Wooten, Sara (2016): Heterosexist Discourses. How Feminist Theory Shaped Campus Sexual Violence Policy. In: Sara Carrigan Wooten und Roland W. Mitchell (Hg.): The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response. New York: Routledge, S. 33–52.
- Erooga, Marcus (2012): Understanding and Responding to People Who Sexually Abuse Children Whilst Employed In Trust. An Overview of the Relevant Literature - Part One: Offenders. In: Marcus Erooga (Hg.): Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them. Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children), S. 7–26.
- Görzig, Anke; Mascheroni, Giovanna; Murru, Maria Francesca (2012): Varieties of access and use. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 59–72.

- Hasebrink, Uwe (2012): Young European's online environments: a typology of user practices. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 127–140.
- Ogan, Christine; Karakus, Türkan; Kursun, Engin; Cagiltay, Kürsat; Kasikci, Duygu (2012): Cognitive interviewing and response to EU Kids Online survey questions. In: Sonia M. Livingstone, Leslie Haddon und Anke Görzig (Hg.): Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective. Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press, S. 33–44.
- Rivers, Ian (2013): Cyberbullying and cyberaggression. Sexualised and gendered experiences explored. In: Ian Rivers (Hg.): Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender. London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education), S. 19–44.
- Shuttleworth, Russell (2012): Bridging Theory and Experience: A Critical-Interpretative Ethnography of Sexuality and Disability. In: Robert McRuer und Anna Mollow (Hg.): Sex and disability. Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press, S. 54–69.
- Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013): Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications. Hove: Psychology.
- Ponzetti, James J. (Hg.) (2016): Evidence-based approaches to sexuality education. A global perspective (Textbooks in family studies series).
- Abajobir, Amanuel Alemu; Kisely, Steve; Williams, Gail Marilyn; Clavarino, Alexandra Marie; Najman, Jakob Moses (2017): Substantiated Childhood Maltreatment and Intimate Partner Violence Victimization in Young Adulthood: A Birth Cohort Study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 165–179. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0558-3.
- Ali, Mir M.; Dwyer, Debra S. (2011): Estimating peer effects in sexual behavior among adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 183–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.12.008.
- Allard, Troy; Rayment-McHugh, Sue; Adams, Dimity; Smallbone, Stephen; McKillop, Nadine (2015): Responding to youth sexual offending. A field-based practice model that “closes the gap” on sexual recidivism among Indigenous and non-Indigenous males. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (1), S. 82–94. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.1003107.
- Allbaugh, Lucy Jane; O'Dougherty Wright, Margaret; Atkins Seltmann, Larissa (2014): An exploratory study of domains of parenting concern among mothers who are childhood sexual abuse survivors. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (8), S. 885–899. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.960636.
- Alleyne, Binta; Coleman-Cowger, Victoria H.; Crown, Laurel; Gibbons, Maya A.; Vines, Linda Nicole (2011): The effects of dating violence, substance use and risky sexual behavior among a diverse sample of Illinois youth. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 11–18. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.03.006.
- Åmot, Ingvild; Ytterhus, Borgunn (2014): 'Talking bodies'. Power and counter-power between children and adults in day care. In: *Childhood* 21 (2), S. 260–273. DOI: 10.1177/0907568213490971.
- Anderson, Gwendolyn D. (2016): The Continuum of Disclosure. Exploring Factors Predicting Tentative Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations During Forensic Interviews and the Implications for Practice, Policy, and Future Research. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 382–402. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153559.
- Arrington-Sanders, Renata; Harper, Gary W.; Morgan, Anthony; Ogunbajo, Adedotun; Trent, Maria; Fortenberry, J. Dennis (2015): The role of sexually explicit material in the sexual development of same-sex-attracted Black adolescent males. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 597–608. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0416-x.
- Babchishin, Kelly M.; Nunes, Kevin L.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Malcom, J. Renee (2015): Implicit sexual interest in children. Does separating gender influence discrimination when using the Implicit Association Test? In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 194–208. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836575.
- Balfe, Myles; Gallagher, Bernard; Masson, Helen; Balfe, Shane; Brugha, Ruairi; Hackett, Simon (2015): Internet Child Sex Offenders' Concerns about Online Security and their Use of Identity Protection Technologies. A Review. In: *Child Abuse Review* 24 (6), S. 427–439. DOI: 10.1002/car.2308.
- Baumgartner, Susanne E.; Valkenburg, Patti M.; Peter, Jochen (2010): Assessing causality in the relationship between adolescents' risky sexual online behavior and their perceptions of this behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1226–1239. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9512-y.

- Benia, Luis Roberto; Hauck-Filho, Nelson; Dillenburg, Mariana; Stein, Lilian Milnitsky (2015): The NICHD Investigative Interview Protocol. A Meta-Analytic Review. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 259–279. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006749.
- Benuto, Lorraine T.; O'Donohue, William (2015): Treatment of the Sexually Abused Child. Review and Synthesis of Recent Meta-Analyses. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 56, S. 52–60. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.06.009.
- Bhana, Deevia; Pattman, Rob (2011): Girls want money, boys want virgins. The materiality of love amongst South African township youth in the context of HIV and AIDS. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 961–972. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.576770.
- Bird, Elizabeth R.; Seehuus, Martin; Clifton, Jessica; Rellini, Alessandra H. (2014): Dissociation during sex and sexual arousal in women with and without a history of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (5), S. 953–964. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0191-0.
- Boratav, Hale Bolak; Çavdar, Alev (2012): Sexual stereotypes and practices of university students in Turkey. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (1), S. 271–281. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9811-8.
- Bos, Henny; Sandfort, Theo (2015): Gender Nonconformity, Sexual Orientation, and Dutch Adolescents' Relationship with Peers. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (5), S. 1269–1279. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0461-5.
- Bos, Henny; van Beusekom, Gabriël; Sandfort, Theo (2014): Sexual attraction and psychological adjustment in Dutch adolescents: coping style as a mediator. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1579–1588. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0308-0.
- Bower, Andrew R.; Nishina, Adrienne; Witkow, Melissa R.; Bellmore, Amy (2015): Nice Guys and Gals Finish Last? Not in Early Adolescence When Empathic, Accepted, and Popular Peers are Desirable. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (12), S. 2275–2288. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0346-5.
- Braje, Sopagna Eap; Eddy, J. Mark; Hall, Gordon C. N. (2016): A Comparison of Two Models of Risky Sexual Behavior During Late Adolescence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (1), S. 73–83. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0523-3.
- Brakefield, Tiffany A.; Mednick, Sara C.; Wilson, Helen W.; Neve, Jan-Emmanuel de; Christakis, Nicholas A.; Fowler, James H. (2014): Same-sex sexual attraction does not spread in adolescent social networks. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 335–344. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0142-9.
- Brooks-Russell, Ashley; Foshee, Vangie A.; Ennett, Susan T. (2013): Predictors of latent trajectory classes of physical dating violence victimization. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 566–580. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9876-2.
- Bui, Thanh Cong; Diamond, Pamela M.; Markham, Christine; Ross, Michael W.; Nguyen-Le, Thanh-An; Tran, Ly Hai Thi (2010): Gender relations and sexual communication among female students in the Mekong River Delta of Vietnam. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (6), S. 591–601. DOI: 10.1080/13691050902968769.
- Buschman, Jos; Wilcox, Dan; Krapohl, Donald; Oelrich, Marty; Hackett, Simon (2010): Cybersex offender risk assessment. An explorative study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 197–209. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003690518.
- Calafat, Amador; Hughes, Karen; Blay, Nicole; Bellis, Mark A.; Mendes, Fernando; Juan, Montse et al. (2013): Sexual harassment among young tourists visiting Mediterranean resorts. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 603–613. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-9979-6.
- Capella, Claudia; Lama, Ximena; Rodriguez, Loreto; Aguila, Daniela; Beiza, Gretchen; Dussert, Denise; Gutierrez, Carolina (2016): Winning a Race. Narratives of Healing and Psychotherapy in Children and Adolescents Who Have Been Sexually Abused. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 73–92. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088915.
- Carlson, Daniel L.; McNulty, Thomas L.; Bellair, Paul E.; Watts, Stephen (2014): Neighborhoods and racial/ethnic disparities in adolescent sexual risk behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (9), S. 1536–1549. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0052-0.
- Carlson, Wendy; Rose, Amanda J. (2012): Brief report. Activities in heterosexual romantic relationships: grade differences and associations with relationship satisfaction. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 219–224. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.09.001.

- Casey, Erin A.; Beadnell, Blair (2010): The structure of male adolescent peer networks and risk for intimate partner violence perpetration: findings from a national sample. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 620–633. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9423-y.
- Cavazos-Rehg, Patricia A.; Spitznagel, Edward L.; Bucholz, Kathleen K.; Nurnberger, John; Edenberg, Howard J.; Kramer, John R. et al. (2010): Predictors of sexual debut at age 16 or younger. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 664–673. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9397-y.
- Chang, Ling-Yin; Foshee, Vangie A.; Reyes, Heathe Luz McNaughton; Ennett, Susan T.; Halpern, Carolyn T. (2015): Direct and indirect effects of neighborhood characteristics on the perpetration of dating violence across adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 727–744. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0190-z.
- Collibee, Charlene; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Chronic and Acute Relational Risk Factors for Dating Aggression in Adolescence and Young Adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (4), S. 763–776. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0427-0.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2013): Homophobic name-calling among secondary school students and its implications for mental health. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 363–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9823-2.
- Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2012): Intergroup contact, attitudes toward homosexuality, and the role of acceptance of gender non-conformity in young adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 899–907. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.12.010.
- Collin-Vézina, Delphine; Garrido, Edward F. (2017): Current issues in child sexual abuse, gender and health outcomes: Shedding new lights to inform worldwide policy and practice. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 245–248. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.11.032.
- Cox, Nele; Vanden Berghe, Wim; Dewaele, Alexis; Vincke, John (2010): Acculturation strategies and mental health in gay, lesbian, and bisexual youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1199–1210. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9435-7.
- Crandall, AliceAnn; Magnusson, Brianna M.; Novilla, M. Lelinneth B.; Novilla, Lynneth Kirsten B.; Dyer, W. Justin (2017): Family Financial Stress and Adolescent Sexual Risk-Taking: The Role of Self-Regulation. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 45–62. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0543-x.
- Crichton, Joanna; Ibisomi, Latifat; Gyimah, Stephen Obeng (2012): Mother-daughter communication about sexual maturation, abstinence and unintended pregnancy. Experiences from an informal settlement in Nairobi, Kenya. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 21–30. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.06.008.
- Cromer, Lisa DeMarni; Goldsmith, Rachel E. (2010): Child sexual abuse myths. Attitudes, beliefs, and individual differences. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (6), S. 618–647. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.522493.
- D'Abreu, Lylla Cysne Frota; Krahe, Barbara (2016): Vulnerability to Sexual Victimization in Female and Male College Students in Brazil: Cross-Sectional and Prospective Evidence. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1101–1115. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0451-7.
- Dahlbäck, Elisabeth; Maimbolwa, Margaret; Yamba, C. Bawa; Kasonka, Lackson; Bergström, Staffan; Ransjö-Arvidson, Anna-Berit (2010): Pregnancy loss. Spontaneous and induced abortions among young women in Lusaka, Zambia. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 247–262. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903353383.
- Dank, Meredith; Lachman, Pamela; Zweig, Janine M.; Yahner, Jennifer (2014): Dating violence experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (5), S. 846–857. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9975-8.
- Das, Aniruddha; Otis, Nicholas (2016): Sexual Contact in Childhood, Revictimization, and Lifetime Sexual and Psychological Outcomes. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1117–1131. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0620-3.
- Dermoddy, Sarah S.; Marshal, Michael P.; Cheong, Jeewon; Burton, Chad; Hughes, Tonda; Aranda, Frances; Friedman, Mark S. (2014): Longitudinal disparities of hazardous drinking between sexual minority and heterosexual individuals from adolescence to young adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (1), S. 30–39. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9905-9.
- Diarsvitri, Wienta; Utomo, Iwu Dwisetyani; Neeman, Teresa; Oktavian, Antonius (2011): Beyond sexual desire and curiosity. Sexuality among senior high school students in Papua and West Papua Provinces (Indonesia) and

implications for HIV prevention. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (9), S. 1047–1060. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.599862.

Dickenson, Janna A.; Huebner, David M. (2016): The Relationship Between Sexual Activity and Depressive Symptoms in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth: Effects of Gender and Family Support. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (3), S. 671–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0571-8.

Dolan, Mairead; Whitworth, Helen (2013): Childhood sexual abuse, adult psychiatric morbidity, and criminal outcomes in women assessed by medium secure forensic service. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (2), S. 191–208. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.751951.

Doty, Nathan Daniel; Willoughby, Brian L. B.; Lindahl, Kristin M.; Malik, Neena M. (2010): Sexuality related social support among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1134–1147. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9566-x.

Edwards, Rachel; Whittaker, Mette Kristensen; Beckett, Richard; Bishopp, Daz; Bates, Andrew (2012): Adolescents who have sexually harmed. An evaluation of a specialist treatment programme. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 91–111. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.635317.

Ellis, Wendy E.; Chung-Hall, Janet; Dumas, Tara M. (2013): The role of peer group aggression in predicting adolescent dating violence and relationship quality. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 487–499. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9797-0.

Eriksson, Elisabet; Lindmark, Gunilla; Axemo, Pia; Haddad, Beverley; Ahlberg, Beth Maina (2010): Ambivalence, silence and gender differences in church leaders' HIV-prevention messages to young people in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 103–114. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903141192.

Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2012): Young women's adolescent experiences of oral sex. Relation of age of initiation to sexual motivation, sexual coercion, and psychological functioning. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (5), S. 1191–1201. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.03.010.

Felson, Richard B.; Cundiff, Patrick R. (2014): Sexual assault as a crime against young people. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 273–284. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0127-8.

Ferguson, Christopher J.; Muñoz, Mónica E.; Garza, Adolfo; Galindo, Mariza (2014): Concurrent and prospective analyses of peer, television and social media influences on body dissatisfaction, eating disorder symptoms and life satisfaction in adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (1), S. 1–14. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9898-9.

Fielder, Robyn L.; Carey, Michael P. (2010): Predictors and consequences of sexual "hookups" among college students: a short-term prospective study. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1105–1119. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9448-4.

Fielder, Robyn L.; Walsh, Jennifer L.; Carey, Kate B.; Carey, Michael P. (2013): Predictors of sexual hookups: a theory-based, prospective study of first-year college women. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1425–1441. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0106-0.

Fish, Jessica N.; Pasley, Kay (2015): Sexual (Minority) Trajectories, Mental Health, and Alcohol Use: A Longitudinal Study of Youth as They Transition to Adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (8), S. 1508–1527. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0280-6.

Fitzpatrick, Kevin M.; Dulin, Akilah; Piko, Bettina (2010): Bullying and depressive symptomatology among low-income, African-American youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 634–645. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9426-8.

Flannery, Dustin D.; Stephens, Clare L.; Thompson, Amy D. (2016): The Impact of High-Profile Sexual Abuse Cases in the Media on a Pediatric Emergency Department. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 627–635. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1187697.

Formby, Eleanor (2011): Sex and relationships education, sexual health, and lesbian, gay and bisexual sexual cultures. Views from young people. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 255–266. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590078.

Foshee, Vangie A.; Benefield, Thad; Dixon, Kimberly S.; Chang, Ling-Yin; Senkomago, Virginia; Ennett, Susan T. et al. (2015): The effects of moms and teens for safe dates: a dating abuse prevention program for adolescents exposed to domestic violence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 995–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0272-6.

- Fredlund, Cecilia; Svensson, Frida; Svedin, Carl Goran; Priebe, Gisela; Wadsby, Marie (2013): Adolescents' lifetime experience of selling sex. Development over five years. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (3), S. 312–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.743950.
- Gakhal, Baldeesh Kaur; Brown, Sarah J. (2011): A comparison of the general public's, forensic professionals' and students' attitudes towards female sex offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 105–116. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.540678.
- Galinsky, Adena M.; Sonenstein, Freya Lund (2013): Relationship commitment, perceived equity, and sexual enjoyment among young adults in the United States. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (1), S. 93–104. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0003-y.
- Gartrell, Nanette K.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Goldberg, Naomi G. (2011): Adolescents of the U.S. National Longitudinal Lesbian Family Study: sexual orientation, sexual behavior, and sexual risk exposure. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (6), S. 1199–1209. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9692-2.
- Gattis, Maurice N.; Woodford, Michael R.; Han, Yoonsun (2014): Discrimination and depressive symptoms among sexual minority youth: is gay-affirming religious affiliation a protective factor? In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1589–1599. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0342-y.
- Geary, Jan; Lambie, Ian; Seymour, Fred (2011): Consumer perspectives of New Zealand community treatment programmes for sexually abusive youth. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 181–195. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003778693.
- Genna, Natacha M. de; Larkby, Cynthia; Cornelius, Marie D. (2011): Pubertal timing and early sexual intercourse in the offspring of teenage mothers. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (10), S. 1315–1328. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9609-3.
- Goldbach, Jeremy T.; Gibbs, Jeremy J. (2017): A developmentally informed adaptation of minority stress for sexual minority adolescents. In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 36–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.007.
- Graaf, Hanneke de; van de Schoot, Rens; Woertman, Liesbeth; Hawk, Skyler T.; Meeus, Wim (2012): Family cohesion and romantic and sexual initiation: a three wave longitudinal study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 583–592. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9708-9.
- Graaf, Hanneke de; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine; Woertman, Liesbeth; Keijsers, Loes; Meijer, Suzanne; Meeus, Wim (2010): Parental support and knowledge and adolescents' sexual health: testing two mediational models in a national Dutch sample. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (2), S. 189–198. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-008-9387-3.
- Gray, Jacqueline M. (2014): What constitutes a “reasonable belief” in consent to sex? A thematic analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 337–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.900122.
- Gwirayi, Pesanayi (2013): The prevalence of child sexual abuse among secondary school pupils in Gweru, Zimbabwe. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 253–263. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.723755.
- Hall, Charlotte L.; Hogue, Todd E.; Guo, Kun (2014): Gaze patterns to child figures reflect deviant sexual preference in child sex offenders—a first glance. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 303–317. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.931475.
- Harden, K. Paige; Mendle, Jane (2011): Adolescent sexual activity and the development of delinquent behavior: the role of relationship context. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 825–838. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9601-y.
- Harper, Craig A.; Bartels, Ross M. (2017): The influence of implicit theories and offender characteristics on judgements of sexual offenders. A moderated mediation analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 139–150. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1250963.
- Hay, Carter; Meldrum, Ryan (2010): Bullying victimization and adolescent self-harm: testing hypotheses from general strain theory. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (5), S. 446–459. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9502-0.
- Haydon, Abigail A.; Halpern, Carolyn Tucker (2010): Older romantic partners and depressive symptoms during adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1240–1251. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9539-0.
- Henry, Olivia; Mandeville-Norden, Rebecca; Hayes, Elizabeth; Egan, Vincent (2010): Do internet-based sexual offenders reduce to normal, inadequate and deviant groups? In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 33–46. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903454132.

- Hooghe, Marc; Meeusen, Cecil (2012): Homophobia and the transition to adulthood: a three year panel study among Belgian late adolescents and young adults, 2008-2011. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (9), S. 1197–1207. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9786-3.
- Houser, John J.; Mayeux, Lara; Cross, Cassandra (2015): Peer status and aggression as predictors of dating popularity in adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 683–695. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0174-z.
- Hovey, Angela; Stalker, Carol A.; Schachter, Candice L.; Teram, Eli; Lasiuk, Gerri (2011): Practical ways psychotherapy can support physical healthcare experiences for male survivors of childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 37–57. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.539963.
- Huitema, Anneloes; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine (2016): Attitudes of Dutch citizens towards male victims of sexual coercion by a female perpetrator. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 308–322. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1159343.
- Ingevaldson, Sara; Goulding, Anneli; Tidefors, Inga (2016): Experiences of intimate relationships in young men who sexually offended during adolescence. Interviews 10 years later. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 410–422. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1177125.
- Jaffe, Anna E.; Cranston, Christopher C.; Shadlow, Joanna O. (2012): Parenting in females exposed to intimate partner violence and childhood sexual abuse. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 684–700. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.726698.
- Jennings, Wesley G.; Richards, Tara N.; Tomsich, Elizabeth; Gover, Angela R. (2015): Investigating the Role of Child Sexual Abuse in Intimate Partner Violence Victimization and Perpetration in Young Adulthood From a Propensity Score Matching Approach. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 659–681. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1057665.
- Jerman, Petra; Constantine, Norman A. (2010): Demographic and psychological predictors of parent-adolescent communication about sex: a representative statewide analysis. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1164–1174. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9546-1.
- Jones, Tiffany Mary (2011): Saving rhetorical children. Sexuality education discourses from conservative to post-modern. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 369–387. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595229.
- Killoren, Sarah E.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; Christopher, F. Scott (2011): Family and cultural correlates of Mexican-origin youths' sexual intentions. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (6), S. 707–718. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9587-5.
- Killoren, Sarah E.; Zeiders, Katharine H.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J. (2016): The Sociocultural Context of Mexican-Origin Pregnant Adolescents' Attitudes Toward Teen Pregnancy and Links to Future Outcomes. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 887–899. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0387-9.
- Kloppen, Kathrine; Haugland, Siren; Svedin, Carl-Göran; Maehle, Magne; Breivik, Kyrre (2016): Prevalence of Child Sexual Abuse in the Nordic Countries. A Literature Review. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 37–55. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1108944.
- Kostolitz, Alessandra C.; Hyman, Scott M.; Gold, Steven N. (2014): How ineffective family environments can compound maldevelopment of critical thinking skills in childhood abuse survivors. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (6), S. 690–707. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.931318.
- Kosuri, Mahathi D.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2017): Child sex tourism. American perceptions of foreign victims. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 207–221. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1231350.
- Krause-Parello, Cheryl A.; Gulick, Elsie E. (2015): Forensic Interviews for Child Sexual Abuse Allegations. An Investigation into the Effects of Animal-Assisted Intervention on Stress Biomarkers. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 873–886. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088916.
- Kucuk, Sibel (2016): Analyses of Child Sex Abuse Cases in Turkey: A Provincial Case. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 262–275. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153557.
- Kuhle, Laura F.; Schlinzig, Eliza; Kaiser, Gerd; Amelung, Till; Konrad, Anna; Röhle, Robert; Beier, Klaus M. (2017): The association of sexual preference and dynamic risk factors with undetected child pornography offending. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 3–18. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1201157.

- La Roi, Chaïm; Kretschmer, Tina; Dijkstra, Jan Kornelis; Veenstra, René; Oldehinkel, Albertine J. (2016): Disparities in Depressive Symptoms Between Heterosexual and Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth in a Dutch Cohort: The TRAILS Study. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (3), S. 440–456. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0403-0.
- Lainpelto, Katrin; Isaksson, Johan; Lindblad, Frank (2016): Does Information About Neuropsychiatric Diagnoses Influence Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations? In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 276–292. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1145164.
- Lambie, Ian; Price, Mnthali (2015): Transitioning youth with sexually harmful behaviour back into the community. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 244–265. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.873829.
- Langeland, Willemiem; Hoogendoorn, Adriaan W.; Mager, Daniel; Smit, Jan H.; Draijer, Nel (2015): Childhood sexual abuse by representatives of the Roman Catholic Church. A prevalence estimate among the Dutch population. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 67–77.
- Lansford, Jennifer E.; Dodge, Kenneth A.; Fontaine, Reid Griffith; Bates, John E.; Pettit, Gregory S. (2014): Peer rejection, affiliation with deviant peers, delinquency, and risky sexual behavior. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (10), S. 1742–1751. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0175-y.
- Lasher, Michael P.; Stinson, Jill D. (2017): Adults with Pedophilic Interests in the United States: Current Practices and Suggestions for Future Policy and Research. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 659–670. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0822-3.
- Leech, Tamara G. J.; Dias, Janice Johnson (2012): Risky sexual behavior: a race-specific social consequence of obesity. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (1), S. 41–52. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9670-6.
- Lev-Wiesel, Rachel; Markus, Liora (2013): Perception vs. circumstances of the child sexual abuse event in relation to depression and post-traumatic stress symptomatology. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 519–533. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800932.
- Lewis, Tiffany; Klettke, Bianca; Day, Andrew (2014): Sentencing in child sexual assault cases. Factors influencing judicial decision-making. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 281–295. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.804603.
- Loftus, Jeni; Kelly, Brian C.; Mustillo, Sarah A. (2011): Depressive symptoms among adolescent girls in relationships with older partners: causes and lasting effects? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 800–813. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9589-3.
- Lopez, Silvia; Faro, Concepcio; Lopetegui, Lourdes; Pujol-Ribera, Enriqueta; Monteagudo, Monica; Avecilla-Palau, Angels et al. (2017): Child and Adolescent Sexual Abuse in Women Seeking Help for Sexual and Reproductive Mental Health Problems. Prevalence, Characteristics, and Disclosure. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 246–269. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1288186.
- Lopez, Vera; Kopak, Albert; Robillard, Alyssa; Gillmore, Mary Rogers; Holliday, Rhonda C.; Braithwaite, Ronald L. (2011): Pathways to sexual risk taking among female adolescent detainees. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (8), S. 945–957. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9623-5.
- Lourie, Michael A.; Needham, Belinda L. (2017): Sexual Orientation Discordance and Young Adult Mental Health. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 943–954. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0553-8.
- Low, Sabina; Polanin, Joshua R.; Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013): The role of social networks in physical and relational aggression among young adolescents. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1078–1089. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9933-5.
- MacDonald, Jo-Ann; Gagnon, Anita J.; Mitchell, Claudia; Di Meglio, Giuseppina; Rennick, Janet E.; Cox, Joseph (2011): Asking to listen. Towards a youth perspective on sexual health education and needs. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 443–457. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595268.
- Makin-Byrd, Kerry; Bierman, Karen L. (2013): Individual and family predictors of the perpetration of dating violence and victimization in late adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 536–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9810-7.
- Makura, Alfred Henry; Zireva, Davison (2013): School heads and mentors in cahoots? Challenges to teaching practice in Zimbabwean teacher education programmes. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 3–16. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.573583.

- Mannix, Karyn; Dawson, David L.; Beckley, Kerry (2013): The implicit theories of male child sexual offenders residing in a high secure psychiatric hospital. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 264–274. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.732616.
- Martin-Storey, Alexa (2015): Prevalence of dating violence among sexual minority youth: variation across gender, sexual minority identity and gender of sexual partners. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 211–224. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0089-0.
- McCartan, Fiona Mairead; Law, Heather; Murphy, Maeve; Bailey, Susan (2011): Child and adolescent females who present with sexually abusive behaviours. A 10-year UK prevalence study. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 4–14. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.488302.
- McElvaney, Rosaleen (2015): Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse. Delays, Non-disclosure and Partial Disclosure. What the Research Tells Us and Implications for Practice. In: *Child Abuse Review* 24 (3), S. 159–169. DOI: 10.1002/car.2280.
- McManus, Michelle Ann; Long, Matthew L.; Alison, Laurence; Almond, Louise (2014): Factors associated with contact child sexual abuse in a sample of indecent image offenders. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 368–384. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927009.
- Milan, Stephanie; Wortel, Sanne (2015): Family obligation values as a protective and vulnerability factor among low-income adolescent girls. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (6), S. 1183–1193. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0206-8.
- Miller, Shari; Williams, Jason; Cutbush, Stacey; Gibbs, Deborah; Clinton-Sherrod, Monique; Jones, Sarah (2013): Dating violence, bullying, and sexual harassment: longitudinal profiles and transitions over time. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 607–618. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9914-8.
- Misurell, Justin R.; Springer, Craig; Tryon, Warren W. (2011): Game-based cognitive-behavioral therapy (GB-CBT) group program for children who have experienced sexual abuse. A preliminary investigation. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 14–36. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.540000.
- Mitchell, Renae C.; Galupo, M. Paz (2015): Interest in child molestation among a community sample of men sexually attracted to children. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (2), S. 224–232. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1056263.
- Moilanen, Kristin L. (2016): Why Do Parents Grant or Deny Consent for Adolescent Participation in Sexuality Research? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 1020–1036. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0445-y.
- Needham, Belinda L. (2012): Sexual attraction and trajectories of mental health and substance use during the transition from adolescence to adulthood. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 179–190. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9729-4.
- Nishina, Adrienne (2012): Microcontextual characteristics of peer victimization experiences and adolescents' daily well-being. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 191–201. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9669-z.
- Novak, Jamie; Furman, Wyndol (2016): Partner Violence During Adolescence and Young Adulthood: Individual and Relationship Level Risk Factors. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (9), S. 1849–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0484-4.
- Nunes, Kevin L.; McPhail, Ian V.; Babchishin, Kelly M. (2012): Social anxiety and sexual offending against children. A cumulative meta-analysis. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (3), S. 284–293. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.549243.
- O'Leary, P.; Tsui, M.-S.; Ruch, G. (2013): The Boundaries of the Social Work Relationship Revisited. Towards a Connected, Inclusive and Dynamic Conceptualisation. In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 43 (1), S. 135–153. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcr181.
- Park, Jisun; Kim, Seunghee (2016): Group size does matter. Differences among sexual assaults committed by lone, double, and groups of three or more perpetrators. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 342–354. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1144801.
- Rasmussen, Lucinda A. (2013): Young people who sexually abuse. A historical perspective and future directions. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (1), S. 119–141. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.744646.
- Savin-Williams, Ritch C.; Joyner, Kara (2014): The dubious assessment of gay, lesbian, and bisexual adolescents of add health. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (3), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0219-5.

- Schmidt, Alexander F.; Babchishin, Kelly M.; Lehmann, Robert J. B. (2017): A Meta-Analysis of Viewing Time Measures of Sexual Interest in Children. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (1), S. 287–300. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0806-3.
- Smith, Connie; Allardyce, Stuart; Hackett, Simon; Bradbury-Jones, Caroline; Lazenbatt, Anne; Taylor, Julie (2014): Practice and policy in the UK with children and young people who display harmful sexual behaviours. An analysis and critical review. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 267–280. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927010.
- Spraitz, Jason D.; Bowen, Kendra N.; Arthurs, Shavonne (2017): Neutralisation and sexual abuse. A study of monks from one Benedictine Abbey. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 195–206. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1204471.
- van Leeuwen, Matthijs L.; van Baaren, Rick B.; Chakhssi, Farid; Loonen, Marijke G. M.; Lippman, Maarten; Dijksterhuis, Ap (2013): Assessment of implicit sexual associations in non-incarcerated pedophiles. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1501–1507. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0094-0.
- Williams, Andy (2015): Child sexual victimisation. Ethnographic stories of stranger and acquaintance grooming. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 28–42. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.948085.
- Wurtele, Sandy K.; Kenny, Maureen C. (2010): Partnering with parents to prevent childhood sexual abuse. In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (2), S. 130–152. DOI: 10.1002/car.1112.
- Yu, Juping (2010): Sex education beyond school. Implications for practice and research. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 187–199. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666515.
- Zhang, Wenjing; Chen, Jingqi; Feng, Yanan; Li, Jingyi; Zhao, Xiaoxia; Luo, Xiaoling (2013): Young children's knowledge and skills related to sexual abuse prevention. A pilot study in Beijing, China. In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 623–630.

8.5. Forschungslücken

- Allard, Troy; Rayment-McHugh, Sue; Adams, Dimity; Smallbone, Stephen; McKillop, Nadine (2015): Responding to youth sexual offending. A field-based practice model that “closes the gap” on sexual recidivism among Indigenous and non-Indigenous males. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (1), S. 82–94. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.1003107.
- Benuto, Lorraine T.; O'Donohue, William (2015): Treatment of the Sexually Abused Child. Review and Synthesis of Recent Meta-Analyses. In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 56, S. 52–60. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2015.06.009.
- Chang, Ling-Yin; Foshee, Vangie A.; Reyes, Heathe Luz McNaughton; Ennett, Susan T.; Halpern, Carolyn T. (2015): Direct and indirect effects of neighborhood characteristics on the perpetration of dating violence across adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 727–744. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0190-z.
- DeHart, Dana; Dwyer, Gregg; Seto, Michael C.; Moran, Robert; Letourneau, Elizabeth; Schwarz-Watts, Donna (2017): Internet sexual solicitation of children. A proposed typology of offenders based on their chats, e-mails, and social network posts. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 77–89. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1241309.
- Doty, Nathan Daniel; Willoughby, Brian L. B.; Lindahl, Kristin M.; Malik, Neena M. (2010): Sexuality related social support among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1134–1147. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9566-x.
- Edwards, Rachel; Whittaker, Mette Kristensen; Beckett, Richard; Bishopp, Daz; Bates, Andrew (2012): Adolescents who have sexually harmed. An evaluation of a specialist treatment programme. In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 91–111. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.635317.
- Galinsky, Adena M.; Sonenstein, Freya Lund (2013): Relationship commitment, perceived equity, and sexual enjoyment among young adults in the United States. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (1), S. 93–104. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0003-y.
- Houser, John J.; Mayeux, Lara; Cross, Cassandra (2015): Peer status and aggression as predictors of dating popularity in adolescence. In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 683–695. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0174-z.
- Lasher, Michael P.; Stinson, Jill D. (2017): Adults with Pedophilic Interests in the United States: Current Practices and Suggestions for Future Policy and Research. In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 659–670. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0822-3.

Bibliographie: Englischsprachiger Forschungsstand „sexuelle Gewalt in pädagogischen Kontexten“

Moilanen, Kristin L. (2016): Why Do Parents Grant or Deny Consent for Adolescent Participation in Sexuality Research? In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 1020–1036. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0445-y.

Muehlenhard, Charlene L.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D. (2016): The Complexities of Sexual Consent Among College Students. A Conceptual and Empirical Review. In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (4-5), S. 1–31.

Ross, Colin A. (2017): Response to Miccio-Fonseca (2015) and Defeo (2015) Concerning Commentary About DSM-5 Sexual Disorders Section. In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 92–95. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1263263.

Yu, Juping (2010): Sex education beyond school. Implications for practice and research. In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 187–199. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666515.

II Bibliographie nach Zeitschriften

Archives of Sexual Behavior

Arrington-Sanders, Renata; Harper, Gary W.; Morgan, Anthony; Ogunbajo, Adedotun; Trent, Maria; Fortenberry, J. Dennis (2015):

The role of sexually explicit material in the sexual development of same-sex-attracted Black adolescent males.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 597–608. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0416-x.

Schlagwörter:

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1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Boratav, Hale Bolak; Çavdar, Alev (2012):

Sexual stereotypes and practices of university students in Turkey.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (1), S. 271–281. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9811-8.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Kommunikation // communication; Muslimische Länder; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college university

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Bos, Henny; Sandfort, Theo (2015):

Gender Nonconformity, Sexual Orientation, and Dutch Adolescents' Relationship with Peers.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (5), S. 1269–1279. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0461-5.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Jugendliche // youth; Peers; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Bos, Henny; van Beusekom, Gabriël; Sandfort, Theo (2014):

Sexual attraction and psychological adjustment in Dutch adolescents: coping style as a mediator.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1579–1588. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0308-0.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse
Braje, Sopagna Eap; Eddy, J. Mark; Hall, Gordon C. N. (2016):

A Comparison of Two Models of Risky Sexual Behavior During Late Adolescence.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (1), S. 73–83. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0523-3.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Risiko // risk; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Trauma

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Brakefield, Tiffany A.; Mednick, Sara C.; Wilson, Helen W.; Neve, Jan-Emmanuel de; Christakis, Nicholas A.; Fowler, James H. (2014):

Same-sex sexual attraction does not spread in adolescent social networks.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 335–344. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0142-9.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Peers; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Calafat, Amador; Hughes, Karen; Blay, Nicole; Bellis, Mark A.; Mendes, Fernando; Juan, Montse et al. (2013):

Sexual harassment among young tourists visiting Mediterranean resorts.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 603–613. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-9979-6.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Cavazos-Rehg, Patricia A.; Spitznagel, Edward L.; Bucholz, Kathleen K.; Nurnberger, John; Edenberg, Howard J.; Kramer, John R. et al. (2010):

Predictors of sexual debut at age 16 or younger.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 664–673. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9397-y.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; erstes Mal // sexual debut; Familie // family; Jugendliche // youth; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

D'Abreu, Lylla Cysne Frota; Krahe, Barbara (2016):

Vulnerability to Sexual Victimization in Female and Male College Students in Brazil: Cross-Sectional and Prospective Evidence.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1101–1115. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0451-7.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Pornografie // pornography; Risiko // risk; sexuelle Skripte // sexual scripts; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Das, Aniruddha; Otis, Nicholas (2016):

Sexual Contact in Childhood, Revictimization, and Lifetime Sexual and Psychological Outcomes.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1117–1131.

Schlagwörter:

Erwachsene; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Revictimisierung // revictimization; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Dickenson, Janna A.; Huebner, David M. (2016):

The Relationship Between Sexual Activity and Depressive Symptoms in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth: Effects of Gender and Family Support.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (3), S. 671–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0571-8.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Familie // family; Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; lesbisch // lesbian; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; schwul // gay; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Felson, Richard B.; Cundiff, Patrick R. (2014):

Sexual assault as a crime against young people.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 273–284. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0127-8.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Fielder, Robyn L.; Carey, Michael P. (2010):

Predictors and consequences of sexual "hookups" among college students: a short-term prospective study.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1105–1119. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9448-4.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Universität // college university

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Fielder, Robyn L.; Walsh, Jennifer L.; Carey, Kate B.; Carey, Michael P. (2013):

Predictors of sexual hookups: a theory-based, prospective study of first-year college women.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1425–1441. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0106-0.

Schlagwörter:

Frauen // women; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Forsman, Mats; Johansson, Ada; Santtila, Pekka; Sandnabba, Kenneth; Långström, Niklas (2015):

Sexually Coercive Behavior Following Childhood Maltreatment.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 149–156.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Gewalt // violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Galinsky, Adena M.; Sonenstein, Freya Lund (2013):

Relationship commitment, perceived equity, and sexual enjoyment among young adults in the United States.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (1), S. 93–104. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0003-y.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Vergnügen // pleasure

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Gartrell, Nanette K.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Goldberg, Naomi G. (2011):

Adolescents of the U.S. National Longitudinal Lesbian Family Study. Sexual orientation, sexual behavior, and sexual risk exposure.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (6), S. 1199–1209. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9692-2.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Jugendliche // youth; lesbisch // lesbian; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Gattis, Maurice N.; Woodford, Michael R.; Han, Yoonsun (2014):

Discrimination and depressive symptoms among sexual minority youth: is gay-affirming religious affiliation a protective factor?

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1589–1599. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0342-y.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Religion; Resilienz // resilience; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Heerde, Jessica A.; Scholes-Balog, Kirsty E.; Hemphill, Sheryl A. (2015):

Associations between youth homelessness, sexual offenses, sexual victimization, and sexual risk behaviors: a systematic literature review.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 181–212. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0375-2.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; obdachlos // homeless; Prostitution; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Soziale Schicht; Übersicht // review; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Hooghe, Marc (2011):

The impact of gendered friendship patterns on the prevalence of homophobia among Belgian late adolescents.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (3), S. 543–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9635-y.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Europa // Europe; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Jugendliche // youth; Peers; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Johnson, Matthew D. (2013):

Parent-child relationship quality directly and indirectly influences hooking up behavior reported in young adulthood through alcohol use in adolescence.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1463–1472. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0098-9.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Eltern // parents; Jugendliche // youth; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Johnston, Lisa G.; Mon, Myo Myo; Steinhaus, Mara; Sass, Justine (2017):

Correlates of Forced Sex Among Young Men Who Have Sex With Men in Yangon and Monywa, Myanmar.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 1001–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0761-z.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Jugendliche // youth; schwul // gay; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Kaestle, Christine E.; Allen, Katherine R. (2011):

The role of masturbation in healthy sexual development: perceptions of young adults.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 983–994. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9722-0.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Medien // media; Pornografie // pornography; sexuelle Skripte // sexual scripts; Solosexualität // masturbation

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Katz, Jennifer; Schneider, Monica E. (2013):

Casual hook up sex during the first year of college: Prospective associations with attitudes about sex and love relationships.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1451–1462. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0078-0.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college university

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Kingston, Drew A.; Graham, Franklyn J.; Knight, Raymond A. (2017):

Relations Between Self-Reported Adverse Events in Childhood and Hypersexuality in Adult Male Sexual Offenders.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 707–720. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0873-5.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2010):

Sexually coercive behavior in male youth: population survey of general and specific risk factors.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (5), S. 1161–1169. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9572-9.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Prostitution; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Koo, Kelly H.; Stephens, Kari A.; Lindgren, Kristen P.; George, William H. (2012):

Misogyny, acculturation, and ethnic identity: relation to rape-supportive attitudes in Asian American college men.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1005–1014. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9729-1.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Identität // identity; Nordamerika // North America; Rape Culture; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college university; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung

Kuyper, Lisette; Wit, John de; Adam, Philippe; Woertman, Liesbeth (2012):

Doing more good than harm? The effects of participation in sex research on young people in the Netherlands.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (2), S. 497–506. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9780-y.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Forschung // research; Jugendliche // youth; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik

Lasher, Michael P.; Stinson, Jill D. (2017):

Adults with Pedophilic Interests in the United States: Current Practices and Suggestions for Future Policy and Research.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 659–670. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0822-3.

Schlagwörter:

Nordamerika // North America; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Policies

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Lea, Toby; Wit, John de; Reynolds, Robert (2014):

Minority stress in lesbian, gay, and bisexual young adults in Australia: associations with psychological distress, suicidality, and substance use.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (8), S. 1571–1578. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0266-6.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Lefkowitz, Eva S.; Vasilenko, Sara A.; Leavitt, Chelom E. (2016):

Oral vs. Vaginal Sex Experiences and Consequences Among First-Year College Students.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (2), S. 329–337. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0654-6.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Lehrer, Jocelyn A.; Lehrer, Evelyn L.; Koss, Mary P. (2013):

Unwanted sexual experiences in young men. Evidence from a survey of university students in Chile.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (2), S. 213–223. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0004-x.

Schlagwörter:

Lateinamerika // Latin America; Latinx; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Luder, Marie-Thérèse; Pittet, Isabelle; Berchtold, André; Akre, Christina; Michaud, Pierre-André; Surís, Joan-Carles (2011):

Associations between online pornography and sexual behavior among adolescents. Myth or reality?

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1027–1035. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9714-0.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Europa // Europe; Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Pornografie // pornography; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Lyons, Heidi; Manning, Wendy; Giordano, Peggy; Longmore, Monica (2013):

Predictors of heterosexual casual sex among young adults.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 585–593. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0051-3.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Macapagal, Kathryn; Janssen, Erick; Matson, Margaret; Finn, Peter R.; Heiman, Julia R. (2017):

The Impact of Gain- and Loss-Framed Messages on Young Adults' Sexual Decision Making: An Experimental Study.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (2), S. 385–394. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0679-x.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Malón, Agustín (2010):

Onanism and child sexual abuse: a comparative study of two hypotheses.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 637–652. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9465-3.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Risiko // risk; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Malón, Agustín (2011):

The “Participating Victim” in the Study of Erotic Experiences Between Children and Adults: An Historical Analysis.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (1), S. 169–188.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Malón, Agustín (2015):

Adult–Child Sex and the Limits of Liberal Sexual Morality.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (4), S. 1071–1083.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; Konsens // consent; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Muise, Amy; Preyde, Michéle; Maitland, Scott B.; Milhausen, Robin R. (2010):

Sexual identity and sexual well-being in female heterosexual university students.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (4), S. 915–925. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9492-8.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Identität // identity; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Mustanski, Brian; Liu, Richard T. (2013):

A longitudinal study of predictors of suicide attempts among lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (3), S. 437–448. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0013-9.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Selbstmord // suicide; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Niehaus, Ashley F.; Jackson, Joan; Davies, Stephanie (2010):

Sexual self-schemas of female child sexual abuse survivors. Relationships with risky sexual behavior and sexual assault in adolescence.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (6), S. 1359–1374. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9600-9.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.4 Übergriff

O'Hara, Ross E.; Cooper, M. Lynne (2015):

Bidirectional associations between alcohol use and sexual risk-taking behavior from adolescence into young adulthood.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (4), S. 857–871. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0510-8.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Oidtman, Jessica; Sherman, Susan G.; Morgan, Anthony; German, Danielle; Arrington-Sanders, Renata (2017):

Satisfaction and Condomless Anal Sex at Sexual Debut and Sexual Risk Among Young Black Same-Sex Attracted Men.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (4), S. 947–959. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0831-2.

Schlagwörter:

erstes Mal // sexual debut; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; schwarz // black; schwul // gay; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Olmstead, Spencer B.; Billen, Rhett M.; Conrad, Kathryn A.; Pasley, Kay; Fincham, Frank D. (2013):

Sex, commitment, and casual sex relationships among college men: a mixed-methods analysis.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (4), S. 561–571. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-012-0047-z.

Schlagwörter:

Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college university

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Ott, Miles Q.; Corliss, Heather L.; Wypij, David; Rosario, Margaret; Austin, S. Bryn (2011):

Stability and change in self-reported sexual orientation identity in young people: application of mobility metrics.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (3), S. 519–532. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9691-3.

Schlagwörter:

Nordamerika // North America; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Pasterski, Vickie; Mastroyannopoulou, Kiki; Wright, Deborah; Zucker, Kenneth J.; Hughes, Ieuan A. (2014):

Predictors of posttraumatic stress in parents of children diagnosed with a disorder of sex development.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (2), S. 369–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0196-8.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Trauma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

Patrick, Megan E.; Lee, Christine M. (2010):

Sexual motivations and engagement in sexual behavior during the transition to college.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 674–681. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9435-9.

Schlagwörter:

Nordamerika // North America; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college university

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Peter, Jochen; Valkenburg, Patti M. (2011):

The use of sexually explicit internet material and its antecedents: a longitudinal comparison of adolescents and adults.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 1015–1025. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9644-x.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Pornografie // pornography; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Rellini, Alessandra H.; Meston, Cindy M. (2011):

Sexual self-schemas, sexual dysfunction, and the sexual responses of women with a history of childhood sexual abuse.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (2), S. 351–362. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9694-0.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Folgen // long-term effects; Frauen // women; Nordamerika // North America; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Rice, Eric; Winetrobe, Hailey; Holloway, Ian W.; Montoya, Jorge; Plant, Aaron; Kordic, Timothy (2015):

Cell phone internet access, online sexual solicitation, partner seeking, and sexual risk behavior among adolescents.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 755–763. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0366-3.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Rieger, Gerulf; Savin-Williams, Ritch C. (2012):

Gender nonconformity, sexual orientation, and psychological well-being.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (3), S. 611–621. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9738-0.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Savin-Williams, Ritch C.; Joyner, Kara (2014):

The dubious assessment of gay, lesbian, and bisexual adolescents of add health.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (3), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0219-5.

Schlagwörter:

Forschung // research; Nordamerika // North America; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Schmidt, Alexander F.; Babchishin, Kelly M.; Lehmann, Robert J. B. (2017):

A Meta-Analysis of Viewing Time Measures of Sexual Interest in Children.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (1), S. 287–300. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0806-3.

Schlagwörter:

Forschung // research; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Schönbucher, Verena; Maier, Thomas; Mohler-Kuo, Meichun; Schnyder, Ulrich; Landolt, Markus A. (2014):

Adolescent perspectives on social support received in the aftermath of sexual abuse: a qualitative study.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (3), S. 571–586. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0230-x.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.4 Resilienz

Senn, Theresa E.; Carey, Michael P.; Coury-Doniger, Patricia (2012):

Mediators of the relation between childhood sexual abuse and women's sexual risk behavior: a comparison of two theoretical frameworks.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (6), S. 1363–1377. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9897-z.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität

Seto, Michael C. (2012):

Is pedophilia a sexual orientation?

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (1), S. 231–236. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9882-6.

Schlagwörter:

Pädosexualität // pedosexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.3 Methodologie

Seto, Michael C.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Kjellgren, Cecilia; Priebe, Gisela; Svedin, Carl Göran; Långström, Niklas (2015):

Viewing child pornography: prevalence and correlates in a representative community sample of young Swedish men.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (1), S. 67–79. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0244-4.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Kinderpornographie; Männer // men

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Sommer, Marni; Likindikoki, Samuel; Kaaya, Sylvia (2015):

"Bend a fish when the fish is not yet dry": adolescent boys' perceptions of sexual risk in Tanzania.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 583–595. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0406-z.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Jungen // boys; Risiko // risk; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergreif; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Stulhofer, Aleksandar; Busko, Vesna; Landripet, Ivan (2010):

Pornography, sexual socialization, and satisfaction among young men.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (1), S. 168–178. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-008-9387-0.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Internet; Jungen // boys; Pornografie // pornography; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Swann, Gregory; Minsheu, Reese; Newcomb, Michael E.; Mustanski, Brian (2016):

Validation of the Sexual Orientation Microaggression Inventory in Two Diverse Samples of LGBTQ Youth.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (6), S. 1289–1298. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0718-2.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Thompson, Ashley E.; Byers, E. Sandra (2017):

Heterosexual Young Adults' Interest, Attitudes, and Experiences Related to Mixed-Gender, Multi-Person Sex.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 46 (3), S. 813–822. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0699-1.

Schlagwörter:

Heterosexualität // heterosexuality; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Turner, Daniel; Hoyer, Juergen; Schmidt, Alexander F.; Klein, Verena; Briken, Peer (2016):

Risk Factors for Sexual Offending in Men Working With Children: A Community-Based Survey.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (7), S. 1851–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0746-y.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

van Leeuwen, Matthijs L.; van Baaren, Rick B.; Chakhssi, Farid; Loonen, Marijke G. M.; Lippman, Maarten; Dijksterhuis, Ap (2013):

Assessment of implicit sexual associations in non-incarcerated pedophiles.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 42 (8), S. 1501–1507. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-013-0094-0.

Schlagwörter:

Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse
van Oosten, Johanna M. F. (2016):

Sexually Explicit Internet Material and Adolescents' Sexual Uncertainty: The Role of Disposition-Content Congruency.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (4), S. 1011–1022. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-015-0594-1.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Pornografie // pornography

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

van Ryzin, Mark J.; Johnson, Amber B.; Leve, Leslie D.; Kim, Hyoun K. (2011):

The number of sexual partners and health-risking sexual behavior: prediction from high school entry to high school exit.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 939–949. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-010-9649-5.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Eltern // parents; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Vandenbosch, Laura; Eggermont, Steven (2015):

The role of mass media in adolescents' sexual behaviors: exploring the explanatory value of the three-step self-objectification process.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 44 (3), S. 729–742. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0292-4.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Medien // media; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Velezmoro, Rodrigo; Negy, Charles; Livia, Jose (2012):

Online sexual activity. Cross-national comparison between United States and Peruvian college students.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 41 (4), S. 1015–1025. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9862-x.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Medien // media; Nordamerika // North America; Pornografie // pornography; Religion; Risiko // risk; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Vries, Hein de; Eggers, Sander Matthijs; Jinabhai, Champak; Meyer-Weitz, Anna; Sathiparsad, Reshma; Taylor, Myra (2014):

Adolescents' beliefs about forced sex in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 43 (6), S. 1087–1095. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-014-0280-8.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Vrouenraets, Lieke Josephina Jeanne Johanna; Fredriks, A. Miranda; Hannema, Sabine E.; Cohen-Kettenis, Peggy T.; Vries, Martine C. de (2016):

Perceptions of Sex, Gender, and Puberty Suppression: A Qualitative Analysis of Transgender Youth.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (7), S. 1697–1703. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0764-9.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Gesundheit // health; Jugendliche // youth; Pubertät // Puberty; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Wetherill, Reagan R.; Neal, Dan J.; Fromme, Kim (2010):

Parents, peers, and sexual values influence sexual behavior during the transition to college.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (3), S. 682–694. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-009-9476-8.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Familie // family; Nordamerika // North America; Peers; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Wilson, Helen W.; Spatz Widom, Cathy (2010):

Does Physical Abuse, Sexual Abuse, or Neglect in Childhood Increase the Likelihood of Same-sex Sexual Relationships and Cohabitation? A Prospective 30-year Follow-up.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 39 (1), S. 63–74.

Schlagwörter:

Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Ybarra, Michele L.; Espelage, Dorothy L.; Langhinrichsen-Rohling, Jennifer; Korchmaros, Josephine D.; Boyd, Danah (2016):

Lifetime Prevalence Rates and Overlap of Physical, Psychological, and Sexual Dating Abuse Perpetration and Victimization in a National Sample of Youth.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 45 (5), S. 1083–1099. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-016-0748-9.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Zimmer-Gembeck, Melanie J.; Ducat, Wendy H.; Boislard-Pepin, Marie-Aude (2011):

A prospective study of young females' sexual subjectivity: associations with age, sexual behavior, and dating.

In: *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 40 (5), S. 927–938. DOI: 10.1007/s10508-011-9751-3.

Schlagwörter:

Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Mädchen // girls; Selbstbestimmung // agency; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Child Abuse & Neglect

Alessi, Edward J.; Kahn, Sarilee; Chatterji, Sangeeta (2016):

‘The darkest times of my life’. Recollections of child abuse among forced migrants persecuted because of their sexual orientation and gender identity.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 51, S. 93–105.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Migration; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Beier, Klaus M.; Oezdemir, Umut C.; Schlinzig, Eliza; Groll, Anna; Hupp, Elena; Hellenschmidt, Tobias (2016):

“Just dreaming of them”. The Berlin Project for Primary Prevention of Child Sexual Abuse by Juveniles (PPJ).

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 52, S. 1–10.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Black, Pamela J.; Wollis, Melissa; Woodworth, Michael; Hancock, Jeffrey T. (2015):

A linguistic analysis of grooming strategies of online child sex offenders: Implications for our understanding of predatory sexual behavior in an increasingly computer-mediated world.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 44, S. 140–149.

Schlagwörter:

Grooming; Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Sprache // language; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.2 Art
Brunnberg, Elinor; Lindén Boström, Margareta; Berglund, Mats (2012):

Sexual force at sexual debut. Swedish adolescents with disabilities at higher risk than adolescents without disabilities.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (4), S. 285–295.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; erstes Mal // sexual debut; Europa // Europe; Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Collin-Vézina, Delphine; Garrido, Edward F. (2017):

Current issues in child sexual abuse, gender and health outcomes: Shedding new lights to inform worldwide policy and practice.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 245–248. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.11.032.

Schlagwörter:

sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Collin-Vézina, Delphine; Sablonnière-Griffin, Mireille de la; Palmer, Andrea M.; Milne, Lise (2015):

A preliminary mapping of individual, relational, and social factors that impede disclosure of childhood sexual abuse.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 43, S. 123–134.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

D'Alton, Paul; Guilfoyle, Michael; Randall, Patrick (2013):

Roman Catholic Clergy who have sexually abused children: Their perceptions of their developmental experience.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 698–702.

Schlagwörter:

Christentum // christianity; Geistliche // clergy; Intimität // intimacy; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender; Vergewaltigung // rape; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.5 Religion; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.9 Kirche; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Delft, Ivanka van; Finkenauer, Catrin; Schipper, J. Clasiën de; Lamers-Winkelmann, Francien; Visser, Margreet M. (2015):

The mediating role of secrecy in the development of psychopathology in sexually abused children.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 27–36.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Geheimnis // secrets; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Finkelhor, David; Ji, Kai; Mikton, Christopher; Dunne, Michael (2013):

Explaining lower rates of sexual abuse in China.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (10), S. 852–860.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Disclosure; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Professionalität // professionalism; Stigmatisierung // stigma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Frías, Sonia M.; Erviti, Joaquina (2014):

Gendered experiences of sexual abuse of teenagers and children in Mexico.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (4), S. 776–787.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Lateinamerika // Latin America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Grossi, Laura M.; Lee, Austin F.; Schuler, Ann; Ryan, Julie L.; Prentky, Robert A. (2016):

Sexualized behaviors in cohorts of children in the child welfare system.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 52, S. 49–61. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.12.014.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 7 Sexualität

Hidalgo, Marco A.; Kuhns, Lisa M.; Kwon, Soyang; Mustanski, Brian; Garofalo, Robert (2015):

The impact of childhood gender expression on childhood sexual abuse and psychopathology among young men who have sex with men.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 103–112.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Nordamerika // North America; schwul // gay; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Trauma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Jackson, Vicki; Browne, Kevin; Joseph, Stephen (2016):

The prevalence of childhood victimization experienced outside of the family. Findings from an English prevalence study.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 51, S. 343–357. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.08.006.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Prävalenz // prevalence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Joyal, Christian C.; Carpentier, Julie; Martin, Caroline (2016):

Discriminant factors for adolescent sexual offending. On the usefulness of considering both victim age and sibling incest.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 54, S. 10–22.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Familie // family; Inzest // incest; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Kaltiala-Heino, Riittakerttu; Fröjd, Sari; Marttunen, Mauri (2016):

Sexual harassment victimization in adolescence. Associations with family background.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 56, S. 11–19.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Familie // family; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Kim, Tae Kyung; Choi, Soul; Shin, Yee Jin (2011):

Psychosocial factors influencing competency of children's statements on sexual trauma.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (3), S. 173–179.

Schlagwörter:

sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Trauma

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Krahé, Barbara; Berger, Anja (2017):

Gendered pathways from child sexual abuse to sexual aggression victimization and perpetration in adolescence and young adulthood.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 261–272. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.10.004.

Schlagwörter:

Revictimisierung // revictimization; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Lacelle, Céline; Hébert, Martine; Lavoie, Francine; Vitaro, Frank; Tremblay, Richard E. (2012):

Sexual health in women reporting a history of child sexual abuse.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (3), S. 247–259.

Schlagwörter:

Frauen // women; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.4 Resilienz

Langeland, Willemiem; Hoogendoorn, Adriaan W.; Mager, Daniel; Smit, Jan H.; Draijer, Nel (2015):

Childhood sexual abuse by representatives of the Roman Catholic Church. A prevalence estimate among the Dutch population.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 67–77.

Schlagwörter:

Christentum // christianity; Europa // Europe; Geistliche // clergy; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.9 Kirche; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Langevin, Rachel; Hébert, Martine; Cossette, Louise (2015):

Emotion regulation as a mediator of the relation between sexual abuse and behavior problems in preschoolers.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 16–26.

Schlagwörter:

Gefühle // emotions; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Leventhal, John M.; Murphy, Janet L.; Asnes, Andrea G. (2010):

Evaluations of child sexual abuse. Recognition of overt and latent family concerns.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34 (5), S. 289–295.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Lin, Danhua; Li, Xiaoming; Fan, Xinghua; Fang, Xiaoyi (2011):

Child sexual abuse and its relationship with health risk behaviors among rural children and adolescents in Hunan, China.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (9), S. 680–687. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2011.05.006.

Schlagwörter:

Gesundheit // health; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Loeb, Tamra B.; Gaines, Tommi; Wyatt, Gail E.; Zhang, Muyu; Liu, Honghu (2011):

Associations between child sexual abuse and negative sexual experiences and revictimization among women. Does measuring severity matter?

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (11), S. 946–955.

Schlagwörter:

Frauen // women; Revictimisierung // revictimization; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Lorenz, Tierney Ahrold; Meston, Cindy May (2012):

Associations among childhood sexual abuse, language use, and adult sexual functioning and satisfaction.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (2), S. 190–199.

Schlagwörter:

Erwachsene; Folgen // long-term effects; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 7 Sexualität

Lueger-Schuster, Brigitte; Kantor, Viktoria; Weindl, Dina; Knefel, Matthias; Moy, Yvonne; Butollo, Asisa et al. (2014):

Institutional abuse of children in the Austrian Catholic Church. Types of abuse and impact on adult survivors' current mental health.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (1), S. 52–64.

Schlagwörter:

Christentum // christianity; Europa // Europe; Geistliche // clergy; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Religion; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Trauma

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.9 Kirche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

Maikovich-Fong, Andrea Kohn; Jaffee, Sara R. (2010):

Sex differences in childhood sexual abuse characteristics and victims' emotional and behavioral problems. Findings from a national sample of youth.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34 (6), S. 429–437. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2009.10.006.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Jugendliche // youth; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Martin, Karin A. (2014):

Making sense of children's sexual behavior in child care. An analysis of adult responses in special investigation reports.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (10), S. 1636–1646.

Schlagwörter:

Grundschule // elementary school; Kinderbetreuung // child care; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.1 Kindertagesstätte; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

McPhail, Ian V.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Fernandez, Yolanda M. (2014):

Correlates of emotional congruence with children in sexual offenders against children. A test of theoretical models in an incarcerated sample.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (2), S. 336–346.

Schlagwörter:

Gefühle // emotions; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Ybarra, Michele L.; Korchmaros, Josephine D. (2014):

Sexual harassment among adolescents of different sexual orientations and gender identities.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (2), S. 280–295.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Technologie // technology; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Morris, Matthew C.; Kouros, Chrystyna D.; Janecek, Kim; Freeman, Rachel; Mielock, Alyssa; Garber, Judy (2017):

Community-level moderators of a school-based childhood sexual assault prevention program.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 63, S. 295–306. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2016.10.005.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; Sicherheit // safety

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Ojanen, Timo Tapani; Boonmongkon, Pimpawun; Samakkeekarom, Ronnapoom; Samoh, Nattharat; Cholratana, Mudjalini; Guadamuz, Thomas Ebanan (2015):

Connections between online harassment and offline violence among youth in Central Thailand.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 44, S. 159–169.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt // violence; Internet; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Priebe, Gisela; Bäckström, Martin; Ainsaar, Mare (2010):

Vulnerable adolescent participants' experience in surveys on sexuality and sexual abuse. Ethical aspects.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 34 (6), S. 438–447.

Schlagwörter:

Ehtik // ethics; Forschung // research; Jugendliche // youth; Sexualität // sexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik

Pullman, Lesleigh E.; Seto, Michael C. (2012):

Assessment and treatment of adolescent sexual offenders. Implications of recent research on generalist versus specialist explanations.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (3), S. 203–209.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Rassenhofer, Miriam; Zimmer, Andreas; Spröder, Nina; Fegert, Jörg M. (2015):

Child sexual abuse in the Roman Catholic Church in Germany: Comparison of victim-impact data collected through church-sponsored and government-sponsored programs.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 40, S. 60–67.

Schlagwörter:

Beschwerdemanagement // complaint management; Christentum // christianity; Disclosure; Empowerment // empowerment; Europa // Europe; Geistliche // clergy; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.5 Religion; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Rumble, Lauren; Mungate, Taizivei; Chigiji, Handrick; Salama, Peter; Nolan, Anthony; Sammon, Elayn; Muwoni, Leon (2015):

Childhood sexual violence in Zimbabwe: evidence for the epidemic against girls.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 46, S. 60–66. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2015.04.015.

Schlagwörter:

Prävalenz // prevalence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Schaeffer, Paula; Leventhal, John M.; Gottsegen Asnes, Andrea (2011):

Children's disclosures of sexual abuse. Learning from direct inquiry.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 35 (5), S. 343–352.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Soylu, Nusret; Ayaz, Muhammed; Yüksel, Tuğb (2014):

Early-married and sexually abused girls differ in their psychiatric outcomes.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 38 (9), S. 1552–1559.

Schlagwörter:

Heirat // marriage; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Sterzing, Paul R.; Ratliff, G. Allen; Gartner, Rachel E.; McGeough, Briana L.; Johnson, Kelly C. (2017):

Social Ecological Correlates of Polyvictimization among a National Sample of Transgender, Genderqueer, and Cisgender Sexual Minority Adolescents.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 67, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.02.017.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Vaillancourt-Morel, Marie-Pier; Godbout, Natacha; Labadie, Chloé; Runtz, Marsha; Lussier, Yvan; Sabourin, Stéphane (2015):

Avoidant and compulsive sexual behaviors in male and female survivors of childhood sexual abuse.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 40, S. 48–59.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Ybarra, Michele L.; Mitchell, Kimberly J.; Palmer, Neal A.; Reisner, Sari L. (2015):

Online social support as a buffer against online and offline peer and sexual victimization among U.S. LGBT and non-LGBT youth.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 39, S. 123–136.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Zhang, Wenjing; Chen, Jingqi; Feng, Yanan; Li, Jingyi; Zhao, Xiaoxia; Luo, Xiaoling (2013):

Young children's knowledge and skills related to sexual abuse prevention. A pilot study in Beijing, China.

In: *Child Abuse & Neglect* 37 (9), S. 623–630.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Kinder // children; Prävention // prevention; Wissen // knowledge

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Child Abuse Review

Allardyce, Stuart; Yates, Peter Michael (2013):

Assessing Risk of Victim Crossover with Children and Young People who display Harmful Sexual Behaviours.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (4), S. 255–267. DOI: 10.1002/car.2277.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Geschwister // siblings; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Allnock, Debra; Radford, Lorraine; Bunting, Lisa; Price, Avril; Morgan-Klein, Natalie; Ellis, Jane; Stafford, Anne (2012):

In Demand. Therapeutic Services for Children and Young People Who Have Experienced Sexual Abuse.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (5), S. 318–334. DOI: 10.1002/car.1205.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.4 Resilienz

Babatsikos, Georgia (2010):

Parents' knowledge, attitudes and practices about preventing child sexual abuse. A literature review.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (2), S. 107–129. DOI: 10.1002/car.1102.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Eltern // parents; Global; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Bajaj, Monika (2012):

Vesicular Genital Lesions in a Toddler – Is it Sexual Abuse?

In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (5), S. 370–373. DOI: 10.1002/car.1188.

Schlagwörter:

sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Balfe, Myles; Gallagher, Bernard; Masson, Helen; Balfe, Shane; Brugha, Ruairi; Hackett, Simon (2015):

Internet Child Sex Offenders' Concerns about Online Security and their Use of Identity Protection Technologies. A Review.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 24 (6), S. 427–439. DOI: 10.1002/car.2308.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Baratvand, Mahmood; Soodani, Mansour; Zarei, Eghbal; Asadollahi, Abdolrahim (2013):

Sexual Abuse and Drug Abuse Among Homeless Children in Ahvaz, Iran.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (6), S. 408–418. DOI: 10.1002/car.2263.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Kinder // children; obdachlos // homeless; Schutz // protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Barron, Ian G.; Topping, Keith J. (2011):

Sexual abuse prevention programme fidelity. Video analysis of interactions.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 134–151. DOI: 10.1002/car.1134.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Connon, Graham; Crooks, Allan; Carr, Alan; Dooley, Barbara; Guerin, Suzanne; Deasy, Derek et al. (2011):

Child sex abuse and the Irish criminal justice system.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 102–119. DOI: 10.1002/car.1156.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Coren, Esther; Thomae, Manuela; Hutchfield, Jemeela; Iredale, Wendy (2013):

Report on the Implementation and Results of an Outcomes-focused Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Interventions in the UK.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (1), S. 44–59. DOI: 10.1002/car.2200.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Folgen // long-term effects; Intervention // intervention; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Fitzpatrick, Mark; Carr, Alan; Dooley, Barbara; Flanagan-Howard, Roisín; Flanagan, Edel; Tierney, Kevin et al. (2010):

Profiles of adult survivors of severe sexual, physical and emotional institutional abuse in Ireland.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (6), S. 387–404. DOI: 10.1002/car.1083.

Schlagwörter:

Geistliche // clergy; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz
Hackett, Simon; Phillips, Josie; Masson, Helen; Balfe, Myles (2013):

Individual, Family and Abuse Characteristics of 700 British Child and Adolescent Sexual Abusers.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 22 (4), S. 232–245. DOI: 10.1002/car.2246.

Schlagwörter:

jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Hawkes, Colin (2011):

Description of a UK study of onset of sexually harmful behaviour before the age of ten years in boys referred to a specialist assessment and treatment service.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 82–101. DOI: 10.1002/car.1133.

Schlagwörter:

Jungen // boys

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Hutchfield, Jemeela; Coren, Esther (2011):

The Child's Voice in Service Evaluation. Ethical and Methodological Issues.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 173–186. DOI: 10.1002/car.1142.

Schlagwörter:

Ehtik // ethics; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik; 8.3 Methodologie

Marriott, Clare; Hamilton-Giachritsis, Catherine; Harrop, Chris (2014):

Factors Promoting Resilience Following Childhood Sexual Abuse. A Structured, Narrative Review of the Literature.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 23 (1), S. 17–34. DOI: 10.1002/car.2258.

Schlagwörter:

Resilienz // resilience; Schutz // protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sprache // language; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.4 Resilienz

McElvaney, Rosaleen (2015):

Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse. Delays, Non-disclosure and Partial Disclosure. What the Research Tells Us and Implications for Practice.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 24 (3), S. 159–169. DOI: 10.1002/car.2280.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

McLoone-Richards, Claire (2012):

Say Nothing! How Pathology within Catholicism Created and Sustained the Institutional Abuse of Children in 20 th Century Ireland.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 21 (6), S. 394–404. DOI: 10.1002/car.2209.

Schlagwörter:

Christentum // christianity; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Kinder // children

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Parent, Sylvie; Demers, Guylaine (2011):

Sexual abuse in sport. A model to prevent and protect athletes.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (2), S. 120–133. DOI: 10.1002/car.1135.

Schlagwörter:

Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sport // sports

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Pearce, Jenny J. (2014):

'What's Going On' to Safeguard Children and Young People from Child Sexual Exploitation. A Review of Local Safeguarding Children Boards' Work to Protect Children from Sexual Exploitation.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 23 (3), S. 159–170. DOI: 10.1002/car.2269.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Roberts, Susan (2011):

Doing Research with Imprisoned Adult Male Child Sexual Abusers. Reflecting on the Challenges.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 187–196. DOI: 10.1002/car.1175.

Schlagwörter:

Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik; 8.3 Methodologie

Wager, Nadia (2011):

Researching Sexual Revictimisation. Associated Ethical and Methodological Issues, and Possible Solutions.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 20 (3), S. 158–172. DOI: 10.1002/car.1152.

Schlagwörter:

Forschung // research; Revictimisierung // revictimization; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Trauma

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik

Wurtele, Sandy K.; Kenny, Maureen C. (2010):

Partnering with parents to prevent childhood sexual abuse.

In: *Child Abuse Review* 19 (2), S. 130–152. DOI: 10.1002/car.1112.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Prävention // prevention; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Childhood

Åmot, Ingvild; Ytterhus, Borgunn (2014):

'Talking bodies'. Power and counter-power between children and adults in day care.

In: *Childhood* 21 (2), S. 260–273. DOI: 10.1177/0907568213490971.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Kinderbetreuung // child care; Kinderrechte // children's rights; Körper // body; Macht // power

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.1 Kindertagesstätte; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Bhana, D. (2016):

'Sex isnt better than love. Exploring South African Indian teenage male and female desires beyond danger.

In: *Childhood* 23 (3), S. 362–377. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216642828.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Chappell, Paul; Rule, Peter; Dlamini, Mfana; Nkala, Nompilo (2014):

Troubling power dynamics. Youth with disabilities as co-researchers in sexuality research in South Africa.

In: *Childhood* 21 (3), S. 385–399. DOI: 10.1177/0907568214525427.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Empowerment // empowerment; Jugendliche // youth; Macht // power; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Professionalität // professionalism; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Sprache // language; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 5 Adressat_innen; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik; 8.3 Methodologie

Pasura, Dominic; Jones, Adele D.; Hafner, James A. H.; Maharaj, Priya E.; Nathaniel-DeCaires, Karene; Johnson, Emmanuel Janagan (2013):

Competing meanings of childhood and the social construction of child sexual abuse in the Caribbean.

In: *Childhood* 20 (2), S. 200–214. DOI: 10.1177/0907568212462255.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Rysst, Mari (2010):

'I Am Only Ten Years Old'. Femininities, clothing-fashion codes and the intergenerational gap of interpretation of young girls' clothes.

In: *Childhood* 17 (1), S. 76–93. DOI: 10.1177/0907568209351552.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Geschlecht // gender; Mädchen // girls; Medien // media; Selbstbestimmung // agency; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; Sexualisierung // sexualization; Weiblichkeit // femininity

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Spišák, Sanna; Paasonen, Susanna (2017):

Bad education? Childhood recollections of pornography, sexual exploration, learning and agency in Finland.

In: *Childhood* 24 (1), S. 99–112. DOI: 10.1177/0907568216646436.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Pornografie // pornography

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Children and Youth Services Review

Benuto, Lorraine T.; O'Donohue, William (2015):

Treatment of the Sexually Abused Child. Review and Synthesis of Recent Meta-Analyses.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 56, S. 52–60. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2015.06.009.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Global; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Biswas, Bipasha; Vaughn, Michael G. (2011):

Really troubled girls. Gender differences in risky sexual behavior and its correlates in a sample of juvenile offenders.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 33 (11), S. 2386–2391. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2011.08.010.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Geschlecht // gender; Gesundheit // health; Heim // residential care; Kinder // children; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht; Sozialisation // socialization; Strafrecht // criminal justice; Trauma; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 2.2.10 Justizvollzugsanstalt; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Boustani, Maya M.; Frazier, Stacy L.; Lesperance, Nephtalie (2017):

Sexual health programming for vulnerable youth. Improving knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 375–383. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2017.01.013.

Schlagwörter:

Heim // residential care; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; Risiko // risk; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Franklin, Anita; Smeaton, Emilie (2017):

Recognising and responding to young people with learning disabilities who experience, or are at risk of, child sexual exploitation in the UK.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 73, S. 474–481. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2016.11.009.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Prävention // prevention; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Schutz // protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Gokten, Emel Sari; Saday Duman, Nagihan (2016):

Factors influencing the development of psychiatric disorders in the victims of sexual abuse. A study on Turkish children.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 69, S. 49–55. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2016.07.022.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender; Trauma

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Goodkind, Sara; Schelbe, Lisa; Joseph, Andrea A.; Beers, Daphne E.; Pinsky, Stephanie L. (2013):

Providing new opportunities or reinforcing old stereotypes? Perceptions and experiences of single-sex public education.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (8), S. 1174–1181. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2013.04.004.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Geschlecht // gender; geschlechtergetrennte Bildung // single-sex education; Nordamerika // North America; Schule // school; Sexualisierung // sexualization; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Graham, Laurie M.; Lanier, Paul; Johnson-Motoyama, Michelle (2016):

National profile of Latino/Latina children reported to the child welfare system for sexual abuse.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 66, S. 18–27. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2016.04.008.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Latinx; Nordamerika // North America; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Katz, Carmit (2013):

Internet-related child sexual abuse. What children tell us in their testimonies.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (9), S. 1536–1542. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2013.06.006.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Katz, Carmit; Hamama, Liat (2013):

“Draw me everything that happened to you”. Exploring children's drawings of sexual abuse.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (5), S. 877–882. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2013.02.007.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Kenny, Maureen C. (2010):

Child sexual abuse education with ethnically diverse families. A preliminary analysis.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 32 (7), S. 981–989. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2010.03.025.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Miller, Susan L.; Hefner, M. Kristen; Leon, Chrysanthi S. (2014):

Diffusing responsibility. A case study of child sexual abuse in popular discourse.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 37, S. 55–63. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2013.12.005.

Schlagwörter:

Medien // media; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Victim-blaming

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Parent, Sylvie; Bannon, Joëlle (2012):

Sexual abuse in sport. What about boys?

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (2), S. 354–359. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2011.11.004.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Jungen // boys; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sport // sports; Sportunterricht // physical education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.3.1 Schulfächer; 2.2.3.1.1 Sportunterricht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Perdahl Fis, Nese; Arman, Ayse; Kalaca, Sibel; Berkem, Meral (2010):

Psychiatric evaluation of sexual abuse cases. A clinical representative sample from Turkey.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 32 (10), S. 1285–1290. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2010.04.020.

Schlagwörter:

Psychiatrie // psychiatry; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Ramseyer Winter, Virginia; Brandon-Friedman, Richard A.; Ely, Gretchen E. (2016):

Sexual health behaviors and outcomes among current and former foster youth. A review of the literature.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 64, S. 1–14. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2016.02.023.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Robertson, Roni Diamant (2013):

The invisibility of adolescent sexual development in foster care. Seriously addressing sexually transmitted infections and access to services.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (3), S. 493–504. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2012.12.009.

Schlagwörter:

Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Seelman, Kristie L.; Forge, Nicholas; Walls, N. Eugene; Bridges, Nadine (2015):

School engagement among LGBTQ high school students. The roles of safe adults and gay–straight alliance characteristics.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 57, S. 19–29. DOI: 10.1016/j.chidyouth.2015.07.021.

Schlagwörter:

Schule // school; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.3.1 Schulfächer; 2.2.3.1.3 AGs; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Walsh, Kerryann; Mathews, Ben; Rassafiani, Mehdi; Farrell, Ann; Butler, Des (2012):

Understanding teachers' reporting of child sexual abuse. Measurement methods matter.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (9), S. 1937–1946. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2012.06.004.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Disclosure; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik

Wells, Elizabeth A.; Asakura, Kenta; Hoppe, Marilyn J.; Balsam, Kimberly F.; Morrison, Diane M.; Beadnell, Blair (2012):

Social Services for Sexual Minority Youth: Preferences for What, Where, and How Services are Delivered.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 36 (2), S. 312–320. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2012.11.011.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Wernick, Laura J.; Kulick, Alex; Inglehart, Marita H. (2013):

Factors predicting student intervention when witnessing anti-LGBTQ harassment. The influence of peers, teachers, and climate.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 35 (2), S. 296–301. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2012.11.003.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Mobbing // bullying; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sprache // language; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Wilson, Bianca; Kastanis, Angeliki A. (2015):

Sexual and gender minority disproportionality and disparities in child welfare. A population-based study.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 58, S. 11–17. DOI: 10.1016/j.chilyouth.2015.08.016.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.3 Schicht; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Wurtele, Sandy K. (2012):

Preventing the sexual exploitation of minors in youth-serving organizations.

In: *Children and Youth Services Review* 34 (12), S. 2442–2453. DOI: 10.1016/j.childyouth.2012.09.009.

Schlagwörter:

institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Jugendorganisationen // youth-serving organisations; Kinder // children; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Nordamerika // North America; Professionalität // professionalism; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 2.2.8 Offene Kinder- und Jugendarbeit; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Culture, Health & Sexuality

Bhana, Deevia; Pattman, Rob (2011):

Girls want money, boys want virgins. The materiality of love amongst South African township youth in the context of HIV and AIDS.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 961–972. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.576770.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Bui, Thanh Cong; Diamond, Pamela M.; Markham, Christine; Ross, Michael W.; Nguyen-Le, Thanh-An; Tran, Ly Hai Thi (2010):

Gender relations and sexual communication among female students in the Mekong River Delta of Vietnam.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (6), S. 591–601. DOI: 10.1080/13691050902968769.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Frauen // women; Gesundheit // health; Jugendliche // youth; Kommunikation // communication; Mädchen // girls; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Burchardt, Marian (2011):

Challenging Pentecostal moralism. Erotic geographies, religion and sexual practices among township youth in Cape Town.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 669–683. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.566356.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Religion; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.5 Religion; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Dahlbäck, Elisabeth; Maimbolwa, Margaret; Yamba, C. Bawa; Kasonka, Lackson; Bergström, Staffan; Ransjö-Arvidson, Anna-Berit (2010):

Pregnancy loss. Spontaneous and induced abortions among young women in Lusaka, Zambia.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 247–262. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903353383.

Schlagwörter:

Frauen // women; Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Schwangerschaftsabbruch // abortion; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Diarsvitri, Wienta; Utomo, Iwu Dwisetyani; Neeman, Teresa; Oktavian, Antonius (2011):

Beyond sexual desire and curiosity. Sexuality among senior high school students in Papua and West Papua Provinces (Indonesia) and implications for HIV prevention.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (9), S. 1047–1060. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.599862.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Prävention // prevention; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Eriksson, Elisabet; Lindmark, Gunilla; Axemo, Pia; Haddad, Beverley; Ahlberg, Beth Maina (2010):

Ambivalence, silence and gender differences in church leaders' HIV-prevention messages to young people in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 103–114. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903141192.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Prävention // prevention; Religion; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.5 Religion; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.9 Kirche; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Froyum, Carissa M. (2010):

Making 'good girls'. Sexual agency in the sexuality education of low-income black girls.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 59–72. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903272583.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; schwarz // black; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; Sexuelle Abstinenz // abstinence; Soziale Schicht; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Fu, Huiyan (2011):

The bumpy road to socialise nature. Sex education in Japan.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 903–915. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.587894.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; Policies; Schule // school; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Govender, Kaymarlin (2011):

The cool, the bad, the ugly, and the powerful. Identity struggles in schoolboy peer culture.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 887–901. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.586436.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Identität // identity; Jungen // boys; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Peers; Schule // school; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Hampshire, Kate; Porter, Gina; Mashiri, Mac; Maponya, Goodhope; Dube, Siphon (2011):

Proposing love on the way to school. Mobility, sexuality and youth transitions in South Africa.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (2), S. 217–231. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.522255.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Risiko // risk; Schule // school; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Hyde, Abbey; Carney, Marie; Drennan, Jonathan; Butler, Michelle; Lohan, Maria; Howlett, Etaoine (2010):

The silent treatment. Parents' narratives of sexuality education with young people.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 359–371. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903514455.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Tabu // taboo

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Kelly, Angela; Worth, Heather; Akuani, Frances; Kepa, Barbara; Kumpul, Martha; Walizopa, Lucy et al. (2010):

Gendered talk about sex, sexual relationships and HIV among young people in Papua New Guinea.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 221–232. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903181107.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Geschlecht // gender; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

McMichael, Celia; Gifford, Sandra (2010):

Narratives of sexual health risk and protection amongst young people from refugee backgrounds in Melbourne, Australia.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (3), S. 263–277. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903359265.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Geflohene // refugees; Jugendliche // youth; Migration; Risiko // risk; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

McMillan, Karen; Worth, Heather (2011):

The impact of socio-cultural context on young people's condom use. Evidence from two Pacific Island countries.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (3), S. 313–326. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2010.529945.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Australien // Australia; Jugendliche // youth; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Mora, Claudia; Monteiro, Simone (2010):

Vulnerability to STIs/HIV. Sociability and the life trajectories of young women who have sex with women in Rio de Janeiro.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (1), S. 115–124. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903180471.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Lateinamerika // Latin America; lesbisch // lesbian; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Muhanguzi, Florence Kyoheirwe (2011):

Gender and sexual vulnerability of young women in Africa. Experiences of young girls in secondary schools in Uganda.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 713–725. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.571290.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Identität // identity; Mädchen // girls; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa; Tabu // taboo; Trauma; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Mulumeoderhwa, Maroyi; Harris, Geoff (2015):

Forced sex, rape and sexual exploitation. Attitudes and experiences of high school students in South Kivu, Democratic Republic of Congo.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 17 (3), S. 284–295.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Munoz-Laboy, Miguel; Murray, Laura R.; Wittlin, Natalie; Wilson, Patrick A.; Terto, Veriano; Parker, Richard (2011):

Divine targets. Youth at the centre of Catholic and Pentecostal responses to HIV and AIDS in Brazil.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (6), S. 657–668. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.565519.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Religion; Selbstbestimmung // agency; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Soziale Schicht; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.8 Offene Kinder- und Jugendarbeit; 2.2.9 Kirche; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Raine, Tina R.; Gard, Jennifer C.; Boyer, Cherrie B.; Haider, Sadia; Brown, Beth A.; Ramirez Hernandez, F. Antonio; Harper, Cynthia C. (2010):

Contraceptive decision-making in sexual relationships. Young men's experiences, attitudes and values.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 12 (4), S. 373–386. DOI: 10.1080/13691050903524769.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Geschlecht // gender; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Shepard Paynea, Jennifer; Galvan, Frank H.; Williams, John K.; Prusinskie, Missy; Zhang, Muyu; Wyatt, Gail E.; Myers, Hector F. (2014):

Impact of childhood sexual abuse on the emotions and behaviours of adult men from three ethnic groups in the USA.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 16 (3), S. 231–245.

Schlagwörter:

Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualität // sexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen
Winskell, Kate; Beres, Laura K.; Hill, Elizabeth; Mbakwem, Benjamin Chigozie; Obyerodhyambo, Oby (2011):

Making sense of abstinence. Social representations in young Africans' HIV-related narratives from six countries.

In: *Culture, Health & Sexuality* 13 (8), S. 945–959. DOI: 10.1080/13691058.2011.591431.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Sexuelle Abstinenz // abstinence; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Feminism & Psychology

Beres, Melanie Ann (2014):

Rethinking the concept of consent for anti-sexual violence activism and education.

In: *Feminism & Psychology* 24 (3), S. 373–389. DOI: 10.1177/0959353514539652.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Konsens // consent; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Prävention // prevention; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Jackson, Sue; Weatherall, Ann (2010):

The (Im)possibilities of Feminist School Based Sexuality Education.

In: *Feminism & Psychology* 20 (2), S. 166–185.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Feminismus // feminism; Geschlecht // gender; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Martin, Karin A.; Verduzco Baker, Lynn; Torres, Jennifer; Luke, Katherine (2011):

Privates, pee-pees, and coochies. Gender and genital labeling for/with young children.

In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (3), S. 420–430. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510384832.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Geschlecht // gender; Kinder // children; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Senn, Charlene Y. (2011):

An imperfect feminist journey. Reflections on the process to develop an effective sexual assault resistance programme for university women.

In: *Feminism & Psychology* 21 (1), S. 121–137. DOI: 10.1177/0959353510386094.

Schlagwörter:

Feminismus // feminism; Policies; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Universität // college university

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Towns, Alison J.; Scott, Hazel (2013):

'I couldn't even dress the way I wanted.' Young women talk of 'ownership' by boyfriends. An opportunity for the prevention of domestic violence?

In: *Feminism & Psychology* 23 (4), S. 536–555. DOI: 10.1177/0959353513481955.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; häusliche Gewalt // domestic violence; Identität // identity; Jugendliche // youth; Prävention // prevention; Selbstbestimmung // agency

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Gender & Society

Hlavka, H. R. (2014):

Normalizing Sexual Violence. Young Women Account for Harassment and Abuse.

In: *Gender & Society* 28 (3), S. 337–358. DOI: 10.1177/0891243214526468.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung

Miller, S. A. (2016):

"How You Bully a Girl". Sexual Drama and the Negotiation of Gendered Sexuality in High School.

In: *Gender & Society* 30 (5), S. 721–744. DOI: 10.1177/0891243216664723.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Mobbing // bullying; Nordamerika // North America; Slut-shaming // slut-shaming

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Myers, Kristen; Raymond, Laura (2010):

Elementary School Girls and Heteronormativity. The Girl Project.

In: *Gender & Society* 24 (2), S. 167–188. DOI: 10.1177/0891243209358579.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Grundschule // elementary school; Gruppensettings // group settings; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Kinder // children; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Pomerantz, S.; Raby, R.; Stefanik, A. (2013):

Girls Run the World? Caught between Sexism and Postfeminism in School.

In: *Gender & Society* 27 (2), S. 185–207. DOI: 10.1177/0891243212473199.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate; Sexismus // sexism

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Whittier, Nancy (2016):

Where Are the Children? Theorizing the Missing Piece in Gendered Sexual Violence.

In: *Gender & Society* 30 (1), S. 95–108. DOI: 10.1177/0891243215612412.

Schlagwörter:

Feminismus // feminism; Geschlecht // gender; Global; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Soziale Schicht; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie

Gender and Education

Blaise, Mindy (2013):

Charting new territories. Re-assembling childhood sexuality in the early years classroom.

In: *Gender and Education* 25 (7), S. 801–817. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2013.797070.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Geschlecht // gender; Grundschule // elementary school; Kinderbetreuung // child care; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Schule // school; Sexualethik // sexual ethics

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.1 Kindertagesstätte; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität

Cameron-Lewis, Vanessa (2016):

Escaping oppositional thinking in the teaching of pleasure and danger in sexuality education.

In: *Gender and Education* 28 (4), S. 491–509. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2016.1171297.

Schlagwörter:

Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Vergnügen // pleasure

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Epstein, Debbie; Kehily, Mary Jane; Renold, E. (2012):

Culture, policy and the un/marked child. Fragments of the sexualisation debates.

In: *Gender and Education* 24 (3), S. 249–254. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2012.670390.

Schlagwörter:

Mädchen // girls; Medien // media; Sexualisierung // sexualization; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Haste, Polly (2013):

Sex education and masculinity. The 'problem' of boys.

In: *Gender and Education* 25 (4), S. 515–527. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2013.789830.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Jungen // boys; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Pornografie // pornography; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Huyge, Ellen; Maele, Dimitri van; Houtte, Mieke van (2014):

Does students' machismo fit in school? Clarifying the implications of traditional gender role ideology for school belonging.

In: *Gender and Education* 27 (1), S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2014.972921.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Kehily, Mary Jane (2012):

Contextualising the sexualisation of girls debate. Innocence, experience and young female sexuality.

In: *Gender and Education* 24 (3), S. 255–268. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2012.670391.

Schlagwörter:

Mädchen // girls; Sexualisierung // sexualization; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Lamb, Sharon; Farmer, Kaelin M.; Kosterina, Elena; Lambe Sariñana, Susan; Plocha, Aleksandra; Randazzo, Renee (2016):

What's sexy? Adolescent girls discuss confidence, danger, and media influence.

In: *Gender and Education* 28 (4), S. 527–545. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1107528.

Schlagwörter:

Coming out; Mädchen // girls; Medien // media; Nordamerika // North America; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Sprache // language; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Larsson, Håkan; Quennerstedt, Mikael; Öhman, Marie (2014):

Heterotopias in physical education. Towards a queer pedagogy?

In: *Gender and Education* 26 (2), S. 135–150. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2014.888403.

Schlagwörter:

Heteronormativität // heteronormativity

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.3.1 Schulfächer; 2.2.3.1.1 Sportunterricht

Neary, Aoife; Gray, Breda; O'Sullivan, Mary (2016):

A queer politics of emotion. Reimagining sexualities and schooling.

In: *Gender and Education* 28 (2), S. 250–265. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1114074.

Schlagwörter:

Gefühle // emotions; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Schule // school; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule

Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2011):

Race, class, and emerging sexuality. Teacher perceptions and sexual harassment in schools.

In: *Gender and Education* 23 (7), S. 799–810. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2010.536143.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Mädchen // girls; Mobbing // bullying; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice

Kategorien:

1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Vares, Tiina; Jackson, Sue (2015):

Preteen girls, magazines, and the negotiation of young sexual femininity.

In: *Gender and Education* 27 (6), S. 700–713. DOI: 10.1080/09540253.2015.1078453.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Medien // media; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Professionalität // professionalism; Sexualisierung // sexualization; Sexualität // sexuality; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Journal of Adolescence

Ali, Mir M.; Dwyer, Debra S. (2011):

Estimating peer effects in sexual behavior among adolescents.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 183–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.12.008.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Peers; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Alleyne, Binta; Coleman-Cowger, Victoria H.; Crown, Laurel; Gibbons, Maya A.; Vines, Linda Nicole (2011):

The effects of dating violence, substance use and risky sexual behavior among a diverse sample of Illinois youth.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 11–18. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.03.006.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Ávila, Marisa; Cabral, Joana; Matos, Paula Mena (2012):

Identity in university students. The role of parental and romantic attachment.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 133–142. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.05.002.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie

Beckmeyer, Jonathon J. (2015):

Comparing the associations between three types of adolescents' romantic involvement and their engagement in substance use.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 42, S. 140–147. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.04.008.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Jugendliche // youth; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Boislard P., Marie-Aude; Poulin, Francois (2011):

Individual, familial, friends-related and contextual predictors of early sexual intercourse.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 289–300. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.05.002.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Freunde // friends

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Caiozzo, Christina N.; Houston, Jessica; Grych, John (2016):

Predicting aggression in late adolescent romantic relationships. A short-term longitudinal study.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 53, S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.10.012.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression; Gewalt in Beziehngen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Student*innen // college students; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Campero, Lourdes; Walker, Dilys; Atienzo, Erika E.; Gutierrez, Juan Pablo (2011):

A quasi-experimental evaluation of parents as sexual health educators resulting in delayed sexual initiation and increased access to condoms.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 215–223. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.05.010.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Frauen // women; Gesundheit // health; Intervention // intervention; Jugendliche // youth; Kommunikation // communication; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Prävention // prevention; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Carlson, Wendy; Rose, Amanda J. (2012):

Brief report. Activities in heterosexual romantic relationships: grade differences and associations with relationship satisfaction.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 219–224. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.09.001.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Heterosexualität // heterosexuality; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Carter, Rona; Williams, Sandra (2016):

Self-perceptions of pubertal timing and patterns of peer group activities and dating behavior among heterosexual adolescent girls.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 47, S. 71–80. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.12.006.

Schlagwörter:

Heterosexualität // heterosexuality; Jugendliche // youth; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; Peers; Pubertät // Puberty

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Choi, Hye Jeong; Ouytsel, Joris van; Temple, Jeff R. (2016):

Association between sexting and sexual coercion among female adolescents.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 53, S. 164–168. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.10.005.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Sexting // sexting; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2012):

Intergroup contact, attitudes toward homosexuality, and the role of acceptance of gender non-conformity in young adolescents.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 899–907. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.12.010.

Schlagwörter:

Homosexualität; Jugendliche // youth; Peers; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Coyne, Sarah M.; Padilla-Walker, Laura M. (2015):

Sex, violence, & rock n' roll. Longitudinal effects of music on aggression, sex, and prosocial behavior during adolescence.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 41, S. 96–104. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.03.002.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Medien // media; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Sexualisierung // sexualization; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Crichton, Joanna; Ibisomi, Latifat; Gyimah, Stephen Obeng (2012):

Mother-daughter communication about sexual maturation, abstinence and unintended pregnancy. Experiences from an informal settlement in Nairobi, Kenya.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 21–30. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.06.008.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Jugendliche // youth; Kommunikation // communication; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Sexuelle Abstinenz // abstinence; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Daddis, Christopher; Randolph, Danielle (2010):

Dating and disclosure: Adolescent management of information regarding romantic involvement.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (2), S. 309–320. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.05.002.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Kinder // children; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Professionalität // professionalism; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Dessel, Adrienne B.; Kulick, Alex; Wernick, Laura J.; Sullivan, Daniel (2017):

The importance of teacher support. Differential impacts by gender and sexuality.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 136–144. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.002.

Schlagwörter:

Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Nordamerika // North America; Professionalität // professionalism; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schulklima // school climate; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Eklund, Jenny M.; Kerr, Margaret; Stattin, Hakan (2010):

Romantic relationships and delinquent behaviour in adolescence: the moderating role of delinquency propensity.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (3), S. 377–386. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.09.002.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Frauen // women; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Risikofaktoren // risk factors

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Espinosa-Hernandez, Graciela; Vasilenko, Sara A.; McPherson, Jenna L.; Gutierrez, Estefania; Rodriguez, Andrea (2017):

Brief report. The role of three dimensions of sexual well-being in adolescents' life satisfaction.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 61–65. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.009.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Latinx; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2012):

Young women's adolescent experiences of oral sex. Relation of age of initiation to sexual motivation, sexual coercion, and psychological functioning.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (5), S. 1191–1201. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.03.010.

Schlagwörter:

Frauen // women; Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Fernet, Mylene; Hébert, Martine; Paradis, Alison (2016):

Conflict resolution patterns and violence perpetration in adolescent couples. A gender-sensitive mixed-methods approach.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 51–59. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.02.004.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Konflikte // conflicts; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art

Goldbach, Jeremy T.; Gibbs, Jeremy J. (2017):

A developmentally informed adaptation of minority stress for sexual minority adolescents.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 36–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.007.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Goodrum, Nada M.; Armistead, Lisa P.; Tully, Erin C.; Cook, Sarah L.; Skinner, Donald (2017):

Parenting and youth sexual risk in context. The role of community factors.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 57, S. 1–12. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.013.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Familie // family; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; schwarz // black; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Hensel, Devon J.; Fortenberry, J. Dennis; O'Sullivan, Lucia F.; Orr, Donald P. (2011):

The developmental association of sexual self-concept with sexual behavior among adolescent women.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 675–684. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.09.005.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Hipwell, Alison E.; Stepp, Stephanie D.; Keenan, Kate; Chung, Tammy; Loeber, Rolf (2011):

Brief report: Parsing the heterogeneity of adolescent girls' sexual behavior. Relationships to individual and interpersonal factors.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (3), S. 589–592. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.03.002.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Livingston, Jennifer A.; Testa, Maria; Windle, Michael; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2015):

Sexual risk at first coitus. Does alcohol make a difference?

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 43, S. 148–158. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.05.018.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Risiko // risk; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Looze, Margaretha de; Harakeh, Zeena; van Dorsselaer, Saskia A. F. M.; Raaijmakers, Quinten A. W.; Vollebergh, Wilma A. M.; ter Bogt, Tom F. M. (2012):

Explaining educational differences in adolescent substance use and early sexual debut. The role of parents and peers.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 1035–1044. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.02.009.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Eltern // parents; erstes Mal // sexual debut; Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Martin-Storey, Alexa; Crosnoe, Robert (2012):

Sexual minority status, peer harassment, and adolescent depression.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (4), S. 1001–1011. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.02.006.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Mobbing // bullying; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Stigmatisierung // stigma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Martin-Storey, Alexa; Fromme, Kim (2016):

Trajectories of dating violence. Differences by sexual minority status and gender.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 28–37. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.02.008.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Meek, Rosie (2011):

The possible selves of young fathers in prison.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (5), S. 941–949. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.12.005.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Jugendliche // youth; Selbstkonzept // self-concept; Soziale Schicht; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.10 Justizvollzugsanstalt; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Moosmann, Danyel A. V.; Roosa, Mark W. (2015):

Exploring Mexican American adolescent romantic relationship profiles and adjustment.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 43, S. 181–192. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.06.004.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Jugendliche // youth; Latinx; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Nordamerika // North America

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Oosten, Johanna M. F. van; Vandenbosch, Laura (2017):

Sexy online self-presentation on social network sites and the willingness to engage in sexting: A comparison of gender and age.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 54, S. 42–50. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.11.006.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Medien // media; Sexting // sexting

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Parkes, Alison; Wight, Daniel; Henderson, Marion; West, Patrick (2010):

Does early sexual debut reduce teenagers' participation in tertiary education? Evidence from the SHARE longitudinal study.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (5), S. 741–754. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.006.

Schlagwörter:

erstes Mal // sexual debut; Europa // Europe; Frauen // women; Jugendliche // youth; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Patrick, Megan E.; Maggs, Jennifer L. (2010):

Profiles of motivations for alcohol use and sexual behavior among first-year university students.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (5), S. 755–765. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.003.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Einstellungen // attitudes; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Petering, Robin (2016):

Sexual risk, substance use, mental health, and trauma experiences of gang-involved homeless youth.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 48, S. 73–81. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.01.009.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Gangs // gangs; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; obdachlos // homeless; Risiko // risk

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Porta, Carolyn M.; Gower, Amy L.; Mehus, Christopher J.; Yu, Xiaohui; Saewyc, Elizabeth M.; Eisenberg, Marla E. (2017):

"Kicked out". LGBTQ youths' bathroom experiences and preferences.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 56, S. 107–112. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2017.02.005.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Pradhan, Manas Ranjan; Ram, Usha (2010):

Perceived gender role that shape youth sexual behaviour. Evidence from rural Orissa, India.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (4), S. 543–551. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.10.014.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Sabina, Chiara; Cuevas, Carlos A.; Cotignola-Pickens, Heather M. (2016):

Longitudinal dating violence victimization among Latino teens: Rates, risk factors, and cultural influences.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 47, S. 5–15. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2015.11.003.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Latinx; Nordamerika // North America

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Sevcikova, Anna (2016):

Girls' and boys' experience with teen sexting in early and late adolescence.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 51, S. 156–162. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.06.007.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Sexting // sexting; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Smiler, Andrew P.; Frankel, Loren B. W.; Savin-Williams, Ritch C. (2011):

From kissing to coitus? Sex-of-partner differences in the sexual milestone achievement of young men.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 727–735. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.08.009.

Schlagwörter:

Jungen // boys; Nordamerika // North America; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Smith-Darden, Joanne P.; Reidy, Dennis E.; Kernsmith, Poco D. (2016):

Adolescent stalking and risk of violence.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 52, S. 191–200. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.08.005.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Risiko // risk; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Sommer, Marni (2010):

Where the education system and women's bodies collide. The social and health impact of girls' experiences of menstruation and schooling in Tanzania.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (4), S. 521–529. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.03.008.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Mädchen // girls; Policies; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Sorhaindo, Annik; Bonell, Chris; Fletcher, Adam; Jessiman, Patricia; Keogh, Peter; Mitchell, Kirstin (2016):

Being targeted. Young women's experience of being identified for a teenage pregnancy prevention programme.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 49, S. 181–190. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.03.013.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; Schule // school; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; schwarz // black; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Stereotype // stereotypes

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Stevens-Watkins, Danelle; Brown-Wright, Lynda; Tyler, Kenneth (2011):

Brief report. The number of sexual partners and race-related stress in African American adolescents: preliminary findings.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (1), S. 191–194. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.02.003.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Rassismus // racism; Risiko // risk; schwarz // black; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Svedin, Carl-Göran; Akerman, Ingrid; Priebe, Gisela (2011):

Frequent users of pornography. A population based epidemiological study of Swedish male adolescents.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (4), S. 779–788. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.04.010.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Pornografie // pornography

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Swenson, Rebecca R.; Houck, Christopher D.; Barker, David; Zeanah, Paula D.; Brown, Larry K. (2012):

Prospective analysis of the transition to sexual experience and changes in sexual self-esteem among adolescents attending therapeutic schools.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 77–85. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.06.002.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Thrane, Lisa E.; Chen, Xiaojin (2012):

Impact of running away on girls' pregnancy.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (2), S. 443–449. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.07.011.

Schlagwörter:

Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; obdachlos // homeless; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Toomey, Russell B.; McGuire, Jenifer K.; Russell, Stephen T. (2012):

Heteronormativity, school climates, and perceived safety for gender nonconforming peers.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 35 (1), S. 187–196. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2011.03.001.

Schlagwörter:

Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Schulklima // school climate; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

van Ouytsel, Joris; Ponnet, Koen; Walrave, Michel (2017):

The associations of adolescents' dating violence victimization, well-being and engagement in risk behaviors.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 55, S. 66–71. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2016.12.005.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Europa // Europe; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Peers; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Vasilenko, Sara A.; Ram, Nilam; Lefkowitz, Eva S. (2011):

Body image and first sexual intercourse in late adolescence.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (2), S. 327–335. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.04.005.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Körper // body; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen
Wargo Aikins, Julie; Simon, Valerie A.; Prinstein, Mitchell J. (2010):

Romantic partner selection and socialization of young adolescents' substance use and behavior problems.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (6), S. 813–826. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.07.007.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Jugendliche // youth; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship;
Nordamerika // North America

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen
Williams, Lela Rankin; Hickie, Kristine E. (2011):

"He cheated on me, I cheated on him back". Mexican American and White adolescents' perceptions of cheating in romantic relationships.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 34 (5), S. 1005–1016. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.11.007.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Jugendliche // youth; Latinx; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Nordamerika // North America

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität;
7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Wong, Carolyn F.; Kipke, Michele D.; Weiss, George; McDavitt, Bryce (2010):

The impact of recent stressful experiences on HIV-risk related behaviors.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (3), S. 463–475. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2009.06.004.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Homosexualität; Nordamerika // North America;
Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität;
7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Zimmer-Gembeck, Melanie J.; Ducat, Wendy (2010):

Positive and negative romantic relationship quality: age, familiarity, attachment and well-being as correlates of couple agreement and projection.

In: *Journal of Adolescence* 33 (6), S. 879–890. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2010.07.008.

Schlagwörter:

Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry

Livingstone, Sonia M.; Smith, Peter K. (2014):

Annual Research Review: Harms experienced by child users of online and mobile technologies. The nature, prevalence and management of sexual and aggressive risks in the digital age.

In: *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry* 55 (6), S. 635–654.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Internet; Kinder // children; Mobbing // bullying; Pornografie // pornography; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Schutz // protection; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Journal of Child Sexual Abuse

Alix, Stephanie; Cossette, Louise; Hebert, Martine; Cyr, Mireille; Frappier, Jean-Yves (2017):

Posttraumatic Stress Disorder and Suicidal Ideation Among Sexually Abused Adolescent Girls. The Mediating Role of Shame.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (2), S. 158–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1280577.

Schlagwörter:

Mädchen // girls; Selbstmord // suicide; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Trauma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Allbaugh, Lucy Jane; O'Dougherty Wright, Margaret; Atkins Seltmann, Larissa (2014):

An exploratory study of domains of parenting concern among mothers who are childhood sexual abuse survivors.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (8), S. 885–899. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.960636.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Eltern // parents; Frauen // women; Kinder // children

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Anderson, Gwendolyn D. (2016):

The Continuum of Disclosure. Exploring Factors Predicting Tentative Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations During Forensic Interviews and the Implications for Practice, Policy, and Future Research.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 382–402. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153559.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Anderson, Jane (2016):

Socialization Processes and Clergy Offenders.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (8), S. 846–865. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1241333.

Schlagwörter:

Christentum // christianity; Eltern // parents; Geistliche // clergy; Männlichkeit // masculinity; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sozialisierung // socialization; Täter*in // offender; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.9 Kirche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie

Benia, Luis Roberto; Hauck-Filho, Nelson; Dillenburg, Mariana; Stein, Lilian Milnitsky (2015):

The NICHD Investigative Interview Protocol. A Meta-Analytic Review.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 259–279. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006749.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Bowman, Rachel A.; Scotti, Joseph R.; Morris, Tracy L. (2010):

Sexual abuse prevention. A training program for developmental disabilities service providers.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 119–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003614718.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Einstellungen // attitudes; Erwachsene; Männer // men; Prävention // prevention

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Caldas, Stephen J.; Bensy, Mary Lou (2014):

The sexual maltreatment of students with disabilities in American school settings.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (4), S. 345–366. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.906530.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Campregher, Julia; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2016):

Attitudes Toward Juvenile Sex Offender Legislation: The Influence of Case-Specific Information.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 466–482. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153558.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Betroffene // survivors; Geschlecht // gender; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.5 Disclosure

Capella, Claudia; Lama, Ximena; Rodriguez, Loreto; Aguila, Daniela; Beiza, Gretchen; Dussert, Denise; Gutierrez, Carolina (2016):

Winning a Race. Narratives of Healing and Psychotherapy in Children and Adolescents Who Have Been Sexually Abused.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 73–92. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088915.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Celik, Gonca Gul; Yolga Tahiroglu, Aysegul; Avci, Ayse; Cekin, Necmi; Evliyaoglu, Nurdan; Yoruldu, Belgin (2012):

Sexual abuse in a classroom of ten male students. A group victimization.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (5), S. 543–552. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.694403.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Coburn, Patricia I.; Chong, Kristin; Connolly, Deborah A. (2017):

The Effect of Case Severity on Sentence Length in Cases of Child Sexual Assault in Canada.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 319–333. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1283651.

Schlagwörter:

sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Strafrecht // criminal justice; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.5 Disclosure

Collins, Christi M.; O'Neill-Arana, Margarita R.; Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Ossege, Jennifer M. (2014):

Catholicism and childhood sexual abuse. Women's coping and psychotherapy.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (5), S. 519–537. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.918071.

Schlagwörter:

Anpassung // adaptation; Betroffene // survivors; Erwachsene; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.5 Religion; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.4 Resilienz

Comartin, Erin B.; Kernsmith, Poco D.; Miles, Bart W. (2010):

Family experiences of young adult sex offender registration.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (2), S. 204–225. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003627207.

Schlagwörter:

Erwachsene; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

Craun, Sarah W.; Bourke, Michael L. (2014):

The use of humor to cope with secondary traumatic stress.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (7), S. 840–852. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.949395.

Schlagwörter:

Angst // anxiety; Anpassung // adaptation; Einstellungen // attitudes; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Professionalität // professionalism; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

Cromer, Lisa DeMarni; Goldsmith, Rachel E. (2010):

Child sexual abuse myths. Attitudes, beliefs, and individual differences.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (6), S. 618–647. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.522493.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Stereotype // stereotypes

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Cyr, Mireille; McDuff, Pierre; Hebert, Martine (2013):

Support and profiles of nonoffending mothers of sexually abused children.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (2), S. 209–230. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.737444.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Daigneault, Isabelle; Hebert, Martine; McDuff, Pierre; Frappier, Jean-Yves (2012):

Evaluation of a sexual abuse prevention workshop in a multicultural, impoverished urban area.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (5), S. 521–542. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.703291.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Kinder // children; Mobbing // bullying; Peers; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

Dolan, Mairead; Whitworth, Helen (2013):

Childhood sexual abuse, adult psychiatric morbidity, and criminal outcomes in women assessed by medium secure forensic service.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (2), S. 191–208. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.751951.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Erwachsene; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Elklit, Ask; Christiansen, Dorte M.; Palic, Sabina; Karsberg, Sidsel; Eriksen, Sara Bek (2014):

Impact of traumatic events on posttraumatic stress disorder among Danish survivors of sexual abuse in childhood.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (8), S. 918–934. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.964440.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Betroffene // survivors; Erwachsene; Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Trauma

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Everson, Mark D.; Faller, Kathleen Coulborn (2012):

Base rates, multiple indicators, and comprehensive forensic evaluations. Why sexualized behavior still counts in assessments of child sexual abuse allegations.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (1), S. 45–71. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.642470.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Fagerlund, Monica; Ellonen, Noora (2016):

Children's Experiences of Completing a Computer-Based Violence Survey. Finnish Child Victim Survey Revisited.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 556–576. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1186769.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Europa // Europe; Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik; 8.3 Methodologie

Flannery, Dustin D.; Stephens, Clare L.; Thompson, Amy D. (2016):

The Impact of High-Profile Sexual Abuse Cases in the Media on a Pediatric Emergency Department.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 627–635. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1187697.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Diskurs // discourse; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Medien // media; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Fontes, Lisa Aronson; Plummer, Carol (2010):

Cultural issues in disclosures of child sexual abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (5), S. 491–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.512520.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Diskurs // discourse; Einstellungen // attitudes; Erwachsene; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Fredlund, Cecilia; Svensson, Frida; Svedin, Carl Goran; Priebe, Gisela; Wadsby, Marie (2013):

Adolescents' lifetime experience of selling sex. Development over five years.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (3), S. 312–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.743950.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Männer // men; Migration; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Fresno, Andres; Spencer, Rosario; Ramos, Nadia; Pierrehumbert, Blaise (2014):

The effect of sexual abuse on children's attachment representations in Chile.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 128–145. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870949.

Schlagwörter:

Gefühle // emotions; Kinder // children; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Fromuth, Mary Ellen; Kelly, David B.; Brallier, Courtney; Williams, Matthew; Benson, Kate (2016):

Effects of duration on perceptions of teacher sexual misconduct.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (2), S. 159–174. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1122692.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Gibson, Kerry; Morgan, Mandy; Woolley, Cheryl; Powis, Tracey (2011):

Growing up at centrepiece. Retrospective accounts of childhood spent at an intentional community.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 413–434. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.591364.

Schlagwörter:

Erwachsene; Kinder // children; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Stereotype // stereotypes

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Goldman, Juliette D. G.; Grimbeek, Peter (2015):

Preservice teachers' sources of information on mandatory reporting of child sexual abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 238–258. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1009607.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Curriculum; Erwachsene; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Haboush, Karen L.; Alyan, Hala (2013):

"Who can you tell?" Features of Arab culture that influence conceptualization and treatment of childhood sexual abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 499–518. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800935.

Schlagwörter:

Erwachsene; Islam; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie

Harris, Taylor; Rice, Eric; Rhoades, Harmony; Winetrobe, Hailey; Wenzel, Suzanne (2017):

Gender Differences in the Path From Sexual Victimization to HIV Risk Behavior Among Homeless Youth.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 334–351. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1287146.

Schlagwörter:

obdachlos // homeless; Revictimisierung // revictimization; Risiko // risk; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Hartley, Sarah; Johnco, Carly; Hofmeyr, Marthinus; Berry, Alexis (2016):

The Nature of Posttraumatic Growth in Adult Survivors of Child Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (2), S. 201–220. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1119773.

Schlagwörter:

Anpassung // adaptation; Betroffene // survivors; Erwachsene; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Trauma

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.4 Resilienz

Hatchard, Christine J.; Goodwin, Jamie L.; Siddall, Eryn; Muniz, Lauren (2017):

Perceptions of Abusive Parenting Behaviors. A Preliminary Exploration Into the Underrecognition of Mother-Daughter Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (4), S. 428–441. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1300971.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Horn, Joan van; Eisenberg, Mara; Nicholls McNaughton, Carol; Mulder, Jules; Webster, Stephen; Paskell, Caroline et al. (2015):

Stop It Now! A Pilot Study Into the Limits and Benefits of a Free Helpline Preventing Child Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 853–872. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088914.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Kinder // children; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Hovey, Angela; Stalker, Carol A.; Schachter, Candice L.; Teram, Eli; Lasiuk, Gerri (2011):

Practical ways psychotherapy can support physical healthcare experiences for male survivors of childhood sexual abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 37–57. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.539963.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Disclosure; Erwachsene; Gesundheit // health; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Professionalität // professionalism; Psychiatrie // psychiatry; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Jaffe, Anna E.; Cranston, Christopher C.; Shadlow, Joanna O. (2012):

Parenting in females exposed to intimate partner violence and childhood sexual abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 684–700. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.726698.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Eltern // parents; Erwachsene; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Jennings, Wesley G.; Richards, Tara N.; Tomsich, Elizabeth; Gover, Angela R. (2015):

Investigating the Role of Child Sexual Abuse in Intimate Partner Violence Victimization and Perpetration in Young Adulthood From a Propensity Score Matching Approach.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 659–681. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1057665.

Schlagwörter:

Erwachsene; Gewalt // violence; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Jin, Yichen; Chen, Jingqi; Yu, Buyi (2016):

Knowledge and Skills of Sexual Abuse Prevention. A Study on School-Aged Children in Beijing, China.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 686–696. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1199079.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Asien // Asia; Einstellungen // attitudes; Kinder // children; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Jones, Sara; Joyal, Christian C.; Cisler, Josh M.; Bai, Shasha (2017):

Exploring Emotion Regulation in Juveniles Who Have Sexually Offended. An fMRI Study.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 40–57. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1259280.

Schlagwörter:

Gefühle // emotions; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Kenny, Maureen C.; Wurtele, Sandy K.; Alonso, Laura (2012):

Evaluation of a personal safety program with Latino preschoolers.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (4), S. 368–385. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.675426.

Schlagwörter:

Gesundheit // health; Latinx; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

Kisanga, Felix; Nystrom, Lennarth; Hogan, Nora; Emmelin, Maria (2011):

Child sexual abuse. Community concerns in urban Tanzania.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (2), S. 196–217. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.555356.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Erwachsene; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; Kinderrechte // children's rights; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.5 Disclosure

Kloppen, Kathrine; Haugland, Siren; Svedin, Carl-Göran; Maehle, Magne; Breivik, Kyrre (2016):

Prevalence of Child Sexual Abuse in the Nordic Countries. A Literature Review.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 37–55. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1108944.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Prävalenz // prevalence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Knoll, James (2010):

Teacher sexual misconduct. Grooming patterns and female offenders.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (4), S. 371–386. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.495047.

Schlagwörter:

Erwachsene; Kinder // children; Professionalität // professionalism; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Kostolitz, Alessandra C.; Hyman, Scott M.; Gold, Steven N. (2014):

How ineffective family environments can compound maldevelopment of critical thinking skills in childhood abuse survivors.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (6), S. 690–707. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.931318.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Krause-Parello, Cheryl A.; Gulick, Elsie E. (2015):

Forensic Interviews for Child Sexual Abuse Allegations. An Investigation into the Effects of Animal-Assisted Intervention on Stress Biomarkers.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 873–886. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1088916.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Krayer, Anne; Seddon, Diane; Robinson, Catherine A.; Gwilym, Hefin (2015):

The influence of child sexual abuse on the self from adult narrative perspectives.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (2), S. 135–151. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1001473.

Schlagwörter:

Angst // anxiety; Anpassung // adaptation; Betroffene // survivors; Disclosure; Erwachsene; Inzest // incest; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Narration // narrative; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Kucuk, Sibel (2016):

Analyses of Child Sex Abuse Cases in Turkey: A Provincial Case.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 262–275. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1153557.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Kinder // children; Muslimische Länder; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Lainpelto, Katrin; Isaksson, Johan; Lindblad, Frank (2016):

Does Information About Neuropsychiatric Diagnoses Influence Evaluation of Child Sexual Abuse Allegations?

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 276–292. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1145164.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Erwachsene; Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Narration // narrative; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Lev-Wiesel, Rachel; Markus, Liora (2013):

Perception vs. circumstances of the child sexual abuse event in relation to depression and post-traumatic stress symptomatology.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (5), S. 519–533. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.800932.

Schlagwörter:

Erwachsene; Europa // Europe; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Sexualität // sexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Liotta, Lindsay; Springer, Craig; Misurell, Justin R.; Block-Lerner, Jennifer; Brandwein, David (2015):

Group treatment for child sexual abuse. Treatment referral and therapeutic outcomes.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 217–237. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006747.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Kinder // children; Latinx; Männer // men; schwarz // black; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Lopez, Silvia; Faro, Concepcio; Lopetegui, Lourdes; Pujol-Ribera, Enriqueta; Monteagudo, Monica; Avecilla-Palau, Angels et al. (2017):

Child and Adolescent Sexual Abuse in Women Seeking Help for Sexual and Reproductive Mental Health Problems. Prevalence, Characteristics, and Disclosure.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 246–269. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1288186.

Schlagwörter:

Frauen // women; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Mahony, David (2010):

Assessing sexual abuse/attack histories with bariatric surgery patients.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (4), S. 469–484. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.496713.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Angst // anxiety; Erwachsene; Jugendliche // youth; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Prävalenz // prevalence

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Man-Ging, Carlos Ignacio; Bohm, Bettina; Fuchs, Katharina Anna; Witte, Susanne; Frick, Eckhard (2015):

Improving Empathy in the Prevention of Sexual Abuse Against Children and Youngsters.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (7), S. 796–815. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1077366.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Erwachsene; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Medien // media; Prävention // prevention; Professionalität // professionalism; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Marquez-Flores, Maria Mercedes; Marquez-Hernandez, Veronica V.; Granados-Gamez, Genoveva (2016):

Teachers' knowledge and beliefs about child sexual abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 538–555. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1189474.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Europa // Europe; Kinder // children; Schule // school

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

McLeod, David Axlyn (2015):

Female offenders in child sexual abuse cases. A national picture.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (1), S. 97–114. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.978925.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Erwachsene; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch
Mejia, Pamela; Cheyne, Andrew; Dorfman, Lori (2012):

News coverage of child sexual abuse and prevention, 2007-2009.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (4), S. 470–487. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.692465.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; Medien // media; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

Milam, Lisa J.; Nugent, William R. (2017):

Children's Knowledge of Genital Anatomy and Its Relationship With Children's Use of the Word "Inside" During Questioning About Possible Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 23–39. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1269863.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure; 7 Sexualität

Misurell, Justin R.; Springer, Craig; Tryon, Warren W. (2011):

Game-based cognitive-behavioral therapy (GB-CBT) group program for children who have experienced sexual abuse. A preliminary investigation.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (1), S. 14–36. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.540000.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

O'Brien, Jennifer E.; White, Kevin; Wu, Qi; Killian-Farrell, Candace (2016):

Mental Health and Behavioral Outcomes of Sexual and Nonsexual Child Maltreatment Among Child Welfare-Involved Youth.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (5), S. 483–503. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1167801.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Olafson, Erna (2012):

A call for field-relevant research about child forensic interviewing for child protection.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (1), S. 109–129. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.642469.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Kinder // children; Nordamerika // North America; Psychiatrie // psychiatry; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

O'Leary, Patrick; Coohy, Carol; Easton, Scott D. (2010):

The effect of severe child sexual abuse and disclosure on mental health during adulthood.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (3), S. 275–289. DOI: 10.1080/10538711003781251.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Disclosure; Erwachsene; Inzest // incest; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Oliver, Brian E.; Holmes, Laura (2015):

Female Juvenile Sexual Offenders. Understanding Who They Are and Possible Steps That May Prevent Some Girls From Offending.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (6), S. 698–715. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1058875.

Schlagwörter:

Frauen // women; Global; Intervention // intervention; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Parkhill, Michele R.; Pickett, Scott M. (2016):

Difficulties in Emotion Regulation as a Mediator of the Relationship Between Child Sexual Abuse Victimization and Sexual Aggression Perpetration in Male College Students.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (6), S. 674–685. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1205161.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression; Gefühle // emotions; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Student*innen // college students; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Pechtel, Pia; Evans, Ian M.; Podd, John V. (2011):

Conceptualization of the complex outcomes of sexual abuse. A signal detection analysis.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (6), S. 677–694. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.627418.

Schlagwörter:

Anpassung // adaptation; Betroffene // survivors; Einstellungen // attitudes; Erwachsene; Kinder // children; Männer // men; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Trauma

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

Rakow, Aaron; Smith, Daniel; Begle, Angela M.; Ayer, Lynsay (2011):

The association of maternal depressive symptoms with child externalizing problems. The role of maternal support following child sexual abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 467–480. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.588189.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression; Anpassung // adaptation; Eltern // parents; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

Rasmussen, Lucinda A. (2013):

Young people who sexually abuse. A historical perspective and future directions.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (1), S. 119–141. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.744646.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Rasmussen, Lucinda A.; Lev-Wiesel, Rachel; Eisikovits, Zvi (2013):

Current perspectives on children and youth who sexually abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (1), S. 1–8. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.744644.

Schlagwörter:

jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Reed-Gavish, Maya (2013):

Cognitive abuse within the incestuous family as a factor in the development of dissociative identity disorder.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (4), S. 444–461. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.781093.

Schlagwörter:

Anpassung // adaptation; Eltern // parents; Erwachsene; Familie // family; Inzest // incest; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Trauma

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

Ross, Colin A. (2017):

Response to Miccio-Fonseca (2015) and Defeo (2015) Concerning Commentary About DSM-5 Sexual Disorders Section.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 92–95. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1263263.

Schlagwörter:

Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Samms, Kimika M.; Cholewa, Blaire E. (2014):

Exploring the context of child sexual abuse in Jamaica. Addressing the deficits.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 115–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.870948.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Bewältigung // coping; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

Sanberk, Ismail; Emen, Meltem; Kabakci, Duygu (2017):

An Investigation of Socially Advantaged and Disadvantaged Turkish Mothers' Views About Training on Preventing Children From Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (3), S. 288–307. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2017.1292338.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Prävention // prevention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Schober, Daniel J.; Fawcett, Stephen B.; Bernier, Jetta (2012):

The Enough Abuse Campaign. Building the movement to prevent child sexual abuse in Massachusetts.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (4), S. 456–469. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.675423.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

Sivis-Cetinkaya, Rahsan (2015):

Turkish School Counselors' Experiences of Reporting Child Sexual Abuse: A Brief Report.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (8), S. 908–921. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1084072.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Ehtik // ethics; Europa // Europe; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Muslimische Länder; Schule // school; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Sozialisation // socialization; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Smothers, Melissa Kraemer; Smothers, D. Brian (2011):

A sexual assault primary prevention model with diverse urban youth.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (6), S. 708–727. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.622355.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Männer // men; Peers; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

Stewart, Catherine Carolyn (2012):

Beyond the call. Mothers of children with developmental disabilities responding to sexual abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 21 (6), S. 701–727. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2012.722182.

Schlagwörter:

Anpassung // adaptation; Behinderung // disability; Einstellungen // attitudes; Eltern // parents; Erwachsene; Kinder // children; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

Stroebel, Sandra S.; O'Keefe, Stephen L.; Griffee, Karen; Kuo, Shih-Ya; Beard, Keith W.; Kommor, Martin J. (2013):

Sister-sister incest. Data from an anonymous computerized survey.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (6), S. 695–719. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.811140.

Schlagwörter:

Alter // age; Anpassung // adaptation; Erwachsene; Homosexualität; Inzest // incest; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Solosexualität // masturbation

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Tishelman, Amy C.; Geffner, Robert (2010):

Forensic, cultural, and systems issues in child sexual abuse cases--part 2. Research and practitioner issues.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (6), S. 609–617. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2010.523514.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

Toledo, Annik van; Seymour, Fred (2016):

Caregiver Needs Following Disclosure of Child Sexual Abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (4), S. 403–414. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1156206.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Behandlung // treatment; Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Bewältigung // coping; Disclosure; Familie // family; Intervention // intervention; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Venable, Victoria M.; Guada, Joseph (2014):

Culturally competent practice with African American juvenile sex offenders.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (3), S. 229–246. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.888122.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Interkulturell // intercultural; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Psychiatrie // psychiatry; schwarz // black; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Weatherred, Jane Long (2017):

Framing Child Sexual Abuse. A Longitudinal Content Analysis of Newspaper and Television Coverage, 2002–2012.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 26 (1), S. 3–22. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1257528.

Schlagwörter:

institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Medien // media; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Williams, Javonda; Nelson-Gardell, Debra; Coulborn Faller, Kathleen; Tishelman, Amy; Cordisco-Steele, Linda (2014):

Is there a place for extended assessments in addressing child sexual abuse allegations? How sensitivity and specificity impact professional perspectives.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 23 (2), S. 179–197. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2014.871380.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Winters, Georgia M.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2016):

I Knew It All Along. The Sexual Grooming Behaviors of Child Molesters and the Hindsight Bias.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (1), S. 20–36. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1108945.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Grooming; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Wondie, Yemataw; Zemene, Workie; Reschke, Konrad; Schroder, Harry (2011):

Early marriage, rape, child prostitution, and related factors determining the psychosocial effects severity of child sexual abuse in Ethiopia.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (3), S. 305–321. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.573458.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Muslimische Länder; Prostitution; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa; Trauma; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Xu, Yin; Zheng, Yong (2015):

Prevalence of Childhood Sexual Abuse among Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual People. A Meta-Analysis.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 24 (3), S. 315–331. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2015.1006746.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Global; Homosexualität; Prävalenz // prevalence; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Yancey, C. Thresa; Hansen, David J.; Naufel, Karen Z. (2011):

Heterogeneity of individuals with a history of child sexual abuse. An examination of children presenting to treatment.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (2), S. 111–127. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.554341.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Erwachsene; Folgen // long-term effects; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Trauma

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Yoder, Jamie R.; Hansen, Jesse; Ruch, Donna; Hodge, Ashleigh (2016):

Effects of School-Based Risk and Protective Factors on Treatment Success Among Youth Adjudicated of a Sexual Crime.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 25 (3), S. 310–325. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2016.1137668.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Jugendliche // youth; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Young, T. Lorraine; Riggs, Matt; Robinson, Jill L. (2011):

Childhood sexual abuse severity reconsidered. A factor structure of CSA characteristics.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 20 (4), S. 373–395. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2011.590124.

Schlagwörter:

Prävalenz // prevalence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Zafar, Sadia; Ross, Erin C. (2013):

Perceptions of childhood sexual abuse survivors. Development and initial validation of a new scale to measure stereotypes of adult survivors of childhood sexual abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 22 (3), S. 358–378. DOI: 10.1080/10538712.2013.743955.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Diskurs // discourse; Einstellungen // attitudes; Erwachsene; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Stereotype // stereotypes

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Zinzow, Heidi; Seth, Puja; Jackson, Joan; Niehaus, Ashley; Fitzgerald, Monica (2010):

Abuse and parental characteristics, attributions of blame, and psychological adjustment in adult survivors of child sexual abuse.

In: *Journal of Child Sexual Abuse* 19 (1), S. 79–98. DOI: 10.1080/10538710903485989.

Schlagwörter:

Anpassung // adaptation; Betroffene // survivors; Erwachsene; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Trauma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Journal of Curriculum Studies

Schmidt, Sandra J. (2015):

A queer arrangement of school. Using spatiality to understand inequity.

In: *Journal of Curriculum Studies* 47 (2), S. 253–273.

Schlagwörter:

sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule

Journal of Sexual Aggression

Allard, Troy; Rayment-McHugh, Sue; Adams, Dimity; Smallbone, Stephen; McKillop, Nadine (2015):

Responding to youth sexual offending. A field-based practice model that “closes the gap” on sexual recidivism among Indigenous and non-Indigenous males.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (1), S. 82–94. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.1003107.

Schlagwörter:

jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jungen // boys

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Almond, Tracy Jane (2014):

Working with children and young people with harmful sexual behaviours. Exploring impact on practitioners and sources of support.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 333–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836576.

Schlagwörter:

Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Europa // Europe; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Kinder // children; Organisation; Professionalität // professionalism; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Atkinson, Chris; Newton, David (2010):

Online behaviours of adolescents. Victims, perpetrators and Web 2.0.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 107–120. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903337683.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Täter*in // offender; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Babchishin, Kelly M.; Nunes, Kevin L.; Hermann, Chantal A.; Malcom, J. Renee (2015):

Implicit sexual interest in children. Does separating gender influence discrimination when using the Implicit Association Test?

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 194–208. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.836575.

Schlagwörter:

Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Berthuisen, Marinus G. C. J.; Brugman, Daniel (2012):

Sexually abusive youths' moral reasoning on sex.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 125–135. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.519126.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.10 Justizvollzugsanstalt; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Buschman, Jos; Wilcox, Dan; Krapohl, Donald; Oelrich, Marty; Hackett, Simon (2010):

Cybersex offender risk assessment. An explorative study.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 197–209. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003690518.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Männer // men; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Risiko // risk; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Clements, Hannah; Dawson, David L.; das Nair, Roshan (2014):

Female-perpetrated sexual abuse. A review of victim and professional perspectives.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 197–215. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.798690.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Einstellungen // attitudes; Frauen // women; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Cowburn, Malcolm; Gill, Aisha K.; Harrison, Karen (2015):

Speaking about sexual abuse in British South Asian communities. Offenders, victims and the challenges of shame and reintegration.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 4–15. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.929188.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Diskurs // discourse; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

DeHart, Dana; Dwyer, Gregg; Seto, Michael C.; Moran, Robert; Letourneau, Elizabeth; Schwarz-Watts, Donna (2017):

Internet sexual solicitation of children. A proposed typology of offenders based on their chats, e-mails, and social network posts.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 77–89. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1241309.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Edwards, Rachel; Whittaker, Mette Kristensen; Beckett, Richard; Bishopp, Daz; Bates, Andrew (2012):

Adolescents who have sexually harmed. An evaluation of a specialist treatment programme.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 91–111. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.635317.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Risikofaktoren // risk factors

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Elliott, Ian A.; Findlater, Donald; Hughes, Teresa (2010):

Practice report. A review of e-Safety remote computer monitoring for UK sex offenders.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 237–248. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003686870.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Sicherheit // safety; Täter*in // offender; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Gakhal, Baldeesh Kaur; Brown, Sarah J. (2011):

A comparison of the general public's, forensic professionals' and students' attitudes towards female sex offenders.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 105–116. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.540678.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Geary, Jan; Lambie, Ian; Seymour, Fred (2011):

Consumer perspectives of New Zealand community treatment programmes for sexually abusive youth.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 181–195. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003778693.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Gillespie, Alisdair (2010):

Legal definitions of child pornography.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 19–31. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903262097.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; Pornografie // pornography; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Glasgow, David (2010):

The potential of digital evidence to contribute to risk assessment of internet offenders.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 87–106. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903428839.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Pornografie // pornography; Risiko // risk; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Gray, Jacqueline M. (2014):

What constitutes a “reasonable belief” in consent to sex? A thematic analysis.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 337–353. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.900122.

Schlagwörter:

Konsens // consent; Vergewaltigung // rape; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Griffin, Helen Louise; Vettor, Shannon (2012):

Predicting sexual re-offending in a UK sample of adolescents with intellectual disabilities.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 64–80. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.617013.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Risiko // risk; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Gwirayi, Pesanayi (2013):

The prevalence of child sexual abuse among secondary school pupils in Gweru, Zimbabwe.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 253–263. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.723755.

Schlagwörter:

Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Hackett, Simon; Carpenter, John; Patsios, Demi; Szilassy, Eszter (2013):

Interprofessional and interagency training for working with young people with harmful sexual behaviours. An evaluation of outcomes.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 329–344. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.753122.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 7 Sexualität

Hall, Charlotte L.; Hogue, Todd E.; Guo, Kun (2014):

Gaze patterns to child figures reflect deviant sexual preference in child sex offenders—a first glance.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 303–317. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.931475.

Schlagwörter:

sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Harper, Craig A.; Bartels, Ross M. (2017):

The influence of implicit theories and offender characteristics on judgements of sexual offenders. A moderated mediation analysis.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 139–150. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1250963.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Henry, Olivia; Mandeville-Norden, Rebecca; Hayes, Elizabeth; Egan, Vincent (2010):

Do internet-based sexual offenders reduce to normal, inadequate and deviant groups?

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 33–46. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903454132.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Höing, Mechtild; Jonker, Marianne; Berlo, Willy van (2010):

Juvenile sex offenders in a Dutch mandatory educational programme. Subtypes and characteristics.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (3), S. 332–346. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903350991.

Schlagwörter:

jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art

Huitema, Anneloes; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine (2016):

Attitudes of Dutch citizens towards male victims of sexual coercion by a female perpetrator.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 308–322. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1159343.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Geschlecht // gender; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Ingevaldson, Sara; Goulding, Anneli; Tidefors, Inga (2016):

Experiences of intimate relationships in young men who sexually offended during adolescence. Interviews 10 years later.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 410–422. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1177125.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Männer // men

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Kemshall, Hazel; Kelly, Gill; Wilkinson, Bernadette (2012):

Child Sex Offender Public Disclosure Scheme. The views of applicants using the English pilot disclosure scheme.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 164–178. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.552987.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Risiko // risk; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Kemshall, Hazel; Moulden, Heather M. (2017):

Communicating about child sexual abuse with the public. Learning the lessons from public awareness campaigns.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 124–138. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1222004.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Kettleborough, Danielle G.; Merdian, Hannah L. (2017):

Gateway to offending behaviour. Permission-giving thoughts of online users of child sexual exploitation material.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 19–32. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1231852.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Kinder // children; Pornografie // pornography; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention;
5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

King, Laura L.; Hanrahan, Kathleen J. (2015):

University student beliefs about sexual violence in prison. Rape myth acceptance, punitiveness, and empathy.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 179–193. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.820851.

Schlagwörter:

Student*innen // college students; Vergewaltigung // rape; Victim-blaming

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 6 Gewalt;
6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung

Kosuri, Mahathi D.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2017):

Child sex tourism. American perceptions of foreign victims.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 207–221. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1231350.

Schlagwörter:

sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung;
8.4 Ergebnisse

Krahé, Barbara; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine (2015):

Mapping an agenda for the study of youth sexual aggression in Europe. Assessment, principles of good practice, and the multilevel analysis of risk factors.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (2), S. 161–176. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1066885.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression; Betroffene // survivors; Jugendliche // youth; Risikofaktoren // risk factors

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Kuhle, Laura F.; Schlinzig, Eliza; Kaiser, Gerd; Amelung, Till; Konrad, Anna; Röhle, Robert; Beier, Klaus M. (2017):

The association of sexual preference and dynamic risk factors with undetected child pornography offending.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 3–18. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1201157.

Schlagwörter:

Pornografie // pornography; Risiko // risk; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Lambie, Ian; Price, Mnthali (2015):

Transitioning youth with sexually harmful behaviour back into the community.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 244–265. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.873829.

Schlagwörter:

jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Lambine, Mackenzie E. (2012):

Unsafe in the Ivory Tower. The sexual victimization of college women.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (3), S. 375–376. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.711657.

Schlagwörter:

sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Sicherheit // safety; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college university

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Leonard, Marcella Mary (2010):

“I did what I was directed to do but he didn't touch me“. The impact of being a victim of internet offending.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 249–256. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003690526.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Internet; Sprache // language; Trauma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Lewis, Tiffany; Klettke, Bianca; Day, Andrew (2014):

Sentencing in child sexual assault cases. Factors influencing judicial decision-making.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 281–295. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.804603.

Schlagwörter:

sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Makura, Alfred Henry; Zireva, Davison (2013):

School heads and mentors in cahoots? Challenges to teaching practice in Zimbabwean teacher education programmes.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 3–16. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.573583.

Schlagwörter:

Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Schule // school; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Mannix, Karyn; Dawson, David L.; Beckley, Kerry (2013):

The implicit theories of male child sexual offenders residing in a high secure psychiatric hospital.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (3), S. 264–274. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.732616.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.10 Justizvollzugsanstalt; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Manson, William (2015):

“Keeping Children Safe”. The Child Sex Offender Disclosure Scheme in Scotland.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 43–55. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.950352.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Kinderrechte // children’s rights; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art

Marshall, W. L.; Marshall, L. E.; Kingston, Drew A. (2011):

Are the cognitive distortions of child molesters in need of treatment?

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 118–129. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.580572.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Masson, Helen; Balfe, Myles; Hackett, Simon; Phillips, Josie (2012):

Making use of historical case material. The problems of looking back and the implications for service development in relation to research and evaluation activities.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 112–122. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.630539.

Schlagwörter:

Forschung // research; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik; 8.3 Methodologie

Maxwell, Louise; Scott, Graham (2014):

A review of the role of radical feminist theories in the understanding of rape myth acceptance.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 40–54. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.773384.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Feminismus // feminism; Geschlecht // gender; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Täter*in // offender; Übersicht // review; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie

McCartan, Fiona Mairead; Law, Heather; Murphy, Maeve; Bailey, Susan (2011):

Child and adolescent females who present with sexually abusive behaviours. A 10-year UK prevalence study.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 4–14. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.488302.

Schlagwörter:

jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

McManus, Michelle Ann; Almond, Louise (2014):

Trends of indecent images of children and child sexual offences between 2005/2006 and 2012/2013 within the United Kingdom.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 142–155. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.893031.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

McManus, Michelle Ann; Long, Matthew L.; Alison, Laurence; Almond, Louise (2014):

Factors associated with contact child sexual abuse in a sample of indecent image offenders.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (3), S. 368–384. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927009.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; Pornografie // pornography; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Merdian, Hannah Lena; Curtis, Cate; Thakker, Jo; Wilson, Nick; Boer, Douglas Pieter (2013):

The three dimensions of online child pornography offending.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 121–132. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.611898.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Kinder // children; Pornografie // pornography; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Mitchell, Renae C.; Galupo, M. Paz (2015):

Interest in child molestation among a community sample of men sexually attracted to children.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (2), S. 224–232. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1056263.

Schlagwörter:

Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Morgan, Wendy; Gilchrist, Elizabeth (2010):

Risk assessment with intimate partner sex offenders.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (3), S. 361–372. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.502976.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Gewalt // violence; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Risikofaktoren // risk factors

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Nunes, Kevin L.; McPhail, Ian V.; Babchishin, Kelly M. (2012):

Social anxiety and sexual offending against children. A cumulative meta-analysis.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (3), S. 284–293. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.549243.

Schlagwörter:

Angst // anxiety; Männer // men; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Ó Ciardha, Caoilte; Gannon, Theresa A. (2011):

The cognitive distortions of child molesters are in need of treatment.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 130–141. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.580573.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

O'Halloran, Elaine; Quayle, Ethel (2010):

A content analysis of a “boy love” support forum. Revisiting Durkin and Bryant.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (1), S. 71–85. DOI: 10.1080/13552600903395319.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Paquette, Sarah; Cortoni, Franca; Proulx, Jean; Longpre, Nicholas (2014):

An examination of implicit theories among francophone child molesters.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (2), S. 182–196. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.798689.

Schlagwörter:

Ehtik // ethics; Einstellungen // attitudes; Nordamerika // North America; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Park, Jisun; Kim, Seunghee (2016):

Group size does matter. Differences among sexual assaults committed by lone, double, and groups of three or more perpetrators.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 342–354. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1144801.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Gruppensettings // group settings; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Täter*in // offender; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Pritchard, Duncan; Graham, Nicola; Penney, Heather; Owen, Gwynne; Peters, Sandra; Mace, F. Charles (2016):

Multi-component behavioural intervention reduces harmful sexual behaviour in a 17-year-old male with autism spectrum disorder. A case study.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 368–378. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1130269.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression; Autismus // autism; Behandlung // treatment; Behinderung // disability; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.4 Resilienz

Rogers, Paul; Wczasek, Ryan; Davies, Michelle (2011):

Attributions of blame in a hypothetical internet solicitation case. Roles of victim naivety, parental neglect and respondent gender.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (2), S. 196–214. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003664869.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Eltern // parents; Gesellschaft // society; Internet; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Sheehan, Valerie; Sullivan, Joe (2010):

A qualitative analysis of child sex offenders involved in the manufacture of indecent images of children.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 143–167. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003698644.

Schlagwörter:

Kinderpornographie; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Slotboom, Anne-Marie; Hendriks, Jan; Verbruggen, Janna (2011):

Contrasting adolescent female and male sexual aggression. A self-report study on prevalence and predictors of sexual aggression.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (1), S. 15–33. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.544413.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Europa // Europe; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Prävalenz // prevalence; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Smith, Connie; Allardyce, Stuart; Hackett, Simon; Bradbury-Jones, Caroline; Lazenbatt, Anne; Taylor, Julie (2014):

Practice and policy in the UK with children and young people who display harmful sexual behaviours. An analysis and critical review.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (3), S. 267–280. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.927010.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Europa // Europe; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Policies; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Spraitz, Jason D.; Bowen, Kendra N.; Arthurs, Shavonne (2017):

Neutralisation and sexual abuse. A study of monks from one Benedictine Abbey.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 195–206. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1204471.

Schlagwörter:

Christentum // christianity; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Nordamerika // North America; Religion; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2.9 Kirche; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Stevens, Peter; Hutchin, Katie; French, Lesley; Craissati, Jackie (2013):

Developmental and offence-related characteristics of different types of adolescent sex offender. A community sample.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 138–157. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.645889.

Schlagwörter:

jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Kinderpornographie

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Strömwall, Leif A.; Alfredsson, Helen; Landström, Sara (2013):

Rape victim and perpetrator blame and the Just World hypothesis. The influence of victim gender and age.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 207–217. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.683455.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Rape Culture; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Vergewaltigung // rape; Victim-blaming

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung

Tidefors, Inga; Arvidsson, Hans; Rudolfsson, Lisa (2012):

Agreement between ratings from self-rating scales and assessments by treatment staff concerning a group of adolescent males who have sexually offended.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 136–148. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.528845.

Schlagwörter:

jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Tomaszewska, Paulina; Krahé, Barbara (2016):

Attitudes towards sexual coercion by Polish high school students. Links with risky sexual scripts, pornography use, and religiosity.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 291–307. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1195892.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Pornografie // pornography; Religion; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexuelle Skripte // sexual scripts; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.5 Religion; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Tsagaris, George S.; Bach, Jesse E.; Cimino, Chrisa (2017):

The characteristics of federal offenders sentenced for sexual exploitation of children within a large urban metropolitan region.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 181–194. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1307463.

Schlagwörter:

Kinderpornographie; Nordamerika // North America; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Ventus, Daniel; Antfolk, Jan; Salo, Benny (2017):

The associations between abuse characteristics in child sexual abuse. A meta-analysis.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (2), S. 167–180. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2017.1318963.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Prävalenz // prevalence; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Weiler, Julia von; Haardt-Becker, Annette; Schulte, Simone (2010):

Care and treatment of child victims of child pornographic exploitation (CPE) in Germany.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 16 (2), S. 211–222. DOI: 10.1080/13552601003759990.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Betroffene // survivors; Europa // Europe; Kinder // children; Kinderpornographie; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

White, Jacquelyn; Buehler, Cheryl; Weymouth, Bridget B. (2014):

Childhood attention deficit hyperactive disorder (ADHD) symptoms and adolescent female sexual victimisation. Mediating and moderating effects of risky behaviours.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 20 (1), S. 23–39. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.782429.

Schlagwörter:

Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Williams, Andy (2015):

Child sexual victimisation. Ethnographic stories of stranger and acquaintance grooming.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (1), S. 28–42. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2014.948085.

Schlagwörter:

Grooming; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Williams, Matthew L.; Hudson, Kirsty (2013):

Public perceptions of internet, familial and localised sexual grooming. Predicting perceived prevalence and safety.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (2), S. 218–235. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.705341.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Europa // Europe; Familie // family; Internet; Medien // media; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Williamson, Laura Helen; Grubb, Amy Rose (2015):

An analysis of the relationship between being deaf and sexual offending.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 21 (2), S. 224–243. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2013.842001.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Sprache // language; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Willis, Gwenda M.; Johnston, Lucy (2012):

Planning helps. The impact of release planning on subsequent re-entry experiences of child sex offenders.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (2), S. 194–208. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.506576.

Schlagwörter:

Frauen // women; Policies; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Strafrecht // criminal justice; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.10 Justizvollzugsanstalt; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Willis, Gwenda M.; Levenson, Jill S. (2016):

The relationship between childhood adversity and adult psychosocial outcomes in females who have sexually offended. Implications for treatment.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (3), S. 355–367. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1131341.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender; Trauma; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Willis, Gwenda M.; Ward, Tony (2011):

Striving for a good life. The good lives model applied to released child molesters.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 17 (3), S. 290–303. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2010.505349.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Winters, Georgia M.; Kaylor, Leah E.; Jeglic, Elizabeth L. (2017):

Sexual offenders contacting children online. An examination of transcripts of sexual grooming.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 23 (1), S. 62–76. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2016.1271146.

Schlagwörter:

Grooming; Internet; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Wonnacott, Jane (2013):

Keeping children safe in nurseries. A focus on culture and context.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 19 (1), S. 32–45. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2012.747631.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Internet; Kinder // children; Kindergarten // nursery; Schutz // protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.1 Kindertagesstätte; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Worling, James (2012):

The assessment and treatment of deviant sexual arousal with adolescents who have offended sexually.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 36–63. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.630152.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Yates, Peter; Allardyce, Stuart; MacQueen, Sarah (2012):

Children who display harmful sexual behaviour. Assessing the risks of boys abusing at home, in the community or across both settings.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 18 (1), S. 23–35. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2011.634527.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Geschwister // siblings; Inzest // incest; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Yoder, Jamie; Ruch, Donna (2015):

A qualitative investigation of treatment components for families of youth who have sexually offended.

In: *Journal of Sexual Aggression* 22 (2), S. 192–205. DOI: 10.1080/13552600.2015.1107141.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Familie // family; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Journal of Youth and Adolescence

Abajobir, Amanuel Alemu; Kisely, Steve; Williams, Gail Marilyn; Clavarino, Alexandra Marie; Najman, Jakob Moses (2017):

Substantiated Childhood Maltreatment and Intimate Partner Violence Victimization in Young Adulthood: A Birth Cohort Study.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 165–179. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0558-3.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Bauermeister, José A. (2014):

How statewide LGB policies go from “under our skin” to “into our hearts”: fatherhood aspirations and psychological well-being among emerging adult sexual minority men.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1295–1305. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0059-6.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Eltern // parents; lesbisch // lesbian; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Politik // politics; schwul // gay

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Bauermeister, José A.; Johns, Michelle Marie; Sandfort, Theo G. M.; Eisenberg, Anna; Grossman, Arnold H.; D'Augelli, Anthony R. (2010):

Relationship trajectories and psychological well-being among sexual minority youth.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1148–1163. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9557-y.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Baumgartner, Susanne E.; Valkenburg, Patti M.; Peter, Jochen (2010):

Assessing causality in the relationship between adolescents' risky sexual online behavior and their perceptions of this behavior.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1226–1239. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9512-y.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Risiko // risk; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Boisvert, Stéphanie; Poulin, François (2016):

Romantic Relationship Patterns from Adolescence to Emerging Adulthood: Associations with Family and Peer Experiences in Early Adolescence.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 945–958. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0435-0.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Familie // family; Jugendliche // youth; Peers

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Bower, Andrew R.; Nishina, Adrienne; Witkow, Melissa R.; Bellmore, Amy (2015):

Nice Guys and Gals Finish Last? Not in Early Adolescence When Empathic, Accepted, and Popular Peers are Desirable.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (12), S. 2275–2288. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0346-5.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression; Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Jugendliche // youth; Peers

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Bowker, Julie C.; Etkin, Rebecca G. (2014):

Does humor explain why relationally aggressive adolescents are popular?

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1322–1332. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0031-5.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression; Gewalt in Beziehngen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Peers

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Brooks-Russell, Ashley; Foshee, Vangie A.; Ennett, Susan T. (2013):

Predictors of latent trajectory classes of physical dating violence victimization.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 566–580. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9876-2.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehngen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Carlson, Daniel L.; McNulty, Thomas L.; Bellair, Paul E.; Watts, Stephen (2014):

Neighborhoods and racial/ethnic disparities in adolescent sexual risk behavior.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (9), S. 1536–1549. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0052-0.

Schlagwörter:

erstes Mal // sexual debut; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Jugendliche // youth; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Casey, Erin A.; Beadnell, Blair (2010):

The structure of male adolescent peer networks and risk for intimate partner violence perpetration: findings from a national sample.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 620–633. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9423-y.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehngen // dating violence; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Peers

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Chang, Ling-Yin; Foshee, Vangie A.; Reyes, Heathe Luz McNaughton; Ennett, Susan T.; Halpern, Carolyn T. (2015):

Direct and indirect effects of neighborhood characteristics on the perpetration of dating violence across adolescence.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 727–744. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0190-z.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehngen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Collibee, Charlene; Furman, Wyndol (2016):

Chronic and Acute Relational Risk Factors for Dating Aggression in Adolescence and Young Adulthood.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (4), S. 763–776. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0427-0.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Gewalt in Beziehngen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Risikofaktoren // risk factors

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G. M. (2013):

Homophobic name-calling among secondary school students and its implications for mental health.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 363–375. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9823-2.

Schlagwörter:

Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Mobbing // bullying; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Cox, Nele; Vanden Berghe, Wim; Dewaele, Alexis; Vincke, John (2010):

Acculturation strategies and mental health in gay, lesbian, and bisexual youth.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1199–1210. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9435-7.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Jugendliche // youth; lesbisch // lesbian; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; schwul // gay; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Crandall, AliceAnn; Magnusson, Brianna M.; Novilla, M. Lelinneth B.; Novilla, Lynneth Kirsten B.; Dyer, W. Justin (2017):

Family Financial Stress and Adolescent Sexual Risk-Taking: The Role of Self-Regulation.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (1), S. 45–62. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0543-x.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Jugendliche // youth; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Dank, Meredith; Lachman, Pamela; Zweig, Janine M.; Yahner, Jennifer (2014):

Dating violence experiences of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (5), S. 846–857. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9975-8.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; lesbisch // lesbian; schwul // gay; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Dermody, Sarah S.; Marshal, Michael P.; Cheong, Jeewon; Burton, Chad; Hughes, Tonda; Aranda, Frances; Friedman, Mark S. (2014):

Longitudinal disparities of hazardous drinking between sexual minority and heterosexual individuals from adolescence to young adulthood.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (1), S. 30–39. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9905-9.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; lesbisch // lesbian; schwul // gay; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Doty, Nathan Daniel; Willoughby, Brian L. B.; Lindahl, Kristin M.; Malik, Neena M. (2010):

Sexuality related social support among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1134–1147. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9566-x.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Jugendliche // youth; lesbisch // lesbian; Resilienz // resilience; schwul // gay; soziale Unterstützung // social support

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Ellis, Wendy E.; Chung-Hall, Janet; Dumas, Tara M. (2013):

The role of peer group aggression in predicting adolescent dating violence and relationship quality.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 487–499. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9797-0.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression; Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Peers

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Farr, Rachel H.; Crain, Emily E.; Oakley, M. K.; Cashen, Krystal K.; Garber, Karin J. (2016):

Microaggressions, Feelings of Difference, and Resilience Among Adopted Children with Sexual Minority Parents.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (1), S. 85–104. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0353-6.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression; Eltern // parents; Kinder // children; lesbisch // lesbian; Resilienz // resilience; schwul // gay; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

Ferguson, Christopher J.; Muñoz, Mónica E.; Garza, Adolfo; Galindo, Mariza (2014):

Concurrent and prospective analyses of peer, television and social media influences on body dissatisfaction, eating disorder symptoms and life satisfaction in adolescent girls.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (1), S. 1–14. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9898-9.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Körper // body; Mädchen // girls; Medien // media; Peers

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Fish, Jessica N.; Pasley, Kay (2015):

Sexual (Minority) Trajectories, Mental Health, and Alcohol Use: A Longitudinal Study of Youth as They Transition to Adulthood.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (8), S. 1508–1527. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0280-6.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Fitzpatrick, Kevin M.; Dulin, Akilah; Piko, Bettina (2010):

Bullying and depressive symptomatology among low-income, African-American youth.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (6), S. 634–645. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9426-8.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Mobbing // bullying; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Foshee, Vangie A.; Benefield, Thad; Dixon, Kimberly S.; Chang, Ling-Yin; Senkomago, Virginia; Ennett, Susan T. et al. (2015):

The effects of moms and teens for safe dates: a dating abuse prevention program for adolescents exposed to domestic violence.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 995–1010. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0272-6.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; häusliche Gewalt // domestic violence; Jugendliche // youth; Prävention // prevention; Wirksamkeit // effectiveness

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Genna, Natacha M. de; Larkby, Cynthia; Cornelius, Marie D. (2011):

Pubertal timing and early sexual intercourse in the offspring of teenage mothers.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (10), S. 1315–1328. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9609-3.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Pubertät // Puberty; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Gillmore, Mary Rogers; Chen, Angela Chia-Chen; Haas, Steven A.; Kopak, Albert M.; Robillard, Alyssa G. (2011):

Do family and parenting factors in adolescence influence condom use in early adulthood in a multiethnic sample of young adults?

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (11), S. 1503–1518. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9631-0.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Jugendliche // youth; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität

Graaf, Hanneke de; van de Schoot, Rens; Woertman, Liesbeth; Hawk, Skyler T.; Meeus, Wim (2012):

Family cohesion and romantic and sexual initiation: a three wave longitudinal study.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 583–592. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9708-9.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Familie // family; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Graaf, Hanneke de; Vanwesenbeeck, Ine; Woertman, Liesbeth; Keijsers, Loes; Meijer, Suzanne; Meeus, Wim (2010):

Parental support and knowledge and adolescents' sexual health: testing two mediational models in a national Dutch sample.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (2), S. 189–198. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-008-9387-3.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Harden, K. Paige; Mendle, Jane (2011):

Adolescent sexual activity and the development of delinquent behavior: the role of relationship context.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 825–838. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9601-y.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Hay, Carter; Meldrum, Ryan (2010):

Bullying victimization and adolescent self-harm: testing hypotheses from general strain theory.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (5), S. 446–459. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-009-9502-0.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Mobbing // bullying; Selbstmord // suicide

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Haydon, Abigail A.; Halpern, Carolyn Tucker (2010):

Older romantic partners and depressive symptoms during adolescence.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1240–1251. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9539-0.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Hooghe, Marc; Meeusen, Cecil (2012):

Homophobia and the transition to adulthood: a three year panel study among Belgian late adolescents and young adults, 2008-2011.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (9), S. 1197–1207. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9786-3.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Jugendliche // youth; Stereotype // stereotypes

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Houser, John J.; Mayeux, Lara; Cross, Cassandra (2015):

Peer status and aggression as predictors of dating popularity in adolescence.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (3), S. 683–695. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0174-z.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Peers

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Jerman, Petra; Constantine, Norman A. (2010):

Demographic and psychological predictors of parent-adolescent communication about sex: a representative statewide analysis.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 39 (10), S. 1164–1174. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9546-1.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Jugendliche // youth; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Killoren, Sarah E.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; Christopher, F. Scott (2011):

Family and cultural correlates of Mexican-origin youths' sexual intentions.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (6), S. 707–718. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9587-5.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Familie // family; Jugendliche // youth; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Killoren, Sarah E.; Zeiders, Katharine H.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J. (2016):

The Sociocultural Context of Mexican-Origin Pregnant Adolescents' Attitudes Toward Teen Pregnancy and Links to Future Outcomes.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 887–899. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0387-9.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Jugendliche // youth; Schwangerschaft // pregnancy

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

La Roi, Chaïm; Kretschmer, Tina; Dijkstra, Jan Cornelis; Veenstra, René; Oldehinkel, Albertine J. (2016):

Disparities in Depressive Symptoms Between Heterosexual and Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Youth in a Dutch Cohort: The TRAILS Study.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (3), S. 440–456. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0403-0.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Eltern // parents; Jugendliche // youth; lesbisch // lesbian; Peers; Pubertät // Puberty; schwul // gay; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Lansford, Jennifer E.; Dodge, Kenneth A.; Fontaine, Reid Griffith; Bates, John E.; Pettit, Gregory S. (2014):

Peer rejection, affiliation with deviant peers, delinquency, and risky sexual behavior.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (10), S. 1742–1751. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0175-y.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Peers; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Leech, Tamara G. J.; Dias, Janice Johnson (2012):

Risky sexual behavior: a race-specific social consequence of obesity.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (1), S. 41–52. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9670-6.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Gesundheit // health; Jugendliche // youth; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Loftus, Jeni; Kelly, Brian C.; Mustillo, Sarah A. (2011):

Depressive symptoms among adolescent girls in relationships with older partners: causes and lasting effects?

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 800–813. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9589-3.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Lopez, Vera; Kopak, Albert; Robillard, Alyssa; Gillmore, Mary Rogers; Holliday, Rhonda C.; Braithwaite, Ronald L. (2011):

Pathways to sexual risk taking among female adolescent detainees.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (8), S. 945–957. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9623-5.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Risiko // risk; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Lourie, Michael A.; Needham, Belinda L. (2017):

Sexual Orientation Discordance and Young Adult Mental Health.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 943–954. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0553-8.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Low, Sabina; Polanin, Joshua R.; Espelage, Dorothy L. (2013):

The role of social networks in physical and relational aggression among young adolescents.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1078–1089. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9933-5.

Schlagwörter:

Aggression; Jugendliche // youth; Peers

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Makin-Byrd, Kerry; Bierman, Karen L. (2013):

Individual and family predictors of the perpetration of dating violence and victimization in late adolescence.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 536–550. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9810-7.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Martin-Storey, Alexa (2015):

Prevalence of dating violence among sexual minority youth: variation across gender, sexual minority identity and gender of sexual partners.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 211–224. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0089-0.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Milan, Stephanie; Wortel, Sanne (2015):

Family obligation values as a protective and vulnerability factor among low-income adolescent girls.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (6), S. 1183–1193. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0206-8.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Miller, Shari; Williams, Jason; Cutbush, Stacey; Gibbs, Deborah; Clinton-Sherrod, Monique; Jones, Sarah (2013):

Dating violence, bullying, and sexual harassment: longitudinal profiles and transitions over time.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 607–618. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9914-8.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Mobbing // bullying; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Moilanen, Kristin L. (2016):

Why Do Parents Grant or Deny Consent for Adolescent Participation in Sexuality Research?

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 1020–1036. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0445-y.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Forschung // research; Jugendliche // youth

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Murry, Velma McBride; Berkel, Cady; Chen, Yi-Fu; Brody, Gene H.; Gibbons, Frederick X.; Gerrard, Meg (2011):

Intervention induced changes on parenting practices, youth self-pride and sexual norms to reduce HIV-related behaviors among rural African American youths.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (9), S. 1147–1163. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9642-x.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Jugendliche // youth; Prävention // prevention; Risiko // risk; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität

Needham, Belinda L. (2012):

Sexual attraction and trajectories of mental health and substance use during the transition from adolescence to adulthood.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 179–190. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9729-4.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Nishina, Adrienne (2012):

Microcontextual characteristics of peer victimization experiences and adolescents' daily well-being.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (2), S. 191–201. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9669-z.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Mobbing // bullying; Peers; Schule // school

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Novak, Jamie; Furman, Wyndol (2016):

Partner Violence During Adolescence and Young Adulthood: Individual and Relationship Level Risk Factors.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (9), S. 1849–1861. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0484-4.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; Risikofaktoren // risk factors

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Orpinas, Pamela; Hsieh, Hsien-Lin; Song, Xiao; Holland, Kristin; Nahapetyan, Lusine (2013):

Trajectories of physical dating violence from middle to high school: association with relationship quality and acceptability of aggression.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 551–565. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9881-5.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Schüler*innen // pupils; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Patrick, Megan E.; Morgan, Nicole; Maggs, Jennifer L.; Lefkowitz, Eva S. (2011):

"I got your back": friends' understandings regarding college student spring break behavior.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (1), S. 108–120. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9515-8.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Nordamerika // North America; Peers; Risiko // risk; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Pearson, Jennifer; Wilkinson, Lindsey (2013):

Family relationships and adolescent well-being: are families equally protective for same-sex attracted youth?

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (3), S. 376–393. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9865-5.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Reyes, H. Luz McNaughton; Foshee, Vangie A.; Niolon, Phyllis Holditch; Reidy, Dennis E.; Hall, Jeffrey E. (2016):

Gender Role Attitudes and Male Adolescent Dating Violence Perpetration: Normative Beliefs as Moderators.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 350–360. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0278-0.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jungen // boys; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Rosario, Margaret; Schrimshaw, Eric W.; Hunter, Joyce (2012):

Homelessness among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth: implications for subsequent internalizing and externalizing symptoms.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 544–560. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9681-3.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Jugendliche // youth; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; Nordamerika // North America; obdachlos // homeless; Risiko // risk; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Rossi, Erika; Poulin, François; Boislard, Marie-Aude (2017):

Trajectories of Annual Number of Sexual Partners from Adolescence to Emerging Adulthood: Individual and Family Predictors.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 995–1008. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0571-6.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Risiko // risk; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Schalet, Amy T.; Santelli, John S.; Russell, Stephen T.; Halpern, Carolyn T.; Miller, Sarah A.; Pickering, Sarah S. et al. (2014):

Invited commentary. Broadening the evidence for adolescent sexual and reproductive health and education in the United States.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (10), S. 1595–1610. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0178-8.

Schlagwörter:

Nordamerika // North America; Policies; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Abstinenz // abstinence; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Schnurr, Melissa P.; Lohman, Brenda J. (2013):

The impact of collective efficacy on risks for adolescents' perpetration of dating violence.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (4), S. 518–535. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9909-5.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Soziale Schicht; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Schwarz, Beate; Stutz, Melanie; Ledermann, Thomas (2012):

Perceived interparental conflict and early adolescents' friendships: the role of attachment security and emotion regulation.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (9), S. 1240–1252. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9769-4.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Familie // family; Freunde // friends; Gefühle // emotions; Jugendliche // youth

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Shandra, Carrie L.; Chowdhury, Afra R. (2012):

The first sexual experience among adolescent girls with and without disabilities.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (4), S. 515–532. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-011-9668-0.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; erstes Mal // sexual debut; Jugendliche // youth

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Shulman, Shmuel; Zlotnik, Aynat; Shachar-Shapira, Lital; Connolly, Jennifer; Bohr, Yvonne (2012):

Adolescent daughters' romantic competence: the role of divorce, quality of parenting, and maternal romantic history.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 593–606. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9748-9.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Eltern // parents; Familie // family; Mädchen // girls

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Sipsma, Heather L.; Ickovics, Jeannette R.; Lin, Haiqun; Kershaw, Trace S. (2015):

The impact of future expectations on adolescent sexual risk behavior.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 170–183. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0082-7.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Risiko // risk; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Sullivan, Terri N.; Garthe, Rachel C.; Goncy, Elizabeth A.; Carlson, Megan M.; Behrhorst, Kathryn L. (2017):

Longitudinal Relations between Beliefs Supporting Aggression, Anger Regulation, and Dating Aggression among Early Adolescents.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 46 (5), S. 982–994. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-016-0569-0.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Temple, Jeff R.; Choi, Hye Jeong; Brem, Meagan; Wolford-Clevenger, Caitlin; Stuart, Gregory L.; Peskin, Melissa Fleschler; Elmquist, JoAnna (2016):

The Temporal Association Between Traditional and Cyber Dating Abuse Among Adolescents.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (2), S. 340–349. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0380-3.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Internet; Jugendliche // youth

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Updegraff, Kimberly A.; McHale, Susan M.; Zeiders, Katharine H.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J.; Perez-Brena, Norma J.; Wheeler, Lorey A.; Rodríguez De Jesús, Sue A. (2014):

Mexican-American adolescents' gender role attitude development: the role of adolescents' gender and nativity and parents' gender role attitudes.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (12), S. 2041–2053. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0128-5.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Familie // family; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Jugendliche // youth; Lateinamerika // Latin America; Nordamerika // North America; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

van Oosten, Johanna M. F.; Peter, Jochen; Boot, Inge (2015):

Exploring associations between exposure to sexy online self-presentations and adolescents' sexual attitudes and behavior.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (5), S. 1078–1091. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0194-8.

Schlagwörter:

Einstellungen // attitudes; Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Risiko // risk; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Vannier, Sarah A.; O'Sullivan, Lucia F. (2012):

Who gives and who gets: why, when, and with whom young people engage in oral sex.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 41 (5), S. 572–582. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-012-9745-z.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Verhoef, Melissa; van den Eijnden, Regina J. J. M.; Koning, Ina M.; Vollebergh, Wilma A. M. (2014):

Age at menarche and adolescent alcohol use.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 43 (8), S. 1333–1345. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-0075-6.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; Mädchen // girls; Pubertät // Puberty; Risiko // risk

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Vézina, Johanne; Hébert, Martine; Poulin, François; Lavoie, Francine; Vitaro, Frank; Tremblay, Richard E. (2011):

Risky lifestyle as a mediator of the relationship between deviant peer affiliation and dating violence victimization among adolescent girls.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 40 (7), S. 814–824. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-010-9602-x.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Peers; Risiko // risk; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Wheeler, Lorey A.; Killoren, Sarah E.; Whiteman, Shawn D.; Updegraff, Kimberly A.; McHale, Susan M.; Umaña-Taylor, Adriana J. (2016):

Romantic Relationship Experiences from Late Adolescence to Young Adulthood: The Role of Older Siblings in Mexican-Origin Families.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 45 (5), S. 900–915. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-015-0392-z.

Schlagwörter:

Familie // family; Jugendliche // youth; Latinx; Liebesbeziehung // romantic relationship; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Wright, Michelle F. (2015):

Cyber aggression within adolescents' romantic relationships: linkages to parental and partner attachment.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 44 (1), S. 37–47. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-014-0147-2.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Familie // family; Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Internet; Jugendliche // youth

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Zweig, Janine M.; Dank, Meredith; Yahner, Jennifer; Lachman, Pamela (2013):

The rate of cyber dating abuse among teens and how it relates to other forms of teen dating violence.

In: *Journal of Youth and Adolescence* 42 (7), S. 1063–1077. DOI: 10.1007/s10964-013-9922-8.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt in Beziehungen // dating violence; Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Prävalenz // prevalence

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Men and Masculinities

Allen, Louisa (2013):

Boys as Sexy Bodies.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 347–365. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13497205.

Schlagwörter:

Jungen // boys; Körper // body; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Anderson, E.; McCormack, M. (2015):

Cuddling and Spooning. Heteromascularity and Homosocial Tactility among Student-athletes.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (2), S. 214–230. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14523433.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Intimität // intimacy; Jungen // boys; Körper // body; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Sport // sports; Sportunterricht // physical education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.3.1 Schulfächer; 2.2.3.1.1 Sportunterricht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Bantjes, J.; Nieuwoudt, J. (2014):

Masculinity and Mayhem. The Performance of Gender in a South African Boys' School.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (4), S. 376–395. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539964.

Schlagwörter:

Jungen // boys; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 7 Sexualität

Bengtsson, T. T. (2016):

Performing Hypermasculinity. Experiences with Confined Young Offenders.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (4), S. 410–428. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15595083.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Männlichkeit // masculinity

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.10 Justizvollzugsanstalt; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Fair, Brian (2011):

Constructing Masculinity through Penetration Discourse. The Intersection of Misogyny and Homophobia in High School Wrestling.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 491–504. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10375936.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate; Sport // sports; Sportunterricht // physical education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.3.1 Schulfächer; 2.2.3.1.1 Sportunterricht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Johnson, Brooke (2010):

A Few Good Boys. Masculinity at a Military-Style Charter School.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 12 (5), S. 575–596. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X09342228.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Jungen // boys; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Nordamerika // North America; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate; schwarz // black; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Langa, Malose (2016):

The Value of Using a Psychodynamic Theory in Researching Black Masculinities of Adolescent Boys in Alexandra Township, South Africa.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (3), S. 260–288. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15586434.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Jungen // boys; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Sub-Sahara-Afrika // Sub-Saharan Africa

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Manninen, Sari; Huuki, Tuija; Sunnari, Vappu (2011):

Earn Yo' Respect! Respect in the Status Struggle of Finnish School Boys.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (3), S. 335–357. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X10369476.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Jungen // boys; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Marcell, Arik V.; Eftim, Sorina E.; Sonenstein, Freya L.; Pleck, Joseph H. (2011):

Associations of Family and Peer Experiences with Masculinity Attitude Trajectories at the Individual and Group Level in Adolescent and Young Adult Males.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (5), S. 565–587. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X11409363.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Jungen // boys; Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Martino, Wayne J.; Cumming-Potvin, Wendy (2015):

Teaching about "Princess Boys" or Not. The Case of One Male Elementary School Teacher and the Polemics of Gender Expression and Embodiment.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 18 (1), S. 79–99. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14551278.

Schlagwörter:

Grundschule // elementary school; Jungen // boys; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Schulklima // school climate

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Norman, Moss E. (2011):

Embodying the Double-Bind of Masculinity. Young Men and Discourses of Normalcy, Health, Heterosexuality, and Individualism.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 14 (4), S. 430–449. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X11409360.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Jungen // boys; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Nordamerika // North America

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Pavlakis, D. (2014):

Reputation and the Sexual Abuse of Boys. Changing Norms in Late-Nineteenth-Century Britain.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (3), S. 325–346. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14539512.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Geschichte // history; Jungen // boys; Männlichkeit // masculinity; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Peacock, Dean; Barker, Gary (2014):

Working with Men and Boys to Prevent Gender-based Violence. Principles, Lessons Learned, and Ways Forward.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 17 (5), S. 578–599. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X14558240.

Schlagwörter:

Global; Jungen // boys; Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Policies; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Piccigallo, Jaqueline R.; Lilley, Terry G.; Miller, Susan L. (2012):

"It's Cool to Care about Sexual Violence". Men's Experiences with Sexual Assault Prevention.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 15 (5), S. 507–525. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X12458590.

Schlagwörter:

Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Prävention // prevention; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Student*innen // college students; Vergewaltigung // rape; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Russell, Brenda L.; Oswald, Debra L. (2016):

When Sexism Cuts Both Ways. Predictors of Tolerance of Sexual Harassment of Men.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 19 (5), S. 524–544. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X15602745.

Schlagwörter:

Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college university; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Vandenbosch, Laura; Eggermont, Steven (2013):

Sexualization of Adolescent Boys.

In: *Men and Masculinities* 16 (3), S. 283–306. DOI: 10.1177/1097184X13477866.

Schlagwörter:

Jungen // boys; Medien // media; Pornografie // pornography; Sexualisierung // sexualization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Pedagogy, Culture & Society

Allen, Louisa (2011):

'Undoing' the self. Should heterosexual teachers 'come out' in the university classroom?

In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 19 (1), S. 79–95. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2011.548990.

Schlagwörter:

Coming out; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Heterosexualität // heterosexuality; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Professionalität // professionalism; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Busche, Mart (2013):

A girl is no girl is a girl_: Girls-work after queer theory.

In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (1), S. 43–56.

Schlagwörter:

Feminismus // feminism

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.8 Offene Kinder- und Jugendarbeit

Kjaraan, Jón; Kristinsdóttir, Guðrún (2014):

Queering the environment and caring for the self. Icelandic LGBT students' experience of the upper secondary school.

In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 23 (1), S. 1–20. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2014.910250.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Coming out; lesbisch // lesbian; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; schwul // gay; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sprache // language; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Koster, Shirley (2011):

The self-managed heart. Teaching gender and doing emotional labour in a higher education institution.

In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 19 (1), S. 61–77. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2011.548988.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Geschlecht // gender; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Professionalität // professionalism; Universität // college university; Unterricht // class; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Paechter, Carrie (2013):

Girls and their bodies. Approaching a more emancipatory physical education.

In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (2), S. 261–277. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.712055.

Schlagwörter:

Körper // body; Mädchen // girls; Sportunterricht // physical education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.3.1 Schulfächer; 2.2.3.1.1 Sportunterricht

Šribar, Renata (2013):

Growing-up challenged and challenging. Gender and sexuality norms in referential research on 'internet risks' and in children.

In: *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* 21 (1), S. 129–145. DOI: 10.1080/14681366.2012.748681.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Geschlecht // gender; Kinder // children; Medien // media; Sexting // sexting; Sexualisierung // sexualization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Qualitative Research

Allen, Louisa (2011):

'Picture this'. Using photo-methods in research on sexualities and schooling.

In: *Qualitative Research* 11 (5), S. 487–504. DOI: 10.1177/1468794111413224.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschung // research; Jugendliche // youth; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Moore, Tim P.; McArthur, Morag; Noble-Carr, Debbie (2017):

More a marathon than a hurdle. Towards children's informed consent in a study on safety.

In: *Qualitative Research* 7 (2), 146879411770070. DOI: 10.1177/1468794117700708.

Schlagwörter:

Forschung // research; Kinder // children; Sicherheit // safety

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik; 8.3 Methodologie

Research in Developmental Disabilities

Asscher, Jessica J.; Put, Claudia E. van der; Stams, Geert Jan (2012):

Differences between juvenile offenders with and without intellectual disability in offense type and risk factors.

In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 33 (6), S. 1905–1913. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2012.05.022.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Risikofaktoren // risk factors

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art

Doughty, Adam H.; Kane, Lindsey M. (2010):

Teaching abuse-protection skills to people with intellectual, disabilities. A review of the literature.

In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 31 (2), S. 331–337. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2009.12.007.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Global; Prävention // prevention; Schutz // protection; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sicherheit // safety; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Embregts, P.; Bogaard, K. van den; Hendriks, L.; Heestermans, M.; Schuitemaker, M.; Wouwe, H. van (2010):

Sexual risk assessment for people with intellectual disabilities.

In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 31 (3), S. 760–767. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2010.01.018.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Europa // Europe; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

McCann, Edward; Lee, Regina; Brown, Michael (2016):

The experiences and support needs of people with intellectual disabilities who identify as LGBT: A review of the literature.

In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 57, S. 39–53. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2016.06.013.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Übersicht // review; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Rushbrooke, Elizabeth; Murray, Craig D.; Townsend, Samantha (2014):

What difficulties are experienced by caregivers in relation to the sexuality of people with intellectual disabilities? A qualitative meta-synthesis.

In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 35 (4), S. 871–886. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2014.01.012.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Professionalität // professionalism; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 7 Sexualität

Soylu, Nusret; Alpaslan, Ahmet Hamdi; Ayaz, Muhammed; Esenyel, Selcen; Oruc, Mucahit (2013):

Psychiatric disorders and characteristics of abuse in sexually abused children and adolescents with and without intellectual disabilities.

In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 34 (12), S. 4334–4342. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2013.09.010.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Vugt, Eveline van; Asscher, Jessica J.; Stams, Geert Jan; Hendriks, Jan; Bijleveld, Catrien; Laan, Peter van der (2011):

Moral judgment of young sex offenders with and without intellectual disabilities.

In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 32 (6), S. 2841–2846. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2011.05.022.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Sexualethik // sexual ethics

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art

Wissink, Inge B.; Vugt, Eveline van; Moonen, Xavier; Stams, Geert Jan; Hendriks, Jan (2015):

Sexual abuse involving children with an intellectual disability (ID): a narrative review.

In: *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 36, S. 20–35. DOI: 10.1016/j.ridd.2014.09.007.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Heim // residential care; Kinder // children; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Übersicht // review; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning

Abbott, Keeley; Ellis, Sonja J.; Abbott, Rachel (2016):

"We've got a lack of family values". An examination of how teachers formulate and justify their approach to teaching sex and relationships education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (6), S. 678–691. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1169398.

Schlagwörter:

Curriculum; Diskurs // discourse; Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Risiko // risk; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Abstinenz // abstinence; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Sprache // language; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 7 Sexualität

Albury, Kath (2013):

Young people, media and sexual learning. Rethinking representation.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S32–S44. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.767194.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Jugendliche // youth; Medien // media; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.3 Methodologie

Attwood, Feona; Smith, Clarissa (2011):

Investigating young people's sexual cultures. An introduction.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* (Vol. 11 No. 3), S. 235–242.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Bale, Clare (2011):

Raunch or romance? Framing and interpreting the relationship between sexualized culture and young people's sexual health.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 303–313. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590088.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Selbstbestimmung // agency; Sexualisierung // sexualization; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Bragg, Sara; Buckingham, David; Russell, Rachel; Willett, Rebekah (2011):

Too much, too soon? Children, 'sexualization' and consumer culture.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 279–292. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590085.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Eltern // parents; Europa // Europe; Kinder // children; Sexualisierung // sexualization; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität

Britzman, Deborah P. (2010):

Teachers and Eros.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 325–330. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491627.

Schlagwörter:

Intimität // intimacy; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 7 Sexualität

Brown, Graham; Sorenson, Anne; Hildebrand, Janina (2012):

How they got it and how they wanted it. Marginalised young people's perspective on their experiences of sexual health education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 599–612. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634141.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Jugendliche // youth; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.3 Peers; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Cameron-Lewis, Vanessa; Allen, Louisa (2013):

Teaching pleasure and danger in sexuality education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (2), S. 121–132. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.697440.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Curriculum; Konsens // consent; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergnügen // pleasure

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Carrion, Melissa L.; Jensen, Robin E. (2014):

Curricular decision-making among public sex educators.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (6), S. 623–634. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919444.

Schlagwörter:

Entscheidungen // decision-making; Schule // school; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.8 Offene Kinder- und Jugendarbeit; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern

Cohen, Jacqueline N.; Byers, E. Sandra; Sears, Heather A. (2011):

Factors affecting Canadian teachers' willingness to teach sexual health education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615606.

Schlagwörter:

Lehrer*innen // Teachers; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Daneback, Kristian; Månsson, Sven-Axel; Ross, Michael W.; Markham, Christine M. (2012):

The Internet as a source of information about sexuality.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 583–598. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627739.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

DePalma, Renée (2013):

Choosing to lose our gender expertise. Queering sex/gender in school settings.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (1), S. 1–15. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634145.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Grundschule // elementary school; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Professionalität // professionalism; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sprache // language; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule

Fava, Nicole M.; Bay-Cheng, Laina Y. (2013):

Trauma-informed sexuality education. Recognising the rights and resilience of youth.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 383–394. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.745808.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Resilienz // resilience; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Trauma

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz

Ferfolja, Tania (2013):

Sexual diversity, discrimination and 'homosexuality policy' in New South Wales' government schools.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (2), S. 159–171. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.697858.

Schlagwörter:

Homosexualität; Schule // school; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule

Flanagan, Paul (2012):

Ethical review and reflexivity in research of children's sexuality.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 535–544. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627731.

Schlagwörter:

Forschung // research; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Übersicht // review; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik

Fletcher, Gillian; Dowsett, Gary W.; Duncan, Duane; Slavin, Sean; Corboz, Julienne (2013):

Advancing Sexuality Studies. A short course on sexuality theory and research methodologies.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (3), S. 319–335. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.742847.

Schlagwörter:

Curriculum; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Formby, Eleanor (2011):

Sex and relationships education, sexual health, and lesbian, gay and bisexual sexual cultures. Views from young people.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 255–266. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590078.

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Jugendliche // youth; lesbisch // lesbian; schwul // gay; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Formby, Eleanor; Hirst, Julia; Owen, Jenny; Hayter, Mark; Stapleton, Helen (2010):

'Selling it as a holistic health provision and not just about condoms ...' Sexual health services in school settings. Current models and their relationship with sex and relationships education policy and provision.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 423–435. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515099.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Schule // school; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Garland-Levett, Sarah (2016):

Exploring discursive barriers to sexual health and social justice in the New Zealand sexuality education curriculum.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 17 (2), S. 121–134. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1233396.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Curriculum; Policies; Schule // school; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität

Gerouki, Margarita (2010):

The boy who was drawing princesses. Primary teachers' accounts of children's non-conforming behaviours.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 335–348. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515092.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Grundschule // elementary school; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Jungen // boys; Kinder // children; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schulklima // school climate; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Gilbert, Jen (2010):

Ambivalence only? Sex education in the age of abstinence.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 233–237. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491631.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Sexuelle Abstinenz // abstinence; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Gilbert, Jen (2015):

Walking through the school: the erotics of research.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 111–115. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1094947.

Schlagwörter:

Forschung // research; Geschlecht // gender; Nordamerika // North America; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.3 Methodologie

Gilliam, Melissa; Jagoda, Patrick; Jaworski, Erin; Hebert, Luciana E.; Lyman, Phoebe; Wilson, M. Claire (2015):

“Because if we don’t talk about it, how are we going to prevent it?”. Lucidity, a narrative-based digital game about sexual violence.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (4), S. 391–404. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1123147.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Medien // media; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Sport // sports

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Goldman, Juliette (2010):

The new sexuality education curriculum for Queensland primary schools.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (1), S. 47–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681810903491370.

Schlagwörter:

Curriculum; Grundschule // elementary school; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Goldman, Juliette (2011):

External providers' sexuality education teaching and pedagogies for primary school students in Grade 1 to Grade 7.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (02), S. 155–174. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.558423.

Schlagwörter:

Grundschule // elementary school; Kinder // children; Pädagogik // pedagogy; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Schule // school; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Goldman, Juliette (2012):

A critical analysis of UNESCO's International Technical Guidance on school-based education for puberty and sexuality.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 199–218. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.609051.

Schlagwörter:

Curriculum; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Pubertät // Puberty; Schule // school; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Sicherheit // safety

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 4.2 Extern

Gray, Emily M. (2013):

Coming out as a lesbian, gay or bisexual teacher. Negotiating private and professional worlds.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (6), S. 702–714. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.807789.

Schlagwörter:

Coming out; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Identität // identity; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Green, Eli R.; Hamarman, Amelia M.; McKee, Ryan W. (2014):

Online sexuality education pedagogy. Translating five in-person teaching methods to online learning environments.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (1), S. 19–30. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.942033.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Greslé-Favier, Claire (2010):

The legacy of abstinence-only discourses and the place of pleasure in US discourses on teenage sexuality.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 413–422. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515098.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Jugendliche // youth; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Abstinenz // abstinence; Vergnügen // pleasure

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Greslé-Favier, Claire (2013):

Adult discrimination against children. The case of abstinence-only education in twenty-first-century USA.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (6), S. 715–725. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.813387.

Schlagwörter:

Kinder // children; Kinderrechte // children's rights; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Greteman, Adam J. (2013):

Fashioning a bareback pedagogy. Towards a theory of risky (sex) education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S20–S31. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.760154.

Schlagwörter:

Ehtik // ethics; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Grondin, Anne-Marie (2011):

Thinking outside specious boxes. Constructionist and post-structuralist readings of 'child sexual abuse'.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (3), S. 243–254. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.590065.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie

Haggis, Jane; Mulholland, Monique (2013):

Rethinking difference and sex education. From cultural inclusivity to normative diversity.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (1), S. 57–66. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.824873.

Schlagwörter:

Intersektionalität // intersectionality; Jugendliche // youth; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.3 Methodologie

Hardie, Ann (2011):

Lesbian teachers and students. Issues and dilemmas of being 'out' in primary school.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–10. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615595.

Schlagwörter:

Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Harrison, Lyn; Ollis, Debbie (2014):

Stepping out of our comfort zones. Pre-service teachers' responses to a critical analysis of gender/power relations in sexuality education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 318–331. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1023284.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Feminismus // feminism; Geschlecht // gender; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Hirst, Julia (2013):

'It's got to be about enjoying yourself'. Young people, sexual pleasure, and sex and relationships education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 423–436. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.747433.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Vergewaltigung // rape; Vergnügen // pleasure; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Johnson, Rebecca L.; Sendall, Marguerite C.; McCuaig, Louise A. (2014):

Primary schools and the delivery of relationships and sexuality education. The experience of Queensland teachers.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 359–374. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.909351.

Schlagwörter:

Curriculum; Grundschule // elementary school; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Jones, Tiffany Mary (2011):

Saving rhetorical children. Sexuality education discourses from conservative to post-modern.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 369–387. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595229.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Einstellungen // attitudes; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Sexuallerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Jones, Tiffany Mary; Hillier, Lynne (2012):

Sexuality education school policy for Australian GLBTIQ students.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (4), S. 437–454. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.677211.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Schule // school; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Kennett, Deborah J.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Schultz, Kristen E. (2011):

Sexual resourcefulness and the impact of family, sex education, media and peers.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning*, S. 1–18. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615624.

Schlagwörter:

Medien // media; Ressourcen // resourcefulness

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Kontula, Osmo (2010):

The evolution of sex education and students' sexual knowledge in Finland in the 2000s.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 373–386. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515095.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Wissen // knowledge

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Lamb, Sharon; Lustig, Kara; Graling, Kelly (2013):

The use and misuse of pleasure in sex education curricula.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (3), S. 305–318. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.738604.

Schlagwörter:

Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Vergnügen // pleasure

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Lampert, Jo (2012):

Sh-h-h-h. Representations of perpetrators of sexual child abuse in picturebooks.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 177–185. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.609048.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Global; Medien // media; Narration // narrative; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Lesko, Nancy (2010):

Feeling abstinent? Feeling comprehensive? Touching the affects of sexuality curricula.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 281–297. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491633.

Schlagwörter:

Curriculum; Schule // school; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Limmer, Mark (2010):

Young men, masculinities and sex education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 349–358. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515093.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Jungen // boys; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Lindroth, Malin (2014):

Sex education and young people in group homes. Balancing risks, rights and resilience in sexual health promotion.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (4), S. 400–413. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.919910.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

MacDonald, Jo-Ann; Gagnon, Anita J.; Mitchell, Claudia; Di Meglio, Giuseppina; Rennick, Janet E.; Cox, Joseph (2011):

Asking to listen. Towards a youth perspective on sexual health education and needs.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 443–457. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.595268.

Schlagwörter:

Partizipation // participation; Schule // school; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Mason, Sacha (2010):

Braving it out! An illuminative evaluation of the provision of sex and relationship education in two primary schools in England.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 157–169. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666366.

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Europa // Europe; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexualisierung // sexualization

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

McKee, Alan (2012):

The importance of entertainment for sexuality education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 499–509. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627727.

Schlagwörter:

heimlicher Lehrplan // hidden curriculum; Medien // media; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

McKee, Alan (2016):

Learning from commercial entertainment producers in order to create entertainment sex education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 17 (1), S. 26–40. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1228528.

Schlagwörter:

Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Murphy, Meghan (2015):

How organisational culture influences teachers' support of openly gay, lesbian and bisexual students.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 263–275.

Schlagwörter:

Coming out; Nordamerika // North America; Organisation; Schule // school; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Newby, Katie; Wallace, Louise M.; Dunn, Orla; Brown, Katherine E. (2012):

A survey of English teenagers' sexual experience and preferences for school-based sex education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (2), S. 231–251. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.615582.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Nielsena, Silja; Paasonen, Susanna; Spišák, Sanna (2015):

'Pervy role-play and such'. Girls' experiences of sexual messaging online.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 472–485.

Schlagwörter:

Coming out; Internet; Mädchen // girls; Sexting // sexting

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

O'Higgins, Siobhán; Gabhainn, Saoirse Nic (2010):

Youth participation in setting the agenda. Learning outcomes for sex education in Ireland.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (4), S. 387–403. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.515096.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Partizipation // participation; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Ollis, Debbie (2010):

'I haven't changed bigots but ...'. Reflections on the impact of teacher professional learning in sexuality education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 217–230. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666523.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Prävention // prevention; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Oswalt, Sara B.; Wagner, Laurie M.; Eastman-Mueller, Heather P.; Nevers, Joleen M. (2014):

Pedagogy and content in sexuality education courses in US colleges and universities.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (2), S. 172–187. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.991958.

Schlagwörter:

Pädagogik // pedagogy; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Preston, Marilyn J. (2015):

'They're just not mature right now': teachers' complicated perceptions of gender and anti-queer bullying.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (1), S. 22–34. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1019665.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Mobbing // bullying; Schule // school; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Quinlivan, Kathleen (2012):

Popular culture as emotional provocation. The material enactment of queer pedagogies in a high school classroom.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (5), S. 511–522. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.627728.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; heimlicher Lehrplan // hidden curriculum; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Popkultur // popular culture; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schulklima // school climate; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.3 Methodologie

Quinlivan, Kathleen (2013):

The methodological im/possibilities of researching sexuality education in schools. Working queer conundrums.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (sup1), S56-S69. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.796288.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Forschung // research; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Schule // school; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Rocha, Ana Cristina; Leal, Cláudia; Duarte, Cidália (2015):

School-based sexuality education in Portugal. Strengths and weaknesses.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (2), S. 172–183. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1087839.

Schlagwörter:

Schule // school; Sexualerziehung // sex ed

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Rudoe, Naomi (2010):

Lesbian teachers' identity, power and the public/private boundary.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (1), S. 23–36. DOI: 10.1080/14681810903491347.

Schlagwörter:

Coming out; Europa // Europe; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; lesbisch // lesbian; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Professionalität // professionalism; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Rutledge, Scott Edward; Siebert, Darcy Clay; Chonody, Jill; Killian, Michael (2011):

Information about human sexuality. Sources, satisfaction, and perceived knowledge among college students.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 11 (4), S. 471–487. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.601133.

Schlagwörter:

Sexualität // sexuality; Student*innen // college students; Wissen // knowledge

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Sandlos, Karyn (2010):

On the aesthetic difficulties of research on sex education. Toward a methodology of affect.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (3), S. 299–308. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2010.491634.

Schlagwörter:

Forschung // research; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Sprache // language; Wirksamkeit // effectiveness

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Sanjakdar, Fida (2013):

Educating for sexual difference? Muslim teachers' conversations about homosexuality.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (1), S. 16–29. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2011.634154.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Curriculum; Homosexualität; Islam; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Religion; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.5 Religion; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 7 Sexualität

Sauntson, Helen (2013):

Sexual diversity and illocutionary silencing in the English National Curriculum.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (4), S. 395–408. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.745809.

Schlagwörter:

Curriculum; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Shannon, Barrie (2016):

Comprehensive for who? Neoliberal directives in Australian 'comprehensive' sexuality education and the erasure of GLBTIQ identity.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 16 (6), S. 573–585. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2016.1141090.

Schlagwörter:

Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Snapp, Shannon D.; McGuire, Jenifer K.; Sinclair, Katarina O.; Gabrion, Karlee; Russell, Stephen T. (2015):

LGBTQ-inclusive curricula. Why supportive curricula matter.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (6), S. 580–596. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1042573.

Schlagwörter:

Curriculum; Inklusion // inclusion; Mobbing // bullying; Schulklima // school climate; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule

van der Stege, Heleen A.; Hilberink, Sander R.; Visser, Adriaan P.; Staa, AnneLoes van (2014):

Motivational factors in discussing sexual health with young people with chronic conditions or disabilities.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 14 (6), S. 635–651. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2014.918877.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Steinhart, Katharina; Kaenel, Andreas von; Cerruti, Stella; Chequer, Pedro; Gomes, Rebeca; Herlt, Claudia; Horstick, Olaf (2013):

International networking for sexuality education. A politically sensitive subject.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 13 (6), S. 630–643. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2013.784194.

Schlagwörter:

Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

Svendsen, Stine Helena Bang (2012):

Elusive sex acts. Pleasure and politics in Norwegian sex education.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (4), S. 397–410. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2012.677209.

Schlagwörter:

Politik // politics; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Tabatabaie, Alireza (2014):

Childhood and adolescent sexuality, Islam, and problematics of sex education. A call for re-examination.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (3), S. 276–288. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1005836.

Schlagwörter:

Islam; Jugendliche // youth; Kinder // children; Selbstbestimmung // agency; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.5 Religion; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Tsaliki, Liza (2015):

Popular culture and moral panics about 'children at risk'. Revisiting the sexualisation-of-young-girls debate.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 15 (5), S. 500–514. DOI: 10.1080/14681811.2015.1022893.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Identität // identity; Kinder // children; Mädchen // girls; Medien // media; Panik // panics; Popkultur // popular culture; Sexualisierung // sexualization; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Wager, Nadia (2012):

Psychogenic amnesia for childhood sexual abuse and risk for sexual revictimisation in both adolescence and adulthood.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 12 (3), S. 331–349.

Schlagwörter:

Revictimisierung // revictimization; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.3 Negative Folgen

Yu, Juping (2010):

Sex education beyond school. Implications for practice and research.

In: *Sex Education: Sexuality, Society and Learning* 10 (2), S. 187–199. DOI: 10.1080/14681811003666515.

Schlagwörter:

Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 8 Forschung; 8.4 Ergebnisse; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Sexuality and Disability

Atkinson, Julie P.; Ward, Karen M. (2012):

The Development of an Assessment of Interpersonal Violence for Individuals with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (3), S. 301–309. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-012-9275-3.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Gewalt // violence; Prävention // prevention

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art

Aylaz, Rukuye; Yilmaz, Ulviye; Polat, Sevinç (2012):

Effect of Difficulties Experienced by Parents of Autistic Children on Their Sexual Life. A Qualitative Study.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (4), S. 395–406. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9251-3.

Schlagwörter:

Autismus // autism; Behinderung // disability; Eltern // parents; Kinder // children; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.3 Eltern und Familie

Corona, Laura L.; Fox, Stephanie A.; Christodulu, Kristin V.; Worlock, Jane Ann (2016):

Providing Education on Sexuality and Relationships to Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder and Their Parents.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 199–214. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-015-9424-6.

Schlagwörter:

Autismus // autism; Eltern // parents; Jugendliche // youth; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Fader Wilkenfeld, B.; Ballan, Michelle S. (2011):

Educators' Attitudes and Beliefs Towards the Sexuality of Individuals with Developmental Disabilities.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (4), S. 351–361. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9211-y.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Einstellungen // attitudes; Konsens // consent; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Nordamerika // North America; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 7 Sexualität

Frawley, Patsie; Wilson, Nathan J. (2016):

Young People with Intellectual Disability Talking About Sexuality Education and Information.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (4), S. 469–484. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9460-x.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Behinderung // disability; Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Hilberink, Sander R.; Kruijver, Egbert; Wiegerink, Diana J. H. G.; Vliet Vlieland, Thea P. M. (2013):

A Pilot Implementation of an Intervention to Promote Sexual Health in Adolescents and Young Adults in Rehabilitation.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 31 (4), S. 373–392. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9288-6.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Europa // Europe; Intervention // intervention; Jugendliche // youth; Prävention // prevention; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health

Kategorien:

1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Kijak, Remigiusz J. (2011):

A Desire for Love: Considerations on Sexuality and Sexual Education of People With Intellectual Disability in Poland.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (1), S. 65–74. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9184-2.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Jugendliche // youth; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Löfgren-Mårtenson, Lotta (2012):

“I Want to Do it Right! ” A Pilot Study of Swedish Sex Education and Young People with Intellectual Disabilities.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 209–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9239-z.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Europa // Europe; Risiko // risk; Selbstbestimmung // agency; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.4 Sonderpädagogik; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Lund, Emily M.; Hammond, Marilyn (2014):

Single-Session Intervention for Abuse Awareness Among People with Developmental Disabilities.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 99–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9335-3.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Intervention // intervention; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Martinello, Emily (2014):

Reviewing strategies for risk reduction of sexual abuse of children with intellectual disabilities. A focus on early intervention.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (2), S. 167–174. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9345-9.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Global; Intervention // intervention; Risiko // risk; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Risikoverhalten // risk behavior; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sprache // language; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Martinello, Emily (2015):

Reviewing Risks Factors of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities as Perpetrators of Sexually Abusive Behaviors.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 33 (2), S. 269–278. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9365-5.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Intervention // intervention; Prävention // prevention; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

McDaniels, Brad; Fleming, Allison (2016):

Sexuality Education and Intellectual Disability. Time to Address the Challenge.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 215–225. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9427-y.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Noonan, A.; Taylor Gomez, Miriam (2011):

Who's Missing? Awareness of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender People with Intellectual Disability.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (2), S. 175–180. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9175-3.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Homosexualität; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Parchomiuk, Monika (2012):

Specialists and Sexuality of Individuals with Disability.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (4), S. 407–419. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9249-x.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Sexualität // sexuality; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Pebdani, Roxanna N. (2016):

Attitudes of Group Home Employees Towards the Sexuality of Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (3), S. 329–339. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9447-7.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Heim // residential care; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Sakellariou, Dikaios (2012):

Sexuality and Disability. A Discussion on Care of the Self.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 187–197. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9219-3.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Schaafsma, Dilana; Kok, Gerjo; Stoffelen, Joke M. T.; Curfs, Leopold M. G. (2017):

People with Intellectual Disabilities Talk About Sexuality. Implications for the Development of Sex Education.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 35 (1), S. 21–38. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9466-4.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Europa // Europe; Intervention // intervention; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Seidel, Anja; Wienholz, Sabine; Michel, Marion; Lupp, Melanie; Riedel-Heller, Steffi Gerlinde (2014):

Sexual Knowledge Among Adolescents with Physical Handicaps. A Systematic Review.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (3), S. 429–441. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9326-4.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Jugendliche // youth; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Sevlever, Melina; Roth, Matthew E.; Gillis, Jennifer M. (2013):

Sexual Abuse and Offending in Autism Spectrum Disorders.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 31 (2), S. 189–200. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9286-8.

Schlagwörter:

Autismus // autism; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Sloane, Heather M. (2014):

Tales of a Reluctant Sex Radical. Barriers to Teaching the Importance of Pleasure for Wellbeing.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 453–467. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9381-5.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Risiko // risk; Sexualekultur // sexuality culture; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights; Vergnügen // pleasure

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Swango-Wilson, Amy (2011):

Meaningful Sex Education Programs for Individuals with Intellectual/Developmental Disabilities.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 29 (2), S. 113–118. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-010-9168-2.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität

Taylor Gomez, Miriam (2012):

The S Words. Sexuality, Sensuality, Sexual Expression and People with Intellectual Disability.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 30 (2), S. 237–245. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-011-9250-4.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Wienholz, Sabine; Seidel, Anja; Michel, Marion; Haeussler-Sczepan, Monika; Riedel-Heller, Steffi Gerlinde (2016):

Sexual Experiences of Adolescents With and Without Disabilities. Results from a Cross-Sectional Study.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 34 (2), S. 171–182. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-016-9433-0.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Jugendliche // youth; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Wilkinson, Verity J.; Theodore, Kate; Raczka, Roman (2015):

'As Normal as Possible'. Sexual Identity Development in People with Intellectual Disabilities Transitioning to Adulthood.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 33 (1), S. 93–105. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9356-6.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Europa // Europe; Identität // identity; Jugendliche // youth; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014):

Discourse Analysis of Curriculum on Sexuality Education. FLASH for Special Education.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (4), S. 485–498. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-014-9387-z.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Diskurs // discourse; Nordamerika // North America; Policies; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Soziale Arbeit

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Winges-Yanez, Nick (2014):

Why All the Talk About Sex? An Authoethnography Identifying the Troubling Discourse of Sexuality and Intellectual Disability.

In: *Sexuality and Disability* 32 (1), S. 107–116. DOI: 10.1007/s11195-013-9331-7.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Diskurs // discourse; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights; Stigmatisierung // stigma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Sexuality Research and Social Policy

Ballonoff Suleiman, Ahna; Brindis, Claire D. (2014):

Adolescent School-Based Sex Education. Using Developmental Neuroscience to Guide New Directions for Policy and Practice.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 137–152. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0147-8.

Schlagwörter:

Gesundheit // health; Jugendliche // youth; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Bay-Cheng, Laina Y.; Fava, Nicole M. (2014):

What puts “At-Risk Girls” at risk? Sexual vulnerability and social inequality in the lives of girls in the child welfare system.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (2), S. 116–125. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0142-5.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Verhütung // contraception; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Berglas, Nancy F.; Angulo-Olaiz, Francisca; Jerman, Petra; Desai, Mona; Constantine, Norman A. (2014):

Engaging Youth Perspectives on Sexual Rights and Gender Equality in Intimate Relationships as a Foundation for Rights-Based Sexuality Education.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 11 (4), S. 288–298. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0148-7.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Policies; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights; Soziale Schicht; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.3 Peers; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Castro, Ángel (2016):

Sexual Behavior and Sexual Risks Among Spanish University Students. A Descriptive Study of Gender and Sexual Orientation.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 13 (1), S. 84–94. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-015-0210-0.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Europa // Europe; Geschlecht // gender; Risiko // risk; Sexuell übertragbare Infektionen // sexually transmitted infections; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college university; Vergewaltigung // rape; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention

Evipidou, Dimitris; Çavuşoğlu, Çise (2015):

English Language Teachers' Attitudes Towards the Incorporation of Gay- and Lesbian-Related Topics in the Classroom. The Case of Greek Cypriot EFL Teachers.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 12 (1), S. 70–80. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-014-0176-3.

Schlagwörter:

sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule

Gill, Michael (2010):

Rethinking sexual abuse, questions of consent, and intellectual disability.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (3), S. 201–213. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0019-9.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Ehtik // ethics; Konsens // consent; Nordamerika // North America; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Strafrecht // criminal justice; Vergewaltigung // rape; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.4 Sonderpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Gilliam, Melissa; Brindis, Claire D. (2011):

Virtual Sex Ed. Youth, Race, Sex, and New Media.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 1–4. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0036-3.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Kommunikation // communication; Medien // media; Nordamerika // North America; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

González-Ortega, Eva; Vicario-Molina, Isabel; Martínez, José Luis; Orgaz, Begoña (2015):

The Internet as a Source of Sexual Information in a Sample of Spanish Adolescents. Associations with Sexual Behavior.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 12 (4), S. 290–300. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-015-0196-7.

Schlagwörter:

Internet

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

James, Adilia E. E. (2010):

Too Early to Talk About Sex? Issues in Creating Culturally Relevant Sexuality Education for Preadolescent Black Girls in the United States.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 7 (2), S. 128–141. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-010-0012-3.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Feminismus // feminism; Grundschule // elementary school; Interkulturell // intercultural; Intersektionalität // intersectionality; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Jugendliche // youth; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Nordamerika // North America; schwarz // black; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik

Levine, Deb (2011):

Using Technology, New Media, and Mobile for Sexual and Reproductive Health.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 18–26. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0040-7.

Schlagwörter:

Medien // media; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; Technologie // technology

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Pascoe, C. J. (2011):

Resource and Risk. Youth Sexuality and New Media Use.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 8 (1), S. 5–17. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0042-5.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; Medien // media; Nordamerika // North America; Ressourcen // resourcefulness; Risiko // risk; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Sicherheit // safety; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Pingel, Emily Sweetnam; Thomas, Laura; Harmell, Chelsea; Bauermeister, Jose (2013):

Creating comprehensive, youth centered, culturally appropriate sex education: What do young gay, bisexual and questioning men want?

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 10 (4). DOI: 10.1007/s13178-013-0134-5.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Schonfeld, David J.; Adams, Ryan E.; Fredstrom, Bridget K.; Tomlin, Ricarda; Voyce, Charlene; Vaughn, Lisa M. (2012):

Social–Emotional Learning in Grades 3 to 6 and the Early Onset of Sexual Behavior.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 9 (2), S. 178–186. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-011-0077-7.

Schlagwörter:

Curriculum; Grundschule // elementary school

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Smith, Marshall (2013):

Youth Viewing Sexually Explicit Material Online. Addressing the Elephant on the Screen.

In: *Sexuality Research and Social Policy* 10 (1), S. 62–75. DOI: 10.1007/s13178-012-0103-4.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Pornografie // pornography; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Teaching and Teacher Education

Clark, Caroline T. (2010):

Preparing LGBTQ-allies and combating homophobia in a U.S. teacher education program.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (3), S. 704–713. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.10.006.

Schlagwörter:

Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Interkulturell // intercultural; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualität // sexuality; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice

Kategorien:

1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Collier, Kate L.; Bos, Henny M. W.; Sandfort, Theo G.M. (2015):

Understanding teachers' responses to enactments of sexual and gender stigma at school.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 48, S. 34–43. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.02.002.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Geschlecht // gender; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Mobbing // bullying; Schule // school; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Sicherheit // safety

Kategorien:

1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

DePalma, Renée; Atkinson, Elizabeth (2010):

The nature of institutional heteronormativity in primary schools and practice-based responses.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (8), S. 1669–1676. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.06.018.

Schlagwörter:

Coming out; Europa // Europe; Grundschule // elementary school; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Endo, Hidehiro; Reece-Miller, Paul Chamness; Santavicca, Nicholas (2010):

Surviving in the trenches. A narrative inquiry into queer teachers' experiences and identity.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (4), S. 1023–1030. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.10.045.

Schlagwörter:

Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Narration // narrative; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Stereotype // stereotypes

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Ferfolja, Tania (2010):

Lesbian teachers, harassment and the workplace.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (3), S. 408–414. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.05.007.

Schlagwörter:

Gewalt // violence; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; lesbisch // lesbian; Schule // school; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Lindahl, Mats G.; Lundin, Mattias (2016):

How do 15–16 year old students use scientific knowledge to justify their reasoning about human sexuality and relationships?

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 60, S. 121–130. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2016.08.009.

Schlagwörter:

Entscheidungen // decision-making

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Malins, Pamela (2016):

How inclusive is “inclusive education” in the Ontario elementary classroom? Teachers talk about addressing diverse gender and sexual identities.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 54, S. 128–138. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2015.11.004.

Schlagwörter:

Curriculum; Geschlecht // gender; Inklusion // inclusion; Pädagogik // pedagogy; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

Nixon, David (2010):

Discrimination, performance and recuperation. How teachers and pupils challenge and recover discourses of sexualities in schools.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 26 (2), S. 145–151. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2009.05.003.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Homosexualität; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Schulklima // school climate

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Paakkari, Leena; Välimaa, Raili (2013):

Ethical issues in the teaching and learning of health topics in schools. The conceptions of teacher trainees.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 34, S. 66–76. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2013.04.004.

Schlagwörter:

Ausbildung // qualification; Ehtik // ethics; Europa // Europe; Gesundheit // health; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Professionalität // professionalism

Kategorien:

4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Riggs, Angela D.; Rosenthal, Amy R.; Smith-Bonahue, Tina (2011):

The impact of a combined cognitive–affective intervention on pre-service teachers’ attitudes, knowledge, and anticipated professional behaviors regarding homosexuality and gay and lesbian issues.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 27 (1), S. 201–209. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2010.08.002.

Schlagwörter:

Ausbildung // qualification; Homosexualität; Intervention // intervention; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Nordamerika // North America; Professionalität // professionalism

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Schmidt, Sandra J.; Chang, Shih-pei; Carolan-Silva, Aliah; Lockhart, John; Anagnostopoulos, Dorothea (2012):

Recognition, responsibility, and risk. Pre-service teachers' framing and reframing of lesbian, gay, and bisexual social justice issues.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 28 (8), S. 1175–1184. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2012.07.002.

Schlagwörter:

Ausbildung // qualification; Curriculum; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Nordamerika // North America; Professionalität // professionalism; Risikofaktoren // risk factors; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Sprache // language

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 7 Sexualität
Shelton, Stephanie Anne; Barnes, Meghan E. (2016):

“Racism just isn't an issue anymore”. Preservice teachers' resistances to the intersections of sexuality and race.

In: *Teaching and Teacher Education* 55, S. 165–174. DOI: 10.1016/j.tate.2016.01.008.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Intersektionalität // intersectionality; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Nordamerika // North America; Rassismus // racism; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

The British Journal of Social Work

Cocker, Christine; Hafford-Letchfield, Trish (2010):

Out and Proud? Social Work's Relationship with Lesbian and Gay Equality.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (6), S. 1996–2008.

Schlagwörter:

Homosexualität; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Craig, Shelley L.; Dentato, Michael P.; Messinger, Lori; McInroy, Lauren B. (2016):

Educational Determinants of Readiness to Practise with LGBTQ Clients. Social Work Students Speak Out.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (1), S. 115–134. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu107.

Schlagwörter:

Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Professionalität // professionalism; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Soziale Arbeit

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 4.2 Extern

Cree, Vivienne (2017):

'Khaki Fever' during the First World War. A Historical Case Study of Social Work's Approach towards Young Women, Sex and Moral Danger.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (7), S. 1839–1854. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcv103.

Schlagwörter:

Geschichte // history; Geschlecht // gender; Risiko // risk; Soziale Arbeit

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 7 Sexualität

Doel, Mark; Allmark, Peter; Conway, Paul; Cowburn, Malcolm; Flynn, Margaret; Nelson, Pete; Tod, Angela (2010):

Professional Boundaries. Crossing a Line or Entering the Shadows?

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (6), S. 1866–1889.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Professionalität // professionalism; Soziale Arbeit; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Firmin, Carlene; Warrington, Camille; Pearce, Jenny (2017):

Sexual Exploitation and Its Impact on Developing Sexualities and Sexual Relationships. The Need for Contextual Social Work Interventions.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2318–2337. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw134.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Jugendliche // youth; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Green, Lorraine (2016):

The Trouble with Touch? New Insights and Observations on Touch for Social Work and Social Care.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work*, bcw071. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw071.

Schlagwörter:

Intimität // intimacy; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Soziale Arbeit

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Hafford-Letchfield, Trish; Cocker, Christine; Ryan, Peter; Melonowska, Justyna (2017):

Rights through Alliances. Findings from a European Project Tackling Homophobic and Transphobic Bullying in Schools through the Engagement of Families and Young People.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2338–2356. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw104.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Mobbing // bullying; Schulklima // school climate; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights; soziale Unterstützung // social support; Stigmatisierung // stigma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Hallett, Sophie (2017):

'An Uncomfortable Comfortableness'. 'Care', Child Protection and Child Sexual Exploitation.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (7), S. 2137–2152. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcv136.

Schlagwörter:

Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Soziale Arbeit

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Hicks, Stephen; Jeyasingham, Dharman (2017):

Social Work, Queer Theory and After. A Genealogy of Sexuality Theory in Neo-Liberal Times.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2357–2373. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw103.

Schlagwörter:

Queer Theory; Sexualität // sexuality; Soziale Arbeit

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Huang, Yu-Te; Souleymanov, Rusty (2016):

Rethinking Epistemological Debates and Transnationalism of Sexuality between the West and Taiwan. Implications for Social Workers.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (1), S. 98–114. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu067.

Schlagwörter:

Asien // Asia; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture; Soziale Arbeit

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie

Kwhali, Josephine; Martin, Linda; Brady, Geraldine; Brown, Sarah J. (2017):

Child Sexual Abuse and Exploitation. Knowledge, Confidence and Training within a Contemporary UK Social Work Practice and Policy Context.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2208–2226. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw154.

Schlagwörter:

Disclosure; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Professionalität // professionalism; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Soziale Arbeit

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Lavie-Ajayi, Maya (2017):

"It Will Continue to Embarrass Me on Some Level, and I Think that's OK". Conceptualising Embarrassment in Discussions about Sex between Social Workers and Service Users.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2282–2299. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw116.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Professionalität // professionalism; Sexualität // sexuality; Soziale Arbeit; Tabu // taboo

Kategorien:

1.2 Diskurse; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 4.2 Extern; 7 Sexualität

Lee, Sally; Fenge, Lee-Ann (2017):

Sexual Well-Being and Physical Disability.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2263–2281. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw107.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Martin, Jennifer (2016):

Child Sexual Abuse Images Online. Implications for Social Work Training and Practice.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (2), S. 372–388. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcu116.

Schlagwörter:

Kinderpornographie; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Professionalität // professionalism; Soziale Arbeit

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Masson, H.; Hackett, Simon; Phillips, J.; Balfe, M. (2014):

Looking Back on the Long-Term Fostering and Adoption of Children with Harmful Sexual Behaviours. Carers' Reflections on Their Experiences.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 44 (8), S. 2200–2217. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bct073.

Schlagwörter:

Betreuer*innen // caregiver; jugendliche Täter*innen // adolescent sex offender; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer

Melville-Wiseman, Janet (2017):

The Sexual Abuse of Vulnerable People by Registered Social Workers in England. An Analysis of the Health and Care Professions Council Fitness to Practise Cases.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2190–2207. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw150.

Schlagwörter:

institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 4.2 Extern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene

Mul, Nick J.; McKenzie, Cameron; Khan, Maryam (2017):

Recognition and Legitimisation of Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity (SOGI) at the UN. A Critical Systemic Analysis.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2245–2262. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw139.

Schlagwörter:

Policies; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

Nelson, Pete; Cowburn, Malcolm (2010):

Social Work Admissions. Applicants with Criminal Convictions -The Challenge of Ethical Risk Assessment.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (4), S. 1081–1099.

Schlagwörter:

Risikofaktoren // risk factors; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Sozialisation // socialization; Täter*in // offender; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.5 Disclosure

Nothdurfter, Urban; Nagy, Andrea (2017):

Few and Far from Radical? LGBT-Related Contributions in European Social Work Journal Publishing.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2227–2244. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw140.

Schlagwörter:

sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Soziale Arbeit; Übersicht // review

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT

O'Leary, P.; Tsui, M.-S.; Ruch, G. (2013):

The Boundaries of the Social Work Relationship Revisited. Towards a Connected, Inclusive and Dynamic Conceptualisation.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 43 (1), S. 135–153. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcr181.

Schlagwörter:

Grenzen // boundaries; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Professionalität // professionalism; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

O'Leary, Patrick J.; Gould, Nick (2010):

Exploring Coping Factors amongst Men Who Were Sexually Abused in Childhood.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 40 (8), S. 2669–2686.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Bewältigung // coping; Männer // men; Mentale Gesundheit // mental health; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.4 Resilienz

Schaub, Jason; Willis, Paul; Dunk-West, Priscilla (2016):

Accounting for Self, Sex and Sexuality in UK Social Workers' Knowledge Base. Findings from an Exploratory Study.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work*, bcw015. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw015.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Professionalität // professionalism; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture; Soziale Arbeit

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.6 Jugendamt; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 4.2 Extern; 7 Sexualität

Smith, Mark; Woodiwiss, Jo (2017):

Sexuality, Innocence and Agency in Narratives of Childhood Sexual Abuse. Implications for Social Work.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2173–2189. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw160.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; kindliche Sexualität // childhood sexuality; Mädchen // girls; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour; Soziale Arbeit

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Turner, George W.; Crane, Betsy (2017):

Sexually Silenced No More, Adults with Learning Disabilities Speak Up. A Call to Action for Social Work to Frame Sexual Voice as a Social Justice Issue.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 46 (8), S. 2300–2317. DOI: 10.1093/bjsw/bcw133.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Selbstbestimmung // agency; sexuelle Rechte // sexual rights; Soziale Arbeit; Stigmatisierung // stigma

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Willis, Paul; Ward, Nicki; Fish, Julie (2011):

Searching for LGBT Carers. Mapping a Research Agenda in Social Work and Social Care.

In: *The British Journal of Social Work* 41 (7), S. 1304–1320.

Schlagwörter:

Betreuer*innen // caregiver; Europa // Europe; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Homosexualität; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sozialisation // socialization; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung

The Journal of Sex Research

Bergen, Emilia; Ahto, Anna; Schulz, Anja; Imhoff, Roland; Antfolk, Jan; Schuhmann, Petya et al. (2015):

Adult-Adult and Adult-Child/Adolescent Online Sexual Interactions. An Exploratory Self-Report Study on the Role of Situational Factors.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 52 (9), S. 1006–1016.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art

Chapleau, Kristine M.; Oswald, Debra L. (2010):

Power, Sex, and Rape Myth Acceptance. Testing Two Models of Rape Proclivity.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 47 (1), S. 66–78.

Schlagwörter:

Macht // power; Nordamerika // North America; Rape Culture; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung

Gowen, L. Kris; Wings-Yanez, Nichole (2014):

Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, and Questioning Youths' Perspectives of Inclusive School-Based Sexuality Education.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), S. 788–800.

Schlagwörter:

Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Graaf, Hanneke de; Rademakers, Jany (2011):

The Psychological Measurement of Childhood Sexual Development in Western Societies. Methodologica IChallenges.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 48 (2-3), S. 118–129.

Schlagwörter:

Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie

Grose, Rose Grace; Grabe, Shelly; Kohfeldt, Danielle (2014):

Sexual Education, Gender Ideology, and Youth Sexual Empowerment.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (7), 742.753.

Schlagwörter:

Empowerment // empowerment; Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Schule // school; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Heywood, Wendy; Patrick, Kent; Pitts, Marian; Mitchell, Anne (2016):

"Dude, I'm Seventeen ... It's Okay Not to Have Sex by This Age": Feelings, Reasons, Pressures, and Intentions Reported by Adolescents Who Have Not Had Sexual Intercourse.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (9), S. 1207–1214. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2015.1092105.

Schlagwörter:

Gefühle // emotions; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience

Kategorien:

5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D.; Sanders, Stephanie A.; Dennis, Barbara; Reece, Michael (2014):

Gender Differences in Heterosexual College Students' Conceptualizations and Indicators of Sexual Consent. Implications for Contemporary Sexual Assault Prevention Education.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 51 (8), S. 904–916.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Konsens // consent; Nordamerika // North America; Prävention // prevention; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Sprache // language; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college university; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Katz-Wise, Sabra L.; Rosario, Margaret; Calzo, Jerel P.; Scherer, Emily A.; Sarda, Vishnudas; Austin, S. Bryn (2017):

Endorsement and Timing of Sexual Orientation Developmental Milestones Among Sexual Minority Young Adults in the Growing Up Today Study.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (2), S. 172–185. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1170757.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Mallet, Pascal; Herbe, Dominique (2011):

Does knowledge about sexuality prevent adolescents from developing rape-supportive beliefs?

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 48 (4), S. 372–380. DOI: 10.1080/00224491003794048.

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Jugendliche // youth; Rape Culture; Sexualität // sexuality; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung

Muehlenhard, Charlene L.; Humphreys, Terry P.; Jozkowski, Kristen N.; Peterson, Zoë D. (2016):

The Complexities of Sexual Consent Among College Students. A Conceptual and Empirical Review.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 53 (4-5), S. 1–31.

Schlagwörter:

Konsens // consent; Nordamerika // North America; Student*innen // college students; Übersicht // review; Universität // college university

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.5 Forschungslücken

Mustanski, Brian; Greene, George J.; Ryan, Daniel; Whitton, Sarah W. (2015):

Feasibility, Acceptability, and Initial Efficacy of an Online Sexual Health Promotion Program for LGBT Youth. The Queer Sex Ed Intervention.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 52 (2), S. 220–230.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Verhütung // contraception

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Rinehart, Jenny K.; Nason, Erica E.; Yeater, Elizabeth A.; Miller, Geoffrey F. (2017):

Do Some Students Need Special Protection From Research on Sex and Trauma? New Evidence for Young Adult Resilience in "Sensitive Topics" Research.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (3), S. 273–283. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1156047.

Schlagwörter:

Resilienz // resilience; Student*innen // college students; Trauma

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 6 Gewalt; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung; 8.1 Forschungsethik

Wolff, Jennifer M.; Rospenda, Kathleen M.; Colaneri, Anthony S. (2017):

Sexual Harassment, Psychological Distress, and Problematic Drinking Behavior Among College Students: An Examination of Reciprocal Causal Relations.

In: *The Journal of Sex Research* 54 (3), S. 362–373. DOI: 10.1080/00224499.2016.1143439.

Schlagwörter:

Drogenkonsum // substance consumption; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment; Student*innen // college students

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Monographien

Best, Joel; Bogle, Kathleen A. (2014):

Kids gone wild. From rainbow parties to sexting, understanding the hype over teen sex.

New York [u.a.]: New York Univ. Press.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Eltern // parents; Jugendliche // youth; Medien // media; Nordamerika // North America; Panik // panics; Sexting // sexting; Sexualisierung // sexualization; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Blackman, Jerome S.; Dring, Kathleen (2016):

Sexual aggression against children. Pedophiles' and abusers' development, dynamics, treatability, and the law.

1 Edition. New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.

Schlagwörter:

Behandlung // treatment; Nordamerika // North America; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Strafrecht // criminal justice; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art
Carlson, Dennis; Roseboro, Donyell L. (2011):

The Sexuality Curriculum and Youth Culture

(Counterpoints, 392).

Schlagwörter:

Curriculum; Jugendliche // youth; Popkultur // popular culture; Selbstbestimmung // agency; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche

Carmody, Moira (2015):

Sex, ethics, and young people.

New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan (Palgrave Macmillan's critical studies in gender, sexuality, and culture).

Schlagwörter:

Ehtik // ethics; Jugendliche // youth; Prävention // prevention; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Cheit, Ross E. (2014):

The witch-hunt narrative. Politics, psychology, and the sexual abuse of children.

New York: Oxford University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Panik // panics; Politik // politics; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Drobac, Jennifer Ann (2016):

Sexual exploitation of teenagers. Adolescent development, discrimination, and consent law.

Chicago, London: The University of Chicago Press.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Konsens // consent; Nordamerika // North America; Policies; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment; Sexuelle Entwicklung // sexual development; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Strafrecht // criminal justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Elliott, Sinikka (2012):

Not my kid. What parents believe about the sex lives of their teenagers.

New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Eltern // parents; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Geschlecht // gender; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualisierung // sexualization; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Ewing, Charles Patrick (2014):

Preventing the sexual victimization of children. Psychological, legal, and public policy perspectives.

Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Christentum // christianity; institutioneller Missbrauch // institutional abuse; Nordamerika // North America; Policies; Prostitution; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sicherheit // safety; Soziale Schicht; Sozialisation // socialization; Strafrecht // criminal justice; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.1 Kindertagesstätte; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 2.2.7 Kinder- und Jugendhilfe; 2.2.8 Offene Kinder- und Jugendarbeit; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.5 Disclosure

Garcia, Lorena (2012):

Respect yourself, protect yourself. Latina girls and sexual identity.

New York, N.Y., London: New York University Press (Intersections / [New York University Press]).

Schlagwörter:

Eltern // parents; Ethnizität // ethnicity; Jugendliche // youth; Latinx; Mädchen // girls; Nordamerika // North America; Sexualität // sexuality; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 5.3 Eltern und Familie; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Gilbert, Jen (2014):

Sexuality in School: The Limits of Education:

University of Minnesota Press.

Schlagwörter:

Grundschule // elementary school

Kategorien:

1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik

Hasinoff, Amy Adele (2015):

Sexting panic. Rethinking criminalization, privacy, and consent.

Urbana: University of Illinois Press (Feminist media studies).

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Mädchen // girls; Sexting // sexting; Sexualethik // sexual ethics

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Keenan, Marie (2013):

Child sexual abuse and the Catholic Church. Gender, power, and organizational culture.

Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Beschwerdemanagement // complaint management; Christentum // christianity; Disclosure; Ethik // ethics; Europa // Europe; Geistliche // clergy; Global; Macht // power; Männer // men; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Organisation; Pädosexualität // pedosexuality; Religion; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Sozialisation // socialization; Täter*in // offender

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.5 Religion; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.8 Offene Kinder- und Jugendarbeit; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Larremore, April (2016):

Disrupting gendered pedagogies in the early childhood classroom.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Grundschule // elementary school; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schulklima // school climate; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Weiblichkeit // femininity

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.1 Kindertagesstätte; 2.2.2 Grundschule; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.5 Diskriminierung; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Miller-Perrin, Cindy L.; Perrin, Robin D. (2013):

Child maltreatment. An introduction.

3. ed. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.

Schlagwörter:

Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Murray, Olivia J. (2014):

Queer Inclusion in Teacher Education. Bridging Theory, Research, and Practice.

London: Taylor & Francis Ltd.

Schlagwörter:

Homosexualität; Inklusion // inclusion; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern

Nelson, Sarah (2016):

Tackling child sexual abuse. Radical approaches to prevention, protection and support.

Bristol: Policy Press.

Schlagwörter:

Betroffene // survivors; Europa // Europe; Gesundheitswesen // public health; Kinder // children; Kinder- und Jugendhilfesystem // child welfare system; Kinder- und Jugendschutz // child protection; Politik // politics; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch; Soziale Schicht; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Sozialisation // socialization; Victim-blaming

Kategorien:

1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.3 Schicht; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Oliver, Kelly (2016):

Hunting Girls. Sexual Violence from The Hunger Games to Campus Rape.

New York: Columbia University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Nordamerika // North America; Popkultur // popular culture; Rape Culture; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Vergewaltigung // rape; Weiblichkeit // femininity

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 6.2.4 Übergriff

Ozyegin, Gul (2015):

New desires, new selves. Sex, love, and piety among Turkish youth.

New York: New York University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Europa // Europe; Geschlechterrolle // gender role; Gesellschaft // society; Heteronormativität // heteronormativity; Homofeindlichkeit // homophobia; Homosexualität; Identität // identity; Islam; Jugendliche // youth; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Muslimische Länder; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; soziale Ungleichheit und/oder Gerechtigkeit // social inequality and/or justice; Sozialisation // socialization; Weiblichkeit // femininity

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Postmus, Judy L. (2013):

Sexual Violence and Abuse. An Encyclopedia of Prevention, Impacts, and Recovery.

Santa Barbara, Calif: ABC-CLIO.

Schlagwörter:

Folgen // long-term effects; Prävention // prevention; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; sexueller Kindesmissbrauch

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.2 Missbrauch; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 6.3 Negative Folgen; 6.4 Resilienz; 6.5 Disclosure

Powell, Anastasia (2010):

Sex, Power and Consent. Youth Culture and the Unwritten Rules.

Port Melbourne, Vic.: Cambridge University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Jugendliche // youth; Konsens // consent; Macht // power; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Rahimi, Regina; Liston, Delores D. (2012):

Pervasive vulnerabilities. Sexual harassment in school.

New York: Peter Lang (Adolescent cultures, school & society, v. 54).

Schlagwörter:

Nordamerika // North America; Schule // school; sexuelle Belästigung // sexual harassment; Vulnerabilität // vulnerability

Kategorien:

1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Sanjakdar, Fida (2012):

Living west, facing east. The deconstruction of Muslim youth's sexual identities.

New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints, 364).

Schlagwörter:

Islam; Jugendliche // youth; Nordamerika // North America; Religion; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexualethik // sexual ethics; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Shariff, Shaheen (2015):

Sexting and cyberbullying. Defining the line for digitally empowered kids.

New York: Cambridge University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Mobbing // bullying; Nordamerika // North America; Policies; Politik // politics; Popkultur // popular culture; Prävention // prevention; Rape Culture; Schulklima // school climate; Sexting // sexting; Sozialisation // socialization; Strafrecht // criminal justice; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.4 Übergriff; 7 Sexualität; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Sammelbände

Allen, Louisa; Rasmussen, Mary Louise; Quinlivan, Kathleen (Hg.) (2014):

The Politics of Pleasure in Sexuality Education. Pleasure Bound.

Hoboken: Taylor and Francis (Routledge Research in Education).

Schlagwörter:

Gesundheit // health; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; Vergnügen // pleasure

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.5 Religion; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 7 Sexualität

Carpenter, Laura M.; DeLamater, John D. (Hg.) (2012):

Sex for life. From virginity to Viagra, how sexuality changes throughout our lives.

New York: New York University Press (Intersections).

Schlagwörter:

Coming out; sexuelle Gesundheit // sexual health; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 7 Sexualität

Carrigan Wooten, Sara; Mitchell, Roland W. (Hg.) (2016):

The crisis of campus sexual violence. Critical perspectives on prevention and response.

New York: Routledge.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Feminismus // feminism; Forschung // research; Policies; Prävention // prevention; Rape Culture; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Student*innen // college students; Universität // college university; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.5 Hochschule; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt

Erooga, Marcus (Hg.) (2012):

Creating safer organisations. Practical steps to prevent the abuse of children by those working with them.

Chichester, West Sussex, Malden, MA: Wiley, Blackwell (The NSPCC/Wiley series in protecting children).

Schlagwörter:

Europa // Europe; Kindesmissbrauch // child abuse; Organisation; Pädagogische Fachkräfte; Prävention // prevention; Sicherheit // safety

Kategorien:

2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 4 Fachkräfte; 4.1 Intern; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.2 Erwachsene; 6.2 Art; 6.2.2 Missbrauch

Fish, Julie; Karban, Kate (Hg.) (2015):

Lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans health inequalities. International perspectives in social work.

Bristol: Policy Press.

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Homosexualität; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Soziale Schicht; Sozialisation // socialization

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion

Florsheim, Paul (Hg.) (2013):

Adolescent romantic relations and sexual behavior. Theory, research, and practical implications.

Hove: Psychology.

Schlagwörter:

Beziehungsgestaltung // relationships; Jugendliche // youth; sexuelle Erfahrung // sexual experience

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Hélie, Anissa; Hoodfar, Homa (Hg.) (2012):

Sexuality in Muslim Contexts. Restrictions and Resistance.

London: Zed Books.

Schlagwörter:

Islam; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion; 7 Sexualität; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung

Henry, Nicola; Powell, Anastasia (Hg.) (2014):

Preventing sexual violence. Interdisciplinary approaches to overcoming a rape.

New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

Schlagwörter:

Prävention // prevention; sexuelle Gewalt // sexual violence; Vergewaltigung // rape

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.1 Policies; 3 Fokus; 3.2 Kinderschutz und Gewaltprävention; 6 Gewalt; 6.2 Art; 6.2.3 Vergewaltigung; 8 Forschung; 8.2 Theorie

Lemma, Alessandra; Lynch, Paul E. (Hg.) (2015):

Sexualities. Contemporary psychoanalytic perspectives.

London, New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.

Schlagwörter:

Diskurs // discourse; Sexualität // sexuality

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.2 Diskurse; 7 Sexualität; 7.1 Beziehungsgestaltung; 7.2 Selbstbestimmung; 7.3 Sexuelle Erfahrungen

Livingstone, Sonia M.; Haddon, Leslie; Görzig, Anke (Hg.) (2012):

Children, risk and safety on the internet. Research and policy challenges in comparative perspective.

Bristol, UK, Chicago, IL: Policy Press.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Kinder // children

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.1 Kinder

McRuer, Robert; Mollow, Anna (Hg.) (2012):

Sex and disability.

Durham [N.C.]: Duke University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Behinderung // disability; Diskriminierung // discrimination; Diskurs // discourse; Einstellungen // attitudes; Empowerment // empowerment; Sexualität // sexuality; Sexualkultur // sexuality culture

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.6 Behinderungen; 7 Sexualität

Meiners, Erica R.; Quinn, Therese (Hg.) (2012):

Sexualities in education. A reader.

New York: Peter Lang (Counterpoints : studies in the postmodern theory of education, v. 367).

Schlagwörter:

Diskriminierung // discrimination; Geschlecht // gender; Geschlechtsidentität // gender identity; Pädagogik // pedagogy; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Sexismus // sexism; Sexualerziehung // sex ed; Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität; 8 Forschung

Meyer, Elizabeth J.; Carlson, Dennis (Hg.) (2014):

Gender and sexualities in education. A reader.

New York: Peter Lang (Gender and sexualities in education, Vol. 5).

Schlagwörter:

Geschlecht // gender; Lehrer*innen // Teachers; Schule // school; Schüler*innen // pupils; Schulklima // school climate; sexuelle Minderheit // sexual minority; Sexuelle Orientierung // sexual orientation; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule

Ozyegin, Gul (Hg.) (2016):

Gender and sexuality in Muslim cultures.

London, New York: Routledge.

Schlagwörter:

Ethnizität // ethnicity; Geschlecht // gender; Islam; Jugendliche // youth; Männlichkeit // masculinity; Muslimische Länder; Nähe-Distanz-Regulation // boundary management; Professionalität // professionalism; Religion; Sexualität // sexuality; Weiblichkeit // femininity

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 1.4.5 Religion

Ponzetti, James J. (Hg.) (2016):

Evidence-based approaches to sexuality education. A global perspective

(Textbooks in family studies series).

Schlagwörter:

Sexuelle Bildung // sexuality education

Kategorien:

3 Fokus; 3.1 Sexualpädagogik; 8 Forschung; 8.3 Methodologie; 8.4 Ergebnisse

Rivers, Ian (Hg.) (2013):

Bullying. Experiences and discourses of sexuality and gender.

London: Routledge (Foundations and futures of education).

Schlagwörter:

Bisexualität // bisexuality; Europa // Europe; Geschlecht // gender; Identität // identity; lesbisch // lesbian; Mobbing // bullying; schwul // gay; Sexualität // sexuality; trans*ident // trans*

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.1 Dynamiken; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung

Saleh, Fabian M.; Grudzinskas, Albert; Judge, Abigail (Hg.) (2014):

Adolescent sexual behavior in the digital age. Considerations for clinicians, legal professionals, and educators.

Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.

Schlagwörter:

Internet; Jugendliche // youth; Sexting // sexting; sexuelles Verhalten // sexual behaviour

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.3 Medien und Technologie; 5 Adressat_innen; 5.2 Jugendliche; 7 Sexualität

Saltmarsh, Sue (Hg.) (2014):

Rethinking school violence. Theory, Gender, Context.

New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

Schlagwörter:

Australien // Australia; Geschlecht // gender; Global; Schule // school; Schulklima // school climate; Soziale Schicht

Kategorien:

1 Sozialer Kontext; 1.4 Identitäten; 1.4.1 Gender; 1.4.2 LGBT; 1.4.3 Schicht; 1.4.4 Ethnizität; 2 Institutioneller Kontext; 2.2 Einrichtungstypen; 2.2.3 Weiterführende Schule; 6 Gewalt; 6.1 Täter*in; 6.1.1 Peer; 6.2 Art; 6.2.1 Belästigung; 6.2.2 Missbrauch